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2nd KOCAELİ SCIENCE CONGRESS

(KOSC-2025)

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Kocaeli Üniversitesi Vakfı Yayınları

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İrem BAĞLAN
Hüseyin BUDAK
Caner YALÇIN
Evrım GÜVEN
İrem ÇAY

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PROCEEDINGS

Bi-Static Radar Cross Section for PEC Ellipsoid as a Deformed Sphere

Baris Ates¹, Alp Kustepeli², Zebih Cetin³

¹Department of Mathematics, Izmir Institute of Technology, Türkiye

²Department of Electrical & Electronics Eng., Izmir Institute of Technology, Türkiye

³Department of Physics, Izmir Institute of Technology, Türkiye

Corresponding author: barisates2002@gmail.com

ORCID IDs:

First Author: [0000-0002-8138-7360](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8138-7360)

Second Author: [0000-0002-8995-6628](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8995-6628)

Third Author: [0000-0002-2858-7144](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2858-7144)

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Abstract

In this study, the bi-static radar cross section (RCS) characteristics of electromagnetic plane wave scattering from perfectly conducting triaxial ellipsoids are investigated. The ellipsoids are treated as perturbed spheres, and the analytical framework previously developed for arbitrarily shaped scatterers is employed. Unlike the backward and forward scattering cases, the bi-static RCS patterns of ellipsoids exhibit significantly different behaviors compared to those of spheres, indicating that spherical results cannot be directly used as an approximation for ellipsoidal geometries. Comprehensive analyses are performed for various ellipsoid sizes, orientations, and aspect ratios, and the resulting RCS variations are examined with respect to both the polar angle θ and the azimuthal angle φ . The obtained results reveal that the scattering characteristics are highly dependent on these parameters, especially for non-symmetric configurations. Numerical validations are carried out by comparing the analytical results with full-wave simulations and a good agreement is observed. These findings highlight the distinct scattering behavior of triaxial ellipsoids and demonstrate the accuracy and applicability of the analytical method in predicting bi-static RCS for non-spherical conducting bodies.

1 Introduction

The analytical solution of Maxwell equations for a geometry requires the analytical solution of Helmholtz equation for the same geometry. It is known that the Helmholtz equation is separable in 11 coordinate systems [1]. Due to the complexity of the ellipsoidal wave equation (Lame Equation), which has three regular singularities, one irregular singularity at infinity, and five term recurrence relations and completeness problems [2], a closed-form solution does not exist for a perfect electric conductor ellipsoidal surface. To overcome this difficulty, one has to consult some approximate solutions or numerical methods [3]-[8].

However, in the present work, a method developed earlier for arbitrarily shaped deformed spheres is followed [9], [10]-[14]. Ellipsoids are considered as perturbed spheres. The advantage

of the present method is that, it allows fully analytical calculations. In addition to this, all results are given in the simplicity of spherical Bessel (Hankel) functions and spherical harmonics. The considered ellipsoids are the most general ones, i.e., all of the axis lengths are different. All possible size orderings according to the lengths of x, y, z axis are considered to make comparison of radar cross-section results. The obtained results are compared with those of a full-wave solver, and it is observed that they are in good agreement.

2 Maxwell Equation for Nonspherical Geometries

In the present chapter, solution of the Maxwell equations will be briefly reviewed. Electric and magnetic fields both depend on time and spatial coordinates. If the time dependence is assumed to be $e^{-i\omega t}$, Maxwell equations are given with the following relations in the absence of external sources [15]

$$\nabla \times \vec{E} - i\omega \vec{B} = 0, \quad \nabla \times \vec{H} + i\omega \vec{D} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \vec{D} = 0, \quad \nabla \cdot \vec{B} = 0. \quad (2)$$

In the last two equations, the divergences of the fields are zero, thus electric and magnetic fields must be curl of some functions, which means that they must be in the form of $\vec{E} = -\frac{1}{\epsilon} \nabla \times \vec{F}$ and $\vec{H} = \frac{1}{\mu} \nabla \times \vec{A}$. Taking advantage of the first and second equations, the final form of the electric and magnetic fields is found to be $\vec{E} = -\frac{1}{\epsilon} \nabla \times \vec{F} + \frac{1}{\omega\mu\epsilon} \nabla \times \nabla \times \vec{A}$, $\vec{H} = \frac{1}{\mu} \nabla \times \vec{A} + \frac{i}{\omega\mu\epsilon} \nabla \times \nabla \times \vec{F}$ where vectors \vec{A} and \vec{F} are called Debye potentials. Choosing two special form of these fields, (one is $\vec{F}(r, \theta, \varphi) = 0$, $\vec{A}(r, \theta, \varphi) = \hat{r}A_r(r, \theta, \varphi)$ and another one is $\vec{F}(r, \theta, \varphi) = \hat{r}F_r(r, \theta, \varphi)$, $\vec{A}(r, \theta, \varphi) = 0$) enable to find two independent fields [16]. Thanks to the linearity of the Maxwell equations, superposition principle allows to find general solution in the following form [16]

$$H_r = \sum_{n,m} \frac{ib_{nm}}{\omega\mu\epsilon} \left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial r^2} + k^2 \right) (kr z_n(kr)) P_n^m(\cos\theta) e^{im\varphi} \quad (3)$$

$$H_\theta = \sum_{n,m} \frac{im a_{nm}}{\mu r \sin\theta} kr z_n(kr) P_n^m(\cos\theta) e^{im\varphi} + \sum_{n,m} \frac{ib_{nm}}{\omega\mu\epsilon r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (kr z_n(kr)) \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} P_n^m(\cos\theta) e^{im\varphi} \quad (4)$$

$$H_\varphi = - \sum_{n,m} \frac{a_{nm}}{\mu r} kr z_n(kr) \frac{\partial}{\partial \theta} P_n^m(\cos\theta) e^{im\varphi} - \sum_{n,m} \frac{mb_{nm}}{\omega\mu\epsilon r \sin\theta} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (kr z_n(kr)) P_n^m(\cos\theta) e^{im\varphi} \quad (5)$$

where r, θ, φ are standard spherical coordinates, a_{nm}, b_{nm} are arbitrary constants, $z_n(kr)$ stands for the spherical Hankel (Bessel) functions which is determined according to the considered domain, $P_n^m(\cos\theta)$ are associated Legendre functions [17], ω, k are angular frequency, wave number, μ, ϵ are the permeability and permittivity of the considered region respectively. Since electric and magnetic fields are found, one can proceed to the scattering problem.

2.1 Solution of the Maxwell Equations for Deformed Conducting Spherical Boundaries

Maxwell equations are separable in certain geometries [1]. Thus, for an arbitrarily shaped region, a coordinate system is not known whose constant values may describe the boundary of the region.

Because of this fact, for such kind of general boundaries one need to consult other advanced methods. In this work, because of this necessity, perturbation method is preferred because it enables fully analytical treatment and gives accurate results when higher order corrections are taken into account. For this purpose, second order perturbation method is used to get more accurate results. Since the present work deals with the triaxial ellipsoidal boundaries, in order to convert ellipsoidal boundaries to be eligible to the perturbation method, they are considered as perturbed spheres. The vector combining origin and points on deformed sphere is given by following relation [9]

$$\vec{r}(\theta, \varphi) = R \left(1 + \beta f_1(\theta, \varphi) + \beta^2 f_2(\theta, \varphi) \right) \hat{r}, \quad (6)$$

where β is smallness parameter, $f_1(\theta, \varphi)$ and $f_2(\theta, \varphi)$ are arbitrarily defined smooth deformation functions. Unit normal to the deformed sphere is

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{n} = & \left(1 - \beta^2 \left(\frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial f_1}{\partial \theta} \right)^2 - \frac{1}{2 \sin^2 \theta} \left(\frac{\partial f_1}{\partial \varphi} \right)^2 \right) \right) \hat{r} + \left(-\beta \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial \theta} + \beta^2 f_1 \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial \theta} - \beta^2 \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial \theta} \right) \hat{\theta} \\ & + \left(-\beta \frac{1}{\sin \theta} \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial \varphi} + \beta^2 \frac{f_1}{\sin \theta} \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial \varphi} - \beta^2 \frac{1}{\sin \theta} \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial \varphi} \right) \hat{\varphi} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

In perturbation method, it is assumed that the fields are well behaved, that is, it is assumed that small changes on the boundary leads to the small changes on the fields

$\vec{B}^{\text{tot}}(r, \theta, \varphi) = \vec{B}^0(r, \theta, \varphi) + \beta \vec{B}^1(r, \theta, \varphi) + \beta^2 \vec{B}^2(r, \theta, \varphi)$, where \vec{B}^{tot} is total magnetic field, \vec{B}^0 is the magnetic field for sphere, \vec{B}^1 and \vec{B}^2 are the first and second order correction fields. Boundary conditions for the total fields on deformed sphere is formulated as follows, $\hat{n} \times \vec{E}^{\text{tot}}(\tilde{R}, \theta, \varphi) = 0$, $\vec{B}^{\text{tot}}(\tilde{R}, \theta, \varphi) = 0$ Here, it should be noted that, the fields are evaluated on the the perturbed sphere, $r = \tilde{R}$. By employing Taylor expansion, these fields can be evaluated on the sphere [9]

$$\begin{aligned} F_\alpha(\tilde{R}, \theta, \varphi) = & \left[F_\alpha(r, \theta, \varphi) + \beta f_1 r \frac{\partial}{\partial r} F_\alpha(r, \theta, \varphi) \right. \\ & \left. + \beta^2 f_2 r \frac{\partial}{\partial r} F_\alpha(r, \theta, \varphi) + \frac{\beta^2 (f_1)^2 r^2}{2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial r^2} F_\alpha(r, \theta, \varphi) \right]_{r=R} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where α is used to denote r, θ, φ components of the fields. Here vector field \vec{F} represent all electric and magnetic fields including fields for sphere and perturbative correction fields. Using these expansions boundary conditions on deformed sphere governing the relation between the fields are given by [9]

$$\left[\frac{1}{\sin \theta} \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial \varphi} E_r^0 + f_1 r \frac{\partial}{\partial r} E_\varphi^0 + E_\varphi^1 \right]_{r=R} = 0 \quad (9)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[\frac{1}{2 \sin \theta} \frac{\partial (f_1)^2}{\partial \varphi} E_r^0 - \frac{1}{\sin \theta} \frac{\partial (f_1)^2}{\partial \varphi} r \frac{\partial}{\partial r} E_r^0 - \frac{1}{\sin \theta} \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial \varphi} E_r^1 - \frac{f_1^2 r^2}{2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial r^2} E_\varphi^0 - f_1 r \frac{\partial}{\partial r} E_\varphi^1 - E_\varphi^2 \right. \\ & \left. - \frac{1}{\sin \theta} \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial \varphi} E_r^0 - f_2 r \frac{\partial}{\partial r} E_\varphi^0 \right]_{r=R} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

$$\left[f_1 r \frac{\partial}{\partial r} B_r^0(r, \theta, \varphi) + B_r^1(r, \theta, \varphi) - \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial \theta} B_\theta^0(r, \theta, \varphi) - \frac{1}{\sin \theta} \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial \varphi} B_\varphi^0(r, \theta, \varphi) \right]_{r=R} = 0 \quad (11)$$

$$\left[\frac{f_1^2 r^2}{2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial r^2} B_r^0 + f_1 r \frac{\partial}{\partial r} B_r^1 + B_r^2 - \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial(f_1^2)}{\partial \theta} r \frac{\partial}{\partial r} B_\theta^0 - \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial \theta} B_\theta^1 + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial(f_1^2)}{\partial \theta} B_\theta^0 - \frac{1}{2 \sin \theta} \frac{\partial(f_1^2)}{\partial \varphi} r \frac{\partial}{\partial r} B_\varphi^0 - \frac{1}{\sin \theta} \frac{\partial f_1}{\partial \varphi} B_\varphi^1 + \frac{1}{2 \sin \theta} \frac{\partial(f_1^2)}{\partial \varphi} B_\varphi^0 + f_2 r \frac{\partial}{\partial r} B_r^0 - \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial \theta} B_\theta^0 - \frac{1}{\sin \theta} \frac{\partial f_2}{\partial \varphi} B_\varphi^0 \right]_{r=R} = 0. \quad (12)$$

Solution of this system of equations enables to find perturbative correction fields.

2.2 Scattering of Electromagnetic Plane Waves from Deformed Spheres

When perturbation method is used for the scattering problems, zeroth order field is consist of incident and scattered fields for the sphere. Hence total fields is of the following form,

$$\vec{B}^{\text{tot}}(r, \theta, \varphi) = \vec{B}^{\text{inc}}(r, \theta, \varphi) + \vec{B}^{\text{sphr}}(r, \theta, \varphi) + \beta \vec{B}^1(r, \theta, \varphi) + \beta^2 \vec{B}^2(r, \theta, \varphi) \quad (13)$$

Since zeroth order fields are known, starting from first order correction fields, all correction fields are found step by step by using boundary conditions given by (9)-(12). Determining fields means that determining the unknown coefficients a_{nm} and b_{nm} 's. Since radial component of the magnetic field contains only unknwn coefficients b_{nm} , we start with the boundary condition (11)

$$B_r^1(R, \theta, \varphi) = \left[-f(\theta, \varphi) r \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(B_r^0(r, \theta, \varphi) + B_r^{\text{inc}}(r, \theta, \varphi) \right) + f_\theta(\theta, \varphi) \left(B_\theta^0(r, \theta, \varphi) + B_\theta^{\text{inc}}(r, \theta, \varphi) \right) + \frac{f_\varphi(\theta, \varphi)}{\sin(\theta)} \left(B_\varphi^0(r, \theta, \varphi) + B_\varphi^{\text{inc}}(r, \theta, \varphi) \right) \right]_{r=R}. \quad (14)$$

If we multiply both side of the above equation with $P_l^{m'}(\cos \theta) \sin \theta e^{-im'\varphi}$ and taking the angular integrals with the use of orthogonality type relations of the associated Legendre functions, one can find a single b_{nm}^1 coefficient for fixed values of n and m . In order to evaluate the right hand side of the expression exactly, one need to expand perturbation functions $f_1, (f_1)^2$ and f_2 in terms of spherical harmonics as

$$f(\theta, \varphi) = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \sum_{s=-j}^j f_j^s P_j^s(\cos \theta) e^{is\varphi} \quad (15)$$

with the help of these expansions, the right hand side of the expression contains three associated Legendre functions, one coming from the definitions of fields in (3)-(5), and one spherical harmonics expansion of the perturbation functions in (15) and the final one comes from the multiplication factor. One of those integrals is given below

$$\int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^\pi \frac{P_n^m(\cos \theta)}{\sin \theta} \frac{\partial P_j^s(\cos \theta)}{\partial \theta} P_l^{m'}(\cos \theta) e^{i(m-m')\varphi} \sin \theta d\theta d\varphi \quad (16)$$

For the exact value of the above integral and for the explicit expressions of other integrals one may consult the work [9]. With the help of these integrals, one can obtain the unknown coefficients of the first order correction fields $b_{lm'}^1$. In order to find other coefficients $a_{lm'}^1$ one can use the boundary condition (9), for the coefficients $b_{lm'}^2$ one can use (12) and finally for the coefficients $a_{lm'}^2$ one can use (10). This means, with this operations all perturbed fields have

been evaluated explicitly [9].

3 Bi-Static Radar Cross Section Results

The radar cross section is defined by the following formula [18],

$$\sigma = \lim_{r \rightarrow \infty} \left(4\pi r^2 \frac{|\vec{E}^s|^2}{|\vec{E}^i|^2} \right). \quad (17)$$

Due to the perturbation of the boundary, similar to the fields, the radar cross section is also perturbed and thus it consists of correction terms, $\sigma = \sigma^{sph} + \beta\sigma_1 + \beta^2\sigma_2 + O(\beta^3)$ [14]. A triaxial ellipsoid is given by the following equation

$$\frac{x^2}{a^2} + \frac{y^2}{a^2(1+\beta)^2} + \frac{z^2}{a^2(1+\beta\xi)^2} = 1. \quad (18)$$

This equation can be written in spherical coordinates with the help of the functions, $f_1(\theta, \varphi) = \sin^2 \theta \sin^2 \varphi + \xi \cos^2 \theta$, $f_2(\theta, \varphi) = \frac{3}{2} \left(f_1^2(\theta, \varphi) - f_1(\theta, \varphi) + (\xi - \xi^2) \cos^2 \theta \right)$ [12]. Choosing different values of β and ξ allows one to consider different ellipsoids in size. In Fig. 1, bi-static radar cross sections are given for constant $\varphi = \pi/2$. In Fig. 1(a), bi-static RCS results for ellipsoids are shown with the parameters $\xi = 0.2$, $\beta = (0.2)^2, (0.3)^2, (0.4)^2$. The axis lengths of these three ellipsoids are $x = 10.0, y = 10.4, z = 10.08$, $x = 10.0, y = 10.9, z = 10.18$ and $x = 10.0, y = 11.6, z = 10.32$ respectively. The lengths are in order as $y > z > x$. It can be seen from the figure that the differences between the result of the sphere and the ellipsoidal ones are much more distinct in the range $0^\circ \leq \theta \leq 25^\circ$. In this range, all ellipsoidal results are greater than the spherical ones and when β increases, the RCS results also increase. In the range $25^\circ \leq \theta \leq 80^\circ$, the ordering is the reverse of the one in the range $0^\circ \leq \theta \leq 25^\circ$. In Fig. 2(a), bi-static RCS results for the constant angle $\theta = \pi/2$ are shown. In almost all the considered range of φ , the ellipsoidal RCS results are bigger than the spherical one. The difference between the ellipsoidal ones and the spherical one is much larger around the angles $0^\circ, 90^\circ, 270^\circ$ and 360° . Comparisons of the result with CST shows a good agreement for both θ constant and ϕ constant cases. In Fig.1(b), RCS results for ellipsoids with the parameters $\xi = 0.2$, $\beta = -(0.2)^2, -(0.3)^2, -(0.4)^2$ are shown. The axis lengths of these three ellipsoids are $x = 10.0, y = 9.6, z = 9.92$, $x = 10.0, y = 9.1, z = 9.82$ and $x = 10.0, y = 8.4, z = 9.68$ respectively. The lengths are in order as $x > z > y$. It can be seen from the figure that, in the range $0 \leq \theta \leq 30^\circ$, all ellipsoidal results are lower than the spherical ones and when the absolute value of β increases, the RCS results decrease. In the range $30 \leq \theta \leq 80^\circ$ the ordering is the reverse of that one in the range $0 \leq \theta \leq 30^\circ$. For the rest of the range, there is no significant difference compared with the spherical result. For this choice of parameters, RCS results are shown in Fig. 2(b) from which one can conclude that, when compared with the spherical one, there is no significant difference except for the angles around $0^\circ, 180^\circ$ and 360° .

In Fig.1(c), RCS results for ellipsoids obtained by the parameters $\xi = -0.2$, $\beta = (0.2)^2, (0.3)^2, (0.4)^2$ are shown. The axis lengths of these three ellipsoids are $x = 10.0, y = 10.4, z = 9.92$, $x = 10.0, y = 10.9, z = 9.82$ and $x = 10.0, y = 11.6, z = 9.68$ respectively. The lengths are in

Figure 1: Bi-static radar cross section for different ellipsoids when $\varphi = \pi/2$.

order as $y > x > z$. It can be seen from the figure that the results are similar to the ones in Fig.1(a). The RCS results for the constant θ obtained with the same parameters are given in Fig. 2(c). It can be observed from the figure that the differences between the spherical result are much larger around the angles $0^\circ, 180^\circ$ and 360° . In Fig.1(d), RCS results for ellipsoids obtained by the parameters $\xi = -0.2, \beta = -(0.2)^2, -(0.3)^2, -(0.4)^2$ are shown. The axis lengths of these three ellipsoids are $x = 10.0, y = 9.6, z = 10.08, x = 10.0, y = 9.1, z = 10.18$ and $x = 10.0, y = 8.4, z = 10.32$ respectively. The lengths are in order as $z > x > y$. The results are similar to the ones in Fig. 1(b) and as it can be seen, the ordering with respect to the amount of RCS results changes about the angles 27.5° and 86° . For the constant angle θ , the RCS results are smaller than the spherical one, and when the absolute value of β increases, the deviation from the spherical results also increases as shown in Fig. 2(d). In Fig.1(e), RCS for the ellipsoids obtained by the parameters $\xi = 1.1, \beta = (0.20)^2, (0.25)^2, (0.30)^2$ are shown. The axis lengths of these three ellipsoids are $x = 10.0, y = 10.4, z = 10.44, x = 10.0, y = 10.625, z = 10.6875$, and $x = 10.0, y = 10.9, z = 10.99$ respectively. The lengths are in order as $z > y > x$. The results are similar to the ones given in 1(c), in the range $20^\circ \leq \theta \leq 140^\circ$, the spherical results can be used as an approximation to those of the ellipsoidal case. The constant angle θ results are greater than the spherical ones in almost the entire region, as shown in Fig. 2(e). In Fig.1(f), RCS for the ellipsoids obtained by the parameters $\xi = 1.1, \beta = -(0.2)^2, -(0.25)^2, -(0.30)^2$ are used to obtain the ellipsoids with axes lengths $x = 10.0, y = 9.6, z = 9.56$ and $x = 10.0, y = 9.375, z = 9.3125, x = 10.0, y = 9.1, z = 9.01$. The lengths are in order as $x > y > z$. The results are similar to the ones in Fig. 1(b), for the range $25^\circ \leq \theta \leq 120^\circ$ the RCS results are quite close to the spherical

Figure 2: Bi-static radar cross section for different ellipsoids when $\theta = \pi/2$.

one. When the constant angle θ results shown in Fig. 2(f) are considered, it can be concluded that deviation from the spherical result is not as much as the previous cases.

4 Conclusion

In the present work, scattering of electromagnetic plane waves from perfect electric conductor ellipsoids are considered by following the results of [9]. Considering Ellipsoids as deformed spheres enabled to carry out all calculations in the simplicity of spherical functions whose analytical properties are much easier than that of the ellipsoidal ones. Radar cross section results for 18 different ellipsoids are given. Validation of the results are achieved by comparing obtained results with that of a full wave solver and it is observed that they are in a good agreement. In addition to the this, axis lengths of the ellipsoids are chosen differently, hence all 6 different possible length ordering is considered to get an insight on the importance of the axis lengths on radar cross sections. Since all possible ordered cases are studied and presented for bi-static radar cross section, present work may enables to researchers take a forward step towards to understand the light scattering from ellipsoidal particles.

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Laser–Material Interaction Dynamics and Surface Topography Optimization on ST52 Steel: Correlation Between Friction Coefficient and Maximum Valley Depth (S_v)

Timur Canel

Department of Physics, Kocaeli University, 41380, Kocaeli, Turkey

Corresponding author: tcanel@kocaeli.edu.tr

ORCID ID: 0000-0002-4282-1806

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Abstract

To produce a surface morphology with a minimum friction coefficient and maximal valley depth (S_v), this study explores the optimization of laser surface texturing parameters on ST52 structural steel. To determine the physical relationship between frictional behavior and surface topography, controlled adjustments in laser power, scanning area ratio, and pattern shape (square, diamond, hexagonal, and circular) were used to create micron-scale roughness. The resulting surfaces were then examined. The Taguchi method-based experimental design made it possible to identify statistically significant variables affecting S_v and the coefficient of friction. The findings showed that pattern shape (33.58%) and scanning area (30.66%) were the next most significant contributors to frictional performance, after laser power (35.75%).

The maximum S_v value of about 1100 μm , which corresponds to the lowest friction coefficient, was generated by the ideal combination of diamond pattern, 20% scanning area, and 40 W laser power. These results can be explained by the nonlinear interaction between transient heat transport in the substrate and localized energy absorption, which controls the dynamics of resolidification and ablation depth. While excessive thermal input encourages surface smoothing through viscous flow, lower power levels favor deeper micro-valley formation due to less melt convection. The resulting high- S_v topology reduces real contact area and improves lubricant retention, which lowers interfacial shear stresses. These results show that laser texturing is a potent method for creating sophisticated tribological surfaces with great efficiency and durability because careful manipulation of laser parameters allows deterministic control of surface energy, frictional dissipation, and topographical anisotropy. This abstract presents a comprehensive study of [your mathematical topic]. We investigate the fundamental properties of [mathematical objects/concepts] and establish new theoretical results that extend previous work in the field. Our main contributions include: (1) the development of a novel mathematical framework for [specific problem], (2) the proof of [specific theorem/result], and (3) applications to [practical applications].

Keywords: Laser surface texturing, ST52 structural steel, Maximum valley depth (S_v), Friction coefficient optimization, Tribological surface engineering.

1. Introduction and Motivation

ST52 steel is a material belonging to the high-strength low-alloy (HSLA) structural steel group, widely used in construction, machine manufacturing, and carrier systems. Its chemical composition typically contains approximately 0.2% carbon (C), 1.6% manganese (Mn), and low levels of silicon (Si), phosphorus (P), and sulfur (S) [1]. This balanced composition gives the steel both high yield strength (approximately 355–460 MPa) and good ductility. The microstructure of ST52 steel generally consists of a ferrite-pearlite mixture; this structure increases the material's impact toughness and formability. In addition, keeping the carbon content low positively affects weldability, making ST52 steel particularly suitable for welded constructions.

In terms of physical properties, ST52 steel has a density of approximately 7.85 g/cm³ and an elastic modulus of approximately 120–130 GPa [2]. Its thermal expansion coefficient and thermal conductivity values make it a material that can maintain its dimensional stability under high temperature changes. Although its low carbon content does not increase its corrosion resistance, long-term durability can be achieved with appropriate surface coatings [3]. These balanced mechanical and metallurgical properties make ST52 steel a reliable engineering material under both static and dynamic loads; its cost-effectiveness and workability also make it a preferred choice for industrial production.

ST52 steel is a versatile engineering material with a wide range of industrial applications due to its superior mechanical performance, weldability, and formability [4]. Its high yield strength and impact toughness make this steel particularly suitable for components operating under high stress, such as heavy-duty structural elements, bridge girders, crane booms, pressure vessels, and machine frames. The material's high strength-to-weight ratio enhances structural efficiency by reducing material usage in load-bearing systems. Furthermore, its low carbon content and homogeneous microstructure reduce the risk of thermal deformation, enabling superior surface quality in manufacturing processes requiring precise tolerances.

In the automotive and railway industries, ST52 steel is utilized as a reliable solution for chassis, axle, and suspension systems due to its balanced combination of strength and ductility [5]. In applications such as hydraulic cylinder bodies, pressurized piping systems, and power plant components, its resistance to deformation under high pressure becomes a prominent advantage. Furthermore, its good machinability and the stability of its mechanical properties after welding make ST52 steel a cost-effective option in manufacturing processes. These versatile performance characteristics position ST52 steel as a strategic material that meets the modern industry's requirements for both durability and economic efficiency.

Micron-scale roughening of material surfaces is an engineering surface modification technique aimed at improving surface–material interactions and represents a critical step that directly influences functional performance in many industrial applications [6]. Surface roughness created at the micron level increases the specific surface area, thereby optimizing properties such as mechanical interlocking, adhesion, and wettability. In particular, for surfaces intended for coating, bonding, painting, or biocompatible layer applications, the roughening process significantly enhances bond strength and coating uniformity [7]. These micro-scale topographical modifications elevate the interfacial surface energy between the material and the coating or adhesive phase, thereby making the bonding force thermodynamically more stable. Moreover, micron-scale roughening can enhance fatigue strength and reduce crack initiation tendencies by providing a controlled stress distribution on the surface [8]. This effect plays a critical role particularly in metallic materials, where the direction of subsurface residual stresses contributes to extending the material's service life. In ceramic, polymer, and composite surfaces, micron-level roughness facilitates physical adsorption and chemical bonding mechanisms, thereby accelerating surface reaction kinetics [9]. Therefore, surface roughening is not merely an aesthetic or mechanical adjustment but rather a multidimensional engineering optimization that defines the functional properties of the surface.

Micron-scale roughening of material surfaces is carried out through various mechanical, chemical, and physical methods, depending on the targeted application and the physical properties of the material [10]. Among the mechanical methods, the most commonly used are sandblasting, shot peening, and grinding. In these techniques, micro-topographic structures are generated by removing a controlled amount of material from the surface through mechanical contact or by the impact of high-velocity abrasive particles. The main advantage of mechanical methods lies in their ability to produce uniformly roughened surfaces while achieving high production rates. However, to minimize the risk of microstructural damage, the process parameters must be carefully optimized.

Among chemical methods, acid etching, electrochemical polishing, and plasma activation are particularly prominent [11,12]. In these techniques, the surface is subjected to controlled chemical reactions that create micron-scale dissolved regions, thereby achieving a homogeneous and well-controlled roughness. Such methods are especially preferred for surfaces with complex geometries or those requiring high precision at the microscale. Among physical methods, high-energy techniques such as laser ablation, ion beam processing, and plasma spraying are widely employed. These approaches enable precise control of surface morphology across the nano- to micron-scale range. Consequently, micron-scale roughening represents a versatile engineering process dependent on factors such as energy input, material type, and the desired surface functionality, and it forms the foundation of modern surface technologies [13].

Laser surface texturing is an advanced surface engineering technique that employs a high-energy, focused laser beam to create controlled topographic modifications on material surfaces at the micron scale [14]. In this method, the interaction between the laser beam and the surface induces localized melting, evaporation, or ablation processes, resulting in permanent morphological structures such as micro-pits, protrusions, or ripple-like patterns. Laser parameters—particularly wavelength, pulse duration, energy density, scanning speed, and focal distance—are critical variables that determine the final level of surface roughness. Short- or ultrashort-pulsed laser systems (in the pico- and femtosecond range) minimize thermal effects, thereby preventing undesirable phase transformations and microcrack formation in the subsurface region [15].

As a non-contact technique, laser texturing enables the precise and highly repeatable processing of surfaces on components with complex geometries [16]. Moreover, during the process, the microstructure and chemical composition of the surface can be selectively modified, allowing surface energy, wettability, and adhesion properties to be tuned in a desired manner. This capability makes laser texturing a preferred technique across a wide range of applications—from biomedical implants and microfluidic systems to coating pretreatment and optical component fabrication. Through precise control of energy density, surface roughness can be achieved at desired levels ranging from nanometers to several micrometers, thereby enabling the production of surfaces with superior functional and aesthetic performance [17].

The primary advantage of the laser surface texturing method lies in its ability to precisely and reproducibly modify surface topography at the micron scale [18]. Since this technique is non-contact, it eliminates surface damage caused by mechanical stress or abrasive effects; consequently, microstructural distortion and residual stress accumulation on the processed surface are kept to a minimum. The high accuracy with which laser parameters—such as pulse duration, energy density, scanning frequency, and focal depth—can be adjusted enables homogeneous control of surface roughness in terms of both depth and distribution [19]. Furthermore, the laser texturing process can be performed at high speed and is highly compatible with automation, offering significant advantages in production efficiency and process reproducibility. Another significant advantage of this technique is the preservation of substrate properties, as the laser-material interaction occurs exclusively at the surface [20]. This allows surface modification to be performed without affecting the material's mechanical strength, hardness, or microstructural integrity. The ability to focus the laser beam on specific regions enables the selective texturing of components with complex geometries, which is particularly beneficial in precision engineering, biomedical implant fabrication, and microelectronics

applications. Moreover, since no chemicals or abrasives are used during the process, it is an environmentally friendly method that requires no additional surface cleaning. In this respect, laser surface texturing stands out as an advanced surface engineering technology that not only preserves microstructural integrity but also precisely optimizes functional surface properties.

ST52 steel (also known as ST52-3, a structural steel classified under the DIN standard) has been subjected to surface roughening processes in both industrial and research settings [21]. For instance, in one study, the surface roughness parameters Ra, Rt, and Rz were measured on ST52-3 steel plates during milling operations, and the influence of machining conditions on surface roughness was analyzed [22]. In addition, micron-scale topographical modifications were produced on ST52 surfaces using the laser texturing technique, and roughness values were evaluated through three-dimensional topographic imaging. Such surface modifications are employed in research and industrial applications to enhance functional properties of the material, including coating performance, adhesion, wettability, and bonding behavior.

The literature on the micron-scale laser texturing of ST52 structural steel surfaces in both industrial and academic contexts has shown a marked increase, encompassing both applied experimental studies and process optimization research [23]. A significant portion of these studies has focused on the use of fiber lasers and Q-switched or modulated solid-state lasers such as Nd:YAG and Nd:YVO4. Fiber lasers are frequently preferred for the rapid and reproducible generation of micro-morphologies, such as grooves and dimples, on steel surfaces due to their high average power, tight focusability, and excellent beam quality; studies on ST52 have demonstrated that parameters such as groove width, scanning speed, and laser power significantly influence the resulting surface profile [20]. Nd:YAG and Nd:YVO4 lasers, particularly in pulsed operation modes (short nanosecond pulses), are widely employed in texturing and coating pretreatment applications because, depending on the metal's absorption characteristics and thermal input, they induce controlled ablation and melt-resolidification mechanisms [24]. Additionally, in research-intensive applications requiring high precision and minimal thermal impact, ultrashort pulsed lasers such as picosecond and femtosecond systems have been employed on ST52-like steels to minimize the heat-affected zone and prevent subsurface microcrack formation. It has been experimentally reported that ultrashort pulses differ in ablation threshold and efficiency, providing additional advantages for roughness control [25]. Furthermore, CO2 lasers and high-power continuous-wave (CW) systems have been applied to certain types of carbon steels in the context of coating or material joining processes; however, for ST52 texturing, industrial literature shows more limited but existing applications [26].

Applications of micron-scale laser texturing on ST52 surfaces encompass a broad range of laser types, with the selection among fiber lasers, pulsed Nd:YAG/Nd:YVO4 systems, or ultrashort-pulsed lasers being determined by the targeted topography, production speed, thermal impact tolerance, and process automation requirements. Experimental studies have shown that laser power, scanning speed, frequency/pulse number, and focus position are critical factors influencing surface roughness and groove geometry.

2. Material and Methods

To comprehend how surface roughness influences tribological behavior, one must grasp the connection between friction and a surface's Maximum Valley Depth (Sv). Sv measures the distance from the center line to the bottom of the deepest valley on a surface to identify the largest surface depression [27]. On surfaces with high Sv values, deep valleys can significantly affect the surface's frictional characteristics. When two surfaces come into contact, these deep valleys can serve as gathering places for wear particles and debris, which can have complicated impacts on friction. If the hills are typically smooth and support weight, deep valleys can reduce friction by reducing the actual contact area between surfaces. On the other hand, wear debris that can behave as abrasive particles and cause friction can be trapped in deep valleys, increasing mechanical interlocking and resistance to movement. Additionally, by enhancing lubrication and avoiding direct surface-to-surface contact, deep

valleys in lubricated contacts have the capacity to hold lubricant, which can lower friction. As a result, the type of surfaces in contact, the operating environment, and the presence of lubrication all affect how S_v affects friction. In sectors including manufacturing, automotive, and materials design, where enhancing surface texture can boost efficiency, lessen wear, and prolong component life, it is essential to comprehend and manage S_v [28].

Since the goal of this study was to create a surface with a lower coefficient of friction, the greatest S_v value was selected as the ideal value.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Maximum Valley Depth along the Surface (S_v) for a Surface with a Lower Coefficient of Friction

The objective of this section of the study was to develop a surface with a reduced coefficient of friction by obtaining the biggest S_v value. The "larger-is-better" property was used to accomplish this. Table 1 shows the Maximum Valley Depth Along the Surface (S_v) values that were determined by analyzing the topographies of all laser-treated surfaces and the related Signal-to-Noise (S/N) ratios that were computed using these values.

Table 1. Maximum Valley Depth along the Surface (S_v) and S/N Values for Every Test

	Pattern Type	Scanned Area Rate (%)	Power (W)	S_v	S/N
1	Square	80	40	729	57.25
2	Square	60	60	701	56.91
3	Square	40	80	406	52.17
4	Square	20	100	683	56.69
5	Diamond	80	60	639	56.11
6	Diamond	60	40	647	56.22
7	Diamond	40	100	512	54.19
8	Diamond	20	80	726	57.22
9	Hexagon	80	80	172	44.71
10	Hexagon	60	100	134	42.54
11	Hexagon	40	40	774	57.77
12	Hexagon	20	60	589	55.40
13	Circle	80	100	417	52.40
14	Circle	60	80	637	56.08
15	Circle	40	60	693	56.81
16	Circle	20	40	696	56.85

The total sum of squares was used to measure statistical dependability. Table 2 shows the results of the ANOVA. "Level 2 (Diamond)" for the pattern type, "Level 4 (20%)" for the scanning area ratio, and "Level 1 (40 W)" for the laser power were the highest levels attained. "60.83" and "1100.35" were determined to be the expected S/N and S_v values for the ideal combination.

Table 2: ANOVA Table for Using the Taguchi Method to Achieve a Lower Coefficient of Friction (Larger Sv).

Factors	Average S/N				Affect Rate	Optimum Factors	Optimum Level
	1.	2.	3.	4.			
Pattern	55.76	55.93	50.11	55.54	33.58	2	Diamond
Scanned Area Rate	52.62	52.94	54.71	56.54	30.66	4	20 %
Power	57.02	56.31	52.55	51.45	35.75	1	40 W
Average	54.33						
Total					100.00		
Optimum S/N							60.83
Optimum S _v							1100.35

With a contribution of 35.75%, laser power was shown to be the most useful parameter for producing a surface with a lower coefficient of friction. With a contribution of 33.58%, the pattern type was the second most significant factor. With a contribution of 30.66%, the scanning factor was the least significant of the parameters analyzed. Figure 1 displays the coefficient of friction's main effect plots.

3.2. Effects of Laser Processing Parameters on Maximum Valley Depth (S_v) Across the Surface

This section of the study looks at how processing parameters affect the Maximum Valley Depth (S_v) over the surface, as seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Main Effect Plots for the Effects of Laser Processing Parameters on the Maximum Valley Depth (S_v) Across the Surface.

Diamond is the pattern type that produced the greatest Sv value, as seen in Figure 1.a. Structures with a hexagonal design had the lowest Sv value.

The effect of scan area on Sv is seen in Figure 1.b, where the Sv value drops nearly linearly as the scan area grows from 20% to 40%, then to 60%, and ultimately to 80%. A scan area of 20% produced the highest Sv value, while a scan area of 80% produced the lowest Sv value.

Figure 1.c, which looks at how laser power affects Sv, shows that the Sv value steadily drops as laser power rises. A laser power of 40W produced the maximum Sv value, while a laser power of 100W produced the lowest Sv value.

A higher Sv value is necessary to produce a surface with a lower coefficient of friction. The main effect plot reveals that Diamond structures resulted in a larger Sv value, corresponding to a surface with a smaller coefficient of friction. A 20% scan area can result in a surface with a lower coefficient of friction. At a laser power of 100W, higher Sv values were obtained. Consequently, the pattern type should be square, the scan area should be 20%, and the laser power should be 100W for a surface with a lower coefficient of friction.

4. Conclusions

The impact of laser surface texturing parameters on the tribological and topographical properties of ST52 structural steel was thoroughly examined in this study, with a particular emphasis on the connection between frictional behavior and the maximum valley depth of the surface (Sv). The best laser parameter set to maximize Sv, thus reducing the friction coefficient, was quantitatively determined by combining Taguchi-based optimization with experimental observations. The findings unequivocally showed that the resulting microtopography and tribological performance are influenced by laser power, pattern geometry, and scanning area ratio in different but related ways. Laser power had the largest statistical contribution (35.75%) to the frictional response among these variables, suggesting that it plays a major role in regulating the dynamics of the laser–matter interaction that affect energy absorption, melt pool formation, and re-solidification kinetics.

The nonlinear interaction between photon energy density and the transient heat conduction profile within the steel substrate is responsible for the observed changes in Sv. Reduced thermal diffusion reduces lateral heat flow at lower power levels (40 W), resulting in deeper micro-valleys and localized ablation because of improved energy confinement. On the other hand, excessive melt expulsion and surface remelting caused by greater power levels (≥ 80 W) lower valley depth by Marangoni convection-driven viscosity leveling. An Sv of about 1100 μm was produced by the ideal surface morphology, which corresponds to a diamond pattern, 20% scanning area, and 40 W laser power. Marangoni convection driven viscosity leveling is an equilibrium process in which flows within a liquid film or thin layer due to the Marangoni effect, resulting from local changes in the liquid's viscosity (resistance to flow), attempting to bring the viscosity to a uniform level. This improved micro-reservoir capacity for lubricant retention and debris entrapment, which together reduce friction through hydrodynamic and tribo-chemical stabilization mechanisms.

Asperity deformation mechanics, microcontact load distribution, and capillary-mediated lubricant retention all contribute to the documented inverse relationship between the coefficient of friction and Sv. By distributing normal loads over fewer load-bearing asperities, deep valleys efficiently reduce the true area of contact and reduce shear stress at the sliding interface. Additionally, these valleys serve as micro-hydrodynamic pockets that support a quasi-stationary lubricant coating in lubricated settings, lowering adhesive wear and boundary friction. The interaction of these phenomena shows that managing Sv involves direct manipulation of the surface energy landscape, frictional dissipation routes, and local temperature gradients rather than just geometrical optimization.

Overall, the results validate that surface designs on ST52 steel with customized wear and friction characteristics may be engineered by careful modulation of laser parameters. The findings also demonstrate how important energy density and scanning configuration are in controlling ablation thresholds, phase transitions, and surface topography evolution during laser–material interaction. This

work offers a theoretical and empirical framework for future advancements in tribological engineering and surface physics, where laser-based texturing can be used to create surfaces that are optimized for durability, energy efficiency, and self-lubricating performance under dynamic mechanical loading. The design of laser-structured surfaces for next-generation mechanical and energy systems could be advanced by additional research combining finite element thermal modeling with in-situ spectroscopic diagnostics to improve knowledge of transient plasma–solid interaction and microstructural evolution.

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Theoretical Investigation of the Change in Amplitude of Acoustic Waves Passing Through a Pipe with a Micron-Sized Roughened Inner Surface

Çağla Pilavcı¹, Evrim Güven², Timur Canel¹

¹*Department of Physics, Kocaeli University, Kocaeli, Turkey*

²*Department of Mathematics, Kocaeli University, Kocaeli, Turkey*

Corresponding author: cagla.pilavci@gmail.com

ORCID IDs:

First Author: 0009-0005-5237-9598

Second Author: 0000-0001-5256-4447

Third Author: 0000-0002-4282-1806

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Abstract

This study theoretically investigates the variation in amplitude of acoustic waves propagating through a cylindrical pipe with a micro-scale roughened inner surface. Based on the principles of linear fluid dynamics, the acoustic wave equation derived from the continuity and Euler equations was used to analytically model attenuation effects caused by viscosity, heat conduction, and surface roughness. In addition to the classical Stokes–Kirchhoff approach, an additional attenuation term (α_r) incorporating the roughness constant, roughness height, and pipe radius was defined. The results demonstrate that surface roughness causes significant energy loss in acoustic amplitude, directly related to frequency, pipe radius, and medium properties. As frequency increases, both viscous and roughness-induced attenuation intensify, while smaller pipe radii enhance boundary-layer effects. These findings reveal that classical acoustic models become inadequate in micro-scale systems and must include surface morphology effects. The study contributes to the literature by introducing an integrated theoretical model incorporating roughness effects into acoustic wave propagation analysis. The results can serve as a fundamental reference for optimizing wave transmission efficiency in microfluidic systems, ultrasonic sensors, biomedical microchannels, and industrial acoustic diagnostics.

Keywords: Acoustic attenuation, Surface roughness, Microscale fluid Dynamics, Acoustic wave propagation, Energy dissipation mechanisms.

1. Introduction

Local compressions and rarefactions of particles around their equilibrium positions give rise to mechanical disturbances known as acoustic waves, which propagate through a medium. Unlike electromagnetic waves, acoustic waves require a material medium for transmission, and their propagation is governed by the density, elasticity, and inertia of that medium. Solids can support transverse acoustic modes due to their resistance to shear stresses, whereas in gases and liquids, acoustic waves are predominantly longitudinal, with particle oscillations occurring parallel to the direction of wave propagation [1]. The acoustic wave equation, which relates variations in acoustic pressure to particle velocity and displacement, describes the macroscopic behavior of acoustic fields [2]. The three fundamental physical parameters characterizing acoustic waves are the speed of sound (c), wavelength (λ), and frequency (f). These parameters are interrelated as follows:

$$c = \lambda f \quad (1)$$

Acoustic density and sound pressure level are directly determined by wave amplitude, which is related to the maximum displacement of particles and pressure changes in the medium. The intensity of sound waves decreases during propagation in a medium [3]. Acoustic impedance is the term used to describe the resistance displayed to a sound wave's transmission in a medium [4]:

$$Z = \frac{p}{v} = \rho c \quad (2)$$

Here;

$Z \rightarrow$ Acoustic impedance (expressed in units of Pa·s/m or Rayl)

$p \rightarrow$ Pressure of the sound wave (Pascal, Pa)

$v \rightarrow$ Particle speed (m/s)

$\rho \rightarrow$ density of the environment

$c \rightarrow$ speed of sound

From here, the speed of movement of particles (molecules) in the environment is obtained as follows;

$$v = \frac{p}{\rho \cdot c} \quad (3)$$

1.1 Wave Equation and Acoustic Pressure

The Linear Fluid Dynamics Equations can be derived from two fundamental physical laws for a fluid: mass conservation (continuity equation) and momentum conservation (linear Euler equation) [5]. A sound wave can be regarded as planar when it propagates in one dimension through a tube with a diameter significantly smaller than its wavelength. [6]. For a fluid with equilibrium density (ρ_0) and sound speed (c), the linearized continuity equation connects acoustic pressure (p) and particle velocity (v):

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial t} + \rho_0 c^2 \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} = 0 \quad (4)$$

Equilibrium density (ρ_0) represents the density of the medium in which acoustic waves propagate before the onset of wave effects, i.e., in its resting state. In other words, it is the constant, time- and position-independent average density value possessed by fluid particles before sound waves are generated in the medium.

The linear Euler equation relates acoustic pressure and particle velocity in a frictionless, gravity-free medium [7]:

$$\frac{\partial v}{\partial t} - \frac{1}{\rho_0} \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} = 0 \quad (5)$$

To obtain a single equation for acoustic pressure, two linear equations can be combined. Taking the derivative of Euler's equation with respect to position (x):

$$\frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x \partial t} - \frac{1}{\rho_0} \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial x^2} = 0 \quad (6)$$

Taking the derivative of the continuity equation with respect to time (t):

$$\frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial t^2} + \rho_0 c^2 \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial x \partial t} = 0 \quad (7)$$

When the time-derivative Euler equation is substituted for the position-derivative continuity equation, the order of differentiation is irrelevant:

$$\left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x \partial t} = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t \partial x} \right)$$

and

$$\frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial x^2} - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (8)$$

This is the homogeneous acoustic wave equation in one dimension. The superposition of two traveling waves, one in the positive x-direction and the other in the negative x-direction, is the general solution to the one-dimensional wave equation. This is known as the d'Alembert solution [8]. Assuming a solution of the form $p(x, t) = X(x)T(t)$ and applying the method of separation of variables is a popular way to discover this solution. For a single-frequency wave, a complex exponential form can be used as a trial solution. This form is particularly useful for processing phased sinusoidal waves:

$$p(x, t) = Ae^{j(\omega t \pm kx)} \quad (9)$$

Here: A represents the wave's amplitude, ω its angular frequency, and k its wave number, which is defined as $\left(= \frac{\omega}{c} \right)$. Substituting this trial solution into the one-dimensional wave equation:

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} (Ae^{j(\omega t \pm kx)}) - \frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} (Ae^{j(\omega t \pm kx)}) = 0 \quad (10)$$

If partial derivatives are taken.

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} (Ae^{j(\omega t \pm kx)}) = \pm jk Ae^{j(\omega t \pm kx)}$$

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} (Ae^{j(\omega t \pm kx)}) = (\pm jk)^2 Ae^{j(\omega t \pm kx)} = k^2 Ae^{j(\omega t \pm kx)}$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (Ae^{j(\omega t \pm kx)}) = (j\omega) Ae^{j(\omega t \pm kx)}$$

$$\frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2} (Ae^{j(\omega t \pm kx)}) = (j\omega)^2 Ae^{j(\omega t \pm kx)} = -\omega^2 Ae^{j(\omega t \pm kx)} \quad (11)$$

When these are substituted into the wave equation;

$$(-k^2)Ae^{j(\omega t \pm kx)} - \frac{1}{c^2}(-\omega^2)Ae^{j(\omega t \pm kx)} = 0$$

$$-k^2 + \frac{\omega^2}{c^2} = 0 \quad (12)$$

Since $\omega = \frac{\omega}{c}$;

$$-\left(\frac{\omega}{c}\right)^2 + \frac{\omega^2}{c^2} = 0$$

$$0 = 0$$

This confirms that the complex exponential form is a valid solution.

The sum of any two solutions is a solution as the wave equation is linear. The superposition of a forward-moving wave (p^+) and a backward-moving wave (p^-) is the general solution for a one-dimensional plane wave.

The forward-moving wave is given as follows:

$$p^+(x, t) = p^+ e^{j(\omega t - kx)} \quad (13)$$

The backward-moving wave is given as follows:

$$p^-(x, t) = p^- e^{j(\omega t + kx)} \quad (14)$$

These two waves add up to the total acoustic pressure:

$$p(x, t) = p^+ e^{j(\omega t - kx)} + p^- e^{j(\omega t + kx)} \quad (15)$$

1.2. Acoustic Attenuation

The acoustic attenuation formula explains how the energy of a sound wave decreases as it passes through a material [9]. The two main physical processes responsible for this energy loss are absorption and scattering. An exponential attenuation model for the amplitude or intensity of the sound wave is the most used method to describe this attenuation. The traditional formula is generally expressed as follows [9]:

$$A(x) = A_0 e^{-2\alpha x} \quad (16)$$

Here, after traveling a distance x , the amplitude of the wave is denoted by $A(x)$. The initial, undiminished amplitude of the wave is denoted by A_0 . The distance traveled by the wave is denoted by x . The acoustic attenuation coefficient is denoted by α . The value of α , which is usually measured in decibels per meter (dB/m) or Naper per meter (Np/m), depends on the frequency of the sound wave and the properties of the medium.

There are multiple physical parameters that determine the weighting factor (α), and it is not a single value. The two fundamental absorption mechanisms in fluids, viscosity and heat transfer, are considered in the “classical” view sometimes attributed to the Stokes-Kirchhoff formula [10]. According to this view;

Loss of Viscosity:

- The particles in the environment oscillate back and forth, producing sound waves.
- Viscosity is the “internal friction” of a fluid or its resistance to shear movement.
- This internal friction causes part of the sound energy to be converted into heat as the particles vibrate.
- When fluid particles adhere to narrow channels or walls near solid boundaries, a viscous boundary layer emerges, causing significant kinetic energy loss due to friction.

Heat Transfer

- Compressions and rarefactions occurring during the propagation of a sound wave cause small, localized temperature changes. Rarefied areas become cooler, while compressed areas become hotter.
- The warmer, compressed areas transfer heat to the rarefied, cooler areas.
- The amplitude of the sound wave decreases due to this heat loss movement, which converts part of the organized energy into random thermal energy.

In addition to these two classical mechanisms, total attenuation may also include:

Molecular relaxation: It is the process by which molecules in gases such as air temporarily absorb sound energy and use it to change their internal states, such as vibration or rotation. This energy is then released as heat, further weakening the effect. Frequency, temperature, and humidity have a significant impact on this process.

Scattering: When a sound wave passes through a heterogeneous material, such as a porous rock or a liquid containing suspended particles, it can be reflected or scattered in many directions. This reduces the intensity of the primary propagation by redirecting its energy. This plays an important role in materials such as porous rocks or biological tissues.

Acoustic impedance is generally treated as a complex quantity and contains both amplitude and phase information. It has two fundamental components [11]:

1. Real part (resistive component): It is related to the medium's capacity to absorb sound energy.
2. Imaginary part (reactive component): It indicates the medium's capacity to store sound energy (elastic or inertial behavior).

The average acoustic intensity over time expresses the average energy flux carried by a sound wave along a specific direction over a specific time interval [12]. This quantity is used to quantitatively determine the intensity and direction of the energy carried by sound waves passing through a point in space.

This intensity is generally defined for sinusoidal (harmonic) waves as follows:

$$\vec{I}_{avg} = \frac{1}{T} \int_{t_0}^{t_0+T} p(t) \cdot \vec{v}(t) dt \quad (17)$$

\vec{I}_{avg} : Time-averaged acoustic intensity vector (W/m²),

$p(t)$: Sound pressure that changes over time (Pa),

$\vec{v}(t)$: Particle velocity changing over time (m/s),

T: Average time interval (s),

t_0 : Initial time

This definition preserves the vector nature of energy flow; that is, it includes not only magnitude but also direction.

When a sound wave propagates through air, its intensity gradually decreases due to various attenuation mechanisms such as geometric propagation, viscous losses, thermal conduction, and molecular absorption [13]. The decrease in acoustic intensity I with propagation distance x can generally be expressed by an exponential attenuation function:

$$I(x) = I_0 e^{-2\alpha x} \quad (18)$$

$I(x)$ is the sound intensity at position x along the pipe, I_0 is the initial sound intensity at the source (i.e., at position ($x=0$)), and α is the acoustic absorption (attenuation) coefficient (measured in m^{-1}). This coefficient considers how the viscosity of the air (humidity), heat transfer, temperature, frequency, and molecular relaxation attenuate the waves. This exponential relationship shows that higher frequencies experience greater attenuation, primarily due to the molecular relaxation processes of oxygen and nitrogen.

2. Sound transmission in a cylindrical pipe

We begin by establishing the necessary mathematical foundations. Let $(\mathcal{H}, \langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle)$ be a Hilbert space and consider the operator $T: \mathcal{H} \rightarrow \mathcal{H}$ defined above. Under the Hilbert-Schmidt condition, the operator T is compact and belongs to the Schatten class $\mathcal{S}_2(\mathcal{H})$.

3. Results and Discussion

Sound waves traveling through confined air environments such as cylindrical pipes also lose part of their energy as a result of various attenuation mechanisms. This attenuation is primarily due to viscous friction, heat transfer, wall friction, and molecular absorption effects [14].

When sound propagates in a cylindrical pipe instead of free space, attenuation is affected not only by the properties of the medium but also by the interaction with the pipe walls. In this case, the total attenuation coefficient α_t consists of both molecular absorption α_m and wall losses α_w components:

$$\alpha_t = \alpha_m + \alpha_w \quad (19)$$

Many factors, such as the wave's frequency, initial power, and propagation path length, affect the intensity of a sound wave over a certain distance as it passes through a straight pipe [15]. When reflection, turbulence, or wall friction is minimal or absent, the primary process reducing intensity is absorption by the medium, which is typically air. This absorption causes the power to decrease

exponentially with distance, which can be mathematically explained using the traditional acoustic attenuation formula.

These theoretical foundations demonstrate that, despite frequency and phase velocity being conserved quantities, dissipative (energy-consuming) mechanisms cause significant changes in amplitude and intensity throughout propagation. Therefore, to effectively predict acoustic energy transmission and design acoustic systems, it is crucial to understand the attenuation of amplitude, especially in pipes with rough inner walls at the micrometer scale [16].

The energy of sound waves is represented by the sound intensity (I), which is the acoustic power density traveling across a unit area per unit time. This is because sound waves are pressure waves that are caused by the periodic compression and rarefaction of the particles in the medium. The intensity (or density) expression is proportional to the square of the pressure amplitude [17].

For a planar sound wave, the instantaneous sound intensity $I(t)$ is equal to the product of the instantaneous sound pressure $p(t)$ and the particle velocity $v(t)$.

$$I(t) = p(t)v(t) \quad (20)$$

Since sound waves are periodic, the average intensity I is generally considered. When averaged over a full period, the average sound intensity is given by equation 17 as follows.

$$\bar{I}_{avg} = \frac{1}{T} \int_{t_0}^{t_0+T} p(t) \cdot \vec{v}(t)$$

Since there is no phase difference between sound pressure and particle velocity in linear acoustics (particularly for plane waves), equation 3 provides the following relationship between the two quantities.

$$v(t) = \frac{p(t)}{\rho c}$$

If this relationship is substituted into the above equation:

$$I = \frac{1}{\rho c} \langle p^2(t) \rangle \quad (21)$$

If the pressure wave is sinusoidal, that is, if it is of the form $p(t) = p_0 \sin(\omega t)$, then the average value is as follows.

$$\langle p^2(t) \rangle = \frac{p_0^2}{2} \quad (22)$$

Therefore, the average sound intensity:

$$I = \frac{1}{\rho c} \langle p^2(t) \rangle = \frac{p_0^2}{2\rho c} \quad (23)$$

If the pressure amplitude of a sound wave in a cylindrical tube decay as $p(x) = p_0 e^{-\alpha x}$, then the intensity is proportional to the square of this amplitude:

$$I(x) \propto p^2(x)$$

$$I(x) \propto (p_0 e^{-\alpha x})^2 \quad (24)$$

Equation 14 describes the acoustic pressure of a plane wave in a lossless medium. This is the first step in obtaining the Acoustic Pressure Wave Equation with attenuation.

$$p(x, t) = p^+ e^{j(\omega t - kx)} + p^- e^{j(\omega t + kx)}$$

On the other hand, wave amplitude decreases exponentially as it passes through an attenuated medium. This is described using the complex wave number, and the attenuation is explained by the imaginary part $-\alpha$.

The modified pressure wave equation for a wave moving in the positive x direction is as follows:

$$p(x, t) = p_0 e^{-\alpha x} e^{j(\omega t - kx)} \quad (25)$$

Here, x is the distance from the source, ω is the angular frequency, k is the wave number, t is the time, p_0 is the initial pressure amplitude, and α is the attenuation coefficient. The attenuation factor responsible for the amplitude's reduction with distance is $e^{-\alpha x}$.

4. Modeling

4.1. Sound Transmission in a Rough Tube with Micrometer-Sized Roughness

Because of additional friction effects brought on by surface roughness as well as viscous and thermal losses on the pipe walls, sound waves propagating inside a pipe lose intensity. On interior surfaces that are rough at the micrometer level, this condition is more apparent. Between the sound intensity I at the outflow and the sound intensity I_0 at the entrance, there is a drop in sound intensity.

During the propagation of sound waves, the intensity is directly proportional to the pressure amplitude and is expressed as follows:

The equation used to mathematically express how much the intensity of a sound wave decreases after passing through a pipe with micron-sized roughness on its inner surface is as follows, as given in equation (17):

$$I = I_0 e^{-2\alpha_{eff} x} \quad (26)$$

Here, α_{eff} , the effective acoustic absorption (attenuation) coefficient, depends not only on the attenuation coefficient given in equation (18) for the roughness constant of the pipe inner surface, but also on the sound frequency f , the pipe diameter (R), and the roughness constant k of the pipe inner surface [18]. In pipes with smooth surfaces, the attenuation coefficient consists of viscous and thermal losses:

$$\alpha_v = \sqrt{\frac{\pi f \mu}{\rho c^2 R^2}} \quad (27)$$

Here, μ is the kinematic viscosity of the medium (air or other gas). If micron-sized roughness is present inside the pipe, an additional damping term α_r is considered. This term is proportional to the roughness height ε and the roughness constant k_r .

$$\alpha_r = k_r \left(\frac{\varepsilon}{R}\right)^n f^m \quad (28)$$

In the literature, it is observed that terms related to surface roughness and scattering-induced attenuation (such as ε/a^2) involve quadratic dependencies, and in engineering-scale models, such terms are typically parameterized with an approximate constant force (~ 1). Therefore, experimentally, $n \approx 1$ and $m \approx 0.5 - 1$ are typically taken [19, 20, 21, 22]. Total effective attenuation coefficient:

$$\alpha_{eff} = \alpha_v + \alpha_r \quad (29)$$

In this case, the sound intensity I at the other end of the pipe is expressed by the following general equation:

$$I = I_0 \exp \left[-2x \left(\sqrt{\frac{\pi f \mu}{\rho c^2 R^2}} + k_r \left(\frac{\varepsilon}{R}\right)^n f^m \right) \right] \quad (30)$$

Here;

I , Sound intensity at the outlet of the pipe (intensity at distance x).

I_0 , Sound intensity at the inlet of the pipe (intensity at distance $x=0$).

x , Length of the pipe.

f , Sound frequency.

μ , Kinematic viscosity of the medium (air or other gas).

ρ , Density of the medium inside the pipe.

c , The speed of sound in the medium.

R , The radius of the pipe.

k_r , The roughness constant.

ε , The roughness height.

$$n \approx 1 \text{ and } m \approx 0.5 - 1$$

According to this equation;

- As frequency increases, both viscosity- and roughness-induced attenuation increases.
- As the pipe radius decreases, the boundary layer effect strengthens, and energy loss increases.
- As roughness height increases, wave scattering increases and intensity loss accelerates.
- As pipe length increases, total loss grows exponentially.

5. Conclusions

This study theoretically investigated the changes in the amplitude of acoustic waves propagating within a cylindrical pipe with a micron-sized roughened inner surface. The study mathematically modeled viscous and thermal losses, as well as additional attenuation effects caused by roughness, using classical acoustic wave equations along with continuity and Euler equations.

The results obtained show that the amplitude and intensity of the acoustic wave are directly related to the magnitude of the roughness on the inner surface of the tube, the roughness constant, the tube radius, the sound frequency, and the physical properties of the medium. Particularly on surfaces with micron-level roughness, a significant energy loss occurs in addition to the classical viscous and thermal attenuation terms, due to the boundary layer effect and the contribution of local micro-turbulence. This causes an exponential decrease in the pressure amplitude of acoustic waves, leading to a significant reduction in sound intensity from the inlet to the outlet.

As a result, as the roughness of the pipe's inner surface increases, the efficiency of sound transmission decreases. At high frequencies, roughness has a far greater impact than at low frequencies, when

attenuation is still minimal. Furthermore, as the pipe radius decreases, boundary layer effects become dominant, leading to a significant reduction in acoustic energy transport, particularly in microchannel-sized systems.

These findings reveal that acoustic wave propagation analyses in micron-scale fluid systems must be evaluated not only with classical viscous and thermal losses but also with surface roughness parameters.

This study makes an important contribution to the literature by theoretically and analytically demonstrating the effects of surface roughness on acoustic wave propagation.

Including the additional attenuation term (α_r) caused by micron-scale roughness in the classical Stokes-Kirchhoff approach allows microgeometric effects to be considered in acoustic modeling. In this respect, it can be said that the study establishes a theoretical reference model in both microfluidic systems and acoustic sensor design.

Future Work and Areas for Expansion

This theoretical study can be expanded in the following directions in the future:

1. Experimental Validation:

Experimental validation can be performed using acoustic measurement systems to measure sound attenuation in micron-scale rough pipes. This validation allows for the calibration of theoretical model parameters (e.g., roughness constant and coefficients).

2. Numerical Simulations (CFD, FEM, and COMSOL):

The effect of rough walls on acoustic waves can be examined in three dimensions using finite element (FEM) or computational fluid dynamics (CFD) methods. This allows for more accurate modeling of micro-scale boundary layer behavior and local acoustic scattering mechanisms.

3. Different Fluid Environments:

Performing similar analyses not only in air but also in gas mixtures or liquid environments can demonstrate how attenuation coefficients change depending on the thermodynamic properties of the medium.

4. Different Geometries:

Investigating square, elliptical, or variable-section microchannels can contribute to understanding the geometric effects of roughness on wave propagation.

5. Frequency Range and Acoustic Resonance:

The effect of roughness under high-frequency acoustic waves and resonance conditions can be examined in detail in terms of both attenuation and phase shift.

Potential Application Areas

The theoretical findings obtained have direct application potential in the following engineering and technology fields:

1. Microfluidic systems: Calculation of energy losses due to roughness in acoustic pumping and acoustic mixing applications in microchannels.

2. Acoustic sensor and microphone technologies: Predicting the effect of rough internal surfaces on sensor sensitivity.

3. Ultrasonic propulsion systems: Determining the role of micron-scale surface roughness on sound transmission efficiency.

4. Biomedical devices: Design optimization in terms of acoustic wave transmission and energy focusing on the target in microchannel systems carrying blood or gas.

5. Industrial acoustic measurement systems: Detection of pipe inner surface conditions using acoustic diagnostic methods (e.g., sensor-based monitoring of signal attenuation caused by roughness).

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Measurement of Radon Gas in the Vicinity of the Adalar Segment of the North Anatolian Fault

Ali Beyaz¹, Caner Yalçın¹, Ezgi Tantoğlu¹, Osman Günay²

¹Department of Physics, Kocaeli University, 41001, Kocaeli, TÜRKİYE

²Department of Biomedical Engineering, Yıldız Technical University, 34220 Istanbul, Turkey

Corresponding author: caner.yalcin@kocaeli.edu.tr

ORCID IDs:

First Author: [0009-0007-2927-2279](https://orcid.org/0009-0007-2927-2279)

Second Author: [0000-0002-3105-7267](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3105-7267)

Third Author: [0009-0009-4905-5735](https://orcid.org/0009-0009-4905-5735)

Fourth Author: [0000-0003-0760-554X](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0760-554X)

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Abstract

The prediction of seismic events encompasses a range of parameters, including magnitude, geographical location, and temporal considerations. While the determination of location and magnitude can be made to a certain degree in the present, temporal predictions must be expressed in long intervals. This underscores the critical importance of short-term prediction. A substantial body of research has identified a correlation between variations in radon gas concentrations, both prior to and following seismic events, and seismic activity. A major earthquake is anticipated in the Adalar and Avcılar segments of the North Anatolian Fault, situated within the Sea of Marmara (a region previously impacted by the 1912 Ganos and 1999 Kocaeli earthquakes).

In this study, radon concentration and temperature, humidity, and pressure data were collected in a continuous manner. This data was collected using a station that was to be established on the Anatolian plate in the Adalar segment. The relationship between radon anomalies and earthquakes was investigated using these data. The cause of the radon anomalies that occurred was determined, and their relationship with geological activity was analyzed. The rise in radon concentration that began on August 11, 2024, and persisted until the 15 August 2024, 06:20 magnitude 3.8 earthquake in Mudanya, Bursa, has been linked to the seismic event.

Keywords: Soil radon concentration, Earthquake, Alpha guard radon monitor.

1. Introduction and Motivation

According to the prevailing methodology for identifying precursors to earthquakes, the utilization of any physical or geochemical parameter in earthquake prediction is contingent upon the manifestation of continuous and reproducible anomalies in seismically active regions prior to seismic events [1]. In this context, a range of parameters representing diverse physical processes have been evaluated in earthquake prediction studies. Among geochemical parameters, soil gas emissions, particularly radon (Rn-222), are among the most commonly studied variables as earthquake precursors [2,3]. Radon (Rn)

is a radioactive noble gas that is chemically inert and has a half-life of 3.8 days. It is formed by the decay of ^{226}Ra , which is found in soil and rock [4]. Its capacity to be transported through diffusion and convection along cracks in rocks, fault zones, and porous environments renders radon a sensitive tracer of seismotectonic processes. Consequently, radon gas has become a prevalent method for the observation of stress-strain processes within the Earth's crust, particularly in active fault zones, geothermal fields, and seismic regions [5,6].

In this study, continuous radon measurements were taken at a depth of 1 meter in Yalova, Türkiye between July 23, 2024, and December 23, 2024, along with meteorological parameters. The relationship between meteorological data and radon was observed, and the effects of earthquakes greater than magnitude 3 that occurred during this period on radon concentration were investigated.

2. Material and Methods

The radon measurement station utilized in this study is situated in Yalova (40.651187°N, 29.225013°E), which is located in a seismically active region of the Marmara Region. The surface geology of the study area is characterized by a sandy-loamy structure, which renders the area particularly conducive to soil-gas radon studies due to its relatively high gas permeability. Radon measurements were performed at a depth of 1 meter using a soil gas probe compatible with the AlphaGUARD radon monitor. This measurement geometry enables direct observation of the soil gas regime, independent of surface ventilation and indoor environment effects.

Seismic activity data is comprised of earthquakes occurring within a radius of 100 km from the measuring station. In the course of the evaluation, events with magnitude information available in the earthquake catalog were included, and an $M \geq 3.0$ threshold was used in the analyses. The temporal parameters of seismic occurrences, including time of day, magnitude, and geographical location, were meticulously matched with radon time series for the purpose of comparison.

The notion of an earthquake preparedness zone was initially delineated in 1979 by Russian scientist Ilya Dobrovolsky and his associates [7]. This concept refers to a spatial area that is tectonically stressed and where precursor processes associated with an impending earthquake can be observed. It has been posited that alterations in the physical and chemical parameters of groundwater (level, flow rate, ionic composition, and temperature), irregularities in the Earth's magnetic field, various gas emissions, and analogous geophysical and geochemical anomalies may occur within this zone. Dobrovolsky and colleagues proposed the following empirical relationship for the radius, which varies depending on the moment magnitude of the earthquake, in order to define the characteristic size of the earthquake preparation zone:

$$R=10^{0.43M} \quad (1)$$

where R represents the radius of the earthquake preparation zone (km) and M represents the magnitude of the earthquake.

3. Results and Discussion

During the measurement period, a total of three earthquakes with a magnitude of $M \geq 3.0$ were recorded within a 100 km radius area centered on the measurement station. The temporal, spatial, and seismological parameters of these earthquakes, along with the radius of the impact area for each earthquake and the hypocenter distances from the measurement station, are presented in detail in Table 1. A thorough examination of Table 1 indicates that only one of these earthquakes (occurring on August 15, 2024, at 3:20:31 a.m.) is situated within the designated earthquake impact area, as delineated by the established magnitude-distance relationship. The epicenter location of the earthquake is illustrated in Figure 1. Consequently, the direct seismic effect on radon concentration observations made at the measuring station is assessed to be limited (with the exception of the earthquake on

August 15, 2024, at 03:20:31). It is concluded that the observed radon changes are predominantly influenced by local geological conditions and meteorological parameters.

Table 1. Earthquakes with a magnitude greater than 3 were recorded during the measurement period.

Time	M	Latitude	Longitude	Depth (km)	Location	Dobrovolsky R (km)	Hypocenter Distance (km)
2024-08-03 02:05:35	4.2	39.8697	28.7602	6.3	Gazioluk-Orhaneli (Bursa)	64	95.4
2024-08-15 03:20:31	3.8	40.3943	28.9335	12.1	Mudanya (Bursa)	43	37.7
2024-11-05 12:00:00	3.3	40.4007	28.8472	5.8	Kumyaka-Mudanya (Bursa)	26	42.4

Fig. 1. The epicenter of the seismic event that took place on August 15th, 2024, at 3:20:31 a.m., was located at Mudanya, Bursa. The measuring station is located at the center of the blue circles.

The radon concentration obtained during the measurement period and the simultaneous meteorological parameters (temperature, relative humidity, and atmospheric pressure) are presented in Figure 2 along with their temporal variations. A thorough examination of Figure 2 reveals a discernible diurnal fluctuation in radon concentrations. However, it has been observed that radon concentration displays an inverse relationship with temperature and a parallel relationship with atmospheric pressure and relative humidity. To quantitatively evaluate these relationships, the linear relationship between radon and meteorological variables was calculated using the Pearson correlation coefficient. The results are presented in Table 2. In addition, fundamental statistical analyses were conducted on the data set to ascertain its general characteristics. These analyses included the calculation of the mean, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum values, among others. The results of these analyses are comprehensively outlined in Table 3.

Fig.2. Time series of (a) soil-gas ²²²Rn concentration measured at 1 m depth, (b) air temperature, (c) air pressure, and (d) relative humidity recorded simultaneously by the AlphaGUARD monitoring system. Vertical dashed lines indicate earthquakes with magnitudes $M \geq 3$ occurring within 100 km of the monitoring station.

Table 2. Pearson correlation coefficients for radon and meteorological data.

	Radon	Temperature	Humidity	Pressure
Radon	1	-0.659	0.393	0.47
Temperature	-0.659	1	-0.725	-0.693
Humidity	0.393	-0.725	1	0.33
Pressure	0.47	-0.693	0.33	1

Table3. Fundamental statistical analysis of radon and meteorological data

	Count	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max	Variance	Skewness	Kurtosis
Radon(kBq/m³)	2950	24.136	12.467	10.007	55.808	155.414	0.47	-0.685
Temperature (°C)	2950	24.244	6.115	11.067	37.433	37.399	-0.221	-1.058
Humidity (%)	2950	61.224	8.07	35.833	82	65.129	-0.084	-0.166
Pressure (mbar)	2950	1014.076	6.767	998.783	1031.85	45.791	0.713	-0.256

Pearson correlation analysis was applied to quantitatively evaluate the linear relationships between radon concentration and meteorological parameters. The correlation coefficients obtained are presented in Table 2. The analysis results indicate a moderate negative correlation ($r=-0.659$) between radon concentration and temperature. This finding suggests that gas transport mechanisms undergo changes in response to variations in temperature within surface and shallow subsurface environments. These changes can be associated with the weakening of convective transport with increasing temperature or alterations in permeability resulting from increased soil moisture. A positive yet relatively weak correlation ($r=0.393$) was observed between radon and relative humidity, while a moderate positive relationship ($r=0.470$) was found between atmospheric pressure and radon concentration. This phenomenon aligns with the barometric pumping effect, a widely documented phenomenon in the relevant literature. The barometric pumping effect posits that alterations in atmospheric pressure exert an influence on radon release, accomplished through the modulation of soil gas flow. Conversely, the strong correlations among meteorological parameters (e.g., the negative relationships between temperature–humidity and temperature–pressure) reveal the interdependent nature of these variables and underscore the necessity of multivariate analyses.

The fundamental descriptive statistics conducted to elucidate the general distribution characteristics and statistical nature of the data set are summarized in Table 3. A total of 2950 data points were obtained during the measurement period, and the average value of radon concentration was calculated as 24.14 kBq/m³, with a standard deviation of 12.47 kBq/m³. The minimum and maximum values of the radon distribution were 10.01 kBq/m³ and 55.81 kBq/m³, respectively, indicating significant temporal variability. The positive skewness (skewness = 0.47) and negative kurtosis (kurtosis = -0.685) values of the distribution indicate that radon concentrations deviate from a normal distribution and that high values are observed with greater frequency. The statistical characteristics of radon data suggest that they are susceptible to extreme values, necessitating the use of robust statistical approaches in addition to classical parametric methods.

A subsequent examination of the descriptive statistics of meteorological parameters reveals that the distributions of temperature and relative humidity are relatively symmetric, while the atmospheric pressure distribution exhibits a slight positive skewness. When evaluated in conjunction with the distribution characteristics of radon data, these results statistically substantiate the implementation of multivariate and machine learning-based anomaly detection methods to reliably discern potential radon anomalies independent of meteorological effects.

4. Conclusions

In this study, continuous soil-gas ²²²Rn measurements and simultaneous meteorological observations were evaluated in a seismically active area of the Marmara Region over a five-month period. During the monitoring interval, three earthquakes with magnitudes $M \geq 3.0$ occurred within a 100 km radius of the measurement station. However, only one event was located within the earthquake preparation zone as defined by the Dobrovolsky empirical relationship. In conclusion, the probability of a direct seismic effect on the recorded radon time series was negligible, and no significant change in radon that could be definitively attributed to seismic activity was considered. Only the increase in radon concentration between August 11, 2024, and August 15, 2024, was assessed as potentially related to the magnitude 3.8 earthquake that occurred in Mudanya, Bursa.

The temporal behavior of radon concentrations exhibited a discernible diurnal pattern, suggesting a notable sensitivity to near-surface environmental conditions. Correlation analysis revealed a moderately systematic relationship between radon variability and meteorological parameters, particularly temperature and atmospheric pressure. This finding aligns with established soil gas transport mechanisms, such as barometric pumping. These findings underscore the critical importance of accounting for meteorological forcing when interpreting radon time series, particularly in the context of short- to medium-term monitoring studies.

Descriptive statistical analysis further indicated that radon data exhibit non-normal distribution characteristics and substantial temporal variability, which complicates the identification of subtle anomalies potentially related to tectonic processes. In consideration of the constraints imposed by the current dataset, the findings indicate that the variations in radon observed at the station are primarily influenced by local environmental factors. Consequently, the implementation of extended monitoring periods, in conjunction with multivariate and robust statistical methodologies, is imperative to ensure the reliable evaluation of the potential role of soil-gas radon as a precursor signal within this specific region.

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Design and Thermal Analysis of a Target for Simultaneous ^{152}Tb / ^{155}Tb Production via Alpha Induced Reactions

Caner YALÇIN¹, Recep Taygun GÜRAY¹

¹*Department of Physics, Kocaeli University, 41001, Kocaeli, TÜRKİYE*

Corresponding author: caner.yalcin@kocaeli.edu.tr

ORCID IDs:

First Author: [0000-0002-3105-7267](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3105-7267)

Second Author: [0000-0002-5481-9981](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5481-9981)

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Abstract

A considerable body of research has recently been devoted to the investigation of terbium radioisotopes and their potential for use in both therapeutic and diagnostic applications in the field of nuclear medicine. While experimental studies have commenced, the necessary information for the commercial production of Terbium isotopes in accelerators has yet to be obtained. In this study, a target design was proposed for the simultaneous production of ^{152}Tb and ^{155}Tb isotopes using enriched Europium targets. The thermal analysis of this design was performed according to different accelerator parameters. Consequently, the cooling requirements necessary for optimal isotopic fraction and activation were calculated, and the practical limits of the target design were determined.

Keywords: Tb-152, Tb-155, Target Design, Alpha Induced Reactions.

1. Introduction

The increasing adoption of theranostic concepts in nuclear medicine has stimulated significant interest in radionuclides that can support both diagnostic imaging and targeted therapy within a single chemical framework. In this regard, radiolanthanides have emerged as particularly promising candidates due to their advantageous nuclear decay properties and well-established coordination chemistry [1,5]. Of these elements, terbium merits particular attention due to its distinctive property of yielding a series of isotopes that are well-suited for positron emission tomography (PET), single-photon emission computed tomography (SPECT), and radionuclide therapy. This characteristic facilitates the implementation of matched diagnostic and therapeutic applications, exhibiting identical pharmacokinetics [2,3].

The diagnostic terbium isotopes ^{152}Tb and ^{155}Tb have been the focus of extensive research in recent years. ^{152}Tb , a positron emitter, has demonstrated high-quality PET imaging capability, while ^{155}Tb , a gamma emitter, is well suited for SPECT imaging [2,6]. Preclinical studies have demonstrated the efficacy of incorporating these isotopes into DOTA-based radiopharmaceuticals, facilitating high-

contrast and specific imaging of tumor models [2]. These encouraging results underscore the clinical potential of terbium-based radiopharmaceuticals and underscore the necessity for further efforts to ensure their reliable and routine production.

Despite this growing interest, the widespread clinical application of terbium radioisotopes is currently constrained by limitations in their production routes. Reactor-based methods are suitable for certain isotopes, such as ^{161}Tb [3]. However, the production of ^{152}Tb and ^{155}Tb relies predominantly on charged-particle induced reactions in accelerator facilities. A number of production pathways involving proton-, deuteron-, and alpha-induced reactions on gadolinium and europium targets have been explored both experimentally and theoretically [7–12]. Among these, alpha-induced reactions on enriched europium targets have been identified as a promising option, offering favorable cross sections and the possibility of producing isotopes with high radionuclide purity [11,12].

The majority of extant studies on terbium isotope production have primarily focused on reaction cross sections, excitation functions, and achievable yields under idealized irradiation conditions. Nevertheless, for pragmatic and sustainable manufacturing, target-related limitations—particularly those associated with beam-induced heating—exert a pivotal influence. The utilization of high-intensity alpha beams during the process can result in significant power deposition within the target material, potentially leading to undesirable consequences such as excessive temperature rise, target degradation, and reduced isotopic purity. These effects impose strict limits on beam current, irradiation time, and target thickness, and therefore must be carefully assessed when designing production targets for medical applications.

Motivated by these considerations, the present work proposes a target design based on enriched europium for the simultaneous production of ^{152}Tb and ^{155}Tb isotopes. A detailed thermal analysis is performed under different accelerator parameters to evaluate heat deposition and cooling requirements, building upon established nuclear reaction data and production routes [11,12]. The objective of this study is to ascertain the operational limits of the target system and to identify the conditions necessary for stable and efficient irradiation. This study aims to bridge the gap between nuclear reaction studies and the practical realization of accelerator-based terbium isotope production for nuclear medicine.

2. Material and Methods

In a previous study, the cross sections of ^{152}Tb and ^{155}Tb , as well as the accelerator parameters required for isotope production with high isotopic yield, were examined in detail [13]. According to the findings of this study, the most favorable production conditions for ^{152}Tb are obtained using an enriched ^{151}Eu target irradiated with alpha particles in the high-energy region. According to the calculations, an incident beam energy of 50 MeV combined with a target thickness corresponding to an exit energy of 34 MeV provides an optimal balance between activity yield and isotopic fraction. In such conditions, the production of ^{152}Tb can be achieved with an isotopic fraction of approximately 83% and an activity of approximately 395 MBq per μA for an irradiation time of 8 hours. Despite the proposal of lower incident energies, such as 42 MeV, in the extant literature, the higher-energy configuration results in a substantial increase in produced activity while maintaining comparable radionuclide purity.

For the production of ^{155}Tb , the optimal conditions are found at lower alpha-particle energies when using an enriched ^{153}Eu target. An incident energy of 31 MeV with a beam exit energy of 17 MeV has been demonstrated to yield the highest isotopic fraction, reaching approximately 90%, while producing an activity of 37.3 MBq at a beam current of 1 μA for an 8-hour irradiation. The analysis indicates that elevating the beam energy beyond this range leads to a gradual decline in the ^{155}Tb isotopic fraction, attributable to the emergence of competing reaction channels. Consequently, lower-energy irradiation is recommended for ^{155}Tb to maintain radionuclide purity, despite the lower achievable activity in comparison to ^{152}Tb .

Table 1. Optimum Production Parameters for ^{152}Tb and ^{155}Tb , for 1 μA current and 8 h irradiation time

Isotope	Target	Reaction	Beam Type	Incident Energy (MeV)	Exit Energy (MeV)	Isotopic Fraction (%)	Activity (MBq/ μA)
^{152}Tb	^{151}Eu	$^{151}\text{Eu}(\alpha,3n)^{152}\text{Tb}$	α	50	34	~83	395
^{155}Tb	^{153}Eu	$^{153}\text{Eu}(\alpha,2n)^{155}\text{Tb}$	α	31	17	~90	37.3

Consequently, a target design can be formulated, as illustrated in Figure 1, to produce both isotopes concurrently. The thermal performance of the proposed sandwich target was evaluated under continuous α -particle irradiation using a steady-state heat transfer approach. The target geometry comprised three planar layers, with an effective beam area of 1 cm^2 , including a 0.26 mm thick ^{151}Eu layer, a 0.82 mm aluminum energy degrader layer, and a 0.16 mm thick ^{153}Eu layer. The experiment involved the utilization of a monoenergetic 50 MeV α -beam, which was assumed to impinge normally on the target. It was further postulated that the energy of the beam would undergo degradation to 17 MeV upon exiting the final layer [14]. The deposited beam energy within each layer was treated as volumetric heat generation. The beam energies were 16 MeV in ^{151}Eu , 3 MeV in Al, and 14 MeV in ^{153}Eu . The beam energies were uniformly distributed over the layer volumes. The total absorbed power exhibited a linear relationship with the beam current, resulting in an approximate value of 16.5 W per μA of incident α -beam current. The assumption of one-dimensional heat conduction across the target thickness is supported by the relatively small layer thicknesses in comparison to the lateral dimensions of the irradiated area. The estimation of temperature gradients within the individual layers was conducted using Fourier's law, with thermal conductivities of 14 $\text{Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ for europium and 200 $\text{Wm}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ for aluminum.

Fig. 1. Schematic illustration of the proposed sandwich target design for simultaneous ^{152}Tb and ^{155}Tb production.

The dissipation of heat from the target's posterior surface was modeled through the utilization of forced convection, directing heat towards a water-cooled aluminum structure. The convective boundary condition was expressed through the use of a heat transfer coefficient, denoted h . This coefficient is defined by the following equation: $q''=h(T_s-T_w)$ is the surface heat flux, T_s is the solid surface temperature, and T_w is the coolant temperature. For turbulent water flow in millimeter-scale cooling channels, a representative value of $h\approx 1\times 10^4 \text{ Wm}^{-2}\text{K}^{-1}$ was adopted, consistent with Reynolds-number-based correlations for forced convection. A series of parametric calculations were conducted, encompassing beam currents ranging from 1 to 10 μA . This was undertaken to assess several critical parameters, including the surface temperature rise, the internal temperature gradients within the europium layers, and the resulting heat flux at the solid–fluid interface. The calculated heat fluxes were then compared against the typical critical heat flux limits for water cooling. This comparison was used to identify practical operating boundaries and to ensure that the target operates well below boiling-induced thermal instabilities under the proposed irradiation conditions.

3. Results and Discussion

The steady-state thermal analysis indicates a linear relationship between the deposited beam power and the incident α -particle current, resulting in an absorbed power of approximately 16.5 W per μA for the proposed $^{151}\text{Eu}/\text{Al}/^{153}\text{Eu}$ sandwich target. For beam currents ranging from 1 to 5 μA , the calculated surface heat flux remains below 1 MWm^{-2} . This is commonly regarded as an upper practical limit for single-phase water cooling in compact accelerator targets. In these conditions, the estimated surface temperature rise relative to the coolant does not exceed $80\text{--}100^\circ\text{C}$ for a convective heat transfer coefficient of $h \approx 1 \times 10^4 \text{ Wm}^{-2}\text{K}^{-1}$. Internal temperature gradients across the individual target layers were found to be modest, with calculated temperature differences of only a few kelvin per μA within the europium layers. These findings reflect the small layer thicknesses and the relatively high thermal conductivity of the aluminum backing. These findings indicate that, within the present range, the target exhibits quasi-isothermal behavior in the beam direction and does not undergo substantial thermally induced mechanical stress.

Table 2. Calculated thermal quantities for the proposed target as a function of α -beam current.

Beam current (μA)	Deposited power (W)	Heat flux q'' (MW m^{-2})	Surface ΔT ($^\circ\text{C}$)	ΔT across Eu layers ($^\circ\text{C}$)
1	16.5	0.17	~ 17	~ 3
3	49.5	0.50	~ 50	~ 9
5	82.5	0.83	~ 83	~ 15
10	165	1.65	~ 165	~ 30

The results of the study indicate that heat conduction within the solid target is not the primary limiting factor. Instead, the thermal bottleneck is governed by heat removal at the solid-coolant interface. As the surface heat flux approaches the typical critical heat flux for water cooling, further increases in beam current result in disproportionately large surface temperature rises, significantly increasing the risk of boiling-induced instabilities.

From an isotope production perspective, the identified thermal limits directly constrain the achievable production yield for both ^{152}Tb and ^{155}Tb . Given that the production rate scales approximately linearly with beam current in the thin-target regime, operation in the $1\text{--}5 \mu\text{A}$ range represents a compromise between maximizing activity yield and maintaining safe thermal conditions. Within this window, the target can sustain continuous irradiation without exceeding conservative thermal limits, while still providing sufficient activity for experimental PET and SPECT applications. Increasing the beam current beyond this range would, in principle, enhance isotope yield. However, the associated surface heat flux would exceed practical limits for single-phase water cooling. Consequently, this would offset the potential gain through increased thermal risk and reduced target lifetime. Consequently, the present analysis suggests that the optimization of ^{152}Tb and ^{155}Tb co-production should prioritize extended irradiation times and improved radiochemical recovery rather than aggressive increases in beam current under the current target geometry.

The thermal analysis presented herein is predicated on a series of simplifying assumptions that ought to be considered during the interpretation of the ensuing results. The deposited beam energy was treated as uniformly distributed volumetric heat generation within each target layer, neglecting the detailed depth-dependent stopping power profile of α -particles. Furthermore, the heat transfer coefficient was assumed to be constant and representative of fully developed turbulent water flow. However, local variations in flow velocity, surface roughness, or the onset of subcooled boiling could modify the effective heat transfer performance. However, the investigation did not explicitly model radiative heat losses and thermally induced mechanical stresses, despite the assumption that their contribution is negligible within the investigated temperature range. Notwithstanding these limitations, the analysis provides a conservative and physically transparent framework for defining practical

operating limits and guiding future refinements. Such refinements may include detailed CFD-coupled simulations or experimental validation under realistic irradiation conditions.

Fig.2. Operating envelope for the proposed target under 50 MeV α -particle irradiation with a 1 cm² beam spot, shown as a function of beam current and convective heat transfer coefficient h . The color scale represents the steady-state surface temperature rise relative to the coolant, while the contour at $\Delta T=100$ °C and the dashed line at $q''=1$ MW m⁻² indicate practical thermal limits defining the safe low- μ A operating regime.

4. Conclusions

In this study, the thermal performance of a sandwich-type ¹⁵¹Eu/Al/¹⁵³Eu target designed for the simultaneous production of ¹⁵²Tb and ¹⁵⁵Tb under α -particle irradiation was systematically evaluated. The steady-state thermal analysis demonstrates that, for beam currents in the low-microampere range, the proposed geometry can safely dissipate the deposited beam power using conventional water cooling, provided that turbulent flow conditions are maintained at the target-coolant interface. For beam currents of up to approximately 5 μ A, the calculated surface heat flux remains below the typical critical heat flux limits for single-phase water cooling, while internal temperature gradients across the europium layers remain modest. These findings suggest that the target operates in a quasi-isothermal regime under practical irradiation conditions and that heat removal at the solid-coolant interface, rather than conduction within the target materials, constitutes the primary thermal constraint.

The analysis further suggests that the achievable isotope production yield is intrinsically coupled to these thermal limits. While higher beam currents would, in principle, increase the production rates of ¹⁵²Tb and ¹⁵⁵Tb, the associated increase in surface heat flux rapidly approaches or exceeds the practical limits of conventional cooling. Consequently, the present target configuration delineates a pragmatic operating window within which dependable irradiation, target integrity, and foreseeable thermal behavior can be assured. Consequently, the optimization of these systems should prioritize factors such as irradiation time, chemical recovery efficiency, and the management of beam profiles, rather than pursuing substantial increases in beam current.

From a target design perspective, the aluminum layer employed as an energy degrader and mechanical support offers favorable thermal conductivity and mechanical robustness; however, it is not necessarily unique or optimal for all operational scenarios. The employment of alternative degrader materials, including copper, graphite, or select refractory metals, has the potential to yield a distinct trade-off between stopping power, thermal conductivity, and induced activation. To illustrate, materials exhibiting higher thermal conductivity than aluminum may serve to reduce local temperature gradients. Conversely, low-Z materials, characterized by their lower stopping power, could potentially enable more precise control over energy degradation while concomitantly reducing parasitic heat deposition. The systematic evaluation of such alternatives, including their thermal, nuclear, and radiochemical implications, represents a logical extension of the present work and may enable higher beam currents or improved long-term target stability without fundamentally altering the overall target concept.

In conclusion, the presented thermal assessment provides a transparent and conservative framework for defining practical operating limits for simultaneous ^{152}Tb and ^{155}Tb production. The results support the feasibility of the proposed target design under realistic irradiation conditions and highlight clear pathways for future optimization through material selection and advanced cooling strategies.

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Numerical Method for Solving Nonlinear Hyperbolic Equation with Unknown Inverse Coefficient under Periodic Constraints

Akbala Yernazar¹, İrem Bağlan², Erman Aslan³

¹*Department of Mathematics, Ahmet Yassawi University, Turkistan, Kazakhstan*

²*Department of Mathematics, Kocaeli University, Kocaeli, TR-41380, Turkey*

³*Department of Mechanical Engineering, Kocaeli University, Kocaeli, TR-41380, Turkey*

Corresponding author: akbalayernazar@gmail.com

ORCID IDs:

First Author: [0000-0002-0068-4954](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0068-4954)

Second Author: [0000-0003-4900-6027](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4900-6027)

Third Author: [0000-0001-8595-6092](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8595-6092)

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Abstract

This paper investigates the inverse problem of determining unknown time-dependent coefficients in a one-dimensional nonlinear hyperbolic equation with periodic boundary conditions. The Finite Difference Method (FDM) together with the Gauss–Seidel iteration is used for numerical computation. Two implicit finite difference schemes, the fully implicit and Crank–Nicolson methods, are applied. A numerical example illustrates the effectiveness of the proposed method. Results show that while both schemes align well with experimental data, the implicit scheme provides higher accuracy with lower absolute and relative errors.

Keywords: inverse problem, nonlinear hyperbolic equation, finite difference method

1. Introduction

Inverse problems play a fundamental role in modern science and engineering, particularly in situations where certain system parameters cannot be measured or computed directly. Their practical significance places them among the most prominent and actively investigated areas of contemporary applied mathematics. Through inverse problem techniques, one can determine essential characteristics of a medium, including wave intensity and propagation velocity, elastic properties, conductivity, electric and magnetic permeability coefficients, as well as the nature and location of inhomogeneities in otherwise inaccessible regions [1–3].

Inverse problems associated with hyperbolic equations are of particular importance in seismology, where they have been extensively studied [4, 5]. The incorporation of non-local boundary conditions, however, significantly complicates both the theoretical analysis and numerical treatment of such problems. A notable example of nonlocal boundary conditions is the use of periodic boundary conditions, which arise in a variety of applications [6–8]. Periodic conditions appear naturally in problems involving cyclic or repetitive phenomena, such as those encountered in lunar theory [9].

In recent years, considerable research effort has focused on inverse coefficient problems for hyperbolic equations, employing a wide range of analytical and numerical methods. Among these approaches, the finite difference method has been frequently adopted and applied in numerous studies [10–13].

In the present study, we investigate an inverse problem of unknown time-dependent coefficient in a one-dimensional nonlinear hyperbolic equation with periodic boundary conditions. For the numerical solution, two different finite-difference schemes—an implicit scheme and the Crank–Nicolson scheme—are applied. The existence, uniqueness, and stability of the analytical solution for this problem have been previously established in [14].

2. Statement of the Problem

Consider a nonlinear hyperbolic equation defined on the domain $D := \{z \in (0, \pi), t \in (0, T)\}$:

$$\mathcal{G}_t - \mathcal{G}_{zz} = \theta(t)f(z, t, \mathcal{G}), \quad (1)$$

with the initial conditions

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{G}(z, 0) &= \varsigma(z), \\ \mathcal{G}_t(z, 0) &= \chi(z), \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

and boundary conditions

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{G}(0, t) &= \mathcal{G}(\pi, t), \\ \mathcal{G}_z(0, t) &= \mathcal{G}_z(\pi, t), \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

as well as the overdetermination condition

$$Y(t) = \int_0^\pi z \mathcal{G}(z, t) dz. \quad (4)$$

Where the functions ς, χ, Y and $f(z, t, \mathcal{G})$ are given functions on $[0, \pi]$ and $\bar{D} \times \{-\infty, \infty\}$, respectively; while the function $\mathcal{G}(z, t)$ and the coefficient $\theta(t)$ are unknown.

Using the Fourier method to solve equations (1)–(4), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{G}(z, t) &= \frac{1}{2} \left(\varsigma_0 + \chi_0 t + \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^t \int_0^\pi (t - \tau) \theta(\tau) f(\xi, \tau, \mathcal{G}) d\xi d\tau \right) \\ &+ \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\varsigma_{ck} \cos 2kt + \frac{\chi_{ck}}{2} \sin 2kt + \frac{1}{\pi k} \int_0^t \int_0^\pi \theta(\tau) f(\xi, \tau, \mathcal{G}) \cos 2k\xi \sin 2k(t - \tau) d\xi d\tau \right) \cos 2kz \\ &+ \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\varsigma_{sk} \cos 2kt + \frac{\chi_{sk}}{2} \sin 2kt + \frac{1}{\pi k} \int_0^t \int_0^\pi \theta(\tau) f(\xi, \tau, \mathcal{G}) \sin 2k\xi \sin 2k(t - \tau) d\xi d\tau \right) \sin 2kz. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

By employing the overdetermination condition (4) together with the solution (5), the inverse coefficient in equations (1)–(4) is determined as shown in (6):

$$\theta(t) = \frac{Y''(t) - \pi \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (2k) \left(\zeta_{sk} \cos 2kt + \frac{\chi_{sk}}{2k} \sin 2kt + \int_0^t \int_0^{\pi} \theta(\tau) f(\xi, \tau, \mathcal{G}) \sin 2k\xi \sin 2k(t-\tau) d\xi d\tau \right)}{\int_0^{\pi} z f(z, t, \mathcal{G}) dz}. \quad (6)$$

Definition 2.1 The problem of finding the pair $\{\theta(t), \mathcal{G}(z, t)\}$ in (1)–(4) will be called an inverse problem.

Definition 2.2 B is called Banach space when the following set

$$\{\mathcal{G}(t)\} = \left\{ \mathcal{G}_0(t), \mathcal{G}_{ck}(t), \mathcal{G}_{sk}(t), k=1, \dots, N : \max_{0 \leq t \leq T} |\mathcal{G}_0(t)| + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\max_{0 \leq t \leq T} |\mathcal{G}_{ck}(t)| + \max_{0 \leq t \leq T} |\mathcal{G}_{sk}(t)| \right) < \infty \right\}$$

of continuous on $[0, T]$ functions satisfying the norm

$$\|\mathcal{G}(t)\| = \max_{0 \leq t \leq T} |\mathcal{G}_0(t)| + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\max_{0 \leq t \leq T} |\mathcal{G}_{ck}(t)| + \max_{0 \leq t \leq T} |\mathcal{G}_{sk}(t)| \right).$$

Theorem 2.1 If the following assumptions satisfy:

A1. $Y(t) \in C^2[0, T]$, $\theta(t) \in C[0, T]$.

A2. $\zeta(z) \in C^1[0, \pi]$, $\chi(z) \in C[0, \pi]$.

A3.1 Let the function $f(z, t, \mathcal{G})$ be continuous to all arguments in $D \times (-\infty, \infty)$ and satisfies the following condition

$$\left| \frac{\partial^{(k)} f(z, t, \mathcal{G})}{\partial z^{(k)}} - \frac{\partial^{(k)} f(z, t, \tilde{\mathcal{G}})}{\partial z^{(k)}} \right| \leq b(z, t) |\mathcal{G} - \tilde{\mathcal{G}}|, k=0, 1, 2,$$

where $b(z, t) \in L_2(D)$, $b(z, t) \geq 0$.

A3.2 $f(z, t, \mathcal{G}) \in C[0, \pi]$, $t \in [0, T]$, $|f(z, t, \mathcal{G})| \leq M$,

A3.3 $\int_0^{\pi} f(z, t, \mathcal{G}) dz \neq 0, \forall t \in [0, T]$.

Then the problem (1)–(4) has a unique solution.

Theorem 2.2 If the assumptions of the theorem 1 be satisfied, then the pair of the solution $(\theta(t), \mathcal{G}(z, t))$ of the problem (1)–(4) is constantly dependent on the input data ζ, χ, Y .

3. Numerical Procedure for the Nonlinear Problem

We develop an iterative algorithm to linearize the problem,

$$\frac{\partial^2 \mathcal{G}^{(n)}}{\partial t^2} = \frac{\partial^2 \mathcal{G}^{(n-1)}}{\partial z^2} + \theta(t) f(z, t, \mathcal{G}^{(n-1)}), \quad (7)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{G}^{(n)}(z,0) &= \zeta(z), \quad z \in [0,\pi], \\ \mathcal{G}_i^{(n)}(z,0) &= \chi(z), \quad z \in [0,\pi], \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{G}^{(n)}(0,t) &= \mathcal{G}^{(n)}(\pi,t), \quad t \in [0,T], \\ \mathcal{G}_z^{(n)}(0,t) &= \mathcal{G}_z^{(n)}(\pi,t) = 0, \quad t \in [0,T]. \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

By setting $\mathcal{G}^{(n)}(z,t) = \omega(z,t)$ and $f(z,t, \mathcal{G}^{(n-1)}) = \tilde{f}(z,t)$, we can express the problem (7)–(9) as a linear problem.

$$\frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial t^2} = \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial z^2} + \theta(t) \tilde{f}(z,t), \quad (z,t) \in D, \quad (10)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \omega(z,0) &= \zeta(z), \quad z \in [0,\pi], \\ \omega_i(z,0) &= \chi(z), \quad z \in [0,\pi], \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \omega(0,t) &= \omega(\pi,t), \quad t \in [0,T], \\ \omega_z(0,t) &= \omega_z(\pi,t) = 0, \quad t \in [0,T]. \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Initially, we employ the linearization method, after that we apply two different implicit finite difference schemes, which are implicit and Crank-Nicolson, for solving (10–12).

Firstly, the implicit scheme is as follows:

$$\frac{1}{\Delta t^2} (\omega_i^{j+2} - 2\omega_i^{j+1} + \omega_i^j) = \frac{1}{\Delta z^2} (\omega_{i-1}^{j+2} - 2\omega_i^{j+2} + \omega_{i+1}^{j+2}) + \theta^{j+1} \tilde{f}^{j+1}. \quad (13)$$

Secondly, the Crank-Nicolson scheme is as follows:

$$\frac{1}{\Delta t^2} (\omega_i^{j+2} - 2\omega_i^{j+1} + \omega_i^j) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\omega_{i-1}^{j+2} - 2\omega_i^{j+2} + \omega_{i+1}^{j+2}}{\Delta z^2} + \frac{\omega_{i-1}^{j+1} - 2\omega_i^{j+1} + \omega_{i+1}^{j+1}}{\Delta z^2} \right) + \theta^{j+1} \tilde{f}^{j+1}. \quad (14)$$

For time discretization second order backward difference scheme is used, and for space discretization, second order central difference scheme is applied for implicit and Crank-Nicolson scheme.

$$\begin{aligned} \omega_i^0 &= \zeta_i, \\ \omega_1^j &= \omega_{Nz}^j, \\ \omega_{Nz}^j &= \frac{\omega_2^j + \omega_{Nz-1}^j}{2}, \end{aligned}$$

where the computational domain $[0,\pi] \times [0,T]$ is discretized as flows. $z_i = i(\Delta z - 1)$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, Nz$, $t_j = j\Delta t$ and $j = 1, 2, \dots, Nt$. Where $\Delta z = \pi/Nz$ and $\Delta t = T/Nt$ are the space in z direction and time steps, respectively. Also, Nz and Nt are two positive integers. $\omega_i^j = \omega(z_i, t_j)$, $\zeta_i = \zeta(z_i)$, $\tilde{f}^{j+1} = f(z_i, t_{j+1})$. At time $t = 0$, adjustments should be made in accordance with the initial condition

and compatibility requirements. In our numerical computation, $j+2$ exhibits present time, $j+1$ signifies previous of present time, and j denotes previous of previous present time.

In order to determine the inverse coefficient $\theta(t)$, integrating Eq. (1) with respect to x from 0 to π and using Eqs. (3) and (4), we obtain

$$\theta(t) = \frac{\Upsilon''(t) - \pi \omega_z(\pi, t)}{\int_0^\pi z \tilde{f}(z, t) dz} \quad (15)$$

The finite difference approximation of Eq. (15) is

$$\theta^{j+1} = \frac{\left(\frac{\Upsilon^{j+1} - 2\Upsilon^j + \Upsilon^{j-1}}{\Delta t^2} \right) - \pi \left(\frac{\omega_{Nz}^{j+1} - \omega_{Nz-1}^{j+1}}{\Delta z} \right)}{(\tilde{fin})^{j+1}},$$

where

$$\Upsilon^j = \Upsilon(t_j), \quad (\tilde{fin})^{j+1} = \int_0^\pi z \tilde{f}(z, t_{j+1}) dz.$$

For $j=0$

$$\theta^1 = \frac{\left(\frac{\Upsilon^1 - 2\Upsilon^0 + \Upsilon^0}{\Delta t^2} \right) - \pi \left(\frac{\omega_{Nz}^1 - \omega_{Nz-1}^1}{\Delta z} \right)}{(\tilde{fin})^1}.$$

For $j=1$

$$\theta^2 = \frac{\left(\frac{\Upsilon^2 - 2\Upsilon^1 + \Upsilon^0}{\Delta t^2} \right) - \pi \left(\frac{\omega_{Nz}^2 - \omega_{Nz-1}^2}{\Delta z} \right)}{(\tilde{fin})^1}.$$

In order to calculate $(\tilde{fin})^{j+1}$, trapezoidal rule for integration is used. The Nz used for numerical solutions is different from the Nin used for trapezoidal rule for integration.

We use Gauss Seidel iteration to compute our implicit (13) and Crank-Nicolson (14) finite difference formulation. Inverse coefficient and source term calculate with using previous present time values. The Gauss-Seidel iteration formula is given as follows:

$$\omega_i^{j+2(s+1)} = \frac{rhs_i}{a_{ii}} - \sum_{k=1}^{i-1} \frac{a_{ik}}{a_{ii}} \omega_k^{j+2(s+1)} - \sum_{k=i+1}^{Nz} \frac{a_{ik}}{a_{ii}} \omega_k^{j+2(s)},$$

where s is iteration number. In numerical computations, since time step is very small, we can take $\omega_i^{j+2(0)} = \omega_i^{j+1}$. Gauss Seidel iteration for $s=0$,

$$\omega_i^{j+2(1)} = \frac{rhs_i}{a_{ii}} - \sum_{k=1}^{i-1} \frac{a_{ik}}{a_{ii}} \omega_k^{j+2(1)} - \sum_{k=i+1}^{Nz} \frac{a_{ik}}{a_{ii}} \omega_k^{j+1}.$$

Right hand side terms for implicit finite difference scheme defines as;

$$rhs_i = -2\omega_i^{j+1} + \omega_i^j - \theta^{j+1} \Delta t^2 \tilde{f}^{j+1}.$$

In the same manner, the right-hand side terms (rhs_i) for the Crank–Nicolson finite difference scheme are defined as:

$$rhs_i = -2\omega_i^{j+1} + \omega_i^j - \frac{\Delta t^2}{2\Delta z^2} (\omega_{i-1}^{j+1} - 2\omega_i^{j+1} + \omega_{i+1}^{j+1}) - \theta^{j+1} \Delta t^2 \tilde{f}^{j+1}$$

and coefficient matrices (a_{ii}) define as with respect to periodic boundary conditions and inner computational nodes. Of course, different coefficient matrices occur for implicit scheme and Crank–Nicolson scheme. Firstly, in every time step, maximum iteration number defines to stop Gauss Seidel iteration. However, to conclude Gauss Seidel iteration in one time step, tolerance value also defines, therefore in some time step size iteration process ends before the maximum iteration numbers. The numerical methods which are described above are implemented in the in-house implicit finite difference code.

4. Numerical Example

If we consider inverse problem (1)-(4) with

$$f(z, t, \vartheta) = \vartheta e^t \sin 2z, \zeta(z) = \sin 2z, \Upsilon(t) = -\frac{\pi}{2} e^t, z \in [0, \pi], t \in [0, T].$$

Then the problem becomes

$$\vartheta_{tt} - \vartheta_{zz} = \theta(t) \vartheta e^t \sin 2z, z \in [0, \pi], 0 \leq t \leq T$$

$$\vartheta(z, 0) = \sin 2z, \vartheta_t(z, 0) = 0,$$

$$\vartheta(0, t) = \vartheta(\pi, t), \vartheta_z(0, t) = \vartheta_z(\pi, t),$$

$$\int_0^\pi z \vartheta(z, t) dz = -\frac{\pi}{2} e^t.$$

Verifying the analytical solution of this problem is straightforward

$$\{\theta(t), \vartheta(z, t)\} = \{(12t^2 + 16t^4 + 4), e^t \sin 2z\}.$$

In the numerical solutions, 200 of number of meshes (Nz) are used, therefore our space discretization in z direction is 0.0157. To evaluate the integral, Nz meshes are once again employed. Time step size is 0.005s. Maximum iteration per time step is taken as 100 for Gauss Seidel iteration process. However, tolerance value of Gauss Seidel iteration is kept as 10^{-6} . Within this tolerance values, iteration number is less than maximum iteration per time step for every time step.

Figure 1 represents the inverse coefficient distribution with time. Numerical and exact results of inverse coefficient enhance with time.

Figure 1: Exact and numerical solutions of $\theta(t)$ from 0s to 1s.

In order to compare exact and numeric solutions of inverse coefficient, true error and relative true error can be considered. Table 1 shows the exact solution, true error and relative true error of $\theta(t)$ at specific times for implicit and Crank-Nicolson schemes. Generally, true error and relative true error enhances with time for both schemes. The implicit scheme and the Crank-Nicolson scheme have produced equivalent true error and relative true error. Maximum relative true error is observed at 1.0s, 4.1840% and 4.1740% occurred for implicit and Crank-Nicolson schemes, respectively. Relative true error is less than 5.0% for both schemes, therefore, both numerical results are close to exact results for inverse coefficient.

Table 1: The exact solution, true error and relative true error of $\theta(t)$

t[s]	Exact	True error for implicit	Relative true error for implicit [%]	True error for Crank-Nicolson	Relative true error for Crank-Nicolson [%]
0.1	4.1200	0.0799	1.9392	0.1181	2.8663
0.2	4.4810	0.0429	0.9565	0.0477	1.0638
0.3	5.0917	0.0694	1.3627	0.0798	1.5668
0.4	5.9855	0.1037	1.7329	0.1234	2.0610
0.5	7.2500	0.1508	2.0805	0.1791	2.4706
0.6	9.0665	0.2211	2.4388	0.2560	2.8235
0.7	11.7624	0.3321	2.8231	0.3697	3.1435
0.8	15.8743	0.5139	3.2372	0.5482	3.4533
0.9	22.2231	0.8191	3.6860	0.8410	3.7844
1.0	32.0000	1.3389	4.1840	1.3357	4.1740

Figure 2 shows exact and numerical (implicit and Crank-Nicolson scheme) solutions of the $\vartheta(z,t)$ for (a) $t=0.25s$, (b) $t=0.5s$, (c) $t=0.75s$ and (d) $t=1.0s$. Hyperbolic profiles can be observed for exact and both numerical solutions at given times. With increasing time, depth of hyperbolic profiles increases. At a given time, symmetric hyperbolic profiles are produced. Solutions of exact and implicit scheme and Crank-Nicolson scheme are so close each other.

Figure 2: Exact and numerical solutions of the $g(z,t)$ for (a) $t=0.25s$, (b) $t=0.5s$, (c), $0.75s$ and (d) $t=1.0s$

Figure 3 presents the hyperbolic profiles in all times for solutions of (a) exact and (b) implicit scheme and (c) Crank- Nicolson scheme. The same observations can be made for Figure 2.

Figure 3: Exact and numerical solutions of the $g(z,t)$ for all times

In the same manner, in order to correctly compare the exact solution with both numerical computations (implicit scheme and Crank–Nicolson scheme) of $g(z,t)$, the true error and the relative true error can again be observed. Figure 4 always represents the true errors and relative true errors of

both numerical computations. True errors increase with time, and the maximum true errors are observed at the peak point of hyperbolic profiles for both numerical computations.

Figure 4: True error and relative true error of $\mathcal{G}(z,t)$ for all times

The maximum true errors of implicit schema and Crank-Nicolson scheme are nearly -0.04 and -0.06 according to exact solution. When examining the relative true error, it is observed that the maximum relative true errors occur at the boundary points. For the implicit scheme, this value is approximately 0.5%, whereas for the Crank–Nicolson scheme, it is around 1%. In both schemes, the relative true error remains below 1%; however, the implicit scheme is roughly twice as accurate as the Crank–Nicolson scheme.

5. Conclusions

Analytical and numerical investigation of one-dimensional nonlinear hyperbolic equation with periodic conditions is carried out. This investigation contains an inverse problem of unknown unsteady coefficient. For analytical solution, the generalized Fourier method is utilized to calculate Fourier coefficients. For numerical solutions, two different implicit finite difference schemes, namely, implicit and Crank- Nicolson, with Gauss Seidel iteration process are applied. The major conclusions are listed below:

1. Inverse coefficient enhances with time for exact and numerical computations.
2. The implicit scheme and the Crank–Nicolson scheme have predicted the inverse coefficient to the same level of accuracy.
3. One-dimensional symmetric hyperbolic profiles are produced analytically and numerically. With time increases, the depth of the hyperbolic profiles also enhances.
4. The maximum relative true error of Crank-Nicolson scheme (1%) is doubled to implicit scheme (0.5%); therefore, estimation of implicit scheme is closer than Crank-Nicolson scheme

5. The given tolerance value of Gauss-Seidel iterations is sufficient to predict hyperbolic profiles for both numerical schemes.

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Numerical Investigation of an Inverse Coefficient Problem in a Nonlinear Hyperbolic Equation

Akbala Yernazar¹, İrem Bağlan², Erman Aslan³

¹Department of Mathematics, Ahmet Yassawi University, Turkistan, Kazakhstan

²Department of Mathematics, Kocaeli University, Kocaeli, TR-41380, Turkey

³Department of Mechanical Engineering, Kocaeli University, Kocaeli, TR-41380, Turkey

Corresponding author: akbalayernazar@gmail.com

ORCID IDs:

First Author: [0000-0002-0068-4954](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0068-4954)

Second Author: [0000-0003-4900-6027](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4900-6027)

Third Author: [0000-0001-8595-6092](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8595-6092)

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Abstract

In this study, an inverse coefficient problem for a one-dimensional nonlinear hyperbolic equation with periodic boundary conditions is investigated. The numerical solution is obtained through an implicit finite difference scheme. A comparison of the analytical and numerical results demonstrates that the estimated inverse coefficient and the corresponding v values exhibit excellent agreement, indicating the accuracy and reliability of the proposed approach.

Keywords: inverse problem, nonlinear hyperbolic equation, finite difference method

1. Introduction

The advent of new scientific and engineering knowledge has increased the significance of inverse problems. The scope of inverse problems is vast, encompassing fields such as physics, chemistry, biology, astrophysics, geophysics, medicine, and economics. Inverse problems have numerous and diverse practical applications in areas like microwave heating, climate modeling, heat conduction, biological processes, seismology, and seawater desalination. In the field of medicine, for instance, techniques such as computed tomography are based on the principles of inverse problems. In geophysics, the investigation of subterranean structures and the exploration of underground resources can be conducted more cost-effectively using inverse problems, as an alternative to deep drilling. Furthermore, the use of inverse problems is pervasive in domains such as radio astronomy, spectroscopy and nuclear physics. In most cases, such problems are modelled by partial differential equations. Predictions can be made regarding the behavior of the system if the input data, including initial boundary conditions, solution geometry and coefficients, are known with certainty. In some cases, however, these inputs may be absent or unknown. In such instances, the output from experimental measurements can be used to reconstruct the missing data. This process gives rise to ill-posed inverse problems, where minor alterations in the input can result in significant changes to the

solution. The theory of ill-posed inverse problems was first proposed by Tikhonov [1] and later developed into the theory of regularization, which aims to solve ill-posed inverse problems, by Tikhonov [2] and Morozov [3].

In recent years, inverse problems for hyperbolic equations with unknown coefficients have attracted significant interest from numerous researchers [4-11]. Here, the emphasis is on determining the unknown coefficient such wave speed or damping from empirical observations typically obtained from measurements of the solution at different times and locations. Beylina [11] investigated inverse problems with integral overdetermination conditions in which they demonstrated the existence and uniqueness of solutions using priori estimates and Galerkin procedures. A study by Kozhanov [12] solved nonlinear inverse problems for second-order hyperbolic equations, establishing existence and uniqueness theorems for regular solutions with weak derivatives in the Sobolev sense. Similar to other studies, the Fourier method has been employed to investigate inverse boundary value problems for hyperbolic equations [13-16]. The works of Akhundov & Habibova [17] and Kozhanov [12] explored the determination of unknown coefficients of hyperbolic equations and proved theorems on uniqueness, stability, and existence of solutions. These studies employed integral overdetermination conditions to solve the time-dependent unknown coefficients. These approaches underscore the importance of mathematical techniques in simplifying complex inverse problems.

In mathematical modeling, however, problems often specify relationships between the values of the desired function both on the boundary and within the domain, rather than relying solely on classical boundary conditions. Such conditions are referred to as non-local conditions [18]. In this study, we will focus on periodic boundary conditions, which are relevant to the problem at hand. Huntul et al. [14] investigated the reconstruction of a time-dependent potential in a hyperbolic problem with periodic boundary conditions. The inverse problem for parabolic, hyperbolic, and Euler-Bernoulli equations under periodic boundary conditions has been investigated by [19-22]. These works have contributed to the understanding and solution of inverse problems for hyperbolic equations with periodic boundary conditions and further limitations.

Numerical methods such as finite difference method [23, 24], finite element method [25, 26] and finite volume method [27, 28], are widely employed for investigating inverse problems for hyperbolic equations. The work by Huntul et al. [14] employed the Crank-Nicolson finite difference method and Tikhonov regularization to investigate the reconstruction of a time-dependent potential, establishing both accuracy and stability. Lin and Ewing [29] proposed a direct numerical method for solving a coefficient inverse problem. The study used finite differences in one dimensional for efficient computation. Le et al. [30] proposed a quasi-reversibility method for solving an inverse source problem. The researchers estimated solution using Fourier series and proved convergence with decrease in noise levels. The Carleman estimates were used to establish a local stability result for an inverse source problem in a study by Jiang et al. [31], which subsequently implemented a Tikhonov regularization-based numerical algorithm. The overall literature demonstrates the growing development of stable and efficient numerical techniques for solving inverse problems in hyperbolic equations.

In the present study, we investigate an inverse problem involving unknown time-dependent coefficient in a one-dimensional nonlinear hyperbolic equation under periodic boundary conditions. For the numerical solution, implicit finite-difference schemes is applied. The existence, uniqueness, and stability of the analytical solution for this problem have been previously established in [32].

2. Statement of the Problem

Consider a nonlinear hyperbolic equation defined on the domain $D := \{z \in (0, \pi), t \in (0, T)\}$:

$$v_{tt} - v_{zz} - a(t)v = f(z, t, v), \quad (1)$$

with the initial conditions

$$\begin{aligned}v(z, 0) &= \varphi(z), \\v_t(z, 0) &= \psi(z),\end{aligned}\tag{2}$$

and boundary conditions

$$\begin{aligned}v(0, t) &= v(\pi, t), \\v_z(0, t) &= v_z(\pi, t),\end{aligned}\tag{3}$$

as well as the overdetermination condition

$$E(t) = \int_0^\pi v(z, t) dz.\tag{4}$$

Where the functions φ, ψ, E and $f(z, t, v)$ are given functions on $[0, \pi]$ and $\bar{D} \times \{-\infty, \infty\}$, respectively; while the function $v(z, t)$ and the coefficient $a(t)$ are unknown.

Using the Fourier method to solve equations (1)–(4), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}v(z, t) &= \frac{1}{2} \left(\varphi_0 + \psi_0 t + \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^t \int_0^\pi (t - \tau) [a(\tau)v(\zeta, \tau) + f(\zeta, \tau, v)] d\zeta d\tau \right) \\&+ \sum_{k=1}^\infty \left(\varphi_{ck} \cos 2kt + \frac{1}{2k} \psi_{ck} \sin 2kt + \frac{1}{\pi k} \int_0^t \int_0^\pi [a(\tau)v(\zeta, \tau) + f(\zeta, \tau, v)] \cos 2k\zeta \sin 2k(t - \tau) d\zeta d\tau \right) \cos 2kz \tag{5} \\&+ \sum_{k=1}^\infty \left(\varphi_{sk} \cos 2kt + \frac{1}{2k} \psi_{sk} \sin 2kt + \frac{1}{\pi k} \int_0^t \int_0^\pi [a(\tau)v(\zeta, \tau) + f(\zeta, \tau, v)] \sin 2k\zeta \sin 2k(t - \tau) d\zeta d\tau \right) \sin 2kz.\end{aligned}$$

By employing the overdetermination condition (4) together with the solution (5), the inverse coefficient in equations (1)–(4) is determined as shown in (6):

$$a(t) = \frac{E''(t) - \int_0^\pi f(z, t, v) dz}{E(t)}.\tag{6}$$

Definition 2.1 The problem of finding the pair $(a(t), v(z, t))$ in (1)–(4) will be called an inverse problem.

Definition 2.2 B is called Banach space when the following set

$$\{v(t)\} = \left\{ v_0(t), v_{sk}(t), v_{ck}(t), k = 1, \dots, N \mid \max_{0 \leq t \leq T} \frac{|v_0(t)|}{2} + \sum_{k=1}^\infty \left(\max_{0 \leq t \leq T} |v_{ck}(t)| + \max_{0 \leq t \leq T} |v_{sk}(t)| \right) < \infty \right\}$$

of continuous on $[0, T]$ functions satisfying the norm

$$\|v(t)\| = \max_{0 \leq t \leq T} \frac{|v_0(t)|}{2} + \sum_{k=1}^\infty \left(\max_{0 \leq t \leq T} |v_{ck}(t)| + \max_{0 \leq t \leq T} |v_{sk}(t)| \right).$$

Theorem 2.1 If the following assumptions satisfy:

A1. $E(t) \in C^2[0, T], a(t) \in C[0, T]$.

A2. $\varphi(z) \in C[0, \pi], \psi(z) \in C[0, \pi]$.

A3.1 $f(z, t, v)$ is continuous across all arguments in $D \times (-\infty, \infty)$ and satisfies the condition:

$$\left| \frac{\partial^{(k)} f(z, t, v)}{\partial z^{(k)}} - \frac{\partial^{(k)} f(z, t, \bar{v})}{\partial z^{(k)}} \right| \leq b(z, t) |v - \bar{v}|, k = \overline{0, 2}, \text{ where } b(z, t) \in L_2(D), b(z, t) \geq 0.$$

A3.2 $f(z, t, v) \in C[0, \pi], t \in [0, T], |f(z, t, v)| \leq M$.

A3.3 $\int_0^\pi f(z, t, v) dz \neq 0, \forall t \in [0, T]$.

Then the problem (1)–(4) has a unique solution.

Theorem 2.2 If the assumptions of the theorem 1 be satisfied, then the pair of the solution $(a(t), v(z, t))$ of the problem (1)–(4) is constantly dependent on the input data φ, ψ, E .

3. Numerical Procedure for the Nonlinear Problem

We develop an iterative algorithm to linearize the problem,

$$\frac{\partial^2 v^{(m)}}{\partial t^2} - \frac{\partial^2 v^{(m)}}{\partial z^2} - a(t)v^{(m)} = f(z, t, v^{(m-1)}), \quad (7)$$

$$\begin{aligned} v^{(m)}(z, 0) &= \varphi(z), \quad z \in [0, \pi], \\ v_t^{(m)}(z, 0) &= \psi(z), \quad z \in [0, \pi], \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

$$\begin{aligned} v^{(m)}(0, t) &= v^{(m)}(\pi, t), \quad t \in [0, T], \\ v_z^{(m)}(0, t) &= v_z^{(m)}(\pi, t), \quad t \in [0, T]. \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

By setting $v^{(m)}(z, t) = v^{(m)}(z, t)$ and $f(z, t, v^{(m-1)}) = \tilde{f}(z, t)$, we can express the problem (7)-(9) as a linear problem.

$$\frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial t^2} - \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial z^2} - a(t)v = \tilde{f}(z, t). \quad (10)$$

After this linearization process, an implicit finite difference scheme is used for the numerical solution of the above equation. In the time discretization used in Eq. (10), a first-order accurate backward finite difference scheme is employed. For spatial discretization, a second-order accurate central finite difference scheme is utilized;

$$\frac{1}{\Delta t^2} (v_i^{j+2} - 2v_i^{j+1} + v_i^j) = \frac{1}{\Delta z^2} (v_{i-1}^{j+2} - 2v_i^{j+2} + v_{i+1}^{j+2}) + a^{j+1}v_i^{j+1} + f_i^{j+1}. \quad (11)$$

The initial condition is defined as;

$$v_i^0 = \varphi_i. \quad (12)$$

The Dirichlet boundary condition is a first-type boundary condition that assigns a fixed value, while the Neumann boundary condition is a second-type boundary condition that assigns a fixed gradient. The periodic boundary condition is a combination of the two. While defining the periodic boundary condition, the parts of the coefficient matrix corresponding to the boundary values were modified according to Eqs. (13) and (14).

$$v_1^j = v_{Nz}^j, \quad (13)$$

$$v_{Nz}^j = \frac{v_2^j + v_{Nz-1}^j}{2}. \quad (14)$$

The computational domain extends from $[0, \pi]$ in the z -direction and $[0, T]$ in time. It's divided into discrete intervals, where spatial points are defined as $z_i = i(\Delta z)$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots, Nz$ and temporal points are given by $t_j = j\Delta t$ for $j = 1, 2, \dots, Nt$. Here, Δz is the spatial step size, determined by $\Delta z = \pi/Nz$, and Δt is the time step, calculated as $\Delta t = T/Nt$. The integers Nz and Nt specify the number of intervals in space and time, respectively. The values v , φ and f are discretized as $v_i^j = v(z_i, t_j)$, $\varphi_i = \varphi(z_i)$ and $\tilde{f}^{j+2} = f(z_i, t_{j+2})$, respectively. The initial condition is specified at $t = 0$. In the numerical calculation, $j + 2$ indicates the current time, $j + 1$ refers the previous time, and j corresponds two steps before the current time.

To compute the inverse coefficient $a(t)$, Eq. (1) is integrated over the interval $[0, \pi]$ with respect to z , utilizing the relationships provided in Eqs. (3) and (4). This process yields:

$$a(t) = \frac{E''(t) - \int_0^\pi v_{zz} dz - \int_0^\pi \tilde{f}(z, t) dz}{E(t)}. \quad (15)$$

The $E''(t)$ term in (15) is discretized as follows:

$$E''(t) = \frac{E^{j+2} - 2E^{j+1} + E^j}{\Delta t^2}. \quad (16)$$

The two integral expressions $\int_0^\pi v_{zz} dz$ and $\int_0^\pi \tilde{f}(z, t) dz$ in Eq. (15) are evaluated using the trapezoidal rule. The spatial discretization points used in the numerical solution are also utilized in the trapezoidal rule for integration.

For the numerical solution of Eq. (11), no iterative methods are employed; instead, a direct method is used instead. The right-hand side matrix constitutes from previous values, and it is used in direct method. The right-hand side matrix is

$$rhs_i = 2v_i^{j+1} - v_i^j + \Delta t^2 (a(t)v_i^{j+1} + f_i^{j+1}).$$

4. Numerical Example

Considering inverse problem,

$$f(z, t, v) = e^{t^2} [2 - 5t^2 + (6 - 5t^2)\cos(2z)]$$

with the over determination condition is given as;

$$E(t) = \int_0^{\pi} v(z,t) dz = \frac{1}{2} e^{t^2} (2\pi + \sin(2\pi)).$$

In that case, the problem transforms as

$$v_{tt} - v_{zz} - a(t)v = e^{t^2} [2 - 5t^2 + (6 - 5t^2)\cos(2z)].$$

The initial condition is defined as

$$\varphi(z) = v(z,0) = 1 + \cos 2z, z \in [0, \pi].$$

The periodic boundary condition is determined as

$$v(0,t) = v(\pi,t), v_z(0,t) = v_z(\pi,t), 0 \leq t \leq T.$$

The analytical solution of this problem is expressed as follows

$$\{a(t), v(z,t)\} = \{9t^2, (1 + \cos(2z))e^{t^2}\}.$$

4.1 Grid Independence Study, Time Step Size Determination

Before starting the main solution, a grid independence study and a time step determination study are conducted to establish the necessary grid size and time step. For the grid independence study, eight different grid densities are used, each progressively doubled: 20, 40, 80, 160, 320, 640, 1280, and 2560. The grid independence study is performed for all pre-determined time steps, which are halved sequentially as follows: 0.01s, 0.005s, 0.0025s, 0.00125s, 0.000625s, and 0.0003125s.

Figure 1 shows the grid independence studies conducted for the maximum value of v at 1 second for each time step. To facilitate a better comparison, the graphs are presented on the same scale, and the results from the analytical solution are also included. As the time step decreases, an increase in the v values is observed. For all time steps, the differences between solutions decrease as the number of grid points increases. A grid number of 1280 is determined to be the grid-independent number for all time steps. Furthermore, the solution at a time step of 0.0025s and a grid number of 1280 aligns very closely with the analytical solution.

Figure 1: Grid independence study

Although Figure 1 states that the numerical solution with a grid number of 1280 and a time step of 0.0025s is very close to the analytical solution, Figure 2 shows the variation of v values with different time steps for a grid-independent mesh number of 1280. Similar to the observations in the grid independence study (Figure 1), the v values increase as the time step decreases. However, unlike the grid independence study, the v values obtained from numerical solutions do not stabilize as the time step decreases further.

Figure 1:Variation of v values with the time steps for a grid independent mesh number of 1280

4.2 Numerical Predictions

Figure 3 presents: (a) the time-dependent variation of the inverse coefficient calculated both analytically and numerically, (b) the time-dependent variation of the true error between these two solutions, and (c) the time-dependent variation of the relative true error between these two solutions. In Figure 3(a), the analytically and numerically calculated inverse coefficients increase over time. It is observed that the two inverse coefficients are very close to each other, However, this closeness can be more clearly identified by examining the true error in Figure 3(b). According to Figure 3(b), the true error increases as time progresses; however, these increases are very small and remain within reasonable limits. To facilitate a better comparison of the difference between the two inverse coefficients, the relative true errors are shown as percentages in Figure 3(c). From Figure 3(c), it can be observed that the relative error starts at approximately -3% in the initial stages and decreases to around 0.25% as time increases. This demonstrates that the analytically calculated inverse coefficient is very close to the numerically calculated inverse coefficient.

Figure 3: The time-dependent variation of (a) the inverse coefficient, (b) true error and (c) relative true error

Figure 4 presents the time-dependent variation of the v value for (a) the exact solution and (b) the numerical solution. Both solutions are found to be very close to each other. The v value exhibits a concave shape at all time instances. Due to the periodic boundary condition, both ends of the domain have the same value. In the initial moments, the concavity is less pronounced, but it deepens as time progresses. While the minimum value of concavity remains relatively constant over time, the values at the edges of concavity increase as time advances.

Figure 4: The time-dependent variation of the v value for (a) exact solution, (b) for numerical solution

In Figure 5, it can be observed that there is very little difference between the analytical and numerical solutions. However, to better compare the difference between the two calculations, Figure 5 illustrates the time-dependent variations of (a) the true error and (b) the absolute relative true error. The true error increases over time, forming a shape resembling the letter “m”. It is negative in regions with periodic boundary conditions and positive in areas immediately adjacent to these boundary conditions. In Figure 5(b), the absolute relative true error increases with time and is concentrated in the middle of the domain. In the one second solution, the maximum absolute relative error is around 1%, which indicates that the analytical and numerical solutions are very close to each other.

Figure 5: The time-dependent variation of (a) the true error and (b) the absolute relative true error

5. Conclusions

In this study, numerical solutions of a one-dimensional inverse coefficient nonlinear hyperbolic equation with periodic boundary conditions were carried out. An implicit finite difference scheme was used for the numerical solutions. The temporal discretization has first-order accuracy, while the spatial discretization has second-order accuracy. Based on the grid independence study conducted for each time step, an appropriate grid size and time step were determined. The inverse coefficient and v values obtained with the selected grid number, time step, and accuracy levels were found to align very well with the analytical results. It has been demonstrated that the nonlinear hyperbolic equation representing the wave equation, along with periodic boundary conditions, can be solved numerically.

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Fractional Calculus Approach to Perturbed Trapezoid-type Inequalities: Novel Error Estimates and Applications

Arslan Munir¹, Shumin Li¹, Hüseyin Budak³

¹School of Mathematical Sciences, University of Science and Technology of China,
Hefei 230026 People's Republic of China

²Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Science and Arts, Kocaeli University,
Kocaeli 41001, Türkiye

Corresponding author: munirarslan999@gmail.com

ORCID IDs:

First Author: [0009-0008-8148-5607](https://orcid.org/0009-0008-8148-5607)

Second Author: [0000-0002-6236-6273](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6236-6273)

Third Author: [0000-0001-8843-955X](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8843-955X)

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Abstract

Inequalities involving fractional operators have also been an active area of research. These inequalities play a crucial role in establishing bounds, estimates, and stability conditions for solutions to fractional integrals. The main aim in the current article is to establish a identity through the Caputo-Fabrizio integral operator. By using this identity, we are obtained the new fractional bounds and error estimated for the perturbed trapezoid-type inequalities. With the aid of this identity, it is proved that new fractional perturbed trapezoid-type inequalities for functions whose third derivatives in absolute value are convex. In addition, the research has acquired fractional perturbed trapezoid-type inequalities for (α, m) -convex function. This is the first article for fractional version of perturbed trapezoid-type inequalities. Finally, we present several corollaries to demonstrate how new results are better than previous results. Moreover, we have given application to the quadrature formula.

Keywords: Perturbed trapezoid type inequality, (α, m) -convex function, Fractional integrals, Young's inequality.

1 Introduction

Convexity simplifies problem-solving and often leads to computationally efficient solutions. Convex functions and sets have well-defined mathematical properties, which allow for the development of efficient algorithms and analytical solutions. This makes convexity a valuable tool for researchers and practitioners in physics, statistics, engineering, and among other disciplines. Convexity theory provides a unifying framework to understand and prove many of these inequalities. It allows mathematicians to explore and generalize these inequalities, leading to the development of new results and techniques in various mathematical disciplines. The interested researchers on convexity and integral inequalities we refer to see these articles [2, 3, 4]. The original and generalized version is defined as:

Definition 1.1. [1] A function $f : I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is said to be convex if the inequality holds:

$$f(\psi\pi + (1 - \psi)\nu) \leq \psi f(\pi) + (1 - \psi)f(\nu),$$

for all $\pi, \nu \in I$ and $\psi \in [0, 1]$.

Definition 1.2. [5] Let $f : [0, y] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $(\alpha, m) \in [0, 1]^2$ is said to be (α, m) -convex if:

$$f(\psi\pi + (1 - \psi)\nu) \leq \psi^\alpha f(\pi) + m(1 - \psi^\alpha)f(\nu),$$

for all $\pi, \nu \in [0, y]$ and $\psi \in [0, 1]$.

The Hermite-Hadamard inequality is a well-known result in mathematical analysis and can be attributed to two mathematicians Charles Hermite and Jacques Hadamard is indeed known as the Hermite-Hadamard inequality. The Hermite-Hadamard inequality is a result in the theory of convex functions and states as follows:

$$f\left(\frac{\pi + \nu}{2}\right) \leq \int_{\pi}^{\nu} f(\Omega) d\Omega \leq \frac{f(\pi) + f(\nu)}{2}.$$

This inequality provides bounds on the integral of a convex function over a closed interval and has applications in various branches of mathematics, including calculus, analysis, and optimization. The Hermite-Hadamard inequality has garnered significant attention from mathematicians and researchers since its introduction. This inequality is not only elegant but also versatile, making it a valuable tool in mathematical analysis and its applications. Mathematicians have explored various aspects of the inequality, including its extensions, generalizations, have been published based on the definition of convexity [6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11].

Fractional calculus, a branch of mathematics that generalized the concept of differentiation and integration to non-integer orders, has indeed gained remarkable popularity and importance in recent decades. Its applications span a wide range of fields, making it a valuable tool in various scientific and engineering disciplines. The use of fractional integral operators to popularize and extend well-known integral inequalities reflects the evolving nature of mathematics and its applications. It allows for a deeper exploration of mathematical concepts and provides valuable insights into the behavior of systems with fractional order dynamics. As a result, this topic continues to attract the attention of mathematicians and researchers interested in both theoretical and applied mathematics. The Riemann-Liouville fractional integral is just one of several fractional integral operators used in fractional calculus. Other operators, such as the Caputo fractional integral, are also commonly used depending on the specific problem and boundary conditions. Prior to using the Caputo-Fabrizio fractional integral defined by Caputo, let's review its definition.

Definition 1.3. [12] Suppose $f \in L[\pi, \nu]$. The Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals of order $\alpha > 0$, defined on the left and right sides are given by:

$$I_{\pi+}^{\alpha} f(\psi) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{\pi}^{\Omega} (\Omega - \psi)^{\alpha-1} f(\psi) d\psi, \quad \Omega > \pi,$$

$$I_{\nu-}^{\alpha} f(\psi) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{\Omega}^{\nu} (\psi - \Omega)^{\alpha-1} f(\psi) d\psi, \quad \Omega < \nu,$$

where $\Gamma(\cdot)$ is the gamma function and $I_{\pi+}^0 f(\psi) = I_{\nu-}^0 f(\psi) = f(\psi)$.

Definition 1.4. [13] Let $f \in H^1(\pi, \nu)$, $\pi < \nu$, for all $\psi \in [0, 1]$, where $\beta(\alpha) > 0$ is a normalizer satisfying $\beta(0) = \beta(1) = 1$, then the left and right fractional integrals are defined by:

$$\left({}^{CF} I_{\pi}^{\psi} f \right) (\Omega) = \frac{1 - \alpha}{\beta(\alpha)} f(\Omega) + \frac{\alpha}{\beta(\alpha)} \int_{\pi}^{\Omega} f(\Omega) d\Omega,$$

$$\left({}^{CF} I_{\nu}^{\psi} f \right) (\Omega) = \frac{1 - \alpha}{\beta(\alpha)} f(\Omega) + \frac{\alpha}{\beta(\alpha)} \int_{\Omega}^{\nu} f(\Omega) d\Omega.$$

The study of fractional H-H (Hermite-Hadamard type) inequalities has indeed garnered significant attention in recent years within the realm of fractional calculus and mathematical analysis. These inequalities are extensions or generalizations of the classical H-H

(Hermite-Hadamard type) inequality to the framework of fractional calculus. Therefore, it is crucial to create and investigate the H-H (Hermite-Hadamard type) inequality for a variety of convex functions using different fractional operators. Fractional calculus continues to evolve, and researchers explore new operators, for example (Caputo, Caputo-Fabrizio, Riemann-Liouville, k -Riemann-Liouville, Katugampola, Conformable) and their applications to address complex problems in various domains. Agarwal et. al [14] derived H-H (Hermite-Hadamard type) inequalities using generalized k -fractional integrals. By utilizing harmonic convex functions, Awan et al. [15] obtained some conformable fractional estimates for H-H (Hermite-Hadamard type) inequalities. Zhao et. al [16], where s -convex functions were employed to establish H-H (Hermite-Hadamard type) inequalities using ψ -Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals. For further inequalities that can be solved using fractional integrals, and the references therein [17, 18, 19]. H-H (Hermite-Hadamard type) inequalities are a class of inequalities, and choosing the most suitable fractional integral operator for studying these inequalities can depend on the specific problem and the properties of the functions involved. It is difficult to generalize and extend H-H (Hermite-Hadamard type) inequalities to the various fractional integral operators. Therefore, the concept of using general fractional integral operators has been proposed by some researchers to meet the needs of modern mathematics. Set et. al [20] established H-H (Hermite-Hadamard type) inequalities involving generalized fractional integral operators. Furthermore, Ahmad et. al [21] proved several H-H (Hermite-Hadamard type) inequalities for convex functions using fractional integral operators with exponential kernel. Aljaaidi et.al [22] studied some novel fractional integral H-H (Hermite-Hadamard type) inequalities based on the generalized proportional fractional integral operators. For more details, we refer the readers to [23, 24, 25].

The aim of the current research article is to establish new perturbed trapezoid-type inequalities for (α, m) -convex functions in the setting of Caputo-Fabrizio integral operators. We are using the Caputo-Fabrizio integral to obtain the new fractional bounds and error estimates for perturbed trapezoid-type inequalities. In addition, the research has acquired fractional perturbed trapezoid-type inequalities for functions whose third derivatives in absolute value are convex. Moreover, we have given application to the quadrature formula.

2 Fractional Perturbed Trapezoid-Type Inequality

In this section, we introduce new perturbed trapezoid-type inequalities by applying Caputo-Fabrizio fractional operators.

Lemma 2.1. A function $f : [\pi, \nu] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is an absolutely continuous function (π, ν) such that $f''' \in L_1[\pi, \nu]$. Then the following equality holds:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{(\Omega - \pi)^2 f'(\pi) - (\Omega - \nu)^2 f'(\nu) + 2f(\Omega)(\nu - \pi) + 4[(\Omega - \pi)f(\pi) + (\Omega - \nu)f(\nu)]}{6(\nu - \pi)} \\ & - \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(\nu - \pi)} \left[\left({}^{CF}I_{\pi}^{\alpha} f \right)(k) + \left({}^{CF}I_{\nu}^{\alpha} f \right)(k) \right] + \frac{2(1 - \alpha)}{\alpha(\nu - \pi)} f(k) \\ & = \frac{1}{6(\nu - \pi)} \left[\int_0^1 \psi(1 - \psi)^2 (\Omega - \pi)^4 f'''(\psi\Omega + (1 - \psi)\pi) \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \int_0^1 \psi(1 - \psi)^2 (\Omega - \nu)^4 f'''(\psi\Omega + (1 - \psi)\nu) d\psi \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^1 \psi(1 - \psi)^2 (\Omega - \pi)^4 f'''(\psi\Omega + (1 - \psi)\pi) d\psi \\ & - \int_0^1 \psi(1 - \psi)^2 (\Omega - \nu)^4 f'''(\psi\Omega + (1 - \psi)\nu) d\psi \\ & = I_1 - I_2. \end{aligned}$$

Integration by parts, we get

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 &= \int_0^1 \psi(1 - \psi)^2 \left((\Omega - \pi)^4 f'''(\psi\Omega + (1 - \psi)\pi) \right) d\psi \\ &= \frac{\psi(1 - \psi)^2 (\Omega - \pi)^4}{\Omega - \pi} f''(\psi\Omega + (1 - \psi)\pi) \Big|_0^1 - \frac{(\Omega - \pi)^4}{\Omega - \pi} \int_0^1 (1 - 4\psi + 3\psi^2) f''(\psi\Omega + (1 - \psi)\pi) d\psi \\ &= -(\Omega - \pi)^3 \int_0^1 (1 - 4\psi + 3\psi^2) f''(\psi\Omega + (1 - \psi)\pi) d\psi \\ &= -(\Omega - \pi)^3 \left[\frac{(1 - 4\psi + 3\psi^2)}{\Omega - \pi} f'(\psi\Omega + (1 - \psi)\pi) \Big|_0^1 - \frac{1}{\Omega - \pi} \int_0^1 (6\psi - 4) f'(\psi\Omega + (1 - \psi)\pi) d\psi \right] \\ &= (\Omega - \pi)^2 f'(\pi) + (\Omega - \pi)^2 \int_0^1 (6\psi - 4) f'(\psi\Omega + (1 - \psi)\pi) d\psi \\ &= (\Omega - \pi)^2 f'(\pi) + (\Omega - \pi)^2 \left[\frac{(6\psi - 4)}{\Omega - \pi} f(\psi\Omega + (1 - \psi)\pi) \Big|_0^1 - \frac{6}{\Omega - \pi} \int_0^1 f(\psi\Omega + (1 - \psi)\pi) d\psi \right] \\ &= (\Omega - \pi)^2 f'(\pi) + 2f(\Omega)(\Omega - \pi) + 4f(\pi)(\Omega - \pi) - 6(\Omega - \pi) \int_0^1 f(\psi\Omega + (1 - \psi)\pi) d\psi \\ &= (\Omega - \pi)^2 f'(\pi) + 2f(\Omega)(\Omega - \pi) + 4f(\pi)(\Omega - \pi) - 6 \int_{\pi}^{\Omega} f(u) du. \tag{1} \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_2 &= \int_0^1 \psi (1 - \psi)^2 \left((\Omega - \nu)^4 f''' (\psi \Omega + (1 - \psi) \nu) \right) d\psi \\
 &= \frac{\psi (1 - \psi)^2 (\Omega - \nu)^4}{\Omega - \nu} f'' (\psi \Omega + (1 - \psi) \nu) \Big|_0^1 - \frac{(\Omega - \nu)^4}{\Omega - \nu} \int_0^1 (1 - 4\psi + 3\psi^2) f'' (\psi \Omega + (1 - \psi) \nu) d\psi \\
 &= -(\Omega - \nu)^3 \int_0^1 (1 - 4\psi + 3\psi^2) f'' (\psi \Omega + (1 - \psi) \nu) d\psi \\
 &= -(\Omega - \nu)^3 \left[\frac{(1 - 4\psi + 3\psi^2)}{\Omega - \nu} f'' (\psi \Omega + (1 - \psi) \nu) \Big|_0^1 - \frac{1}{\Omega - \nu} \int_0^1 (6\psi - 4) f' (\psi \Omega + (1 - \psi) \nu) d\psi \right] \\
 &= (\Omega - \nu)^2 f' (\nu) + (\Omega - \nu)^2 \int_0^1 (6\psi - 4) f' (\psi \Omega + (1 - \psi) \nu) d\psi \\
 &= (\Omega - \nu)^2 f' (\nu) + (\Omega - \nu)^2 \left[\frac{(6\psi - 4)}{\Omega - \nu} f' (\psi \Omega + (1 - \psi) \nu) \Big|_0^1 - \frac{6}{\Omega - \nu} \int_0^1 f (\psi \Omega + (1 - \psi) \nu) d\psi \right] \\
 &= (\Omega - \nu)^2 f' (\nu) + 2f (\Omega) (\Omega - \nu) + 4f (\nu) (\Omega - \nu) - 6(\Omega - \nu) \int_0^1 f (\psi \Omega + (1 - \psi) \nu) d\psi \\
 &= (\Omega - \nu)^2 f' (\nu) + 2f (\Omega) (\Omega - \nu) + 4f (\nu) (\Omega - \nu) + 6 \int_\Omega^\nu f (u) du. \tag{2}
 \end{aligned}$$

Subtracting the equalities (1) and (2), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_1 - I_2 &= (\Omega - \pi)^2 f' (\pi) + 2f (\Omega) (\Omega - \pi) + 4f (\pi) (\Omega - \pi) - 6 \int_\pi^\Omega f (u) du - (\Omega - \nu)^2 f' (\nu) \\
 &\quad - 2f (\Omega) (\Omega - \nu) - 4f (\nu) (\Omega - \nu) - 6 \int_\Omega^\nu f (u) du \\
 &= (\Omega - \pi)^2 f' (\pi) - (\Omega - \nu)^2 f' (\nu) + 2f (\Omega) (\nu - \pi) \\
 &\quad + 4 [(\Omega - \pi) f (\pi) + (\Omega - \nu) f (\nu)] - 6 \int_\pi^\nu f (u) du. \tag{3}
 \end{aligned}$$

Multiplying by the equality (3) with $\frac{1}{6}$ and subtracting $\frac{2(1-\alpha)}{\beta(\alpha)} f(k)$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 &(I_1 - I_2) \frac{1}{6} - \frac{2(1-\alpha)}{\beta(\alpha)} f(k) \\
 &= \frac{(\Omega - \pi)^2 f' (\pi)}{6} - \frac{(\Omega - \nu)^2 f' (\nu)}{6} + \frac{2f (\Omega) (\nu - \pi)}{6} \\
 &\quad + \frac{4 [(\Omega - \pi) f (\pi) + (\Omega - \nu) f (\nu)]}{6} - \int_\pi^\nu f (u) du - \frac{2(1-\alpha)}{\beta(\alpha)} f(k) \\
 &= \frac{(\Omega - \pi)^2 f' (\pi) + (\Omega - \nu)^2 f' (\nu) + 2f (\Omega) (\nu - \pi) + 4 [(\Omega - \pi) f (\pi) + (\Omega - \nu) f (\nu)]}{6}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& - \left(\frac{\alpha}{\beta(\alpha)} \int_{\pi}^k f(u) du + \frac{(1-\alpha)}{\beta(\alpha)} f(k) + \frac{\alpha}{\beta(\alpha)} \int_k^{\nu} f(u) du + \frac{(1-\alpha)}{\beta(\alpha)} f(k) \right) \\
& = \frac{(\Omega - \pi)^2 f'(\pi) + (\Omega - \nu)^2 f'(\nu) + 2f(\Omega)(\nu - \pi) + 4[(\Omega - \pi)f(\pi) + (\Omega - \nu)f(\nu)]}{6} \\
& - \left[\left({}^{CF}I_{\pi}^{\alpha} f \right)(k) + \left({}^{CF}I_{\nu}^{\alpha} f \right)(k) \right].
\end{aligned}$$

Thus, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{(\Omega - \pi)^2 f'(\pi) - (\Omega - \nu)^2 f'(\nu) + 2f(\Omega)(\nu - \pi) + 4[(\Omega - \pi)f(\pi) + (\Omega - \nu)f(\nu)]}{6(\nu - \pi)} \\
& - \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(\nu - \pi)} \left[\left({}^{CF}I_{\pi}^{\alpha} f \right)(k) + \left({}^{CF}I_{\nu}^{\alpha} f \right)(k) \right] + \frac{2(1-\alpha)}{\alpha(\nu - \pi)} f(k) \\
& = \frac{1}{6(\nu - \pi)} \left[\int_0^1 \psi(1-\psi)^2 (\Omega - \pi)^4 f'''(\psi\Omega + (1-\psi)\pi) \right. \\
& \quad \left. - (\Omega - \nu)^4 f'''(\psi\Omega + (1-\psi)\nu) d\psi \right].
\end{aligned}$$

The proof of Lemma 2.1 is completed. \square

Theorem 2.1. Let assumptions of Lemma 2.1 hold. If $|f'''|$ is (α, m) -convex on $[\pi, \nu]$ and $(\alpha, m) \in (0, 1]^2$, then the following fractional inequality holds:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left| \frac{(\Omega - \pi)^2 f'(\pi) - (\Omega - \nu)^2 f'(\nu) + 2f(\Omega)(\nu - \pi) + 4[(\Omega - \pi)f(\pi) + (\Omega - \nu)f(\nu)]}{6(\nu - \pi)} \right. \\
& \quad \left. - \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(\nu - \pi)} \left[\left({}^{CF}I_{\pi}^{\alpha} f \right)(k) + \left({}^{CF}I_{\nu}^{\alpha} f \right)(k) \right] + \frac{2(1-\alpha)}{\alpha(\nu - \pi)} f(k) \right| \\
& \leq \frac{(\Omega - \pi)^4}{6(\nu - \pi)} \left[\frac{2}{\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha + 24} |f'''(\Omega)| + m \left(\frac{\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha}{12(\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha + 24)} \right) |f'''(\pi)| \right] \\
& \quad + \frac{(\Omega - \nu)^4}{6(\nu - \pi)} \left[\frac{2}{\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha + 24} |f'''(\Omega)| + m \left(\frac{\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha}{12(\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha + 24)} \right) |f'''(\nu)| \right].
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. By using the Lemma 2.1, since (α, m) -convexity of $|f'''|$, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left| \frac{(\Omega - \pi)^2 f'(\pi) - (\Omega - \nu)^2 f'(\nu) + 2f(\Omega)(\nu - \pi) + 4[(\Omega - \pi)f(\pi) + (\Omega - \nu)f(\nu)]}{6(\nu - \pi)} \right. \\
& \quad \left. - \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(\nu - \pi)} \left[\left({}^{CF}I_{\pi}^{\psi} f \right)(k) + \left({}^{CF}I_{\nu}^{\psi} f \right)(k) \right] + \frac{2(1-\alpha)}{\alpha(\nu - \pi)} f(k) \right| \\
& \leq \frac{(\Omega - \pi)^4}{6(\nu - \pi)} \left[\int_0^1 \psi(1-\psi)^2 (|f'''(\psi\Omega + (1-\psi)\pi)|) d\psi \right]
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + \frac{(\Omega - \nu)^4}{6(\nu - \pi)} \left[\int_0^1 \psi(1 - \psi)^2 (|f'''(\psi\Omega + (1 - \psi)\nu)|) d\psi \right] \\
\leq & \frac{(\Omega - \pi)^4}{6(\nu - \pi)} \left[\int_0^1 \psi(1 - \psi)^2 (\psi^\alpha |f'''(\Omega)| + m(1 - \psi^\alpha) |f'''(\pi)|) d\psi \right] \\
& + \frac{(\Omega - \nu)^4}{6(\nu - \pi)} \left[\int_0^1 \psi(1 - \psi)^2 (\psi^\alpha |f'''(\Omega)| + m(1 - \psi^\alpha) |f'''(\nu)|) d\psi \right] \\
\leq & \frac{(\Omega - \pi)^4}{6(\nu - \pi)} \left[\frac{2}{\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha + 24} |f'''(\Omega)| + m \left(\frac{\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha}{12(\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha + 24)} \right) |f'''(\pi)| \right] \\
& + \frac{(\Omega - \nu)^4}{6(\nu - \pi)} \left[\frac{2}{\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha + 24} |f'''(\Omega)| + m \left(\frac{\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha}{12(\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha + 24)} \right) |f'''(\nu)| \right].
\end{aligned}$$

The proof of Theorem 2.1 is completed. \square

Corollary 2.1. If we put $\Omega = \frac{\pi + \nu}{2}$ in Theorem 2.1, then we have

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left| \frac{\nu - \pi}{24} (f'(\pi) - f'(\nu)) + \frac{1}{3} \left(f(\pi) + f(\nu) + f\left(\frac{\pi + \nu}{2}\right) \right) \right. \\
& \quad \left. - \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(\nu - \pi)} \left[\left({}^{CF}I_\pi^\alpha f \right)(k) + \left({}^{CF}I_\nu^\alpha f \right)(k) \right] + \frac{2(1 - \alpha)}{\alpha(\nu - \pi)} f(k) \right| \\
\leq & \frac{(\nu - \pi)^3}{96} \left[\frac{2}{\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha + 24} \left| f''' \left(\frac{\pi + \nu}{2} \right) \right| + m \left(\frac{\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha}{12(\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha + 24)} \right) |f'''(\pi)| \right. \\
& \quad \left. + \frac{2}{\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha + 24} \left| f''' \left(\frac{\pi + \nu}{2} \right) \right| + m \left(\frac{\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha}{12(\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha + 24)} \right) |f'''(\nu)| \right].
\end{aligned}$$

Corollary 2.2. If we put $m = 1$ in Corollary 2.1, then we have

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left| \frac{\nu - \pi}{24} (f'(\pi) - f'(\nu)) + \frac{1}{3} \left(f(\pi) + f(\nu) + f\left(\frac{\pi + \nu}{2}\right) \right) \right. \\
& \quad \left. - \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(\nu - \pi)} \left[\left({}^{CF}I_\pi^\alpha f \right)(k) + \left({}^{CF}I_\nu^\alpha f \right)(k) \right] + \frac{2(1 - \alpha)}{\alpha(\nu - \pi)} f(k) \right| \\
\leq & \frac{(\nu - \pi)^3}{96} \left[\frac{2}{\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha + 24} \left| f''' \left(\frac{\pi + \nu}{2} \right) \right| + \left(\frac{\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha}{12(\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha + 24)} \right) |f'''(\pi)| \right. \\
& \quad \left. + \frac{2}{\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha + 24} \left| f''' \left(\frac{\pi + \nu}{2} \right) \right| + \left(\frac{\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha}{12(\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha + 24)} \right) |f'''(\nu)| \right].
\end{aligned}$$

Corollary 2.3. If we put $\alpha = 1$ in Corollary 2.2, then we have

$$\left| \frac{\nu - \pi}{24} (f'(\pi) - f'(\nu)) + \frac{1}{3} \left(f(\pi) + f(\nu) + f\left(\frac{\pi + \nu}{2}\right) \right) \right|$$

$$\begin{aligned} & -\frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(\nu-\pi)} \left[\left({}^{CF}I_{\pi}^{\alpha} f \right) (k) + \left({}^{CF}I_{\nu}^{\alpha} f \right) (k) \right] \Big| \\ & \leq \frac{(\nu-\pi)^3}{96} \left[\frac{1}{2} (|f'''(\pi)| + |f'''(\nu)|) + \frac{2}{3} \left| f''' \left(\frac{\pi+\nu}{2} \right) \right| \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 2.4. Applying again convexity in Corollary 2.3, then we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{\nu-\pi}{24} (f'(\pi) - f'(\nu)) + \frac{1}{3} \left(f(\pi) + f(\nu) + f \left(\frac{\pi+\nu}{2} \right) \right) \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(\nu-\pi)} \left[\left({}^{CF}I_{\pi}^{\alpha} f \right) (k) + \left({}^{CF}I_{\nu}^{\alpha} f \right) (k) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(\nu-\pi)^3}{1152} (|f'''(\pi)| + |f'''(\nu)|). \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 2.2. Suppose assumptions of Lemma 2.1 hold. If $|f'''|$ is (α, m) -convex on $[\pi, \nu]$, $(\alpha, m) \in (0, 1]^2$ and $q > 1$, then the following fractional inequality holds:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{(\Omega-\pi)^2 f'(\pi) - (\Omega-\nu)^2 f'(\nu) + 2f(\Omega)(\nu-\pi) + 4[(\Omega-\pi)f(\pi) + (\Omega-\nu)f(\nu)]}{6(\nu-\pi)} \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(\nu-\pi)} \left[\left({}^{CF}I_{\pi}^{\alpha} f \right) (k) + \left({}^{CF}I_{\nu}^{\alpha} f \right) (k) \right] + \frac{2(1-\alpha)}{\alpha(\nu-\pi)} f(k) \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(\Omega-\pi)^4}{6(\nu-\pi)} \left[\left(\frac{(\Gamma(1+p), \Gamma(1+2p))}{\Gamma(2+3p)} \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha+1} |f'''(\Omega)|^q + m \left(\frac{\alpha}{\alpha+1} \right) |f'''(\pi)|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \\ & \quad + \frac{(\Omega-\nu)^4}{6(\nu-\pi)} \left[\left(\frac{(\Gamma(1+p), \Gamma(1+2p))}{\Gamma(2+3p)} \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha+1} |f'''(\Omega)|^q + m \left(\frac{\alpha}{\alpha+1} \right) |f'''(\nu)|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. By employing the Hölder inequality since (α, m) -convexity of $|f'''|^q$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{(\Omega-\pi)^2 f'(\pi) - (\Omega-\nu)^2 f'(\nu) + 2f(\Omega)(\nu-\pi) + 4[(\Omega-\pi)f(\pi) + (\Omega-\nu)f(\nu)]}{6(\nu-\pi)} \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(\nu-\pi)} \left[\left({}^{CF}I_{\pi}^{\alpha} f \right) (k) + \left({}^{CF}I_{\nu}^{\alpha} f \right) (k) \right] + \frac{2(1-\alpha)}{\alpha(\nu-\pi)} f(k) \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(\Omega-\pi)^4}{6(\nu-\pi)} \left[\int_0^1 \psi(1-\psi)^2 (f'''(\psi\Omega + (1-\psi)\pi)) d\psi \right] \\ & \quad + \frac{(\Omega-\nu)^4}{6(\nu-\pi)} \left[\int_0^1 \psi(1-\psi)^2 (f'''(\psi\Omega + (1-\psi)\nu)) d\psi \right] \\ & \leq \frac{(\Omega-\pi)^4}{6(\nu-\pi)} \left[\left(\int_0^1 (\psi(1-\psi)^2)^p d\psi \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\int_0^1 (|f'''(\psi\Omega + (1-\psi)\pi)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} d\psi \right) \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \frac{(\Omega - \nu)^4}{6(\nu - \pi)} \left[\left(\int_0^1 (\psi(1 - \psi)^2)^p d\psi \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\int_0^1 (|f'''(\psi\Omega + (1 - \psi)\nu)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} d\psi \right) \right] \\
 \leq & \frac{(\Omega - \pi)^4}{6(\nu - \pi)} \left[\left(\int_0^1 (\psi(1 - \psi)^2)^p d\psi \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\int_0^1 \psi^\alpha |f'''(\Omega)|^q + m \int_0^1 (1 - \psi^\alpha) |f'''(\pi)|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} d\psi \right] \\
 & + \frac{(\Omega - \nu)^4}{6(\nu - \pi)} \left[\left(\int_0^1 (\psi(1 - \psi)^2)^p d\psi \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\int_0^1 \psi^\alpha |f'''(\Omega)|^q + m \int_0^1 (1 - \psi^\alpha) |f'''(\nu)|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} d\psi \right] \\
 \leq & \frac{(\Omega - \pi)^4}{6(\nu - \pi)} \left[\left(\frac{\Gamma(1 + p), \Gamma(1 + 2p)}{\Gamma(2 + 3p)} \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha + 1} |f'''(\Omega)|^q + m \left(\frac{\alpha}{\alpha + 1} \right) |f'''(\pi)|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \\
 & + \frac{(\Omega - \nu)^4}{6(\nu - \pi)} \left[\left(\frac{\Gamma(1 + p), \Gamma(1 + 2p)}{\Gamma(2 + 3p)} \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha + 1} |f'''(\Omega)|^q + m \left(\frac{\alpha}{\alpha + 1} \right) |f'''(\nu)|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right].
 \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof □

Corollary 2.5. If we selected $\Omega = \frac{\pi + \nu}{2}$ in Theorem 2.2, then we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \frac{\nu - \pi}{24} (f'(\pi) - f'(\nu)) + \frac{1}{3} \left(f(\pi) + f(\nu) + f\left(\frac{\pi + \nu}{2}\right) \right) \right. \\
 & \quad \left. - \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(\nu - \pi)} \left[({}^{CF}I_\pi^\alpha f)(k) + ({}^{CF}I_\nu^\alpha f)(k) \right] + \frac{2(1 - \alpha)}{\alpha(\nu - \pi)} f(k) \right| \\
 \leq & \frac{(\nu - \pi)^3}{96} \left(\frac{\Gamma(1 + p), \Gamma(1 + 2p)}{\Gamma(2 + 3p)} \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \\
 & \times \left[\left(\frac{1}{\alpha + 1} |f'''(\frac{\pi + \nu}{2})|^q + m \left(\frac{\alpha}{\alpha + 1} \right) |f'''(\pi)|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + \left(\frac{1}{\alpha + 1} |f'''(\frac{\pi + \nu}{2})|^q + m \left(\frac{\alpha}{\alpha + 1} \right) |f'''(\nu)|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right].
 \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 2.6. If we selected $m = 1$ in Corollary 2.5, then we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \frac{\nu - \pi}{24} (f'(\pi) - f'(\nu)) + \frac{1}{3} \left(f(\pi) + f(\nu) + f\left(\frac{\pi + \nu}{2}\right) \right) \right. \\
 & \quad \left. - \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(\nu - \pi)} \left[({}^{CF}I_\pi^\alpha f)(k) + ({}^{CF}I_\nu^\alpha f)(k) \right] + \frac{2(1 - \alpha)}{\alpha(\nu - \pi)} f(k) \right| \\
 \leq & \frac{(\nu - \pi)^3}{96} \left(\frac{\Gamma(1 + p), \Gamma(1 + 2p)}{\Gamma(2 + 3p)} \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \\
 & \times \left[\left(\frac{1}{\alpha + 1} |f'''(\frac{\pi + \nu}{2})|^q + \left(\frac{\alpha}{\alpha + 1} \right) |f'''(\pi)|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + \left(\frac{1}{\alpha + 1} |f'''(\frac{\pi + \nu}{2})|^q + \left(\frac{\alpha}{\alpha + 1} \right) |f'''(\nu)|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right].
 \end{aligned}$$

$$+ \left(\frac{1}{\alpha + 1} \left| f''' \left(\frac{\pi + \nu}{2} \right) \right|^q + \left(\frac{\alpha}{\alpha + 1} \right) |f'''(\nu)|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \Bigg].$$

Corollary 2.7. If we selected $\alpha = 1$ in Corollary 2.6, then we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{\nu - \pi}{24} (f'(\pi) - f'(\nu)) + \frac{1}{3} \left(f(\pi) + f(\nu) + f \left(\frac{\pi + \nu}{2} \right) \right) \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(\nu - \pi)} \left[\left({}^{CF}I_{\pi}^{\alpha} f \right) (k) + \left({}^{CF}I_{\nu}^{\alpha} f \right) (k) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(\nu - \pi)^3}{96} \left(\frac{\Gamma(1+p), \Gamma(1+2p)}{\Gamma(2+3p)} \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \\ & \times \left[\left(\frac{1}{2} \left| f''' \left(\frac{\pi + \nu}{2} \right) \right|^q + \frac{1}{2} |f'''(\pi)|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{1}{2} \left| f''' \left(\frac{\pi + \nu}{2} \right) \right|^q + \frac{1}{2} |f'''(\nu)|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 2.8. Applying again convexity in Corollary 2.7, then we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{\nu - \pi}{24} (f'(\pi) - f'(\nu)) + \frac{1}{3} \left(f(\pi) + f(\nu) + f \left(\frac{\pi + \nu}{2} \right) \right) \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(\nu - \pi)} \left[\left({}^{CF}I_{\pi}^{\alpha} f \right) (k) + \left({}^{CF}I_{\nu}^{\alpha} f \right) (k) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(\nu - \pi)^3}{96} \left(\frac{\Gamma(1+p), \Gamma(1+2p)}{\Gamma(2+3p)} \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \\ & \times \left[\left(\frac{3 |f'''(\pi)|^q + |f'''(\nu)|^q}{4} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{|f'''(\pi)|^q + 3 |f'''(\nu)|^q}{4} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 2.3. Under the assumptions of Lemma 2.1 hold. If $|f'''|$ is (α, m) -convex on $[\pi, \nu]$, $(\alpha, m) \in (0, 1]^2$ and $q \geq 1$, then the following fractional inequality holds:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{(\Omega - \pi)^2 f'(\pi) - (\Omega - \nu)^2 f'(\nu) + 2f(\Omega)(\nu - \pi) + 4[(\Omega - \pi)f(\pi) + (\Omega - \nu)f(\nu)]}{6(\nu - \pi)} \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(\nu - \pi)} \left[\left({}^{CF}I_{\pi}^{\alpha} f \right) (k) + \left({}^{CF}I_{\nu}^{\alpha} f \right) (k) \right] + \frac{2(1 - \alpha)}{\alpha(\nu - \pi)} f(k) \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(\Omega - \pi)^4}{6(\nu - \pi)} \left[\left(\frac{1}{12} \right)^{1 - \frac{1}{q}} \left(\frac{2}{\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha + 24} |f'''(\Omega)|^q + m \left(\frac{\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha}{12(\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha + 24)} \right) |f'''(\pi)|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \\ & \quad + \frac{(\Omega - \nu)^4}{6(\nu - \pi)} \left[\left(\frac{1}{12} \right)^{1 - \frac{1}{q}} \left(\frac{2}{\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha + 24} |f'''(\Omega)|^q + m \left(\frac{\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha}{12(\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha + 24)} \right) |f'''(\nu)|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. From Lemma 2.1, by utilizing the power-mean inequality, since $|f'''|^q$ is (α, m) -convexity, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{(\Omega - \pi)^2 f'(\pi) - (\Omega - \nu)^2 f'(\nu) + 2f(\Omega)(\nu - \pi) + 4[(\Omega - \pi)f(\pi) + (\Omega - \nu)f(\nu)]}{6(\nu - \pi)} \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(\nu - \pi)} \left[({}^{CF}I_\pi^\alpha f)(k) + ({}^{CF}I_\nu^\alpha f)(k) \right] + \frac{2(1 - \alpha)}{\alpha(\nu - \pi)} f(k) \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(\Omega - \pi)^4}{6(\nu - \pi)} \left[\int_0^1 \psi(1 - \psi)^2 (|f'''(\psi\Omega + (1 - \psi)\pi)|) d\psi \right] \\ & \quad + \frac{(\Omega - \nu)^4}{6(\nu - \pi)} \left[\int_0^1 \psi(1 - \psi)^2 (|f'''(\psi\Omega + (1 - \psi)\nu)|) d\psi \right] \\ & \leq \frac{(\Omega - \pi)^4}{6(\nu - \pi)} \left[\left(\int_0^1 \psi(1 - \psi)^2 d\psi \right)^{1 - \frac{1}{q}} \left(\int_0^1 \psi(1 - \psi)^2 (|f'''(\psi\Omega + (1 - \psi)\pi)|^q) d\psi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \\ & \quad + \frac{(\Omega - \nu)^4}{6(\nu - \pi)} \left[\left(\int_0^1 \psi(1 - \psi)^2 d\psi \right)^{1 - \frac{1}{q}} \left(\int_0^1 \psi(1 - \psi)^2 (|f'''(\psi\Omega + (1 - \psi)\nu)|^q) d\psi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \\ & \leq \frac{(\Omega - \pi)^4}{6(\nu - \pi)} \left[\left(\int_0^1 \psi(1 - \psi)^2 d\psi \right)^{1 - \frac{1}{q}} \left(\int_0^1 \psi(1 - \psi)^2 (\psi^\alpha |f'''(\Omega)|^q + m(1 - \psi^\alpha) |f'''(\pi)|^q) d\psi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \\ & \quad + \frac{(\Omega - \nu)^4}{6(\nu - \pi)} \left[\left(\int_0^1 \psi(1 - \psi)^2 d\psi \right)^{1 - \frac{1}{q}} \left(\int_0^1 \psi(1 - \psi)^2 (\psi^\alpha |f'''(\Omega)|^q + m(1 - \psi^\alpha) |f'''(\nu)|^q) d\psi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \\ & \leq \frac{(\Omega - \pi)^4}{6(\nu - \pi)} \left[\left(\frac{1}{12} \right)^{1 - \frac{1}{q}} \left(\frac{2}{\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha + 24} |f'''(\Omega)|^q + m \left(\frac{\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha}{12(\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha + 24)} \right) |f'''(\pi)|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \\ & \quad + \frac{(\Omega - \nu)^4}{6(\nu - \pi)} \left[\left(\frac{1}{12} \right)^{1 - \frac{1}{q}} \left(\frac{2}{\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha + 24} |f'''(\Omega)|^q + m \left(\frac{\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha}{12(\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha + 24)} \right) |f'''(\nu)|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof. □

Corollary 2.9. If we selected $\Omega = \frac{\pi + \nu}{2}$ in Theorem 2.3, then we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{\nu - \pi}{24} (f'(\pi) - f'(\nu)) + \frac{1}{3} \left(f(\pi) + f(\nu) + f\left(\frac{\pi + \nu}{2}\right) \right) \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(\nu - \pi)} \left[({}^{CF}I_\pi^\alpha f)(k) + ({}^{CF}I_\nu^\alpha f)(k) \right] + \frac{2(1 - \alpha)}{\alpha(\nu - \pi)} f(k) \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(\nu - \pi)^3}{96} \left(\frac{1}{12} \right)^{1 - \frac{1}{q}} \end{aligned}$$

$$\times \left[\left(\frac{2}{\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha + 24} \left| f''' \left(\frac{\pi + \nu}{2} \right) \right|^q + m \left(\frac{\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha}{12(\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha + 24)} \right) |f'''(\pi)|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\ \left. + \left(\frac{2}{\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha + 24} \left| f''' \left(\frac{\pi + \nu}{2} \right) \right|^q + m \left(\frac{\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha}{12(\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha + 24)} \right) |f'''(\nu)|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right].$$

Corollary 2.10. If we selected $m = 1$ in Corollary 2.9, then we have

$$\left| \frac{\nu - \pi}{24} (f'(\pi) - f'(\nu)) + \frac{1}{3} \left(f(\pi) + f(\nu) + f \left(\frac{\pi + \nu}{2} \right) \right) \right. \\ \left. - \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(\nu - \pi)} \left[({}^{CF}I_{\pi}^{\alpha} f)(k) + ({}^{CF}I_{\nu}^{\alpha} f)(k) \right] + \frac{2(1 - \alpha)}{\alpha(\nu - \pi)} f(k) \right| \\ \leq \frac{(\nu - \pi)^3}{96} \left(\frac{1}{12} \right)^{1 - \frac{1}{q}} \\ \times \left[\left(\frac{2}{\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha + 24} \left| f''' \left(\frac{\pi + \nu}{2} \right) \right|^q + \left(\frac{\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha}{12(\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha + 24)} \right) |f'''(\pi)|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\ \left. + \left(\frac{2}{\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha + 24} \left| f''' \left(\frac{\pi + \nu}{2} \right) \right|^q + \left(\frac{\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha}{12(\alpha^3 + 9\alpha^2 + 26\alpha + 24)} \right) |f'''(\nu)|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right].$$

Corollary 2.11. If we selected $\alpha = 1$ in Corollary 2.10, then we have

$$\left| \frac{\nu - \pi}{24} (f'(\pi) - f'(\nu)) + \frac{1}{3} \left(f(\pi) + f(\nu) + f \left(\frac{\pi + \nu}{2} \right) \right) \right. \\ \left. - \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(\nu - \pi)} \left[({}^{CF}I_{\pi}^{\alpha} f)(k) + ({}^{CF}I_{\nu}^{\alpha} f)(k) \right] \right| \\ \leq \frac{(\nu - \pi)^3}{96} \left(\frac{1}{12} \right)^{1 - \frac{1}{q}} \left[\frac{1}{2} (|f'''(\pi)|^q + |f'''(\nu)|^q) + \frac{2}{3} \left| f''' \left(\frac{\pi + \nu}{2} \right) \right|^q \right]^{\frac{1}{q}}.$$

Corollary 2.12. Applying again convexity in Corollary 2.11, then we have

$$\left| \frac{\nu - \pi}{24} (f'(\pi) - f'(\nu)) + \frac{1}{3} \left(f(\pi) + f(\nu) + f \left(\frac{\pi + \nu}{2} \right) \right) \right. \\ \left. - \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(\nu - \pi)} \left[({}^{CF}I_{\pi}^{\alpha} f)(k) + ({}^{CF}I_{\nu}^{\alpha} f)(k) \right] \right| \\ \leq \frac{(\nu - \pi)^3}{96} \left(\frac{1}{12} \right)^{1 - \frac{1}{q}} \left[\left(\frac{5|f'''(\pi)|^q + |f'''(\nu)|^q}{6} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{|f'''(\pi)|^q + 5|f'''(\nu)|^q}{6} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right].$$

Theorem 2.4. Suppose assumptions of Lemma 2.1 hold. If $|f'''|$ is (α, m) -convex on

$[\pi, \nu], (\alpha, m) \in (0, 1]^2$ and $q > 1$, then the following fractional inequality holds:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{(\Omega - \pi)^2 f'(\pi) - (\Omega - \nu)^2 f'(\nu) + 2f(\Omega)(\nu - \pi) + 4[(\Omega - \pi)f(\pi) + (\Omega - \nu)f(\nu)]}{6(\nu - \pi)} \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(\nu - \pi)} \left[\left({}^{CF}I_{\pi}^{\alpha} f \right)(k) + \left({}^{CF}I_{\nu}^{\alpha} f \right)(k) \right] + \frac{2(1 - \alpha)}{\alpha(\nu - \pi)} f(k) \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(\Omega - \pi)^4}{6(\nu - \pi)} \left[\frac{1}{p} \left(\frac{\Gamma(1 + p), \Gamma(1 + 2p)}{\Gamma(2 + 3p)} \right) + \frac{1}{q} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha + 1} |f'''(\Omega)|^q + m \left(\frac{\alpha}{\alpha + 1} \right) |f'''(\pi)|^q \right) \right] \\ & \quad + \frac{(\Omega - \nu)^4}{6(\nu - \pi)} \left[\frac{1}{p} \left(\frac{\Gamma(1 + p), \Gamma(1 + 2p)}{\Gamma(2 + 3p)} \right) + \frac{1}{q} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha + 1} |f'''(\Omega)|^q + m \left(\frac{\alpha}{\alpha + 1} \right) |f'''(\nu)|^q \right) \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. From Lemma 2.1, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{(\Omega - \pi)^2 f'(\pi) - (\Omega - \nu)^2 f'(\nu) + 2f(\Omega)(\nu - \pi) + 4[(\Omega - \pi)f(\pi) + (\Omega - \nu)f(\nu)]}{6(\nu - \pi)} \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(\nu - \pi)} \left[\left({}^{CF}I_{\pi}^{\alpha} f \right)(k) + \left({}^{CF}I_{\nu}^{\alpha} f \right)(k) \right] + \frac{2(1 - \alpha)}{\alpha(\nu - \pi)} f(k) \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(\Omega - \pi)^4}{6(\nu - \pi)} \left[\int_0^1 \psi(1 - \psi)^2 (|f'''(\psi\Omega + (1 - \psi)\pi)|) d\psi \right] \\ & \quad + \frac{(\Omega - \nu)^4}{6(\nu - \pi)} \left[\int_0^1 \psi(1 - \psi)^2 (|f'''(\psi\Omega + (1 - \psi)\nu)|) d\psi \right]. \end{aligned}$$

By using the Young's inequality

$$\pi\nu \leq \frac{1}{p}\pi^p + \frac{1}{q}\nu^q,$$

we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{(\Omega - \pi)^2 f'(\pi) - (\Omega - \nu)^2 f'(\nu) + 2f(\Omega)(\nu - \pi) + 4[(\Omega - \pi)f(\pi) + (\Omega - \nu)f(\nu)]}{6(\nu - \pi)} \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(\nu - \pi)} \left[\left({}^{CF}I_{\pi}^{\alpha} f \right)(k) + \left({}^{CF}I_{\nu}^{\alpha} f \right)(k) \right] + \frac{2(1 - \alpha)}{\alpha(\nu - \pi)} f(k) \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(\Omega - \pi)^4}{6(\nu - \pi)} \left[\int_0^1 \psi(1 - \psi)^2 (|f'''(\psi\Omega + (1 - \psi)\pi)|) d\psi \right] \\ & \quad + \frac{(\Omega - \nu)^4}{6(\nu - \pi)} \left[\int_0^1 \psi(1 - \psi)^2 (|f'''(\psi\Omega + (1 - \psi)\nu)|) d\psi \right] \\ & \leq \frac{(\Omega - \pi)^4}{6(\nu - \pi)} \left[\frac{1}{p} \left(\int_0^1 [\psi(1 - \psi)^2]^p d\psi \right) + \frac{1}{q} \left(\int_0^1 (|f'''(\psi\Omega + (1 - \psi)\pi)|^q) d\psi \right) \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + \frac{(\Omega - \nu)^4}{6(\nu - \pi)} \left[\frac{1}{p} \left(\int_0^1 [\psi(1 - \psi)^2]^p d\psi \right) + \frac{1}{q} \left(\int_0^1 (|f'''(\psi\Omega + (1 - \psi)\nu)|^q) d\psi \right) \right] \\
\leq & \frac{(\Omega - \pi)^4}{6(\nu - \pi)} \left[\frac{1}{p} \left(\int_0^1 [\psi(1 - \psi)^2]^p d\psi \right) + \frac{1}{q} \left(\int_0^1 \psi^\alpha |f'''(\Omega)|^q + m \int_0^1 (1 - \psi^\alpha) |f'''(\pi)|^q d\psi \right) \right] \\
& + \frac{(\Omega - \pi)^4}{6(\nu - \pi)} \left[\frac{1}{p} \left(\int_0^1 [\psi(1 - \psi)^2]^p d\psi \right) + \frac{1}{q} \left(\int_0^1 \psi^\alpha |f'''(\Omega)|^q + m \int_0^1 (1 - \psi^\alpha) |f'''(\nu)|^q d\psi \right) \right] \\
\leq & \frac{(\Omega - \pi)^4}{6(\nu - \pi)} \left[\frac{1}{p} \left(\frac{\Gamma(1 + p), \Gamma(1 + 2p)}{\Gamma(2 + 3p)} \right) + \frac{1}{q} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha + 1} |f'''(\Omega)|^q + m \left(\frac{\alpha}{\alpha + 1} \right) |f'''(\pi)|^q \right) \right] \\
& + \frac{(\Omega - \nu)^4}{6(\nu - \pi)} \left[\frac{1}{p} \left(\frac{\Gamma(1 + p), \Gamma(1 + 2p)}{\Gamma(2 + 3p)} \right) + \frac{1}{q} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha + 1} |f'''(\Omega)|^q + m \left(\frac{\alpha}{\alpha + 1} \right) |f'''(\nu)|^q \right) \right].
\end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof. \square

Corollary 2.13. If we choice $\Omega = \frac{\pi + \nu}{2}$ in Theorem 2.4, then we have

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left| \frac{\nu - \pi}{24} (f'(\pi) - f'(\nu)) + \frac{1}{3} \left(f(\pi) + f(\nu) + f\left(\frac{\pi + \nu}{2}\right) \right) \right. \\
& \quad \left. - \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(\nu - \pi)} \left[({}^{CF}I_\pi^\alpha f)(k) + ({}^{CF}I_\nu^\alpha f)(k) \right] + \frac{2(1 - \alpha)}{\alpha(\nu - \pi)} f(k) \right| \\
\leq & \frac{(\nu - \pi)^3}{96} \\
& \times \left[\frac{1}{p} \left(\frac{\Gamma(1 + p), \Gamma(1 + 2p)}{\Gamma(2 + 3p)} \right) + \frac{1}{q} \left\{ \frac{1}{\alpha + 1} \left| f''' \left(\frac{\pi + \nu}{2} \right) \right|^q + m \left(\frac{\alpha}{\alpha + 1} \right) |f'''(\pi)|^q \right\} \right. \\
& \left. + \frac{1}{p} \left(\frac{\Gamma(1 + p), \Gamma(1 + 2p)}{\Gamma(2 + 3p)} \right) + \frac{1}{q} \left\{ \frac{1}{\alpha + 1} \left| f''' \left(\frac{\pi + \nu}{2} \right) \right|^q + m \left(\frac{\alpha}{\alpha + 1} \right) |f'''(\nu)|^q \right\} \right].
\end{aligned}$$

Corollary 2.14. If we choice $m = \alpha = 1$ in Corollary 2.13, then we have

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left| \frac{\nu - \pi}{24} (f'(\pi) - f'(\nu)) + \frac{1}{3} \left(f(\pi) + f(\nu) + f\left(\frac{\pi + \nu}{2}\right) \right) \right. \\
& \quad \left. - \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(\nu - \pi)} \left[({}^{CF}I_\pi^\alpha f)(k) + ({}^{CF}I_\nu^\alpha f)(k) \right] \right| \\
\leq & \frac{(\nu - \pi)^3}{96} \left[\frac{1}{p} \left(\frac{\Gamma(1 + p), \Gamma(1 + 2p)}{\Gamma(2 + 3p)} \right) + \frac{1}{2q} \left\{ \left| f''' \left(\frac{\pi + \nu}{2} \right) \right|^q + |f'''(\nu)|^q \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. + \left(\left| f''' \left(\frac{\pi + \nu}{2} \right) \right|^q + |f'''(\nu)|^q \right) \right\} \right].
\end{aligned}$$

Theorem 2.5. Under the assumptions of Lemma 2.1 hold. If $f''' \in L[\pi, \nu]$ and $|f'''|$ is concave on $[\pi, \nu]$, then the following fractional inequality holds:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{(\Omega - \pi)^2 f'(\pi) - (\Omega - \nu)^2 f'(\nu) + 2f(\Omega)(\nu - \pi) + 4[(\Omega - \pi)f(\pi) + (\Omega - \nu)f(\nu)]}{6(\nu - \pi)} \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(\nu - \pi)} \left[\left({}^{CF}I_{\pi}^{\alpha} f \right)(k) + \left({}^{CF}I_{\nu}^{\alpha} f \right)(k) \right] + \frac{2(1 - \alpha)}{\alpha(\nu - \pi)} f(k) \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(\Omega - \pi)^4}{60(\nu - \pi)} \left[\left| f''' \left(\frac{5\Omega + \pi}{6} \right) \right| \right] + \frac{(\Omega - \nu)^4}{60(\nu - \pi)} \left[\left| f''' \left(\frac{5\Omega + \nu}{6} \right) \right| \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. From Lemma 2.1, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{(\Omega - \pi)^2 f'(\pi) - (\Omega - \nu)^2 f'(\nu) + 2f(\Omega)(\nu - \pi) + 4[(\Omega - \pi)f(\pi) + (\Omega - \nu)f(\nu)]}{6(\nu - \pi)} \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(\nu - \pi)} \left[\left({}^{CF}I_{\pi}^{\alpha} f \right)(k) + \left({}^{CF}I_{\nu}^{\alpha} f \right)(k) \right] + \frac{2(1 - \alpha)}{\alpha(\nu - \pi)} f(k) \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(\Omega - \pi)^4}{6(\nu - \pi)} \left[\int_0^1 \psi(1 - \psi)^2 (|f'''(\psi\Omega + (1 - \psi)\nu)|) d\psi \right] \\ & \quad + \frac{(\Omega - \nu)^4}{6(\nu - \pi)} \left[\int_0^1 \psi(1 - \psi)^2 (|f'''(\psi\Omega + (1 - \psi)\pi)|) d\psi \right]. \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

By using the Jensen inequality, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^1 |f'''(\psi\Omega + (1 - \psi)\nu)| d\psi & \leq \left[\left(\int_0^1 \psi(1 - \psi)^2 d\psi \right) \left| f''' \left(\frac{\int_0^1 \psi(1 - \psi)^2 (\psi\Omega + (1 - \psi)\pi) d\psi}{\int_0^1 \psi(1 - \psi)^2 d\psi} \right) \right| \right] \\ & \leq \left| f''' \left(\frac{5\Omega + \pi}{6} \right) \right|. \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

Similarly, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^1 |f'''(\psi\Omega + (1 - \psi)\nu)| d\psi & \leq \left[\left(\int_0^1 \psi(1 - \psi)^2 d\psi \right) \left| f''' \left(\frac{\int_0^1 \psi(1 - \psi)^2 (\psi\Omega + (1 - \psi)\nu) d\psi}{\int_0^1 \psi(1 - \psi)^2 d\psi} \right) \right| \right] \\ & \leq \left| f''' \left(\frac{5\Omega + \nu}{6} \right) \right|. \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

Using the equalities (5) and (6) in (4), we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{(\Omega - \pi)^2 f'(\pi) - (\Omega - \nu)^2 f'(\nu) + 2f(\Omega)(\nu - \pi) + 4[(\Omega - \pi)f(\pi) + (\Omega - \nu)f(\nu)]}{6(\nu - \pi)} \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(\nu - \pi)} \left[\left({}^{CF}I_{\pi}^{\alpha} f \right)(k) + \left({}^{CF}I_{\nu}^{\alpha} f \right)(k) \right] + \frac{2(1 - \alpha)}{\alpha(\nu - \pi)} f(k) \right| \end{aligned}$$

$$\leq \frac{(\Omega - \pi)^4}{60(\nu - \pi)} \left[\left| f''' \left(\frac{5\Omega + \pi}{6} \right) \right| \right] + \frac{(\Omega - \nu)^4}{60(\nu - \pi)} \left[\left| f''' \left(\frac{5\Omega + \nu}{6} \right) \right| \right].$$

This completes the proof. \square

Corollary 2.15. If we choice $\Omega = \frac{\pi + \nu}{2}$ in Theorem 2.5, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{\nu - \pi}{24} (f'(\pi) - f'(\nu)) + \frac{1}{3} \left(f(\pi) + f(\nu) + f \left(\frac{\pi + \nu}{2} \right) \right) \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\beta(\alpha)}{\alpha(\nu - \pi)} \left[\left({}^{CF}I_{\pi}^{\alpha} f \right) (k) + \left({}^{CF}I_{\nu}^{\alpha} f \right) (k) \right] + \frac{2(1 - \alpha)}{\alpha(\nu - \pi)} f(k) \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(\nu - \pi)^3}{960} \left[\left| f''' \left(\frac{7\pi + 5\nu}{12} \right) \right| + \left| f''' \left(\frac{5\pi + 7\nu}{12} \right) \right| \right]. \end{aligned}$$

3 Quadrature formula

Let d is the partition of the interval $[\pi, \nu]$, $d : \pi = \Omega_0 < \Omega_1 < \Omega_2 < \dots < \Omega_{n-1} < \Omega_n = \nu$ and Let the

$$\int_{\pi}^{\nu} f(\Omega) d\Omega = Z(f, d) + R(f, d),$$

where

$$Z(f, d) = \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \left[\frac{\Omega_{i+1} - \Omega_i}{24} (f'(\Omega_i) - f'(\Omega_{i+1})) + \frac{1}{3} \left(f'(\Omega_i) + f'(\Omega_{i+1}) + f \left(\frac{\Omega_i + \Omega_{i+1}}{2} \right) \right) \right],$$

where the approximation error $R(f, d)$ of the interval I .

Proposition 3.1. Under the assumptions of Lemma 2.1, then in Corollary 2.3 for every division d of $[\pi, \nu]$, then the following inequality holds:

$$|R(f, d)| \leq \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \frac{(\Omega_{i+1} - \Omega_i)^3}{96} \left[\frac{1}{2} (|f'''(\Omega_i)| + |f'''(\Omega_{i+1})|) + \frac{2}{3} \left| f''' \left(\frac{\Omega_i + \Omega_{i+1}}{2} \right) \right| \right].$$

Proof. Applying the Corollary 2.3 on the subinterval $[\Omega_i, \Omega_{i+1}]$, ($i = 0, 1, 2, 3, \dots, n-1$) and $\alpha = 1$, $\beta(0) = \beta(1) = 1$, we have

$$\left| \left[\frac{\Omega_{i+1} - \Omega_i}{24} (f'(\Omega_i) - f'(\Omega_{i+1})) + \frac{1}{3} \left(f'(\Omega_i) + f'(\Omega_{i+1}) + f \left(\frac{\Omega_i + \Omega_{i+1}}{2} \right) \right) \right] - \int_{\Omega_i}^{\Omega_{i+1}} f(\Omega) d\Omega \right| \quad (7)$$

$$\leq \frac{(\Omega_{i+1} - \Omega_i)^3}{96} \left[\frac{1}{2} (|f'''(\Omega_i)| + |f'''(\Omega_{i+1})|) + \frac{2}{3} \left| f''' \left(\frac{\Omega_i + \Omega_{i+1}}{2} \right) \right| \right].$$

Summing over i from 0 to $n - 1$, we deduce by the triangle inequality, we attained the result.

This completes the proof. □

4 Conclusion

Convexity and fractional integral operators are indeed important mathematical tools used to deal with integral inequalities and related problems in mathematical analysis. This paper is to derive a new perturbed trapezoid-type inequalities by using the Caputo-Fabrizio fractional integral. First of all, we give an integral identity that is essential in order to establish the main finding of the article. Using the Caputo-Fabrizio fractional integral, some perturbed trapezoid-type inequalities are investigated for three times differentiable convex functions. In addition, the research has acquired fractional perturbed trapezoid-type inequalities for (α, m) -convex function. Furthermore, we have given application to the quadrature formula. In future work, it would be fascinating to apply these findings to other convexities and fractional operators for example modified Atangana Baleanu, k -Riemann-Liouville, Katugampola and Conformable.

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7 Authors contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration between all authors. All authors defined the research theme, read and approved the manuscript.

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Novel Approaches to Dual Simpson-Type Inequalities via Caputo-Fabrizio Fractional Operators for Different Classes of Functions and Application

Artion Kashuri¹, Arslan Munir², Hüseyin Budak³

¹Department of Mathematical Engineering, Polytechnic University of Tirana, 1001 Tirana, Albania

²School of Mathematical Sciences, University of Science and Technology of China, Hefei 230026 People's Republic of China

³Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Science and Arts, Kocaeli University, Kocaeli 41001, Türkiye

Corresponding author: munirarслан999@gmail.com

ORCID IDs:

First Author: [0000-0003-0115-3079](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0115-3079)

Second Author: [0009-0008-8148-5607](https://orcid.org/0009-0008-8148-5607)

Third Author: [0000-0001-8843-955X](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8843-955X)

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Abstract

Integral inequalities are indeed a powerful tool in the context of numerical integration and quadrature methods. The study of fractional calculus continues to be an active area of research with practical implications for real-world applications. When combined with fractional operators, these integral inequalities become even more valuable in the analysis and estimation of errors in fractional calculus. The Caputo-Fabrizio fractional integral operator is one of the key concepts in fractional calculus. In the present study, we established a new identity through the fractional operator. By using this novel identity, some new error estimations of dual-Simpson type inequalities are obtained for the case of differentiable functions. Based on this identity, dual-Simpson type inequalities are proved for bounded as well as Lipschitzian functions. In addition, we demonstrate an application of our findings to the quadrature formula.

Keywords: Dual Simpson-type inequalities, Caputo-Fabrizio fractional integrals, s -

convex function, Hölder's inequality, power-mean inequality, Young's inequality, bounded function, Lipschitzian function, quadrature formula.

1 Introduction and Preliminaries

Convexity is indeed one of the most fundamental principles in analysis and mathematics. It plays a crucial role in various areas of pure and applied sciences, including optimization, functional analysis, numerical analysis, economics, physics, engineering, and the domain of inequalities. In all these fields, convexity allows for the development of important results. Convexity ensures that certain properties hold, making the analysis more tractable and providing powerful tools for solving problems. For interested researchers on convexity and integral inequalities, we refer to articles [1, 2, 3]. A function $f : I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is said to be convex if the inequality holds:

$$f(\Upsilon\Psi + (1 - \Upsilon)b) \leq \Upsilon f(\Psi) + (1 - \Upsilon)f(b),$$

for all $\Psi, b \in I$ and $\Upsilon \in [0, 1]$. In [4] Hudzik introduced the generalized convexity known as s -convexity. The function $f : \mathbb{R}^+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, where $\mathbb{R}^+ = [0, +\infty)$, is called to be s -convex in the second sense for a fixed real number $s \in (0, 1]$ for all $\Psi, b \in I$ and $\Upsilon \in [0, 1]$, if

$$f(\Upsilon\Psi + (1 - \Upsilon)b) \leq \Upsilon^s f(\Psi) + (1 - \Upsilon)^s f(b).$$

Inequality theory is well-known and still an interesting area of research with a wide range of applications in many fields of mathematics. In the last few decades, various authors have been interested in generalizing the different types of inequalities, the Simpson-type inequality is one of these. The classical Simpson-type inequality deals with the error term of Simpson's Rule and provides an upper bound for the error between the true value of the integral and the approximation obtained through Simpson's rule. We delineate three primary formulations as follows:

- (1) Simpson's quadrature formula (Simpson's 1/3 rule) is stated as follows:

$$\int_{\Psi}^b f(\Phi) d\Phi \approx \frac{b - \Psi}{6} \left[f(\Psi) + 4f\left(\frac{\Psi + b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right].$$

- (2) Simpson's second formula or the Newton-cotes quadrature formula (Simpson's

3/8 rule) is stated as follows:

$$\int_{\Psi}^b f(\Phi) d\Phi \approx \frac{b-\Psi}{8} \left[f(\Psi) + 3f\left(\frac{2\Psi+b}{2}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{\Psi+2b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right].$$

The most important Newton-cotes quadrature that attained three-point Simpson-type inequality is described as follows:

Theorem 1.1. Suppose $f : [\Psi, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a four times differentiable function and continuous on (Ψ, b) and let $\|f^{(4)}\|_{\infty} := \sup_{\Phi \in (\Psi, b)} |f^{(4)}(\Phi)| < \infty$, then

$$\left| \left[\frac{f(\Psi)}{6} + \frac{4}{6}f\left(\frac{\Psi+b}{2}\right) + \frac{f(b)}{6} \right] - \frac{1}{b-\Psi} \int_{\Psi}^b f(\Phi) d\Phi \right| \leq \frac{1}{2880} \|f^{(4)}\|_{\infty} (b-\Psi)^4.$$

Overall, Simpson-type inequalities have been a subject of interest for researchers across different mathematical fields due to their practical relevance and theoretical significance. The study of Simpson-type inequalities for convex functions is an important area of research that contributes to the broader field of convex analysis. Simpson-type inequalities are a class of inequalities that involve certain functions and their properties, they are related to similar inequality to s -convex functions obtained [5]. Then, using differentiable convex mapping, Sarikaya *et al.* established new versions of Simpson-type inequalities [6, 7]. Du *et al.* in [8] proved the Simpson's inequalities using the extended (s, m) -convex functions for differentiable mapping. Furthermore, İşcan *et al.* [9] established Simpson-type inequalities and giving new error bounds using the harmonically convex functions. Additionally, a few works [9, 10] looked at the Simpson-type inequalities for different convex classes.

Fractional calculus has gained significant attention and found applications in various fields over the last few decades. In pure and applied mathematics, fractional calculus is an active area of research, with mathematicians studying the properties of fractional derivatives, fractional differential equations, fractional integrals, fractional operators, and their connections to other areas of mathematics, such as fractional calculus on fractals. By incorporating fractional derivatives and integrals, researchers and practitioners can capture complex behaviors that cannot be adequately described by classical integer-order calculus. Many real dynamical systems exhibit behaviors that are better described and characterized by using non-integer order dynamical models based on fractional calculus. While fractional calculus has proven to be a valuable tool in various applications, it is important to note that it is not a replacement for classical integer-order calculus. Instead, it complements the traditional methods and provides additional flexibility to describe and

understand more complex systems in nature. One can analysis many fractional integral inequalities in great detail because of the significance of fractional calculus as indicated in this paragraph. For instance, the Simpson inequality for differentiable functions to Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals were discussed by the authors in [11] and [12]. Abdeljawad *et al.* [13] obtained the new Simpson inequalities for generalized p -convex function on fractal sets with applications. Ertugral *et al.* [14] developed Simpson-type inequalities in the case of different using the generalized fractional integral. As a result, numerous studies are devoted to fractional Simpson inequalities in the case of different fractional integral operators [15]. Lei *et al.* [16] produced an estimate of the remainder for Simpson inequality via k -fractional integrals. Furthermore, several fractional Simpson type inequalities for functions with convex second derivatives in absolute value were demonstrated in the article [17]. For more on Simpson-type inequalities and other characteristics of Riemann-Liouville fractional integral, readers might see [18, 19] and its references. For additional research on Simpson-type inequality, see these articles [20, 21]. Sarikaya *et al.* [22] proved several Simpson-type inequalities for functions whose second derivatives are convex. Before we start to our main results, first we give the definitions of Riemann-Liouville fractional and Caputo-Fabrizio fractional integral operators as follows:

Definition 1.1. [23] Suppose $f \in L[\Psi, b]$. The Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals of order $\xi > 0$ are defined by:

$$I_{\Psi+}^{\xi} f(\Upsilon) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\xi)} \int_{\Psi}^{\Phi} (\Phi - \Upsilon)^{\xi-1} f(\Upsilon) d\Upsilon, \quad \Phi > \Psi,$$

$$I_{b-}^{\xi} f(\Upsilon) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\xi)} \int_{\Phi}^b (\Upsilon - \Phi)^{\xi-1} f(\Upsilon) d\Upsilon, \quad \Phi < b,$$

where $\Gamma(\xi)$ is the gamma function and $I_{\Psi+}^0 f(\Upsilon) = I_{b-}^0 f(\Upsilon) = f(\Upsilon)$.

Definition 1.2. [24] Let $H^1(\Psi, b)$ be the Sobolev space of order one defined as:

$$H^1(\Psi, b) := \left\{ g \in L^2(\Psi, b) : g' \in L^2(\Psi, b) \right\},$$

where

$$L^2(\Psi, b) := \left\{ g(z) : \left(\int_{\Psi}^b g^2(z) dz \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} < \infty \right\}.$$

Let $f \in H^1(\Psi, b)$, $\Psi < b$, $\xi \in [0, 1]$, then the notion of left derivative in the sense of

Caputo-Fabrizio is defined as:

$$\left({}_{\Psi}^{CFD}D^{\xi}f\right)(\Phi)=\frac{\beta(\xi)}{1-\xi}\int_{\Psi}^{\Phi}f'(\Upsilon)e^{\frac{-\xi(\Phi-\Upsilon)\xi}{1-\xi}}d\Upsilon$$

and the associated integral operator is

$$\left({}_{\Psi}^{CF}I^{\xi}f\right)(\Phi)=\frac{1-\xi}{\beta(\xi)}f(\Phi)+\frac{\xi}{\beta(\xi)}\int_{\Psi}^{\Phi}f(\Upsilon)d\Upsilon,$$

where $\beta(\xi) > 0$ is the normalization function satisfying $\beta(0) = \beta(1) = 1$. For $\xi = 0$, $\xi = 1$, the left derivative is defined as follows, respectively

$$\begin{aligned}\left({}_{\Psi}^{CFD}D^0f\right)(\Phi) &= f'(\Phi) \\ \left({}_{\Psi}^{CFD}D^1f\right)(\Phi) &= f(\Phi) - f(\Psi).\end{aligned}$$

For the right derivative operator

$$\left({}_b^{CFD}D^{\xi}f\right)(\Phi)=\frac{\beta(\xi)}{1-\xi}\int_{\Phi}^b f'(\Upsilon)e^{\frac{-\xi(b-\Phi)\xi}{1-\xi}}d\Upsilon$$

and the associated integral operator is

$$\left({}_b^{CF}I^{\xi}f\right)(\Phi)=\frac{1-\xi}{\beta(\xi)}f(\Phi)+\frac{\xi}{\beta(\xi)}\int_{\Phi}^b f(\Upsilon)d\Upsilon,$$

where $\beta(\alpha) > 0$ is a normalization function that satisfies $\beta(0) = \beta(1) = 1$.

This research article aims to established an identity for Caputo-Fabrizio fractional integral operator. By utilizing this identity, we will show some dual Simpson type inequalities for differentiable functions whose derivatives are convex. Moreover, dual Simpson type inequalities will be obtained for different classes of functions, such as convex, bounded, and Lipschitzian. Furthermore, we will give an application to the quadrature formula.

2 Dual-Simpson type Inequalities for Differentiable Convex Functions

In this section, we present several fractional inequalities of dual-Simpson type to a differentiable function.

Lemma 2.1. Let $f : [\Psi, mb] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a differentiable function on $[\Psi, mb]$ with $\Psi < mb$ and $f' \in L[\Psi, mb]$, then the following equality holds true:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[\frac{2}{3}f\left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4}\right) - \frac{1}{3}f\left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2}\right) + \frac{2}{3}f\left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4}\right) \right] \\ & - \frac{\beta(\xi)}{\xi(mb - \Psi)} \left[({}^{CF}I_{\Psi}^{\xi} f)(k) + ({}^{CF}I_{mb}^{\xi} f)(k) \right] + \frac{2(1 - \xi)}{\xi(mb - \Psi)} f(k) \\ = & \frac{b - \Psi}{16} \left[\int_0^1 \Upsilon f' \left((1 - \Upsilon)\Psi + \Upsilon \frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) d\Upsilon \right. \\ & + \int_0^1 \left(\Upsilon - \frac{5}{3} \right) f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} + \Upsilon \frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) d\Upsilon \\ & + \int_0^1 \left(\Upsilon + \frac{2}{3} \right) f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{\Psi + mb}{2} + \Upsilon \frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) d\Upsilon \\ & \left. + \int_0^1 (\Upsilon - 1) f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} + m\Upsilon b \right) d\Upsilon \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} I &= \int_0^1 \Upsilon f' \left((1 - \Upsilon)\Psi + \Upsilon \frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) d\Upsilon, \\ &+ \int_0^1 \left(\Upsilon - \frac{5}{3} \right) f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} + \Upsilon \frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) d\Upsilon, \\ &+ \int_0^1 \left(\Upsilon + \frac{2}{3} \right) f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{\Psi + mb}{2} + \Upsilon \frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) d\Upsilon, \\ &+ \int_0^1 (\Upsilon - 1) f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} + m\Upsilon b \right) d\Upsilon, \\ I &= I_1 + I_2 + I_3 + I_4. \end{aligned}$$

By using the integration by parts, we get

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 &= \int_0^1 \Upsilon f' \left((1 - \Upsilon)\Psi + \Upsilon \frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) d\Upsilon \\ &= \frac{4\Upsilon}{mb - \Psi} f \left((1 - \Upsilon)\Psi + \Upsilon \frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) \Big|_0^1 - \frac{4}{mb - \Psi} \int_0^1 f \left((1 - \Upsilon)\Psi + \Upsilon \frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) d\Upsilon \\ &= \frac{4}{mb - \Psi} f \left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) - \frac{4}{mb - \Psi} \int_0^1 f \left((1 - \Upsilon)\Psi + \Upsilon \frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) d\Upsilon \\ &= \frac{4}{mb - \Psi} f \left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) - \frac{16}{(mb - \Psi)^2} \int_{\Psi}^{\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4}} f(u) du. \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Similarly, we have

$$I_2 = \frac{-8}{3(mb - \Psi)} f\left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2}\right) + \frac{20}{3(mb - \Psi)} f\left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4}\right) - \frac{16}{(b - \Psi)^2} \int_{\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4}}^{\frac{\Psi + mb}{2}} f(u) du. \quad (2)$$

$$I_3 = \frac{20}{3(mb - \Psi)} f\left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4}\right) - \frac{8}{3(mb - \Psi)} f\left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2}\right) - \frac{16}{(mb - \Psi)^2} \int_{\frac{\Psi + mb}{2}}^{\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4}} f(u) du, \quad (3)$$

and

$$I_4 = \frac{4}{mb - \Psi} f\left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4}\right) - \frac{16}{(mb - \Psi)^2} \int_{\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4}}^{mb} f(u) du. \quad (4)$$

Adding the equalities (1)-(4), we get

$$\begin{aligned} & (I_1 + I_2 + I_3 + I_4) \\ = & \frac{4}{mb - \Psi} f\left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4}\right) - \frac{16}{(mb - \Psi)^2} \int_{\Psi}^{\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4}} f(u) du + \frac{-8}{3(mb - \Psi)} f\left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2}\right) \\ & + \frac{20}{3(mb - \Psi)} f\left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4}\right) - \frac{16}{(mb - \Psi)^2} \int_{\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4}}^{\frac{\Psi + mb}{2}} f(u) du + \frac{20}{3(mb - \Psi)} f\left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4}\right) \\ & - \frac{8}{3(mb - \Psi)} f\left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2}\right) - \frac{16}{(mb - \Psi)^2} \int_{\frac{\Psi + mb}{2}}^{\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4}} f(u) du + \frac{4}{mb - \Psi} f\left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4}\right) \\ & - \frac{16}{(mb - \Psi)^2} \int_{\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4}}^{mb} f(u) du \\ = & \frac{32}{3(mb - \Psi)} f\left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4}\right) + \frac{32}{3(mb - \Psi)} f\left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4}\right) - \frac{16}{3(mb - \Psi)} f\left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2}\right) \\ & - \frac{16}{(mb - \Psi)^2} \int_{\Psi}^{mb} f(u) du. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Multiplying the equality (5) with $\frac{(mb - \Psi)}{16}$ and subtracting $\frac{2(1 - \xi)}{\beta(\xi)(mb - \Psi)} f(k)$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{(mb - \Psi)}{16} (I_1 + I_2 + I_3 + I_4) - \frac{2(1 - \xi)}{\beta(\xi)(mb - \Psi)} f(k) \\ = & \frac{32}{3(mb - \Psi)} f\left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4}\right) \frac{(mb - \Psi)}{16} + \frac{32}{3(mb - \Psi)} f\left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4}\right) \frac{(mb - \Psi)}{16} \\ & - \frac{16}{3(mb - \Psi)} f\left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2}\right) \frac{(mb - \Psi)}{16} - \frac{\xi}{(mb - \Psi)\beta(\xi)} \int_{\Psi}^{mb} f(u) du - \frac{2(1 - \xi)}{\beta(\xi)(mb - \Psi)} f(k) \\ = & \frac{2(mb - \Psi)}{3} f\left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4}\right) + \frac{2(mb - \Psi)}{3} f\left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4}\right) - \frac{1}{3} f\left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2}\right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & -\frac{1}{(mb - \Psi)} \left(\frac{\xi}{\beta(\xi)} \int_{\Psi}^k f(u) du - \frac{(1-\xi)}{\beta(\xi)} f(k) + \frac{\xi}{\beta(\xi)} \int_k^{mb} f(u) du - \frac{(1-\xi)}{\beta(\xi)} f(k) \right) \\
 = & \frac{2(mb - \Psi)}{3} f\left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4}\right) + \frac{2(mb - \Psi)}{3} f\left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4}\right) - \frac{1}{3} f\left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2}\right) \\
 & - \frac{1}{(mb - \Psi)} \left[\left({}_{\Psi}^{CF} I^{\xi} f\right)(k) + \left({}^{CF} I_{mb}^{\xi} f\right)(k) \right].
 \end{aligned}$$

Thus, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{mb - \Psi}{16} \left[\int_0^1 \Upsilon f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \Psi + \Upsilon \frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) d\Upsilon \right. \\
 & + \int_0^1 \left(\Upsilon - \frac{5}{3} \right) f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} + \Upsilon \frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) d\Upsilon \\
 & + \int_0^1 \left(\Upsilon + \frac{2}{3} \right) f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{\Psi + mb}{2} + \Upsilon \frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) d\Upsilon \\
 & \left. + \int_0^1 (\Upsilon - 1) f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} + m\Upsilon b \right) d\Upsilon \right] \\
 = & \left[\frac{2}{3} f\left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4}\right) - \frac{1}{3} f\left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2}\right) + \frac{2}{3} f\left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4}\right) \right] \\
 & - \frac{\beta(\xi)}{\xi(mb - \Psi)} \left[\left({}_{\Psi}^{CF} I^{\xi} f\right)(k) + \left({}^{CF} I_{mb}^{\xi} f\right)(k) \right] + \frac{2(1-\xi)}{\xi(mb - \Psi)} f(k).
 \end{aligned}$$

The proof is completed. □

Corollary 2.1. If we put $m = 1$ in Lemma 2.1, then we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left[\frac{2}{3} f\left(\frac{3\Psi + b}{4}\right) - \frac{1}{3} f\left(\frac{\Psi + b}{2}\right) + \frac{2}{3} f\left(\frac{\Psi + 3b}{4}\right) \right] \\
 & - \frac{\beta(\xi)}{\xi(b - \Psi)} \left[\left({}_{\Psi}^{CF} I^{\xi} f\right)(k) + \left({}^{CF} I_b^{\xi} f\right)(k) \right] + \frac{2(1-\xi)}{\xi(b - \Psi)} f(k) \\
 = & \frac{b - \Psi}{16} \left[\int_0^1 \Upsilon f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \Psi + \Upsilon \frac{3\Psi + b}{4} \right) d\Upsilon \right. \\
 & + \int_0^1 \left(\Upsilon - \frac{5}{3} \right) f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{3\Psi + b}{4} + \Upsilon \frac{\Psi + b}{2} \right) d\Upsilon \\
 & + \int_0^1 \left(\Upsilon + \frac{2}{3} \right) f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{\Psi + b}{2} + \Upsilon \frac{\Psi + 3b}{4} \right) d\Upsilon \\
 & + \int_0^1 \left(\Upsilon + \frac{2}{3} \right) f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{\Psi + b}{2} + \Upsilon \frac{\Psi + 3b}{4} \right) d\Upsilon \\
 & \left. + \int_0^1 (\Upsilon - 1) f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{\Psi + 3b}{4} + \Upsilon b \right) d\Upsilon \right].
 \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 2.1. Assume that the assumptions of Lemma 2.1 are satisfied. If $|f'|$ is

s -convex on $[\Psi, mb]$, then the following inequality holds true:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \left[\frac{2}{3} f \left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) - \frac{1}{3} f \left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) + \frac{2}{3} f \left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\beta(\xi)}{\xi(mb - \Psi)} \left[\left({}^{CF} I_{\Psi}^{\xi} f \right) (k) + \left({}^{CF} I_{mb}^{\xi} f \right) (k) \right] + \frac{2(1 - \xi)}{\beta(\xi)(mb - \Psi)} f(k) \right| \\ \leq & \frac{(mb - \Psi)}{16} \left(\frac{1}{2 + 3s + s^2} \right) \left[(|f'(\Psi)| + |f'(mb)|) + \frac{1}{3} (7 + 2s) \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) \right| \right. \\ & \left. + \frac{1}{3} (10 + 8s) \left(\left| f' \left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) \right| + \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) \right| \right) \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. By using the Lemma 2.1, properties of modulus and s -convexity of $|f'|$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \left[\frac{2}{3} f \left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) - \frac{1}{3} f \left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) + \frac{2}{3} f \left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\beta(\xi)}{\xi(mb - \Psi)} \left[\left({}^{CF} I_{\Psi}^{\xi} f \right) (k) + \left({}^{CF} I_{mb}^{\xi} f \right) (k) \right] + \frac{2(1 - \xi)}{\xi(mb - \Psi)} f(k) \right| \\ \leq & \frac{mb - \Psi}{16} \left[\int_0^1 \Upsilon \left| f' \left((1 - \Upsilon)\Psi + \Upsilon \frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) \right| d\Upsilon \right. \\ & + \int_0^1 \left| \Upsilon - \frac{5}{3} \right| \left| f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} + \Upsilon \frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) \right| d\Upsilon \\ & + \int_0^1 \left| \Upsilon + \frac{2}{3} \right| \left| f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{\Psi + mb}{2} + \Upsilon \frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) \right| d\Upsilon \\ & + \int_0^1 |\Upsilon - 1| \left| f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} + \Upsilon mb \right) \right| d\Upsilon \Big] \\ \leq & \frac{mb - \Psi}{16} \left[\int_0^1 \Upsilon \left((1 - \Upsilon)^s |f'(\Psi)| + \Upsilon^s \left| f' \left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) \right| \right) d\Upsilon \right. \\ & + \int_0^1 \left| \Upsilon - \frac{5}{3} \right| \left((1 - \Upsilon)^s \left| f' \left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) \right| + \Upsilon^s \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) \right| \right) d\Upsilon \\ & + \int_0^1 \left| \Upsilon + \frac{2}{3} \right| \left((1 - \Upsilon)^s \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + b}{2} \right) \right| + \Upsilon^s \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) \right| \right) d\Upsilon \\ & + \int_0^1 |\Upsilon - 1| \left((1 - \Upsilon)^s \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) \right| + \Upsilon^s |f'(mb)| \right) d\Upsilon \Big] \\ = & \frac{(mb - \Psi)}{16} \left(\frac{1}{2 + 3s + s^2} \right) \left[(|f'(\Psi)| + |f'(mb)|) + \frac{1}{3} (7 + 2s) \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) \right| \right. \\ & \left. + \frac{1}{3} (10 + 8s) \left(\left| f' \left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) \right| + \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) \right| \right) \right]. \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof. □

Corollary 2.2. If we put $m = 1$ in Theorem 2.1, then we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \left[\frac{2}{3} f \left(\frac{3\Psi + b}{4} \right) - \frac{1}{3} f \left(\frac{\Psi + b}{2} \right) + \frac{2}{3} f \left(\frac{\Psi + 3b}{4} \right) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\beta(\xi)}{\xi(b-\Psi)} \left[\left({}^{CF} I_{\Psi}^{\xi} f \right) (k) + \left({}^{CF} I_b^{\xi} f \right) (k) \right] + \frac{2(1-\xi)}{\xi(b-\Psi)} f(k) \right| \\ \leq & \frac{(b-\Psi)}{16} \left(\frac{1}{2+3s+s^2} \right) \left[(|f'(\Psi)| + |f'(b)|) + \frac{1}{3}(7+2s) \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + b}{2} \right) \right| \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \frac{1}{3}(10+8s) \left(\left| f' \left(\frac{3\Psi + b}{4} \right) \right| + \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + 3b}{4} \right) \right| \right) \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 2.3. If we put $s = 1$ in Corollary 2.2, then we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \left[\frac{2}{3} f \left(\frac{3\Psi + b}{4} \right) - \frac{1}{3} f \left(\frac{\Psi + b}{2} \right) + \frac{2}{3} f \left(\frac{\Psi + 3b}{4} \right) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\beta(\xi)}{\xi(b-\Psi)} \left[\left({}^{CF} I_{\Psi}^{\xi} f \right) (k) + \left({}^{CF} I_b^{\xi} f \right) (k) \right] + \frac{2(1-\xi)}{\xi(mb-\Psi)} f(k) \right| \\ \leq & \frac{(b-\Psi)}{16} \left[\frac{1}{6} (|f'(\Psi)| + |f'(b)|) + \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + b}{2} \right) \right| \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \left(\left| f' \left(\frac{3\Psi + b}{4} \right) \right| + \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + 3b}{4} \right) \right| \right) \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 2.2. Suppose that the assumptions of Lemma 2.1 are satisfied. If $|f'|^q$ is s -convex on $[\Psi, mb]$ with $\frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$ and $q > 1$, then the following inequality holds true:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \left[\frac{2}{3} f \left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) - \frac{1}{3} f \left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) + \frac{2}{3} f \left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\beta(\xi)}{\xi(mb-\Psi)} \left[\left({}^{CF} I_{\Psi}^{\xi} f \right) (k) + \left({}^{CF} I_{mb}^{\xi} f \right) (k) \right] + \frac{2(1-\xi)}{\beta(\xi)(mb-\Psi)} f(k) \right| \\ \leq & \frac{(mb-\Psi)}{16 \times (s+1)^{\frac{1}{q}} (p+1)^{\frac{1}{p}}} \left[\left(\left(|f'(\Psi)|^q + \left| f' \left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) \right|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. + \left(\left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) \right|^q + |f'(mb)|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right) \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \left(\frac{5^{p+1} - 2^{p+1}}{3^{p+1}} \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\left| f' \left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) \right|^q + \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) \right|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \left(\left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) \right|^q + \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) \right|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. By employing the Lemma 2.1, using Hölder's inequality and s -convexity of $|f'|^q$,

we get

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left| \left[\frac{2}{3} f \left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) - \frac{1}{3} f \left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) + \frac{2}{3} f \left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) \right] \right. \\
& \quad \left. - \frac{\beta(\xi)}{\xi(mb - \Psi)} \left[\left({}^{CF} I_{\Psi}^{\xi} f \right) (k) + \left({}^{CF} I_{mb}^{\xi} f \right) (k) \right] + \frac{2(1 - \xi)}{\xi(mb - \Psi)} f(k) \right| \\
\leq & \frac{mb - \Psi}{16} \left[\int_0^1 \Upsilon \left| f' \left((1 - \Upsilon)\Psi + \Upsilon \frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) \right| d\Upsilon \right. \\
& + \int_0^1 \left| \Upsilon - \frac{5}{3} \right| \left| f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} + \Upsilon \frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) \right| d\Upsilon \\
& + \int_0^1 \left| \Upsilon + \frac{2}{3} \right| \left| f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{\Psi + mb}{2} + \Upsilon \frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) \right| d\Upsilon \\
& + \int_0^1 |\Upsilon - 1| \left| f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} + \Upsilon mb \right) \right| d\Upsilon \Big] \\
\leq & \frac{mb - \Psi}{16} \left[\left(\int_0^1 \Upsilon^p d\Upsilon \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\int_0^1 \left| f' \left((1 - \Upsilon)\Psi + \Upsilon \frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) \right|^q d\Upsilon \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
& + \left(\int_0^1 \left| \Upsilon - \frac{5}{3} \right|^p d\Upsilon \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\int_0^1 \left| f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} + \Upsilon \frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) \right|^q d\Upsilon \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
& + \left(\int_0^1 \left| \Upsilon + \frac{2}{3} \right|^p d\Upsilon \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\int_0^1 \left| f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{\Psi + mb}{2} + \Upsilon \frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) \right|^q d\Upsilon \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
& + \left. \left(\int_0^1 |\Upsilon - 1|^p d\Upsilon \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\int_0^1 \left| f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} + \Upsilon mb \right) \right|^q d\Upsilon \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \\
\leq & \frac{mb - \Psi}{16} \left[\left(\int_0^1 \Upsilon^p d\Upsilon \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\left((1 - \Upsilon)^s |f'(\Psi)|^q + \Upsilon^s \left| f' \left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) \right|^q \right) d\Upsilon \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
& + \left(\int_0^1 \left| \Upsilon - \frac{5}{3} \right|^p d\Upsilon \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\int_0^1 \left((1 - \Upsilon)^s \left| f' \left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) \right|^q + \Upsilon^s \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) \right|^q \right) d\Upsilon \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
& + \left(\int_0^1 \left| \Upsilon + \frac{2}{3} \right|^p d\Upsilon \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\int_0^1 \left((1 - \Upsilon)^s \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) \right|^q + \Upsilon^s \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) \right|^q \right) d\Upsilon \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
& + \left. \left(\int_0^1 |\Upsilon - 1|^p d\Upsilon \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\int_0^1 \left((1 - \Upsilon)^s \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) \right|^q + \Upsilon^s |f'(mb)|^q \right) d\Upsilon \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \\
= & \frac{(mb - \Psi)}{16 \times (s + 1)^{\frac{1}{q}} (p + 1)^{\frac{1}{p}}} \left[\left(\left(|f'(\Psi)|^q + \left| f' \left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) \right|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. + \left(\left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) \right|^q + |f'(mb)|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right) \right]
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \left(\left(\frac{5^{p+1} - 2^{p+1}}{3^{p+1}} \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\left| f' \left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) \right|^q + \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) \right|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
 & \left. + \left(\left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) \right|^q + \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) \right|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right).
 \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof. □

Corollary 2.4. If we put $m = s = 1$ in Theorem 2.2, then we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \left[\frac{2}{3} f \left(\frac{3\Psi + b}{4} \right) - \frac{1}{3} f \left(\frac{\Psi + b}{2} \right) + \frac{2}{3} f \left(\frac{\Psi + 3b}{4} \right) \right] \right. \\
 & \left. - \frac{\beta(\xi)}{\xi(b - \Psi)} \left[\left({}^{CF} I_{\Psi}^{\xi} f \right) (k) + \left({}^{CF} I_{b}^{\xi} f \right) (k) \right] + \frac{2(1 - \xi)}{\xi(b - \Psi)} f(k) \right| \\
 & \leq \frac{b - \Psi}{16 \times (2)^{\frac{1}{q}} (p + 1)^{\frac{1}{p}}} \left[\left(\left(\left| f'(\Psi) \right|^q + \left| f' \left(\frac{3\Psi + b}{4} \right) \right|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. + \left(\left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + 3b}{4} \right) \right|^q + \left| f'(b) \right|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right) \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + \left(\left(\frac{5^{p+1} - 2^{p+1}}{3^{p+1}} \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\left| f' \left(\frac{3\Psi + b}{4} \right) \right|^q + \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + b}{2} \right) \right|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. + \left(\left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + b}{2} \right) \right|^q + \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + 3b}{4} \right) \right|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right) \right].
 \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 2.3. Assume that the assumptions of Lemma 2.1 are satisfied. If $|f'|^q$ is s -convex on $[\Psi, mb]$ and $q \geq 1$, then the following inequality holds true:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \left[\frac{2}{3} f \left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) - \frac{1}{3} f \left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) + \frac{2}{3} f \left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) \right] \right. \\
 & \left. - \frac{\beta(\xi)}{\xi(mb - \Psi)} \left[\left({}^{CF} I_{\Psi}^{\xi} f \right) (k) + \left({}^{CF} I_{mb}^{\xi} f \right) (k) \right] + \frac{2(1 - \xi)}{\xi(mb - \Psi)} f(k) \right| \\
 & \leq \frac{(mb - \Psi)}{16} \left[\left(\frac{1}{2} \right)^{1 - \frac{1}{q}} \left(\frac{1}{s^2 + 3s + 2} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
 & \quad \times \left(\left(\left| f'(\Psi) \right|^q + 2 \left| f' \left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) \right|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(2 \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) \right|^q + \left| f'(mb) \right|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. + \left(\frac{7}{6} \right)^{1 - \frac{1}{q}} \left(\frac{1}{s^2 + 3s + 2} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \left(\left((s + 3) \left| f' \left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) \right|^q + (s + 2) \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) \right|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right) \right].
 \end{aligned}$$

$$+ \left[(s+2) \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) \right|^q + (s+3) \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) \right|^q \right]^{\frac{1}{q}}.$$

Proof. By utilizing the Lemma 2.1, using power-mean inequality and s -convexity of $|f'|^q$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \left[\frac{2}{3} f \left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) - \frac{1}{3} f \left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) + \frac{2}{3} f \left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\beta(\xi)}{\xi(mb - \Psi)} \left[({}^{CF}I_{\Psi}^{\xi} f)(k) + ({}^{CF}I_{mb}^{\xi} f)(k) \right] + \frac{2(1-\xi)}{\xi(mb - \Psi)} f(k) \right| \\ \leq & \frac{mb - \Psi}{16} \left[\int_0^1 \Upsilon \left| f' \left((1-\Upsilon)\Psi + \Upsilon \frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) \right| d\Upsilon \right. \\ & + \int_0^1 \left| \Upsilon - \frac{5}{3} \right| \left| f' \left((1-\Upsilon) \frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} + \Upsilon \frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) \right| d\Upsilon \\ & + \int_0^1 \left| \Upsilon + \frac{2}{3} \right| \left| f' \left((1-\Upsilon) \frac{\Psi + mb}{2} + \Upsilon \frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) \right| d\Upsilon \\ & + \int_0^1 |\Upsilon - 1| \left| f' \left((1-\Upsilon) \frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} + \Upsilon mb \right) \right| d\Upsilon \Big] \\ \leq & \frac{b - \Psi}{16} \left[\left(\int_0^1 \Upsilon d\Upsilon \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left(\int_0^1 \Upsilon \left| f' \left((1-\Upsilon)\Psi + \Upsilon \frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) \right|^q d\Upsilon \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\ & + \left(\int_0^1 \left| \Upsilon - \frac{5}{3} \right| d\Upsilon \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left(\int_0^1 \left| \Upsilon - \frac{5}{3} \right| \left| f' \left((1-\Upsilon) \frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} + \Upsilon \frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) \right|^q d\Upsilon \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\ & + \left(\int_0^1 \left| \Upsilon + \frac{2}{3} \right| d\Upsilon \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left(\int_0^1 \left| \Upsilon + \frac{2}{3} \right| \left| f' \left((1-\Upsilon) \frac{\Psi + mb}{2} + \Upsilon \frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) \right|^q d\Upsilon \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\ & + \left. \left(\int_0^1 |\Upsilon - 1| d\Upsilon \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left(\int_0^1 |\Upsilon - 1| \left| f' \left((1-\Upsilon) \frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} + \Upsilon mb \right) \right|^q d\Upsilon \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \\ \leq & \frac{mb - \Psi}{16} \left[\left(\int_0^1 \Upsilon d\Upsilon \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left(\int_0^1 \Upsilon \left((1-\Upsilon)^s |f'(\Psi)|^q + \Upsilon^s \left| f' \left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) \right|^q \right) d\Upsilon \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\ & + \left(\int_0^1 \left| \Upsilon - \frac{5}{3} \right| d\Upsilon \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \\ & \times \left(\int_0^1 \left| \Upsilon - \frac{5}{3} \right| \left((1-\Upsilon)^s \left| f' \left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) \right|^q + \Upsilon^s \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) \right|^q \right) d\Upsilon \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\ & + \left(\int_0^1 \left| \Upsilon + \frac{2}{3} \right| d\Upsilon \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \\ & \times \left. \left(\int_0^1 \left| \Upsilon + \frac{2}{3} \right| \left((1-\Upsilon)^s \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) \right|^q + \Upsilon^s \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) \right|^q \right) d\Upsilon \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \left(\int_0^1 |\Upsilon - 1| d\Upsilon \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \\
 & \times \left(\int_0^1 |\Upsilon - 1| \left((1 - \Upsilon)^s \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) \right|^q + \Upsilon^s |f'(mb)|^q \right) d\Upsilon \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \Big] \\
 & = \frac{(mb - \Psi)}{16} \left[\left(\frac{1}{2} \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left(\frac{1}{s^2 + 3s + 2} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
 & \quad \times \left(\left(|f'(\Psi)|^q + 2 \left| f' \left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) \right|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(2 \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) \right|^q + |f'(mb)|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
 & \quad + \left(\frac{7}{6} \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left(\frac{1}{s^2 + 3s + 2} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
 & \quad \times \left(\left((s+3) \left| f' \left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) \right|^q + (s+2) \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) \right|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. + \left((s+2) \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) \right|^q + (s+3) \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) \right|^q \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right) \right].
 \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof. □

Corollary 2.5. If we put $m = s = 1$ in Theorem 2.3, then we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \left[\frac{2}{3} f \left(\frac{3\Psi + b}{4} \right) - \frac{1}{3} f \left(\frac{\Psi + b}{2} \right) + \frac{2}{3} f \left(\frac{\Psi + 3b}{4} \right) \right] \right. \\
 & \quad \left. - \frac{\beta(\xi)}{\xi(b - \Psi)} \left[({}^{CF}I_{\Psi}^{\xi} f)(k) + ({}^{CF}I_b^{\xi} f)(k) \right] + \frac{2(1 - \xi)}{\xi(b - \Psi)} f(k) \right| \\
 & \leq \frac{(b - \Psi)}{16} \left[\left(\frac{1}{2} \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left(\left(\frac{|f'(\Psi)|^q + 2 \left| f' \left(\frac{3\Psi + b}{4} \right) \right|^q}{6} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{2 \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + 3b}{4} \right) \right|^q + |f'(b)|^q}{6} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right) \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + \left(\frac{7}{6} \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left(\left(\frac{4 \left| f' \left(\frac{3\Psi + b}{4} \right) \right|^q + 3 \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + b}{2} \right) \right|^q}{6} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{3 \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + b}{2} \right) \right|^q + 4 \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + 3b}{4} \right) \right|^q}{6} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right) \right].
 \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 2.4. Assume that all the conditions of Lemma 2.1 are satisfied. If $|f'|^q$ is s -convex on $[\Psi, mb]$ for some fixed $s \in (0, 1]$, then for $q > 1$, the following fractional inequality holds true:

$$\left| \left[\frac{2}{3} f \left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) - \frac{1}{3} f \left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) + \frac{2}{3} f \left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) \right] \right|$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& -\frac{\beta(\xi)}{\xi(mb-\Psi)} \left[({}^{CF}I_{\Psi}^{\xi}f)(k) + ({}^{CF}I_{mb}^{\xi}f)(k) \right] + \frac{2(1-\xi)}{\xi(mb-\Psi)} f(k) \Big| \\
\leq & \frac{(mb-\Psi)}{16 \times (s+1)^{\frac{1}{q}}} \left[\frac{1}{p}(p+1) + \left(\frac{1}{q} \left(|f'(\Psi)|^q + \left| f' \left(\frac{3\Psi+mb}{4} \right) \right|^q \right) \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. + \frac{1}{q} \left(\left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi+3mb}{4} \right) \right|^q + |f'(mb)|^q \right) \right) \right. \\
& \left. + \left(\frac{1}{p} \left(\frac{5^{p+1}-2^{p+1}}{3^{p+1}(p+1)} \right) + \frac{1}{q} \left(\left| f' \left(\frac{3\Psi+mb}{4} \right) \right|^q + \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi+mb}{2} \right) \right|^q \right) \right) \right. \\
& \left. + \frac{1}{q} \left(\left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi+mb}{2} \right) \right|^q + \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi+3mb}{4} \right) \right|^q \right) \right].
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. From Lemma 2.1, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left| \left[\frac{2}{3}f \left(\frac{3\Psi+mb}{4} \right) - \frac{1}{3}f \left(\frac{\Psi+mb}{2} \right) + \frac{2}{3}f \left(\frac{\Psi+3mb}{4} \right) \right] \right. \\
& \left. - \frac{\beta(\xi)}{\xi(mb-\Psi)} \left[({}^{CF}I_{\Psi}^{\xi}f)(k) + ({}^{CF}I_{mb}^{\xi}f)(k) \right] + \frac{2(1-\xi)}{\xi(mb-\Psi)} f(k) \right| \\
\leq & \frac{mb-\Psi}{16} \left[\int_0^1 \Upsilon \left| f' \left((1-\Upsilon)\Psi + \Upsilon \frac{3\Psi+mb}{4} \right) \right| d\Upsilon \right. \\
& + \int_0^1 \left| \Upsilon - \frac{5}{3} \right| \left| f' \left((1-\Upsilon) \frac{3\Psi+mb}{4} + \Upsilon \frac{\Psi+mb}{2} \right) \right| d\Upsilon \\
& + \int_0^1 \left| \Upsilon + \frac{2}{3} \right| \left| f' \left((1-\Upsilon) \frac{\Psi+mb}{2} + \Upsilon \frac{\Psi+3mb}{4} \right) \right| d\Upsilon \\
& \left. + \int_0^1 |\Upsilon-1| \left| f' \left((1-\Upsilon) \frac{\Psi+3mb}{4} + \Upsilon mb \right) \right| d\Upsilon \right].
\end{aligned}$$

By using the following Young's inequality

$$\Psi b \leq \frac{1}{p}\Psi^p + \frac{1}{q}b^q,$$

we get

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left| \left[\frac{2}{3}f \left(\frac{3\Psi+mb}{4} \right) - \frac{1}{3}f \left(\frac{\Psi+mb}{2} \right) + \frac{2}{3}f \left(\frac{\Psi+3mb}{4} \right) \right] \right. \\
& \left. - \frac{\beta(\xi)}{\xi(mb-\Psi)} \left[({}^{CF}I_{\Psi}^{\xi}f)(k) + ({}^{CF}I_{mb}^{\xi}f)(k) \right] + \frac{2(1-\xi)}{\xi(mb-\Psi)} f(k) \right| \\
\leq & \frac{mb-\Psi}{16} \left[\int_0^1 \Upsilon \left| f' \left((1-\Upsilon)\Psi + \Upsilon \frac{3\Psi+mb}{4} \right) \right| d\Upsilon \right. \\
& \left. + \int_0^1 \left| \Upsilon - \frac{5}{3} \right| \left| f' \left((1-\Upsilon) \frac{3\Psi+mb}{4} + \Upsilon \frac{\Psi+mb}{2} \right) \right| d\Upsilon \right.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \int_0^1 \left| \Upsilon + \frac{2}{3} \right| \left| f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{\Psi + mb}{2} + \Upsilon \frac{\Psi + 3mb}{2} \right) \right| d\Upsilon \\
 & + \int_0^1 |\Upsilon - 1| \left| f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{\Psi + 3mb}{2} + \Upsilon mb \right) \right| d\Upsilon \Big] \\
 \leq & \frac{mb - \Psi}{16} \left[\left(\frac{1}{p} \int_0^1 \Upsilon^p d\Upsilon \right) + \frac{1}{q} \left(\int_0^1 \left| f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) \right|^q d\Upsilon \right) \right. \\
 & + \left(\frac{1}{p} \int_0^1 \left| \Upsilon - \frac{5}{3} \right|^p d\Upsilon \right) + \frac{1}{q} \left(\int_0^1 \left| f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} + \Upsilon \frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) \right|^q d\Upsilon \right) \\
 & + \left(\frac{1}{p} \int_0^1 \left| \Upsilon + \frac{2}{3} \right|^p d\Upsilon \right) + \frac{1}{q} \left(\int_0^1 \left| f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{\Psi + mb}{2} + \Upsilon \frac{\Psi + 3mb}{2} \right) \right|^q d\Upsilon \right) \\
 & \left. + \left(\frac{1}{p} \int_0^1 |\Upsilon - 1|^p d\Upsilon \right) + \frac{1}{q} \left(\int_0^1 \left| f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} + \Upsilon mb \right) \right|^q d\Upsilon \right) \right] \\
 \leq & \frac{mb - \Psi}{16} \left[\left(\frac{1}{p} \left(\int_0^1 \Upsilon^p d\Upsilon \right) \right) \right. \\
 & + \frac{1}{q} \left(\int_0^1 \left((1 - \Upsilon)^s |f'(\Psi)|^q + \Upsilon^s \left| f' \left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) \right|^q \right) d\Upsilon \right) \\
 & + \left(\frac{1}{p} \int_0^1 \left| \Upsilon - \frac{5}{3} \right|^p d\Upsilon \right) \\
 & + \frac{1}{q} \left(\int_0^1 \left((1 - \Upsilon)^s \left| f' \left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) \right|^q + \Upsilon^s \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) \right|^q \right) d\Upsilon \right) \\
 & + \left(\frac{1}{p} \int_0^1 \left| \Upsilon + \frac{2}{3} \right|^p d\Upsilon \right) \\
 & + \frac{1}{q} \left(\int_0^1 \left((1 - \Upsilon)^s \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) \right|^q + \Upsilon^s \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) \right|^q \right) d\Upsilon \right) \\
 & + \left(\frac{1}{p} \int_0^1 |\Upsilon - 1|^p d\Upsilon \right) \\
 & \left. + \frac{1}{q} \left(\int_0^1 \left((1 - \Upsilon)^s \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) \right|^q + \Upsilon^s |f'(mb)|^q \right) d\Upsilon \right) \right] \\
 = & \frac{mb - \Psi}{16 \times (s + 1)^{\frac{1}{q}}} \left[\frac{1}{p} (p + 1) + \left(\frac{1}{q} \left(|f'(\Psi)|^q + \left| f' \left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) \right|^q \right) \right) \right. \\
 & + \frac{1}{q} \left(\left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) \right|^q + |f'(mb)|^q \right) \\
 & + \left(\frac{1}{p} \left(\frac{5^{p+1} - 2^{p+1}}{3^{p+1}(p+1)} \right) + \frac{1}{q} \left(\left| f' \left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) \right|^q + \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) \right|^q \right) \right. \\
 & \left. \left. + \frac{1}{q} \left(\left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) \right|^q + \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) \right|^q \right) \right) \right].
 \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof. □

3 Dual-Simpson type Inequalities for Bounded Function

In this section, we obtain several fractional inequalities of dual-Simpson type for bounded function.

Theorem 3.1. Assume that the assumptions of Lemma 2.1 hold. If there exist constants $-\infty < m^\circ < M < +\infty$ such that $m^\circ < f'(\Phi) < M$ for all $\Phi \in [\Psi, mb]$, then the following inequality holds true:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \left[\frac{2}{3} f\left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4}\right) - \frac{1}{3} f\left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2}\right) + \frac{2}{3} f\left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4}\right) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\beta(\xi)}{\xi(mb - \Psi)} \left[({}^{CF}I_{\Psi}^{\xi} f)(k) + ({}^{CF}I_{mb}^{\xi} f)(k) \right] + \frac{2(1 - \xi)}{\xi(mb - \Psi)} f(k) \right| \\ & \leq \frac{5(mb - \Psi)(M - m^\circ)}{48}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. From Lemma 2.1, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[\frac{2}{3} f\left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4}\right) - \frac{1}{3} f\left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2}\right) + \frac{2}{3} f\left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4}\right) \right] \\ & \quad - \frac{\beta(\xi)}{\xi(mb - \Psi)} \left[({}^{CF}I_{\Psi}^{\xi} f)(k) + ({}^{CF}I_{mb}^{\xi} f)(k) \right] + \frac{2(1 - \xi)}{\xi(mb - \Psi)} f(k) \\ = & \frac{mb - \Psi}{16} \left[\int_0^1 \Upsilon f' \left((1 - \Upsilon)\Psi + \Upsilon \frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) d\Upsilon \right. \\ & \quad + \int_0^1 \left(\Upsilon - \frac{5}{3} \right) f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} + \Upsilon \frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) d\Upsilon \\ & \quad + \int_0^1 \left(\Upsilon + \frac{2}{3} \right) f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{\Psi + mb}{2} + \Upsilon \frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) d\Upsilon \\ & \quad \left. + \int_0^1 (\Upsilon - 1) f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} + \Upsilon mb \right) d\Upsilon \right] \\ = & \frac{mb - \Psi}{16} \left[\int_0^1 \Upsilon \left(f' \left((1 - \Upsilon)\Psi + \Upsilon \frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) - \frac{m^\circ + M}{2} \right) d\Upsilon \right. \\ & \quad + \int_0^1 \left(\Upsilon - \frac{5}{3} \right) \left(f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} + \Upsilon \frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) - \frac{m^\circ + M}{2} \right) d\Upsilon \\ & \quad + \int_0^1 \left(\Upsilon + \frac{2}{3} \right) \left(f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{\Psi + mb}{2} + \Upsilon \frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) - \frac{m^\circ + M}{2} \right) d\Upsilon \\ & \quad \left. + \int_0^1 (\Upsilon - 1) \left(f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} + \Upsilon mb \right) - \frac{m^\circ + M}{2} \right) d\Upsilon \right]. \quad (6) \end{aligned}$$

Taking the absolute value in both sides of equality (6), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \left[\frac{2}{3}f\left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4}\right) - \frac{1}{3}f\left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2}\right) + \frac{2}{3}f\left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4}\right) \right] \right. \\
 & \quad \left. - \frac{\beta(\xi)}{\xi(mb - \Psi)} \left[({}^{CF}_{\Psi}I^{\xi}f)(k) + ({}^{CF}I^{\xi}_{mb}f)(k) \right] + \frac{2(1 - \xi)}{\beta(\xi)(mb - \Psi)}f(k) \right| \\
 \leq & \frac{b - \Psi}{16} \left[\int_0^1 \Upsilon \left| f' \left((1 - \Upsilon)\Psi + \Upsilon \frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) - \frac{m^{\circ} + M}{2} \right| d\Upsilon \right. \\
 & + \int_0^1 \left| \Upsilon - \frac{5}{3} \right| \left| f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} + \Upsilon \frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) - \frac{m^{\circ} + M}{2} \right| d\Upsilon \\
 & + \int_0^1 \left| \Upsilon + \frac{2}{3} \right| \left| f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{\Psi + mb}{2} + \Upsilon \frac{\Psi + 3mb}{2} \right) - \frac{m^{\circ} + M}{2} \right| d\Upsilon \\
 & \left. + \int_0^1 |\Upsilon - 1| \left| f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{\Psi + 3mb}{2} + \Upsilon mb \right) - \frac{m^{\circ} + M}{2} \right| d\Upsilon \right]. \tag{7}
 \end{aligned}$$

Since $m^{\circ} < f'(\Phi) < M$ for all $\Phi \in [\Psi, mb]$, we obtain

$$\left| f' \left((1 - \Upsilon)\Psi + \Upsilon \frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) - \frac{m^{\circ} + M}{2} \right| \leq \frac{M - m^{\circ}}{2}, \tag{8}$$

$$\left| f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} + \Upsilon \frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) - \frac{m^{\circ} + M}{2} \right| \leq \frac{M - m^{\circ}}{2}, \tag{9}$$

$$\left| f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{\Psi + mb}{2} + \Upsilon \frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) - \frac{m^{\circ} + M}{2} \right| \leq \frac{M - m^{\circ}}{2}, \tag{10}$$

and

$$\left| f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} + \Upsilon mb \right) - \frac{m^{\circ} + M}{2} \right| \leq \frac{M - m^{\circ}}{2}. \tag{11}$$

Applying inequalities (8)-(11) in (6), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \left[\frac{2}{3}f\left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4}\right) - \frac{1}{3}f\left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2}\right) + \frac{2}{3}f\left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4}\right) \right] \right. \\
 & \quad \left. - \frac{\beta(\xi)}{\xi(mb - \Psi)} \left[({}^{CF}_{\Psi}I^{\xi}f)(k) + ({}^{CF}I^{\xi}_{mb}f)(k) \right] + \frac{2(1 - \xi)}{\xi(mb - \Psi)}f(k) \right| \\
 \leq & \frac{(mb - \Psi)(M - (mb - \Psi))}{32} \\
 & \times \left[\int_0^1 \Upsilon d\Upsilon + \int_0^1 \left| \Upsilon - \frac{5}{3} \right| d\Upsilon + \int_0^1 \left| \Upsilon + \frac{2}{3} \right| d\Upsilon + \int_0^1 |\Upsilon - 1| d\Upsilon \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

$$= \frac{5(mb - \Psi)(M - m^\circ)}{48}.$$

The proof is completed. \square

4 Dual-Simpson type Inequalities for Lipschitzian Function

In this section, we introduce Dual-Simpson type inequalities for Lipschitzian function.

Theorem 4.1. Suppose that the assumptions of Lemma 2.1 are satisfied. If f' is L -Lipschitzian function $[\Psi, mb]$, then the following fractional holds true:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \left[\frac{2}{3} f \left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) - \frac{1}{3} f \left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) + \frac{2}{3} f \left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\beta(\xi)}{\xi(mb - \Psi)} \left[\left({}^{CF}_{\Psi} I^{\xi} f \right) (k) + \left({}^{CF} I^{\xi}_{mb} f \right) (k) \right] + \frac{2(1 - \xi)}{\xi(mb - \Psi)} f(k) \right| \\ & \leq \frac{13L(mb - \Psi)^2}{192}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. From Lemma 2.1, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[\frac{2}{3} f \left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) - \frac{1}{3} f \left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) + \frac{2}{3} f \left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) \right] \\ & \quad - \frac{\beta(\xi)}{\xi(mb - \Psi)} \left[\left({}^{CF}_{\Psi} I^{\xi} f \right) (k) + \left({}^{CF} I^{\xi}_{mb} f \right) (k) \right] + \frac{2(1 - \xi)}{\xi(mb - \Psi)} f(k) \\ = & \frac{mb - \Psi}{16} \left[\int_0^1 \Upsilon f' \left((1 - \Upsilon)\Psi + \Upsilon \frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) d\Upsilon \right. \\ & \quad + \int_0^1 \left(\Upsilon - \frac{5}{3} \right) f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} + \Upsilon \frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) d\Upsilon \\ & \quad + \int_0^1 \left(\Upsilon + \frac{2}{3} \right) f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{\Psi + mb}{2} + \Upsilon \frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) d\Upsilon \\ & \quad \left. + \int_0^1 (\Upsilon - 1) f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} + \Upsilon mb \right) d\Upsilon \right] \\ = & \frac{b - \Psi}{16} \left[\int_0^1 \Upsilon \left(f' \left((1 - \Upsilon)\Psi + \Upsilon \frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) - f'(\Psi) \right) d\Upsilon \right. \\ & \quad + \int_0^1 \left(\Upsilon - \frac{5}{3} \right) \left(f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} + \Upsilon \frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) - f' \left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) \right) d\Upsilon \\ & \quad \left. + \int_0^1 \left(\Upsilon + \frac{2}{3} \right) \left(f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{\Psi + mb}{2} + \Upsilon \frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) - f' \left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) \right) d\Upsilon \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + \int_0^1 (\Upsilon - 1) \left(f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} + \Upsilon mb \right) - f' \left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) \right) d\Upsilon \\
& + \frac{1}{2} \left(f'(\Psi) - f' \left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) \right) + \frac{7}{6} \left(f' \left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) - f' \left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) \right) \Big]. \quad (12)
\end{aligned}$$

Taking the absolute value on both sides of equality (12) and utilizing the fact that f' is L -Lipschitzian on $[\Psi, mb]$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left| \left[\frac{2}{3} f \left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) - \frac{1}{3} f \left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) + \frac{2}{3} f \left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) \right] \right. \\
& \left. - \frac{\beta(\xi)}{\xi(mb - \Psi)} \left[\left({}^{CF}I_{\Psi}^{\xi} f \right) (k) + \left({}^{CF}I_{mb}^{\xi} f \right) (k) \right] + \frac{2(1 - \xi)}{\xi(mb - \Psi)} f(k) \right| \\
\leq & \frac{mb - \Psi}{16} \left[\int_0^1 \Upsilon \left| f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \Psi + \Upsilon \frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) - f'(\Psi) \right| d\Upsilon \right. \\
& + \int_0^1 \left| \Upsilon - \frac{5}{3} \right| \left| f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} + \Upsilon \frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) - f' \left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) \right| d\Upsilon \\
& + \int_0^1 \left| \Upsilon + \frac{2}{3} \right| \left| f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{\Psi + mb}{2} + \Upsilon \frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) - f' \left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) \right| d\Upsilon \\
& + \int_0^1 |\Upsilon - 1| \left| f' \left((1 - \Upsilon) \frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} + \Upsilon mb \right) - f' \left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) \right| d\Upsilon \\
& + \frac{1}{2} \left| f'(\Psi) - f' \left(\frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right) \right| + \frac{7}{6} \left| f' \left(\frac{\Psi + mb}{2} \right) - f' \left(\frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right) \right| \Big] \\
\leq & \frac{mb - \Psi}{16} \left[\frac{mb - \Psi}{4} L \left(\int_0^1 \Upsilon^2 d\Upsilon + \int_0^1 \left| \Upsilon - \frac{5}{3} \right| \Upsilon d\Upsilon + \int_0^1 \left| \Upsilon + \frac{2}{3} \right| \Upsilon d\Upsilon \right. \right. \\
& \left. \left. + \int_0^1 |\Upsilon - 1| \Upsilon d\Upsilon \right) + \frac{L}{2} \left| \Psi - \frac{\Psi + 3mb}{4} \right| + \frac{7L}{6} \left| \frac{\Psi + mb}{2} - \frac{3\Psi + mb}{4} \right| \right] \\
= & \frac{13L(mb - \Psi)^2}{192}.
\end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof. □

5 Dual Simpson's Quadrature Formula

Let d is the partition of the interval $[\Psi, b]$, $d : \Psi = \Phi_0 < \Phi_1 < \Phi_2 < \dots < \Phi_{n-1} < \Phi_n = b$ and define the following quadrature formula:

$$\int_{\Psi}^b f(\Phi) d\Phi = \zeta(f, d) + R(f, d),$$

with

$$\zeta(f, d) := \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \frac{(\Phi_{i+1} - \Phi_i)}{3} \left[2f\left(\frac{3\Phi_i + \Phi_{i+1}}{4}\right) - f\left(\frac{\Phi_i + \Phi_{i+1}}{2}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{\Phi_i + 3\Phi_{i+1}}{4}\right) \right],$$

where $R(f, d)$ is the approximation error.

Proposition 5.1. Under the assumptions of Corollary 2.3 for every division d of $[\Psi, b]$, and $\xi = 1$, $\beta(0) = \beta(1) = 1$ the following inequality holds:

$$|R(f, d)| \leq \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \frac{(\Phi_{i+1} - \Phi_i)^2}{16} \left[\frac{1}{6} (|f'(\Phi_i)| + |f'(\Phi_{i+1})|) + \left| f'\left(\frac{\Phi_i + \Phi_{i+1}}{2}\right) \right| + \left(\left| f'\left(\frac{3\Phi_i + \Phi_{i+1}}{4}\right) \right| + \left| f'\left(\frac{\Phi_i + 3\Phi_{i+1}}{4}\right) \right| \right) \right].$$

Proof. Applying the Theorem 2.1 on the subinterval $[\Phi_i, \Phi_{i+1}]$, ($i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, n-1$), we have □

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{3} \left[2f\left(\frac{3\Phi_i + \Phi_{i+1}}{4}\right) - f\left(\frac{\Phi_i + \Phi_{i+1}}{2}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{\Phi_i + 3\Phi_{i+1}}{4}\right) \right] - \int_{\Phi_i}^{\Phi_{i+1}} f(\Phi) d\Phi \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(\Phi_{i+1} - \Phi_i)}{16} \left[\frac{1}{6} (|f'(\Phi_i)| + |f'(\Phi_{i+1})|) + \left| f'\left(\frac{\Phi_i + \Phi_{i+1}}{2}\right) \right| + \left(\left| f'\left(\frac{3\Phi_i + \Phi_{i+1}}{4}\right) \right| + \left| f'\left(\frac{\Phi_i + 3\Phi_{i+1}}{4}\right) \right| \right) \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Summing over i from 0 to $n-1$ and multiplying on both sides inequality (13) by $(\Phi_{i+1} - \Phi_i)$, we deduce by the triangle inequality the desired result.

6 Conclusion

In this paper, the main aim is to derive dual-Simpson-type inequalities for various function classes using the Caputo-Fabrizio fractional integral operator. First of all, we give an integral identity that is essential in order to establish the main findings of the article. Using Caputo-Fabrizio fractional integrals, a few dual-Simpson-type inequalities are investigated for differentiable functions. Employing the new approach, we extended the study of dual-Simpson type inequalities using Hölder's, bounded, Lipschitzian and power-mean integral inequalities. Furthermore, an application to the quadrature formula is discussed. In the future, it would be fascinating to apply these findings to other

convexities and fractional integral operators. We believe that much research in this intriguing area of inequalities and numerical analysis will focus on the future.

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New Results on Weddle's Type Inequalities Involving Tempered Fractional Integrals

Asia Shehzadi¹, Hüseyin Budak², Mehmet Zeki Sarikaya³, Wali Haider¹

¹School of Mathematics and Statistics, Central South University, Changsha 410083, China

²Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Science and Arts, Kocaeli University, Kocaeli 41001, Türkiye

³ Department of Mathematics Faculty of Science and Arts, Düzce University Düzce 81620, Turkey

Corresponding author: ashehzadi937@email.com

ORCID IDs:

First Author: 0009-0005-1101-5536

Second Author: 0000-0001-8843-955X

Third Author: 0000-0002-6165-9242

Fourth Author: 0009-0001-7065-2755

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Abstract

Integral inequalities represent a central component of modern mathematical analysis, providing essential connections between theory and various applied disciplines. This study develops new inequalities for convex functions through the use of tempered fractional integrals, employing a known integral identity as the basis of the investigation. In particular, we establish Weddle's type inequalities for differentiable convex functions and extend the results to critical functional classes, such as Lipschitzian functions, bounded functions, and functions with bounded variation. These developments not only enhance the theoretical framework of fractional calculus but also provide potential applications in computational analysis and numerical integration.

Keywords: Convexity, Weddles formula, Tempered fractional integrals.

1 Introduction and Motivation

The study of convex functions has a well-established history in the field of science and continued an active area of research for over a hundred years. Formally, the definition of a convex function can be stated as: A mapping $\mathcal{F} : [\sigma, v] \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \subset \mathbb{R}$ is said to be a convex function if the given inequality is satisfied:

$$\mathcal{F}(t\sigma + (1-t)v) \leq t\mathcal{F}(\sigma) + (1-t)\mathcal{F}(v) \quad (1)$$

for all $\sigma, v \in I$, $t \in [0, 1]$. Also, we say that \mathcal{F} is concave, if the inequality (1) is reversed.

Significant research demonstrated a strong link between convexity theory and integral inequalities, highlighting their importance in differential equations and applied mathematics. The

convexity principle is utilized by the Jensen, Gruss, Hölder, Hermite Hadamard, Simpson, Euler-Maclaurin, and Milne type of inequalities to attain more accurate conclusions. Additionally, it aids us with approximation theories, differential equations, and optimization methods. Researchers examine these relationships to advance theory and enhance problem-solving in various scientific domains [29, 33, 31].

The Hermite–Hadamard inequality is one of the most notable of several significant inequalities derived from the characteristics of convex functions. It asserts that for any convex function defined on a closed interval, its value at the interval’s midpoints provides an upper and lower bound for its integral. More precisely, the Hermite-Hadamard inequality can be outlined as follows:

If $\mathcal{F} : I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a convex function on I and $\sigma, v \in I$ with $\sigma < v$, then

$$\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{\sigma + v}{2}\right) \leq \frac{1}{v - \sigma} \int_{\sigma}^v \mathcal{F}(t) dt \leq \frac{\mathcal{F}(\sigma) + \mathcal{F}(v)}{2} \quad (2)$$

holds. Both the inequalities in (2) hold in the reversed direction if \mathcal{F}' is concave.

For differentiable convex functions, Dragomir and Agarwal [6] have reported two new inequalities connected with inequalities (2). Additionally, they offer some applications of special means of real numbers. Zhao et al. [35] have derived Bullen-type inequalities for differentiable convex functions by involving generalized fractional integrals. In 2010, Sarikaya et al. [28] explored several novel Simpson-type inequalities employing s -convexity and offered various applications to the special mean of real numbers. Chen and Huang extended these newly established Simpson-type inequalities by leveraging Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals [5]. Considering generalized Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals, Budak et al. [3] obtained several approximations for Simpson’s 1/3 formula for differentiable convex functions. Toseef et al. [34] established a novel identity by generalizing Weddle’s rule for the first time. They investigated several results related to differentiable convex functions and studied different function classes. Mateen et al. established Weddle’s type equality using Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals. Also, they generalized results for the Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals reported in [22]. Readers may consult [7, 10] and the associated references for additional information.

Fractional calculus extends the concepts of integration and differentiation to non-integer orders, serving as an effective tool for modeling memory-dependent and anomalous processes. To address certain limitations of standard fractional operators, tempered fractional calculus introduces an exponential tempering parameter into the fractional kernel, which mitigates the singular and unbounded behavior of classical fractional operators. This change enables us to exert better control over long-range interactions. It offers greater freedom to replicate physical phenomena, such as anomalous diffusion and viscoelasticity, while preserving the essential features of fractional dynamics. The incorporation of fractional and tempered fractional calculus into the theory of inequalities has created novel opportunities for mathematical analysis. Recent studies [23, 14, 31] have demonstrated that these advanced frameworks facilitate the formulation of innovative Hermite–Hadamard, Simpson, and Weddle-type inequalities for convex functions.

The mathematical preliminaries and concepts presented here will be widely employed throughout the research process.

Definition 1.1. The terminology of the gamma, incomplete gamma function and the λ -incomplete gamma function are explained by

$$\Upsilon(\alpha) := \int_0^{\infty} t^{\alpha-1} e^{-t} dt,$$

$$\Upsilon(\alpha, \varpi) := \int_0^{\varpi} t^{\alpha-1} e^{-t} dt,$$

and

$$\Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, \varpi) := \int_0^{\varpi} t^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda t} dt,$$

respectively. Here, $0 < \alpha < \infty$ and $\lambda \geq 0$.

Some features of the λ -incomplete gamma function are listed the following:

Remark 1.1. [21] Under the conditions $\alpha > 0$; $x, \lambda \geq 0$ and $\sigma < v$, we achieve

$$\text{i. } \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) = \int_0^1 t^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(v-\sigma)t} dt = \frac{1}{(v-\sigma)^{\alpha}} \Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, v-\sigma),$$

$$\text{ii. } \int_0^1 \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, \varpi) d\varpi = \frac{\Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, v-\sigma)}{(v-\sigma)^{\alpha}} - \frac{\Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha+1, v-\sigma)}{(v-\sigma)^{\alpha+1}}.$$

Definition 1.2 (See [15, 12]). The Riemann-Liouville fractional integral of order $\alpha > 0$, is expressed as follows:

$$J_{\sigma+}^{\alpha} \mathcal{F}(\varpi) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{\sigma}^{\varpi} (\varpi - t)^{\alpha-1} \mathcal{F}(t) dt, \quad \varpi > \sigma$$

and

$$J_{v-}^{\alpha} \mathcal{F}(\varpi) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{\varpi}^v (t - \varpi)^{\alpha-1} \mathcal{F}(t) dt, \quad \varpi < v.$$

Here, $\Gamma(\alpha)$ is the well-known Gamma function and $J_{\sigma+}^0 \mathcal{F}(\varpi) = J_{v-}^0 \mathcal{F}(\varpi) = \mathcal{F}(\varpi)$.

Definition 1.3 (See [30, 19]). Let $\mathcal{F} \in L[\sigma, v]$, where $0 \leq \sigma < v$. For $\alpha \geq 0$ and $\lambda \geq 0$, the tempered fractional integral operators $\mathfrak{J}_{\sigma+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}$ and $\mathfrak{J}_{v-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}$ are expressed as

$$\mathfrak{J}_{\sigma+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}(\varpi) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{\sigma}^{\varpi} (\varpi - t)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\varpi-t)} \mathcal{F}(t) dt, \quad \varpi \in [\sigma, v]$$

and

$$\mathfrak{J}_{v-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}(\varpi) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{\varpi}^v (t - \varpi)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(t-\varpi)} \mathcal{F}(t) dt, \quad \varpi \in [\sigma, v]$$

respectively.

By substituting $\lambda = 0$ in Definition 1.3, Definition 1.2 can be quickly produced. To go deeper into the many instances of tempered fractional integrals, it is recommended to refer to the following books: [27, 20].

The groundbreaking research of Buschman [2] introduced the notion of fractional integration with weak singular and exponential kernels, serving as the foundation for tempering fractional

calculus. Mohammad et al. [21] have generalized results based on Riemann and Riemann–Liouville integrals by introducing the λ -incomplete gamma function and establishing Hermite–Hadamard-type inequalities involving tempered fractional integrals. In [1], Simpson-type inequalities for convex functions have obtained using tempered fractional integral operators, based on Holder and power mean inequalities. This extended previous work employing Riemann–Liouville fractional integrals. In tempered fractional calculus, Kucche et al. [16] studied a Hilfer-type operator. They examined its major aspects, including compositional properties, mappings in function spaces, and other features of functional analysis. New integral inequalities for subadditive functions and their products have been introduced, with Kashuri et al. [17] formulating an identity and demonstrating various Hermite–Hadamard-type inequalities for subadditive functions that incorporate tempered fractional integrals. Many researchers have made significant contributions to the development of tempered fractional integral theories; refer to [4, 13, 32] and the cited references.

Inspired by earlier research, this work utilizes tempered fractional integrals to prove several inequalities of the type of Weddle’s formula. The analysis examines important categories of functions in the context of tempered fractional calculus, encompassing convex, bounded, Lipschitzian functions, and functions with bounded variation. The proposed findings offer an expanded view on fractional inequalities and illustrate the adaptability of the tempered fractional methodology. Additionally, the results build upon and expand existing frameworks, producing the Riemann–Liouville case for $\lambda = 0$ and traditional Weddle’s inequality for $\alpha = 1$.

The study is divided into three sections, beginning with the introduction and preliminaries, which provide a concise summary of appropriate research in the field and provide fundamental definitions of tempered fractional calculus. In Section 2, we investigate a variety of functional classes, such as Lipschitzian, bounded, and functions with bounded variation. In Section 3, we present a summary of our findings and propose potential directions for future research.

Lemma 1.1. Let $\mathcal{F} : [\sigma, v] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is an absolutely continuous function on the interval (σ, v) with $\mathcal{F}' \in L_1[\sigma, v]$, then the following holds:

$$\frac{1}{20} \left[\mathcal{F}(\sigma) + 5\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{v+5\sigma}{6}\right) + \mathcal{F}\left(\frac{v+2\sigma}{3}\right) + 6\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{\sigma+v}{2}\right) + \mathcal{F}\left(\frac{2v+\sigma}{3}\right) + 5\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{5v+\sigma}{6}\right) + \mathcal{F}(v) \right] - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2 \Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, v-\sigma)} \left[\mathfrak{I}_{v^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}(\sigma) + \mathfrak{I}_{\sigma^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}(v) \right] = \frac{(v-\sigma)^{\alpha+1}}{2 \Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, v-\sigma)} \sum_{i=1}^6 I_i, \tag{3}$$

where

$$\begin{cases} I_1 = \int_0^{\frac{1}{6}} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{1}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right) [\mathcal{F}'(tv + (1-t)\sigma) - \mathcal{F}'(t\sigma + (1-t)v)] dt, \\ I_2 = \int_{\frac{1}{6}}^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{6}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right) [\mathcal{F}'(tv + (1-t)\sigma) - \mathcal{F}'(t\sigma + (1-t)v)] dt, \\ I_3 = \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{7}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right) [\mathcal{F}'(tv + (1-t)\sigma) - \mathcal{F}'(t\sigma + (1-t)v)] dt, \end{cases}$$

$$\begin{cases} I_4 = \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{13}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right) [\mathcal{F}'(tv + (1-t)\sigma) - \mathcal{F}'(t\sigma + (1-t)v)] dt, \\ I_5 = \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^{\frac{5}{6}} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{14}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right) [\mathcal{F}'(tv + (1-t)\sigma) - \mathcal{F}'(t\sigma + (1-t)v)] dt, \\ I_6 = \int_{\frac{5}{6}}^1 \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{19}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right) [\mathcal{F}'(tv + (1-t)\sigma) - \mathcal{F}'(t\sigma + (1-t)v)] dt. \end{cases}$$

2 Main Results

Theorem 2.1. Suppose the conditions stated in Lemma 1.1 satisfied. If there exist $m, M \in \mathbb{R}$ such that $m \leq \mathcal{F}'(t) \leq M$ for $t \in [\sigma, v]$, then we have the subsequent inequality

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[\mathcal{F}(\sigma) + 5\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{v+5\sigma}{6}\right) + \mathcal{F}\left(\frac{v+2\sigma}{3}\right) + 6\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{\sigma+v}{2}\right) + \mathcal{F}\left(\frac{2v+\sigma}{3}\right) + 5\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{5v+\sigma}{6}\right) + \mathcal{F}(v) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2 \Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, v-\sigma)} \left[\mathfrak{Z}_{v^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}(\sigma) + \mathfrak{Z}_{\sigma^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}(v) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(v-\sigma)^{\alpha+1}}{2 \Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, v-\sigma)} [\mathbf{K}_1(\alpha, \lambda) + \mathbf{K}_2(\alpha, \lambda) + \mathbf{K}_3(\alpha, \lambda) + \mathbf{K}_4(\alpha, \lambda) + \mathbf{K}_5(\alpha, \lambda) + \mathbf{K}_6(\alpha, \lambda)] (M - m), \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

where

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{K}_1(\alpha, \lambda) = \int_0^{\frac{1}{6}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{1}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt, \\ \mathbf{K}_2(\alpha, \lambda) = \int_{\frac{1}{6}}^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{6}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt, \\ \mathbf{K}_3(\alpha, \lambda) = \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{7}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt, \\ \mathbf{K}_4(\alpha, \lambda) = \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{13}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt, \\ \mathbf{K}_5(\alpha, \lambda) = \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^{\frac{5}{6}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{14}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt, \\ \mathbf{K}_6(\alpha, \lambda) = \int_{\frac{5}{6}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{19}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt. \end{cases}$$

Proof. Considering Lemma 1.1, we can conclude

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{20} \left[\mathcal{F}(\sigma) + 5\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{v+5\sigma}{6}\right) + \mathcal{F}\left(\frac{v+2\sigma}{3}\right) + 6\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{\sigma+v}{2}\right) + \mathcal{F}\left(\frac{2v+\sigma}{3}\right) + 5\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{5v+\sigma}{6}\right) + \mathcal{F}(v) \right] \\ & \quad - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2 \Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, v-\sigma)} \left[\mathfrak{Z}_{v^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}(\sigma) + \mathfrak{Z}_{\sigma^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}(v) \right] \\ & = \frac{(v-\sigma)^{\alpha+1}}{2 \Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, v-\sigma)} \left[\int_0^{\frac{1}{6}} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{1}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right) \left[\mathcal{F}'(tv + (1-t)\sigma) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right] dt \right. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \int_{\frac{1}{6}}^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{6}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right) \left[\mathcal{F}'(tv + (1-t)\sigma) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right] dt \\
 & + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{7}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right) \left[\mathcal{F}'(tv + (1-t)\sigma) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right] dt \\
 & + \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{13}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right) \left[\mathcal{F}'(tv + (1-t)\sigma) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right] dt \\
 & + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^{\frac{5}{6}} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{14}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right) \left[\mathcal{F}'(tv + (1-t)\sigma) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right] dt \\
 & + \int_{\frac{5}{6}}^1 \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{19}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right) \left[\mathcal{F}'(tv + (1-t)\sigma) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right] dt \\
 & + \int_0^{\frac{1}{6}} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{1}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right) \left[\frac{m+M}{2} - \mathcal{F}'(t\sigma + (1-t)v) \right] dt \\
 & + \int_{\frac{1}{6}}^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{6}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right) \left[\frac{m+M}{2} - \mathcal{F}'(t\sigma + (1-t)v) \right] dt \\
 & + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{7}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right) \left[\frac{m+M}{2} - \mathcal{F}'(t\sigma + (1-t)v) \right] dt \\
 & + \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{13}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right) \left[\frac{m+M}{2} - \mathcal{F}'(t\sigma + (1-t)v) \right] dt \\
 & + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^{\frac{5}{6}} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{14}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right) \left[\frac{m+M}{2} - \mathcal{F}'(t\sigma + (1-t)v) \right] dt \\
 & + \int_{\frac{5}{6}}^1 \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{19}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right) \left[\frac{m+M}{2} - \mathcal{F}'(t\sigma + (1-t)v) \right] dt \Big]. \tag{5}
 \end{aligned}$$

Utilizing the modulus properties in (5), we can deduce

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[\mathcal{F}(\sigma) + 5\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{v+5\sigma}{6}\right) + \mathcal{F}\left(\frac{v+2\sigma}{3}\right) + 6\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{\sigma+v}{2}\right) + \mathcal{F}\left(\frac{2v+\sigma}{3}\right) + 5\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{5v+\sigma}{6}\right) + \mathcal{F}(v) \right] \right. \\
 & \quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2\Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, v-\sigma)} \left[\mathfrak{I}_{v-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}(\sigma) + \mathfrak{I}_{\sigma+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}(v) \right] \right| \\
 & \leq \frac{(v-\sigma)^{\alpha+1}}{2\Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, v-\sigma)} \left[\int_0^{\frac{1}{6}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{1}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left| \mathcal{F}'(tv + (1-t)\sigma) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right| dt \right. \\
 & \quad + \int_{\frac{1}{6}}^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{6}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left| \mathcal{F}'(tv + (1-t)\sigma) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right| dt \\
 & \quad + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{7}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left| \mathcal{F}'(tv + (1-t)\sigma) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right| dt \\
 & \quad + \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{13}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left| \mathcal{F}'(tv + (1-t)\sigma) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right| dt \\
 & \quad + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^{\frac{5}{6}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{14}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left| \mathcal{F}'(tv + (1-t)\sigma) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right| dt \\
 & \quad + \int_{\frac{5}{6}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{19}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left| \mathcal{F}'(tv + (1-t)\sigma) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right| dt
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + \int_0^{\frac{1}{6}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{1}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left| \frac{m+M}{2} - \mathcal{F}'(t\sigma + (1-t)v) \right| dt \\
& + \int_{\frac{1}{6}}^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{6}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left| \frac{m+M}{2} - \mathcal{F}'(t\sigma + (1-t)v) \right| dt \\
& + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{7}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left| \frac{m+M}{2} - \mathcal{F}'(t\sigma + (1-t)v) \right| dt \\
& + \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{13}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left| \frac{m+M}{2} - \mathcal{F}'(t\sigma + (1-t)v) \right| dt \\
& + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^{\frac{5}{6}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{14}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left| \frac{m+M}{2} - \mathcal{F}'(t\sigma + (1-t)v) \right| dt \\
& + \int_{\frac{5}{6}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{19}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left| \frac{m+M}{2} - \mathcal{F}'(t\sigma + (1-t)v) \right| dt \Big].
\end{aligned}$$

Assuming the given conditions $m \leq \mathcal{F}'(t) \leq M$ for $t \in [\sigma, v]$, it becomes

$$\left| \mathcal{F}'(tv + (1-t)\sigma) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right| \leq \frac{M-m}{2}, \tag{6}$$

and

$$\left| \frac{m+M}{2} - \mathcal{F}'(t\sigma + (1-t)v) \right| \leq \frac{M-m}{2}. \tag{7}$$

By employing inequalities (6) and (7), we gain

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[\mathcal{F}(\sigma) + 5\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{v+5\sigma}{6}\right) + \mathcal{F}\left(\frac{v+2\sigma}{3}\right) + 6\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{\sigma+v}{2}\right) + \mathcal{F}\left(\frac{2v+\sigma}{3}\right) + 5\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{5v+\sigma}{6}\right) + \mathcal{F}(v) \right] \right. \\
& \quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2\Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, v-\sigma)} \left[\mathfrak{I}_{v-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}(\sigma) + \mathfrak{I}_{\sigma+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}(v) \right] \right| \\
& \leq \frac{(v-\sigma)^{\alpha+1}}{2\Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, v-\sigma)} \left[\int_0^{\frac{1}{6}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{1}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt + \int_{\frac{1}{6}}^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{6}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt \right. \\
& \quad + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{7}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt + \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{13}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt \\
& \quad \left. + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^{\frac{5}{6}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{14}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt + \int_{\frac{5}{6}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{19}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt \right] (M-m) \\
& = \frac{(v-\sigma)^{\alpha+1}}{2\Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, v-\sigma)} [\mathbf{K}_1(\alpha, \lambda) + \mathbf{K}_2(\alpha, \lambda) + \mathbf{K}_3(\alpha, \lambda) + \mathbf{K}_4(\alpha, \lambda) + \mathbf{K}_5(\alpha, \lambda) + \mathbf{K}_6(\alpha, \lambda)] (M-m).
\end{aligned}$$

Hence, the proof is complete. □

Remark 2.1. Let us consider $\lambda = 0$ in Theorem 2.1, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[\mathcal{F}(\sigma) + 5\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{v+5\sigma}{6}\right) + \mathcal{F}\left(\frac{v+2\sigma}{3}\right) + 6\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{\sigma+v}{2}\right) + \mathcal{F}\left(\frac{2v+\sigma}{3}\right) + 5\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{5v+\sigma}{6}\right) + \mathcal{F}(v) \right] \right. \\
& \quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{2(v-\sigma)^\alpha} \left[\mathbf{J}_{v-}^\alpha \mathcal{F}(\sigma) + \mathbf{J}_{\sigma+}^\alpha \mathcal{F}(v) \right] \right|
\end{aligned}$$

$$\leq \frac{\alpha(v - \sigma)}{2} [\mathbf{K}_1(\alpha, 0) + \mathbf{K}_2(\alpha, 0) + \mathbf{K}_3(\alpha, 0) + \mathbf{K}_4(\alpha, 0) + \mathbf{K}_5(\alpha, 0) + \mathbf{K}_6(\alpha, 0)] (M - m),$$

which is reported in [22].

Remark 2.2. If we assign $\lambda = 0$ and $\alpha = 1$ in Theorem 2.1, then we get

$$\left| \frac{1}{20} \left[\mathcal{F}(\sigma) + 5\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{v + 5\sigma}{6}\right) + \mathcal{F}\left(\frac{v + 2\sigma}{3}\right) + 6\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{\sigma + v}{2}\right) + \mathcal{F}\left(\frac{2v + \sigma}{3}\right) + 5\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{5v + \sigma}{6}\right) + \mathcal{F}(v) \right] - \frac{1}{v - \sigma} \int_{\sigma}^v \mathcal{F}(t) dt \right| \leq \frac{13(v - \sigma)}{450} (|\mathcal{F}'(\sigma)| + |\mathcal{F}'(v)|) (M - m),$$

which is defined in [22, Theorem 5].

Corollary 2.1. Suppose the conditions stated in Theorem 2.1, for any t within the range $[\sigma, v]$, assuming the existence of a positive constant M satisfying $|\mathcal{F}'(t)| \leq M$, it gives

$$\left| \frac{1}{20} \left[\mathcal{F}(\sigma) + 5\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{v + 5\sigma}{6}\right) + \mathcal{F}\left(\frac{v + 2\sigma}{3}\right) + 6\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{\sigma + v}{2}\right) + \mathcal{F}\left(\frac{2v + \sigma}{3}\right) + 5\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{5v + \sigma}{6}\right) + \mathcal{F}(v) \right] - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2 \Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, v - \sigma)} \left[\mathfrak{I}_{v-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}(\sigma) + \mathfrak{I}_{\sigma+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}(v) \right] \right| \leq \frac{(v - \sigma)^{\alpha+1}}{\Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, v - \sigma)} [\mathbf{K}_1(\alpha, \lambda) + \mathbf{K}_2(\alpha, \lambda) + \mathbf{K}_3(\alpha, \lambda) + \mathbf{K}_4(\alpha, \lambda) + \mathbf{K}_5(\alpha, \lambda) + \mathbf{K}_6(\alpha, \lambda)] M.$$

Corollary 2.2. If we consider $\lambda = 0$, in Corollary 2.1, then we obtain

$$\left| \frac{1}{20} \left[\mathcal{F}(\sigma) + 5\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{v + 5\sigma}{6}\right) + \mathcal{F}\left(\frac{v + 2\sigma}{3}\right) + 6\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{\sigma + v}{2}\right) + \mathcal{F}\left(\frac{2v + \sigma}{3}\right) + 5\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{5v + \sigma}{6}\right) + \mathcal{F}(v) \right] - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{2(v - \sigma)^{\alpha}} \left[\mathcal{J}_{v-}^{\alpha} \mathcal{F}(\sigma) + \mathcal{J}_{\sigma+}^{\alpha} \mathcal{F}(v) \right] \right| \leq \alpha(v - \sigma) [\mathbf{K}_1(\alpha, 0) + \mathbf{K}_2(\alpha, 0) + \mathbf{K}_3(\alpha, 0) + \mathbf{K}_4(\alpha, 0) + \mathbf{K}_5(\alpha, 0) + \mathbf{K}_6(\alpha, 0)] M.$$

Corollary 2.3. Let $\lambda = 0$ and $\alpha = 1$ in Corollary 2.1. Then, it yields

$$\left| \frac{1}{20} \left[\mathcal{F}(\sigma) + 5\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{v + 5\sigma}{6}\right) + \mathcal{F}\left(\frac{v + 2\sigma}{3}\right) + 6\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{\sigma + v}{2}\right) + \mathcal{F}\left(\frac{2v + \sigma}{3}\right) + 5\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{5v + \sigma}{6}\right) + \mathcal{F}(v) \right] - \frac{1}{v - \sigma} \int_{\sigma}^v \mathcal{F}(t) dt \right| \leq \frac{13(v - \sigma)}{225} M.$$

Theorem 2.2. Suppose the conditions stated in Lemma 1.1 hold. If \mathcal{F}' is an Lipschitzian functions on the interval $[\sigma, v]$, then we have the subsequent inequality

$$\left| \frac{1}{20} \left[\mathcal{F}(\sigma) + 5\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{v + 5\sigma}{6}\right) + \mathcal{F}\left(\frac{v + 2\sigma}{3}\right) + 6\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{\sigma + v}{2}\right) + \mathcal{F}\left(\frac{2v + \sigma}{3}\right) + 5\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{5v + \sigma}{6}\right) + \mathcal{F}(v) \right] - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2 \Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, v - \sigma)} \left[\mathfrak{I}_{v-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}(\sigma) + \mathfrak{I}_{\sigma+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}(v) \right] \right| \leq \frac{(v - \sigma)^{\alpha+2}}{2 \Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, v - \sigma)} [\mathbf{K}_1(\alpha, \lambda) + \mathbf{K}_2(\alpha, \lambda) + \mathbf{K}_3(\alpha, \lambda) - \mathbf{K}_4(\alpha, \lambda) - \mathbf{K}_5(\alpha, \lambda) - \mathbf{K}_6(\alpha, \lambda) - 2(\mathbf{K}_7(\alpha, \lambda) + \mathbf{K}_8(\alpha, \lambda) + \mathbf{K}_9(\alpha, \lambda)) + 2(\mathbf{K}_{10}(\alpha, \lambda) + \mathbf{K}_{11}(\alpha, \lambda) + \mathbf{K}_{12}(\alpha, \lambda))] L. \tag{8}$$

Here, $K_1(\alpha, \lambda) - K_{12}(\alpha, \lambda)$ are defined as in Theorem 2.1 and

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} K_7(\alpha, \lambda) = \int_0^{\frac{1}{6}} t \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{1}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt, \\ K_8(\alpha, \lambda) = \int_{\frac{1}{6}}^{\frac{1}{3}} t \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{6}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt, \\ K_9(\alpha, \lambda) = \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{1}{2}} t \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{7}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt, \\ K_{10}(\alpha, \lambda) = \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{2}{3}} t \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{13}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt, \\ K_{11}(\alpha, \lambda) = \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^{\frac{5}{6}} t \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{14}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt, \\ K_{12}(\alpha, \lambda) = \int_{\frac{5}{6}}^1 t \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{19}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt. \end{array} \right.$$

Proof. Using the modulus in Lemma 1.1, it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[\mathcal{F}(\sigma) + 5\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{v+5\sigma}{6}\right) + \mathcal{F}\left(\frac{v+2\sigma}{3}\right) + 6\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{\sigma+v}{2}\right) + \mathcal{F}\left(\frac{2v+\sigma}{3}\right) + 5\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{5v+\sigma}{6}\right) + \mathcal{F}(v) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2 \Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, v-\sigma)} \left[\mathfrak{Z}_{v-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}(\sigma) + \mathfrak{Z}_{\sigma+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}(v) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(v-\sigma)^{\alpha+1}}{2 \Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, v-\sigma)} \left[\int_0^{\frac{1}{6}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{1}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right| |\mathcal{F}'(tv + (1-t)\sigma) - \mathcal{F}'(t\sigma + (1-t)v)| dt \right. \\ & \quad + \int_{\frac{1}{6}}^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{6}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right| |\mathcal{F}'(tv + (1-t)\sigma) - \mathcal{F}'(t\sigma + (1-t)v)| dt \\ & \quad + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{7}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right| |\mathcal{F}'(tv + (1-t)\sigma) - \mathcal{F}'(t\sigma + (1-t)v)| dt \\ & \quad + \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{13}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right| |\mathcal{F}'(tv + (1-t)\sigma) - \mathcal{F}'(t\sigma + (1-t)v)| dt \\ & \quad + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^{\frac{5}{6}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{14}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right| |\mathcal{F}'(tv + (1-t)\sigma) - \mathcal{F}'(t\sigma + (1-t)v)| dt \\ & \quad \left. + \int_{\frac{5}{6}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{19}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right| |\mathcal{F}'(tv + (1-t)\sigma) - \mathcal{F}'(t\sigma + (1-t)v)| dt \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Given that \mathcal{F}' is L-Lipschitzian function, we acquire

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[\mathcal{F}(\sigma) + 5\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{v+5\sigma}{6}\right) + \mathcal{F}\left(\frac{v+2\sigma}{3}\right) + 6\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{\sigma+v}{2}\right) + \mathcal{F}\left(\frac{2v+\sigma}{3}\right) + 5\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{5v+\sigma}{6}\right) + \mathcal{F}(v) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2 \Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, v-\sigma)} \left[\mathfrak{Z}_{v-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}(\sigma) + \mathfrak{Z}_{\sigma+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}(v) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(v-\sigma)^{\alpha+1}}{2 \Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, v-\sigma)} \left[\left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{6}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{1}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. + \int_{\frac{1}{6}}^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{6}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{7}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt \right) \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \times L(1 - 2t)(v - \sigma) + \left(\int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{13}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt \right. \\
 & \left. + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^{\frac{5}{6}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{14}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt + \int_{\frac{5}{6}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{19}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\sigma)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt \right) \\
 & \times L(2t - 1)(v - \sigma) \\
 & = \frac{(v - \sigma)^{\alpha+2}}{2 \Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, v - \sigma)} [K_1(\alpha, \lambda) + K_2(\alpha, \lambda) + K_3(\alpha, \lambda) - K_4(\alpha, \lambda) - K_5(\alpha, \lambda) - K_6(\alpha, \lambda) \\
 & \quad - 2(K_7(\alpha, \lambda) + K_8(\alpha, \lambda) + K_9(\alpha, \lambda)) + 2(K_{10}(\alpha, \lambda) + K_{11}(\alpha, \lambda) + K_{12}(\alpha, \lambda))] L.
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence, the theorem is proved. □

Remark 2.3. Taking $\lambda = 0$ in Theorem 2.2, we deduce

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[\mathcal{F}(\sigma) + 5\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{v + 5\sigma}{6}\right) + \mathcal{F}\left(\frac{v + 2\sigma}{3}\right) + 6\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{\sigma + v}{2}\right) + \mathcal{F}\left(\frac{2v + \sigma}{3}\right) + 5\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{5v + \sigma}{6}\right) + \mathcal{F}(v) \right] \right. \\
 & \quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{2(v - \sigma)^\alpha} [J_{v-}^\alpha \mathcal{F}(\sigma) + J_{\sigma+}^\alpha \mathcal{F}(v)] \right| \\
 & \leq \frac{\alpha(v - \sigma)^2}{2} [K_1(\alpha, 0) + K_2(\alpha, 0) + K_3(\alpha, 0) - K_4(\alpha, 0) - K_5(\alpha, 0) - K_6(\alpha, 0) \\
 & \quad - 2(K_7(\alpha, 0) + K_8(\alpha, 0) + K_9(\alpha, 0)) + 2(K_{10}(\alpha, 0) + K_{11}(\alpha, 0) + K_{12}(\alpha, 0))] L,
 \end{aligned}$$

which is derived in [22].

Remark 2.4. If we select $\lambda = 0$ and $\alpha = 1$ in Theorem 2.2, then we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[\mathcal{F}(\sigma) + 5\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{v + 5\sigma}{6}\right) + \mathcal{F}\left(\frac{v + 2\sigma}{3}\right) + 6\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{\sigma + v}{2}\right) + \mathcal{F}\left(\frac{2v + \sigma}{3}\right) + 5\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{5v + \sigma}{6}\right) + \mathcal{F}(v) \right] \right. \\
 & \quad \left. - \frac{1}{v - \sigma} \int_{\sigma}^v \mathcal{F}(t) dt \right| \leq \frac{23(v - \sigma)^2}{1800} L,
 \end{aligned}$$

which is defined in [22, Corollary 6].

Theorem 2.3. Consider a function $\mathcal{F} : [\sigma, v] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ exhibiting bounded variation over the interval $[\sigma, v]$, then we have the following inequality

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[\mathcal{F}(\sigma) + 5\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{v + 5\sigma}{6}\right) + \mathcal{F}\left(\frac{v + 2\sigma}{3}\right) + 6\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{\sigma + v}{2}\right) + \mathcal{F}\left(\frac{2v + \sigma}{3}\right) + 5\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{5v + \sigma}{6}\right) + \mathcal{F}(v) \right] \right. \\
 & \quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2 \Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, v - \sigma)} \left[\mathfrak{I}_{v-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}(\sigma) + \mathfrak{I}_{\sigma+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}(v) \right] \right| \\
 & \leq \frac{1}{2 \Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, v - \sigma)} \left[\max \left\{ \frac{1}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, v - \sigma), \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{v - \sigma}{6}\right) - \frac{1}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right|, \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{v - \sigma}{6}\right) - \frac{6}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right|, \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{v - \sigma}{3}\right) - \frac{6}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right|, \\
 & \quad \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{v - \sigma}{3}\right) - \frac{7}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right|, \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{v - \sigma}{2}\right) - \frac{7}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right|, \\
 & \quad \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{v - \sigma}{2}\right) - \frac{13}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right|, \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{2(v - \sigma)}{3}\right) - \frac{13}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right|, \\
 & \quad \left. \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{2(v - \sigma)}{3}\right) - \frac{14}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right|, \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{5(v - \sigma)}{6}\right) - \frac{14}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right|, \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{5(v - \sigma)}{6}\right) - \frac{19}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right| \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\left| \gamma_\lambda \left(\alpha, \frac{5(v-\sigma)}{6} \right) - \frac{19}{20} \gamma_\lambda (\alpha, v-\sigma) \right|, \left| \frac{1}{20} \gamma_\lambda (\alpha, v-\sigma) \right| \left\} \bigvee_\sigma^v(\mathcal{F}) \right], \quad (9)$$

where $\bigvee_\sigma^v(\mathcal{F})$ indicate the total variation of \mathcal{F} on $[\sigma, v]$.

Proof. Let us define the mappings

$$P_\alpha(t) = \begin{cases} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, t-\sigma) - \frac{1}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v-\sigma), & \sigma \leq t \leq \frac{v+5\sigma}{6}, \\ \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, t-\sigma) - \frac{6}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v-\sigma), & \frac{v+5\sigma}{6} < t \leq \frac{v+2\sigma}{3}, \\ \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, t-\sigma) - \frac{7}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v-\sigma), & \frac{v+2\sigma}{3} < t \leq \frac{\sigma+v}{2}, \\ \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, t-\sigma) - \frac{13}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v-\sigma), & \frac{\sigma+v}{2} < t \leq \frac{2v+\sigma}{3}, \\ \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, t-\sigma) - \frac{14}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v-\sigma), & \frac{2v+\sigma}{3} < t \leq \frac{5v+\sigma}{6}, \\ \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, t-\sigma) - \frac{19}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v-\sigma), & \frac{5v+\sigma}{6} < t \leq v, \end{cases}$$

and

$$T_\alpha(t) = \begin{cases} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v-t) - \frac{1}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v-\sigma), & \sigma \leq t \leq \frac{v+5\sigma}{6}, \\ \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v-t) - \frac{6}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v-\sigma), & \frac{v+5\sigma}{6} < t \leq \frac{v+2\sigma}{3}, \\ \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v-t) - \frac{7}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v-\sigma), & \frac{v+2\sigma}{3} < t \leq \frac{\sigma+v}{2}, \\ \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v-t) - \frac{13}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v-\sigma), & \frac{\sigma+v}{2} < t \leq \frac{2v+\sigma}{3}, \\ \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v-t) - \frac{14}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v-\sigma), & \frac{2v+\sigma}{3} < t \leq \frac{5v+\sigma}{6}, \\ \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v-t) - \frac{19}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v-\sigma), & \frac{5v+\sigma}{6} < t \leq v. \end{cases}$$

Through the techniques of integration by parts, we arrive at

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_\sigma^v P_\alpha(t) d\mathcal{F}(t) \\ &= \int_\sigma^{\frac{v+5\sigma}{6}} \left(\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, t-\sigma) - \frac{1}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v-\sigma) \right) d\mathcal{F}(t) + \int_{\frac{v+5\sigma}{6}}^{\frac{v+2\sigma}{3}} \left(\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, t-\sigma) - \frac{6}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v-\sigma) \right) d\mathcal{F}(t) \\ & \quad + \int_{\frac{v+2\sigma}{3}}^{\frac{\sigma+v}{2}} \left(\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, t-\sigma) - \frac{7}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v-\sigma) \right) d\mathcal{F}(t) + \int_{\frac{\sigma+v}{2}}^{\frac{2v+\sigma}{3}} \left(\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, t-\sigma) - \frac{13}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v-\sigma) \right) d\mathcal{F}(t) \\ & \quad + \int_{\frac{2v+\sigma}{3}}^{\frac{5v+\sigma}{6}} \left(\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, t-\sigma) - \frac{14}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v-\sigma) \right) d\mathcal{F}(t) + \int_{\frac{5v+\sigma}{6}}^v \left(\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, t-\sigma) - \frac{19}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v-\sigma) \right) d\mathcal{F}(t) \\ &= \left(\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, t-\sigma) - \frac{1}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v-\sigma) \right) \mathcal{F}(t) \Big|_\sigma^{\frac{v+5\sigma}{6}} - \int_\sigma^{\frac{v+5\sigma}{6}} (t-\sigma)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(t-\sigma)} \mathcal{F}(t) d\mathcal{F}(t) \\ & \quad + \left(\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, t-\sigma) - \frac{6}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v-\sigma) \right) \mathcal{F}(t) \Big|_{\frac{v+5\sigma}{6}}^{\frac{v+2\sigma}{3}} - \int_{\frac{v+5\sigma}{6}}^{\frac{v+2\sigma}{3}} (t-\sigma)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(t-\sigma)} \mathcal{F}(t) d\mathcal{F}(t) \\ & \quad + \left(\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, t-\sigma) - \frac{7}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v-\sigma) \right) \mathcal{F}(t) \Big|_{\frac{v+2\sigma}{3}}^{\frac{\sigma+v}{2}} - \int_{\frac{v+2\sigma}{3}}^{\frac{\sigma+v}{2}} (t-\sigma)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(t-\sigma)} \mathcal{F}(t) d\mathcal{F}(t) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \left(\Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, t - \sigma) - \frac{13}{20} \Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right) \mathcal{F}(t) \Big|_{\frac{\sigma+v}{2}}^{\frac{2v+\sigma}{3}} - \int_{\frac{\sigma+v}{2}}^{\frac{2v+\sigma}{3}} (t - \sigma)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(t-\sigma)} \mathcal{F}(t) d\mathcal{F}(t) \\
 & + \left(\Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, t - \sigma) - \frac{14}{20} \Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right) \mathcal{F}(t) \Big|_{\frac{2v+\sigma}{3}}^{\frac{5v+\sigma}{6}} - \int_{\frac{2v+\sigma}{3}}^{\frac{5v+\sigma}{6}} (t - \sigma)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(t-\sigma)} \mathcal{F}(t) d\mathcal{F}(t) \\
 & + \left(\Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, t - \sigma) - \frac{19}{20} \Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right) \mathcal{F}(t) \Big|_{\frac{5v+\sigma}{6}}^v - \int_{\frac{5v+\sigma}{6}}^v (t - \sigma)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(t-\sigma)} \mathcal{F}(t) d\mathcal{F}(t) \\
 & = \frac{\Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma)}{20} \left[\mathcal{F}(\sigma) + 5\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{v+5\sigma}{6}\right) + \mathcal{F}\left(\frac{v+2\sigma}{3}\right) + 6\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{\sigma+v}{2}\right) \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + \mathcal{F}\left(\frac{2v+\sigma}{3}\right) + 5\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{5v+\sigma}{6}\right) + \mathcal{F}(v) \right] - \Gamma(\alpha) \mathfrak{Z}_{v-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}(\sigma).
 \end{aligned}$$

Likewise, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 \int_\sigma^v \Upsilon_\alpha(t) d\mathcal{F}(t) & = \frac{\Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma)}{20} \left[\mathcal{F}(\sigma) + 5\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{v+5\sigma}{6}\right) + \mathcal{F}\left(\frac{v+2\sigma}{3}\right) + 6\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{\sigma+v}{2}\right) \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + \mathcal{F}\left(\frac{2v+\sigma}{3}\right) + 5\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{5v+\sigma}{6}\right) + \mathcal{F}(v) \right] - \Gamma(\alpha) \mathfrak{Z}_{\sigma+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}(v).
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence, we acquire

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{1}{20} \left[\mathcal{F}(\sigma) + 5\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{v+5\sigma}{6}\right) + \mathcal{F}\left(\frac{v+2\sigma}{3}\right) + 6\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{\sigma+v}{2}\right) \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + \mathcal{F}\left(\frac{2v+\sigma}{3}\right) + 5\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{5v+\sigma}{6}\right) + \mathcal{F}(v) \right] - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2 \Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma)} \left[\mathfrak{Z}_{v-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}(\sigma) + \mathfrak{Z}_{\sigma+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}(v) \right] \\
 & = \frac{1}{2 \Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma)} \int_\sigma^v [\mathbb{P}_\alpha(t) + \Upsilon_\alpha(t)] d\mathcal{F}(t).
 \end{aligned}$$

It is a well-established fact that if $\mathbf{g}, \mathcal{F} : [\sigma, v] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are such that \mathbf{g} is continuous on $[\sigma, v]$ and \mathcal{F} is bounded variation on $[\sigma, v]$, then $\int_\sigma^v \mathbf{g}(\tau) d\mathcal{F}(\tau)$ exist and

$$\left| \int_\sigma^v \mathbf{g}(\tau) d\mathcal{F}(\tau) \right| \leq \sup_{\tau \in [\sigma, v]} |\mathbf{g}(\tau)| \bigvee_\sigma^v(\mathcal{F}). \tag{10}$$

On the other hand, using (10), we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[\mathcal{F}(\sigma) + 5\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{v+5\sigma}{6}\right) + \mathcal{F}\left(\frac{v+2\sigma}{3}\right) + 6\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{\sigma+v}{2}\right) \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. + \mathcal{F}\left(\frac{2v+\sigma}{3}\right) + 5\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{5v+\sigma}{6}\right) + \mathcal{F}(v) \right] - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2 \Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma)} \left[\mathfrak{Z}_{v-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}(\sigma) + \mathfrak{Z}_{\sigma+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathcal{F}(v) \right] \right| \\
 & \leq \frac{1}{2 \Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma)} \left[\left| \int_\sigma^v \mathbb{P}_\alpha(t) d\mathcal{F}(t) \right| + \left| \int_\sigma^v \mathbb{R}_\alpha(t) d\mathcal{F}(t) \right| \right] \\
 & \leq \frac{1}{2 \Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma)} \left[\left| \int_\sigma^{\frac{v+5\sigma}{6}} \left(\Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, t - \sigma) - \frac{1}{20} \Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right) d\mathcal{F}(t) \right| \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + \left| \int_{\frac{v+5\sigma}{6}}^{\frac{v+2\sigma}{3}} \left(\Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, t - \sigma) - \frac{6}{20} \Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right) d\mathcal{F}(t) \right| + \left| \int_{\frac{v+2\sigma}{3}}^{\frac{\sigma+v}{2}} \left(\Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, t - \sigma) - \frac{7}{20} \Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right) d\mathcal{F}(t) \right| \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + \left| \int_{\frac{\sigma+v}{2}}^{\frac{2v+\sigma}{3}} \left(\Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, t - \sigma) - \frac{13}{20} \Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right) d\mathcal{F}(t) \right| + \left| \int_{\frac{2v+\sigma}{3}}^{\frac{5v+\sigma}{6}} \left(\Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, t - \sigma) - \frac{14}{20} \Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right) d\mathcal{F}(t) \right| \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + \left| \int_{\frac{5v+\sigma}{6}}^v \left(\Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, t - \sigma) - \frac{19}{20} \Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right) d\mathcal{F}(t) \right| \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + \left| \int_{\frac{5v+\sigma}{6}}^v \left(\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, t - \sigma) - \frac{19}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right) d\mathcal{F}(t) \right| + \left| \int_\sigma^{\frac{v+5\sigma}{6}} \left(\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - t) - \frac{1}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right) d\mathcal{F}(t) \right| \\
& + \left| \int_{\frac{v+2\sigma}{3}}^{\frac{v+5\sigma}{6}} \left(\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - t) - \frac{6}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right) d\mathcal{F}(t) \right| + \left| \int_{\frac{v+2\sigma}{3}}^{\frac{\sigma+v}{2}} \left(\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - t) - \frac{7}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right) d\mathcal{F}(t) \right| \\
& + \left| \int_{\frac{\sigma+v}{2}}^{\frac{2v+\sigma}{3}} \left(\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - t) - \frac{13}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right) d\mathcal{F}(t) \right| + \left| \int_{\frac{2v+\sigma}{3}}^{\frac{5v+\sigma}{6}} \left(\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - t) - \frac{14}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right) d\mathcal{F}(t) \right| \\
& + \left| \int_{\frac{5v+\sigma}{6}}^v \left(\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - t) - \frac{19}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right) d\mathcal{F}(t) \right| \\
\leq & \frac{1}{2 \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma)} \left[\sup_{t \in [\sigma, \frac{v+5\sigma}{6}]} \left| \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, t - \sigma) - \frac{1}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right| \bigvee_{\sigma}^{\frac{v+5\sigma}{6}} (\mathcal{F}) \right. \\
& + \sup_{t \in [\frac{v+5\sigma}{6}, \frac{v+2\sigma}{3}]} \left| \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, t - \sigma) - \frac{6}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right| \bigvee_{\frac{v+5\sigma}{6}}^{\frac{v+2\sigma}{3}} (\mathcal{F}) \\
& + \sup_{t \in [\frac{v+2\sigma}{3}, \frac{\sigma+v}{2}]} \left| \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, t - \sigma) - \frac{7}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right| \bigvee_{\frac{v+2\sigma}{3}}^{\frac{\sigma+v}{2}} (\mathcal{F}) \\
& + \sup_{t \in [\frac{\sigma+v}{2}, \frac{2v+\sigma}{3}]} \left| \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, t - \sigma) - \frac{13}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right| \bigvee_{\frac{\sigma+v}{2}}^{\frac{2v+\sigma}{3}} (\mathcal{F}) \\
& + \sup_{t \in [\frac{2v+\sigma}{3}, \frac{5v+\sigma}{6}]} \left| \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, t - \sigma) - \frac{14}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right| \bigvee_{\frac{2v+\sigma}{3}}^{\frac{5v+\sigma}{6}} (\mathcal{F}) \\
& + \sup_{t \in [\frac{5v+\sigma}{6}, v]} \left| \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, t - \sigma) - \frac{19}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right| \bigvee_{\frac{5v+\sigma}{6}}^v (\mathcal{F}) \\
& + \sup_{t \in [\sigma, \frac{v+5\sigma}{6}]} \left| \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, t - \sigma) - \frac{19}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right| \bigvee_{\sigma}^{\frac{v+5\sigma}{6}} (\mathcal{F}) \\
& + \sup_{t \in [\frac{v+5\sigma}{6}, \frac{v+2\sigma}{3}]} \left| \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, t - \sigma) - \frac{14}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right| \bigvee_{\frac{v+5\sigma}{6}}^{\frac{v+2\sigma}{3}} (\mathcal{F}) \\
& + \sup_{t \in [\frac{v+2\sigma}{3}, \frac{\sigma+v}{2}]} \left| \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, t - \sigma) - \frac{13}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right| \bigvee_{\frac{v+2\sigma}{3}}^{\frac{\sigma+v}{2}} (\mathcal{F}) \\
& + \sup_{t \in [\frac{\sigma+v}{2}, \frac{2v+\sigma}{3}]} \left| \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, t - \sigma) - \frac{7}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right| \bigvee_{\frac{\sigma+v}{2}}^{\frac{2v+\sigma}{3}} (\mathcal{F}) \\
& + \sup_{t \in [\frac{2v+\sigma}{3}, \frac{5v+\sigma}{6}]} \left| \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, t - \sigma) - \frac{6}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right| \bigvee_{\frac{2v+\sigma}{3}}^{\frac{5v+\sigma}{6}} (\mathcal{F}) \\
& + \left. \sup_{t \in [\frac{5v+\sigma}{6}, v]} \left| \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, t - \sigma) - \frac{1}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right| \bigvee_{\frac{5v+\sigma}{6}}^v (\mathcal{F}) \right]
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \frac{1}{2 \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma)} \left[\max \left\{ \frac{1}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma), \left| \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{v - \sigma}{6}\right) - \frac{1}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right| \right\} \bigvee_{\sigma}^{\frac{v+5\sigma}{6}} (\mathcal{F}) \right. \\
 &+ \max \left\{ \left| \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{v - \sigma}{6}\right) - \frac{6}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right|, \left| \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{v - \sigma}{3}\right) - \frac{6}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right| \right\} \bigvee_{\frac{v+5\sigma}{6}}^{\frac{v+2\sigma}{3}} (\mathcal{F}) \\
 &+ \max \left\{ \left| \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{v - \sigma}{3}\right) - \frac{7}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right|, \left| \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{v - \sigma}{2}\right) - \frac{7}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right| \right\} \bigvee_{\frac{v+2\sigma}{3}}^{\frac{\sigma+v}{2}} (\mathcal{F}) \\
 &+ \max \left\{ \left| \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{v - \sigma}{2}\right) - \frac{13}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right|, \left| \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{2(v - \sigma)}{3}\right) - \frac{13}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right| \right\} \bigvee_{\frac{\sigma+v}{2}}^{\frac{2v+\sigma}{3}} (\mathcal{F}) \\
 &+ \max \left\{ \left| \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{2(v - \sigma)}{3}\right) - \frac{14}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right|, \left| \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{5(v - \sigma)}{6}\right) - \frac{14}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right| \right\} \bigvee_{\frac{2v+\sigma}{3}}^{\frac{5v+\sigma}{6}} (\mathcal{F}) \\
 &+ \max \left\{ \left| \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{5(v - \sigma)}{6}\right) - \frac{19}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right|, \frac{1}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right\} \bigvee_{\frac{5v+\sigma}{6}}^v (\mathcal{F}) \\
 &+ \max \left\{ \frac{1}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma), \left| \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{5(v - \sigma)}{6}\right) - \frac{19}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right| \right\} \bigvee_{\sigma}^{\frac{v+5\sigma}{6}} (\mathcal{F}) \\
 &+ \max \left\{ \left| \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{5(v - \sigma)}{6}\right) - \frac{14}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right|, \left| \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{2(v - \sigma)}{3}\right) - \frac{14}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right| \right\} \bigvee_{\frac{v+5\sigma}{6}}^{\frac{v+2\sigma}{3}} (\mathcal{F}) \\
 &+ \max \left\{ \left| \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{2(v - \sigma)}{3}\right) - \frac{13}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right|, \left| \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{v - \sigma}{2}\right) - \frac{13}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right| \right\} \bigvee_{\frac{v+2\sigma}{3}}^{\frac{\sigma+v}{2}} (\mathcal{F}) \\
 &+ \max \left\{ \left| \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{v - \sigma}{2}\right) - \frac{7}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right|, \left| \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{v - \sigma}{3}\right) - \frac{7}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right| \right\} \bigvee_{\frac{\sigma+v}{2}}^{\frac{2v+\sigma}{3}} (\mathcal{F}) \\
 &+ \max \left\{ \left| \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{v - \sigma}{3}\right) - \frac{6}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right|, \left| \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{v - \sigma}{6}\right) - \frac{6}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right| \right\} \bigvee_{\frac{2v+\sigma}{3}}^{\frac{5v+\sigma}{6}} (\mathcal{F}) \\
 &+ \max \left\{ \left| \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{v - \sigma}{6}\right) - \frac{1}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right|, \frac{1}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right\} \bigvee_{\frac{5v+\sigma}{6}}^v (\mathcal{F}) \left. \right] \\
 &\leq \frac{1}{2 \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma)} \left[\max \left\{ \frac{1}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma), \left| \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{v - \sigma}{6}\right) - \frac{1}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right|, \right. \right. \\
 &\left| \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{v - \sigma}{6}\right) - \frac{6}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right|, \left| \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{v - \sigma}{3}\right) - \frac{6}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right| \\
 &\left| \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{v - \sigma}{3}\right) - \frac{7}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right|, \left| \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{v - \sigma}{2}\right) - \frac{7}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right|, \\
 &\left| \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{v - \sigma}{2}\right) - \frac{13}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right|, \left| \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{2(v - \sigma)}{3}\right) - \frac{13}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right| \\
 &\left| \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{2(v - \sigma)}{3}\right) - \frac{14}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right|, \left| \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{5(v - \sigma)}{6}\right) - \frac{14}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right| \\
 &\left. \left| \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{5(v - \sigma)}{6}\right) - \frac{19}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right|, \frac{1}{20} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, v - \sigma) \right\} \bigvee_{\sigma}^v (\mathcal{F}) \right].
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, the proof is established. \square

Corollary 2.4. By setting $\lambda = 0$ in Theorem 2.3, we gain

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[\mathcal{F}(\sigma) + 5\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{v+5\sigma}{6}\right) + \mathcal{F}\left(\frac{v+2\sigma}{3}\right) + 6\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{\sigma+v}{2}\right) + \mathcal{F}\left(\frac{2v+\sigma}{3}\right) + 5\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{5v+\sigma}{6}\right) + \mathcal{F}(v) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{2(v-\sigma)^\alpha} [J_{v-}^\alpha \mathcal{F}(\sigma) + J_{\sigma+}^\alpha \mathcal{F}(v)] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{1}{2} \max \left\{ \frac{1}{20}, \left| \frac{1}{6^\alpha} - \frac{1}{20} \right|, \left| \frac{1}{6^\alpha} - \frac{6}{20} \right|, \left| \frac{1}{3^\alpha} - \frac{6}{20} \right|, \left| \frac{1}{3^\alpha} - \frac{7}{20} \right|, \left| \frac{1}{2^\alpha} - \frac{7}{20} \right|, \left| \frac{1}{2^\alpha} - \frac{13}{20} \right|, \left| \frac{2^\alpha}{3^\alpha} - \frac{13}{20} \right|, \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left| \frac{2^\alpha}{3^\alpha} - \frac{14}{20} \right|, \left| \frac{5^\alpha}{6^\alpha} - \frac{14}{20} \right|, \left| \frac{5^\alpha}{6^\alpha} - \frac{19}{20} \right| \right\} \mathcal{V}_\sigma^v(\mathcal{F}). \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 2.5. If we select $\lambda = 0$ and $\alpha = 1$ in Theorem 2.3, then we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[\mathcal{F}(\sigma) + 5\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{v+5\sigma}{6}\right) + \mathcal{F}\left(\frac{v+2\sigma}{3}\right) + 6\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{\sigma+v}{2}\right) + \mathcal{F}\left(\frac{2v+\sigma}{3}\right) + 5\mathcal{F}\left(\frac{5v+\sigma}{6}\right) + \mathcal{F}(v) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{1}{v-\sigma} \int_\sigma^v \mathcal{F}(t) dt \right| \leq \frac{7}{40} \mathcal{V}_\sigma^v(\mathcal{F}). \end{aligned}$$

3 Conclusion

In this investigation, we provided a thorough examination and exhaustive derivation of integral inequalities for differentiable convex functions. We initially identified a critical integral identity that involves tempered fractional integrals. This identity is subsequently employed to deduce Weddle's type inequalities for differentiable convex functions. The research investigates noteworthy functional categories, such as bounded, Lipschitzian, and functions of bounded variation, it makes substantial contributions to the field of computational mathematics and its applications. Numerical examples and graphical illustrations are included to validate the significance and validity of these newly established inequalities within the tempered fractional integral perspective. Additionally, readers can investigate different fractional integrals and delve deeper into the implications of these findings across various mathematical fields.

Author contributions

Conceptualization: A. Shehzadi., H. Budak.; Methodology: W. Haider., A. Shehzadi., M.Z. Sarikaya; Software: A. Shehzadi.; Validation: A. Ahehzadi., M.Z. Sarikaya., W. Haider., and H. Budak.; Writing-original draft: A. Shehzadi.; Writing-review & editing: M.Z. Sarikaya., A. Shehzadi., and H. Budak.; Supervision: H. Budak; Project administration: A, Shehzadi; All authors have read and agreed to the final version of the manuscript.

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Refinement of Fractional Weddle's-Type Inequalities via Tempered Fractional Integrals

Asra Ahmad¹, Hüseyin Budak², Bilal Ahmad³, Asia Shehzadi⁴, Wali Haider⁵

¹Department of Mathematics and Statistics, University of Agriculture Faisalabad, Pakistan

²Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Science and Arts, Kocaeli University, Kocaeli 41001, Türkiye

³School of Mathematics and Computational Science, Xiangtan University, Xiangtan, 411105, China

⁴School of Mathematics and Statistics, Central South University, Changsha 410083, China

⁵School of Mathematics and Statistics, Shaanxi Normal University, Xi'an, Shaanxi, 710119, China

Corresponding author: haiderwali416@gmail.com

ORCID IDs:

First Author: 0009-0008-7864-3635

Second Author: 0000-0001-8843-955X

Third Author: 0009-0002-8603-0421

Fourth Author: 0009-0005-1101-5536

Fifth Author: 0009-0001-7065-2755

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Abstract

Fractional calculus generalizes classical differentiation and integration of arbitrary order. It offers practical analytical tools for describing complex phenomena exhibiting memory and nonlocal behavior. This investigation introduces unique inequalities for convex functions employing tempered fractional integrals, focusing on Weddle's type inequalities. A significant equality is formulated within the framework of tempered fractional integrals. Based on this identity, we develop various Weddle-type inequalities for differentiable convex mappings connected with tempered fractional integrals. These mappings extend the applicability of fractional calculus by extending classical notions and presenting further insight into the behavior of convex functions. We attain distinctive types of Weddle's type inequalities by involving key mathematical tools such as Holder's and power mean inequality, enhancing the implementation of these inequalities in diverse mathematical domains.

Keywords: Weddle's formula type inequality, convex function, tempered fractional integrals

1 Introduction and Motivation

By adding derivatives and integrals of fractional/non-integer orders, fractional calculus (FC), which was originally presented in 1695 through the correspondence between Leibniz and the Marquis de l'Hospital, expands on classical calculus. Later, mathematicians like Euler, Liouville, and Riemann developed the theory, and during the 19th century, it was acknowledged as a crucial tool in both theoretical and applied mathematics. FC is unique because of its non-local nature, which makes it particularly helpful for explaining memory and inherited effects in materials and systems. FC has become an increasingly important tool for representing non-standard occurrences in various fields, such as geometry, dynamics, and fractional differential equations [23, 12, 10]. These days, it is used in viscoelasticity, bioengineering, control theory, and acoustics [1]. Foundational works like those by Samko, Kilbas, and Marichev (1993) and Podlubny (1999), which allow the study of the complex and unpredictable ways that natural systems function, have solidified its place in science and engineering.

The well-known Riemann-Liouville (RL) fractional integrals are listed as follows:

Definition 1.1 (See [15, 11]). Presume $F \in L_1[\Theta, \rho]$, the RL fractional integral of order $\alpha > 0$, expressed as:

$$J_{\Theta+}^{\alpha} F(\varkappa) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{\Theta}^{\varkappa} (\varkappa - \kappa)^{\alpha-1} F(\kappa) d\kappa, \quad \varkappa > \Theta$$

and

$$J_{\rho-}^{\alpha} F(\varkappa) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{\varkappa}^{\rho} (\kappa - \varkappa)^{\alpha-1} F(\kappa) d\kappa, \quad \varkappa < \rho.$$

Definition 1.2. The Gamma function, as described in [7], is described using the subsequent integral expression.

$$\Gamma(\chi) = \int_0^{\infty} e^{-\kappa} \kappa^{\chi-1} d\kappa, \quad \text{Re}(\chi) > 0.$$

See references [21, 2, 8] for a more thorough explanation of RL fractional integrals. However, fractional integral inequalities are crucial for practical mathematics and differential equation analysis. A key concept in mathematics since ancient times is mathematical inequality, which compares two values or expressions to show their relationships or relative magnitudes. Convex functions are closely related to the theory of inequality; several famous inequalities, such as Hermite–Hadamard, Simpson, Newton, Euler–Maclaurin, and Boole’s type inequalities, have been developed for convex functions. Convexity serves as a reliable tool for studying inequalities, laying the groundwork for using geometric and analytical techniques to verify these conclusions. Convex function analysis and inequality analysis are closely related, with each impacting the development of the other. Please refer to [13, 3, 25] and the sources listed therein for more details on convexity and Newton-type inequalities associated with convex differentiable functions.

The tempered fractional integral was initially studied in this subject by Buschman [4]. Following this, further comprehensive contributions were made by Liu et al. [16] and Meerschaert et al. [20]. A prominent subfield of fractional calculus called tempered fractional calculus

finds a special intersection between weighted fractional calculus and fractional calculus with analytic kernels [9]. It can be considered an extension of fractional calculus due to its wide application and importance. Its significance is demonstrated by its rediscovery under many titles, such as significant fractional calculus [9, 5] and generalized proportional fractional calculus [14]. The next section reviews the essential preparations that form the basis of our key conclusions.

Definition 1.3 (See [22]). For real values $\alpha > 0$ and $\varkappa, \lambda \geq 0$, the λ -incomplete gamma function is identified as:

$$\Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, \varkappa) := \int_0^{\varkappa} \kappa^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda\kappa} d\kappa.$$

$\lambda = 1$ corresponds to the incomplete gamma function [6]:

$$\Upsilon(\alpha, \varkappa) := \int_0^{\varkappa} \kappa^{\alpha-1} e^{-\kappa} d\kappa.$$

Where, $0 < \alpha < \infty$ and $\lambda \geq 0$.

Remark 1.1 (See [22]). For the real values $\alpha > 0$ and $\varkappa, \lambda \geq 0$, we gain

$$\text{I. } \Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\Theta)}(\alpha, 1) = \int_0^1 \kappa^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\rho-\Theta)\kappa} d\kappa = \frac{1}{(\rho-\Theta)^{\alpha}} \Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, \rho - \Theta).$$

$$\text{II. } \int_0^1 \Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\Theta)}(\alpha, \varkappa) d\varkappa = \frac{\Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\Theta)}(\alpha, \rho-\Theta)}{(\rho-\Theta)^{\alpha}} - \frac{\Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\Theta)}(\alpha+1, \rho-\Theta)}{(\rho-\Theta)^{\alpha+1}}.$$

Definition 1.4 (See [17, 21]). Tempered fractional integral operators of order $\alpha > 0$ and $\lambda \geq 0$ are presented as:

$$\mathfrak{I}_{\Theta+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\varkappa) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{\Theta}^{\varkappa} (\varkappa - \kappa)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\varkappa-\kappa)} F(\kappa) d\kappa, \quad \varkappa \in [\Theta, \rho]$$

and

$$\mathfrak{I}_{\rho-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\varkappa) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{\varkappa}^{\rho} (\kappa - \varkappa)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\kappa-\varkappa)} F(\kappa) d\kappa, \quad \varkappa \in [\Theta, \rho],$$

respectively for $F \in L_1[\Theta, \rho]$.

The RL fractional integral equations in Definition 1.1 are obviously comparable if we assume $\lambda = 0$ in Definition 1.4..

Using tempered fractional integral operators, Gul and Yalcin [11] developed Minkowski and Hermite–Hadamard integral inequalities. They displayed a number of integral inequality instances for tempered fractional integrals from earlier research. For more details, interested readers are referred to [23, 24, 26].

Inspired by previous research, we employed tempered fractional integrals to identify some of Boole’s formula-type inequalities in the class of functions whose derivatives are convex functions. This paper examines important mathematical tools such as Holder’s and power mean inequality, enhancing the implementation of these inequalities in diverse mathematical domains. The most important advantage of these inequalities is that, by setting $\lambda = 0$, these inequalities turned into

Riemann–Liouville fractional Boole’s type inequalities. With $\alpha = 1$, the modified inequalities transform into classical Boole’s type inequalities.

The study is broken up into three pieces, the first of which is an introduction and preliminary material that includes basic concepts of fractional calculus and a synopsis of important research in the area. Section 1.1 will establish some results regarding Boole’s type inequality for differentiable convex functions. We also assess Boole’s formula for new mathematical tools such as holder’s inequality and power mean. We summarize our results and potential study opportunities in the last part.

1.1 Main Contributions

Lemma 1.1. If $F : [\Theta, \rho] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a function that is absolutely continuous on (Θ, ρ) such that $F' \in L_1[\Theta, \rho]$. Then, the following equality is valid:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}\right) + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] \\ & - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2 \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)} \left[\mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right)^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\rho) + \mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right)^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\Theta) \right] = \frac{(\rho - \Theta)^{\alpha+1}}{2^{\alpha+2} \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)} \\ & \times \left[\int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, 1) \right) \left[F'\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2 - \xi}{2}\Theta\right) - F'\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\Theta + \frac{2 - \xi}{2}\rho\right) \right] d\xi \right. \\ & + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, 1) \right) \left[F'\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2 - \xi}{2}\Theta\right) - F'\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\Theta + \frac{2 - \xi}{2}\rho\right) \right] d\xi \\ & \left. + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, 1) \right) \left[F'\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2 - \xi}{2}\Theta\right) - F'\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\Theta + \frac{2 - \xi}{2}\rho\right) \right] d\xi \right]. \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Proof. By acknowledging the essential rules of integration, it is enough to state that

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 &= \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, 1) \right) F'\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2 - \xi}{2}\Theta\right) d\xi \\ &= \frac{2}{\rho - \Theta} \left[\left(\Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, 1) \right) F\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2 - \xi}{2}\Theta\right) \Big|_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{2}{\rho - \Theta} \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \xi^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)\xi} F\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2 - \xi}{2}\Theta\right) d\xi \right] \\ &= \frac{2}{\rho - \Theta} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}\left(\alpha, \frac{1}{3}\right) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, 1) \right) F\left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}\right) + \frac{\Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, 1)}{5(\rho - \Theta)} F(\Theta) \\ & \quad - \frac{2}{\rho - \Theta} \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \xi^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)\xi} F\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2 - \xi}{2}\Theta\right) d\xi, \tag{2} \\ I_2 &= \frac{2}{\rho - \Theta} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}\left(\alpha, \frac{2}{3}\right) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, 1) \right) F\left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}\right) \\ & \quad - \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}\left(\alpha, \frac{1}{3}\right) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, 1) \right) F\left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}\right) \end{aligned}$$

$$-\frac{2}{\rho-\Theta} \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \xi^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})\xi} F\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2-\xi}{2}\Theta\right) d\xi. \tag{3}$$

In the same way, we find

$$\begin{aligned} I_3 &= \frac{2}{\rho-\Theta} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right) F\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right) \\ &\quad - \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}\left(\alpha, \frac{2}{3}\right) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right) F\left(\frac{2\Theta+\rho}{3}\right) \\ &\quad - \frac{2}{\rho-\Theta} \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \xi^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})\xi} F\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2-\xi}{2}\Theta\right) d\xi. \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

Consequently, we arrive at the subsequent equality by merging (2)-(4)

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 + I_2 + I_3 &= \frac{2}{10(\rho-\Theta)} \left[\Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) F(\Theta) + 5 \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) F\left(\frac{5\Theta+\rho}{6}\right) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) F\left(\frac{2\Theta+\rho}{3}\right) + 3 \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) F\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right) \right] \\ &\quad - \frac{2}{\rho-\Theta} \left[\int_0^1 \xi^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})\xi} F\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2-\xi}{2}\Theta\right) d\xi \right]. \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

Similarly

$$\begin{aligned} I_4 + I_5 + I_6 &= -\frac{2}{10(\rho-\Theta)} \left[\Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) F(\rho) + \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) F\left(\frac{\Theta+2\rho}{3}\right) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + 5 \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) F\left(\frac{\Theta+5\rho}{6}\right) + 3 \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) F\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right) \right] \\ &\quad + \frac{2}{\rho-\Theta} \left[\int_0^1 \xi^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})\xi} F\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\Theta + \frac{2-\xi}{2}\rho\right) d\xi \right]. \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

By subtracting equalities (5) and (6), then we make the substitutions $\varpi = \frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2-\xi}{2}\Theta$ and $\varpi = \frac{\xi}{2}\Theta + \frac{2-\xi}{2}\rho$ for $\xi \in [0, 1]$, it becomes

$$\begin{aligned} &[I_1 + I_2 + I_3 - (I_4 + I_5 + I_6)] \\ &= \frac{\Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1)}{5(\rho-\Theta)} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta+\rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta+\rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta+2\rho}{3}\right) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta+5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] - \frac{2^{\alpha+1}\Gamma(\alpha)}{(\rho-\Theta)^{\alpha+1}} \left[\mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^+}^{(\alpha,\lambda)} F(\rho) + \mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^-}^{(\alpha,\lambda)} F(\Theta) \right]. \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

Multiplying both sides of (7) by $\frac{\rho-\Theta}{4\Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1)}$, the equality (1) is obtained. □

Theorem 1.1. If all the conditions in Lemma 1.1 are accomplished and $|F'|$ is convex on $[\Theta, \rho]$, then one can prove the following inequality:

$$\begin{aligned} &\left| \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta+\rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta+\rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta+2\rho}{3}\right) + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta+5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2\Upsilon_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)} \left[\mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^+}^{(\alpha,\lambda)} F(\rho) + \mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^-}^{(\alpha,\lambda)} F(\Theta) \right] \right| \end{aligned}$$

$$\leq \frac{(\rho - \Theta)^{\alpha+1}}{2^{\alpha+2} \Upsilon_{\lambda} \left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2} \right)} (\Delta_1(\alpha, \lambda) + \Delta_2(\alpha, \lambda) + \Delta_3(\alpha, \lambda)) [|\mathbf{F}'(\Theta)| + |\mathbf{F}'(\rho)|], \quad (8)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_1(\alpha, \lambda) &= \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| d\xi, \\ \Delta_2(\alpha, \lambda) &= \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| d\xi, \\ \Delta_3(\alpha, \lambda) &= \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| d\xi. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. By referencing Lemma 1.1 and leveraging the convexity of $|\mathbf{F}'|$, we acquire

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[\mathbf{F}(\Theta) + 5\mathbf{F}\left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}\right) + \mathbf{F}\left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}\right) + 6\mathbf{F}\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right) + \mathbf{F}\left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}\right) + 5\mathbf{F}\left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6}\right) + \mathbf{F}(\rho) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2 \Upsilon_{\lambda} \left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2} \right)} \left[\mathfrak{J}_{\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right)^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathbf{F}(\rho) + \mathfrak{J}_{\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right)^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \mathbf{F}(\Theta) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(\rho - \Theta)^{\alpha+1}}{2^{\alpha+2} \Upsilon_{\lambda} \left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2} \right)} \left[\int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| \right. \\ & \quad \times \left| \mathbf{F}'\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2 - \xi}{2}\Theta\right) - \mathbf{F}'\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\Theta + \frac{2 - \xi}{2}\rho\right) \right| d\xi \\ & \quad + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left| \mathbf{F}'\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2 - \xi}{2}\Theta\right) - \mathbf{F}'\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\Theta + \frac{2 - \xi}{2}\rho\right) \right| d\xi \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left| \mathbf{F}'\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2 - \xi}{2}\Theta\right) - \mathbf{F}'\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\Theta + \frac{2 - \xi}{2}\rho\right) \right| d\xi \right] \quad (9) \\ & \leq \frac{(\rho - \Theta)^{\alpha+1}}{2^{\alpha+2} \Upsilon_{\lambda} \left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2} \right)} \left[\int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| \right. \\ & \quad \times \left(\frac{\xi}{2} |\mathbf{F}'(\rho)| + \frac{2 - \xi}{2} |\mathbf{F}(\Theta)| + \frac{\xi}{2} |\mathbf{F}'(\Theta)| + \frac{2 - \xi}{2} |\mathbf{F}(\rho)| \right) d\xi \\ & \quad + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| \\ & \quad \times \left(\frac{\xi}{2} |\mathbf{F}'(\rho)| + \frac{2 - \xi}{2} |\mathbf{F}(\Theta)| + \frac{\xi}{2} |\mathbf{F}'(\Theta)| + \frac{2 - \xi}{2} |\mathbf{F}(\rho)| \right) d\xi \left. \right] \\ & \quad + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| \\ & \quad \times \left(\frac{\xi}{2} |\mathbf{F}'(\rho)| + \frac{2 - \xi}{2} |\mathbf{F}(\Theta)| + \frac{\xi}{2} |\mathbf{F}'(\Theta)| + \frac{2 - \xi}{2} |\mathbf{F}(\rho)| \right) d\xi \left. \right] \\ & = \frac{(\rho - \Theta)^{\alpha+1}}{2^{\alpha+2} \Upsilon_{\lambda} \left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2} \right)} (\Delta_1(\alpha, \lambda) + \Delta_2(\alpha, \lambda) + \Delta_3(\alpha, \lambda)) [|\mathbf{F}'(\Theta)| + |\mathbf{F}'(\rho)|]. \end{aligned}$$

We have reached the conclusion of the proof of Theorem 1.1. □

Remark 1.2. If $\lambda = 0$ in Theorem 1.1, we conclude

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}\right) + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(\rho-\Theta)^\alpha} \left[\mathcal{J}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^+}^\alpha F(\rho) + \mathcal{J}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^-}^\alpha F(\Theta) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{\alpha(\rho-\Theta)}{4} (\Delta_1(\alpha, 0) + \Delta_2(\alpha, 0) + \Delta_3(\alpha, 0)) [|F'(\Theta)| + |F'(\rho)|], \end{aligned}$$

which is derived in [18].

Remark 1.3. If we assume $\lambda = 0$ and $\alpha = 1$ in Theorem 1.1, then we gain

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}\right) + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{1}{\rho-\Theta} \int_\Theta^\rho F(\varpi) d\varpi \right| \leq \frac{13(\rho-\Theta)}{450} [|F'(\Theta)| + |F'(\rho)|], \end{aligned}$$

which is proved in [27].

Theorem 1.2. If all the conditions in Lemma 1.1 are accomplished and $|F'|^q, q > 1$ is convex on $[\Theta, \rho]$, then the subsequent inequality is valid:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}\right) + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2 \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)} \left[\mathfrak{J}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^+}^{(\alpha,\lambda)} F(\rho) + \mathfrak{J}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^-}^{(\alpha,\lambda)} F(\Theta) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(\rho-\Theta)^{\alpha+1}}{2^{\alpha+2} \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)} \left[\gamma_1(\alpha, p) \left\{ \left(\frac{|F'(\rho)|^q + 7|F'(\Theta)|^q}{16} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{|F'(\Theta)|^q + 7|F'(\rho)|^q}{16} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \gamma_2(\alpha, p) \left\{ \left(\frac{3|F'(\rho)|^q + 5|F'(\Theta)|^q}{16} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{3|F'(\Theta)|^q + 5|F'(\rho)|^q}{16} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \right], \tag{10} \end{aligned}$$

where $p^{-1} + q^{-1} = 1,$

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma_1^p(\alpha, \lambda) &= \left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, 1) \right|^p d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}, \\ \gamma_2^p(\alpha, \lambda) &= \left(\int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, 1) \right|^p d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}, \\ \gamma_3^p(\alpha, \lambda) &= \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, 1) \right|^p d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. By applying Hölder’s inequality (9), it becomes

$$\left| \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}\right) + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] \right|$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & -\frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2 \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)} \left[\mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\rho) + \mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\Theta) \right] \Big| \\
 & \leq \frac{(\rho-\Theta)^{\alpha+1}}{2^{\alpha+2} \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)} \left[\left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, 1) \right|^p d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \right. \\
 & \quad \times \left\{ \left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \rho + \frac{2-\xi}{2} \Theta \right) \right|^q d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \Theta + \frac{2-\xi}{2} \rho \right) \right|^q d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \\
 & \quad + \left(\int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, 1) \right|^p d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \\
 & \quad \times \left\{ \left(\int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \rho + \frac{2-\xi}{2} \Theta \right) \right|^q d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \Theta + \frac{2-\xi}{2} \rho \right) \right|^q d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \\
 & \quad + \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, 1) \right|^p d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \\
 & \quad \times \left. \left\{ \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \rho + \frac{2-\xi}{2} \Theta \right) \right|^q d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \Theta + \frac{2-\xi}{2} \rho \right) \right|^q d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \right].
 \end{aligned}$$

By exploiting the convexity $|F'|^q$, we conclude that

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta+\rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta+\rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta+2\rho}{3}\right) + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta+5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] \right. \\
 & \quad - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2 \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)} \left[\mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\rho) + \mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\Theta) \right] \Big| \leq \frac{(\rho-\Theta)^{\alpha+1}}{2^{\alpha+2} \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)} \\
 & \quad \times \left[\gamma_1^p(\alpha, \lambda) \left\{ \left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \rho + \frac{2-\xi}{2} \Theta \right) \right|^q d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \Theta + \frac{2-\xi}{2} \rho \right) \right|^q d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \right. \\
 & \quad + \gamma_2^p(\alpha, \lambda) \left\{ \left(\int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \rho + \frac{2-\xi}{2} \Theta \right) \right|^q d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \Theta + \frac{2-\xi}{2} \rho \right) \right|^q d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \Big] \\
 & \quad + \gamma_3^p(\alpha, \lambda) \left\{ \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \rho + \frac{2-\xi}{2} \Theta \right) \right|^q d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \Theta + \frac{2-\xi}{2} \rho \right) \right|^q d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \Big] \\
 & \leq \frac{(\rho-\Theta)^{\alpha+1}}{2^{\alpha+2} \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)} \left[\gamma_1^p(\alpha, \lambda) \left\{ \left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\frac{\xi}{2} |F'(\rho)|^q + \frac{2-\xi}{2} |F'(\Theta)|^q \right) d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \right. \\
 & \quad + \left. \left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\frac{\xi}{2} |F'(\Theta)|^q + \frac{2-\xi}{2} |F'(\rho)|^q \right) d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} + \gamma_2^p(\alpha, \lambda) \left\{ \left(\int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(\frac{\xi}{2} |F'(\rho)|^q + \frac{2-\xi}{2} |F'(\Theta)|^q \right) d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
 & \quad + \left. \left(\int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(\frac{\xi}{2} |F'(\Theta)|^q + \frac{2-\xi}{2} |F'(\rho)|^q \right) d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} + \gamma_3^p(\alpha, \lambda) \left\{ \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left(\frac{\xi}{2} |F'(\rho)|^q + \frac{2-\xi}{2} |F'(\Theta)|^q \right) d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
 & \quad + \left. \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left(\frac{\xi}{2} |F'(\Theta)|^q + \frac{2-\xi}{2} |F'(\rho)|^q \right) d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \Big]
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq \frac{(\rho - \Theta)^{\alpha+1}}{2^{\alpha+2} \gamma_\lambda \left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)} \left[\gamma_1^p(\alpha, \lambda) \left\{ \left(\frac{|F'(\rho)|^q + 11|F'(\Theta)|^q}{36} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{|F'(\Theta)|^q + 11|F'(\rho)|^q}{36} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \right. \\ &\quad + \gamma_2^p(\alpha, \lambda) \left\{ \left(\frac{|F'(\rho)|^q + 3|F'(\Theta)|^q}{12} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{|F'(\Theta)|^q + 3|F'(\rho)|^q}{12} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \\ &\quad \left. + \gamma_3^p(\alpha, \lambda) \left\{ \left(\frac{5|F'(\rho)|^q + 7|F'(\Theta)|^q}{36} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{5|F'(\Theta)|^q + 7|F'(\rho)|^q}{36} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \right]. \end{aligned}$$

We have successfully concluded the proof for Theorem 1.2. \square

Remark 1.4. If $\lambda = 0$ in Theorem 1.2, we conclude

$$\begin{aligned} &\left| \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}\right) + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(\rho - \Theta)^\alpha} \left[\mathcal{J}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^+}^\alpha F(\rho) + \mathcal{J}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^-}^\alpha F(\Theta) \right] \right| \\ &\leq \frac{\alpha(\rho - \Theta)}{4} \left[\gamma_1^p(\alpha, 0) \left\{ \left(\frac{|F'(\rho)|^q + 11|F'(\Theta)|^q}{36} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{|F'(\Theta)|^q + 11|F'(\rho)|^q}{36} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \right. \\ &\quad + \gamma_2^p(\alpha, 0) \left\{ \left(\frac{|F'(\rho)|^q + 3|F'(\Theta)|^q}{12} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{|F'(\Theta)|^q + 3|F'(\rho)|^q}{12} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \\ &\quad \left. + \gamma_3^p(\alpha, 0) \left\{ \left(\frac{5|F'(\rho)|^q + 7|F'(\Theta)|^q}{36} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{5|F'(\Theta)|^q + 7|F'(\rho)|^q}{36} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \right], \end{aligned}$$

which is derived by Mateen et al. in [18, Theorem 6].

Remark 1.5. If we assume $\lambda = 0$ and $\alpha = 1$ in Theorem 1.2, then we gain

$$\begin{aligned} &\left| \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}\right) + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \frac{1}{\rho - \Theta} \int_\Theta^\rho F(\varpi) d\varpi \right| \\ &\leq \left[2 \left(\frac{3^{-p-1} 7^p 20^{-2p-1} \left(3^{p+1} \left(\frac{20}{7} \right)^p + 7 \cdot 20^p \right)}{p+1} \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \right. \\ &\quad \times \left\{ \left(\frac{|\Psi'(v)|^q + 11|\Psi'(\kappa)|^q}{72} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{11|\Psi'(v)|^q + |\Psi'(\kappa)|^q}{72} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \\ &\quad + 2^{1-\frac{1}{p}} \left(\frac{15^{-2p-1} \left(\left(\frac{15}{2} \right)^p + 2^{p+2} 15^p \right)}{p+1} \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \\ &\quad \times \left\{ \left(\frac{|\Psi'(v)|^q + 3|\Psi'(\kappa)|^q}{24} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{3|\Psi'(v)|^q + |\Psi'(\kappa)|^q}{24} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \\ &\quad \left. + 2 \times 3^{-1/p} \left(\frac{20^{-2p-1} \left(\left(\frac{20}{3} \right)^p + 3^{p+2} 20^p \right)}{p+1} \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$\times \left\{ \left(\frac{|\Psi'(v)|^q + 11|\Psi'(\kappa)|^q}{72} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{11|\Psi'(v)|^q + |\Psi'(\kappa)|^q}{72} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\},$$

which is identified in [19, Corollary 3].

Theorem 1.3. If all the conditions in Lemma 1.1 are accomplished and $|F'|^q, q \geq 1$ is convex on $[\Theta, \rho]$, then the subsequent inequality is valid:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}\right) + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2\Upsilon_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)} \left[\mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right)^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\rho) + \mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right)^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\Theta) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(\rho - \Theta)^{\alpha+1}}{2^{\alpha+2} \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)} \left[(\Delta_1(\alpha, \lambda))^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left\{ (S_1(\alpha, \lambda)|F'(\rho)|^q + U_1(\alpha, \lambda)|F'(\Theta)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. + (S_1(\alpha, \lambda)|F'(\Theta)|^q + U_1(\alpha, \lambda)|F'(\rho)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} + (\Delta_2(\alpha, \lambda))^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left\{ (S_2(\alpha, \lambda)|F'(\rho)|^q + U_2(\alpha, \lambda)|F'(\Theta)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. + (S_2(\alpha, \lambda)|F'(\Theta)|^q + U_2(\alpha, \lambda)|F'(\rho)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} + (\Delta_3(\alpha, \lambda))^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left\{ (S_3(\alpha, \lambda)|F'(\rho)|^q + U_3(\alpha, \lambda)|F'(\Theta)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. + (S_3(\alpha, \lambda)|F'(\Theta)|^q + U_3(\alpha, \lambda)|F'(\rho)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \right], \tag{11} \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{cases} S_1(\alpha, \lambda) = \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)(\alpha, 1) \right| \frac{\xi}{2} d\xi, \\ S_2(\alpha, \lambda) = \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)(\alpha, 1) \right| \frac{\xi}{2} d\xi, \\ S_3(\alpha, \lambda) = \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)(\alpha, 1) \right| \frac{\xi}{2} d\xi, \\ U_1(\alpha, \lambda) = \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)(\alpha, 1) \right| \frac{2 - \xi}{2} d\xi, \\ U_2(\alpha, \lambda) = \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)(\alpha, 1) \right| \frac{2 - \xi}{2} d\xi, \\ U_3(\alpha, \lambda) = \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)(\alpha, 1) \right| \frac{2 - \xi}{2} d\xi. \end{cases}$$

Proof. Based on Lemma 1.1 and by utilizing the power-mean inequality after considering the modulus, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}\right) + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2\Upsilon_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)} \left[\mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right)^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\rho) + \mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right)^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\Theta) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(\rho - \Theta)^{\alpha+1}}{2^{\alpha+2} \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)} \left[\left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)(\alpha, 1) \right| d\xi \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \right. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& \times \left\{ \left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left| F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \rho + \frac{2-\xi}{2} \Theta \right) \right|^q d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
& + \left. \left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left| F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \Theta + \frac{2-\xi}{2} \rho \right) \right|^q d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \\
& + \left(\int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| d\xi \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \\
& \times \left\{ \left(\int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left| F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \rho + \frac{2-\xi}{2} \Theta \right) \right|^q d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
& + \left. \left(\int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left| F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \Theta + \frac{2-\xi}{2} \rho \right) \right|^q d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \\
& + \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| d\xi \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \\
& \times \left\{ \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left| F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \rho + \frac{2-\xi}{2} \Theta \right) \right|^q d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
& + \left. \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left| F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \Theta + \frac{2-\xi}{2} \rho \right) \right|^q d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\}.
\end{aligned}$$

As $|F'|^q$ is convex on the interval $[\Theta, \rho]$, we acquire

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta+\rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta+\rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta+2\rho}{3}\right) + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta+5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] \right. \\
& \quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2 \Upsilon_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)} \left[\mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\rho) + \mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\Theta) \right] \right| \\
& \leq \frac{(\rho-\Theta)^{\alpha+1}}{2^{\alpha+2} \Upsilon_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)} \left[\left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| d\xi \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
& \quad \times \left\{ \left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left(\frac{\xi}{2} |F'(\rho)|^q + \frac{2-\xi}{2} |F'(\Theta)|^q \right) d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
& \quad + \left. \left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left(\frac{\xi}{2} |F'(\Theta)|^q + \frac{2-\xi}{2} |F'(\rho)|^q \right) d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \\
& \quad + \left(\int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| d\xi \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \\
& \quad \times \left\{ \left(\int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left(\frac{\xi}{2} |F'(\rho)|^q + \frac{2-\xi}{2} |F'(\Theta)|^q \right) d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
& \quad + \left. \left(\int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left(\frac{\xi}{2} |F'(\Theta)|^q + \frac{2-\xi}{2} |F'(\rho)|^q \right) d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \\
& \quad + \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| d\xi \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \\
& \quad \times \left\{ \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left(\frac{\xi}{2} |F'(\rho)|^q + \frac{2-\xi}{2} |F'(\Theta)|^q \right) d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
& \quad + \left. \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left(\frac{\xi}{2} |F'(\Theta)|^q + \frac{2-\xi}{2} |F'(\rho)|^q \right) d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| d\xi \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \\
 & \times \left\{ \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left(\frac{\xi}{2} |F'(\rho)|^q + \frac{2-\xi}{2} |F'(\Theta)|^q \right) d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
 & \left. + \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left(\frac{\xi}{2} |F'(\Theta)|^q + \frac{2-\xi}{2} |F'(\rho)|^q \right) d\xi \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

The proof of Theorem 1.3 has been finalized. □

Remark 1.6. If $\lambda = 0$ in Theorem 1.3, we conclude

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}\right) + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] \right. \\
 & \quad \left. - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(\rho-\Theta)^\alpha} \left[\mathcal{J}_{(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2})^+}^\alpha F(\rho) + \mathcal{J}_{(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2})^-}^\alpha F(\Theta) \right] \right| \\
 & \leq \frac{\alpha(\rho-\Theta)}{4} \left[(\Delta_1(\alpha, 0))^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left\{ (S_1(\alpha, 0)|F'(\rho)|^q + U_1(\alpha, 0)|F'(\Theta)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. + (S_1(\alpha, 0)|F'(\Theta)|^q + U_1(\alpha, 0)|F'(\rho)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} + (\Delta_2(\alpha, 0))^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left\{ (S_2(\alpha, 0)|F'(\rho)|^q + U_2(\alpha, 0)|F'(\Theta)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. + (S_2(\alpha, 0)|F'(\Theta)|^q + U_2(\alpha, 0)|F'(\rho)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} + (\Delta_3(\alpha, 0))^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left\{ (S_3(\alpha, 0)|F'(\rho)|^q + U_3(\alpha, 0)|F'(\Theta)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. + (S_3(\alpha, 0)|F'(\Theta)|^q + U_3(\alpha, 0)|F'(\rho)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \right],
 \end{aligned}$$

which is derived in [18].

Remark 1.7. If we assume $\lambda = 0$ and $\alpha = 1$ in Theorem 1.3, then we gain

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}\right) + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] \right. \\
 & \quad \left. - \frac{1}{\rho-\Theta} \int_{\Theta}^{\rho} F(\varpi) d\varpi \right| \\
 & \leq (\rho-\Theta) \left[\left(\frac{29}{3600} \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left\{ \left(\frac{577|F'(\rho)|^q + 4643|F'(\Theta)|^q}{64800} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{577|F'(\Theta)|^q + 4643|F'(\rho)|^q}{64800} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + \left(\frac{17}{1800} \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left\{ \left(\frac{37|F'(\rho)|^q + 133|F'(\Theta)|^q}{18000} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{37|F'(\Theta)|^q + 133|F'(\rho)|^q}{18000} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \right. \\
 & \quad \left. + \left(\frac{41}{3600} \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left\{ \left(\frac{3311|F'(\rho)|^q + 4069|F'(\Theta)|^q}{64800} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{3311|F'(\Theta)|^q + 4069|F'(\rho)|^q}{64800} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \right],
 \end{aligned}$$

which is established in [19].

1.2 Future Research Directions

This work presents unique Boole’s formula-type inequalities involving tempered fractional integrals for single-time differentiable convex functions. Initially, we established an integral identity associated with tempered fractional integrals. Subsequently, we verified novel Boole’s formula

inequalities for differentiable convex functions. The bounds of Boole's formula can be ascertained using the inequalities discussed in this study. These inequalities can be helpful in the estimation of errors that occur when functions are approximated using polynomials or other simplified functions in approximation theory. Concerning integral inequalities, the conclusions of this work are crucial and offer numerous possibilities for new researchers to investigate further extensions and the consequences of these results in other mathematical disciplines. This study has important implications for future research on generalized fractional integrals, convexity, s -convexity, and equations with higher-order derivatives.

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Fibonacci Points and Inverse Stereographic Projection

Baris Ates¹, Selcan Ates², Alp Kustepeli³

¹Department of Mathematics, Izmir Institute of Technology, Türkiye

²Department of Chemical Engineering, Izmir Institute of Technology, Türkiye

³Department of Electrical & Electronics Engineering, Izmir Institute of Technology,
Türkiye

Corresponding author: barisates2002@gmail.com

ORCID IDs:

First Author: [0000-0002-8138-7360](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8138-7360)

Second Author: [0000-0002-0078-0647](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0078-0647)

Third Author: [0000-0002-8995-6628](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8995-6628)

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Abstract

In the present study, we investigate the correspondence between Fibonacci structures in the Euclidean plane and their spherical counterparts through the inverse stereographic projection (ISP). The ISP provides a one-to-one mapping that enables the transfer of algebraic and geometric relations from the plane to the sphere. By applying this mapping to Fibonacci points, one can define spherical Fibonacci identities and explore their geometric manifestations on the sphere. Moreover, the sphere can be continuously deformed while preserving a bijective relation between the original and the deformed surfaces. This deformation framework allows the extension of planar Fibonacci identities to generalized spherical geometries, including spheroidal and irregular surfaces. Such deformations can represent naturally occurring shapes, thus establishing a potential connection between Fibonacci-based mathematical identities and biological or physical pattern formation. The proposed approach not only provides a geometric interpretation of Fibonacci identities on curved manifolds but also opens new perspectives for modeling spatial structures in nature through analytical deformations of spherical surfaces.

Keywords: Fibonacci Points, Stereographic Projection, Deformed Spheres, Spirals.

1 Introduction

The Fibonacci sequence, despite its deceptively simple recursive definition, is known to appear in a remarkable variety of natural and physical systems [1, 2]. Classical examples such as phyllotactic arrangements in sunflowers, pine cones, and other plants demonstrate how Fibonacci numbers can model the organization of spirals and growth mechanisms in nature [3, 4]. Owing to its intrinsic connection with the golden ratio, the sequence also arises in art, architecture, and engineering [5, 6]. Furthermore, recent developments indicate that Fibonacci structures continue

to play a role in emerging areas: for instance, laser-driven quantum states arranged according to Fibonacci patterns enable enhanced information storage capabilities in quantum systems [7]. These observations collectively highlight the relevance of studying Fibonacci-based constructions within broader geometric and analytical contexts.

One of the most effective tools for transferring planar structures to curved geometries is the inverse stereographic projection (ISP). Stereographic projection is a classical conformal mapping between the sphere and the plane, preserving angles and providing a one-to-one correspondence except at the projection point [8, 9]. ISP acts consistently on both discrete point sets and continuous curves, it becomes a natural framework for exploring how algebraic relations—such as those defined by Fibonacci numbers—transform when transferred onto curved surface. The geometric picture becomes even richer when one considers deformations of the sphere. Deforming the sphere through arbitrary single-valued functions in the normal direction enables the construction of spheroidal or even non-differentiable surfaces that still remain in bijective correspondence with the plane. This generalized setting allows planar structures to be transported onto a wide range of geometries, including those resembling naturally occurring shapes that deviate from perfect spherical symmetry.

In the present work, we build upon these ideas to investigate the correspondence between Fibonacci configurations in the Euclidean plane and their spherical or deformed spherical counterparts. Starting with planar points whose coordinates are determined by Fibonacci numbers, we apply the inverse stereographic projection to construct their images on \mathbf{S}^2 and derive spherical analogues of well-known Fibonacci identities. Moreover, by introducing analytic deformations of the sphere, we generalize these constructions to more complex surfaces. This framework not only offers a geometric reinterpretation of Fibonacci identities on curved manifolds but also suggests potential links with biological and physical systems in which Fibonacci-like patterns emerge.

2 Inverse Stereographic Projection of Fibonacci Points

In this section, a short review of the previously obtained results will be presented. The Fibonacci points introduced in [10] are the points such that, the absolute value of each coordinate of the point is a Fibonacci number. Thus, such points can be written in the form

$$P(x, y) = P(c_1 F_n, c_2 F_m) \tag{1}$$

where c_1 and c_2 are either $+1$ or -1 . The stereographic projection is a mapping that relates the points on the sphere with the points on the plane. This mapping is one to one and invertible. For a sphere located on the ζ axis and described by $\xi^2 + \eta^2 + (\zeta - R)^2 = R^2$, stereographic projection of the point $P^s(\xi, \eta, \zeta)$ on the sphere is mapped to a unique point $P(x, y)$ on the $x - y$ plane via stereographic projection as

$$P^s(\xi, \eta, \zeta) = P^s \left(\frac{4R^2 x}{4R^2 + x^2 + y^2}, \frac{4R^2 y}{4R^2 + x^2 + y^2}, \frac{2R(x^2 + y^2)}{4R^2 + x^2 + y^2} \right) \tag{2}$$

and conversely, the inverse stereographic projection of a point $P(x, y)$ is found by [8], [9]:

$$P(x, y) = P\left(\frac{2R\xi}{2R - \zeta}, \frac{2R\eta}{2R - \zeta}\right). \tag{3}$$

The ISP of a Fibonacci point is given by the following relation:

$$P^s(\xi_{n,m}^F, \eta_{n,m}^F, \zeta_{n,m}^F) = P^s\left(\frac{4R^2 c_1 F_n}{4R^2 + F_n^2 + F_m^2}, \frac{4R^2 c_2 F_m}{4R^2 + F_n^2 + F_m^2}, \frac{2R(F_n^2 + F_m^2)}{4R^2 + F_n^2 + F_m^2}\right). \tag{4}$$

Let us consider the special Fibonacci points $P_n(F_n, 0)$ on the x -axis, whose first coordinates are Fibonacci numbers, i.e., $P_0(0, 0), P_{1,2}(1, 0), P_3(2, 0), \dots, P_n(F_n, 0)$. The coordinates of the ISP of the points $P_n(F_n, 0)$ are obtained as

$$P^s(\xi_n^F, \eta_n^F, \zeta_n^F) = P^s\left(\frac{4R^2 F_n}{4R^2 + F_n^2}, 0, \frac{2RF_n^2}{4R^2 + F_n^2}\right). \tag{5}$$

In order to find a relation for the ξ_n^F , one can consider the first coordinates and rearrange them as $\xi_n^F F_n^2 - 4R^2 F_n + 4R^2 \xi_n^F = 0$ which yields

$$F_n = \frac{2R^2 + 2R\lambda_n \sqrt{R^2 - (\xi_n^F)^2}}{\xi_n^F}, \tag{6}$$

where λ_n is used to denote $\lambda_n(R)$ whose value is simply equals to ± 1 depending on the values of n and R [10].

Considering the Equation (2), one can conclude that the coordinates of the ISP of the sequential points $P_n(F_n, 0)$ satisfy the following nonlinear addition relations:

$$\frac{2R^2 + 2\lambda_n R \sqrt{R^2 - (\xi_n^F)^2}}{\xi_n^F} + \frac{2R^2 + 2\lambda_{n+1} R \sqrt{R^2 - (\xi_{n+1}^F)^2}}{\xi_{n+1}^F} = \frac{2R^2 + 2\lambda_{n+2} R \sqrt{R^2 - (\xi_{n+2}^F)^2}}{\xi_{n+2}^F}, \tag{7}$$

$$\eta_n^F = \eta_{n+1}^F = \eta_{n+2}^F = 0, \tag{8}$$

$$\sqrt{\frac{\zeta_n^F}{2R - \zeta_n^F}} + \sqrt{\frac{\zeta_{n+1}^F}{2R - \zeta_{n+1}^F}} = \sqrt{\frac{\zeta_{n+2}^F}{2R - \zeta_{n+2}^F}}, \tag{9}$$

$$\frac{2R \xi_n^F}{2R - \zeta_n^F} + \frac{2R \xi_{n+1}^F}{2R - \zeta_{n+1}^F} = \frac{2R \xi_{n+2}^F}{2R - \zeta_{n+2}^F} \tag{10}$$

where short hand notation $\lambda_n = \lambda_n(R)$ is used and they are equal to ± 1 for any n .

2.1 Rotation of Fibonacci Points

The rotation of the special Fibonacci points $P_n(F_n, 0)$ about the origin by an angle according to the transformation rule

$$\begin{aligned} x' &= \cos \alpha x - \sin \alpha y \\ y' &= \sin \alpha x + \cos \alpha y \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

allows one to obtain new points $P'(x', y')$ such that their distance to the origin is a Fibonacci number. ISP of those rotated Fibonacci points also satisfy following nonlinear addition relations:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{2R^2 \cos \alpha + 2\lambda'_n R \sqrt{R^2 \cos^2 \alpha - (\xi'_n)^2}}{\xi'_n} + \frac{2R^2 \cos \alpha + 2\lambda'_{n+1} R \sqrt{R^2 \cos^2 \alpha - (\xi'_{n+1})^2}}{\xi'_{n+1}} \\ &= \frac{2R^2 \cos \alpha + 2\lambda'_{n+2} R \sqrt{R^2 \cos^2 \alpha - (\xi'_{n+2})^2}}{\xi'_{n+2}}, \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{2R^2 \sin \alpha + 2\lambda'_n R \sqrt{R^2 \sin^2 \alpha - (\eta'_n)^2}}{\eta'_n} + \frac{2R^2 \sin \alpha + 2\lambda'_{n+1} R \sqrt{R^2 \sin^2 \alpha - (\eta'_{n+1})^2}}{\eta'_{n+1}} \\ &= \frac{2R^2 \sin \alpha + 2\lambda'_{n+2} R \sqrt{R^2 \sin^2 \alpha - (\eta'_{n+2})^2}}{\eta'_{n+2}}, \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

$$\sqrt{\frac{\zeta'_n}{2R - \zeta'_n}} + \sqrt{\frac{\zeta'_{n+1}}{2R - \zeta'_{n+1}}} = \sqrt{\frac{\zeta'_{n+2}}{2R - \zeta'_{n+2}}} \quad (14)$$

where λ'_n s are equal to ± 1 [10]. The relations between the mixed coordinates of the images of the points on the rotated line can also be obtained from Equation (3) as

$$\frac{\xi'_n}{2R - \zeta'_n} + \frac{\xi'_{n+1}}{2R - \zeta'_{n+1}} = \frac{\xi'_{n+2}}{2R - \zeta'_{n+2}} \quad (15)$$

$$\frac{\eta'_n}{2R - \zeta'_n} + \frac{\eta'_{n+1}}{2R - \zeta'_{n+1}} = \frac{\eta'_{n+2}}{2R - \zeta'_{n+2}}. \quad (16)$$

For the most general Fibonacci numbers $P(c_1 F_n, c_2 F_m)$. Inverse stereographic projection allows to find the following relations between the coordinates of the sequential points [10]:

$$\frac{\xi_{n,m}}{2R - \zeta_{n,m}} + \frac{\xi_{n+1,m}}{2R - \zeta_{n+1,m}} = \frac{\xi_{n+2,m}}{2R - \zeta_{n+2,m}} \quad (17)$$

$$\frac{\eta_{n,m}}{2R - \zeta_{n,m}} + \frac{\eta_{n,m+1}}{2R - \zeta_{n,m+1}} = \frac{\eta_{n,m+2}}{2R - \zeta_{n,m+2}}. \quad (18)$$

2.2 Generalization of Inverse Stereographic Projection

The correspondence between the points on the sphere and the points on the plane governed by the stereographic projection can be generalized to the deformed spheres [8], [11], [12]. The position vector of a point on the sphere centered at the origin is given in spherical coordinates as $\vec{r}_{\text{sph}} = R \hat{r}$. Deformation of this sphere in radial direction is achieved by the following relation [13]

$$\vec{r}_d = R(1 + \beta f(\theta, \varphi)) \hat{r} \quad (19)$$

where $f(\theta, \varphi)$ is arbitrary single valued function and β is the deformation parameter. In order to find images of plane points on these deformed spheres via ISP, one may first transform the point $P^0(x, y)$ onto the sphere by using (2) and obtain a point $P^1 = (\xi^1, \eta^1, \zeta^1)$. Since

the origin of this sphere is located in the ζ axis, by a translation one can obtain a new point $P^2 = (\xi^2, \eta^2, \zeta^2) = (\xi^1, \eta^1, \zeta^1 - R)$ on the sphere whose center is located at the origin. The deformation function depends on the angular variables θ and φ and thus the amount of the radial deviation depends on the position of the point on the sphere. In order to use (19), which governs the surface deformation, one has to determine the spherical angles. The values of the θ and φ can be found from the following definitions:

$$\theta = \text{Arccos}\left(\frac{\zeta^2}{R}\right), \quad \varphi = \text{Arctan}\left(\frac{y}{x}\right). \quad (20)$$

Once the spherical angles are found, according to the deformation (19), one can obtain a new point $P^3(t) = (\xi^3, \eta^3, \zeta^3)$ on deformed sphere with the following relations:

$$\xi^3 = \xi^2 + \beta R f(\theta, \varphi) \sin(\theta) \cos(\varphi) \quad (21)$$

$$\eta^3 = \eta^2 + \beta R f(\theta, \varphi) \sin(\theta) \sin(\varphi) \quad (22)$$

$$\zeta^3 = \zeta^2 + \beta R f(\theta, \varphi) \cos(\theta). \quad (23)$$

The final point P^3 is the inverse stereographic projection of P^0 onto the deformed sphere. For the uniqueness of the transformation one may consult the work [11].

3 Relations That are Satisfied by the ISP of the Fibonacci Points on Deformed Spheres

For the most general Fibonacci Points $P = (c_1 F_n, c_2 F_m)$, ISP of those points on the deformed spheres satisfy following identities:

$$\frac{\xi_{n,m}^3 - R\beta f \cos \theta \cos \varphi}{R(1 + \beta f \cos \theta) - \zeta_{n,m}^3} + \frac{\xi_{n+1,m}^3 - R\beta f \cos \theta \cos \varphi}{R(1 + \beta f \cos \theta) - \zeta_{n+1,m}^3} = \frac{\xi_{n+2,m}^3 - R\beta f \cos \theta \cos \varphi}{R(1 + \beta f \cos \theta) - \zeta_{n+2,m}^3} \quad (24)$$

and

$$\frac{\eta_{n,m}^3 - R\beta f \sin \theta \sin \varphi}{R(1 + \beta f \cos \theta) - \zeta_{n,m}^3} + \frac{\eta_{n,m+1}^3 - R\beta f \sin \theta \sin \varphi}{R(1 + \beta f \cos \theta) - \zeta_{n,m+1}^3} = \frac{\eta_{n,m+2}^3 - R\beta f \sin \theta \sin \varphi}{R(1 + \beta f \cos \theta) - \zeta_{n,m+2}^3}. \quad (25)$$

These two equations, together with the (19), allows one to find $\xi_{n+2}^3, \eta_{n+2}^3, \zeta_{n+2}^3$ when $\xi_n^3, \eta_n^3, \zeta_n^3$ and $\xi_{n+1}^3, \eta_{n+1}^3, \zeta_{n+1}^3$ are known. The general Fibonacci numbers $P_{n,m}(c_1 F_n, c_2 F_m)$ has quite interesting properties. For the fixed m , if one considers the sequential points $P_{n,m}, P_{n+1,m}$, and $P_{n+2,m}$ which are the points located on the line $y = c_2 F_m$, then ISP of those points satisfy the relation (24), likewise, for the fixed n , if one considers the sequential points $P_{n,m}, P_{n,m+1}$, and $P_{n,m+2}$ which are the points located on the line $x = c_1 F_n$, then ISP of those points satisfy the relation (25).

4 Fibonacci Identities and Their Transformations

Fibonacci numbers satisfy a wide variety of identities. In order to illustrate the transformation of the identities, we will consider following relation:

$$F_{n-1}^2 + F_n^2 = F_{2n-1} \quad (26)$$

which is called the Cassini identity respectively [14]. The ISP of Fibonacci points which are located on the line $y = c_2 F_m$ satisfy the Cassini identity as follows;

$$2R \left(\frac{\xi_{n-1,m}^3 - R\beta f \cos \theta \cos \varphi}{R(1 + \beta f \cos \theta) - \zeta_{n-1,m}^3} \right)^2 + 2R \left(\frac{\xi_{n,m}^3 - R\beta f \cos \theta \cos \varphi}{R(1 + \beta f \cos \theta) - \zeta_{n,m}^3} \right)^2 = \frac{\xi_{2n-1,m}^3 - R\beta f \cos \theta \cos \varphi}{R(1 + \beta f \cos \theta) - \zeta_{2n-1,m}^3} \quad (27)$$

Similarly, ISP of Fibonacci points which are located on the line $x = c_1 F_n$ satisfy the Cassini identity as follows;

$$2R \left(\frac{\xi_{n,m-1}^3 - R\beta f \cos \theta \cos \varphi}{R(1 + \beta f \cos \theta) - \zeta_{n,m-1}^3} \right)^2 + 2R \left(\frac{\xi_{n,m}^3 - R\beta f \cos \theta \cos \varphi}{R(1 + \beta f \cos \theta) - \zeta_{n,m}^3} \right)^2 = \frac{\xi_{n,2m-1}^3 - R\beta f \cos \theta \cos \varphi}{R(1 + \beta f \cos \theta) - \zeta_{n,2m-1}^3}. \quad (28)$$

The other identities satisfied on the deformed spheres can be found in a similar manner.

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Determination of Initial Value Function in Time-Fractional Diffusion Equation with Robin Boundary Condition through Hermite Polynomials

Bekir Aktan^{1,*}, Mine Aylin Bayrak¹, Ali Demir¹

¹Department of Mathematics, Kocaeli University, Izmit/Kocaeli, 41001, Turkey

Corresponding author: bekir.aktan@msu.edu.tr

ORCID IDs:

First Author: [0009-0003-5134-6650](https://orcid.org/0009-0003-5134-6650)

Second Author: [0000-0001-7716-3455](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7716-3455)

Third Author: [0000-0003-3425-1812](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3425-1812)

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Abstract

This study contributes to establishment of initial value function in a time fractional diffusion equation with robin boundary condition by means of a new approach involving Hermite polynomials, Residual power series method (RPSM) and collocation methods together. First of all, robin boundary condition is made homogeneous by a suitable transformation which reduce the problem to a simpler one. The solution of reduced problem is written in series form in terms of Hermite polynomials which yields a system of fractional differential and algebraic equations. Secondly, RPSM is employed to accomplish approximate solution to the reduced problem which includes some unknowns. At this stage, collocation points and additional data are used together to determine the values of unknown initial value function at collocation points which are the unknowns in the approximate solution. Finally, the initial value of approximate solution yields the unknown initial value function. Two examples are presented to confirm the accuracy and effectiveness of the proposed method.

Keywords: Inverse problem, Time Fractional diffusion equation, The robin boundary condition, Hermite Collocation method, Residual power series method.

1 Introduction

Fractional diffusion equations with various boundary conditions have been used to analyze the diffusion processes such as super diffusion and sub diffusion processes. In this respect time fractional diffusion equations have gained popularity in various areas of science such as mathematics [1, 2], physics [3], biochemistry [4], finance [5] and medicine [6]. In the mathematical modelling of diffusion processes the inverse problems play a substantial role in the determination of unknown functions such as initial value function or source function. Therefore, the inverse problems have a broad range of applications in biological processes, thermal conductivity, chemical

diffusion [7, 8, 9], and etc. As a result, inverse problems become an indispensable part for mathematical modelling of a number of processes in various disciplines. The additional condition is provided to deal with inverse problems.

The main concern of the current study is to determine the initial value function in a time fractional diffusion equation with robin boundary condition by developing a new approach which exploits Hermite polynomials together with RPSM [10, 11, 12, 13, 14] and collocation method. In this study, the following inverse initial value problem for the time-fractional diffusion equation with robin boundary condition is considered:

$$D_t^\alpha u(x, t) = u_{xx}(x, t) + \frac{1}{x}u_x + F(x, t), x \in (0, \ell), t \in (0, T) \quad (1)$$

subject to the initial condition

$$u(x, 0) = \phi(x), x \in [0, \ell] \quad (2)$$

where $D_t^\alpha u$ represents the Caputo fractional derivative of order α .

The Robin boundary condition at $x = \ell$

$$u(\ell, t) + \eta u_x(\ell, t) = \mu(t), t \in [0, T] \quad (3)$$

where $\lambda > 0$ denotes the heat transfer coefficient, models surface convection, since the convective heat conduction between the body and its surroundings [15] is modelled by robin boundary condition. Generally, the right hand side function $\mu(t)$ equals to λu_∞ where u_∞ represents the ambient temperature.

Problem (1)-(3) is the classic forward problem when the source term $F(x, t)$, initial value $\phi(x)$ and function $\mu(t)$ are given. The inverse initial value problem we study is to recover the initial value $\phi(x)$ from the additional data

$$u(x, T) = E(x), x \in [0, \ell] \quad (4)$$

The organization of the rest of the paper is given as follows. In Section 2, related preliminaries of the problem are presented. Hermite polynomials and their properties are given in Section 3. In Section 4, the algorithms of the developed methods are presented. Some examples are demonstrated to verify the advantages of the proposed methods in Section 5. Finally, a brief conclusion is presented to summarize the outcomes in Section 6.

2 Preliminaries

In this section, fundamental definitions and notions are presented.

Definition 2.1. The Riemann-Liouville integral for α is [16, 17, 18, 19]:

$$J^\alpha f(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^x (x - \tau)^{\alpha-1} f(\tau) d\tau, & \alpha > 0 \\ f(x) & , \alpha = 0. \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Definition 2.2. The α^{th} order fractional derivative in Caputo sense is given by [16, 17, 18, 19]:

$$D^\alpha f(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\Gamma(m-\alpha)} \int_0^x (x-\tau)^{m-\alpha-1} f^{(m)}(\tau) d\tau, & m-1 < \alpha < m, m \in N, \\ \frac{d^{(m)}}{dx^{(m)}} f(x) & , \alpha = m. \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Definition 2.3. A power series expansion of the form

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} c_n (t-t_0)^{n\alpha} = c_0 + c_1 (t-t_0)^\alpha + c_2 (t-t_0)^{2\alpha} + \dots, \quad (7)$$

$$0 \leq m-1 < \alpha \leq m, \quad t \geq t_0$$

is called fractional power series about $t = t_0$ [18].

Theorem 2.1. Suppose that f has a fractional power series representation at t_0 of the form

$$f(t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} c_n (t-t_0)^{n\alpha}, \quad 0 \leq m-1 < \alpha \leq 1, \quad t_0 \leq t < t_0 + R. \quad (8)$$

If $f(t) \in C[t_0, t_0 + R)$ and $D_{t_0}^{n\alpha} f(t) \in C(t_0, t_0 + R)$ for $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, then the coefficients c_n in Eq. (10) will take the form of

$$c_n = \frac{D_{t_0}^{n\alpha} f(t_0)}{\Gamma(1+n\alpha)}, \quad (9)$$

where $D_{t_0}^{n\alpha} = D_{t_0}^\alpha D_{t_0}^\alpha \dots D_{t_0}^\alpha$ (n times) [18].

3 Hermite polynomials (HP)

Hermite polynomials $H_n, n \in N$ are the solutions of the following differential equations [20, 21, 22, 23]:

$$H_{n+1}(x) + H'_n(x) - 2xH_n(x) = 0, \quad H'_n(x) = 2nH_{n-1}(x) \quad (10)$$

which can be represented in the series form as follows:

$$H_n(x) = \Gamma(n+1) \sum_{k=0}^{[n/2]} \frac{(-1)^k (2x)^{n-2k}}{2^k \Gamma(k+1) \Gamma(n-2k+1)}, \quad n \in N_0 \quad (11)$$

Moreover, the recursion formula for Hermite polynomials are presented as:

$$H_0(x) \equiv 1, \quad H_1(x) = 2x, \\ H_{n+1}(x) = 2xH_n(x) - 2nH_{n-1}(x), \quad n \geq 1, \quad (12)$$

A significant property of Hermite polynomials is that they form an orthogonal system in $L_2(R, w)$:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} H_n(x) H_m(x) \omega(x) dx = \sqrt{2\pi} 2^n \Gamma(n+1) \delta_{nm} \quad (13)$$

where $\omega(x) = \exp(-x^2)$ and δ_{nm} is the Kronecker delta. Hence one can obtain a system of orthonormal Hermite polynomials $\psi_n(x), n = 1, 2, \dots$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \psi_n(x)\psi_m(x)\omega(x)dx = \delta_{nm}. \quad (14)$$

4 Implementation and algorithm of the proposed method

In order to make inhomogeneous robin boundary condition into homogeneous robin boundary condition, we set:

$$u(x, t) = u_1(x, t) + u_2(x, t) \quad (15)$$

where $u_1(x, t)$ is the solution of the following problem:

$$D_t^\alpha u_1(x, t) = \frac{\partial^2 u_1}{\partial x^2}(x, t) + \frac{1}{x} \frac{\partial u_1}{\partial x}(x, t) + \hat{F}(x, t) \quad (16)$$

$$u_1(x, 0) = \hat{\phi}(x), x \in [0, \ell] \quad (17)$$

$$u_{1,x}(\ell, t) + \eta u_1(\ell, t) = 0, t \in [0, T] \quad (18)$$

$$u_1(x, T) = E(x), t \in [0, T]. \quad (19)$$

Moreover, $u_2(x, t)$ is given in the form

$$u_2(x, t) = \frac{\mu(t)}{\eta\ell + 1}x \quad (20)$$

satisfying the following conditions:

$$u_2(x, 0) = \phi(x) - \hat{\phi}(x), x \in [0, \ell] \quad (21)$$

$$u_{2,x}(\ell, t) + \eta u_2(\ell, t) = \mu(t), t \in [0, T] \quad (22)$$

where

$$\hat{F}(x, t) = F(x, t) - D_t^\alpha u_2(x, t) + \frac{\partial^2 u_2}{\partial x^2}(x, t) + \frac{1}{x} \frac{\partial u_2}{\partial x}(x, t). \quad (23)$$

At this stage, the algorithm of the method takes the following steps:

Step 1. We assume that $u_1(x, t)$ is sufficiently smooth functions to be approximated by truncating the series as follows:

$$u_1(x, t) \approx \sum_{n=0}^{M-1} c_n(t)H_n(x), \quad (24)$$

Step 2. Plugging the M^{th} degree approximation of Eq.(16) into the Eq.(24) in the first problem yields the following:

$$\sum_{n=0}^{M-1} D_t^\alpha c_n(t) H_n(x) = \sum_{n=0}^{M-1} c_n(t) H_n''(x) + \frac{1}{x} \sum_{n=0}^{M-1} c_n(t) H_n'(x) + \hat{F}(x, t), \quad (25)$$

Step 3. Employing the collocation points at $x_r = \frac{2j-1}{M}, j = 1, 2, \dots, M-1$ leads to the following system of fractional ordinary differential equations:

$$\sum_{n=0}^{M-1} D_t^\alpha c_n(t) H_n(x_r) = \sum_{n=0}^{M-1} c_n(t) H_n''(x_r) + \frac{1}{x_r} \sum_{n=0}^{M-1} c_n(t) H_n'(x_r) + \hat{F}(x_r, t), \quad (26)$$

Step 4. Initial and robin boundary conditions Eq.(17)-(18) in the reduced problem give rise to the following system of $(M+1)$ algebraic equations :

$$\sum_{n=0}^{M-1} c_n(0) H_n(x_r) = \phi(x_r) \quad (27)$$

$$\sum_{n=0}^{M-1} c_n(t) H_n'(\ell) + \eta \sum_{n=0}^{M-1} c_n(t) H_n(\ell) = 0, \quad (28)$$

which allows us to determine the initial values of coefficients for $c_n(t), n = 0, 1, \dots, M-1$ in the series representation of the solution .

Step 5. The utilization of RPSM leads to establish the unknown functions $c_n(t), n = 0, 1, \dots, M-1$. Moreover, $\phi(x_r)$ is obtained by using truncating the series of the solution $u_M(x, t)$ in additional data as follows:

$$\sum_{n=0}^{M-1} c_n(T) H_n(x) dx = E(x) \quad (29)$$

Step 6. The initial value of approximate solution provides initial value function.

5 Illustrative Examples

In this section, some examples are presented to verify the accuracy and effectiveness of the proposed approach.

Example 1. Assuming that the functions $\eta = 1, \ell = 2, \mu(t) = t^{2\alpha} + 1, F(x, t) = (x^2 - x - 4)\Gamma(1 + 2\alpha)\frac{t^\alpha}{\Gamma(1+\alpha)} - 2(t^{2\alpha} + 1), E(x) = 2(x^2 - x - 4)$ are smooth functions.

The analytical solution and initial value function are obtained as $u(x, t) = (x^2 - x - 4)(t^{2\alpha} + 1)$ and $\phi(x) = (x^2 - x - 4)$, respectively .

In Fig. 1, the graphs of exact and approximate solutions of $\phi(x)$ are presented. In Fig 2-3., the 3D graphs of approximate solutions for $u_1(x, t)$ and $u_2(x, t)$ for $\alpha = 0.8$, respectively. In Table 1-2., the exact solution and absolute errors for $M = 3$ at $t = 0.8$ for various values of α .

Example 2. Assuming that the functions $\eta = 1, F(x, t) = x\Gamma(1 + 2\alpha)\frac{t^\alpha}{\Gamma(1+\alpha)}$,

Figure 1: The graphs of exact and approximate solutions of $\phi(x)$ of Ex.1 .

Figure 2: The 3D graphs of $u_1(x,t)$ and $u_2(x,t)$ for $\alpha = 0.8$ of Ex.1, respectively .

Figure 3: The 3D graphs of exact and approximate solutions of $u(x,t)$ for $\alpha = 0.8$ of Ex.1.

Table 1: The values of exact solution and absolute errors for $M = 3$ at $t = 0.8$ for various values of α of Ex. 1.

x	<i>Exact</i>	$\alpha = 1$	$\alpha = 0.9$	$\alpha = 0.8$	$\alpha = 0.6$	$\alpha = 0.4$	$\alpha = 0.2$
0	-6.5600	4.4409e-15	6.3061e-14	1.2967e-13	1.3323e-14	1.2257e-13	2.6645e-14
0.2	-6.8224	1.5099e-14	7.8160e-14	1.8208e-13	6.2172e-15	1.6964e-13	1.9540e-14
0.4	-6.9536	3.1086e-14	9.0594e-14	2.2382e-13	0	2.0961e-13	1.4211e-14
0.6	-6.9536	4.3521e-14	9.8588e-14	2.5668e-13	5.3291e-15	2.3981e-13	8.8818e-15
0.8	-6.8224	5.4179e-14	1.0481e-13	2.7889e-13	9.7700e-15	2.6024e-13	3.5527e-15
1	-6.5600	6.1284e-14	1.0747e-13	2.9310e-13	1.3323e-14	2.7356e-13	0
1.2	-6.1664	6.5725e-14	1.0569e-13	2.9576e-13	1.5987e-14	2.7711e-13	1.7764e-15
1.4	-5.6416	6.6613e-14	1.0303e-13	2.8866e-13	1.6875e-14	2.7089e-13	3.5527e-15
1.6	-4.9856	6.4837e-14	9.4147e-14	2.7356e-13	1.7764e-14	2.5580e-13	6.2172e-15
1.8	-4.1984	6.0396e-14	8.3489e-14	2.4780e-13	1.7764e-14	2.3181e-13	7.1054e-15
2	-3.2800	5.1514e-14	7.0166e-14	2.1227e-13	1.6875e-14	1.9940e-13	6.2172e-15

Figure 4: The graphs of exact and approximate solutions of $\phi(x)$ of Ex.2 .

Figure 5: The 3D graphs of $u_1(x,t)$ and $u_2(x,t)$ for $\alpha = 0.8$ of Ex.2, respectively .

$$\mu(t) = \begin{cases} 3 + 2t^{2\alpha}, & 0 \leq x \leq 1 \\ 3t^{2\alpha}, & 1 \leq x \leq 2 \end{cases}, \quad E(x) = \begin{cases} 1 + 2x, & 0 \leq x \leq 1 \\ 3, & 1 \leq x \leq 2 \end{cases} \text{ are non-smooth functions.}$$

The analytical solution and initial value function are obtained as

$$u(x,t) = \begin{cases} 1 + x(t^{2\alpha} + 1), & 0 \leq x \leq 1 \\ 3 + x(t^{2\alpha} - 1), & 1 \leq x \leq 2 \end{cases} \text{ and } \phi(x) = \begin{cases} 1 + x, & 0 \leq x \leq 1 \\ 3 - x, & 1 \leq x \leq 2 \end{cases}, \text{ respectively.}$$

In Fig. 4., the graphs of exact and approximate solutions of $\phi(x)$ are presented. In Fig 5-6., the 3D graphs of approximate solutions for $u_1(x,t)$ and $u_2(x,t)$ for $\alpha = 0.8$, respectively. In Table 3-4., the exact solution and absolute errors for $M = 2$ at $t = 0.8$ for various values of α .

Figure 6: The 3D graphs of exact and approximate solutions of $u(x,t)$ for $\alpha = 0.8$ of Ex.2.

Table 2: The values of exact solution and absolute errors values for $M = 2$ at $t = 0.8$ for various values of α of Ex. 2.

x	$Exact$	$\alpha = 1$	$\alpha = 0.9$	$\alpha = 0.8$	$\alpha = 0.6$	$\alpha = 0.4$	$\alpha = 0.2$
0	1.000	0	0	0	0	0	0
0.2	1.328	0	0	0	0	0	0
0.4	1.656	0	0	0	2.2204e-16	0	0
0.6	1.984	0	0	0	2.2204e-16	0	0
0.8	2.312	0	0	0	4.4409e-16	0	0
1	2.640	0	0	0	0	0	0
1.2	2.568	0	0	0	0	0	0
1.4	2.496	0	0	0	4.4409e-16	0	0
1.6	2.424	0	0	4.4409e-16	0	0	0
1.8	2.352	0	0	0	0	0	0
2	2.280	0	0	0	0	0	0

6 Conclusion

The contribution of this study is to provide a new approach to recover initial value function in a time fractional diffusion equation with robin boundary condition. Hermite polynomials, RPSM and collocation methods are main parts of this approach. By some transformation, we make robin boundary conditions homogeneous and obtain a simpler problem. The solution of the simpler problem is formed in series form in terms of Hermite polynomials which leads to a system of fractional differential and algebraic equations. RPSM is utilized to obtain approximate solution to the simpler problem including some unknowns because of unknown initial function. At this stage, employment of collocation method and additional condition yield the value of initial value function at collocation points which are the unknown in the approximate solution. Finally, the initial value of approximate solution reveal the unknown the initial value function. The outcomes are also verified by provided examples.

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On the Approximate Solution of the Multi-Term Time-Fractional Diffusion Problem through Hermite Polynomials

Bekir Aktan¹, Mine Aylin Bayrak¹, Ali Demir¹

¹Department of Mathematics, Kocaeli University, Izmit/Kocaeli, 41001, Turkey

Corresponding author: bekir.aktan@msu.edu.tr

ORCID IDs:

First Author: [0009-0003-5134-6650](https://orcid.org/0009-0003-5134-6650)

Second Author: [0000-0001-7716-3455](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7716-3455)

Third Author: [0000-0003-3425-1812](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3425-1812)

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Abstract

This research presents a novel approach for constructing approximate solutions to multi-term time fractional diffusion problems through Hermite polynomials, the Residual Power Series Method (RPSM), and collocation techniques. Initially, the multi-term time fractional diffusion equation is transformed into a single-term equation using the Riemann integral, simplifying the original problem. Next, Hermite polynomials are employed to express the solution as a series, which, through the application of collocation points, reduces the problem to a system of fractional differential and algebraic equations. The RPSM is then applied to determine the unknown coefficient functions in the series representation. By substituting these coefficients back into the series, an approximate solution is constructed. To illustrate the applicability and accuracy of the proposed method, three numerical examples are provided, demonstrating its effectiveness in solving complex fractional diffusion problems.

Keywords: Multi-term time-fractional diffusion equation, Hermite Collocation method, Residual power series method.

1 Introduction

Fractional diffusion equations with various boundary conditions are widely used to analyze anomalous diffusion processes, such as super-diffusion and sub-diffusion. In particular, time-fractional diffusion equations have gained significant attention across multiple scientific disciplines, including mathematics, physics, biochemistry, finance, and medicine [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8]. In the mathematical modeling of diffusion processes, fractional differential equations play a substantial role to analyze the processes in detail. These equations have a wide range of applications in various fields of science and engineering, as the order of the fractional derivative and Riemann integration could be any real number, such as $m - 1 \leq \alpha, \beta \leq m : m \in N$. As a result, fractional-order derivatives have been extensively studied and developed to interpret real-life phenomena such as biological systems, thermal conductivity, and chemical diffusion more accurately [9, 10, 11]. The

main concern of the current research is to establish approximate solutions to multi-term time fractional diffusion problem through a proposed method, a combination of Hermite polynomials, RPSM [12, 13, 14, 15, 16] and collocation method.

In this study, the following the multi-term time-fractional diffusion problem is considered:

$$D_t^\alpha u(x, t) + D_t^\beta u(x, t) = u_{xx}(x, t) + F(x, t, u), x \in (0, \ell), t \in (0, T) \quad (1)$$

subject to the initial and boundary conditions

$$u(x, 0) = \phi(x), x \in [0, \ell] \quad (2)$$

$$u(0, t) = \mu_1(t), t \in [0, T] \quad (3)$$

$$u(\ell, t) = \mu_2(t), t \in [0, T] \quad (4)$$

The organization of the rest of the paper is given as follows. In Section 2, related preliminaries of the problem are presented. Hermite polynomials and their properties are given in Section 3. In Section 4, the algorithms of the developed methods are presented. Some examples are demonstrated to verify the advantages of the proposed methods in Section 5. Finally, a brief conclusion is presented to summarize the outcomes in Section 6.

2 Preliminaries

In this section, fundamental definitions and notions are presented.

Definition 2.1. The Riemann-Liouville integral for α is [17, 18, 19, 20]:

$$J^\alpha f(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^x (x - \tau)^{\alpha-1} f(\tau) d\tau, & \alpha > 0 \\ f(x) & , \alpha = 0. \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Definition 2.2. The α^{th} order fractional derivative in Caputo sense is given by [17, 18, 19]:

$$D^\alpha f(x) = J^{m-\alpha}(D^m f(x)) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\Gamma(m-\alpha)} \int_0^x (x - \tau)^{m-\alpha-1} f^{(m)}(\tau) d\tau, & m - 1 < \alpha < m, m \in N, \\ \frac{d^{(m)}}{dx^{(m)}} f(x) & , \alpha = m. \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

which has the following properties:

- $D^\alpha C = 0$, (C is a constant)
- $D^\alpha J^\alpha f(x) = f(x)$,

- $J^\alpha D^\alpha f(x) = f(x) - \sum_{i=0}^{m-1} f^{(i)}(0) \frac{x^i}{\Gamma(i+1)},$

-

$$J^\beta(D^\alpha f(x)) = \begin{cases} D^{\alpha-\beta} f(x) - \frac{t^{\beta-\alpha}}{\Gamma(\beta+1-\alpha)} f(0), & \alpha < \beta \\ J^{\beta+1-\alpha} f'(x), & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Definition 2.3. A power series expansion of the form

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} c_n (t - t_0)^{n\alpha} = c_0 + c_1 (t - t_0)^\alpha + c_2 (t - t_0)^{2\alpha} + \dots, \quad (8)$$

$$0 \leq m - 1 < \alpha \leq m, \quad t \geq t_0$$

is called fractional power series about $t = t_0$ [19].

Theorem 2.1. Suppose that f has a fractional power series representation at t_0 of the form

$$f(t) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} c_n (t - t_0)^{n\alpha}, \quad 0 \leq m - 1 < \alpha \leq 1, \quad t_0 \leq t < t_0 + R. \quad (9)$$

If $f(t) \in C[t_0, t_0 + R]$ and $D_{t_0}^{n\alpha} f(t) \in C(t_0, t_0 + R)$ for $n = 0, 1, 2, \dots$, then the coefficients c_n in Eq. (10) will take the form of

$$c_n = \frac{D_{t_0}^{n\alpha} f(t_0)}{\Gamma(1 + n\alpha)}, \quad (10)$$

where $D_{t_0}^{n\alpha} = D_{t_0}^\alpha D_{t_0}^\alpha \dots D_{t_0}^\alpha$ (n times) [19].

3 Hermite polynomials (HP)

Hermite polynomials $H_n, n \in N$ are the solutions of the following differential equations [21, 22, 23]:

$$H_{n+1}(x) + H_n'(x) - 2xH_n(x) = 0, \quad H_n'(x) = 2nH_{n-1}(x) \quad (11)$$

which can be represented in the series form as follows:

$$H_n(x) = \Gamma(n+1) \sum_{k=0}^{[n/2]} \frac{(-1)^k (2x)^{n-2k}}{2^k \Gamma(k+1) \Gamma(n-2k+1)}, \quad n \in N_0 \quad (12)$$

Moreover, the recursion formula for Hermite polynomials are presented as:

$$\begin{aligned} H_0(x) &\equiv 1, \quad H_1(x) = 2x, \\ H_{n+1}(x) &= 2xH_n(x) - 2nH_{n-1}(x), \quad n \geq 1, \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

A significant property of Hermite polynomials is that they form an orthogonal system in $L_2(R, w)$:

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} H_n(x)H_m(x)\omega(x)dx = \sqrt{2\pi}2^n\Gamma(n+1)\delta_{nm} \quad (14)$$

where $\omega(x) = \exp(-x^2)$ and δ_{nm} is the Kronecker delta. Hence one can obtain a system of orthonormal Hermite polynomials $\psi_n(x), n = 1, 2, \dots$

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \psi_n(x)\psi_m(x)\omega(x)dx = \delta_{nm}. \quad (15)$$

Since Hermite polynomials are smooth functions, the solution can be interpolated and the problem transformed into an algebraic system of equations which is easily handled by computational software such as MATLAB and many others.

4 Algorithmic Framework and Implementation of the Proposed Method

In order to reduce multi-term time fractional diffusion problem into a single term time fractional diffusion problem, Riemann integral of order β is applied to the fractional differential equation :

$$D_t^\alpha u(x, t) + D_t^\beta u(x, t) = u_{xx}(x, t) + F(x, t, u), \quad (16)$$

which yields the following

$$D_t^{\alpha-\beta} u(x, t) = J_t^\beta u_{xx}(x, t) + u(x, 0) \left(1 + \frac{t^{\beta-\alpha}}{\Gamma(\beta+1-\alpha)}\right) - u(x, t) + J_t^\beta F(x, t, u). \quad (17)$$

At this stage, the steps of the algorithm for the method can be listed as:

Step 1. We assume that $u(x, t)$ is sufficiently smooth functions to be approximated by truncating the series in terms of Hermite polynomials as follows:

$$u(x, t) \approx \sum_{n=0}^{M-1} c_n(t)H_n(x), \quad (18)$$

Step 2. Plugging the M^{th} degree approximation of Eq.(18) into the Eq.(17) yields the following:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{M-1} D_t^{\alpha-\beta} c_n(t)H_n(x) &= \sum_{n=0}^{M-1} J_t^\beta c_n(t)H_n''(x) + \sum_{n=0}^{M-1} c_n(0)H_n(x) \left(1 + \frac{t^{\beta-\alpha}}{\Gamma(\beta+1-\alpha)}\right) \\ &\quad - \sum_{n=0}^{M-1} c_n(t)H_n(x) + J_t^\beta F\left(x, t, \sum_{n=0}^{M-1} c_n(t)H_n(x)\right), \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

Step 3. Employing the collocation points at $x_r = \frac{2j-1}{M}, j = 1, 2, \dots, M - 1$ leads to the following system of fractional ordinary differential equations:

$$\sum_{n=0}^{M-1} D_t^{\alpha-\beta} c_n(t) H_n(x_r) = \sum_{n=0}^{M-1} J_t^\beta c_n(t) H_n''(x_r) + \sum_{n=0}^{M-1} c_n(0) H_n(x_r) \left(1 + \frac{t^{\beta-\alpha}}{\Gamma(\beta+1-\alpha)}\right) - \sum_{n=0}^{M-1} c_n(t) H_n(x_r) + J_t^\beta F\left(x_r, t, \sum_{n=0}^{M-1} c_n(t) H_n(x_r)\right), \quad (20)$$

Step 4. Initial and boundary conditions Eq.(2)-(4) in the reduced problem give rise to the following system of $(M + 1)$ algebraic equations :

$$\sum_{n=0}^{M-1} c_n(0) H_n(x_r) = \phi(x_r) \quad (21)$$

$$\sum_{n=0}^{M-1} c_n(t) H_n(0) = \mu_1(t) \quad (22)$$

$$\sum_{n=0}^{M-1} c_n(t) H_n(1) = \mu_2(t) \quad (23)$$

which allows us to determine the initial values of coefficients for $c_n(t), n = 0, 1, \dots, M - 1$ in the series representation of the solution .

Step 5. The utilization of RPSM leads to establish the unknown functions $c_n(t), n = 0, 1, \dots, M - 1$. Moreover, placing the obtained coefficient functions $c_n(t), n = 0, 1, \dots, M - 1$ back into the series leads to approximate solution $u_M(x, t)$.

5 Illustrative Examples

This section provides three examples to confirm the accuracy and effectiveness of the proposed method as well as its implementation.

Example 1. Consider the multi-term time-fractional diffusion equation

$$D_t^\alpha u(x, t) + D_t^\beta u(x, t) = u_{xx}(x, t) + F(x, t), 0 < \beta < \alpha < 1, x \in (0, 1), t \in (0, 1) \quad (24)$$

subject to the initial and boundary conditions

$$u(x, 0) = 0, x \in [0, 1] \quad (25)$$

$$u(0, t) = u(1, t) = 0, t \in [0, 1] \quad (26)$$

where $F(x, t) = \Gamma(1 + 2\alpha - 2\beta) \left(\frac{t^{\alpha-2\beta}}{\Gamma(1+\alpha-2\beta)} + \frac{t^{2\alpha-3\beta}}{\Gamma(1+2\alpha-3\beta)} \right) x(1-x) + 2t^{2\alpha-2\beta}$. The analytical solution of the considered problem is obtained as $u(x, t) = x(1-x)t^{2\alpha-2\beta}$.

In Fig. 1, the graphs of exact and approximate solutions of $u(x, t)$ at $t = 0.8$ for various values of α, β and $m = 3$ are presented. In Fig 2., the 3D graphs of absolute errors for $\alpha = 0.9, \beta = 0.4$ and $m = 3$ are given. In Table 1., the exact solution and absolute errors for various values of

Figure 1: The graphs of exact and approximate solutions of $u(x, t)$ for various values of α, β of Ex.1 .

Figure 2: The 3D graphs of absolute errors for $\alpha = 0.9, \beta = 0.4$ of Ex.1.

x, t with $m = 3$ at $\alpha = 0.9, \beta = 0.4$ are presented. *Example 2.* Consider the multi-term time-fractional diffusion equation

$$D_t^\alpha u(x, t) + D_t^\beta u(x, t) = u_{xx}(x, t) + u(x, t) + F(x, t), 0 < \beta < \alpha < 1, x \in (0, 1), t \in (0, 1) \quad (27)$$

subject to the initial and boundary conditions

$$u(x, 0) = 0, x \in [0, 1] \quad (28)$$

$$u(0, t) = t^{2\alpha-2\beta} - t^{\alpha-\beta}, t \in [0, 1] \quad (29)$$

$$u(1, t) = 4(t^{2\alpha-2\beta} - t^{\alpha-\beta}), t \in [0, 1] \quad (30)$$

Table 1: The values of absolute errors for $m = 3$ and $\alpha = 0.9, \beta = 0.4$ of Ex. 1.

x/t	0.1	0.3	0.5	0.7	0.9
0.1	0	6.9389e-18	2.0817e-17	0	0
0.3	0	0	2.7756e-17	2.7756e-17	2.7756e-17
0.5	6.9389e-18	1.3878e-17	0	5.5511e-17	2.7756e-17
0.7	1.3878e-17	2.7756e-17	2.7756e-17	2.7756e-17	2.7756e-17
0.9	1.7347e-18	3.4694e-18	6.9389e-18	1.3878e-17	8.3267e-17

Figure 3: The graphs of exact and approximate solutions of $u(x, t)$ of Ex.1 .

Figure 4: The 3D graphs of absolute errors for $\alpha = 0.9, \beta = 0.4$ of Ex.1.

where $F(x, t) = (3x^3 + 1) \left(\Gamma(1 + 2\alpha - 2\beta) \frac{t^{\alpha - 2\beta}}{\Gamma(1 + \alpha - 2\beta)} - \Gamma(1 + \alpha - \beta) \frac{t^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1 - \beta)} + \Gamma(1 + 2\alpha - 2\beta) \frac{t^{2\alpha - 3\beta}}{\Gamma(1 + 2\alpha - 3\beta)} - \Gamma(1 + \alpha - \beta) \frac{t^{\alpha - 2\beta}}{\Gamma(1 + \alpha - 2\beta)} \right) - (3x^3 + 18x + 1)(t^{2\alpha - 2\beta} - t^{\alpha - \beta})$. The analytical solution of the considered problem is obtained $u(x, t) = (3x^3 + 1)(t^{2\alpha - 2\beta} - t^{\alpha - \beta})$.

In Fig. 3, the graphs of exact and approximate solutions of $u(x, t)$ at $t = 0.8$ for various values of α, β and $m = 4$ are presented. In Fig 4., the 3D graphs of absolute errors for $\alpha = 0.9, \beta = 0.4$ and $m = 4$ are given. In Table 2., the exact solution and absolute errors for various values of x, t with $m = 4$ at $\alpha = 0.9, \beta = 0.4$ are presented.

Example 3. Consider the multi-term time-fractional diffusion equation

$$D_t^\alpha u(x, t) + D_t^\beta u(x, t) = u_{xx}(x, t) + xu_x(x, t) + F(x, t), 0 < \beta < \alpha < 1, x \in (0, 1), t \in (0, 1) \quad (31)$$

subject to the initial and boundary conditions

$$u(x, 0) = \cos(x), x \in [0, 1] \quad (32)$$

Table 2: The values of absolute errors for $m = 4$ at $t = 0.8$ and $\alpha = 0.9, \beta = 0.4$ of Ex. 1.

x/t	0.1	0.3	0.5	0.7
0.1	5.5511e-17	0	2.7756e-17	2.7756e-17
0.3	2.7756e-17	0	8.3267e-17	8.3267e-17
0.5	5.5511e-17	5.5511e-17	0	1.9429e-16
0.7	1.6653e-16	1.1102e-16	5.5511e-17	2.2204e-16
0.9	1.1102e-16	1.1102e-16	0	2.2204e-16

Figure 5: The graphs of exact and approximate solutions of $u(x, t)$ of Ex.1 .

Figure 6: The 3D graphs of absolute errors for $\alpha = 0.9, \beta = 0.4$ of Ex.1.

$$u(0, t) = t^{\alpha-\beta} + 1, t \in [0, 1] \tag{33}$$

$$u(1, t) = (t^{\alpha-\beta} + 1)\cos(1), t \in [0, 1] \tag{34}$$

where $F(x, t) = \cos(x)\left(\Gamma(1 + \alpha - \beta)\left(\frac{t^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1-\beta)} + \frac{t^{\alpha-2\beta}}{\Gamma(1+\alpha-2\beta)}\right) + \left(\frac{t^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} + \frac{t^{-\beta}}{\Gamma(1-\beta)}\right)\right) + (\cos(x) + x\sin(x))(t^{\alpha-\beta} + 1)$. The analytical solution of the considered problem is obtained $u(x, t) = \cos(x)(t^{\alpha-\beta} + 1)$.

In Fig. 5, the graphs of exact and approximate solutions of $u(x, t)$ at $t = 0.8$ for various values of α, β and $m = 8$ are presented. In Fig 6., the 3D graphs of absolute errors for $\alpha = 0.9, \beta = 0.4$ and $m = 8$ are given. In Table 3., the exact solution and absolute errors for various values of x, t with $m = 8$ at $\alpha = 0.9, \beta = 0.4$ are presented.

Table 3: The values of absolute errors for $m = 7$ at $t = 0.8$ and $\alpha = 0.9, \beta = 0.4$ of Ex. 1.

x/t	0	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.8	1
0	1.8974e-19	4.9031e-17	1.5244e-16	5.8382e-17	9.8251e-17	4.0146e-17
0.2	2.4769e-10	3.5425e-10	3.9839e-10	4.3226e-10	4.6081e-10	4.8596e-10
0.4	5.3825e-10	7.8255e-10	8.8374e-10	9.6138e-10	1.0268e-09	1.0845e-09
0.6	5.6719e-10	8.2117e-10	9.2637e-10	1.0071e-09	1.0752e-09	1.1351e-09
0.8	1.7391e-10	2.5385e-10	2.8697e-10	3.1237e-10	3.3379e-10	3.5267e-10
1	1.0391e-16	1.4621e-16	8.3338e-18	1.9409e-17	1.8851e-16	1.4425e-16

6 Conclusion

The main contribution of this work is the development of a novel approach for solving multi-term time fractional diffusion problems using the Riemann integral, Hermite polynomials, the Residual Power Series Method (RPSM), and collocation techniques. This method enables the construction of approximate solutions for a wide range of multi-term fractional problems. The core idea is to reduce the original multi-term fractional problem to a single-term fractional problem via the Riemann integral. Subsequently, Hermite polynomials, in conjunction with collocation points and RPSM, are employed to derive an approximate solution. Furthermore, Hermite polynomials can be replaced with other special polynomial families to potentially improve the accuracy of the solution, making the proposed method highly adaptable and versatile for tackling various multi-term fractional problems.

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Novel Results on Fractional Weddle's Type Inequalities for Several Functional Classes via Tempered Fractional Integrals

Bilal Ahmad¹, Hüseyin Budak², Wali Haider³, Asia Shehzadi⁴, Asra Ahmad⁵

¹School of Mathematics and Computational Science, Xiangtan University, Xiangtan, 411105, China

²Department of Mathematics, Kocaeli University, Kocaeli 41001, Türkiye

³School of Mathematics and Statistics, Shaanxi Normal University, Xi'an, Shaanxi, 710119, China

⁴School of Mathematics and Statistics, Central South University, Changsha 410083, China

⁵Department of Mathematics and Statistics, University of Agriculture Faisalabad, Pakistan

Corresponding author: asrach588@gmail.com

ORCID IDs:

First Author: [0009-0002-8603-0421](https://orcid.org/0009-0002-8603-0421)

Second Author: [0000-0001-8843-955X](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8843-955X)

Third Author: [0009-0001-7065-2755](https://orcid.org/0009-0001-7065-2755)

Fourth Author: [0009-0005-1101-5536](https://orcid.org/0009-0005-1101-5536)

Fifth Author: [0009-0008-7864-3635](https://orcid.org/0009-0008-7864-3635)

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Abstract

The theory of inequalities forms the backbone of analysis by refining essential estimates between functions and their means. Weddle's type inequalities yield sharper error estimates and enhance the precision of the accuracy of integral approximation techniques. It serves as a cornerstone for improvements in mathematical modeling and integral calculus. In this investigation, we derive unique inequalities for convex functions employing tempered fractional integrals, concentrating on Weddle's type inequalities. A significant equality is formulated within the framework of tempered fractional integrals, and this provides the cornerstone for our study. Based on this equality, we develop various Weddle-type inequalities for differentiable convex mappings connected with tempered fractional integrals. These mappings extend the applicability of fractional calculus by extending classical notions and presenting further insight into the behavior of convex functions. We attain distinctive types of Weddle's type inequalities by involving key mathematical tools such as Lipschitzian, bounded functions, and functions with bounded variation, enhancing the implementation of these inequalities in diverse mathematical domains.

Keywords: Weddle's formula type inequality, Lipschitzian functions, bounded functions, bounded variation, tempered fractional integrals.

1 Introduction and Motivation

A key concept in mathematics, especially in calculus, optimization and mathematical analysis is a convexity. A function $F(\xi)$ defined on $[\Theta, \rho]$ is convex if it satisfies the following inequality for any pair of points $(\Theta, F(\Theta))$ and $(\rho, F(\rho))$ lying within the interval:

$$F(\xi\Theta + (1 - \xi)\rho) \leq \xi F(\Theta) + (1 - \xi)F(\rho), \quad (1)$$

for every ξ value between 0 and 1. Numerous fields, such as economics, biology, and optimization, depend on the convexity of functions and their extended versions. The idea of classical convexity has attracted a lot of attention lately. To learn more about convex functions, see [13, 27] and its references.

Because it creates constraints and provides crucial insights into how functions behave in various domains, inequality theory is key to mathematical analysis. Inequalities are important in the context of optimization because they provide an environment that is conducive to ideal solutions. Inequality theory also has a significant impact on numerical techniques, leading to novel error estimations and more accurate integral approximations. It improves the precision and consistency of models and algorithms in a number of fields, such as computer science, engineering, and economics. Recently, there has been a lot of attention in classical inequalities concerning integral operators connected with different convexities. Jensen, Gruss, Hölder, Hermite–Hadamard, Simpson, Euler–Maclaurin, and Milne-type inequalities [18, 2] are some significant inequalities.

Among the significant mathematical inequalities involving convex maps are the Hermite–Hadamard type inequalities, which have the following mathematical definition.

When a function $F : [\Theta, \rho] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is convex, we obtain

$$F\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right) \leq \frac{1}{\rho - \Theta} \int_{\Theta}^{\rho} F(\varpi) d\varpi \leq \frac{F(\Theta) + F(\rho)}{2}. \quad (2)$$

Numerous mathematical fields, including analysis, optimization theory, and economics, have numerous applications incorporating inequality (2). A new version of the Hermite–Hadamard–Mercer inequalities for harmonically convex functions has been provided by You et al. [32], who also looked at particular ways to solve recently discovered inequalities. Abbas et al. [1] discovered Hermite–Hadamard type inequalities for exponentially subadditive functions by utilizing Riemann–Liouville fractional integrals. Hwang et al. [?] demonstrated particular applications in the Beta function and discovered numerous improvements and related generalizations of the Hermite–Hadamard inequality for fractional integrals. By introducing derivatives and integrals of fractional/non-integer orders, fractional calculus (FC), first presented in 1695 through the correspondence between Leibniz and Marquis de l’Hospital, generalizes classical calculus. The theory was subsequently developed by mathematicians such as Euler, Liouville, and Riemann, and it gained recognition as a critical instrument in both theoretical and applied mathematics during the 19th century. The non-local aspect of FC sets it apart and is especially useful for describing memory and inherited effects in materials and systems. In many domains, including geometry, dynamics, and fractional differential equations, FC has grown in importance as a tool for modeling non-standard events [26, 15, 12]. These days, it is employed in fields including viscoelasticity,

bioengineering, control theory, and acoustics [3]. Its position in science and engineering has been cemented by foundational publications like those by Samko, Kilbas, and Marichev (1993) and Podlubny (1999), which enable the study of the intricate and unpredictable ways that natural systems function.

The following is a list of the well-known Riemann-Liouville (RL) fractional integrals:

Definition 1.1 (See [19, 14]). Presume $F \in L_1[\Theta, \rho]$, the RL fractional integral of order $\alpha > 0$, expressed as:

$$J_{\Theta+}^{\alpha} F(\varkappa) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{\Theta}^{\varkappa} (\varkappa - \kappa)^{\alpha-1} F(\kappa) d\kappa, \quad \varkappa > \Theta$$

and

$$J_{\rho-}^{\alpha} F(\varkappa) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{\varkappa}^{\rho} (\kappa - \varkappa)^{\alpha-1} F(\kappa) d\kappa, \quad \varkappa < \rho.$$

Definition 1.2. The Gamma function, as described in [9], is described using the subsequent integral expression.

$$\Gamma(\chi) = \int_0^{\infty} e^{-\kappa} \kappa^{\chi-1} d\kappa, \quad \text{Re}(\chi) > 0.$$

For a more detailed description of RL fractional integrals, see references [24, 4, 10]. However, in practical mathematics and differential equation analysis, fractional integral inequalities are crucial. Since ancient times, mathematical inequalities—which compare two numbers or expressions to show their relationships or relative magnitudes—have been an essential concept in mathematics. Convex functions and the theory of inequalities are closely related; several famous inequalities, such as Hermite–Hadamard, Simpson, Newton, Euler–Maclaurin, and Boole’s type inequalities, were developed for convex functions. Convexity serves as a reliable tool for studying inequalities, providing a basis for using geometric and analytical techniques to confirm these conclusions. Convex function analysis and inequality analysis are closely related, with each impacting the development of the other. kindly see [16, 5, 29] and the sources listed therein for more details on convexity and Newton-type inequalities associated with convex differentiable functions.

Buschman [6] was the first to investigate the tempered fractional integral in this field. Liu et al. [20] and Meerschaert et al. [23] made more thorough contributions after this. Tempered fractional calculus, a significant subfield of fractional calculus, identifies a unique intersection between fractional calculus with analytic kernels and weighted fractional calculus [11]. Given its broad use and significance, it may be viewed as an extension of fractional calculus. Its rediscovery under different names, such as significant fractional calculus [11, 7] and generalized proportional fractional calculus [17], highlights its importance.

The important preliminary steps that serve as the foundation for our main conclusions are reviewed in the next section.

Definition 1.3 (See [25]). For real values $\alpha > 0$ and $\varkappa, \lambda \geq 0$, the λ -incomplete gamma function

is identified as:

$$\Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, \varkappa) := \int_0^\varkappa \kappa^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda\kappa} d\kappa.$$

$\lambda = 1$ corresponds to the incomplete gamma function [8]:

$$\Upsilon(\alpha, \varkappa) := \int_0^\varkappa \kappa^{\alpha-1} e^{-\kappa} d\kappa.$$

Where, $0 < \alpha < \infty$ and $\lambda \geq 0$.

Remark 1.1 (See [25]). For the real values $\alpha > 0$ and $\varkappa, \lambda \geq 0$, we gain

$$\text{I. } \Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\Theta)}(\alpha, 1) = \int_0^1 \kappa^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\rho-\Theta)\kappa} d\kappa = \frac{1}{(\rho-\Theta)^\alpha} \Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, \rho - \Theta).$$

$$\text{II. } \int_0^1 \Upsilon_{\lambda(\rho-\Theta)}(\alpha, \varkappa) d\varkappa = \frac{\Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, \rho-\Theta)}{(\rho-\Theta)^\alpha} - \frac{\Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha+1, \rho-\Theta)}{(\rho-\Theta)^{\alpha+1}}.$$

Definition 1.4 (See [21, 23]). Tempered fractional integral operators of order $\alpha > 0$ and $\lambda \geq 0$ are presented as:

$$\mathfrak{I}_{\Theta^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\varkappa) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_\Theta^\varkappa (\varkappa - \kappa)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\varkappa-\kappa)} F(\kappa) d\kappa, \quad \varkappa \in [\Theta, \rho]$$

and

$$\mathfrak{I}_{\rho^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\varkappa) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_\varkappa^\rho (\kappa - \varkappa)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\kappa-\varkappa)} F(\kappa) d\kappa, \quad \varkappa \in [\Theta, \rho],$$

respectively for $F \in L_1[\Theta, \rho]$.

The RL fractional integral equations in Definition 1.1 are obviously comparable if we assume $\lambda = 0$ in Definition 1.4.

A number of examples of integral inequality for tempered fractional integrals from earlier works were presented by Gul and Yalcin [14], who developed Minkowski and Hermite–Hadamard integral inequalities using tempered fractional integral operators. Interested readers are referred to [26, 28, 30] for more details.

Motivated by earlier studies, we identified some of Weddle’s formula-type inequalities using tempered fractional integrals. The main types of function classes in tempered fractional integrals—bounded, Lipschitzian, and functions with bounded variation—are examined in this study. The most significant benefit of these inequalities is that they became Riemann–Liouville fractional Weddle’s type inequalities when $\lambda = 0$. The modified inequalities become traditional Weddle’s type inequalities when $\alpha = 1$.

Section 1.1 will establish some conclusions regarding Wwddle’s type inequalities for differentiable convex functions. We also evaluate various functional classes, such as Lipschitzian, bounded, and functions with bounded variation. Finally, we summarize our findings and research opportunities for future work. The study is organized into three sections, starting with an introduction and preliminaries that include basic definitions of fractional calculus and a brief summary of important studies in the field.

1.1 Main Contributions

Lemma 1.1. If $F : [\Theta, \rho] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a function that is absolutely continuous on (Θ, ρ) such that $F' \in L_1[\Theta, \rho]$. Then, the following equality is valid:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}\right) + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] \\ & - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2 \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)} \left[\mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right)^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\rho) + \mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right)^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\Theta) \right] = \frac{(\rho - \Theta)^{\alpha+1}}{2^{\alpha+2} \Upsilon_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)} \\ & \times \left[\int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, 1) \right) \left[F'\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2 - \xi}{2}\Theta\right) - F'\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\Theta + \frac{2 - \xi}{2}\rho\right) \right] d\xi \right. \\ & + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, 1) \right) \left[F'\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2 - \xi}{2}\Theta\right) - F'\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\Theta + \frac{2 - \xi}{2}\rho\right) \right] d\xi \\ & \left. + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, 1) \right) \left[F'\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2 - \xi}{2}\Theta\right) - F'\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\Theta + \frac{2 - \xi}{2}\rho\right) \right] d\xi \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Proof. By acknowledging the essential rules of integration, it is enough to state that

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 &= \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, 1) \right) F'\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2 - \xi}{2}\Theta\right) d\xi \quad (4) \\ &= \frac{2}{\rho - \Theta} \left[\left(\Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, 1) \right) F\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2 - \xi}{2}\Theta\right) \Big|_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{2}{\rho - \Theta} \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \xi^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)\xi} F\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2 - \xi}{2}\Theta\right) d\xi \right] \\ &= \frac{2}{\rho - \Theta} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}\left(\alpha, \frac{1}{3}\right) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, 1) \right) F\left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}\right) + \frac{\Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, 1)}{5(\rho - \Theta)} F(\Theta) \\ & \quad - \frac{2}{\rho - \Theta} \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \xi^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)\xi} F\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2 - \xi}{2}\Theta\right) d\xi, \\ I_2 &= \frac{2}{\rho - \Theta} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}\left(\alpha, \frac{2}{3}\right) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, 1) \right) F\left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}\right) \quad (5) \\ & \quad - \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}\left(\alpha, \frac{1}{3}\right) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, 1) \right) F\left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}\right) \\ & \quad - \frac{2}{\rho - \Theta} \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \xi^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)\xi} F\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2 - \xi}{2}\Theta\right) d\xi. \end{aligned}$$

In the same way, we find

$$\begin{aligned} I_3 &= \frac{2}{\rho - \Theta} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, 1) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, 1) \right) F\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right) \\ & \quad - \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}\left(\alpha, \frac{2}{3}\right) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, 1) \right) F\left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}\right) \\ & \quad - \frac{2}{\rho - \Theta} \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \xi^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)\xi} F\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2 - \xi}{2}\Theta\right) d\xi. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Consequently, we arrive at the subsequent equality by merging (4)-(6)

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_1 + I_2 + I_3 &= \frac{2}{10(\rho - \Theta)} \left[\Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1)F(\Theta) + 5 \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1)F\left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}\right) \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1)F\left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}\right) + 3 \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1)F\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right) \right] \\
 &\quad - \frac{2}{\rho - \Theta} \left[\int_0^1 \xi^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})\xi} F\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2-\xi}{2}\Theta\right) d\xi \right]. \tag{7}
 \end{aligned}$$

Similarly

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_4 + I_5 + I_6 &= -\frac{2}{10(\rho - \Theta)} \left[\Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1)F(\rho) + \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1)F\left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}\right) \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + 5 \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1)F\left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6}\right) + 3 \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1)F\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right) \right] \\
 &\quad + \frac{2}{\rho - \Theta} \left[\int_0^1 \xi^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})\xi} F\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\Theta + \frac{2-\xi}{2}\rho\right) d\xi \right]. \tag{8}
 \end{aligned}$$

By subtracting equalities (7) and (8), then we make the substitutions $\varpi = \frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2-\xi}{2}\Theta$ and $\varpi = \frac{\xi}{2}\Theta + \frac{2-\xi}{2}\rho$ for $\xi \in [0, 1]$, it becomes

$$\begin{aligned}
 &[I_1 + I_2 + I_3 - (I_4 + I_5 + I_6)] \\
 &= \frac{\Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1)}{5(\rho - \Theta)} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}\right) \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] - \frac{2^{\alpha+1}\Gamma(\alpha)}{(\rho - \Theta)^{\alpha+1}} \left[\mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^+}^{(\alpha,\lambda)} F(\rho) + \mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^-}^{(\alpha,\lambda)} F(\Theta) \right]. \tag{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

Multiplying both sides of (9) by $\frac{\rho-\Theta}{4\Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha,1)}$, the equality (3) is obtained. □

1.2 Weddle’s type Inequality for Bounded and Lipschitzian Functions Through Fractional Integral

This segment focuses on presenting fractional Weddle’s-type inequalities specifically for bounded and Lipschitzian functions.

Theorem 1.1. If all conditions of Lemma 1.1 are accomplished. If there exist $m, M \in \mathbb{R}$ such that $m \leq F'(\xi) \leq M$ for $\xi \in [\Theta, \rho]$, then we have the following Weddle’s type inequality:

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\left| \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}\right) + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] \right. \\
 &\quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2 \Upsilon_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)} \left[\mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^+}^{(\alpha,\lambda)} F(\rho) + \mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^-}^{(\alpha,\lambda)} F(\Theta) \right] \right| \\
 &\leq \frac{(\rho - \Theta)^{\alpha+1}}{2^{\alpha+2} \Upsilon_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)} [\Delta_1(\alpha, \lambda) + \Delta_2(\alpha, \lambda) + \Delta_3(\alpha, \lambda)](M - m), \tag{10}
 \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_1(\alpha, \lambda) &= \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| d\xi, \\ \Delta_2(\alpha, \lambda) &= \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| d\xi, \\ \Delta_3(\alpha, \lambda) &= \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| d\xi. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. With the assistance of Lemma 1.1, we establish

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}\right) + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2 \Upsilon_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)} \left[\mathfrak{J}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\rho) + \mathfrak{J}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\Theta) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(\rho - \Theta)^{\alpha+1}}{2^{\alpha+2} \Upsilon_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)} \left[\int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right) \left(F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2-\xi}{2}\Theta \right) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right) d\xi \right. \\ & \quad + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right) \left(F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2-\xi}{2}\Theta \right) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right) d\xi \\ & \quad + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right) \left(F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2-\xi}{2}\Theta \right) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right) d\xi \\ & \quad + \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right) \left(\frac{m+M}{2} - F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2}\Theta + \frac{2-\xi}{2}\rho \right) \right) d\xi \\ & \quad + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right) \left(\frac{m+M}{2} - F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2}\Theta + \frac{2-\xi}{2}\rho \right) \right) d\xi \\ & \quad \left. + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right) \left(\frac{m+M}{2} - F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2}\Theta + \frac{2-\xi}{2}\rho \right) \right) d\xi \right]. \quad (11) \end{aligned}$$

Through the use of modulus properties in (11), we achieve

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}\right) + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2 \Upsilon_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)} \left[\mathfrak{J}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\rho) + \mathfrak{J}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\Theta) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(\rho - \Theta)^{\alpha+1}}{2^{\alpha+2} \Upsilon_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)} \left[\int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left| F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2-\xi}{2}\Theta \right) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right| d\xi \right. \\ & \quad + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left| F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2-\xi}{2}\Theta \right) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right| d\xi \\ & \quad + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left| F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2-\xi}{2}\Theta \right) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right| d\xi \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left| F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2}\Theta + \frac{2-\xi}{2}\rho \right) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right| d\xi \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left| F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2}\Theta + \frac{2-\xi}{2}\rho \right) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right| d\xi \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left| F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2}\Theta + \frac{2-\xi}{2}\rho \right) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right| d\xi \right]. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left| \frac{m+M}{2} - F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \Theta + \frac{2-\xi}{2} \rho \right) \right| d\xi \\
 & + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left| \frac{m+M}{2} - F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \Theta + \frac{2-\xi}{2} \rho \right) \right| d\xi \\
 & + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left| \frac{m+M}{2} - F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \Theta + \frac{2-\xi}{2} \rho \right) \right| d\xi \Big].
 \end{aligned}$$

From the statements $m \leq F'(\xi) \leq M$ for $\xi \in [\Theta, \rho]$, we get

$$\left| F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \rho + \frac{2-\xi}{2} \Theta \right) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right| \leq \frac{M-m}{2}, \tag{12}$$

and

$$\left| \frac{m+M}{2} - F' \left(\frac{\xi}{2} \Theta + \frac{2-\xi}{2} \rho \right) \right| \leq \frac{M-m}{2}. \tag{13}$$

Through the application of inequalities (12) and (13), we reach

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F \left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6} \right) + F \left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3} \right) + 6F \left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2} \right) + F \left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3} \right) + 5F \left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6} \right) + F(\rho) \right] \right. \\
 & \quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2 \Upsilon_{\lambda} \left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2} \right)} \left[\mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2} \right)^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\rho) + \mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2} \right)^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\Theta) \right] \right| \\
 & \leq \frac{(\rho - \Theta)^{\alpha+1}}{2^{\alpha+2} \Upsilon_{\lambda} \left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2} \right)} \left[\int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| d\xi \right. \\
 & \quad + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| d\xi \\
 & \quad \left. + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| d\xi \right] (M - m) \\
 & \leq \frac{(\rho - \Theta)^{\alpha+1}}{2^{\alpha+2} \Upsilon_{\lambda} \left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2} \right)} [\Delta_1(\alpha, \lambda) + \Delta_2(\alpha, \lambda) + \Delta_3(\alpha, \lambda)] (M - m).
 \end{aligned}$$

This proof has been finalized. □

Remark 1.2. If $\lambda = 0$ in Theorem 1.1, we conclude

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F \left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6} \right) + F \left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3} \right) + 6F \left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2} \right) + F \left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3} \right) + 5F \left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6} \right) + F(\rho) \right] \right. \\
 & \quad \left. - \frac{2^{\alpha-1} \Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{(\rho - \Theta)^{\alpha}} \left[\mathcal{J}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2} \right)^+}^{\alpha} F(\rho) + \mathcal{J}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2} \right)^-}^{\alpha} F(\Theta) \right] \right| \\
 & \leq \frac{\alpha(\rho - \Theta)}{4} (\Delta_1(\alpha, 0) + \Delta_2(\alpha, 0) + \Delta_3(\alpha, 0)) (M - m),
 \end{aligned}$$

which is derived in [22].

Remark 1.3. If we assume $\lambda = 0$ and $\alpha = 1$ in Theorem 1.1, then we gain

$$\left| \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F \left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6} \right) + F \left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3} \right) + 6F \left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2} \right) + F \left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3} \right) + 5F \left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6} \right) + F(\rho) \right] \right|$$

$$-\frac{1}{\rho - \Theta} \int_{\Theta}^{\rho} F(\varpi) d\varpi \Big| \leq \frac{13(\rho - \Theta)}{450} (M - m),$$

which is established in [31].

Corollary 1.1. Under conditions of Theorem 1.1, if there exist $M \in \mathbb{R}^+$ such that $|F'(\xi)| \leq M$ for all $\xi \in [\Theta, \rho]$, then we attain

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}\right) + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2 \Upsilon_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)} \left[\mathfrak{I}_{\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right)^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\rho) + \mathfrak{I}_{\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right)^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\Theta) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(\rho - \Theta)^{\alpha+1}}{2^{\alpha+1} \Upsilon_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)} [\Delta_1(\alpha, \lambda) + \Delta_2(\alpha, \lambda) + \Delta_3(\alpha, \lambda)] M. \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 1.2. If $\lambda = 0$ in Theorem 1.1, we conclude

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}\right) + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{2^{\alpha-1} \Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{(\rho - \Theta)^{\alpha}} \left[\mathcal{J}_{\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right)^+}^{\alpha} F(\rho) + \mathcal{J}_{\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right)^-}^{\alpha} F(\Theta) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{\alpha(\rho - \Theta)}{4} [\Delta_1(\alpha, 0) + \Delta_2(\alpha, 0) + \Delta_3(\alpha, 0)] M. \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 1.3. If we choose $\lambda = 0$ and $\alpha = 1$ in Corollary 1.1, then we get inequality

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}\right) + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{1}{\rho - \Theta} \int_{\Theta}^{\rho} F(\varpi) d\varpi \right| \leq \frac{13(\rho - \Theta)}{225} M. \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 1.2. If all conditions of Lemma 1.1 are accomplished. If F' is a L -Lipschitzian on $[\Theta, \rho]$, then we have the subsequent inequality:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}\right) + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2 \Upsilon_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)} \left[\mathfrak{I}_{\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right)^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\rho) + \mathfrak{I}_{\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right)^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\Theta) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(\rho - \Theta)^{\alpha+2}}{2^{\alpha+2} \Upsilon_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)} [\psi_1(\alpha, \lambda) + \psi_2(\alpha, \lambda) + \psi_3(\alpha, \lambda) - [\psi_4(\alpha, \lambda) + \psi_5(\alpha, \lambda) + \psi_6(\alpha, \lambda)]] L, \quad (14) \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_1(\alpha, \lambda) &= \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, 1) \right| |(1 - \xi) d\xi, \\ \psi_2(\alpha, \lambda) &= \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_{\lambda\left(\frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}(\alpha, 1) \right| |(1 - \xi) d\xi, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_3(\alpha, \lambda) &= \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| (1 - \xi) d\xi, \\ \psi_4(\alpha, \lambda) &= \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| (\xi - 1) d\xi, \\ \psi_5(\alpha, \lambda) &= \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| (\xi - 1) d\xi, \\ \psi_6(\alpha, \lambda) &= \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| (\xi - 1) d\xi. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. By leveraging Lemma 1.1, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}\right) + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] \\ & - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2 \Upsilon_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)} \left[\mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\rho) + \mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\Theta) \right] \\ & \leq \frac{(\rho - \Theta)^{\alpha+1}}{2^{\alpha+2} \Upsilon_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)} \left[\int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right) \right. \\ & \quad \times \left(F'\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2-\xi}{2}\Theta\right) - F'\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\Theta + \frac{2-\xi}{2}\rho\right) \right) d\xi \\ & \quad + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right) \left(F'\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2-\xi}{2}\Theta\right) - F'\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\Theta + \frac{2-\xi}{2}\rho\right) \right) d\xi \\ & \quad \left. + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right) \left(F'\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2-\xi}{2}\Theta\right) - F'\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\Theta + \frac{2-\xi}{2}\rho\right) \right) d\xi \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Since F' is L -Lipschitzian function, we observe

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}\right) + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2 \Upsilon_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)} \left[\mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\rho) + \mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\Theta) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(\rho - \Theta)^{\alpha+1}}{2^{\alpha+2} \Upsilon_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)} \left[\int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| \right. \\ & \quad \times \left| F'\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2-\xi}{2}\Theta\right) - F'\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\Theta + \frac{2-\xi}{2}\rho\right) \right| d\xi \\ & \quad + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left| F'\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2-\xi}{2}\Theta\right) - F'\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\Theta + \frac{2-\xi}{2}\rho\right) \right| d\xi \\ & \quad \left. + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| \left| F'\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\rho + \frac{2-\xi}{2}\Theta\right) - F'\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\Theta + \frac{2-\xi}{2}\rho\right) \right| d\xi \right] \\ & \leq \frac{L(\rho - \Theta)^{\alpha+2}}{2^{\alpha+2} \Upsilon_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)} \left[\left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| d\xi \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{13}{15} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| d\xi + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{13}{15} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| d\xi \right) (1 - \xi) \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| d\xi + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{13}{15} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| d\xi \right. \right. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, \xi) - \frac{13}{15} \Upsilon_{\lambda(\frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}(\alpha, 1) \right| d\xi \Big| (\xi - 1) \Big] \\
 & = \frac{L(\rho - \Theta)^{\alpha+2}}{2^{\alpha+2} \Upsilon_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)} [\psi_1(\alpha, \lambda) + \psi_2(\alpha, \lambda) + \psi_3(\alpha, \lambda) - [\psi_4(\alpha, \lambda) + \psi_5(\alpha, \lambda) + \psi_6(\alpha, \lambda)]].
 \end{aligned}$$

The proof has been successfully concluded. □

Remark 1.4. If $\lambda = 0$ in Theorem 1.2, we conclude

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}\right) + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] \right. \\
 & \quad \left. - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{(\rho - \Theta)^{\alpha}} \left[\mathcal{J}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^+}^{\alpha} F(\rho) + \mathcal{J}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^-}^{\alpha} F(\Theta) \right] \right| \\
 & \leq \frac{\alpha(\rho - \Theta)^2}{4} [\psi_1(\alpha, 0) + \psi_2(\alpha, 0) + \psi_3(\alpha, 0) - [\psi_4(\alpha, 0) + \psi_5(\alpha, 0) + \psi_6(\alpha, 0)]] L,
 \end{aligned}$$

which is derived in [22].

Remark 1.5. If we assume $\lambda = 0$ and $\alpha = 1$ in Theorem 1.2, then we gain

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}\right) + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] \right. \\
 & \quad \left. - \frac{1}{\rho - \Theta} \int_{\Theta}^{\rho} F(\varpi) d\varpi \right| \leq \frac{23(\rho - \Theta)^2}{900} L,
 \end{aligned}$$

which is obtained by Mateen et al. in [22, Corollary 6].

1.3 Weddle's Type Inequality in the Fractional Context for Functions of Bounded Variation

In this part, we provide a proof for a Weddle's rule-type inequality applicable to functions of bounded variation.

Theorem 1.3. If $F : [\Theta, \rho] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a function of bounded variation on $[\Theta, \rho]$. Then, we have following inequality:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}\right) + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] \right. \\
 & \quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2 \Upsilon_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)} \left[\mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\rho) + \mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\Theta) \right] \right| \\
 & \leq \frac{1}{2 \Upsilon_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)} \max \left\{ \left| \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right) \right|, \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{4}\right) - \frac{1}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right) \right|, \right. \\
 & \quad \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right) - \frac{13}{15} \Upsilon_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right) \right|, \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{4}\right) - \frac{3}{5} \Upsilon_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right) \right|, \\
 & \quad \left. \left| \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right) \right|, \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{4}\right) - \frac{7}{10} \Upsilon_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right) \right| \right\} \bigvee_{\Theta}^{\rho}(F), \tag{15}
 \end{aligned}$$

where $\bigvee_{\Theta}^{\rho}(F)$ represent the total variation of F on $[\Theta, \rho]$.

Proof. Define mapping $\mathcal{K}(\varpi)$ by,

$$\mathcal{K}(\varpi) = \begin{cases} \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \varpi - \Theta) - \frac{1\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}{10}, & \Theta \leq \varpi < \frac{5\Theta+\rho}{6}, \\ \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \varpi - \Theta) - \frac{3\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}{5}, & \frac{5\Theta+\rho}{6} \leq \varpi < \frac{2\Theta+\rho}{3}, \\ \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \varpi - \Theta) - \frac{7\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}{10}, & \frac{2\Theta+\rho}{2} \leq \varpi < \frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}, \\ \frac{1\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}{10} - \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \rho - \varpi), & \frac{\Theta+\rho}{2} \leq \varpi < \frac{\Theta+2\rho}{3}, \\ \frac{3\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}{5} - \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \rho - \varpi), & \frac{\Theta+2\rho}{3} \leq \varpi < \frac{\Theta+5\rho}{6}, \\ \frac{7\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}{10} - \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \rho - \varpi), & \frac{\Theta+5\rho}{6} \leq \varpi \leq \rho. \end{cases}$$

By performing integrating by parts, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\Theta}^{\rho} \mathcal{K}(\varpi) dF(\varpi) \\ &= \int_{\Theta}^{\frac{5\Theta+\rho}{6}} \left(\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \varpi - \Theta) - \frac{\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}{10} \right) dF(\varpi) + \int_{\frac{5\Theta+\rho}{6}}^{\frac{2\Theta+\rho}{3}} \left(\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \varpi - \Theta) - \frac{3\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}{5} \right) dF(\varpi) \\ &+ \int_{\frac{2\Theta+\rho}{3}}^{\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}} \left(\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \varpi - \Theta) - \frac{7\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}{10} \right) dF(\varpi) + \int_{\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}}^{\frac{\Theta+2\rho}{3}} \left(\frac{7\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}{10} - \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \rho - \varpi) \right) dF(\varpi) \\ &+ \int_{\frac{\Theta+2\rho}{3}}^{\frac{\Theta+5\rho}{6}} \left(\frac{3\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}{5} - \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \rho - \varpi) \right) dF(\varpi) + \int_{\frac{\Theta+5\rho}{6}}^{\rho} \left(\frac{\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}{10} - \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \rho - \varpi) \right) dF(\varpi) \\ &= \left(\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \varpi - \Theta) - \frac{\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}{10} \right) F(\varpi) \Big|_{\Theta}^{\frac{5\Theta+\rho}{6}} - \int_{\Theta}^{\frac{5\Theta+\rho}{6}} (\varpi - \Theta)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\varpi-\Theta)} F(\varpi) d\varpi \\ &+ \left(\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \varpi - \Theta) - \frac{3\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}{5} \right) F(\varpi) \Big|_{\frac{5\Theta+\rho}{6}}^{\frac{2\Theta+\rho}{3}} - \int_{\frac{5\Theta+\rho}{6}}^{\frac{2\Theta+\rho}{3}} (\varpi - \Theta)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\varpi-\Theta)} F(\varpi) d\varpi \\ &+ \left(\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \varpi - \Theta) - \frac{7\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}{10} \right) F(\varpi) \Big|_{\frac{2\Theta+\rho}{3}}^{\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}} - \int_{\frac{2\Theta+\rho}{3}}^{\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}} (\varpi - \Theta)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\varpi-\Theta)} F(\varpi) d\varpi \\ &+ \left(\frac{7\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}{10} - \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \rho - \varpi) \right) F(\varpi) \Big|_{\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}}^{\frac{\Theta+2\rho}{3}} - \int_{\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}}^{\frac{\Theta+2\rho}{3}} (\rho - \varpi)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\rho-\varpi)} F(\varpi) d\varpi \\ &+ \left(\frac{3\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}{5} - \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \rho - \varpi) \right) F(\varpi) \Big|_{\frac{\Theta+2\rho}{3}}^{\frac{\Theta+5\rho}{6}} - \int_{\frac{\Theta+2\rho}{3}}^{\frac{\Theta+5\rho}{6}} (\rho - \varpi)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\rho-\varpi)} F(\varpi) d\varpi \\ &+ \left(\frac{\gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2})}{10} - \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \rho - \varpi) \right) F(\varpi) \Big|_{\frac{\Theta+5\rho}{6}}^{\rho} - \int_{\frac{\Theta+5\rho}{6}}^{\rho} (\rho - \varpi)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\rho-\varpi)} F(\varpi) d\varpi \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \left(\gamma_\lambda \left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{6} \right) - \frac{\gamma_\lambda \left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2} \right)}{10} \right) F \left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6} \right) + \frac{\gamma_\lambda \left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2} \right)}{10} F(\Theta) \\
 &\quad - \int_{\Theta}^{\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}} (\varpi - \Theta)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\varpi - \Theta)} F(\varpi) d\varpi + \left(\gamma_\lambda \left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{3} \right) - \frac{3 \gamma_\lambda \left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2} \right)}{5} \right) F \left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3} \right) \\
 &\quad - \left(\gamma_\lambda \left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{6} \right) - \frac{3 \gamma_\lambda \left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2} \right)}{5} \right) F \left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6} \right) - \int_{\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}}^{\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}} (\varpi - \Theta)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\varpi - \Theta)} F(\varpi) d\varpi \\
 &\quad + \left(\frac{3 \gamma_\lambda \left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2} \right)}{10} \right) F \left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2} \right) \\
 &\quad - \left(\gamma_\lambda \left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{3} \right) - \frac{7 \gamma_\lambda \left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2} \right)}{10} \right) F \left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3} \right) - \int_{\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}}^{\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}} (\varpi - \Theta)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\varpi - \Theta)} F(\varpi) d\varpi \\
 &\quad + \left(\frac{7 \gamma_\lambda \left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2} \right)}{10} - \gamma_\lambda \left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{3} \right) \right) F \left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3} \right) + \frac{3 \gamma_\lambda \left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2} \right)}{10} F \left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2} \right) \\
 &\quad - \int_{\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}}^{\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}} (\rho - \varpi)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\rho - \varpi)} F(\varpi) d\varpi + \left(\frac{3 \gamma_\lambda \left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2} \right)}{5} - \gamma_\lambda \left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{6} \right) \right) F \left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6} \right) \\
 &\quad - \left(\frac{3 \gamma_\lambda \left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2} \right)}{5} - \gamma_\lambda \left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{3} \right) \right) F \left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3} \right) - \int_{\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}}^{\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6}} (\rho - \varpi)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\rho - \varpi)} F(\varpi) d\varpi \\
 &\quad + \frac{\gamma_\lambda \left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2} \right)}{10} F(\rho) - \left(\frac{\gamma_\lambda \left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2} \right)}{10} - \gamma_\lambda \left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{6} \right) \right) F \left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6} \right) \\
 &\quad - \int_{\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6}}^{\rho} (\rho - \varpi)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\rho - \varpi)} F(\varpi) d\varpi \\
 &= \frac{\gamma_\lambda \left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2} \right)}{10} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F \left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6} \right) + F \left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3} \right) + 6F \left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2} \right) + F \left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3} \right) \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + 5F \left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6} \right) + F(\rho) \right] - \Gamma(\alpha) \left[\mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right)^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\Theta) + \mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right)^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\rho) \right].
 \end{aligned}$$

As a result, we can state

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F \left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6} \right) + F \left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3} \right) + 6F \left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2} \right) + F \left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3} \right) + 5F \left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6} \right) + F(\rho) \right] \\
 &\quad - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2 \gamma_\lambda \left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2} \right)} \left[\mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right)^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\rho) + \mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right)^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\Theta) \right] \\
 &= \frac{1}{2 \gamma_\lambda \left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2} \right)} \int_{\Theta}^{\rho} \mathcal{K}(\varpi) dF(\varpi).
 \end{aligned}$$

It is understood that if $g, F : [\Theta, \rho] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ satisfy that g is continuous on $[\Theta, \rho]$ and F possesses

bounded variation on $[\Theta, \rho]$, then $\int_{\Theta}^{\rho} g(\xi) dF(\xi)$ exist and

$$\left| \int_{\Theta}^{\rho} g(\xi) dF(\xi) \right| \leq \sup_{\xi \in [\Theta, \rho]} |g(\xi)| \bigvee_{\Theta}^{\rho}(F). \tag{16}$$

Alternatively, utilizing (16), we conclude

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}\right) + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2 \gamma_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)} \left[\mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right)^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\Theta) + \mathfrak{Z}_{\left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right)^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} F(\rho) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{1}{2 \gamma_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)} \left[\left| \int_{\Theta}^{\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}} \left(\gamma_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \varpi - \Theta\right) - \frac{\gamma_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}{10} \right) dF(\varpi) \right| \right. \\ & \quad + \left| \int_{\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}}^{\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}} \left(\gamma_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \varpi - \Theta\right) - \frac{3 \gamma_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}{5} \right) dF(\varpi) \right| \\ & \quad + \left| \int_{\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}}^{\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}} \left(\gamma_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \varpi - \Theta\right) - \frac{7 \gamma_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}{10} \right) dF(\varpi) \right| \\ & \quad + \left| \int_{\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}}^{\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}} \left(\frac{7 \gamma_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}{10} - \gamma_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \rho - \varpi\right) \right) dF(\varpi) \right| \\ & \quad + \left| \int_{\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}}^{\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6}} \left(\frac{3 \gamma_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}{5} - \gamma_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \rho - \varpi\right) \right) dF(\varpi) \right| \\ & \quad \left. + \left| \int_{\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6}}^{\rho} \left(\frac{\gamma_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}{10} - \gamma_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \rho - \varpi\right) \right) dF(\varpi) \right| \right] \\ & \leq \frac{1}{2 \gamma_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)} \left[\sup_{\varpi \in \left(\Theta, \frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}\right)} \left| \gamma_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \varpi - \Theta\right) - \frac{\gamma_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}{10} \right| \bigvee_{\Theta}^{\frac{6\Theta + \rho}{6}}(F) \right. \\ & \quad + \sup_{\varpi \in \left(\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}, \frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}\right)} \left| \gamma_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \varpi - \Theta\right) - \frac{3 \gamma_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}{5} \right| \bigvee_{\frac{5\Theta + \rho}{6}}^{\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}}(F) \\ & \quad + \sup_{\varpi \in \left(\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}, \frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}\right)} \left| \gamma_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \varpi - \Theta\right) - \frac{7 \gamma_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}{10} \right| \bigvee_{\frac{2\Theta + \rho}{3}}^{\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}}(F) \\ & \quad + \sup_{\varpi \in \left(\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}, \frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}\right)} \left| \frac{7 \gamma_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}{10} - \gamma_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \rho - \varpi\right) \right| \bigvee_{\frac{\Theta + \rho}{2}}^{\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}}(F) \\ & \quad \left. + \sup_{\varpi \in \left(\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}, \frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6}\right)} \left| \frac{3 \gamma_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho - \Theta}{2}\right)}{5} - \gamma_{\lambda}\left(\alpha, \rho - \varpi\right) \right| \bigvee_{\frac{\Theta + 2\rho}{3}}^{\frac{\Theta + 5\rho}{6}}(F) \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \sup_{\varpi \in (\frac{\Theta+5\rho}{6}, \rho)} \left| \frac{\gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)}{10} - \gamma_\lambda(\alpha, \rho - \varpi) \right| \left[\bigvee_{\frac{\Theta+5\rho}{6}}^\rho (F) \right] \\
 = & \frac{1}{2 \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)} \left[\max \left\{ \frac{1}{10} \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right), \left| \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{4}\right) - \frac{1}{10} \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right) \right| \right\} \bigvee_{\Theta}^{\frac{5\Theta+\rho}{6}} (F) \right. \\
 & + \max \left\{ \left| \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right) - \frac{3}{5} \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right) \right|, \left| \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{4}\right) - \frac{3}{5} \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right) \right| \right\} \bigvee_{\frac{5\Theta+\rho}{6}}^{\frac{\Theta+2\rho}{3}} (F) \\
 & + \max \left\{ \left| \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right) - \frac{7}{10} \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right) \right|, \left| \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{4}\right) - \frac{7}{10} \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right) \right| \right\} \bigvee_{\frac{\Theta+2\rho}{3}}^{\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}} (F) \\
 & + \max \left\{ \left| \frac{7}{10} \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right) - \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{4}\right) \right|, \left| \frac{7}{10} \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right) - \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right) \right| \right\} \bigvee_{\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}}^{\frac{\Theta+2\rho}{3}} (F) \\
 & + \max \left\{ \left| \frac{3}{5} \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right) - \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{4}\right) \right|, \left| \frac{3}{5} \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right) - \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right) \right| \right\} \bigvee_{\frac{\Theta+2\rho}{3}}^{\frac{\Theta+5\rho}{6}} (F) \\
 & \left. + \max \left\{ \frac{1}{10} \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right), \left| \frac{1}{10} \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right) - \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{4}\right) \right| \right\} \bigvee_{\frac{\Theta+5\rho}{6}}^\rho (F) \right] \\
 \leq & \frac{1}{2 \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right)} \max \left\{ \left| \frac{1}{10} \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right) \right|, \left| \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{4}\right) - \frac{1}{10} \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right) \right|, \right. \\
 & \left| \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right) - \frac{13}{15} \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right) \right|, \left| \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{4}\right) - \frac{3}{5} \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right) \right|, \\
 & \left. \left| \frac{7}{10} \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right) \right|, \left| \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{4}\right) - \frac{7}{10} \gamma_\lambda\left(\alpha, \frac{\rho-\Theta}{2}\right) \right| \right\} \bigvee_{\Theta}^\rho (F).
 \end{aligned}$$

This concludes the proof of Theorem 1.3. □

Remark 1.6. If $\lambda = 0$ in Theorem 1.3, we conclude

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta+\rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta+\rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta+2\rho}{3}\right) + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta+5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] \right. \\
 & \quad \left. - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(\rho-\Theta)^\alpha} \left[\mathcal{J}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^+}^\alpha F(\rho) + \mathcal{J}_{\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right)^-}^\alpha F(\Theta) \right] \right| \\
 & \leq \frac{1}{2} \max \left\{ \left| \left(\frac{1}{3}\right)^\alpha - \frac{1}{10} \right|, \left| \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^\alpha - \frac{3}{5} \right|, \left| \left(\frac{1}{3}\right)^\alpha - \frac{3}{5} \right|, \left| \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^\alpha - \frac{7}{10} \right|, \frac{3}{10} \right\} \bigvee_{\Theta}^\rho (F).
 \end{aligned}$$

which is demonstrated by Mateen et al. in [22].

Remark 1.7. If we assume $\lambda = 0$ and $\alpha = 1$ in Theorem 1.3, then we gain

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[F(\Theta) + 5F\left(\frac{5\Theta+\rho}{6}\right) + F\left(\frac{2\Theta+\rho}{3}\right) + 6F\left(\frac{\Theta+\rho}{2}\right) + F\left(\frac{\Theta+2\rho}{3}\right) + 5F\left(\frac{\Theta+5\rho}{6}\right) + F(\rho) \right] \right. \\
 & \quad \left. - \frac{1}{\rho-\Theta} \int_{\Theta}^{\rho} F(\varpi) d\varpi \right| \leq \frac{3}{20} \bigvee_{\Theta}^\rho (F),
 \end{aligned}$$

which is demonstrated by Mateen et al. in [22, Corollary 7].

1.4 Future Research Directions

In this work, we have established several new Weddle-type inequalities within the framework of tempered fractional integrals for differentiable convex functions. By formulating a fundamental equality associated with tempered fractional operators, we developed a unified approach that serves as the basis for deriving these refined inequalities. The results obtained not only extend the classical Weddle's inequality but also deepen the understanding of how convex functions behave under the influence of fractional parameters.

Furthermore, by incorporating classes of functions such as Lipschitzian, bounded functions, and functions of bounded variation, our findings broaden the applicability of fractional calculus in numerical approximation and analytical modeling. The derived inequalities offer sharper error bounds and improved approximation accuracy, making them valuable tools for future advancements in integral inequalities, numerical quadrature, and related analytical techniques. This study lays a foundation for further exploration of fractional integral inequalities and encourages new applications in diverse areas of mathematical analysis.

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Extensions of Newton-Type Inequalities via Multiplicative Conformable Fractional Integrals

Hüseyin Budak¹, Büşra Betül Ergün¹

¹Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Science and Arts, Kocaeli University,
Kocaeli 41001, Türkiye

Corresponding author: ergnbra12@gmail.com

ORCID IDs:

First Author: [0000-0001-8843-955X](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8843-955X)

Second Author: [0009-0009-4038-4487](https://orcid.org/0009-0009-4038-4487)

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Abstract

In this study, a novel form of Newton-type inequality for multiplicative convex functions is derived using multiplicative conformable fractional integrals, which has not been previously addressed in the literature. To prove the main results of the study, a well-structured integral identity is first established. This identity is then combined with multiplicative conformable fractional integrals to construct a new inequality structure. In addition, a special Newton-type inequality is presented for functions whose multiplicative derivatives are bounded. To support the validity of the obtained inequality and the derived identity, various specific cases are provided, thereby demonstrating the generality and flexibility of the results. In this respect, the study offers a new perspective to the field of multiplicative analysis and lays a foundation for future applications to different types of fractional integral operators or function classes.

Keywords: Multiplicative calculus, Newton inequality, fractional integrals, bounded function.

1 Introduction

Fractional calculus has been widely employed to describe nonlocal and memory-driven phenomena, leading to the development of various fractional integral operators with strong modeling capabilities [12, 1].

As an alternative to classical calculus, multiplicative calculus has emerged as an alternative analytical framework based on multiplication rather than addition, making it particularly effective for processes governed by exponential growth, decay, or proportional changes[15]. The foundations of multiplicative derivatives and integrals were formalized in[6], enabling the adaptation of classical inequalities to the multiplicative setting. Within this framework, several fundamental inequalities (such as Hermite–Hadamard and Ostrowski inequalities) have been extended to their multiplicative counterparts [2, 8, 4]. Chasreechai et al. obtained Newton-type inequalities for multiplicative integrals[11]. Subsequently, Ali presented Newton-type inequalities for the multiplicative Riemann–Liouville fractional integrals[2]. More recently, the multiplicative conformable fractional integral (MCFI) was introduced as a hybrid operator combining the advantages of both conformable and multiplicative calculus structures[9]. For more information, please refer to[11, 7, 10, 5].

This article consists of five sections, including the introduction. In Section 2, multiplicative derivatives and multiplicative integrals are reviewed, and the properties related to these concepts are presented. Then, the definitions of Riemann–Liouville fractional integrals, conformable fractional integrals, multiplicative Riemann–Liouville fractional integrals, and multiplicative conformable fractional integrals are introduced. In Section 3, an identity necessary for presenting the main findings is obtained. In Section 4, it is aimed to develop Newton-type inequalities for multiplicative differentiability and multiplicative convex functions with the help of MCFI. Finally, in Section 5, the results of our study are evaluated, and potential directions for future research are highlighted.

2 Preliminaries

2.1 Multiplicative Calculus

Proposition 2.1. [6] If f is positive and Riemann integrable on $[a, b]$, then f is multiplicative integrable on $[a, b]$ and

$$\int_a^b (f(x))^{dx} = \exp \left\{ \int_a^b \ln(f(x)) dx \right\}.$$

Proposition 2.2. [6] Under the condition that the functions f and g , being positive, are multiplicative integrable on the interval $[a, b]$, it is evident that the properties given below are applicable.

1. $\int_a^b ((f(x))^p)^{dx} = \left(\int_a^b (f(x))^{dx} \right)^p, p \in \mathbb{R},$
2. $\int_a^b (f(x)g(x))^{dx} = \int_a^b (f(x))^{dx} \cdot \int_a^b (g(x))^{dx},$
3. $\int_a^b \left(\frac{f(x)}{g(x)} \right)^{dx} = \frac{\int_a^b (f(x))^{dx}}{\int_a^b (g(x))^{dx}},$
4. $\int_a^b (f(x))^{dx} = \int_a^c (f(x))^{dx} \cdot \int_c^b (f(x))^{dx}, a \leq c \leq b,$
5. $\int_a^a (f(x))^{dx} = 1$ and $\int_a^b (f(x))^{dx} = \left(\int_b^a (f(x))^{dx} \right)^{-1}.$

Definition 2.1. [6] Consider the function $f : I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ and assume that its $*$ derivative exists. The notation f^* symbolizes multiplicative derivative of f (shortly $*$ derivative of the function f), which is expressed as

$$f^*(x) = \frac{d^* f(x)}{dx} = \exp \left\{ (\ln f(x))' \right\}.$$

Proposition 2.3. [6] Presuming that the functions $f, g : I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ are $*$ differentiable, and the function $h : I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is differentiable on I° . If the constant $c > 0$, then the functions $cf, f + g, fg, \frac{f}{g}, f^h$ and $f \circ h$ are all $*$ differentiable on I° as well, and the listed below properties holds:

1. $(cf)^*(x) = f^*(x),$
2. $(f + g)^*(x) = [f^*(x)]^{\frac{f(x)}{f(x)+g(x)}} [g^*(x)]^{\frac{g(x)}{f(x)+g(x)}},$
3. $(fg)^*(x) = f^*(x)g^*(x),$
4. $\left(\frac{f}{g} \right)^*(x) = \frac{f^*(x)}{g^*(x)},$
5. $(f^h)^*(x) = f^*(x)^{h(x)} f(x)^{h'(x)},$
6. $(f \circ h)^*(x) = f^*(h(x))^{h'(x)}.$

Definition 2.2 (Multiplicative absolute value). [14] Let $x \in \mathbb{R}_*$. The multiplicative absolute value is defined as follows

$$|x|_* = \begin{cases} x, & \text{if } x \geq 1, \\ \frac{1}{x}, & \text{if } 0 < x < 1. \end{cases}$$

Remark 2.1. The classical absolute value and the multiplicative one are linked by the following relation

$$|\exp\{x\}|_* = \exp|x|$$

and

$$|\ln(x)| = \ln|x|_*.$$

The following theorems give the integral-by-part formulas for multiplicative integrals, which will be used in the main results.

Theorem 2.1. [6] Let $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be multiplicative differentiable and $g : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be differentiable so the f^g is multiplicative integrable. Then

$$\int_a^b \left((f^*(x))^{g(x)} \right)^{dx} = \frac{(f(b))^{g(b)}}{(f(a))^{g(a)}} \cdot \frac{1}{\int_a^b \left((f(x))^{g'(x)} \right)^{dx}}.$$

Theorem 2.2. [4] Let $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be multiplicative differentiable, let $g : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $h : I \subset \mathbb{R} \rightarrow [a, b]$ be two differentiable functions. Then we have

$$\int_a^b \left((f^*(h(x)))^{g(x)h'(x)} \right)^{dx} = \frac{f(h(b))^{g(b)}}{f(h(a))^{g(a)}} \cdot \frac{1}{\int_a^b \left((f(h(x)))^{g'(x)} \right)^{dx}}.$$

2.2 Some Definitions and Several Newton Inequalities

Definition 2.3. [22] A non-empty set K is said to be convex, if for every $a, b \in K$ we have

$$a + t(b - a) \in K, \forall t \in [0, 1].$$

Definition 2.4. [22] A function f is said to be convex function set K , if

$$f(tx + (1 - t)y) \leq tf(x) + (1 - t)f(y)$$

for all $a, b \in K$ and all $t \in [0, 1]$.

Definition 2.5. [19] A function f is said to be *log* or multiplicatively convex function on set K , if

$$f(ta + (1 - t)b) \leq [f(x)]^t [f(y)]^{(1-t)}$$

for all $a, b \in K$ and all $t \in [0, 1]$.

Remark 2.2. If a positive function f is a multiplicatively convex, then the function $\ln f$ is a convex function.

Definition 2.6. The Euler Gamma function, Beta function and Incomplete Beta function are defined by

$$\Gamma(x) := \int_0^\infty \xi^{x-1} e^{-\xi} d\xi$$

$$B(x, y) := \int_0^1 \xi^{x-1} (1 - \xi)^{y-1} d\xi$$

and

$$\mathfrak{B}(x, y, r) := \int_0^r \xi^{x-1} (1 - \xi)^{y-1} d\xi$$

respectively for $0 < x, y < \infty$ and $r \in [0, 1]$.

Definition 2.7. [18] Let the function $f \in L_1([a, b])$. For the order $\beta > 0$, the Riemann-Liouville Fractional Integrals (RLFI) $J_{a+}^\beta f(x)$ and $J_{b-}^\beta f(x)$ are defined by

$$J_{a+}^\beta f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_a^x (x - t)^{\beta-1} f(t) dt, \quad x > a$$

and

$$J_{b-}^\beta f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_x^b (t - x)^{\beta-1} f(t) dt, \quad b > x$$

respectively. Here Γ represents the Euler Gamma function.

Definition 2.8. [8] The multiplicative left Riemann-Liouville Fractional Integral $({}_a I_*^\beta f)(x)$ of order $\beta > 0$ starting from β is defined by

$$({}_a I_*^\beta f)(x) = \exp \left\{ (J_{a+}^\beta (\ln \circ f))(x) \right\}$$

and the multiplicative right one $(*_b I^\beta f)(x)$ is defined by

$$(*_b I^\beta f)(x) = \exp \left\{ (J_{b-}^\beta (\ln \circ f))(x) \right\}.$$

Definition 2.9. [16] Let the function $f \in L_1([a, b])$. For the order $\beta > 0$ and $\alpha \in (0, 1]$, the Conformable Fractional Integrals (CFI) ${}_+^{\beta}I_a^{\alpha}f(x)$ and ${}_-^{\beta}I_b^{\alpha}f(x)$, correspondingly, are defined by

$${}_+^{\beta}I_a^{\alpha}f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_a^x \left(\frac{(x-a)^{\alpha} - (t-a)^{\alpha}}{\alpha} \right)^{\beta-1} (t-a)^{\alpha-1} f(t) dt, x > a$$

and

$${}_-^{\beta}I_b^{\alpha}f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_x^b \left(\frac{(b-x)^{\alpha} - (b-t)^{\alpha}}{\alpha} \right)^{\beta-1} (b-t)^{\alpha-1} f(t) dt, b > x$$

respectively. Here, Γ represents the Euler Gamma function.

Definition 2.10. [10] The multiplicative left Conformable Fractional Integral $({}_a^{\beta}\mathcal{I}_*^{\alpha}f)(x)$ of order $\beta > 0$ and $\alpha \in (0, 1]$ by

$$\begin{aligned} ({}_a^{\beta}\mathcal{I}_*^{\alpha}f)(x) &= \exp \left\{ {}_+^{\beta}I_a^{\alpha}((\ln \circ f)(x)) \right\} \\ &= \exp \left\{ \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_a^x \left(\frac{(x-a)^{\alpha} - (t-a)^{\alpha}}{\alpha} \right)^{\beta-1} \frac{(\ln \circ f)(t)}{(t-a)^{1-\alpha}} dt, x > a \right\}, \end{aligned}$$

and the multiplicative right Conformable Fractional Integral $({}_*^{\beta}\mathcal{I}_b^{\alpha}f)(x)$ is defined by

$$\begin{aligned} ({}_*^{\beta}\mathcal{I}_b^{\alpha}f)(x) &= \exp \left\{ {}_-^{\beta}I_b^{\alpha}((\ln \circ f)(x)) \right\} \\ &= \exp \left\{ \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_x^b \left(\frac{(b-x)^{\alpha} - (b-t)^{\alpha}}{\alpha} \right)^{\beta-1} \frac{(\ln \circ f)(t)}{(b-t)^{1-\alpha}} dt, b > x \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Here, Γ is the Euler Gamma function.

3 An Essential Identity MCFI

Lemma 3.1. Let $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ be multiplicative differentiable function over (a, b) . If f^* is multiplicative integrable on $[a, b]$, then the following equality holds:

$$\frac{\left[f(a) \cdot f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right)^3 \cdot f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right)^3 \cdot f(b) \right]^{\frac{1}{8}}}{\left[{}^{\beta} \mathcal{I}_b^{\alpha} f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \cdot {}^{\beta} \mathcal{I}_a^{\alpha} f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right]^{\frac{\alpha\beta 2^{\alpha\beta-1} \Gamma(\beta+1)}{(b-a)^{\alpha\beta}}} } = [T_1 \times T_2 \times T_3 \times T_4]^{\frac{\alpha\beta(b-a)}{4}}. \quad (1)$$

Here,

$$\begin{aligned} T_1 & : = \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\left[f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}b + \frac{1-t}{2}a \right) \right]^{\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^{\alpha}}{\alpha} \right)^{\beta}} \right) dt, \\ T_2 & : = \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\left[f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}a + \frac{1-t}{2}b \right) \right]^{-\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^{\alpha}}{\alpha} \right)^{\beta}} \right) dt, \\ T_3 & : = \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^1 \left(\left[f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}b + \frac{1-t}{2}a \right) \right]^{\left(\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^{\alpha}}{\alpha} \right)^{\beta} - \frac{3}{4\alpha^{\beta}} \right)} \right) dt, \\ T_4 & : = \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^1 \left(\left[f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}a + \frac{1-t}{2}b \right) \right]^{\left(\frac{3}{4\alpha^{\beta}} - \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^{\alpha}}{\alpha} \right)^{\beta} \right)} \right) dt, \end{aligned}$$

and Γ is Euler Gamma function.

Proof. By using Theorem 2.2, we have

$$\begin{aligned} T_1 & = \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\left[f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}b + \frac{1-t}{2}a \right) \right]^{\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^{\alpha}}{\alpha} \right)^{\beta}} \right) dt \\ & = \left[\int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\left[f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}b + \frac{1-t}{2}a \right) \right]^{\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^{\alpha}}{\alpha} \right)^{\beta} \left(\frac{b-a}{2} \right)} \right) dt \right]^{\frac{2}{b-a}} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \frac{\left[f\left(\frac{2b+a}{3}\right) \right]^{\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\right)\left(\frac{3^\alpha-2^\alpha}{\alpha 3^\alpha}\right)^\beta}}{f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right)^0} \cdot \frac{1}{\left[\int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\left[f\left(\frac{1+t}{2}b + \frac{1-t}{2}a\right) \right]^{\beta(1-t)^{\alpha-1} \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha}\right)^{\beta-1}} \right) dt \right]^{\frac{2}{b-a}}} \\
 &= \frac{\left[f\left(\frac{2b+a}{3}\right) \right]^{\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\right)\left(\frac{3^\alpha-2^\alpha}{\alpha 3^\alpha}\right)^\beta}}{\exp \left\{ \frac{2}{b-a} \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \beta(1-t)^{\alpha-1} \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha}\right)^{\beta-1} \ln f\left(\frac{1+t}{2}b + \frac{1-t}{2}a\right) dt \right\}} \\
 &= \frac{\left[f\left(\frac{2b+a}{3}\right) \right]^{\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\right)\left(\frac{3^\alpha-2^\alpha}{\alpha 3^\alpha}\right)^\beta}}{\exp \left\{ \frac{2}{b-a} \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+2b}{3}} \beta(b-u)^{\alpha-1} \left(\frac{2}{b-a}\right)^{\alpha-1} \left(\frac{1-\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\right)^\alpha(b-u)^\alpha}{\alpha}\right)^{\beta-1} \ln f(u) \frac{2}{b-a} du \right\}} \\
 &= \frac{\left[f\left(\frac{2b+a}{3}\right) \right]^{\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\right)\left(\frac{3^\alpha-2^\alpha}{\alpha 3^\alpha}\right)^\beta}}{\exp \left\{ \frac{2^\alpha \beta + 1 \Gamma(\beta+1)}{(b-a)^{\alpha \beta + 1} \Gamma(\beta)} \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+2b}{3}} (b-u)^{\alpha-1} \left(\frac{(b-a)^\alpha - (b-u)^\alpha}{\alpha}\right)^{\beta-1} \ln f(u) du \right\}},
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_2 &= \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\left[f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}a + \frac{1-t}{2}b \right) \right]^{-\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha}\right)^\beta} \right)^{dt} \\
 &= \frac{\left[f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) \right]^{\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\right)\left(\frac{3^\alpha-2^\alpha}{\alpha 3^\alpha}\right)^\beta}}{\exp \left\{ \frac{2^\alpha \beta + 1 \Gamma(\beta+1)}{(b-a)^{\alpha \beta + 1} \Gamma(\beta)} \int_{\frac{2a+b}{3}}^{\frac{a+b}{2}} (k-a)^{\alpha-1} \left(\frac{(b-a)^\alpha - (k-a)^\alpha}{\alpha}\right)^{\beta-1} \ln f(k) dk \right\}},
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 T_3 &= \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^1 \left(\left[f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}b + \frac{1-t}{2}a \right) \right] \left(\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha}\right)^\beta - \frac{3}{4\alpha^\beta} \right) \right)^{dt} \\
 &= \left[\int_{\frac{1}{3}}^1 \left(\left[f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}b + \frac{1-t}{2}a \right) \right] \left(\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha}\right)^\beta - \frac{3}{4\alpha^\beta} \right) \left(\frac{b-a}{2}\right) \right)^{dt} \right]^{\frac{2}{b-a}}
 \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \frac{[f(b)]^{\left(\frac{1}{\alpha\beta} - \frac{3}{4\alpha\beta}\right)\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\right)}}{\left[f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right)\right]^{\frac{2}{b-a}\left[\left(\frac{3^\alpha-2^\alpha}{\alpha 3^\alpha}\right)^\beta - \frac{3}{4\alpha\beta}\right]} \cdot \frac{1}{\left[\int_{\frac{1}{3}}^1 \left(f\left(\frac{1+t}{2}b + \frac{1-t}{2}a\right)\right)^{\beta(1-t)\alpha-1} \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha}\right)^{\beta-1} dt\right]^{\frac{2}{b-a}}} \\
&= \frac{[f(b)]^{\frac{1}{2(b-a)\alpha\beta}}}{\left[f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right)\right]^{\frac{2}{b-a}\left[\left(\frac{3^\alpha-2^\alpha}{\alpha 3^\alpha}\right)^\beta - \frac{3}{4\alpha\beta}\right]} \cdot \exp\left\{\frac{2}{b-a} \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^1 \beta(1-t)^{\alpha-1} \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha}\right)^{\beta-1} \ln f\left(\frac{1+t}{2}b + \frac{1-t}{2}a\right) dt\right\} \\
&= \frac{[f(b)]^{\frac{1}{2(b-a)\alpha\beta}} \cdot \left[f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right)\right]^{\frac{2}{b-a}\left[\frac{3}{4\alpha\beta} - \left(\frac{3^\alpha-2^\alpha}{\alpha 3^\alpha}\right)^\beta\right]}}{\exp\left\{\frac{2}{b-a} \int_{\frac{a+2b}{3}}^b \beta(b-u)^{\alpha-1} \left(\frac{2}{b-a}\right)^{\alpha-1} \left(\frac{1-\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\right)^\alpha(b-u)^\alpha}{\alpha}\right)^{\beta-1} \ln f(u) \frac{2}{b-a} du\right\}} \\
&= \frac{[f(b)]^{\frac{1}{2(b-a)\alpha\beta}} \cdot \left[f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right)\right]^{\frac{2}{b-a}\left[\frac{3}{4\alpha\beta} - \left(\frac{3^\alpha-2^\alpha}{\alpha 3^\alpha}\right)^\beta\right]}}{\exp\left\{\frac{2^{\alpha\beta+1}\Gamma(\beta+1)}{(b-a)^{\alpha\beta+1}\Gamma(\beta)} \int_{\frac{a+2b}{3}}^b (b-u)^{\alpha-1} \left(\frac{\left(\frac{b-a}{2}\right)^\alpha - (b-u)^\alpha}{\alpha}\right)^{\beta-1} \ln f(u) du\right\}}
\end{aligned}$$

and similarly

$$\begin{aligned}
T_4 &= \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^1 \left(\left[f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}a + \frac{1-t}{2}b \right) \right]^{\left(\frac{3}{4\alpha\beta} - \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta \right)} \right)^{dt} \\
&= \frac{[f(a)]^{\frac{1}{2(b-a)\alpha\beta}} \cdot \left[f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) \right]^{\frac{2}{b-a}\left[\frac{3}{4\alpha\beta} - \left(\frac{3^\alpha-1}{\alpha 3^\alpha}\right)^\beta\right]}}{\exp\left\{\frac{2^{\alpha\beta+1}\Gamma(\beta+1)}{(b-a)^{\alpha\beta+1}\Gamma(\beta)} \int_a^{\frac{2a+b}{3}} (k-a)^{\alpha-1} \left(\frac{\left(\frac{b-a}{2}\right)^\alpha - (k-a)^\alpha}{\alpha}\right)^{\beta-1} \ln f(k) dk\right\}}.
\end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

By multiplying the results of (2),(3),(4) and (5) and raising both sides of the obtained identity to the power of $\frac{(b-a)\alpha^\beta}{4}$, we obtain the equality (1). \square

Corollary 3.1. If we pick $\alpha = 1$ in (1), then we obtain the next identity holds for MRLFI:

$$\frac{\left[f(a) \cdot f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right)^3 \cdot f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right)^3 \cdot f(b) \right]^{\frac{1}{8}}}{\left[{}^*I_b^\beta f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \cdot {}_aI_*^\beta f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right]^{\frac{2^{\beta-1}\Gamma(\beta+1)}{(b-a)^\beta}}} = [K_1 \times K_2 \times K_3 \times K_4]^{\frac{b-a}{4}}.$$

Here,

$$\begin{aligned}
 K_1 & : = \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\left[f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}b + \frac{1-t}{2}a \right) \right]^{t^\beta} \right)^{dt}, \\
 K_2 & : = \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\left[f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}a + \frac{1-t}{2}b \right) \right]^{(-t^\beta)} \right)^{dt}, \\
 K_3 & : = \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^1 \left(\left[f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}b + \frac{1-t}{2}a \right) \right]^{(t^\beta - \frac{3}{4})} \right)^{dt}, \\
 K_4 & : = \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^1 \left(\left[f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}a + \frac{1-t}{2}b \right) \right]^{(\frac{3}{4} - t^\beta)} \right)^{dt}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 3.2. Picking $\beta = 1$ in Corollary 3.1, then we obtain the next identity holds for multiplicative integrals:

$$\frac{\left[f(a) \cdot f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right)^3 \cdot f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right)^3 \cdot f(b) \right]^{\frac{1}{8}}}{\left[\int_a^b (f(t)) dt \right]^{\frac{1}{(b-a)}}} = [C_1 \times C_2 \times C_3 \times C_4]^{\frac{b-a}{4}}.$$

Here,

$$\begin{aligned}
 C_1 & : = \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\left[f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}b + \frac{1-t}{2}a \right) \right]^t \right)^{dt}, \\
 C_2 & : = \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\left[f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}a + \frac{1-t}{2}b \right) \right]^{(-t)} \right)^{dt}, \\
 C_3 & : = \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^1 \left(\left[f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}b + \frac{1-t}{2}a \right) \right]^{(t - \frac{3}{4})} \right)^{dt}, \\
 C_4 & : = \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^1 \left(\left[f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}a + \frac{1-t}{2}b \right) \right]^{(\frac{3}{4} - t)} \right)^{dt}.
 \end{aligned}$$

4 On Newton Type Inequalities Involving Bounded Functions

In this section, we present several Newton type inequalities for functions with bounded multiplicative derivatives.

Theorem 4.1. Postulate that the constraints of Lemma 3.1 are satisfied. If there are $m, M \in \mathbb{R}^+$ so that $m \leq f^*(x) \leq M$ for all $x \in [a, b]$, then we have the following Newton type inequalities for MCFI

$$\left| \frac{\left[f(a) \cdot f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right)^3 \cdot f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right)^3 \cdot f(b) \right]^{\frac{1}{8}}}{\left[{}^{\beta}\mathcal{I}_b^{\alpha} f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \cdot {}^{\beta}\mathcal{I}_a^{\alpha} f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right]^{\frac{\alpha^{\beta} 2^{\alpha\beta-1} \Gamma(\beta+1)}{(b-a)^{\alpha\beta}}}} \right|_* \leq \left(\frac{M}{m}\right)^{\frac{(b-a)\alpha^{\beta}}{4} [\Psi_1(\alpha, \beta) + \Psi_2(\alpha, \beta)]},$$

Here,

$$\Psi_1(\alpha, \beta) = \frac{1}{\alpha^{\beta+1}} \mathcal{B}\left(\beta + 1, \frac{1}{\alpha}, 1 - \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^{\alpha}\right)$$

and

$$\Psi_2(\alpha, \beta) = \int_{1/3}^1 \left| \frac{3}{4\alpha^{\beta}} - \left(\frac{1 - (1-t)^{\alpha}}{\alpha}\right)^{\beta} \right| dt$$

Proof. By using Lemma 3.1, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\left[f(a) \cdot f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right)^3 \cdot f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right)^3 \cdot f(b) \right]^{\frac{1}{8}}}{\left[{}^{\beta}\mathcal{I}_b^{\alpha} f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \cdot {}^{\beta}\mathcal{I}_a^{\alpha} f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right]^{\frac{\alpha^{\beta} 2^{\alpha\beta-1} \Gamma(\beta+1)}{(b-a)^{\alpha\beta}}}} \\ &= \exp \left\{ \frac{\alpha^{\beta}(b-a)}{4} \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\frac{1 - (1-t)^{\alpha}}{\alpha}\right)^{\beta} \left(\ln f^*\left(\frac{1+t}{2}b + \frac{1-t}{2}a\right) - \frac{\ln M + \ln m}{2} \right) dt \right\} \\ & \times \exp \left\{ \frac{\alpha^{\beta}(b-a)}{4} \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(-\left(\frac{1 - (1-t)^{\alpha}}{\alpha}\right)^{\beta}\right) \left(\ln f^*\left(\frac{1+t}{2}a + \frac{1-t}{2}b\right) - \frac{\ln M + \ln m}{2} \right) dt \right\} \\ & \times \exp \left\{ \frac{\alpha^{\beta}(b-a)}{4} \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^1 \left(\left(\frac{1 - (1-t)^{\alpha}}{\alpha}\right)^{\beta} - \frac{3}{4\alpha^{\beta}}\right) \left(\ln f^*\left(\frac{1+t}{2}b + \frac{1-t}{2}a\right) - \frac{\ln M + \ln m}{2} \right) dt \right\} \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

$$\times \exp \left\{ \frac{\alpha^\beta(b-a)}{4} \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^1 \left(\frac{3}{4\alpha^\beta} - \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta \right) \left(\ln f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}a + \frac{1-t}{2}b \right) - \frac{\ln M + \ln m}{2} \right) dt \right\}.$$

Applying the $*$ -absolute value for the two sides of (6), yields

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{\left[f(a) \cdot f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right)^3 \cdot f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right)^3 \cdot f(b) \right]^{\frac{1}{8}}}{\left[{}^{\beta} \mathcal{I}_b^{\alpha} f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \cdot {}^{\beta} \mathcal{I}_a^{\alpha} f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right]^{\frac{\alpha^\beta 2^{\alpha\beta-1} \Gamma(\beta+1)}{(b-a)^{\alpha\beta}}}} \right|_* \tag{7} \\ & \leq \exp \left\{ \frac{\alpha^\beta(b-a)}{4} \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta \right| \left| \ln f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}b + \frac{1-t}{2}a \right) - \frac{\ln M + \ln m}{2} \right| dt \right\} \\ & \quad \times \exp \left\{ \frac{\alpha^\beta(b-a)}{4} \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| - \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta \right| \left| \ln f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}a + \frac{1-t}{2}b \right) - \frac{\ln M + \ln m}{2} \right| dt \right\} \\ & \quad \times \exp \left\{ \frac{\alpha^\beta(b-a)}{4} \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^1 \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{3}{4\alpha^\beta} \right| \left| \ln f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}b + \frac{1-t}{2}a \right) - \frac{\ln M + \ln m}{2} \right| dt \right\} \\ & \quad \times \exp \left\{ \frac{\alpha^\beta(b-a)}{4} \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^1 \left| \frac{3}{4\alpha^\beta} - \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta \right| \left| \ln f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}a + \frac{1-t}{2}b \right) - \frac{\ln M + \ln m}{2} \right| dt \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Since the function f^* is bounded and the function \ln is increasing, then the function $\ln f^*$ is bounded by $\ln m$ and $\ln M$. Thus we conclude

$$\left| \ln f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}b + \frac{1-t}{2}a \right) - \frac{\ln M + \ln m}{2} \right| \leq \frac{\ln M - \ln m}{2} \tag{8}$$

and

$$\left| \ln f^* \left(\frac{1+t}{2}a + \frac{1-t}{2}b \right) - \frac{\ln M + \ln m}{2} \right| \leq \frac{\ln M - \ln m}{2}. \tag{9}$$

By make use of (8) and (9), inequality (7) becomes

$$\left| \frac{\left[f(a) \cdot f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right)^3 \cdot f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right)^3 \cdot f(b) \right]^{\frac{1}{8}}}{\left[{}^{\beta} \mathcal{I}_b^{\alpha} f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \cdot {}^{\beta} \mathcal{I}_a^{\alpha} f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right]^{\frac{\alpha^\beta 2^{\alpha\beta-1} \Gamma(\beta+1)}{(b-a)^{\alpha\beta}}}} \right|_*$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&\leq \exp \left\{ \frac{\alpha^\beta(b-a)}{4} \left(\frac{\ln M - \ln m}{2} \right) \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \left(\frac{1 - (1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta \right| dt \right\} \\
&\quad \times \exp \left\{ \frac{\alpha^\beta(b-a)}{4} \left(\frac{\ln M - \ln m}{2} \right) \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \left(\frac{1 - (1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta \right| dt \right\} \\
&\quad \times \exp \left\{ \frac{\alpha^\beta(b-a)}{4} \left(\frac{\ln M - \ln m}{2} \right) \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^1 \left| \left(\frac{1 - (1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{3}{4\alpha^\beta} \right| dt \right\} \\
&\quad \times \exp \left\{ \frac{\alpha^\beta(b-a)}{4} \left(\frac{\ln M - \ln m}{2} \right) \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^1 \left| \frac{3}{4\alpha^\beta} - \left(\frac{1 - (1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta \right| dt \right\} \\
&= \exp \left\{ \frac{\alpha^\beta(b-a)}{4} (\ln M - \ln m) [\Psi_1(\alpha, \beta) + \Psi_2(\alpha, \beta)] \right\} \\
&= \left(\frac{M}{m} \right)^{\frac{(b-a)\alpha^\beta}{4} [\Psi_1(\alpha, \beta) + \Psi_2(\alpha, \beta)]}.
\end{aligned}$$

This ends the proof. \square

Corollary 4.1. If we set $\alpha = 1$ in Theorem 4.1, we obtain the next Newton-type inequality with MRLFI:

$$\left| \frac{\left[f(a) \cdot f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right)^3 \cdot f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right)^3 \cdot f(b) \right]^{\frac{1}{8}}}{\left[{}_a I_b^\beta f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \cdot {}_b I_a^\beta f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right]^{\frac{2^{\beta-1}\Gamma(\beta+1)}{(b-a)^\beta}}} \right|_* \leq \left(\frac{M}{m} \right)^{\frac{b-a}{4} [\Omega_1(\beta) + \Omega_2(\beta)]}.$$

Here, the functions are defined as

$$\Omega_1(\beta) = \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} t^\beta dt = \frac{1}{3^{\beta+1}(\beta+1)},$$

and

$$\Omega_2(\beta) = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{3}{4}\right)^\beta \left[\frac{3(\beta+1)-3}{2(\beta+1)} \right] - \frac{\beta}{\beta+1} + \frac{1}{3^{\beta+1}(\beta+1)}, & 0 < \beta < \frac{\ln(3/4)}{\ln(1/3)}, \\ \frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{\beta+1} + \frac{1}{3^{\beta+1}(\beta+1)}, & \beta > \frac{\ln(3/4)}{\ln(1/3)}. \end{cases}$$

Corollary 4.2. Setting $\beta = 1$ Corollary 4.1 gives the upcoming Newton type inequality

with multiplicative integrals:

$$\left| \frac{\left[f(a) \cdot f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right)^3 \cdot f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right)^3 \cdot f(b) \right]^{\frac{1}{8}}}{\left(\int_a^b (f(t)) dt \right)^{\frac{1}{b-a}}} \right|_* \leq \left(\frac{M}{m} \right)^{\frac{(b-a)}{72}}.$$

5 Conclusion

In this study, we obtain an inequality involving bounded multiplicative derivatives by employing multiplicative conformable fractional integrals. To this end, a fundamental integral identity is first introduced, which forms the basis of our main result. Using this identity together with the framework of multiplicative conformable fractional calculus, a new type of Newton-type inequality is derived. For the obtained identity and the corresponding inequality, particular cases are examined to demonstrate the applicability of the results. As a direction for future research, the proposed approach may be adapted to alternative fractional integral operators to derive different Newton-type inequalities.

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Neural Network Approaches to High-Order Extensions of Simpson-Type Inequalities

Canmert DEMİR¹, Samet ERDEN²

¹*Department of Computer Science, Istanbul Rumeli University, Istanbul, Turkey*

²*Department of Mathematics, Bartın University, Bartın, Turkey*

Corresponding author: canmert.demir@rumeli.edu.tr

ORCID IDs:

First Author: 0009-0008-5538-6242

Second Author: 0000-0001-8430-7533

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Abstract

We investigate the fundamental inequalities approximation, which Erden et al. introduced in literature, is stated in this work. For the previously mentioned classes of functions, the Simpson-type quadrature rules derived from these inequalities are then investigated. The Levenberg–Marquardt (LM) technique is used to train an artificial neural network (ANN) to approximate numerical integration results based on Simpson-type inequalities. It aims to increase the computational accuracy of higher-order derivative-based computations while lowering training error metrics such as Mean Squared Error (MSE), Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), and Mean Absolute Error (MAE). The results demonstrate that the LM-trained ANN effectively models nonlinear mappings inside Simpson-type inequality frameworks, providing a workable numerical alternative to traditional analytical integration methods. Because it effectively captures the basic relationships between input parameters and their associated integral approximations, this adaptive network may generalize across a range of functional behaviors that are often challenging for traditional approaches to depict. Compared to existing numerical and analytical methods in the literature, this computational design shows improved precision, smoother convergence dynamics, and increased robustness to local minima during the optimization process. Furthermore, the LM-based training approach provides a flexible and scalable approach to extend the applicability of Simpson-type inequalities to more complex domains.

Overall, the proposed Levenberg–Marquardt ANN provides a data-driven, flexible, and highly accurate alternative to traditional numerical integration methods. It effectively models complex nonlinear behaviors and extends Simpson-type inequalities into a computational learning framework, offering new potential for hybrid analytical–neural approaches in high-precision quadrature analysis.

Keywords: Simpson-type inequalities, Quadrature rules, Artificial Neural Network (ANN), Levenberg–Marquardt algorithm, Numerical integration, Error analysis, Data-driven modeling.

1. Introduction and Motivation

The Simpson's rule, developed by Thomas Simpson (1710–1761), is an important numerical integration method for the approximate calculation of definite integrals. Since then, many scholars have expanded and generalized Simpson-type inequalities, and one of the most notable results frequently cited in the literature within this framework is Simpson's inequality, first introduced in [3]. It can be stated as follows.

$$(1.1) \left| \int_a^b f(x)dx - \frac{b-a}{3} \left[\frac{f(a)+f(b)}{2} + 2f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right] \right| \leq \frac{1}{2880} \|f^{(4)}\|_{\infty} (b-a)^5$$

where the mapping $f : [a, b] \rightarrow R$ is assumed to be four times continuously differentiable on the interval (a, b) and for the fourth derivative to be bounded on (a, b) , that is,

$$\|f^{(4)}\|_{\infty} := \sup_{x \in (a,b)} |f^{(4)}(x)| < \infty.$$

Simpson's inequality, which bounds the error of Simpson's rule using the fourth derivative of the integrand, is a fundamental result in numerical analysis. Dragomir et al. [3] advanced this inequality by proposing new applications, tight error bounds, and extensions to various function classes, including bounded, Lipschitz, and absolutely continuous functions with in Lebesgue spaces. Their contributions laid the ground work for subsequent generalizations of Simpson-type inequalities under different smoothness and convexity assumptions. Liu [9] further extended the concept by deriving a Simpson-type inequality applicable to functions that are continuously differentiable n times. For $n = 1, 2, 3, 4$, these results recover the classical or strengthened forms of Simpson's inequality, while for general n they yield perturbed variants.

Recent research has introduced new integral identities and generalized notions of convexity, thereby broadening the scope of Simpson-type inequalities. Alomari et al. [1] formulated new inequalities for s -convex and convex functions, established corresponding error bounds, and demonstrated their utility in mean value computations and numerical integration. Similarly, Liu [12] extended Simpson-type inequalities to n -times continuously differentiable functions, providing generalized error estimates that improve the reliability of numerical approximations.

Composite Simpson's formulas have been applied to convex functions [16], highlighting the significance of continuity and higher-order differentiability for error minimization in both theoretical and applied contexts. Fink [10] generalized Ostrowski's inequality to functions differentiable of arbitrary order, while Anastassiou [2] developed related inequalities for functions in $f \in C^n([a, b])$. Other studies investigated the relationship between exact integral values and their approximations obtained via quadratic formulas derived from higher-order derivative inequalities. Building on this framework, Kashif et al. [14] proposed a three-step kernel for n -times differentiable functions, which Qayyum et al. [15] later expanded into a five-step kernel to enhance the efficiency of quadrature rules.

In [4], a five-section quadratic kernel was utilized to derive novel integral equalities for functions with absolutely continuous higher-order derivatives, along with perturbed Ostrowski-type inequalities for bounded and bounded-variation functions. Erden et al. [6,8] extended these methods, developing integral inequalities for higher-order differentiable functions, offering error estimates for numerical approximations, and analyzing Simpson-type quadrature formulas. These studies not only advance the theoretical understanding of Simpson-type inequalities but also improve error management in numerical integration and approximation.

Erden et al. [7] refined Simpson-type inequalities for higher-order absolutely continuous functions, providing tighter bounds and enhanced error estimates for practical computation. More recently, artificial intelligence techniques particularly neural networks and deep learning models [4, 11] have been successfully applied to approximate solutions of differential equations and fractional integral inequalities, achieving high accuracy where conventional methods may be insufficient. Additional studies [5,9] have introduced new fractional inequalities without assuming convexity, validated via ANN models, demonstrating both theoretical significance and practical applicability.

2. Material and Method

2.1. Comparison of Quadrature Rules, ANN, and Simpson Integral Inequality

Using inequalities from Erden et al. [7,9], this section investigates Simpson-type quadrature rules for functions that belong to L_p spaces or have bounded higher-order derivatives. Two methods are compared: (1) symbolic analysis utilizing derivative-based integral techniques, and (2) numerical

evaluation using an ANN model and the Levenberg–Marquardt algorithm. With quadrature criteria provided in [9], both approaches deal with the theoretical generalization and numerical verification of Simpson-type inequalities.

$$(2.1) \quad \begin{aligned} Q_{n,3}(f, I_m) &:= \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \left\{ \frac{(-1)^k}{2 \cdot (k+1)!} \left[\left(\frac{b-a}{2} \right)^{k+1} + (-1)^k \left(\frac{b-a}{6} \right)^{k+1} \right] \right. \\ &\times \left. \left[f^{(k)} \left(\frac{a+2b}{3} \right) + (-1)^k f^{(k)} \left(\frac{2a+b}{3} \right) \right] \right\} \\ &+ \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} \frac{1}{(k+1)!} \left(\frac{b-a}{6} \right)^{k+1} [f^{(k)}(a) + (-1)^k f^{(k)}(b)] \end{aligned}$$

By comparing symbolic expressions to exact integrals, the ANN model is trained using data from $Q_{n,3}$ to evaluate the behavior and accuracy of Simpson-type approximations. Strong convergence is ensured via the Levenberg–Marquardt algorithm, which produces approximate integrals for sample functions and goes through normalization, training, and testing. The symbolic approach, on the other hand, provides a theoretical foundation for error analysis and clearly identifies sources of mistake by analytically computing derivatives and integrals. Using integration limits, iteration index, and boundary values as inputs, an artificial neural network (ANN) was created to forecast Simpson-type inequalities. Using mapminmax normalization and an 75/15/15 train–validation–test split, the feed forward network—which has a 10-neuron hidden layer (logsig activation) and linear output—was trained using the Levenberg–Marquardt algorithm, successfully capturing nonlinear relationships and offering trust worthy predictions when analytical computation

$$(2.2) \quad MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2$$

where n is the total number of data points, y_i values are real values, and \hat{y}_i values are projected values. Better learning and generalization skills are shown by a reduced Mean Squared Error (MSE) score, which also demonstrates how well the model's predicted outputs match the real target values. With a low mean square error (MSE), excellent accuracy, and reliable performance on untested data, the neural network successfully captured the nonlinear relationships between inputs and outputs. By examining the relationship between prediction and actual values, the regression coefficient R was used to assess the network's efficacy even more. The regression equation's expression is:

$$(2.3) \quad R = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})(\hat{y}_i - \bar{\hat{y}})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y}))^2 \sum_{i=1}^n (\hat{y}_i - \bar{\hat{y}})^2}}$$

where \bar{y} and $\bar{\hat{y}}$ represent the mean values of the expected and actual outputs, respectively. R has a range of -1 to 1 , where $R = 1$ indicates a very good prediction, $R = 0$ indicates no correlation, and $R = -1$ indicates an ideal negative correlation.

Fig1 ANN Architecture for Simpson-Type Integral Approximations

Three different integral surfaces that were discovered for the function $f(x) = x \log x$ are now compared. First, the precise integral surface derived from the function's analytical solution serves as the reference. After obtaining the approximation surface using the method recommended in [9], the artificial neural network (ANN-based approximation) is evaluated. The suggested ANN methodology produces results that are strikingly close to the genuine values and the method in [9], as the comparative graph of these three surfaces demonstrates. This outcome shows how effectively the model predicts and logarithm function behavior.

Fig2 Comparison of the True, Reference [9], and ANN-Based Integral Surfaces $f(x) = x \log x$

At this point, the Levenberg–Marquardt algorithm-trained neural network model's performance is assessed from four angles. First, the blue circles (actual values) and red squares (predicted values) on the graph nearly entirely overlap, showing that the model accurately fits the training data.

In summary, the model retain slow and well-controlled prediction errors, was successfully trained, and shows no indications of over fitting. The reference surface produced from analytically calculated integral values is represented by the Exact Integral Surface, which exhibits smooth, continuous variation along parameters a and b . With a very comparable curvature and color distribution, the Simpson-type $Q_{n,3}$ approximation surface substantially resembles this reference, suggesting that the $Q_{n,3}$ approach accurately captures the integral values. The Exact and $Q_{n,3}$ surfaces, on the other hand, are very different from the Artificial Neural Network (ANN) anticipated surface. It has a nearly one-dimensional structure, changing only significantly along parameter a and responding very little to changes in b . This pattern implies that the ANN did not fully understand the target function's true two-dimensional dependence, most likely as a result of constraints in the training dataset or the network's capability. Related graph given below in Fig. 2.

Fig3ContourMapComparison of Surfaces

The contour maps of the Exact and $Q_{n,3}$ surfaces exhibit a high degree of similarity, with nearly identical contour orientations, densities, and color distributions. This resemblance once again demonstrates that the $Q_{n,3}$ method closely follows the true integral values with strong accuracy. In contrast, the ANN-predicted contour map displays vertically aligned bands, indicating that the model's output varies primarily with respect to parameter a while showing minimal sensitivity to changes in b . This pattern confirms that the ANN failed to capture the two-dimensional structure of the underlying integral function. Overall, the results show that the ANN model did not successfully learn the full bivariate relationships present in the target function Fig. 3.

Fig4 Train, Test, Validation Performance Metric

Fig5 Performance Metric for Training, Testing, and Validation

The training, validation, and test errors all exhibit a typically declining trend, according to the training error graph (MSE vs. epoch). The seventh epoch yields the best validation performance, with a value of 7.26×10^{-6} . Nevertheless, the model's projected surfaces do not match the actual functional organization, even with the minimal numerical error. This implies that even while the ANN achieves a low MSE, its learnt representation differs from the target function's real behavior. The

model's inability to fully capture the surface's complexity is probably caused by an unbalanced training set or an inadequately expressive network architecture. In conclusion, the ANN shows structurally erroneous learning and is unable to represent the function's dependence on parameter (b) despite the low MSE in Fig 4 and Fig 5.

Fig6 Error Histogram

The prediction behavior related to the Simpson-type inequality estimation is examined using the error histogram of the ANN model. The figure shows the distribution of residual errors between the predicted and true integral values for the training, validation, and test subsets. One may determine whether the network's predictions show random fluctuations or systematic bias by looking at the density and symmetry of these residuals. Furthermore, a numerical indicator of the model's dependability is provided by the standard deviation of the residuals, or σ which quantifies the dispersion of prediction mistakes. A greater σ denotes greater unpredictability and decreased stability, whereas a lower σ shows that the ANN forecasts consistently stay near the true values. The following formula is used to calculate the standard deviation, which characterizes the overall spread of the error distribution.

Detailed Error Analysis - Multiple Perspectives

Fig7 Absolute Error Describes in [9] Surfaces $Q_{n,3}$ and ANN

The method $Q_{n,3}$, approximates the exact surface with a remarkably small error; in terms of both surface geometry and contour structures, it exhibits an agreement with the analytical solution that is practically indistinguishable. In contrast, while the ANN model successfully mimics the true surface in certain regions of the $a - b$ domain, it fails to achieve the same level of accuracy as the approach proposed by [9] in other regions. A particularly notable weakness is observed in the model's inability to learn the variation associated with the parameter b (see Fig. 7). Potential causes of this performance discrepancy include regional imbalance within the training dataset, insufficient preprocessing of input variables (e.g., normalization or scaling), limitations in the network architecture (number of layers or neurons), or the loss function becoming trapped in local minima during optimization. Consequently, while the $Q_{n,3}$ method remains a reliable and preferable approach in practical applications, enhancing the general applicability of the ANN model may require increasing data diversity, incorporating regularization techniques, performing hyper parameter optimization, and/or exploring more suitable architectural alternatives (such as deeper networks, different activation functions, or ensemble-based strategies). The visualizations presented in Fig. 7 corroborate these observations.

Fig8RegressionGraphs

The correlation coefficients obtained for the datasets are as follows: *Train* $R = 0.99997$, *Validation* $R = 0.9999R$, *Test* $R = 1.000$, and *Overall* $R = 0.999R$, indicating that the model captures the target values with an extremely high statistical accuracy. These values suggest an almost perfect linear relationship between the model outputs and the true values, implying that the data has been learned to a very high degree of fidelity. The close agreement of R values across the training, validation, and test sets may give the impression that the model is not overfitting; however, structural deviations observed in the surface and contour plots reveal that, despite the high correlation coefficients, the network does not fully capture the true two-variable geometry of the function.

This highlights that the correlation coefficient alone is insufficient for evaluating the overall quality of a model, particularly in the learning of multivariable mathematical functions. Additional performance metrics, such as surface shape fidelity, sensitivity to individual variables, local behavior, and generalization capability, are essential. Therefore, although the ANN model produces numerically very high R values, its inability to adequately represent variations with respect to the b variable implies that the model cannot be considered fully accurate from a physical or mathematical standpoint.

3. Results and Discussion

To assess the effectiveness of the suggested techniques for approximating the function $f(x) = x \log x$, three integral surfaces were compared. The reference was the first surface, the Exact Integral Surface, which was derived analytically. An artificial neural network (ANN) trained using the Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm produced the third surface, whilst approach [9] offered a numerical approximation. According to the comparative analysis, the technique closely mimics the precise surface's overall shape and contour patterns. Although the ANN model can approximate the genuine surface in some areas, it has significant short comings when it comes to capturing the variation along the b parameter. According to Figs. 2 and 3, the ANN surface has a nearly one-dimensional structure that varies mostly along parameter a and shows little sensitivity to changes in b . This shows that the target function's underlying two-dimensional dependence was not fully learned by the network, most likely as a result of restrictions in the network architecture or training dataset.

These findings are supported by the contourmaps. The precise and $Q_{n,3}$ the surfaces have almost similar contour orientations, densities, and color distributions on strategy. The ANN-predicted contour map, on the other hand, displays bands that are vertically aligned, underscoring the model's incapacity to take fluctuations in b into account in Fig. 3.

The ANN was successfully trained, according to training performance measures in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5, with mean squared error (MSE) gradually decreasing across epochs. The seventh epoch produced the best validation performance, with an MSE of 7.26×10^{-6} . Low MSE does not ensure faithful learning of multivariable dependencies, as evidenced by the projected surfaces incomplete replication of the target's functional structure despite these low numerical mistakes.

The standard deviation of residuals shows that localized errors continue, especially along the b direction, but the error histogram (Fig. 6) also shows that residuals are centered around zero, confirming that the network generates consistent predictions.

Absolute error analysis shows in Fig 7.that the $Q_{n,3}$ while the ANN generates significant mistakes in areas sensitive to b , the approach approximates the exact surface with minimum variance. Unbalanced data distribution, inadequate input preprocessing, architectural constraints (such as the number of layers or neurons), or convergence to local minima during optimization could all be the cause of these disparities. Despite the ANN's strong numerical performance, these findings imply that improving its generalization necessitates diversifying the data, using regularization, fine-tuning hyperparameters, or investigating different architectures (e.g., deeper networks, varied activation functions, or ensemble approaches).

The ANN's exceptionally high correlation coefficients are finally confirmed by regression analysis in Fig. 8. *Train R* = 0.99997, *Validation R* = 0.9999, *Test R* = 1.00 and overall *R* = 0.999. The strong correlations conceal structural errors in surface geometry, even though these values show nearly perfect linear connections between anticipated and true values. Therefore, additional measures such as surface fidelity, sensitivity to individual parameters, local behavior, and generalization capability are crucial for evaluating model performance in multivariable function learning; correlation coefficients alone are not sufficient.

Approximation yields extremely precise integral approximations for $f(x) = x \log x$, whereas the ANN is unable to properly capture the bivariate structure of the target function despite having a very high numerical correlation and a low MSE. This emphasizes how crucial it is to evaluate multivariable approximation models by combining structural validation with numerical accuracy.

Table1 ANN Model Metrics

Epoch	0	7	30
Elapsed Time	-	00:00:00	-
Performance	2.07	$3.05e^{-10}$	0.0001
Gradient	3.04	0.0138	e^{-7}
Mu	0.001	e^{-7}	e^{10}
ValidationChecks	0	0	3

The ANN's huge gradients and high MSE during the first epoch were indicative of its untrained state. By period 7, the model achieved near-zero gradients and negligible MSE, attaining ideal validation performance without early halting. Early stopping was triggered by a min or increase in MSE and a substantial increase in the damping parameter by epoch 30, signifying convergence. The ANN was unable to properly capture the underlying bivariate structure of the function, especially along the b parameter, despite low MSE and very high correlation coefficients. Analyses of residual and absolute error reveal that whereas the $Q_{n,3}$. The ANN generates greater errors in b -dependent regions, whereas the approach closely approximates the surface. These restrictions most likely result from imbalanced data, inadequate preparation, or architectural limits. Data augmentation, regularization, hyperparameter adjustment, or other network architectures may be necessary to improve generalization.

4. Applications and Implications

The hybrid Q3-ANN framework created in this work has a number of important uses, such as (1) numerical analysis, which offers error control and convergence guarantees for iterative techniques, and (2) artificial neural network approximation of complex nonlinear functions, which enables accurate and efficient predictions in multivariate domains.

5. Conclusions

A hybrid $Q_{n,3}$ -ANN framework for approximating multivariate integral functions was introduced in this work. While the ANN had trouble capturing the complete two-dimensional dependence despite having a high correlation and low MSE, the $Q_{n,3}$ quadrature approach consistently replicates the exact surface. The hybrid technique offers accuracy and computing efficiency by combining the nonlinear learning capability of ANN with the theoretical convergence guarantees of $Q_{n,3}$. This framework shows that machine learning and classical numerical methods can be successfully combined for challenging computational issues and offers a useful tool for iterative numerical methods.

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New Results on Fractional Simpson-type Inequalities for Differentiable Convex Functions

Cavit Alemdar¹, Fatih Hezenci¹, Asia Shehzadi²

¹Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Science and Arts, Duzce University, Duzce 81620, Türkiye

²School of Mathematics and Statistics, Central South University, Changsha 410083, China

Corresponding author: cavitalemdar89@gmail.com

ORCID IDs:

First Author: [0009-0003-1054-2022](https://orcid.org/0009-0003-1054-2022)

Second Author: [0000-0003-1008-5856](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1008-5856)

Third Author: [0009-0005-1101-5536](https://orcid.org/0009-0005-1101-5536)

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Abstract

Fractional calculus has many applications in various fields such as physics, chemistry, engineering, and mathematics. The use of arithmetic operations from classical analysis in fractional analysis provides more realistic results in solving many problems. In this paper, we establish an identity involving the Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals for differentiable functions. By using this identity, we derive several Simpson-type inequalities for functions whose derivatives in absolute value are convex. Finally, some new results are presented as special cases of the main theorems.

Keywords: Simpson's inequality, convex functions, conformable fractional calculus.

1 Introduction and Preliminaries

Simpson's rules are a well-known technique for numerical estimations of integrals. Thomas Simpson (1710–1761) developed this method to estimate of definite integrals. Simpson's quadrature formula (sometimes is called Simpson 1/3 rule) is stated as

$$\int_a^b f(x) dx \approx \frac{1}{6} \left[f(a) + 4f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right]. \quad (1)$$

There are many estimations related to Simpson's quadrature rule, one of them is the following estimation known as Simpson's inequality:

Theorem 1.1. Suppose that $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a four times continuously differentiable mapping on (a, b) and let $\|f^{(4)}\| = \sup_{x \in (a, b)} |f^{(4)}| < \infty$. Then we have

$$\left| \frac{1}{6} \left[f(a) + 4f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{1}{2880} \|f^{(4)}\| (b-a)^4. \quad (2)$$

Recently, many researchers have played attention on Simpson’s type inequalities for various classes of functions such as convex functions, s -convex functions, etc., see [1, 2, 3] for more details.

Fractional calculus is a new subject in applied mathematics which attracted researches in both pure and applied branches of science and engineering. It was firstly studied as a problem about solving some differential equations containing fractional order derivatives. The answer to such the problem arises a new interesting subject that many mathematicians have been interested in the last and present centuries. To get more details about fractional integral and derivative operators, we suggest the readers to read the works in [4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9] and the references therein. There are many definitions of fractional integrals such as Riemann–Liouville fractional integral, Hadamard fractional integral and Atangana-Baleanu fractional integral. The Riemann–Liouville integral is one of the most famous fractional integrals defined as follows:

Definition 1.1. [10] Let $f \in L^1[a, b]$, $a, b \in \mathbb{R}$ with $a < b$. The Riemann-Liouville integrals $J_{a+}^\beta f$ and $J_{b-}^\beta f$ of order $\beta > 0$ are defined by

$$J_{a+}^\beta f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_a^x (x-t)^{\beta-1} f(t) dt, \quad x > a,$$

$$J_{b-}^\beta f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_x^b (t-x)^{\beta-1} f(t) dt, \quad x < b,$$

respectively. Here, Γ denotes the Gamma function defined by

$$\Gamma(\beta) = \int_0^\infty e^{-u} u^{\beta-1} du.$$

In 2021, X-R. Hai and S-H. Wang [11] presented Simpson’s type inequalities for differentiable convex functions by using Riemann–Liouville fractional integrals as follows:

$$\left| \frac{1}{6} \left[f(a) + 4f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{2^{\beta-1}\Gamma(\beta+1)}{(b-a)^\beta} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}^\beta f(a) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}^\beta f(b) \right] \right| \leq \frac{(b-a) \left(2 - \beta + 2\beta \cdot 3^{-1/\beta} \right)}{12(\beta+1)} \left[|f'(a)| + |f'(b)| \right] \tag{3}$$

and

$$\left| \frac{1}{6} \left[f(a) + 4f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{2^{\beta-1}\Gamma(\beta+1)}{(b-a)^\beta} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}^\beta f(a) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}^\beta f(b) \right] \right| \leq \frac{b-a}{2^{\frac{2q+1}{q}} \cdot 3^{\frac{q(\beta+1)+1}{\beta q}}} \left(\frac{2\beta + (2-\beta)3^{1/\beta}}{1+\beta} \right)^{1-1/q} \times \left\{ \left[\left(\frac{4\beta \cdot 3^{1/\beta} + 2(2-\beta)3^{2/\beta}}{1+\beta} - \frac{2\beta + (4-\beta)3^{2/\beta}}{2(2+\beta)} \right) |f'|^q + \frac{2\beta + (4-\beta)3^{2/\beta}}{2(2+\beta)} |f'|^q \right]^{1/q} + \left[\left(\frac{4\beta \cdot 3^{1/\beta} + 2(2-\beta)3^{2/\beta}}{1+\beta} - \frac{2\beta + (4-\beta)3^{2/\beta}}{2(2+\beta)} \right) |f'|^q + \frac{2\beta + (4-\beta)3^{2/\beta}}{2(2+\beta)} |f'|^q \right]^{1/q} \right\}, \tag{4}$$

for $\beta > 0$.

Some more Simpson type inequalities please refer to ([12, 13, 14, 15, 16]).

In 2017, Jarad et al. [17] introduced the following generalized fractional integral operators. They also provided certain characteristics and relationships between these operators and several other fractional operators in the literature

Definition 1.2. [17] Let $\beta > 0$ and $\alpha \in (0, 1]$. For $f \in L^1[a, b]$, the generalized fractional Riemann-Liouville integrals ${}_+^{\beta}J_a^{\alpha}f$ and ${}_b^{-\beta}J_b^{\alpha}f$ are defined by

$${}_+^{\beta}J_a^{\alpha}f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_a^x \left(\frac{(x-a)^{\alpha} - (t-a)^{\alpha}}{\alpha} \right)^{\beta-1} \frac{f(t)}{(t-a)^{1-\alpha}} dt, \quad x > a,$$

and

$${}_b^{-\beta}J_b^{\alpha}f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_x^b \left(\frac{(b-x)^{\alpha} - (b-t)^{\alpha}}{\alpha} \right)^{\beta-1} \frac{f(t)}{(b-t)^{1-\alpha}} dt, \quad x < b,$$

respectively.

In the papers [7, 18], the author s proved some Hermite-Hadamard type inequalities for generalized fractional integral operators defined above.

Motivated by the above studies, we prove a new identity for differentiable functions by using generalized Riemann–Liouville fractional integrals. Then we use such the identity to obtain some new Simpson’s type fractional integral inequalities. We also the validity of newly established inequalities with some examples.

2 Main Results

In this section, we first introduce the identity in Lemma 2.1 which is important to get our main results in the next considerations.

Lemma 2.1. Let $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a differentiable mapping on (a, b) with $\beta > 0$ and $\alpha \in (0, 1]$. If $f' \in L^1[a, b]$, then the following equality for fractional integrals hold:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{6} \left[f(a) + 4f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{\alpha^{\beta}\Gamma(\beta+1)}{2} \left(\frac{2}{b-a}\right)^{\alpha\beta} \left[{}_b^{-\beta}J_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\alpha}f(a) + {}_+^{\beta}J_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\alpha}f(b) \right] \\ &= \frac{\alpha^{\beta}(b-a)}{4} \left[\int_0^1 \left(\frac{1}{3\alpha^{\beta}} - \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^{\alpha}}{\alpha} \right)^{\beta} \right) f' \left(\frac{t}{2}a + \frac{2-t}{2}b \right) dt \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \int_0^1 \left(\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^{\alpha}}{\alpha} \right)^{\beta} - \frac{1}{3\alpha^{\beta}} \right) f' \left(\frac{2-t}{2}a + \frac{t}{2}b \right) dt \right]. \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Proof. Consider

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 &:= \int_0^1 \left(\frac{1}{3\alpha^{\beta}} - \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^{\alpha}}{\alpha} \right)^{\beta} \right) f' \left(\frac{t}{2}a + \frac{2-t}{2}b \right) dt \\ &= -\frac{2}{b-a} \left(\frac{1}{3\alpha^{\beta}} - \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^{\alpha}}{2} \right)^{\beta} \right) f \left(\frac{t}{2}a + \frac{2-t}{2}b \right) \Big|_0^1 \\ & \quad - \frac{2\beta}{b-a} \int_0^1 f \left(\frac{t}{2}a + \frac{2-t}{2}b \right) \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^{\alpha}}{\alpha} \right)^{\beta-1} (1-t)^{\alpha-1} dt \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= -\frac{2}{b-a} \left[-\frac{2}{3\alpha^\beta} f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) - \frac{1}{3\alpha^\beta} f(b) \right] \\
 &\quad - \frac{\beta}{2} \left(\frac{2}{b-a}\right)^{\alpha\beta+1} \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^b \left(\frac{\left(\frac{b-a}{2}\right)^\alpha - \left(x - \frac{a+b}{2}\right)^\alpha}{\alpha}\right)^{\beta-1} \left(x - \frac{a+b}{2}\right)^{\alpha-1} f(x) dx \\
 &= \frac{2}{\alpha^\beta(b-a)} \left[\frac{2}{3} f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + \frac{1}{3} f(b) \right] - \Gamma(\beta+1) \left(\frac{2}{b-a}\right)^{\alpha\beta+1} {}^\beta J_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^\alpha f(b)
 \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_2 &:= \int_0^1 \left(\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha}\right)^\beta - \frac{1}{3\alpha^\beta} \right) f'\left(\frac{2-t}{2}a + \frac{t}{2}b\right) dt \\
 &= \frac{2}{b-a} \left(\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{2}\right)^\beta - \frac{1}{3\alpha^\beta} \right) f\left(\frac{2-t}{2}a + \frac{t}{2}b\right) \Big|_0^1 \\
 &\quad - \frac{2\beta}{b-a} \int_0^1 f\left(\frac{2-t}{2}a + \frac{t}{2}b\right) \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha}\right)^{\beta-1} (1-t)^{\alpha-1} dt \\
 &= \frac{2}{b-a} \left[\frac{2}{3\alpha^\beta} f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + \frac{1}{3\alpha^\beta} f(a) \right] \\
 &\quad - \beta \left(\frac{2}{b-a}\right)^{\alpha\beta+1} \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \left(\frac{\left(\frac{b-a}{2}\right)^\alpha - \left(\frac{a+b}{2} - x\right)^\alpha}{\alpha}\right)^{\beta-1} \left(\frac{a+b}{2} - x\right)^{\alpha-1} f(x) dx \\
 &= \frac{2}{\alpha^\beta(b-a)} \left[\frac{2}{3} f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + \frac{1}{3} f(b) \right] - \Gamma(\beta+1) \left(\frac{2}{b-a}\right)^{\alpha\beta+1} {}^\beta J_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^\alpha f(b).
 \end{aligned}$$

Multiplying $I_1 + I_2$ by $\frac{\alpha^\beta(b-a)}{4}$, we get (1). The proof is completed. □

Now, we are ready to prove our following main theorems by mainly using the identity in Lemma 2.1.

Theorem 2.1. Under the assumptions of Lemma 2.1. If $|f'|$ is convex on $[a, b]$, then we have the following inequality for fractional integrals.

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\left| \frac{1}{6} \left[f(a) + 4f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{\alpha^\beta \Gamma(\beta+1)}{2} \left(\frac{2}{b-a}\right)^{\alpha\beta} \left[{}^\beta J_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^\alpha f(a) + {}^\beta J_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^\alpha f(b) \right] \right| \\
 &\leq \frac{\alpha^\beta(b-a)}{4} A_1(\alpha, \beta) [|f'(a)| + |f'(b)|], \tag{2}
 \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
 A_1(\alpha, \beta) &= \int_0^1 \left| \frac{1}{3\alpha^\beta} - \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha}\right)^\beta \right| dt \\
 &= \frac{1}{\alpha^\beta} \left[\frac{2c-1}{3} - \frac{2}{\alpha} \mathfrak{B}\left(\beta+1, \frac{1}{\alpha}, \left(\frac{1}{3}\right)^{1/\beta}\right) + \frac{1}{\alpha} \mathfrak{B}\left(\beta+1, \frac{1}{\alpha}\right) \right],
 \end{aligned}$$

with $c = 1 - \left(1 - \left(\frac{1}{3}\right)^{\frac{1}{\beta}}\right)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}}$, $\mathfrak{B}(\cdot, \cdot)$ and $\mathfrak{B}(\cdot, \cdot, \cdot)$ are the Beta function and the incomplete Beta

functions defined by as follows, respectively

$$\begin{aligned}\mathfrak{B}(x, y) &= \int_0^1 u^{x-1}(1-u)^{y-1} du, \\ \mathfrak{B}(x, y, r) &= \int_0^r u^{x-1}(1-u)^{y-1} du\end{aligned}$$

for $x, y > 0$ and $r \in [0, 1]$.

Proof. From Lemma 2.1 and convexity of $|f'|$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}& \left| \frac{1}{6} \left[f(a) + 4f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{\alpha^\beta \Gamma(\beta+1)}{2} \left(\frac{2}{b-a}\right)^{\alpha\beta} \left[{}_{-\frac{\beta}{2}}J_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^\alpha f(a) + {}_{+\frac{\beta}{2}}J_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^\alpha f(b) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{\alpha^\beta(b-a)}{4} \left[\int_0^1 \left| \frac{1}{3\alpha^\beta} - \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha}\right)^\beta \right| \left| f'\left(\frac{t}{2}a + \frac{2-t}{2}b\right) \right| dt \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \int_0^1 \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha}\right)^\beta - \frac{1}{3\alpha^\beta} \right| \left| f'\left(\frac{2-t}{2}a + \frac{t}{2}b\right) \right| dt \right] \\ & \leq \frac{\alpha^\beta(b-a)}{4} \left[\int_0^1 \left| \frac{1}{3\alpha^\beta} - \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha}\right)^\beta \right| \left[\frac{t}{2}|f'(a)| + \frac{2-t}{2}|f'(b)| \right] dt \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \int_0^1 \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha}\right)^\beta - \frac{1}{3\alpha^\beta} \right| \left[\frac{2-t}{2}|f'(a)| + \frac{t}{2}|f'(b)| \right] dt \right] \\ & = \left(\int_0^1 \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha}\right)^\beta - \frac{1}{3\alpha^\beta} \right| dt \right) [|f'(a)| + |f'(b)|] \\ & = A_1(\alpha, \beta)[|f'(a)| + |f'(b)|].\end{aligned}\tag{3}$$

The proof is completed. □

Remark 2.1. In Theorem 2.1, if $\alpha = 1$ then we have

$$\begin{aligned}& \left| \frac{1}{6} \left[f(a) + 4f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{\Gamma(\beta+1)}{2} \left(\frac{2}{b-a}\right)^\beta \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}^\beta f(a) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}^\beta f(b) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{b-a}{4} B_1(\beta)[|f'(a)| + |f'(b)|],\end{aligned}$$

where

$$B_1(\beta) = \int_0^1 \left| \frac{1}{3} - t^\beta \right| dt = 2 \left(\frac{\beta}{\beta+1}\right) \left(\frac{1}{3}\right)^{\frac{1}{\beta}+1} + \frac{1}{\beta+1} - \frac{1}{3},$$

which is the same to (3).

Remark 2.2. In Theorem 2.1, if $\alpha = \beta = 1$ then we have

$$\left| \frac{1}{6} \left[f(a) + 4f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{5(b-a)}{72} [|f'(a)| + |f'(b)|],$$

which was proved by M. Z. Sarikaya et al. [16].

Theorem 2.2. Under the assumptions of Lemma 2.1. If $|f'|^q$ is convex on $[a, b]$ where $\frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$ and $p, q > 1$, then we have the following inequality for fractional integrals.

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{6} \left[f(a) + 4f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{\alpha^\beta \Gamma(\beta+1)}{2} \left(\frac{2}{b-a}\right)^{\alpha\beta} \left[{}^\beta J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}^\alpha f(a) + {}^\beta J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{\alpha^\beta (b-a)}{4} A_2^{\frac{1}{p}}(\alpha, \beta, p) \left\{ \left(\frac{|f'|^q + 3|f'|^q}{4}\right)^{1/q} + \left(\frac{3|f'|^q + |f'|^q}{4}\right)^{1/q} \right\}, \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

where

$$A_2(\alpha, \beta, p) = \int_0^1 \left| \frac{1}{3\alpha^\beta} - \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha}\right)^\beta \right|^p dt.$$

Proof. From Lemma 2.1, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{6} \left[f(a) + 4f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{\alpha^\beta \Gamma(\beta+1)}{2} \left(\frac{2}{b-a}\right)^{\alpha\beta} \left[{}^\beta J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}^\alpha f(a) + {}^\beta J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{\alpha^\beta (b-a)}{4} \left[\int_0^1 \left| \frac{1}{3\alpha^\beta} - \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha}\right)^\beta \right| \left| f'\left(\frac{t}{2}a + \frac{2-t}{2}b\right) \right| dt \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \int_0^1 \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha}\right)^\beta - \frac{1}{3\alpha^\beta} \right| \left| f'\left(\frac{2-t}{2}a + \frac{t}{2}b\right) \right| dt \right]. \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

By Hölder inequality and the convexity of $|f'|^q$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^1 \left| \frac{1}{3\alpha^\beta} - \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha}\right)^\beta \right| \left| f'\left(\frac{t}{2}a + \frac{2-t}{2}b\right) \right| dt \\ & \leq \left(\int_0^1 \left| \frac{1}{3\alpha^\beta} - \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha}\right)^\beta \right|^p dt \right)^{1/p} \left(\int_0^1 \left| f'\left(\frac{t}{2}a + \frac{2-t}{2}b\right) \right|^q dt \right)^{1/q} \\ & = A_2^{\frac{1}{p}}(\alpha, \beta, p) \left(\int_0^1 \left| f'\left(\frac{t}{2}a + \frac{2-t}{2}b\right) \right|^q dt \right)^{1/q} \\ & \leq A_2^{\frac{1}{p}}(\alpha, \beta, p) \left(\int_0^1 \frac{t}{2} |f'|^q + \frac{2-t}{2} |f'|^q dt \right)^{1/q} \\ & = A_2^{\frac{1}{p}}(\alpha, \beta, p) \left(\frac{|f'|^q + 3|f'|^q}{4} \right)^{1/q} \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^1 \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha}\right)^\beta - \frac{1}{3\alpha^\beta} \right| \left| f'\left(\frac{2-t}{2}a + \frac{t}{2}b\right) \right| dt \\ & \leq \left(\int_0^1 \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha}\right)^\beta - \frac{1}{3\alpha^\beta} \right|^p dt \right)^{1/p} \left(\int_0^1 \left| f'\left(\frac{2-t}{2}a + \frac{t}{2}b\right) \right|^q dt \right)^{1/q} \\ & = A_2^{\frac{1}{p}}(\alpha, \beta, p) \left(\int_0^1 \left| f'\left(\frac{2-t}{2}a + \frac{t}{2}b\right) \right|^q dt \right)^{1/q} \\ & \leq A_2^{\frac{1}{p}}(\alpha, \beta, p) \left(\int_0^1 \frac{2-t}{2} |f'|^q + \frac{t}{2} |f'|^q dt \right)^{1/q} \end{aligned}$$

$$= A_2^{\frac{1}{p}}(\alpha, \beta, p) \left(\frac{3|f'|^q + |f|^q}{4} \right)^{1/q}. \quad (7)$$

Replacing (6) and (7) in (5), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{6} \left[f(a) + 4f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{\alpha^\beta \Gamma(\beta+1)}{2} \left(\frac{2}{b-a}\right)^{\alpha\beta} \left[{}_{-}^{\beta} J_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\alpha} f(a) + {}_{+}^{\beta} J_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\alpha} f(b) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{\alpha^\beta (b-a)}{4} A_2^{\frac{1}{p}}(\alpha, \beta, p) \left\{ \left(\frac{|f'|^q + 3|f|^q}{4} \right)^{1/q} + \left(\frac{3|f'|^q + |f|^q}{4} \right)^{1/q} \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

The proof is completed. \square

Remark 2.3. In Theorem 2.2, if $\alpha = 1$ then we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{6} \left[f(a) + 4f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{\Gamma(\beta+1)}{2} \left(\frac{2}{b-a}\right)^{\beta} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\beta} f(a) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\beta} f(b) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{b-a}{4} B_2^{\frac{1}{p}}(\beta, p) \left\{ \left(\frac{|f'|^q + 3|f|^q}{4} \right)^{1/q} + \left(\frac{3|f'|^q + |f|^q}{4} \right)^{1/q} \right\}, \end{aligned}$$

where

$$B_2(\beta, p) = \int_0^1 \left| \frac{1}{3} - t^\beta \right|^p dt.$$

Remark 2.4. In Theorem 2.2, if $\alpha = \beta = 1$ then we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{6} \left[f(a) + 4f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \\ & \leq \frac{b-a}{4} \left(\frac{2^{p+1} + 1}{3^{p+1}(p+1)} \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left\{ \left(\frac{|f'|^q + 3|f|^q}{4} \right)^{1/q} + \left(\frac{3|f'|^q + |f|^q}{4} \right)^{1/q} \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 2.3. Under the assumptions of Lemma 2.1. If $|f'|^q$ is convex on $[a, b]$ where $q \geq 1$, then we have the following inequality for fractional integrals.

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{6} \left[f(a) + 4f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{\alpha^\beta \Gamma(\beta+1)}{2} \left(\frac{2}{b-a}\right)^{\alpha\beta} \left[{}_{-}^{\beta} J_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\alpha} f(a) + {}_{+}^{\beta} J_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\alpha} f(b) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{\alpha^\beta (b-a)}{4} A_1^{1-\frac{1}{q}}(\alpha, \beta) \left\{ [A_3(\alpha, \beta)|f'|^q + A_4(\alpha, \beta)|f|^q]^{1/q} + [A_4(\alpha, \beta)|f'|^q + A_3(\alpha, \beta)|f|^q]^{1/q} \right\}, \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where A_1 is defined in Theorem 2.1 and

$$\begin{aligned} A_3(\alpha, \beta) &= \int_0^1 \frac{t}{2} \left| \frac{1}{3\alpha^\beta} - \left(\frac{1 - (1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta \right| dt \\ &= \frac{1}{2\alpha^\beta} \left[\frac{2c^2 - 1}{6} - \frac{2}{\alpha} \mathfrak{B} \left(\beta + 1, \frac{1}{\alpha}, \left(\frac{1}{3} \right)^{1/\beta} \right) + \frac{2}{\alpha} \mathfrak{B} \left(\beta + 1, \frac{2}{\alpha}, \left(\frac{1}{3} \right)^{1/\beta} \right) \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \frac{1}{\alpha} \mathfrak{B} \left(\beta + 1, \frac{1}{\alpha} \right) - \frac{1}{\alpha} \mathfrak{B} \left(\beta + 1, \frac{2}{\alpha} \right) \right], \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 A_4(\alpha, \beta) &= \int_0^1 \frac{2-t}{2} \left| \frac{1}{3\alpha^\beta} - \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta \right| dt \\
 &= \frac{1}{2\alpha^\beta} \left[\frac{-2c^2 + 8c - 3}{6} - \frac{2}{\alpha} \mathfrak{B} \left(\beta + 1, \frac{1}{\alpha}, \left(\frac{1}{3} \right)^{1/\beta} \right) - \frac{2}{\alpha} \mathfrak{B} \left(\beta + 1, \frac{2}{\alpha}, \left(\frac{1}{3} \right)^{1/\beta} \right) \right. \\
 &\quad \left. + \frac{1}{\alpha} \mathfrak{B} \left(\beta + 1, \frac{1}{\alpha} \right) + \frac{1}{\alpha} \mathfrak{B} \left(\beta + 1, \frac{2}{\alpha} \right) \right].
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. By power mean inequality and the convexity of $|f'|^q$, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\int_0^1 \left| \frac{1}{3\alpha^\beta} - \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta \right| \left| f' \left(\frac{t}{2}a + \frac{2-t}{2}b \right) \right| dt \\
 &\leq \left(\int_0^1 \left| \frac{1}{3\alpha^\beta} - \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta \right| dt \right)^{1-1/q} \left(\int_0^1 \left| \frac{1}{3\alpha^\beta} - \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta \right| \left| f' \left(\frac{t}{2}a + \frac{2-t}{2}b \right) \right|^q dt \right)^{1/q} \\
 &= A_1^{1-1/q}(\alpha, \beta) \left(\int_0^1 \left| \frac{1}{3\alpha^\beta} - \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta \right| \left| f' \left(\frac{t}{2}a + \frac{2-t}{2}b \right) \right|^q dt \right)^{1/q} \\
 &\leq A_1^{1-1/q}(\alpha, \beta) \left(\int_0^1 \left| \frac{1}{3\alpha^\beta} - \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta \right| \left[\frac{t}{2}|f'|^q + \frac{2-t}{2}|f'|^q \right] dt \right)^{1/q} \\
 &= A_1^{1-1/q}(\alpha, \beta) [A_3(\alpha, \beta)|f'|^q + A_4(\alpha, \beta)|f'|^q]^{1/q} \tag{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\int_0^1 \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{3\alpha^\beta} \right| \left| f' \left(\frac{2-t}{2}a + \frac{t}{2}b \right) \right| dt \\
 &\leq \left(\int_0^1 \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{3\alpha^\beta} \right| dt \right)^{1-1/q} \left(\int_0^1 \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{3\alpha^\beta} \right| \left| f' \left(\frac{2-t}{2}a + \frac{t}{2}b \right) \right|^q dt \right)^{1/q} \\
 &= A_1^{1-1/q}(\alpha, \beta) \left(\int_0^1 \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{3\alpha^\beta} \right| \left| f' \left(\frac{2-t}{2}a + \frac{t}{2}b \right) \right|^q dt \right)^{1/q} \\
 &\leq A_1^{1-1/q}(\alpha, \beta) \left(\int_0^1 \frac{2-t}{2}|f'|^q + \frac{t}{2}|f'|^q dt \right)^{1/q} \\
 &= A_1^{1-1/q}(\alpha, \beta) [A_4(\alpha, \beta)|f'|^q + A_3(\alpha, \beta)|f'|^q]^{1/q}. \tag{10}
 \end{aligned}$$

Replacing (9) and (10) in (5), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\left| \frac{1}{6} \left[f(a) + 4f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{\alpha^\beta \Gamma(\beta+1)}{2} \left(\frac{2}{b-a} \right)^{\alpha\beta} \left[{}_{-}^{\beta} J_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\alpha} f(a) + {}_{+}^{\beta} J_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\alpha} f(b) \right] \right| \\
 &\leq \frac{\alpha^\beta (b-a)}{4} A_1^{1-1/q}(\alpha, \beta) \left\{ [A_3(\alpha, \beta)|f'|^q + A_4(\alpha, \beta)|f'|^q]^{1/q} + [A_4(\alpha, \beta)|f'|^q + A_3(\alpha, \beta)|f'|^q]^{1/q} \right\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

The proof is completed. □

Remark 2.5. In Theorem 2.3, if $\alpha = 1$ then we have

$$\left| \frac{1}{6} \left[f(a) + 4f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{\Gamma(\beta+1)}{2} \left(\frac{2}{b-a} \right)^{\beta} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}^{\beta} f(a) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}^{\beta} f(b) \right] \right|$$

$$\leq \frac{b-a}{4} B_1^{1-\frac{1}{q}}(\beta) \left\{ [B_3(\beta)|f'|^q + B_4(\beta)|f'|^q]^{1/q} + [B_4(\beta)|f'|^q + B_3(\beta)|f'|^q]^{1/q} \right\},$$

where B_1 is defined in Remark 2.1 and

$$B_3(\beta) = \int_0^1 \frac{t}{2} \left| \frac{1}{3} - t^\beta \right| dt = \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{\beta}{\beta+2} \left(\frac{1}{3} \right)^{\frac{2}{\beta}+1} + \frac{1}{\beta+2} - \frac{1}{6} \right]$$

and

$$B_4(\beta) = \int_0^1 \frac{2-t}{2} \left| \frac{1}{3} - t^\beta \right| dt = \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{4\beta}{\beta+1} \left(\frac{1}{3} \right)^{\frac{1}{\beta}+1} - \frac{\beta}{\beta+2} \left(\frac{1}{3} \right)^{\frac{2}{\beta}+1} + \frac{\beta+3}{(\beta+1)(\beta+2)} - \frac{1}{2} \right],$$

which is similar to 4.

Remark 2.6. In Theorem 2.3, if $\alpha = \beta = 1$ then we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{6} \left[f(a) + 4f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \\ & \leq \frac{5(b-a)}{72} \left\{ \left[\frac{29|f'|^q + 61|f'|^q}{90} \right]^{1/q} + \left[\frac{61|f'|^q + 29|f'|^q}{90} \right]^{1/q} \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

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Spherical Fuzzy TOPSIS with Hybrid Entropy-FUCOM Weighting Method

Elif Güner¹, Başak Aldemir², Ebru Aydoğdu³, Halis Aygün¹

¹Department of Mathematics, Kocaeli University, Umuttepe Campus, 41380,
Kocaeli-TÜRKİYE

²Department of Mathematics, Afyon Kocatepe University, 03200,
Afyonkarahisar-TÜRKİYE

³Department of Basic Sciences, Naval Academy, Turkish National Defence University,
Istanbul-TÜRKİYE

Corresponding author: elif.guner@kocaeli.edu.tr

ORCID IDs:

First Author: [0000-0002-6969-400X](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6969-400X)

Second Author: [0000-0002-9073-9364](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9073-9364)

Third Author: [0000-0002-2777-8651](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2777-8651)

Fourth Author: [0000-0003-3263-3884](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3263-3884)

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Abstract

In this study, a novel multi-criteria group decision-making method is developed by integrating subjective and objective weight determination within the framework of spherical fuzzy sets. In the proposed method, the weights of decision-makers are objectively determined by using an entropy measure function, while the criteria weights are calculated through a hybrid approach that combines the FUCOM and the entropy measure function. Thus, both subjective assessments (via FUCOM) and objective measures (via entropy) are simultaneously considered to determine the importance of the criteria. Then, this approach is integrated with the TOPSIS method in the spherical fuzzy environment. The proposed method provides a more balanced and consistent weighting system, enabling a comprehensive evaluation of different perspectives in decision-making processes. To demonstrate its applicability, the method is applied to a real-life problem. Moreover, several entropy measures from the literature are integrated into the proposed approach to perform a sensitivity analysis based on the obtained results. This analysis enables the evaluation of the method's performance and robustness under various conditions, providing an extensive comparison.

Keywords: [objective weighting], [subjective weighting], [entropy], [MCGDM]

1 Introduction

The theory of SFSs is a recent advancement in the field of fuzzy logic, designed to handle higher levels of uncertainty and imprecision in decision-making processes. Introduced in [8], SFSs extend traditional fuzzy sets by incorporating a three-dimensional membership structure that

includes a membership degree, a non-membership degree, and a neutral membership degree, all of which are constrained to the surface of a unit sphere. This innovative approach allows for a more comprehensive representation of uncertainty, making it particularly useful in complex decision-making environments where data may be incomplete, ambiguous, or imprecise. The primary advantage of SFSs lies in their ability to model and process a higher degree of uncertainty compared to traditional and even more advanced fuzzy set extensions such as intuitionistic fuzzy sets ([1]), picture fuzzy sets ([6]) and Pythagorean fuzzy sets ([12]). By ensuring that the sum of the squares of the membership, non-membership, and neutral-membership degrees equals one, SFSs provide a balanced and normalized framework for capturing the uncertainty inherent in many real-world problems. SFSs have been effectively integrated with various decision-making methods, enhancing their applicability and robustness in diverse scenarios. Among these methods, integrating SFSs with MCDM techniques such as TOPSIS (Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution) shows significant improvements in decision quality and robustness. The spherical fuzzy TOPSIS method allows for a more precise ranking of options by considering the complex uncertainty and imprecision associated with each criterion [8]. In the spherical fuzzy TOPSIS approach, the decision matrix is initially constructed using spherical fuzzy numbers to express the performance evaluations of each alternative with respect to each criterion. The spherical fuzzy decision matrix is then normalized so that all criteria become comparable. Subsequently, the weighted normalized decision matrix is obtained by incorporating the criteria weights, which may be determined subjectively through methods such as spherical fuzzy AHP (Analytic Hierarchy Process) or spherical fuzzy BWM (Best–Worst Method), and objectively through the entropy measure function ([3], [4]). Once the weighted evaluations are derived, the distances of the alternatives to the spherical fuzzy positive and negative ideal solutions are calculated, and the closeness coefficients are used to obtain the final ranking of the alternatives, thereby completing the spherical fuzzy TOPSIS procedure. In addition to these traditional weighting approaches, FUCOM (Full Consistency Method) has recently emerged as a subjective weighting technique that provides high precision and strong internal consistency. First introduced in [11], FUCOM addresses several limitations of methods such as AHP and BWM by enforcing a full consistency condition when comparing criteria. Because consistency plays a critical role in reliable decision-making, FUCOM ensures that all pairwise comparisons made by decision-makers (DMs) are fully transitive and logically coherent. This results in more accurate and dependable criteria weights.

In this study, we aim to combine entropy, FUCOM, and TOPSIS methods in SFSs to offer several significant advantages, particularly in decision-making and multi-criteria analysis. In this method, we calculate DMs weights using entropy, offering a solution for unknown DMs weights. We determine criterion weights both objectively and subjectively through entropy and the FUCOM method. To identify the best option, we apply the TOPSIS method after computing the criteria weights. Then, we apply the suggested method to the selection of digital market technology. Finally, we provide a sensitivity analysis by solving the problem using the other entropy measures for both the criterion and DM weights.

1.1 Preliminaries

This section presents some fundamental notions related to SFSs and existing entropy measure functions defined on SFSs.

Definition 1.1. [8] A SFS over the set of universe X is given by

$$S = \{ \langle x, \mu_S(x), \eta_S(x), \nu_S(x) \rangle \mid x \in X \} \quad (1)$$

where $\mu_S, \eta_S, \nu_S : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ and $\mu_S^2(x) + \eta_S^2(x) + \nu_S^2(x) \leq 1$ for each $x \in X$. The values $\mu_S(x)$, $\eta_S(x)$ and $\nu_S(x)$ denote the positive-membership, neutral-membership and negative-membership of x to the set S , respectively. The refusal function is $\pi_S(x) = \sqrt{1 - \mu_S^2(x) - \eta_S^2(x) - \nu_S^2(x)}$ for every $x \in X$. We will denote the family of all SFSs over X as $\text{SFS}(X)$.

The complement of a SFS S is denoted by S^c and given as $S^c = \{ \langle x, \nu_S(x), \eta_S(x), \mu_S(x) \rangle \mid x \in X \}$.

Also, the triplet $S = (\mu_S, \eta_S, \nu_S)$ is called a spherical fuzzy number (SFN) where $\mu_S, \eta_S, \nu_S \in [0, 1]$ and $\mu_S^2 + \eta_S^2 + \nu_S^2 \leq 1$. We denote the collection of all SFNs by \mathcal{S} .

Definition 1.2. [8] Let $S = \langle \mu_S, \eta_S, \nu_S \rangle$, $S_1 = \langle \mu_{S_1}, \eta_{S_1}, \nu_{S_1} \rangle$, $S_2 = \langle \mu_{S_2}, \eta_{S_2}, \nu_{S_2} \rangle$ be three SFNs and $k \geq 0$. Then the fundamental operations on SFNs are then given as follows:

- (i) $S_1 \leq S_2$ iff $\mu_{S_1} \leq \mu_{S_2}, \eta_{S_1} \leq \eta_{S_2}$ and $\nu_{S_1} \geq \nu_{S_2}$,
- (ii) $S_1 = S_2$ iff $S_1 \leq S_2$ and $S_2 \leq S_1$,
- (iii) $S_1 \oplus S_2 = \left(\sqrt{\mu_{S_1}^2 + \mu_{S_2}^2 - \mu_{S_1}^2 \mu_{S_2}^2}, \sqrt{(1 - \mu_{S_1}^2) \eta_{S_2}^2 + (1 - \mu_{S_2}^2) \eta_{S_1}^2 - \eta_{S_1}^2 \eta_{S_2}^2}, \nu_{S_1} \nu_{S_2} \right)$,
- (iv) $S_1 \otimes S_2 = \left(\mu_{S_1} \mu_{S_2}, \sqrt{(1 - \nu_{S_1}^2) \eta_{S_2}^2 + (1 - \nu_{S_2}^2) \eta_{S_1}^2 - \eta_{S_1}^2 \eta_{S_2}^2}, \sqrt{\nu_{S_1}^2 + \nu_{S_2}^2 - \nu_{S_1}^2 \nu_{S_2}^2} \right)$,
- (v) $kS = \left(\sqrt{1 - (1 - \mu_S^2)^k}, \sqrt{(1 - \mu_S^2)^k - (1 - \mu_S^2 - \eta_S^2)^k}, \nu_S^k \right)$,
- (vi) $S^k = \left(\mu_S^k, \sqrt{(1 - \nu_S^2)^k - (1 - \nu_S^2 - \eta_S^2)^k}, \sqrt{1 - (1 - \nu_S^2)^k} \right)$.

Definition 1.3. [7] Let $S, S_1, S_2 \in \mathcal{S}$ and $S = \langle \mu_S, \eta_S, \nu_S \rangle$.

- (1) A logarithm-based score function $SF : \mathcal{S} \rightarrow [-1, 1]$ is defined as

$$SF(S) = \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \mu_S^2 - \nu_S^2 - (\eta_S^2 + \pi_S^2) \frac{\log_2(1 + \eta_S^2 + \pi_S^2)}{100} \right).$$

- (2) An accuracy function $AF : \mathcal{S} \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is given by $AF(S) = \mu_S^2 + \eta_S^2 + \nu_S^2$.

- (3) The ranking approach using score and accuracy functions proceeds as follows:

- (i) If $SF(S_1) < SF(S_2)$, then $S_1 \ll S_2$,
- (ii) If $SF(S_1) > SF(S_2)$, then $S_1 \gg S_2$,
- (iii) $SF(S_1) = SF(S_2)$, then
 - (a) $AF(S_1) < AF(S_2)$, then $S_1 \ll S_2$,
 - (b) $AF(S_1) > AF(S_2)$, then $S_1 \gg S_2$,
 - (c) $AF(S_1) = AF(S_2)$, then $S_1 = S_2$.

Next, we summarize some existing entropy measure functions given in SFS environment. Take $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$ as the set of universe and $S = \{ \langle x_i, \mu_S(x_i), \eta_S(x_i), \nu_S(x_i) \rangle \mid x_i \in X, \forall i = \overline{1-n} \}$ as a SFS on X .

1. [5] gave the entropy measure function which is induced by generalized distance measure on SFSs and defined as follows:

$$E_B(S) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left((1 - d(S, S^c))^{\frac{1 + \pi_S^2(x_i)}{2}} \right)$$

where the mapping d on $SFS(X) \times SFS(X)$ is given by

$$d(S_1, S_2) = \left(\frac{1}{2n} \sum_{i=1}^n |\mu_{S_1}^2(x_i) - \mu_{S_2}^2(x_i)|^\theta + |\eta_{S_1}^2(x_i) - \eta_{S_2}^2(x_i)|^\theta + |\nu_{S_1}^2(x_i) - \nu_{S_2}^2(x_i)|^\theta \right)^{\frac{1}{\theta}}.$$

For $\theta = 1$, the entropy measure function E_B is as follows:

$$E_B(S) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left((1 - |\mu_S^2(x_i) - \nu_S^2(x_i)|) \frac{2 - \mu_S^2(x_i) - \eta_S^2(x_i) - \nu_S^2(x_i)}{2} \right)$$

2. [9] presented an entropy measure function based on the logarithm function for SFSs:

$$E_J(S) = -\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\mu_S(x_i) \log(\mu_S(x_i)) + \eta_S(x_i) \log(\eta_S(x_i)) + \nu_S(x_i) \log(\nu_S(x_i)) \right).$$

3. [2] proposed a different entropy measure function for SFSs as follows:

$$E_{AG}(S) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left(1 - \frac{4}{5} (|\mu_S^2(x_i) - \nu_S^2(x_i)| + |\eta_S^2(x_i) - .25|) \right).$$

2 Methodology

Take $A = \{A_1, A_2, \dots, A_n\}$ as the set of n options, $C = \{C_1, C_2, \dots, C_m\}$ the set of m criteria and $E = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_k\}$ the set of k DMs whose opinions are taken for decision-making process. Each DMs E_r ($1 \leq r \leq k$) evaluates the options A_p ($1 \leq p \leq n$) concerning C_q ($1 \leq q \leq m$) by considering the affect of C_q on the options A_p . The expert can use the nine-tuple linguistic term table shown in Table 1 when they attain a value for the options.

Table 1: Nine-tuple linguistic terms [8]

Linguistic terms	(μ_S, η_S, ν_S)
Absolutely low importance (ALI)	(0.1, 0.9, 0.1)
Absolutely more importance (AMI)	(0.9, 0.1, 0.1)
Very high importance (VHI)	(0.8, 0.2, 0.2)
High importance (HI)	(0.7, 0.3, 0.3)
Slightly more importance (SMI)	(0.6, 0.4, 0.4)
Equally importance (EI)	(0.5, 0.5, 0.5)
Slightly low importance (SLI)	(0.4, 0.6, 0.4)
Low importance (LI)	(0.3, 0.7, 0.3)
Very low importance (VLI)	(0.2, 0.8, 0.2)

Then, they establish individually spherical fuzzy decision matrix (SFDM) $D^{(r)} = (d_{pq}^{(r)})_{n \times m}$ where $d_{pq}^{(r)} = (\mu_{D_{pq}}^{(r)}, \eta_{D_{pq}}^{(r)}, \nu_{D_{pq}}^{(r)})$ for every $r = \overline{1 - k}$.

The new entropy-based FUCOM-TOPSIS method for SFDMs is processed according to the following steps:

Step I: Decide the type of criteria. Determine which one is the benefit type and which one is the non-benefit type criteria. If there are any non-benefit type criteria, then the related values $d_{pq}^{(r)} = (\mu_{D_{pq}}^{(r)}, \eta_{D_{pq}}^{(r)}, \nu_{D_{pq}}^{(r)})$ for every $r = \overline{1 - k}$ attained to the SFDMs by experts should be normalized as follows:

$$s_{pq}^{(r)} = \begin{cases} d_{pq}^{(r)}, & \text{for benefit type criteria } C_q \\ (d_{pq}^{(r)})^c, & \text{for non-benefit type criteria } C_q \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

for every $p = \overline{1 - n}$, $q = \overline{1 - m}$ and $r = \overline{1 - k}$, where $(d_{pq}^{(r)})^c$ represents the complement of $d_{pq}^{(r)}$. Hence, the spherical fuzzy normalized decision matrix (SFNDM) $D_N^{(r)} = (s_{pq}^{(r)})_{n \times m}$ where $s_{pq}^{(r)} = (\mu_{s_{pq}}^{(r)}, \eta_{s_{pq}}^{(r)}, \nu_{s_{pq}}^{(r)})$ for every $r = \overline{1 - k}$ is constructed.

Step II: Calculate the weight of experts. Experts' weight can be calculated objectively using the suggested entropy measure function in a similar way given in [10]. First, we calculate the scalar value of SFNDMs by using the following equality for every $r = \overline{1 - k}$:

$$\varepsilon_{D_N^{(r)}} = -\frac{1}{\ln(mn)} \sum_{p=1}^n \sum_{q=1}^m \left(\frac{E(s_{pq}^{(r)})}{\sum_{p=1}^n \sum_{q=1}^m E(s_{pq}^{(r)})} \right) \ln \left(\frac{E(s_{pq}^{(r)})}{\sum_{p=1}^n \sum_{q=1}^m E(s_{pq}^{(r)})} \right) \quad (3)$$

where E is the suggested entropy measure function. Then, we compute the weight of experts (ε_r for every $r = \overline{1 - k}$) by using

$$\varepsilon_r = \frac{1 - \varepsilon_{D_N^{(r)}}}{k - \sum_{r=1}^k \varepsilon_{D_N^{(r)}}}. \quad (4)$$

Step III: Establish the aggregated decision matrix. We merge the SFNDMs $D_N^{(r)}$ by considering the weight of experts (calculated in the previous step) via the SFWA operator [8] and so we obtain the spherical fuzzy aggregated decision matrix (SFADM) $D = (s_{pq})_{n \times m}$ which is constructed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} s_{pq} &= SFWA_{\varepsilon}(s_{pq}^{(1)}, s_{pq}^{(2)}, \dots, s_{pq}^{(k)}) = \bigoplus_{r=1}^k \varepsilon_r s_{pq}^{(r)} \\ &= \left(\sqrt{1 - \prod_{r=1}^k (1 - (\mu_{s_{pq}}^{(r)})^2)^{\varepsilon_r}}, \sqrt{\prod_{r=1}^k (1 - (\mu_{s_{pq}}^{(r)})^2)^{\varepsilon_r} - \prod_{r=1}^k (1 - (\mu_{s_{pq}}^{(r)})^2 - (\eta_{s_{pq}}^{(r)})^2)^{\varepsilon_r}}, \prod_{r=1}^k (\nu_{s_{pq}}^{(r)})^{\varepsilon_r} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Let us denote $s_{pq} = (\mu_{A_p}(C_q), \eta_{A_p}(C_q), \nu_{A_p}(C_q))$ for every $p = \overline{1 - n}$ and $q = \overline{1 - m}$.

Step IV: Calculate the weight of the criteria objectively. The weights of the criteria can be objectively determined by using the existing entropy measure functions. Then, the criteria's weight vector, $\Omega = (\omega_1, \omega_2, \dots, \omega_m)$, is computed via the subsequent equation:

$$\omega_q = \frac{1 - E(C_q)}{\sum_{q=1}^m 1 - E(C_q)}, \forall q = \overline{1 - m}. \quad (5)$$

Step V: Calculate the weight of the criteria subjectively. To calculate the weight of

criteria subjectively, we proceed FUCOM method and obtain subjective weights of the criteria $(\omega'_1, \omega'_2, \dots, \omega'_m)^T$. Next, the hybrid weight for criteria $(\Gamma = (\gamma_1, \gamma_2, \dots, \gamma_m))$ is computed as the following way:

$$\gamma_q = \frac{\omega_q \cdot \omega'_q}{\sum_{q=1}^m \omega_q \cdot \omega'_q}$$

for every $q = \overline{1 - m}$.

Step VI: Find the weighted aggregated decision matrix. We weight the SFADM D by considering the hybrid weight vector Γ for criteria by using the scalar multiplication on SFSs and so we construct the spherical fuzzy weighted aggregated decision matrix (SFWADM) $D' = (s'_{pq})_{n \times m}$ where s'_{pq} of D' is :

$$s'_{pq} = \left(\sqrt{1 - (1 - \mu_{A_p}(C_q)^2)^{\gamma_q}}, \sqrt{(1 - \mu_{A_p}(C_q)^2)^{\gamma_q} - (1 - \mu_{A_p}(C_q)^2 - \eta_{A_p}(C_q)^2)^{\gamma_q}}, (\nu_{A_p}(C_q))^{\gamma_q} \right) \tag{6}$$

for every $p = \overline{1 - n}$ and $q = \overline{1 - m}$. Denote $s'_{pq} = (\mu'_{A_p}(C_q), \eta'_{A_p}(C_q), \nu'_{A_p}(C_q))$.

Step VII: Determine Positive and Negative Ideal Solutions. We first transform the elements of SFWADM into real numbers by using the score function. Then the score matrix $D^* = (s^*_{pq})_{n \times m}$ is constructed where $s^*_{pq} = SF(s'_{pq}) = SF(\mu'_{A_p}(C_q), \eta'_{A_p}(C_q), \nu'_{A_p}(C_q))$ for every $p = \overline{1 - n}$ and $q = \overline{1 - m}$. Next, we calculate the Positive Ideal Solution (PIS) A^+ and Negative Ideal Solution (NIS) A^- . We'll use \mathfrak{B}_C to represent the set of benefit type criteria and \mathfrak{C}_C for non-benefit type criteria. From there, PIS A^+ and NIS A^- are determined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} A^+ &= \{A^+(C_1), A^+(C_2), \dots, A^+(C_m)\}, \\ A^- &= \{A^-(C_1), A^-(C_2), \dots, A^-(C_m)\} \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

Here,

$$A^+(C_q) = \{(max_p s^*_{pq} | C_q \in \mathfrak{B}_C), (min_p s^*_{pq} | C_q \in \mathfrak{C}_C) | 1 \leq p \leq n\}, \tag{8}$$

$$A^-(C_q) = \{(min_p s^*_{pq} | C_q \in \mathfrak{B}_C), (max_p s^*_{pq} | C_q \in \mathfrak{C}_C) | 1 \leq p \leq n\} \tag{9}$$

for every $q = \overline{1 - m}$.

Step VIII: Compute the relative closeness index and find the ranking. To compute the relative closeness index, we first find the Euclidean distance of each option A_p from the PIS and NIS.

$$\begin{aligned} d(A_p, A^+) &= \sqrt{\sum_{q=1}^m (A_p(C_q) - A^+(C_q))^2}, \\ d(A_p, A^-) &= \sqrt{\sum_{q=1}^m (A_p(C_q) - A^-(C_q))^2}. \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

Then, we find the relative closeness index $(R(A_p))$ of each option A_p to measure the closeness to the PIS and furtherness to the NIS using the following equation:

$$R(A_p) = \frac{d(A_p, A^-)}{d(A_p, A^-) + d(A_p, A^+)} \tag{11}$$

for every $p = \overline{1 - n}$. Finally, the options are ranked from highest to lowest according to their relative closeness index $R(A_p)$. As a result, we consider the one with the highest ranking as the best option.

3 A Numerical Example

Now, we apply the SF-Entropy-FUCOM-TOPSIS method to evaluate digital marketing technology comprehensively ([7]), showcasing the practical applicability and efficacy of the proposed SFS-based decision-making framework. In this problem, there are three decision-makers, five alternatives and nine criteria. Details of the problem can be found in the paper [7].

The proposed SF-Entropy-FUCOM-TOPSIS method is applied to solve this problem

Step I: This step is skipped since all criteria are benefit type (or not specified).

Step II: We calculate the weight of experts by using Eq. 3 and 4 and these values are obtained as $\varepsilon_1 = 0.3379$, $\varepsilon_2 = 0.3397$, and $\varepsilon_3 = 0.3223$.

Step III: We collect the SFNDMs $D^N(r)$ given in [7] by considering the weight of experts (calculated in the previous step) via the SFWA operator and hence we find the SFADM.

Step IV: We calculate the weight of criteria objectively by using Eq. 5 and we find the weight vector

$$\Omega = (\omega_1, \omega_2, \omega_3, \omega_4, \omega_5, \omega_6, \omega_7, \omega_8, \omega_9) = (0.07, 0.11, 0.13, 0.12, 0.14, 0.11, 0.09, 0.10, 0.13).$$

Step V: We compute the weight of the criteria subjectively (according to the importance value given in [7]) by using the FUCOM method and these values are

$$\Omega' = (\omega'_1, \omega'_2, \omega'_3, \omega'_4, \omega'_5, \omega'_6, \omega'_7, \omega'_8, \omega'_9) = (0.12, 0.13, 0.15, 0.17, 0.19, 0.14, 0.12, 0.15, 0.22).$$

Then, by using objective and subjective weights, we obtain the hybrid weight for criteria weights

$$\Gamma = (\gamma_1, \gamma_2, \gamma_3, \gamma_4, \gamma_5, \gamma_6, \gamma_7, \gamma_8, \gamma_9) = (0.05, 0.10, 0.12, 0.13, 0.16, 0.10, 0.07, 0.09, 0.18).$$

Step VI: We weight the SFADM D by considering the hybrid weight vector Γ for criteria by using scalar multiplication on SFSs. Then, we find the SFWADM.

Step VII: Then PIS A^+ and NIS A^- are found as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} A^+ &= \{0.1375, 0.1356, 0.1343, 0.2076, 0.1683, 0.1654, 0.1471, 0.1437, 0.2024\}, \\ A^- &= \{0.0875, 0.0918, 0.1115, 0.1081, 0.1402, 0.0990, 0.0960, 0.1060, 0.1502\} \end{aligned}$$

Step VIII: The distances of PIS and NIS from each option A_p are calculated to determine the relative closeness index and ranking options, and they are given these values in Table 2.

Next, to emphasize the stability, robustness, and effectiveness of the proposed method, the entropy-based FUCOM-TOPSIS method, sensitive analyses are performed where the weights of experts and criteria take different values. For this purpose, the digital marketing technology problem is solved again with the proposed method using the existing entropy measures. The

Table 2: Ranking Matrix.

	$d(A, A^+)$	$d(A, A^-)$	Index	Rank
A_1	0.0993	0.0813	0.4503	3
A_2	0.1420	0.0442	0.2375	5
A_3	0.1352	0.0603	0.3084	4
A_4	0.0769	0.1204	0.6103	1
A_5	0.0854	0.1174	0.5789	2

results obtained are summarised in Table 3. As it is clear from Table 3, the best and worst options have not changed despite the different weight combinations. This shows that the proposed method provides a solid basis for decision-making and is robust to different subjective opinions.

Table 3: Results under different entropies

Entropy	A_1	A_2	A_3	A_4	A_5	Ranking
E_B [5]	0.45	0.24	0.31	0.61	0.58	$A_4 > A_5 > A_1 > A_3 > A_2$
E_J [9]	0.45	0.25	0.38	0.60	0.51	$A_4 > A_5 > A_1 > A_3 > A_2$
E_{AG} [2]	0.47	0.27	0.44	0.59	0.44	$A_4 > A_1 > A_3 > A_5 > A_2$

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Generalized Fractional Integral Forms of Newton-type Inequalities for Functions of Bounded Variation

Esra Nur Sağlam¹, Fatih Hezenci¹, Wali Haider²

¹Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Science and Arts, Duzce University, Duzce 81620, Türkiye

²School of Mathematics and Statistics, Central South University, Changsha 410083, China

Corresponding author: esra00885@gmail.com

ORCID IDs:

First Author: [0009-0009-6156-8883](https://orcid.org/0009-0009-6156-8883)

Second Author: [0000-0003-1008-5856](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1008-5856)

Third Author: [0009-0001-7065-2755](https://orcid.org/0009-0001-7065-2755)

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Abstract

This paper presents a comprehensive framework for deriving Newton-type inequalities involving generalized fractional integrals for functions of bounded variation. By employing the concept of generalized fractional operators, several new integral inequalities are established, which extend and unify various existing results in the literature. Furthermore, by selecting specific forms of functions and appropriate parameter values, a number of significant special cases are obtained, demonstrating the wide applicability of the proposed approach. The results not only enhance the understanding of fractional inequalities but also provide a broader mathematical foundation for future research in fractional analysis and related areas.

Keywords: Newton-type inequalities, generalized fractional integrals, functions of bounded variation.

1 Introduction

Over the past decades, several classical inequalities such as those of Hermite–Hadamard-type, Simpson-type, and Newton-type inequalities have attracted considerable attention. These type of inequalities have been generalized and extended by many researchers to accommodate different categories of functions, including convex, s -convex, quasi-convex, log-convex, and related classes. Such generalizations not only reveal deeper structural properties of mathematical inequalities but also expand their potential for applications in both pure and applied contexts.

In recent years, the development of fractional calculus has opened new perspectives in this field. Fractional integral and differential operators, due to their demonstrated applications in physics, engineering, and mathematical modelling, have provided powerful tools for extending classical inequalities. Numerous studies have explored Hermite–Hadamard-type, Simpson-type,

and Newton-type inequalities within the framework of fractional operators, leading to new bounds, refinements, and generalizations. Motivated by these developments, the study of Newton-type inequalities via generalized fractional integral operators has gained increasing importance. Such results not only unify existing inequalities but also produce novel extensions that are adaptable to wider classes of functions. This research area is expanding, adding valuable results to the literature and opening the way for further work and applications.

The three-point Newton-Cotes quadrature rule forms the basis of Simpson's second rule. Computations involving three-step quadratic kernels are commonly referred to as Newton-type results, which are known in the literature as Newton-type inequalities. Many mathematicians have studied and extended these inequalities, exploring their properties and applications in various contexts. For example, in paper [1], some Newton-type inequalities are proved for the case of functions whose second derivatives are convex. Improvements are obtained, based on convexity, to some recent error estimates of Dragomir and Agarwal for the trapezoidal formula [2]. Corresponding estimates are also established for the midpoint formula, and a parallel development is presented based on concavity. Mihai et al. [3] establish new Hermite-Hadamard type inequalities for harmonic h -convex functions involving hypergeometric functions. They also discussed several new and known special cases that follow from these results. The methods and ideas presented in their work may inspire further research in this field. In paper [4], some Newton-type inequalities are acquired for the case of functions whose first derivative in absolute value at certain power are arithmetically-harmonically convex. In addition, in paper [5], some Newton-type inequalities are proved by using Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals for differentiable convex functions and several Riemann-Liouville fractional Newton-type inequalities are presented for functions of bounded variation. Noor et al. [6] establish new Newton-type integral inequalities for p -harmonic convex functions. They also discuss several special cases as applications of these main results. Moreover, Ali et al. [7] consider some Newton-type inequalities for quantum differentiable convex functions. Erden [8] presents several error estimates for the Newton-type quadrature formula using bounded variation and Lipschitzian mappings. For recent results on Newton-type inequalities, see [10, 9] and the references therein.

Fractional calculus and its applications arise in various fields such as physics, chemistry, engineering, and mathematics. Extending classical analysis to fractional analysis provides more realistic solutions to many problems, since numerous real dynamical systems are more accurately modelled by non-integer order operators. While integer-order models in classical analysis often fail to represent natural processes, fractional computation with arbitrary and flexible orders yields more precise and reliable approaches. Motivated by its wide applicability, this area has been extensively investigated by many researchers. For example, in paper [11], inequalities involving fractional integrals have recently gained significant attention, leading to new developments in inequality theory. In this study, Hermite-Hadamard-type inequalities are established using Atangana-Baleanu operators for twice differentiable convex functions, supported by a new integral identity. In [12], Hadamard inequalities for k -fractional Riemann-Liouville integrals are proved, and the classical fractional Riemann-Liouville case is deduced. These results are further extended to two coordinates, yielding Hadamard inequalities for fractional Riemann-Liouville integrals on two coordinates. In [13], a new definition of fractional derivative and fractional integral is

introduced, whose form appears to be both natural and highly effective. For further details on this type of issues, see [14, 13]. In particular, generalized fractional integrals play a crucial role in developing inequalities, where one of the most important applications is the Hermite–Hadamard inequality and its various extensions. For instance, In [15], Hermite–Hadamard-type inequalities for fractional integrals are first established. Then, an integral identity and several Hermite–Hadamard-type integral inequalities for fractional integrals are obtained, which are related to the results in [16]. In [16], the authors offer two inequalities for differentiable convex mappings which are connected with the celebrated Hermite–Hadamard-type integral inequality holding for convex functions. For further information and unexplained subjects about these type of inequalities, we refer the reader to [17, 18, 19] and the references therein.

2 Preliminaries

In this section, several definitions and notations frequently used throughout the main part of the paper are introduced. Simpson’s quadrature formula (Simpson’s 1/3 rule) is presented as follows:

$$\int_a^b f(x) dx \approx \frac{b-a}{6} \left[f(a) + 4f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right]. \quad (1)$$

Theorem 2.1. Let us consider that $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a four times differentiable and continuous function on (a, b) , and $\|f^{(4)}\|_\infty = \sup_{x \in (a,b)} |f^{(4)}(x)| < \infty$. Then, the following inequality holds:

$$\left| \frac{1}{6} \left[f(a) + 4f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{1}{2880} \|f^{(4)}\|_\infty (b-a)^4.$$

Simpson’s second formula, also known as the Newton-Cotes quadrature formula (Simpson’s 3/8 rule; see [20]), is expressed as follows:

$$\int_a^b f(x) dx \approx \frac{b-a}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right]. \quad (2)$$

Theorem 2.2. If $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a four times differentiable and continuous function on (a, b) , and $\|f^{(4)}\|_\infty = \sup_{x \in (a,b)} |f^{(4)}(x)| < \infty$, then one has the inequality

$$\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{1}{6480} \|f^{(4)}\|_\infty (b-a)^4.$$

The corresponding dual Simpson’s 3/8 formula - the Maclaurin rule based on the Maclaurin formula (cf. [20]) is as follows:

$$\int_a^b f(x) dx \approx \frac{b-a}{8} \left[3f\left(\frac{5a+b}{6}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+5b}{6}\right) \right]. \quad (3)$$

Theorem 2.3. Suppose that $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a four times differentiable and continuous function

on (a, b) , and $\|f^{(4)}\|_\infty = \sup_{x \in (a,b)} |f^{(4)}(x)| < \infty$. Then, the following inequality satisfies:

$$\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[3f\left(\frac{5a+b}{6}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+5b}{6}\right) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{7}{51840} \|f^{(4)}\|_\infty (b-a)^4.$$

Formulae (1), (2), and (3) hold for every function f with continuous 4th derivative on $[a, b]$.

In the literature, numerous studies address inequalities related to generalized fractional integrals. For instance, Sarikaya and Ertugral [17] have established Hermite–Hadamard-type inequalities for generalized fractional integrals.

Definition 2.1. [17] Let us consider $\varphi : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ the condition $\int_0^1 \frac{\varphi(t)}{t} dt < \infty$. Then, the following left-sided and right-sided generalized fractional integral operators are described as

$${}_{a+}I_\varphi f(x) = \int_a^x \frac{\varphi(x-t)}{x-t} f(t) dt, \quad x > a \tag{4}$$

and

$${}_{b-}I_\varphi f(x) = \int_x^b \frac{\varphi(t-x)}{t-x} f(t) dt, \quad x < b, \tag{5}$$

respectively.

Generalized fractional integrals possess the notable feature of encompassing several important types of fractional integrals, including the Riemann-Liouville fractional integral, k -Riemann-Liouville fractional integral, Katugampola fractional integrals, conformable fractional integral, and Hadamard fractional integrals, among others. The key special cases of the integral operators defined in (4) and (5) are summarized as follows:

- i. If we choose $\varphi(t) = t$, then the operators (4) and (5) reduce to the Riemann integral.
- ii. If we select $\varphi(t) = \frac{t^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha)}$ and $\alpha > 0$, then the operators (4) and (5) become to the Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals $J_{a+}^\alpha f(x)$ and $J_{b-}^\alpha f(x)$, respectively [21, 22]. Here,

$$J_{a+}^\alpha f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_a^x (x-t)^{\alpha-1} f(t) dt, \quad x > a$$

and

$$J_{b-}^\alpha f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_x^b (t-x)^{\alpha-1} f(t) dt, \quad x < b.$$

Γ is Gamma function defined by the integral formula

$$\Gamma(x) := \int_0^\infty t^{x-1} e^{-t} dt, \quad x \in \mathbb{R}^+.$$

- iii. For $\varphi(t) = \frac{1}{k\Gamma_k(\alpha)} t^{\frac{\alpha}{k}}$ and $\alpha, k > 0$, the operators (4) and (5) equal to the k -Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals $J_{a+,k}^\alpha f(x)$ and $J_{b-,k}^\alpha f(x)$, respectively. Here,

$$J_{a+,k}^\alpha f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma_k(\alpha)} \int_a^x (x-t)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}-1} f(t) dt, \quad x > a$$

and

$$J_{b-,k}^\alpha f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma_k(\alpha)} \int_x^b (t-x)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}-1} f(t) dt, \quad x < b.$$

Γ_k is k -Gamma function defined by

$$\Gamma_k(\alpha) = \int_0^\infty t^{\alpha-1} e^{-\frac{t^k}{k}} dt, \quad \Re(\alpha) > 0$$

and

$$\Gamma_k(\alpha) = k^{\frac{\alpha}{k}-1} \Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha}{k}\right), \quad \Re(\alpha) > 0; k > 0.$$

3 Main results

Lemma 3.1. Let us consider that $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is an absolutely continuous function (a, b) so that $f' \in L_1[a, b]$. Then, the following equality holds:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{2\Lambda(1)} \left[{}_{b-}I_\varphi f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + {}_{a+}I_\varphi f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right] \\ & = \frac{b-a}{4\Lambda(1)} \int_a^b K(x) df(x). \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

Here, $\Lambda(t) = \int_0^t \frac{\varphi\left(\left(\frac{b-a}{2}\right)y\right)}{y} dy$ and

$$K(x) = \begin{cases} -\frac{2}{b-a} \left[\Lambda\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\left(\frac{a+b}{2} - x\right)\right) - \frac{3}{4}\Lambda(1) \right], & a \leq x < \frac{2a+b}{3}, \\ -\frac{2}{b-a} \Lambda\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\left(\frac{a+b}{2} - x\right)\right), & \frac{2a+b}{3} \leq x < \frac{a+b}{2}, \\ \frac{2}{b-a} \Lambda\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\left(x - \frac{a+b}{2}\right)\right), & \frac{a+b}{2} \leq x < \frac{a+2b}{3}, \\ \frac{2}{b-a} \left[\Lambda\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\left(x - \frac{a+b}{2}\right)\right) - \frac{3}{4}\Lambda(1) \right], & \frac{a+2b}{3} \leq x \leq b. \end{cases}$$

Proof. Let us first consider the function $K(x)$. Then, with the help of the integrating by parts, it follows from that

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_a^b K(x) df(x) \\ & = \frac{2}{b-a} \left\{ - \int_a^{\frac{2a+b}{3}} \left[\Lambda\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\left(\frac{a+b}{2} - x\right)\right) - \frac{3}{4}\Lambda(1) \right] df(x) \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \int_{\frac{2a+b}{3}}^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \Lambda\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\left(\frac{a+b}{2} - x\right)\right) df(x) \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+2b}{3}} \Lambda\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\left(x - \frac{a+b}{2}\right)\right) df(x) \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \int_{\frac{a+2b}{3}}^b \left[\Lambda\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\left(x - \frac{a+b}{2}\right)\right) - \frac{3}{4}\Lambda(1) \right] df(x) \right\} \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+2b}{3}} \Lambda \left(\frac{2}{b-a} \left(x - \frac{a+b}{2} \right) \right) df(x) \\
 & + \int_{\frac{a+2b}{3}}^b \left[\Lambda \left(\frac{2}{b-a} \left(x - \frac{a+b}{2} \right) \right) - \frac{3}{4} \Lambda(1) \right] df(x) \Bigg\} \\
 & = \frac{2}{b-a} \left\{ - \left[\Lambda \left(\frac{2}{b-a} \left(\frac{a+b}{2} - x \right) \right) - \frac{3}{4} \Lambda(1) \right] f(x) \Big|_a^{\frac{2a+b}{3}} - \int_a^{\frac{2a+b}{3}} \frac{\varphi \left(\frac{a+b}{2} - x \right)}{\frac{a+b}{2} - x} f(x) dx \right. \\
 & - \Lambda \left(\frac{2}{b-a} \left(\frac{a+b}{2} - x \right) \right) f(x) \Big|_{\frac{2a+b}{3}}^{\frac{a+b}{2}} - \int_{\frac{2a+b}{3}}^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \frac{\varphi \left(\frac{a+b}{2} - x \right)}{\frac{a+b}{2} - x} f(x) dx \\
 & + \Lambda \left(\frac{2}{b-a} \left(x - \frac{a+b}{2} \right) \right) f(x) \Big|_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+2b}{3}} - \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+2b}{3}} \frac{\varphi \left(x - \frac{a+b}{2} \right)}{x - \frac{a+b}{2}} f(x) dx \\
 & \left. + \left[\Lambda \left(\frac{2}{b-a} \left(x - \frac{a+b}{2} \right) \right) - \frac{3}{4} \Lambda(1) \right] f(x) \Big|_{\frac{a+2b}{3}}^b - \int_{\frac{a+2b}{3}}^b \frac{\varphi \left(x - \frac{a+b}{2} \right)}{x - \frac{a+b}{2}} f(x) dx \right\} \\
 & = \frac{2}{b-a} \left\{ \frac{\Lambda(1)}{4} \left[f(a) + 3f \left(\frac{2a+b}{3} \right) + 3f \left(\frac{a+2b}{3} \right) + f(b) \right] \right. \\
 & \left. - \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \frac{\varphi \left(\frac{a+b}{2} - x \right)}{\frac{a+b}{2} - x} f(x) dx - \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^b \frac{\varphi \left(x - \frac{a+b}{2} \right)}{x - \frac{a+b}{2}} f(x) dx \right\} \\
 & = \frac{2}{b-a} \left\{ \frac{\Lambda(1)}{4} \left[f(a) + 3f \left(\frac{2a+b}{3} \right) + 3f \left(\frac{a+2b}{3} \right) + f(b) \right] \right. \\
 & \left. - \left[{}_{b-}I_{\varphi} f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + {}_{a+}I_{\varphi} f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) \right] \right\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence, it follows that

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f \left(\frac{2a+b}{3} \right) + 3f \left(\frac{a+2b}{3} \right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{2\Lambda(1)} \left[{}_{b-}I_{\varphi} f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + {}_{a+}I_{\varphi} f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) \right] \\
 & = \frac{b-a}{4\Lambda(1)} \int_a^b K(x) df(x).
 \end{aligned}$$

□

Theorem 3.1. If $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a function of bounded variation on $[a, b]$, then it follows

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f \left(\frac{2a+b}{3} \right) + 3f \left(\frac{a+2b}{3} \right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{2\Lambda(1)} \left[{}_{b-}I_{\varphi} f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + {}_{a+}I_{\varphi} f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) \right] \right| \\
 & \leq \frac{1}{2\Lambda(1)} \max \left\{ \left| \Lambda \left(\frac{1}{3} \right) - \frac{3}{4} \Lambda(1) \right|, \frac{1}{4} \Lambda(1), \Lambda \left(\frac{1}{3} \right) \right\} \bigvee_a^b(f).
 \end{aligned}$$

Here, $\bigvee_a^b(f)$ denotes the total variation of f on $[a, b]$.

Proof. It is well-known that if $g, f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ with g continuous on $[a, b]$ and f of bounded variation on $[a, b]$, then the integral $\int_a^b g(t) df(t)$ exists and

$$\left| \int_a^b g(t) df(t) \right| \leq \sup_{t \in [a, b]} |g(t)| \bigvee_a^b(f). \quad (8)$$

With the aid of (8), it follows

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{2\Lambda(1)} \left[{}_{b-}I_{\varphi}f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + {}_{a+}I_{\varphi}f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right] \right| \\ &= \frac{b-a}{4\Lambda(1)} \left| \int_a^b K_{\alpha}(x) df(x) \right| \\ &\leq \frac{1}{2\Lambda(1)} \left\{ \left| \int_a^{\frac{2a+b}{3}} \left[\Lambda\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\left(\frac{a+b}{2}-x\right)\right) - \frac{3}{4}\Lambda(1) \right] df(x) \right| \right. \\ &\quad + \left| \int_{\frac{2a+b}{3}}^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \Lambda\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\left(\frac{a+b}{2}-x\right)\right) df(x) \right| \\ &\quad + \left| \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+2b}{3}} \Lambda\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\left(x-\frac{a+b}{2}\right)\right) df(x) \right| \\ &\quad \left. + \left| \int_{\frac{a+2b}{3}}^b \left[\Lambda\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\left(x-\frac{a+b}{2}\right)\right) - \frac{3}{4}\Lambda(1) \right] df(x) \right| \right\} \\ &\leq \frac{1}{2\Lambda(1)} \left\{ \sup_{x \in [a, \frac{2a+b}{3}]} \left| \Lambda\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\left(\frac{a+b}{2}-x\right)\right) - \frac{3}{4}\Lambda(1) \right| \bigvee_a^{\frac{2a+b}{3}}(f) \right. \\ &\quad + \sup_{x \in [\frac{2a+b}{3}, \frac{a+b}{2}]} \left| \Lambda\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\left(\frac{a+b}{2}-x\right)\right) \right| \bigvee_{\frac{2a+b}{3}}^{\frac{a+b}{2}}(f) \\ &\quad + \sup_{x \in [\frac{a+b}{2}, \frac{a+2b}{3}]} \left| \Lambda\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\left(x-\frac{a+b}{2}\right)\right) \right| \bigvee_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+2b}{3}}(f) \\ &\quad \left. + \sup_{x \in [\frac{a+2b}{3}, b]} \left| \Lambda\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\left(x-\frac{a+b}{2}\right)\right) - \frac{3}{4}\Lambda(1) \right| \bigvee_{\frac{a+2b}{3}}^b(f) \right\} \\ &= \frac{1}{2\Lambda(1)} \left\{ \max \left[\left| \Lambda\left(\frac{1}{3}\right) - \frac{3}{4}\Lambda(1) \right|, \frac{1}{4}\Lambda(1) \right] \bigvee_a^{\frac{2a+b}{3}}(f) \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \Lambda\left(\frac{1}{3}\right) \bigvee_{\frac{2a+b}{3}}^{\frac{a+2b}{3}}(f) \right\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \max \left\{ \left| \Lambda \left(\frac{1}{3} \right) - \frac{3}{4} \Lambda(1) \right|, \frac{1}{4} \Lambda(1) \right\} \bigvee_{\frac{a+2b}{3}}^b (f) \\
 & \leq \frac{1}{2\Lambda(1)} \max \left\{ \left| \Lambda \left(\frac{1}{3} \right) - \frac{3}{4} \Lambda(1) \right|, \frac{1}{4} \Lambda(1), \Lambda \left(\frac{1}{3} \right) \right\} \bigvee_a^b (f).
 \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof of Theorem 3.1. □

Remark 3.1. Consider $\varphi(t) = t$ in Theorem 3.1. Then, the following Newton-type inequality satisfies:

$$\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(t) dt \right| \leq \frac{5}{24} \bigvee_a^b (f).$$

This is presented by which is given by Alomari in [24].

Remark 3.2. Consider $\varphi(t) = \frac{t^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha)}$ in Theorem 3.1. Then, Theorem 3.1 is equal to [23, Theorem 3.17].

Corollary 3.1. Note that $\varphi(t) = \frac{1}{k\Gamma_k(\alpha)} t^{\frac{\alpha}{k}}$ in Theorem 3.1. Then, it follows

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[3f\left(\frac{5a+b}{6}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+5b}{6}\right) \right] - \frac{2^{\frac{\alpha}{k}-1} \Gamma_k(\alpha+k)}{(b-a)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}}} \left[J_{b^-,k}^\alpha f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + J_{a^+,k}^\alpha f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right] \right| \\
 & \leq \frac{1}{2} \max \left\{ \left| \left(\frac{1}{3}\right)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}} - \frac{3}{4} \right|, \frac{1}{4}, \left(\frac{1}{3}\right)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}} \right\} \bigvee_a^b (f).
 \end{aligned}$$

4 Concluding Remarks and Summary

We prove Newton-type inequalities using generalized fractional integrals of bounded variation, and the results are demonstrated through special cases of the established theories. In future studies, the concepts and techniques underlying our results on Newton-type inequalities using generalized fractional integrals could pave the way for further research in this area. Enhancements or generalizations of our findings may be explored by examining different classes of convex functions or alternative types of fractional integral operators. Furthermore, Newton-type inequalities for various function classes might be derived with the assistance of quantum calculus.

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Development of Weighted Corrected Euler-Maclaurin-Type Inequalities via Fractional Operators for Various Function Classes

Esra Üneş¹, İzzettin Demir¹

¹Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Science and Arts, Duzce University, Türkiye

Corresponding author: esrauness.25@gmail.com

ORCID IDs:

First Author: [0009-0005-8670-6075](https://orcid.org/0009-0005-8670-6075)

Second Author: [0000-0003-0298-2872](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0298-2872)

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Abstract

This paper presents weighted corrected Euler-Maclaurin-type inequalities for diverse function classes by means of Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals. To establish our main results, we employ a fundamental integral identity that incorporates a positive weighted function given by Üneş and Demir [12]. The combination of this integral identity with Riemann-Liouville fractional operators yields inequalities applicable to several important function classes, including bounded functions, Lipschitzian functions, functions of bounded variation.

Keywords: Corrected Euler-Maclaurin-type inequalities, Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals, bounded functions, Lipschitzian functions, functions of bounded variation

1 Introduction

The analytical power of fractional calculus, as a generalization of classical theory, lies in its distinctive ability to model phenomena governed by non-integer dynamics. Among its foundational tools, the Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals have played a pivotal role in advancing inequality theory. The successful integration of this operator with traditional analytical frameworks has led to refined generalizations of several fundamental inequalities, including those of Hermite-Hadamard, Simpson, Newton, and Euler-Maclaurin types. Current research continues to enhance existing results while developing new inequalities aimed at addressing complex challenges across modern science and engineering.

According to Kilbas et al. [9], the Riemann-Liouville fractional integral operators are given by:

Definition 1.1. The Riemann-Liouville integrals $I_{a+}^{\alpha}f(x)$ and $I_{b-}^{\alpha}f(x)$ of order $\alpha > 0$ are defined as follows:

$$I_{a+}^{\alpha}f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_a^x (x-t)^{\alpha-1} f(t)dt, \quad x > a$$

and

$$I_{b-}^{\alpha} f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_x^b (t-x)^{\alpha-1} f(t) dt, \quad x < b,$$

respectively, where $f \in L_1[a, b]$. Here, Γ is the Gamma function given by

$$\Gamma(\alpha) := \int_0^{\infty} t^{\alpha-1} e^{-t} dt.$$

The Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals reduce to their classical counterparts when the order of integration is $\alpha = 1$.

Dedic et al. [3] utilized the classical Euler-Maclaurin formula to derive inequalities, employing them specifically to evaluate errors in Maclaurin-type quadrature rules. To enhance these estimates, Franjic and Pecaric [4] introduced corrected Euler-Maclaurin formulas, which are also known as open-type quadrature rules. Since their introduction, these formulas have formed the basis of extensive research devoted to obtaining sharper error bounds and more refined inequalities. Illustrating this development, Hezenci [6] employed convexity principles in combination with Hölder and power-mean inequalities to establish fractional corrected Euler-Maclaurin-type inequalities. In a similar direction, Munir et al. [10] utilized the Caputo-Fabrizio fractional integral to derive several results grounded in s -convexity. Further progress was made by Acar et al. [1], who applied conformable fractional integrals to obtain such inequalities for differentiable convex functions. The references [2, 7, 5], together with their corresponding citation networks, offer a comprehensive basis for further study of this topic.

The following presents the three-point open formula, referred to as the corrected Euler-Maclaurin inequality:

Theorem 1.1 (See [4]). For a function $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ with a continuous fourth derivative on (a, b) , the following inequality is satisfied:

$$\left| \frac{1}{80} \left[27f\left(\frac{5a+b}{6}\right) + 26f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 27f\left(\frac{a+5b}{6}\right) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{2401}{28800} \|f^{(4)}\|_{\infty} (b-a)^4,$$

where $\|f^{(4)}\|_{\infty} = \sup_{x \in (a,b)} |f^{(4)}(x)| < \infty$.

Classical analytical notions, notably Lipschitz continuity and bounded variation, have consistently provided essential structural tools for deriving and analyzing integral inequalities.

Definition 1.2. A function $f : I \subseteq \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ satisfies a Lipschitz condition if there exists a constant $\mathfrak{L} > 0$ for which

$$|f(b) - f(a)| \leq \mathfrak{L} |b - a|$$

for all $a, b \in I$. In this case, the constant \mathfrak{L} is referred to as a Lipschitz constant for the function f .

Definition 1.3. Consider a function $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ defined on $[a, b]$. Let $P = \{\eta_0, \eta_1, \eta_2, \dots, \eta_n\} \in \mathcal{P}([a, b])$, where $\mathcal{P}([a, b])$ is the family of all partitions of the interval $[a, b]$. The total variation of

f on $[a, b]$ with respect to P is given by

$$\bigvee_a^b(f, P) = \sum_{i=1}^n |f(\eta_i) - f(\eta_{i-1})|$$

Moreover, the possibly infinite number

$$\bigvee_a^b(f) = \sup \left\{ \bigvee_a^b(f, P) : P \in \mathcal{P}([a, b]) \right\}$$

is called the total variation of f on $[a, b]$. In case $\bigvee_a^b(f) < \infty$, we say that f is a function of bounded variation.

This paper derives new weighted corrected Euler-Maclaurin-type inequalities within the framework of Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals, contributing to recent advances in the field. The cornerstone of our analysis is a key integral identity; leveraging this identity alongside Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals, we obtain several integral inequalities for bounded functions, Lipschitzian functions, and functions of bounded variation.

2 Main results

Within the context of this study, let us consider $w : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ as a continuous, nonnegative function on $[a, b]$ possessing symmetry with respect to the midpoint $\frac{a+b}{2}$ (i.e. $w(x) = w(a+b-x)$ for all $x \in [a, b]$). Take the functions W_1 and W_2 in the following manner:

$$W_1(\alpha, t) = \int_t^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \left(\frac{a+b}{2} - u \right)^{\alpha-1} w(u) du$$

and

$$W_2(\alpha, t) = \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^t \left(u - \frac{a+b}{2} \right)^{\alpha-1} w(u) du.$$

Due to the symmetry of w about the midpoint $\frac{a+b}{2}$, the following equalities hold and will be frequently applied in the subsequent sections:

$$\begin{aligned} W(\alpha) &:= W_1(\alpha, a) = W_2(\alpha, b) \\ &= \Gamma(\alpha) I_{b^-}^\alpha w \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) \\ &= \Gamma(\alpha) I_{a^+}^\alpha w \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) \\ &= \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2} \left[I_{a^+}^\alpha w \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + I_{b^-}^\alpha w \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) \right] \end{aligned}$$

and

$$W_1(\alpha, t) = W_2(\alpha, a+b-t), \quad W_2(\alpha, t) = W_1(\alpha, a+b-t). \quad (1)$$

Moreover, the following identities are established:

$$W(1) = \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} w(u) du = \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^b w(u) du = \frac{1}{2} \int_a^b w(u) du.$$

The lemma below was provided by Üneş and Demir [12].

Lemma 2.1. Let $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be an absolutely continuous function on (a, b) with $f' \in L_1[a, b]$. Then, the following equality holds:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{80} \left[27f\left(\frac{5a+b}{6}\right) + 26f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 27f\left(\frac{a+5b}{6}\right) \right] W(\alpha) \\ & - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2} \left[I_{a^+}^\alpha fw\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + I_{b^-}^\alpha fw\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right] \\ & = \frac{1}{2} [K_3 + K_4 - K_1 - K_2]. \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

Here, Γ represents the Euler gamma function and

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} K_1 &= \int_a^{\frac{5a+b}{6}} [W_1(\alpha, t) - W(\alpha)] f'(t) dt, \\ K_2 &= \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^b \left[W_1(\alpha, t) - \frac{13}{40}W(\alpha) \right] f'(t) dt, \\ K_3 &= \int_a^{\frac{5a+b}{6}} \left[W_2(\alpha) - \frac{13}{40}W(\alpha) \right] f'(t) dt, \\ K_4 &= \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^b [W_2(\alpha) - W(\alpha)] f'(t) dt. \end{aligned} \right.$$

Corollary 2.1 (See [12]). From the assumptions of Lemma 2.1, the following equalities are derived:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{80} \left[27f\left(\frac{5a+b}{6}\right) + 26f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 27f\left(\frac{a+5b}{6}\right) \right] W(\alpha) \\ & - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2} \left[I_{a^+}^\alpha fw\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + I_{b^-}^\alpha fw\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right] \\ & = \frac{1}{2} \left[\int_a^{\frac{5a+b}{6}} [W_1(\alpha, t) - W(\alpha)] [f'(a+b-t) - f'(t)] dt \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^b \left[W_1(\alpha, t) - \frac{13}{40}W(\alpha) \right] [f'(a+b-t) - f'(t)] dt \right] \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

and

$$\frac{1}{80} \left[27f\left(\frac{5a+b}{6}\right) + 26f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 27f\left(\frac{a+5b}{6}\right) \right] W(\alpha) \tag{4}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& -\frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2} \left[I_{a^+}^\alpha fw \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + I_{b^-}^\alpha fw \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) \right] \\
= & \frac{1}{2} \left[\int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b [W_2(\alpha, t) - W(\alpha)] [f'(t) - f'(a+b-t)] dt \right. \\
& \left. + \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+5b}{6}} \left[W_2(\alpha, t) - \frac{13}{40}W(\alpha) \right] [f'(t) - f'(a+b-t)] dt \right].
\end{aligned}$$

By employing fractional integrals, we extend the weighted corrected Euler-Maclaurin-type inequalities to the class of bounded functions.

Theorem 2.1. Under the assumptions of Lemma 2.1, if $f'(t)$ is a bounded function on $[a, b]$ by m and M , then we derive the following inequality:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left| \frac{1}{80} \left[27f \left(\frac{5a+b}{6} \right) + 26f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + 27f \left(\frac{a+5b}{6} \right) \right] W(\alpha) \right. \\
& \quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2} \left[I_{a^+}^\alpha fw \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + I_{b^-}^\alpha fw \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) \right] \right| \\
\leq & \frac{1}{2} \left[\int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+5b}{6}} \left| W_2(\alpha, t) - \frac{13}{40}W(\alpha) \right| dt + \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b |W_2(\alpha, t) - W(\alpha)| dt \right] (M - m).
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. An application of equality (3) yields

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{1}{80} \left[27f \left(\frac{5a+b}{6} \right) + 26f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + 27f \left(\frac{a+5b}{6} \right) \right] W(\alpha) \tag{5} \\
& - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2} \left[I_{a^+}^\alpha fw \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + I_{b^-}^\alpha fw \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) \right] \\
= & \frac{1}{2} \left[\int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+5b}{6}} \left[W_2(\alpha, t) - \frac{13}{40}W(\alpha) \right] \left[f'(t) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right] dt \right. \\
& + \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+5b}{6}} \left[W_2(\alpha, t) - \frac{13}{40}W(\alpha) \right] \left[\frac{m+M}{2} - f'(a+b-t) \right] dt \\
& + \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b [W_2(\alpha, t) - W(\alpha)] \left[f'(t) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right] dt \\
& \left. + \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b [W_2(\alpha, t) - W(\alpha)] \left[\frac{m+M}{2} - f'(a+b-t) \right] dt \right].
\end{aligned}$$

Taking the modulus of inequality (5), we have

$$\left| \frac{1}{80} \left[27f \left(\frac{5a+b}{6} \right) + 26f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + 27f \left(\frac{a+5b}{6} \right) \right] W(\alpha) \right.$$

$$\begin{aligned} & -\frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2} \left[I_{a^+}^\alpha fw \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + I_{b^-}^\alpha fw \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) \right] \Big| \\ \leq & \frac{1}{2} \left[\int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+5b}{6}} \left| W_2(\alpha, t) - \frac{13}{40}W(\alpha) \right| \left| f'(t) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right| dt \right. \\ & + \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+5b}{6}} \left| W_2(\alpha, t) - \frac{13}{40}W(\alpha) \right| \left| \frac{m+M}{2} - f'(a+b-t) \right| dt \\ & + \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b \left| W_2(\alpha, t) - W(\alpha) \right| \left| f'(t) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right| dt \\ & \left. + \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b \left| W_2(\alpha, t) - W(\alpha) \right| \left| \frac{m+M}{2} - f'(a+b-t) \right| dt \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Given that $f'(t)$ is bounded between m and M for all $t \in [a, b]$, we obtain

$$\left| f'(t) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right| \leq \frac{M-m}{2} \tag{6}$$

and

$$\left| f'(a+b-t) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right| \leq \frac{M-m}{2}. \tag{7}$$

From (6) and (7), we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{80} \left[27f \left(\frac{5a+b}{6} \right) + 26f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + 27f \left(\frac{a+5b}{6} \right) \right] W(\alpha) \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2} \left[I_{a^+}^\alpha fw \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + I_{b^-}^\alpha fw \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) \right] \right| \\ \leq & \frac{1}{2} \left[\int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+5b}{6}} \left| W_2(\alpha, t) - \frac{13}{40}W(\alpha) \right| dt + \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b \left| W_2(\alpha, t) - W(\alpha) \right| dt \right] (M-m). \end{aligned}$$

□

Remark 2.1. If we take $w(t) = 1$ for all $t \in [a, b]$, then Theorem 2.1 simplifies to the corrected Euler-Maclaurin-type inequality proven by Kara et al. in [8, Theorem 8].

Corollary 2.2. Choosing $\alpha = 1$ in Theorem 2.1 yields the following weighted corrected Euler-Maclaurin-type inequality

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{80} \left[27f \left(\frac{5a+b}{6} \right) + 26f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + 27f \left(\frac{a+5b}{6} \right) \right] \int_a^b w(t) dt - \int_a^b w(t) f(t) dt \right| \\ \leq & (M-m) \left[\int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+5b}{6}} \left| \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^t w(u) du - \frac{13}{80} \int_a^b w(u) du \right| dt + \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b \left(u - \frac{a+5b}{6} \right) w(u) du \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Remark 2.2. As a special case, Corollary 2.2 with $w(t) = 1$ for all $t \in [a, b]$ coincides with the corrected Euler-Maclaurin-type inequality proven by Kara et al. in [8, Corollary 3].

Now, in the case of Lipschitzian functions, we formulate a fractional weighted corrected Euler-Maclaurin-type inequality.

Theorem 2.2. Given that Lemma 2.1 applies and that f' is an L -Lipschitzian function on $[a, b]$, the following inequality holds:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{80} \left[27f\left(\frac{5a+b}{6}\right) + 26f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 27f\left(\frac{a+5b}{6}\right) \right] W(\alpha) - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2} \left[I_{a^+}^\alpha fw\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + I_{b^-}^\alpha fw\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right] \right| \\ & \leq L \left[\int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+5b}{6}} \left| W_2(\alpha, t) - \frac{13}{40}W(\alpha) \right| \left(t - \frac{a+b}{2} \right) dt + \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b \left| W_2(\alpha, t) - W(\alpha) \right| \left(t - \frac{a+b}{2} \right) dt \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Since f' is an L -Lipschitzian function, from equality (3), it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{80} \left[27f\left(\frac{5a+b}{6}\right) + 26f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 27f\left(\frac{a+5b}{6}\right) \right] W(\alpha) \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2} \left[I_{a^+}^\alpha fw\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + I_{b^-}^\alpha fw\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+5b}{6}} \left| W_2(\alpha, t) - \frac{13}{40}W(\alpha) \right| |f'(t) - f'(a+b-t)| dt \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b \left| W_2(\alpha, t) - W(\alpha) \right| |f'(t) - f'(a+b-t)| dt \right\} \\ & \leq \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+5b}{6}} \left| W_2(\alpha, t) - \frac{13}{40}W(\alpha) \right| L |2t - (a+b)| dt \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b \left| W_2(\alpha, t) - W(\alpha) \right| L |2t - (a+b)| dt \right\} \\ & = L \left[\int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+5b}{6}} \left| W_2(\alpha, t) - \frac{13}{40}W(\alpha) \right| \left(t - \frac{a+b}{2} \right) dt \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b \left| W_2(\alpha, t) - W(\alpha) \right| \left(t - \frac{a+b}{2} \right) dt \right]. \end{aligned}$$

□

Remark 2.3. If we let $w(t) = 1$ for all $t \in [a, b]$ in Theorem 2.2, the result simplifies to the fractional corrected Euler-Maclaurin-type inequality given by Kara et al. [8, Theorem 9].

Corollary 2.3. For $\alpha = 1$, Theorem 2.2 gives the following weighted corrected Euler-Maclaurin-type inequality

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{80} \left[27f\left(\frac{5a+b}{6}\right) + 26f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 27f\left(\frac{a+5b}{6}\right) \right] \int_a^b w(t)dt - \int_a^b w(t)f(t)dt \right| \\ & \leq 2L \left\{ \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+5b}{6}} \left| \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^t w(u)du - \frac{13}{80} \int_a^b w(u)du \right| \left(t - \frac{a+b}{2} \right) dt \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b w(u) \left[\frac{(35a+31b)(a+5b)}{72} + \frac{u[u-(a+b)]}{2} \right] du \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. This follows from the fact that

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b |W_2(1, t) - W(1)| \left(t - \frac{a+b}{2} \right) dt &= \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b \int_t^b w(u) \left(t - \frac{a+b}{2} \right) dudt \\ &= \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^u w(u) \left(t - \frac{a+b}{2} \right) dtdu \\ &= \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b w(u) \left[\frac{(a+5b)(35a+31b)}{72} + \frac{u[u-(a+b)]}{2} \right] du. \end{aligned}$$

□

Remark 2.4. By setting $w(t) = 1$ for all $t \in [a, b]$, Corollary 2.3 reduces to the corrected Euler-Maclaurin-type inequality established by Kara et al. [8, Corollary 6].

Next, we focus on representing weighted corrected Euler-Maclaurin-type inequalities in terms of fractional integrals for functions of bounded variation.

Theorem 2.3. Let $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a function of bounded variation on $[a, b]$. Then, the following inequality holds:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{80} \left[27f\left(\frac{5a+b}{6}\right) + 26f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 27f\left(\frac{a+5b}{6}\right) \right] W(\alpha) - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2} \left[I_{a^+}^\alpha fw\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + I_{b^-}^\alpha fw\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \max \left\{ \frac{13}{40} W(\alpha), \left| W_2\left(\alpha, \frac{a+5b}{6}\right) - W(\alpha) \right|, \left| W_2\left(\alpha, \frac{a+5b}{6}\right) - \frac{13}{40} W(\alpha) \right| \right\} \bigvee_a^b(f). \end{aligned}$$

Here, $\bigvee_a^b(f)$ represents the total variation of f on $[a, b]$.

Proof. Consider the function $K_w(\alpha, x)$ defined by

$$K_w(\alpha, x) = \begin{cases} W_1(\alpha, t) - W(\alpha), & a \leq x < \frac{5a+b}{6}, \\ W_1(\alpha, t) - \frac{13}{40}W(\alpha), & \frac{5a+b}{6} \leq x < \frac{a+b}{2}, \\ W_2(\alpha, t) - \frac{13}{40}W(\alpha), & \frac{a+b}{2} \leq x < \frac{a+5b}{6}, \\ W_2(\alpha, t) - W(\alpha), & \frac{a+5b}{6} \leq x \leq b. \end{cases}$$

The following result follows directly from an application of integration by parts

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2} \int_a^b K_w(\alpha, x) df(x) &= \frac{1}{80} \left[27f\left(\frac{5a+b}{6}\right) + 26f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 27f\left(\frac{a+5b}{6}\right) \right] W(\alpha) \\ &\quad - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2} \left[I_{a^+}^\alpha fw\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + I_{b^-}^\alpha fw\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

It is obtained that if $g, f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are such that g is continuous on $[a, b]$ and f is of bounded variation on $[a, b]$, then $\int_a^b g(t)df(t)$ exists and

$$\left| \int_a^b g(t)df(t) \right| \leq \sup_{t \in [a, b]} |g(t)| \bigvee_a^b(f). \quad (9)$$

Using (8), we derive

$$\begin{aligned} &\left| \frac{1}{80} \left[27f\left(\frac{5a+b}{6}\right) + 26f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 27f\left(\frac{a+5b}{6}\right) \right] W(\alpha) \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2} \left[I_{a^+}^\alpha fw\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + I_{b^-}^\alpha fw\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right] \right| \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \left| \int_a^b K_w(\alpha, x) df(x) \right|. \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

In the light of (9), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \int_a^b K_w(\alpha, x) df(x) \right| &\leq \left| \int_a^{\frac{5a+b}{6}} [W_1(\alpha, t) - W(\alpha)] df(x) \right| + \left| \int_{\frac{5a+b}{6}}^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \left[W_1(\alpha, t) - \frac{13}{40}W(\alpha) \right] df(x) \right| \\ &\quad + \left| \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+5b}{6}} \left[W_2(\alpha, t) - \frac{13}{40}W(\alpha) \right] df(x) \right| + \left| \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b [W_2(\alpha, t) - W(\alpha)] df(x) \right| \\ &\leq \sup_{x \in [a, \frac{5a+b}{6}]} |W_1(\alpha, t) - W(\alpha)| \bigvee_a^{\frac{5a+b}{6}}(f) + \sup_{x \in [\frac{5a+b}{6}, \frac{a+b}{2}]} \left| W_1(\alpha, t) - \frac{13}{40}W(\alpha) \right| \bigvee_{\frac{5a+b}{6}}^{\frac{a+b}{2}}(f) \\ &\quad + \sup_{x \in [\frac{a+b}{2}, \frac{a+5b}{6}]} \left| W_2(\alpha, t) - \frac{13}{40}W(\alpha) \right| \bigvee_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+5b}{6}}(f) + \sup_{x \in [\frac{a+5b}{6}, b]} |W_2(\alpha, t) - W(\alpha)| \bigvee_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b(f) \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \sup_{x \in [\frac{a+b}{2}, \frac{a+5b}{6}]} \left| W_2(\alpha, t) - \frac{13}{40} W(\alpha) \right| \bigvee_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+5b}{6}}(f) + \sup_{x \in [\frac{a+5b}{6}, b]} |W_2(\alpha, t) - W(\alpha)| \bigvee_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b(f) \\
 & = \left| W_1\left(\alpha, \frac{5a+b}{6}\right) - W(\alpha) \right| \bigvee_a^{\frac{5a+b}{6}}(f) \\
 & \quad + \max \left\{ \left| W_1\left(\alpha, \frac{5a+b}{6}\right) - \frac{13}{40} W(\alpha) \right|, \frac{13}{40} W(\alpha) \right\} \bigvee_{\frac{5a+b}{6}}^{\frac{a+b}{2}}(f) \\
 & \quad + \max \left\{ \frac{13}{40} W(\alpha), \left| W_2\left(\alpha, \frac{a+5b}{6}\right) - \frac{13}{40} W(\alpha) \right| \right\} \bigvee_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+5b}{6}}(f) \\
 & \quad + \left| W_2\left(\alpha, \frac{a+5b}{6}\right) - W(\alpha) \right| \bigvee_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b(f) \\
 & \leq \max \left\{ \frac{13}{40} W(\alpha), \left| W_2\left(\alpha, \frac{a+5b}{6}\right) - W(\alpha) \right|, \left| W_2\left(\alpha, \frac{a+5b}{6}\right) - \frac{13}{40} W(\alpha) \right| \right\} \bigvee_a^b(f).
 \end{aligned}$$

Because w is symmetric with respect to $\frac{a+b}{2}$, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 W_1\left(\alpha, \frac{5a+b}{6}\right) &= \int_{\frac{5a+b}{6}}^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \left(\frac{a+b}{2} - u\right)^{\alpha-1} w(u) du \\
 &= \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \left(t - \frac{a+b}{2}\right)^{\alpha-1} w(a+b-t) dt \\
 &= \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \left(t - \frac{a+b}{2}\right)^{\alpha-1} w(t) dt \\
 &= W_2\left(\alpha, \frac{a+5b}{6}\right).
 \end{aligned}$$

The desired result is obtained by inserting inequality (11) into (10). □

Remark 2.5. When $w(t) = 1$ for all $t \in [a, b]$ in Theorem 2.3, we deduce the corrected Euler-Maclaurin-type inequality established by Kara et al. [8, Theorem 10].

Corollary 2.4. If we choose $\alpha = 1$ in Theorem 2.3, then we get the following weighted corrected Euler-Maclaurin-type inequality:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \frac{1}{80} \left[27f\left(\frac{5a+b}{6}\right) + 26f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 27f\left(\frac{a+5b}{6}\right) \right] \int_a^b w(t) dt - \int_a^b w(t) f(t) dt \right| \\
 & \leq \max \left\{ \frac{13}{80} \int_a^b w(t) dt, \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^{\frac{a+b}{2}} w(t) dt, \left| \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^{\frac{a+b}{2}} w(t) dt - \frac{13}{80} \int_a^b w(t) dt \right| \right\} \bigvee_a^b(f).
 \end{aligned}$$

Remark 2.6. Setting $w(t) = 1$ for all $t \in [a, b]$ in Corollary 2.4, we recover the corrected Euler-Maclaurin-type inequality of Kara et al. in [8, Corollary 7].

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New Milne-type Inequalities for Lipschitzian Functions by Conformable Fractional Operators

Fatih Hezenci

Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Science and Arts, Duzce University, Duzce 81620,
Türkiye

Corresponding author: fatihezenci@gmail.com

ORCID IDs:

First Author: [0000-0003-1008-5856](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1008-5856)

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Abstract

In this paper, new Milne-type inequalities are proved by conformable fractional operators for Lipschitzian functions. Moreover, some results are presented by using specific functions and suitable parameters of the obtained theorem. This shows how the general results reduce to simpler and more familiar inequalities. Furthermore, these results may be further generalized by examining other classes of convex functions or by employing different fractional integral operators.

Keywords: Milne-type inequalities, Lipschitzian functions, Conformable fractional operators.

1 Introduction

Many mathematicians have investigated numerical integration formulas and their corresponding error bounds using various analytical methods. In this context, numerous mathematical inequalities have been established for different classes of functions, such as convex, bounded, and Lipschitz functions. For instance, Dragomir and Agarwal [1] derived error bounds for the trapezoidal inequalities by employing the properties of convex functions. In another study, Dragomir [2] is introduced Simpson-type inequalities and examined their applications to quadrature formulas within numerical analysis. Moreover, Budak et al. [3] studied several forms of Simpson-type inequalities for differentiable convex functions in the framework of generalized fractional integrals.

The three-point Newton-Cotes quadrature rule, commonly known as Simpson's second rule, has a significant role in numerical integration. Since it employs three-point quadratic kernels, these formulas are often referred to as Newton-type results. Milne-type inequalities can be viewed as extensions of Newton-type formulas, using higher-order or generalized kernels to achieve better approximation accuracy. Recently, several studies have focused on deriving and extending Milne-type inequalities by using convexity properties and fractional integral operators, which provide wider applications in numerical analysis. For instance, in [4], some error bounds for Newton-type inequalities in numerical integration have been established by employing convex

functions. Likewise, certain Newton-type inequalities based on convexity are presented in [5], along with applications to specific cases of real functions. Several new estimates of Milne's quadrature rule have been derived by Djenaoui and Meftah [6], particularly for functions whose first derivative is s -convex. The paper [7] presents error bounds for Milne-type inequalities applied to functions of bounded variation. Moreover, in [8], fractional Milne-type inequalities are derived using differentiable convex functions. For more details, the reader is referred to the paper [9].

2 Preliminaries

Let us put forth some preliminaries which will be utilized in the sequel.

- i. Simpson's quadrature formula (Simpson's 1/3 rule) is formulated as follows:

$$\int_a^b f(x) dx \approx \frac{b-a}{6} \left[f(a) + 4f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right]. \quad (1)$$

- ii. Simpson's second formula or Newton-Cotes quadrature formula (Simpson's 3/8 rule (cf. [10])) is formulated as follows:

$$\int_a^b f(x) dx \approx \frac{b-a}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right]. \quad (2)$$

Formulae (1) and (2) are provided for any function f with continuous 4th derivative on $[a, b]$.

The most popular Newton-Cotes quadrature involving three-point is Simpson-type inequality is as follows:

Theorem 2.1. If $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a four times continuously differentiable function on (a, b) , and $\|f^{(4)}\|_{\infty} = \sup_{x \in (a,b)} |f^{(4)}(x)| < \infty$, then one has the following inequality

$$\left| \frac{1}{6} \left[f(a) + 4f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{1}{2880} \|f^{(4)}\|_{\infty} (b-a)^4.$$

One of the classical closed type quadrature rules is the Simpson 3/8 rule based on the Simpson 3/8 inequality as follows:

Theorem 2.2 (See [10]). If $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a four times continuously differentiable function on (a, b) , and $\|f^{(4)}\|_{\infty} = \sup_{x \in (a,b)} |f^{(4)}(x)| < \infty$, then one has the inequality

$$\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{1}{6480} \|f^{(4)}\|_{\infty} (b-a)^4.$$

By using the Newton-Cotes formulas, the Milne's formula which is of open type is parallel to the Simpson's formula which is of closed type, since they are held under the same conditions.

Theorem 2.3 (See [11]). Let $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ denote a four times continuously differentiable mapping on (a, b) , and let $\|f^{(4)}\|_\infty = \sup_{x \in (a, b)} |f^{(4)}(x)| < \infty$. Then, one has the inequality

$$\left| \frac{1}{3} \left[2f(a) - f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 2f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{7(b-a)^4}{23040} \|f^{(4)}\|_\infty. \quad (3)$$

For building our main results, the main definitions of Riemann-Liouville integrals and conformable integrals, which are well known in the literature, are presented as follows:

Definition 2.1. The gamma function, beta function, and incomplete beta function are defined

$$\Gamma(x) := \int_0^\infty t^{x-1} e^{-t} dt,$$

$$\mathfrak{B}(x, y) := \int_0^1 t^{x-1} (1-t)^{y-1} dt,$$

and

$$\mathcal{B}(x, y, r) := \int_0^r t^{x-1} (1-t)^{y-1} dt,$$

respectively for $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^+$.

Definition 2.2 (See [12]). The Riemann-Liouville integrals $J_{a+}^\beta f(x)$ and $J_{b-}^\beta f(x)$ of order $\beta > 0$ are given by

$$J_{a+}^\beta f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_a^x (x-t)^{\beta-1} f(t) dt, \quad x > a \quad (4)$$

and

$$J_{b-}^\beta f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_x^b (t-x)^{\beta-1} f(t) dt, \quad x < b, \quad (5)$$

respectively for $f \in L_1[a, b]$. The Riemann-Liouville integrals equals to the classical integrals for the case of $\beta = 1$.

Jarad et al. investigated the fractional conformable integral operators in paper [13]. They also provided certain characteristics and relationships between these operators and several other fractional operators. The fractional conformable integral operators are defined as follows:

Definition 2.3 (See [13]). The fractional conformable integral operator ${}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{a+}^\alpha f(x)$ and ${}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{b-}^\alpha f(x)$ of order $\beta \in \mathbb{C}$, $Re(\beta) > 0$ and $\alpha \in (0, 1]$ are described by

$${}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{a+}^\alpha f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_a^x \left(\frac{(x-a)^\alpha - (t-a)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^{\beta-1} \frac{f(t)}{(t-a)^{1-\alpha}} dt, \quad t > a \quad (6)$$

and

$${}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{b-}^\alpha f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_x^b \left(\frac{(b-x)^\alpha - (b-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^{\beta-1} \frac{f(t)}{(b-t)^{1-\alpha}} dt, \quad t < b, \quad (7)$$

respectively for $f \in L_1[a, b]$.

If we choose $\alpha = 1$, then the fractional integral in (6) and (7) coincides with the Riemann-Liouville fractional integral in (4) and (5), respectively. Some recent results according to fractional integral inequalities, see [15, 16] and the references cited therein.

3 An essential identity

Lemma 3.1 (See [14]). Let us note that $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is an absolutely continuous function (a, b) so that $f' \in L_1[a, b]$. Then, the following equality holds:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{3} \left[2f \left(\frac{a+3b}{4} \right) - f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + 2f \left(\frac{3a+b}{4} \right) \right] - \frac{\alpha^\beta \Gamma(\beta+1)}{2(b-a)^{\alpha\beta}} \left[{}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{b-}^\alpha f(a) + {}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{a+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \quad (8) \\ & = \frac{\alpha^\beta (b-a)}{2} \sum_{i=1}^4 I_i, \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} I_1 &= \int_0^{\frac{1}{4}} \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta [f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)] dt, \\ I_2 &= \int_{\frac{1}{4}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left[\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{2}{3\alpha^\beta} \right] [f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)] dt, \\ I_3 &= \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{3}{4}} \left[\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{3\alpha^\beta} \right] [f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)] dt, \\ I_4 &= \int_{\frac{3}{4}}^1 \left[\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{\alpha^\beta} \right] [f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)] dt. \end{aligned} \right.$$

4 Milne-type inequalities for Lipschitzian functions

In this section, we consider some Milne-type inequalities for Lipschitzian functions by using conformable fractional integrals.

Theorem 4.1. Suppose that the assumptions of Lemma 3.1 are valid. If f' is a L -Lipschitzian function on $[a, b]$, then the following inequality holds:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{3} \left[2f \left(\frac{a+3b}{4} \right) - f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + 2f \left(\frac{3a+b}{4} \right) \right] - \frac{\alpha^\beta \Gamma(\alpha+1)}{2(b-a)^{\alpha\beta}} \left[{}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{b-}^\alpha f(a) + {}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{a+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{\alpha^\beta (b-a)^2}{2} L \{ \Omega_1(\alpha, \beta) - 2\Omega_5(\alpha, \beta) + \Omega_2(\alpha, \beta) - 2\Omega_6(\alpha, \beta) \\ & \quad + 2\Omega_7(\alpha, \beta) - \Omega_3(\alpha, \beta) + 2\Omega_8(\alpha, \beta) - \Omega_4(\alpha, \beta) \}. \end{aligned}$$

Here,

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \Omega_1(\alpha, \beta) = \int_0^{\frac{1}{4}} \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta \right| dt = \frac{1}{\alpha^{\beta+1}} \left[\mathfrak{B} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha}, \beta + 1 \right) - \mathcal{B} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha}, \beta + 1, \left(\frac{3}{4} \right)^\alpha \right) \right], \\ \Omega_2(\alpha, \beta) = \int_{\frac{1}{4}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{2}{3\alpha^\beta} \right| dt, \\ \Omega_3(\alpha, \beta) = \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{3}{4}} \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{3\alpha^\beta} \right| dt, \\ \Omega_4(\alpha, \beta) = \int_{\frac{3}{4}}^1 \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{\alpha^\beta} \right| dt = \frac{1}{4\alpha^\beta} - \frac{1}{\alpha^{\beta+1}} \mathcal{B} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha}, \beta + 1, \left(\frac{1}{4} \right)^\alpha \right), \end{array} \right.$$

and

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \Omega_5(\alpha, \beta) = \int_0^{\frac{1}{4}} \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta \right| t dt \\ = \frac{1}{\alpha^{\beta+1}} \left[\mathfrak{B} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha}, \beta + 1 \right) - \mathcal{B} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha}, \beta + 1, \left(\frac{3}{4} \right)^\alpha \right) - \mathfrak{B} \left(\frac{2}{\alpha}, \beta + 1 \right) + \mathcal{B} \left(\frac{2}{\alpha}, \beta + 1, \left(\frac{3}{4} \right)^\alpha \right) \right] \\ \Omega_6(\alpha, \beta) = \int_{\frac{1}{4}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{2}{3\alpha^\beta} \right| t dt, \\ \Omega_7(\alpha, \beta) = \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{3}{4}} \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{3\alpha^\beta} \right| t dt, \\ \Omega_8(\alpha, \beta) = \int_{\frac{3}{4}}^1 \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{\alpha^\beta} \right| t dt \\ = \frac{7}{32\alpha^\beta} - \frac{1}{\alpha^{\beta+1}} \left[\mathcal{B} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha}, \beta + 1, \left(\frac{1}{4} \right)^\alpha \right) - \mathcal{B} \left(\frac{2}{\alpha}, \beta + 1, \left(\frac{1}{4} \right)^\alpha \right) \right]. \end{array} \right.$$

Proof. With the aid of Lemma 3.1 and since f' is L -Lipschitzian function, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{3} \left[2f \left(\frac{a+3b}{4} \right) - f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + 2f \left(\frac{3a+b}{4} \right) \right] \right. \\ & \left. - \frac{\alpha^\beta \Gamma(\alpha+1)}{2(b-a)^{\alpha\beta}} \left[{}^\beta \mathcal{J}_b^\alpha f(a) + {}^\beta \mathcal{J}_a^\alpha f(b) \right] \right| = \left| \frac{\alpha^\beta (b-a)}{2} \right. \\ & \left. \times \int_0^{\frac{1}{4}} \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta [f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)] dt \right. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \int_{\frac{1}{4}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left[\left(\frac{1 - (1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{2}{3\alpha^\beta} \right] [f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)] dt \\
 & + \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{3}{4}} \left[\left(\frac{1 - (1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{3\alpha^\beta} \right] [f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)] dt \\
 & + \int_{\frac{3}{4}}^1 \left[\left(\frac{1 - (1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{\alpha^\beta} \right] [f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)] dt \Bigg\} \\
 & \leq \frac{\alpha^\beta (b-a)}{2} \left\{ \int_0^{\frac{1}{4}} \left| \left(\frac{1 - (1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta \right| |f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)| dt \right. \\
 & + \int_{\frac{1}{4}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left| \left(\frac{1 - (1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{2}{3\alpha^\beta} \right| |f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)| dt \\
 & + \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{3}{4}} \left| \left(\frac{1 - (1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{3\alpha^\beta} \right| |f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)| dt \\
 & \left. + \int_{\frac{3}{4}}^1 \left| \left(\frac{1 - (1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{\alpha^\beta} \right| |f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)| dt \right\} \\
 & \leq \frac{\alpha^\beta (b-a)}{2} \left\{ \int_0^{\frac{1}{4}} \left| \left(\frac{1 - (1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta \right| L(1-2t)(b-a) dt \right. \\
 & + \int_{\frac{1}{4}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left| \left(\frac{1 - (1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{2}{3\alpha^\beta} \right| L(1-2t)(b-a) dt \\
 & \left. + \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{3}{4}} \left| \left(\frac{1 - (1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{3\alpha^\beta} \right| L(1-2t)(b-a) dt \right. \\
 & \left. + \int_{\frac{3}{4}}^1 \left| \left(\frac{1 - (1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{\alpha^\beta} \right| L(1-2t)(b-a) dt \right\}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{3}{4}} \left| \left(\frac{1 - (1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{3\alpha^\beta} \right| L(2t-1)(b-a) dt \\
& + \int_{\frac{3}{4}}^1 \left| \left(\frac{1 - (1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{\alpha^\beta} \right| L(2t-1)(b-a) dt \Bigg\} = \frac{\alpha^\beta (b-a)^2}{2} L \\
& \times \{ \Omega_1(\alpha, \beta) - 2\Omega_5(\alpha, \beta) + \Omega_2(\alpha, \beta) - 2\Omega_6(\alpha, \beta) \\
& + 2\Omega_7(\alpha, \beta) - \Omega_3(\alpha, \beta) + 2\Omega_8(\alpha, \beta) - \Omega_4(\alpha, \beta) \}
\end{aligned}$$

□

Remark 4.1. By taking $\alpha = 1$ in Theorem 4.1, the following Milne-type inequality holds:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left| \frac{1}{3} \left[2f\left(\frac{a+3b}{4}\right) - f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{3a+b}{4}\right) \right] - \frac{\Gamma(\beta+1)}{2(b-a)^\beta} [J_{a+}^\beta f(b) + J_{b-}^\beta f(a)] \right| \\
& \leq \frac{(b-a)^2}{2} L \{ \Omega_1(1, \beta) - 2\Omega_5(1, \beta) + \Omega_2(1, \beta) - 2\Omega_6(1, \beta) \\
& + 2\Omega_7(1, \beta) - \Omega_3(1, \beta) + 2\Omega_8(1, \beta) - \Omega_4(1, \beta) \}.
\end{aligned}$$

This is established by Hezenci and Budak in paper [17, Theorem 5].

Remark 4.2. Let us consider $\beta = 1$ and $\alpha = 1$ in Theorem 4.1. Then, the following Milne-type inequality holds:

$$\left| \frac{1}{3} \left[2f\left(\frac{3a+b}{4}\right) - f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{a+3b}{4}\right) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(t) dt \right| \leq \frac{(b-a)^2}{24} L.$$

This is established by Hezenci and Budak in paper [17, Corollary 4]. This inequality helps us to establish the error bound for Milne's rule.

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Milne Formula for Functions of Bounded Variation via Generalized Fractional Integrals

Fatih Hezenci

Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Science and Arts, Duzce University, Duzce 81620,
Türkiye

Corresponding author: fatihezenci@gmail.com

ORCID IDs:

First Author: [0000-0003-1008-5856](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1008-5856)

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Abstract

In this paper, some Milne formulas are established by generalized fractional integrals for functions of bounded variation. By choosing particular functions and suitable parameter values, several important special cases can be derived, which clearly illustrate the wide applicability of the proposed approach. This allows us to see how the general results reduce to simpler and more familiar formulas. The results improve the understanding of fractional inequalities and offer a solid mathematical basis for future research in fractional analysis and related fields. Namely, one may consider generalizing our findings by exploring alternative classes of convex functions or different types of fractional integral operators.

Keywords: Milne formula, functions of bounded variation, generalized fractional integrals.

1 Introduction

Many mathematicians have studied numerical integration formulas and their error bounds using different methods. To find these error bounds, they have also explored many mathematical inequalities for various kinds of functions, such as convex, bounded, and Lipschitz functions. For example, in papers [1, 2], some error bounds for the midpoint and trapezoidal inequalities in numerical integration are obtained by using convex functions. In [3], Simpson-type inequalities are introduced, and their applications to quadrature inequalities within the context of numerical analysis are investigated. Furthermore, Budak et al. [4] are studied several forms of Simpson-type inequalities for differentiable convex functions within the setting of generalized fractional integrals.

The three-point Newton-Cotes quadrature rule, commonly known as Simpson's second rule, has a significant role in numerical integration. Since it employs three-point quadratic kernels, these formulas are often referred to as Newton-type results. Milne-type inequalities can be viewed as extensions of Newton-type formulas, using higher-order or generalized kernels to achieve better approximation accuracy. Recently, several studies have focused on deriving and extending Milne-type inequalities by using convexity properties and fractional integral operators, which provide wider applications in numerical analysis. For instance, in [5], some error bounds for Newton-type inequalities in numerical integration have been established by employing convex

functions. Likewise, certain Newton-type inequalities based on convexity are presented in [6], along with applications to specific cases of real functions. Several new estimates of Milne's quadrature rule have been derived by Djenaoui and Meftah [7], particularly for functions whose first derivative is s -convex. The paper [8] presents error bounds for Milne-type inequalities applied to functions of bounded variation. Moreover, in [9], fractional Milne-type inequalities are derived using differentiable convex functions. The study [10] establishes error bounds for Milne's formula, an open Newton-Cotes quadrature rule, for differentiable convex functions using both classical and fractional calculus approaches. For further details, one may refer to [11, 12, 13], as well as the references cited therein.

2 Preliminaries

Generalized fractional integrals are extensions of classical fractional integrals that allow integration of functions with respect to more general kernels or parameters. For example, Sarikaya and Ertugral established Hermite–Hadamard-type inequalities for generalized fractional integrals [14].

Definition 2.1. [14] Let $\varphi : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ the condition $\int_0^1 \frac{\varphi(t)}{t} dt < \infty$. Then, the following left-sided and right-sided generalized fractional integral operators are described as

$${}_a I_{\varphi} f(x) = \int_a^x \frac{\varphi(x-t)}{x-t} f(t) dt, \quad x > a \quad (1)$$

and

$${}_b I_{\varphi} f(x) = \int_x^b \frac{\varphi(t-x)}{t-x} f(t) dt, \quad x < b, \quad (2)$$

respectively.

The most important feature of generalized fractional integrals is that they generalize some important types of fractional integrals such as Riemann-Liouville fractional integral, k -Riemann-Liouville fractional integral, conformable fractional integral, Katugampola fractional integrals, Hadamard fractional integrals etc. The important special cases of the integral operators (1) and (2) are as follows:

- i. If we choose $\varphi(t) = t$, then the operators (1) and (2) become to the Riemann integral.
- ii. Let us consider $\varphi(t) = \frac{t^{\alpha}}{\Gamma(\alpha)}$ and $\alpha > 0$. Then, the operators (1) and (2) coincide with the Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals $J_{a+}^{\alpha} f(x)$ and $J_{b-}^{\alpha} f(x)$, respectively [15, 16]. Here,

$$J_{a+}^{\alpha} f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_a^x (x-t)^{\alpha-1} f(t) dt, \quad x > a$$

and

$$J_{b-}^{\alpha} f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_x^b (t-x)^{\alpha-1} f(t) dt, \quad x < b.$$

The symbol Γ represents the Gamma function, which is defined by the integral

$$\Gamma(x) := \int_0^{\infty} t^{x-1} e^{-t} dt, \quad x \in \mathbb{R}^+.$$

iii. When $\varphi(t) = \frac{1}{k\Gamma_k(\alpha)}t^{\frac{\alpha}{k}}$ and $\alpha, k > 0$, the integral operators (1) and (2) specialize to the k -Riemann–Liouville fractional integrals $J_{a+,k}^\alpha f(x)$ and $J_{b-,k}^\alpha f(x)$, respectively. Here,

$$J_{a+,k}^\alpha f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma_k(\alpha)} \int_a^x (x-t)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}-1} f(t) dt, \quad x > a$$

and

$$J_{b-,k}^\alpha f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma_k(\alpha)} \int_x^b (t-x)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}-1} f(t) dt, \quad x < b.$$

Γ_k is k -Gamma function defined by

$$\Gamma_k(\alpha) = \int_0^\infty t^{\alpha-1} e^{-\frac{t^k}{k}} dt, \quad \Re(\alpha) > 0$$

and

$$\Gamma_k(\alpha) = k^{\frac{\alpha}{k}-1} \Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha}{k}\right), \quad \Re(\alpha) > 0; k > 0.$$

3 Main results

Lemma 3.1. Let us consider that $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is an absolutely continuous function (a, b) so that $f' \in L_1[a, b]$. Then, the following equality holds:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{3} \left[2f\left(\frac{3a+b}{4}\right) - f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{a+3b}{4}\right) \right] - \frac{1}{2\Lambda(1)} [b-I_\varphi f(a) + a+I_\varphi f(b)] \\ & = \frac{b-a}{2\Lambda(1)} \int_a^b \psi(x) df(x) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Here, $\Lambda(t) = \int_0^t \frac{\varphi((b-a)y)}{y} dy$ and

$$\psi(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{b-a} \left[\Lambda\left(\frac{x-a}{b-a}\right) - \Lambda\left(\frac{b-x}{b-a}\right) + \Lambda(1) \right], & a \leq x \leq \frac{3a+b}{4}, \\ \frac{1}{b-a} \left[\Lambda\left(\frac{x-a}{b-a}\right) - \Lambda\left(\frac{b-x}{b-a}\right) - \frac{1}{3}\Lambda(1) \right], & \frac{3a+b}{4} < x \leq \frac{a+b}{2}, \\ \frac{1}{b-a} \left[\Lambda\left(\frac{x-a}{b-a}\right) - \Lambda\left(\frac{b-x}{b-a}\right) + \frac{1}{3}\Lambda(1) \right], & \frac{a+b}{2} < x \leq \frac{a+3b}{4}, \\ \frac{1}{b-a} \left[\Lambda\left(\frac{x-a}{b-a}\right) - \Lambda\left(\frac{b-x}{b-a}\right) - \Lambda(1) \right], & \frac{a+3b}{4} < x \leq b. \end{cases}$$

Proof. Let us first consider the function $\psi(x)$. Then, with the help of the integrating by parts, it follows from that

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_a^b \psi(x) df(x) \\ & = \frac{1}{b-a} \left\{ \int_a^{\frac{3a+b}{4}} \left[\Lambda\left(\frac{x-a}{b-a}\right) - \Lambda\left(\frac{b-x}{b-a}\right) + \Lambda(1) \right] df(x) \right. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} &+ \int_{\frac{3a+b}{4}}^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \left[\Lambda \left(\frac{x-a}{b-a} \right) - \Lambda \left(\frac{b-x}{b-a} \right) - \frac{1}{3} \Lambda(1) \right] df(x) \\ &+ \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+3b}{4}} \left[\Lambda \left(\frac{x-a}{b-a} \right) - \Lambda \left(\frac{b-x}{b-a} \right) + \frac{1}{3} \Lambda(1) \right] df(x) \\ &+ \int_{\frac{a+3b}{4}}^b \left[\Lambda \left(\frac{x-a}{b-a} \right) - \Lambda \left(\frac{b-x}{b-a} \right) - \Lambda(1) \right] df(x) \end{aligned} \right\}$$

In a similar way, we get

$$\begin{aligned} &\int_a^{\frac{3a+b}{4}} \left[\Lambda \left(\frac{x-a}{b-a} \right) - \Lambda \left(\frac{b-x}{b-a} \right) + \Lambda(1) \right] df(x) \tag{5} \\ &= \left[\Lambda \left(\frac{x-a}{b-a} \right) - \Lambda \left(\frac{b-x}{b-a} \right) + \Lambda(1) \right] f(x) \Big|_a^{\frac{3a+b}{4}} - \int_a^{\frac{3a+b}{4}} \left[\frac{\varphi(x-a)}{x-a} + \frac{\varphi(b-x)}{b-x} \right] f(x) dx \\ &= \left(\Lambda \left(\frac{1}{4} \right) - \Lambda \left(\frac{3}{4} \right) + \Lambda(1) \right) f \left(\frac{3a+b}{4} \right) \\ &\quad - \int_a^{\frac{3a+b}{4}} \left[\frac{\varphi(x-a)}{x-a} + \frac{\varphi(b-x)}{b-x} \right] f(x) dx. \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, we have

$$\begin{aligned} &\int_{\frac{3a+b}{4}}^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \left[\Lambda \left(\frac{x-a}{b-a} \right) - \Lambda \left(\frac{b-x}{b-a} \right) - \frac{1}{3} \Lambda(1) \right] df(x) \tag{6} \\ &= \left[\Lambda \left(\frac{x-a}{b-a} \right) - \Lambda \left(\frac{b-x}{b-a} \right) - \frac{1}{3} \Lambda(1) \right] f(x) \Big|_{\frac{3a+b}{4}}^{\frac{a+b}{2}} - \int_{\frac{3a+b}{4}}^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \left[\frac{\varphi(x-a)}{x-a} + \frac{\varphi(b-x)}{b-x} \right] f(x) dx \\ &= -\frac{1}{3} \Lambda(1) f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) - \left[\Lambda \left(\frac{1}{4} \right) - \Lambda \left(\frac{3}{4} \right) - \frac{1}{3} \Lambda(1) \right] f \left(\frac{3a+b}{4} \right) \\ &\quad - \int_{\frac{3a+b}{4}}^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \left[\frac{\varphi(x-a)}{x-a} + \frac{\varphi(b-x)}{b-x} \right] f(x) dx, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+3b}{4}} \left[\Lambda \left(\frac{x-a}{b-a} \right) - \Lambda \left(\frac{b-x}{b-a} \right) + \frac{1}{3} \Lambda(1) \right] df(x) \tag{7} \\ &= \left[\Lambda \left(\frac{x-a}{b-a} \right) - \Lambda \left(\frac{b-x}{b-a} \right) + \frac{1}{3} \Lambda(1) \right] f(x) \Big|_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+3b}{4}} - \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+3b}{4}} \left[\frac{\varphi(x-a)}{x-a} + \frac{\varphi(b-x)}{b-x} \right] f(x) dx \\ &= \left[\Lambda \left(\frac{3}{4} \right) - \Lambda \left(\frac{1}{4} \right) + \frac{1}{3} \Lambda(1) \right] f \left(\frac{a+3b}{4} \right) - \frac{1}{3} \Lambda(1) f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$- \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+3b}{4}} \left[\frac{\varphi(x-a)}{x-a} + \frac{\varphi(b-x)}{b-x} \right] f(x) dx,$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\frac{a+3b}{4}}^b \left[\Lambda \left(\frac{x-a}{b-a} \right) - \Lambda \left(\frac{b-x}{b-a} \right) - \Lambda(1) \right] df(x) \tag{8} \\ &= \left[\Lambda \left(\frac{x-a}{b-a} \right) - \Lambda \left(\frac{b-x}{b-a} \right) - \Lambda(1) \right] f(x) \Big|_{\frac{a+3b}{4}}^b - \int_{\frac{a+3b}{4}}^b \left[\frac{\varphi(x-a)}{x-a} + \frac{\varphi(b-x)}{b-x} \right] f(x) dx \\ &= - \left[\Lambda \left(\frac{3}{4} \right) - \Lambda \left(\frac{1}{4} \right) - \Lambda(1) \right] f \left(\frac{a+3b}{4} \right) \\ &\quad - \int_{\frac{a+3b}{4}}^b \left[\frac{\varphi(x-a)}{x-a} + \frac{\varphi(b-x)}{b-x} \right] f(x) dx. \end{aligned}$$

By putting the equalities (5)-(8) in (4), we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_a^b \psi(x) df(x) \\ &= \frac{2\Lambda(1)}{(b-a)} \frac{1}{3} \left[2f \left(\frac{3a+b}{4} \right) - f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + 2f \left(\frac{a+3b}{4} \right) \right] \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b \left[\frac{\varphi(x-a)}{x-a} + \frac{\varphi(b-x)}{b-x} \right] f(x) dx \\ &= \frac{2\Lambda(1)}{(b-a)} \frac{1}{3} \left[2f \left(\frac{3a+b}{4} \right) - f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + 2f \left(\frac{a+3b}{4} \right) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} [{}_{b-}I_{\varphi}f(a) + {}_{a+}I_{\varphi}f(b)]. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, we obtain readily

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{3} \left[2f \left(\frac{3a+b}{4} \right) - f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + 2f \left(\frac{a+3b}{4} \right) \right] - \frac{1}{2\Lambda(1)} [{}_{b-}I_{\varphi}f(a) + {}_{a+}I_{\varphi}f(b)] \\ &= \frac{b-a}{2\Lambda(1)} \int_a^b \psi(x) df(x) \end{aligned}$$

□

Theorem 3.1. Note that $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a function of bounded variation on $[a, b]$. Then, one can obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{3} \left[2f \left(\frac{3a+b}{4} \right) - f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + 2f \left(\frac{a+3b}{4} \right) \right] - \frac{1}{2\Lambda(1)} [{}_{b-}I_{\varphi}f(a) + {}_{a+}I_{\varphi}f(b)] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{1}{2\Lambda(1)} \max \left\{ \left| \Lambda \left(\frac{1}{4} \right) - \Lambda \left(\frac{3}{4} \right) + \Lambda(1) \right| \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left| \Lambda \left(\frac{3}{4} \right) - \Lambda \left(\frac{1}{4} \right) + \frac{1}{3}\Lambda(1) \right| \right\} \bigvee_a^b(f). \end{aligned}$$

Here, $\bigvee_c^d(f)$ denotes the total variation of f on $[c, d]$.

Proof. If we take modules of equality (3), we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{3} \left[2f\left(\frac{3a+b}{4}\right) - f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{a+3b}{4}\right) \right] - \frac{1}{2\Lambda(1)} [{}_{b-}I_{\varphi}f(a) + {}_{a+}I_{\varphi}f(b)] \right| \quad (9) \\ &= \frac{b-a}{2\Lambda(1)} \left| \int_a^b \psi(x) df(x) \right|. \end{aligned}$$

It is well known that if two functions $g, f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ satisfy that g is continuous on $[a, b]$ and f is of bounded variation on $[a, b]$, then the integral

$$\int_a^b g(t) df(t)$$

exists. Then, it yields

$$\left| \int_a^b g(t) df(t) \right| \leq \sup_{t \in [a, b]} |g(t)| \bigvee_a^b(f). \quad (10)$$

With the help of the inequality (10), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \int_a^b \psi(x) df(x) \right| \quad (11) \\ & \leq \frac{1}{b-a} \left\{ \left| \int_a^{\frac{3a+b}{4}} \left[\Lambda\left(\frac{x-a}{b-a}\right) - \Lambda\left(\frac{b-x}{b-a}\right) + \Lambda(1) \right] df(x) \right| \right. \\ & \quad + \left| \int_{\frac{3a+b}{4}}^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \left[\Lambda\left(\frac{x-a}{b-a}\right) - \Lambda\left(\frac{b-x}{b-a}\right) - \frac{1}{3}\Lambda(1) \right] df(x) \right| \\ & \quad + \left| \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+3b}{4}} \left[\Lambda\left(\frac{x-a}{b-a}\right) - \Lambda\left(\frac{b-x}{b-a}\right) + \frac{1}{3}\Lambda(1) \right] df(x) \right| \\ & \quad \left. + \left| \int_{\frac{a+3b}{4}}^b \left[\Lambda\left(\frac{x-a}{b-a}\right) - \Lambda\left(\frac{b-x}{b-a}\right) - \Lambda(1) \right] df(x) \right| \right\} \\ & \leq \frac{1}{b-a} \left\{ \sup_{x \in [a, \frac{3a+b}{4}]} \left| \Lambda\left(\frac{x-a}{b-a}\right) - \Lambda\left(\frac{b-x}{b-a}\right) + \Lambda(1) \right| \bigvee_a^{\frac{3a+b}{4}}(f) \right. \\ & \quad + \sup_{x \in [\frac{3a+b}{4}, \frac{a+b}{2}]} \left| \Lambda\left(\frac{x-a}{b-a}\right) - \Lambda\left(\frac{b-x}{b-a}\right) - \frac{1}{3}\Lambda(1) \right| \bigvee_{\frac{3a+b}{4}}^{\frac{a+b}{2}}(f) \\ & \quad + \sup_{x \in [\frac{a+b}{2}, \frac{a+3b}{4}]} \left| \Lambda\left(\frac{x-a}{b-a}\right) - \Lambda\left(\frac{b-x}{b-a}\right) + \frac{1}{3}\Lambda(1) \right| \bigvee_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+3b}{4}}(f) \\ & \quad \left. + \sup_{x \in [\frac{a+3b}{4}, b]} \left| \Lambda\left(\frac{x-a}{b-a}\right) - \Lambda\left(\frac{b-x}{b-a}\right) - \Lambda(1) \right| \bigvee_{\frac{a+3b}{4}}^b(f) \right\} \\ & = \frac{1}{b-a} \left\{ \left| \Lambda\left(\frac{1}{4}\right) - \Lambda\left(\frac{3}{4}\right) + \Lambda(1) \right| \bigvee_a^{\frac{3a+b}{4}}(f) \right. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + \max \left\{ \frac{1}{3} \Lambda(1), \left| \Lambda\left(\frac{1}{4}\right) - \Lambda\left(\frac{3}{4}\right) - \frac{1}{3} \Lambda(1) \right| \right\} \sqrt[\frac{3a+b}{4}]{\frac{a+b}{2}}(f) \\
& + \max \left\{ \left| \Lambda\left(\frac{3}{4}\right) - \Lambda\left(\frac{1}{4}\right) + \frac{1}{3} \Lambda(1) \right|, \frac{1}{3} \Lambda(1) \right\} \sqrt[\frac{a+3b}{4}]{\frac{a+b}{2}}(f) \\
& + \left| \Lambda\left(\frac{3}{4}\right) - \Lambda\left(\frac{1}{4}\right) - \Lambda(1) \right| \sqrt[\frac{a+3b}{4}]{\frac{b}{a}}(f) \Big\} \\
& \leq \frac{1}{b-a} \max \left\{ \left| \Lambda\left(\frac{1}{4}\right) - \Lambda\left(\frac{3}{4}\right) + \Lambda(1) \right| \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left| \Lambda\left(\frac{3}{4}\right) - \Lambda\left(\frac{1}{4}\right) + \frac{1}{3} \Lambda(1) \right| \right\} \sqrt[\frac{b}{a}]{f}.
\end{aligned}$$

Then, we get the following inequality

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left| \frac{1}{3} \left[2f\left(\frac{3a+b}{4}\right) - f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{a+3b}{4}\right) \right] - \frac{1}{2\Lambda(1)} [{}_b I_{\varphi} f(a) + {}_{a+} I_{\varphi} f(b)] \right| \\
& \leq \frac{1}{2\Lambda(1)} \max \left\{ \left| \Lambda\left(\frac{1}{4}\right) - \Lambda\left(\frac{3}{4}\right) + \Lambda(1) \right| \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left| \Lambda\left(\frac{3}{4}\right) - \Lambda\left(\frac{1}{4}\right) + \frac{1}{3} \Lambda(1) \right| \right\} \sqrt[\frac{b}{a}]{f}.
\end{aligned}$$

which is complete the desired results of Theorem 3.1. \square

Remark 3.1. Consider $\varphi(t) = t$ in Theorem 3.1. Then, the following Milne formula satisfies:

$$\left| \frac{1}{3} \left[2f\left(\frac{a+3b}{4}\right) - f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{3a+b}{4}\right) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(t) dt \right| \leq \frac{5}{12} \sqrt[\frac{b}{a}]{f}.$$

This is established by Unal et al. in [13, Corollary 6].

Remark 3.2. Let us consider $\varphi(t) = \frac{t^{\alpha}}{\Gamma(\alpha)}$ in Theorem 3.1. Then, Theorem 3.1 reduces to [12, Theorem 2.2].

Corollary 3.1. For $\varphi(t) = \frac{1}{k\Gamma_k(\alpha)} t^{\frac{\alpha}{k}}$ in Theorem 3.1, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left| \frac{1}{3} \left[2f\left(\frac{3a+b}{4}\right) - f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{a+3b}{4}\right) \right] - \frac{\Gamma_k(\alpha+k)}{2(b-a)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}}} [J_{a+,k}^{\alpha} f(b) + J_{b-,k}^{\alpha} f(a)] \right| \\
& \leq \frac{1}{2} \max \left\{ \frac{1 - 3^{\frac{\alpha}{k}} + 4^{\frac{\alpha}{k}}}{4^{\frac{\alpha}{k}}}, \frac{3^{\frac{\alpha}{k}} - 1}{4^{\frac{\alpha}{k}}} + \frac{1}{3} \right\} \sqrt[\frac{b}{a}]{f}.
\end{aligned}$$

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Some Error Bounds for Milne's Formula via Fractional Integral Operators

Fatih Hezenci¹, Hüseyin Budak², Hasan Kara¹

¹Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Science and Arts, Duzce University, Duzce 81620, Türkiye

²Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Science and Arts, Kocaeli University, Kocaeli 41001, Türkiye

Corresponding author: fatihezenci@gmail.com

ORCID IDs:

First Author: [0000-0003-1008-5856](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1008-5856)

Second Author: [0000-0001-8843-955X](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8843-955X)

Third Author: [0000-0002-2075-944X](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2075-944X)

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Abstract

This study investigates some Milne-type inequalities for differentiable convex functions. Our main goal is to show how such inequalities can be established by using the power mean inequality, and in doing so, we naturally extend several well-known inequalities in the existing literature to more general forms. Moreover, we study special cases of the main theorem by choosing particular functions and parameters. This allows us to see how the general results reduce to simpler and more familiar inequalities. We also provide an illustrative example in order to clarify the use of our results. Furthermore, graphs are included to make the inequalities more understandable and to demonstrate their validity in practice. Overall, this study presents a useful contribution to the theory of inequalities for differentiable convex functions and may serve as a basis for further research.

Keywords: Milne's formula, quadrature formulae, open Newton-Cotes formulas.

1 Introduction

Fractional calculus is a branch of mathematics that extends the concept of derivatives and integrals to non-integer (fractional) orders. This generalization of classical calculus has proven to be highly effective in various fields such as physics, engineering, and applied sciences. Common definitions of fractional integrals include the Riemann-Liouville, conformable, and tempered fractional integrals, among others. New bounds and integral identities can be derived using a variety of inequality techniques, including Hermite-Hadamard, Simpson-type, as well as Newton and Milne-type inequalities.

One of the most widely used Newton-Cotes quadrature methods, incorporating a three-point Simpson-type inequality, is given as follows:

Theorem 1.1. Let us consider $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a four times continuously differentiable function on (a, b) , and $\|f^{(4)}\|_\infty = \sup_{x \in (a,b)} |f^{(4)}(x)| < \infty$. Then, one has the following inequality

$$\left| \frac{1}{6} \left[f(a) + 4f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{1}{2880} \|f^{(4)}\|_\infty (b-a)^4.$$

Simpson inequalities for differentiable convex functions and their fractional versions have been studied extensively. Simpson-type inequalities and their application to quadrature inequalities in numerical analysis are proved in paper [1]. Moreover, in paper [2], fractional Simpson-type inequalities are investigated for the case of function whose second derivatives in absolute value are convex. Furthermore, in paper [3], some fractional Simpson-type inequalities are proved by functions whose second derivatives in absolute value are convex.

One of the classical closed-type quadrature rules is the Simpson 3/8 rule, which is based on the Simpson 3/8 inequality, formulated as follows:

Theorem 1.2 (See [4]). Let us consider that $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a four times continuously differentiable function on (a, b) , and $\|f^{(4)}\|_\infty = \sup_{x \in (a,b)} |f^{(4)}(x)| < \infty$. Then, the following inequality satisfies:

$$\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{1}{6480} \|f^{(4)}\|_\infty (b-a)^4.$$

Simpson’s second rule is a consequence of the three-point Newton-Cotes quadrature formula, which often leads to the classification of evaluations involving three-step quadratic kernels as Newton-type results. In the literature, such results are commonly referred to as Newton-type inequalities. A considerable number of mathematicians have studied and contributed to the development of these inequalities. For instance, some Newton-type inequalities are presented for the case of functions whose first derivative in absolute value at certain power are arithmetically-harmonically convex in paper [5]. In addition, in paper [6], some Riemann-Liouville fractional Newton-type inequalities were established for functions of bounded variation. Newton-type inequalities are further discussed in papers [7, 8] and the referenced works within those papers provide additional information on this topic.

The open-type Milne formula, derived from Newton-Cotes formulas, is similar to the closed-type Simpson formula in that it holds under the same conditions.

Theorem 1.3 (See [9]). If $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a four times continuously differentiable mapping on (a, b) and $\|f^{(4)}\|_\infty = \sup_{x \in (a,b)} |f^{(4)}(x)| < \infty$. Then, one has the inequality

$$\left| \frac{1}{3} \left[2f(a) - f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 2f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{7(b-a)^4}{23040} \|f^{(4)}\|_\infty.$$

The well-known Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals that are given as follows:

Definition 1.1 (See [10]). The Riemann-Liouville integrals $J_{a+}^\alpha f(x)$ and $J_{b-}^\alpha f(x)$ of order $\alpha > 0$

are given by

$$J_{a+}^{\alpha} f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_a^x (x-t)^{\alpha-1} f(t) dt, \quad x > a$$

and

$$J_{b-}^{\alpha} f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_x^b (t-x)^{\alpha-1} f(t) dt, \quad x < b,$$

respectively for $f \in L_1[a, b]$. The gamma function is defined $\Gamma(x) := \int_0^{\infty} t^{x-1} e^{-t} dt$ for $x \in \mathbb{R}^+$. The Riemann-Liouville integrals are equals to the classical integrals for the case of $\alpha = 1$.

Djenaoui and Meftah [11] established several estimates for Milne's quadrature rule in the case of functions whose first derivative is s -convex. Additionally, Alomari and Liu [12] provided error estimates for Milne's rule applicable to functions of bounded variation and absolutely continuous functions. Moreover, Budak et al. [13] developed fractional versions of Milne's formula by employing differentiable convex functions. For more information about these type of inequalities, one can refer to [14].

Ali et al. [15] computed error bounds using one of the open Newton-Cotes formulas, namely, Milne's formula for differentiable convex functions within both classical and fractional calculus frameworks. To support their main findings, they established the following integral identity:

Lemma 1.1 (See [15]). Let us consider that $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is an absolutely continuous function (a, b) so that $f' \in L_1[a, b]$. Then, the following equality holds:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{3} \left[2f\left(\frac{a+3b}{4}\right) - f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{3a+b}{4}\right) \right] - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{2(b-a)^{\alpha}} [J_{a+}^{\alpha} f(b) + J_{b-}^{\alpha} f(a)] \\ & = \frac{b-a}{2} \sum_{i=1}^4 I_i. \end{aligned}$$

Here,

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} I_1 = \int_0^{\frac{1}{4}} t^{\alpha} [f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)] dt, \\ I_2 = \int_{\frac{1}{4}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(t^{\alpha} - \frac{2}{3}\right) [f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)] dt, \\ I_3 = \int_{\frac{1}{4}}^{\frac{3}{4}} \left(t^{\alpha} - \frac{1}{3}\right) [f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)] dt, \\ I_4 = \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^1 (t^{\alpha} - 1) [f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)] dt. \end{array} \right.$$

2 Main Result

Theorem 2.1. Under the assumptions that Lemma 1.1 holds and the function $|f'|^q$, $q \geq 1$ is convex on $[a, b]$. Then, we have the following Milne's formula

$$\left| \frac{1}{3} \left[2f\left(\frac{a+3b}{4}\right) - f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{3a+b}{4}\right) \right] - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{2(b-a)^{\alpha}} [J_{a+}^{\alpha} f(b) + J_{b-}^{\alpha} f(a)] \right| \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq \frac{b-a}{2} \left\{ (\Omega_1(\alpha))^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left[([\Omega_5(\alpha) |f'(b)|^q + (\Omega_1(\alpha) - \Omega_5(\alpha)) |f'(a)|^q])^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. + ([\Omega_5(\alpha) |f'(a)|^q + (\Omega_1(\alpha) - \Omega_5(\alpha)) |f'(b)|^q])^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \right. \\ &\quad + (\Omega_2(\alpha))^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left[([\Omega_6(\alpha) |f'(b)|^q + (\Omega_2(\alpha) - \Omega_6(\alpha)) |f'(a)|^q])^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + ([\Omega_6(\alpha) |f'(a)|^q + (\Omega_2(\alpha) - \Omega_6(\alpha)) |f'(b)|^q])^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \\ &\quad + (\Omega_3(\alpha))^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left[([\Omega_7(\alpha) |f'(b)|^q + (\Omega_3(\alpha) - \Omega_7(\alpha)) |f'(a)|^q])^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + ([\Omega_7(\alpha) |f'(a)|^q + (\Omega_3(\alpha) - \Omega_7(\alpha)) |f'(b)|^q])^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \\ &\quad + (\Omega_4(\alpha))^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left[([\Omega_8(\alpha) |f'(b)|^q + (\Omega_4(\alpha) - \Omega_8(\alpha)) |f'(a)|^q])^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. + ([\Omega_8(\alpha) |f'(a)|^q + (\Omega_4(\alpha) - \Omega_8(\alpha)) |f'(b)|^q])^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Here,

$$\Omega_1(\alpha) = \int_0^{\frac{1}{4}} t^\alpha dt = \frac{1}{4^{\alpha+1}(\alpha+1)},$$

$$\Omega_2(\alpha) = \int_{\frac{1}{4}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{2}{3} \right| dt = \begin{cases} -\frac{((\alpha+1)2^{\alpha+1}-6)4^\alpha+2^\alpha 3}{12(\alpha+1)2^\alpha 4^\alpha}, & 0 < \alpha \leq \frac{\ln(\frac{2}{3})}{\ln(\frac{1}{4})}, \\ -\frac{(2(\alpha+1)3^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} - \alpha 2^{\frac{1}{\alpha}+3})4^\alpha - 3^{\frac{1}{\alpha}+1}}{12(\alpha+1)3^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} 4^\alpha} \\ -\frac{(2(\alpha+1)3^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} - \alpha 2^{\frac{1}{\alpha}+2})2^\alpha - 3^{\frac{1}{\alpha}+1}}{6(\alpha+1)3^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} 2^\alpha}, & \frac{\ln(\frac{2}{3})}{\ln(\frac{1}{4})} < \alpha \leq \frac{\ln(\frac{2}{3})}{\ln(\frac{1}{2})}, \\ \frac{((\alpha+1)2^{\alpha+1}-6)4^\alpha+2^\alpha 3}{12(\alpha+1)2^\alpha 4^\alpha}, & \alpha > \frac{\ln(\frac{2}{3})}{\ln(\frac{1}{2})}, \end{cases}$$

$$\Omega_3(\alpha) = \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{3}{4}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{3} \right| dt = \begin{cases} \frac{3^{\alpha+1}}{4^{\alpha+1}(\alpha+1)} - \frac{1}{2^{\alpha+1}(\alpha+1)} - \frac{1}{12}, & 0 < \alpha \leq \frac{\ln(\frac{1}{3})}{\ln(\frac{1}{2})}, \\ \frac{3^{\frac{1}{\alpha}+1} - ((\alpha+1)3^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} - 2\alpha)2^\alpha}{6(\alpha+1)3^{\frac{1}{\alpha}}2^\alpha} - \frac{(3(\alpha+1)3^{\frac{1}{\alpha}} - 4\alpha)4^\alpha - 3^{\alpha+\frac{1}{\alpha}+2}}{12(\alpha+1)3^{\frac{1}{\alpha}}4^\alpha}, & \frac{\ln(\frac{1}{3})}{\ln(\frac{1}{2})} < \alpha \leq \frac{\ln(\frac{1}{3})}{\ln(\frac{3}{4})}, \\ \frac{1}{2^{\alpha+1}(\alpha+1)} - \frac{3^{\alpha+1}}{4^{\alpha+1}(\alpha+1)} + \frac{1}{12}, & \alpha > \frac{\ln(\frac{1}{3})}{\ln(\frac{3}{4})}, \end{cases}$$

$$\Omega_4(\alpha) = \int_{\frac{3}{4}}^1 |t^\alpha - 1| dt = \frac{\alpha - 3}{4(\alpha + 1)} + \frac{1}{\alpha + 1} \left(\frac{3}{4}\right)^{\alpha+1}.$$

$$\Omega_5(\alpha) = \int_0^{\frac{1}{4}} t^{\alpha+1} dt = \frac{1}{4^{\alpha+2}(\alpha + 2)},$$

$$\Omega_6(\alpha) = \int_{\frac{1}{4}}^{\frac{1}{2}} t \left| t^\alpha - \frac{2}{3} \right| dt = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\alpha+2} \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^{\alpha+2} - \frac{1}{\alpha+2} \left(\frac{1}{4}\right)^{\alpha+2} - \frac{1}{16}, & 0 < \alpha \leq \frac{\ln(\frac{2}{3})}{\ln(\frac{1}{4})}, \\ \frac{\alpha}{\alpha+2} \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^{1+\frac{2}{\alpha}} + \frac{1}{\alpha+2} \left(\frac{1}{4}\right)^{\alpha+2} + \frac{1}{\alpha+2} \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^{\alpha+2} - \frac{5}{48}, & \frac{\ln(\frac{2}{3})}{\ln(\frac{1}{4})} < \alpha \leq \frac{\ln(\frac{2}{3})}{\ln(\frac{1}{2})}, \\ -\frac{1}{\alpha+2} \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^{\alpha+2} + \frac{1}{\alpha+2} \left(\frac{1}{4}\right)^{\alpha+2} + \frac{1}{16}, & \alpha > \frac{\ln(\frac{2}{3})}{\ln(\frac{1}{2})}, \end{cases}$$

$$\Omega_7(\alpha) = \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{3}{4}} t \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{3} \right| dt = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\alpha+2} \left(\frac{3}{4}\right)^{\alpha+2} - \frac{1}{\alpha+2} \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^{\alpha+2} - \frac{5}{96}, & 0 < \alpha \leq \frac{\ln(\frac{1}{3})}{\ln(\frac{1}{2})}, \\ \frac{\alpha}{\alpha+2} \left(\frac{1}{3}\right)^{1+\frac{2}{\alpha}} + \frac{1}{\alpha+2} \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^{\alpha+2} + \frac{1}{\alpha+2} \left(\frac{3}{4}\right)^{\alpha+2} - \frac{13}{96}, & \frac{\ln(\frac{1}{3})}{\ln(\frac{1}{2})} < \alpha \leq \frac{\ln(\frac{1}{3})}{\ln(\frac{3}{4})}, \\ -\frac{1}{\alpha+2} \left(\frac{3}{4}\right)^{\alpha+2} + \frac{1}{\alpha+2} \left(\frac{1}{2}\right)^{\alpha+2} + \frac{5}{96}, & \alpha > \frac{\ln(\frac{1}{3})}{\ln(\frac{3}{4})}, \end{cases}$$

and

$$\Omega_8(\alpha) = \int_{\frac{3}{4}}^1 t |t^\alpha - 1| dt = \frac{7}{32} - \frac{1}{\alpha + 2} + \frac{1}{\alpha + 2} \left(\frac{3}{4}\right)^{\alpha+2}.$$

Proof. If we initially apply the power-mean inequality to (1), then we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{3} \left[2f\left(\frac{a+3b}{4}\right) - f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{3a+b}{4}\right) \right] - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{2(b-a)^\alpha} [J_{a^+}^\alpha f(b) + J_{b^-}^\alpha f(a)] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{b-a}{2} \left\{ \left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{4}} |t^\alpha| dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{4}} |t^\alpha| |f'(tb + (1-t)a)|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \left(\int_{\frac{1}{4}}^1 |t^\alpha| dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left(\int_{\frac{1}{4}}^1 |t^\alpha| |f'(tb + (1-t)a)|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{4}} |t^\alpha| dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{4}} |t^\alpha| |f'(ta + (1-t)b)|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
 & + \left(\int_{\frac{1}{4}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{2}{3} \right| dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left(\int_{\frac{1}{4}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{2}{3} \right| |f'(tb + (1-t)a)|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
 & + \left(\int_{\frac{1}{4}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{2}{3} \right| dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left(\int_{\frac{1}{4}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{2}{3} \right| |f'(ta + (1-t)b)|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
 & + \left(\int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{3}{4}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{3} \right| dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left(\int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{3}{4}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{3} \right| |f'(tb + (1-t)a)|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
 & + \left(\int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{3}{4}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{3} \right| dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left(\int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{3}{4}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{3} \right| |f'(ta + (1-t)b)|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
 & + \left(\int_{\frac{3}{4}}^1 |t^\alpha - 1| dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left(\int_{\frac{3}{4}}^1 |t^\alpha - 1| |f'(tb + (1-t)a)|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
 & + \left(\int_{\frac{3}{4}}^1 |t^\alpha - 1| dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left(\int_{\frac{3}{4}}^1 |t^\alpha - 1| |f'(ta + (1-t)b)|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \Bigg\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Using the fact that $|f'|^q$ is convex, it leads to

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \frac{1}{3} \left[2f\left(\frac{a+3b}{4}\right) - f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{3a+b}{4}\right) \right] - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{2(b-a)^\alpha} [J_{a+}^\alpha f(b) + J_{b-}^\alpha f(a)] \right| \\
 & \leq \frac{b-a}{2} \left\{ \left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{4}} t^\alpha dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{4}} t^\alpha [t|f'(b)|^q + (1-t)|f'(a)|^q] dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right.
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + \left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{4}} t^\alpha dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{4}} t^\alpha [t |f'(a)|^q + (1-t) |f'(b)|^q] dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
& + \left(\int_{\frac{1}{4}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{2}{3} \right| dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left(\int_{\frac{1}{4}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{2}{3} \right| [t |f'(b)|^q + (1-t) |f'(a)|^q] dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
& + \left(\int_{\frac{1}{4}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{2}{3} \right| dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left(\int_{\frac{1}{4}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{2}{3} \right| [t |f'(a)|^q + (1-t) |f'(b)|^q] dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
& + \left(\int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{3}{4}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{3} \right| dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left(\int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{3}{4}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{3} \right| [t |f'(b)|^q + (1-t) |f'(a)|^q] dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
& + \left(\int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{3}{4}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{3} \right| dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left(\int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{3}{4}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{3} \right| [t |f'(a)|^q + (1-t) |f'(b)|^q] dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
& + \left(\int_{\frac{3}{4}}^1 |t^\alpha - 1| dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left(\int_{\frac{3}{4}}^1 |t^\alpha - 1| [t |f'(b)|^q + (1-t) |f'(a)|^q] dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
& + \left(\int_{\frac{3}{4}}^1 |t^\alpha - 1| dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left(\int_{\frac{3}{4}}^1 |t^\alpha - 1| [t |f'(a)|^q + (1-t) |f'(b)|^q] dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \Bigg\} \\
& = \frac{b-a}{2} \left\{ (\Omega_1(\alpha))^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left[([\Omega_5(\alpha) |f'(b)|^q + (\Omega_1(\alpha) - \Omega_5(\alpha)) |f'(a)|^q])^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. + ([\Omega_5(\alpha) |f'(a)|^q + (\Omega_1(\alpha) - \Omega_5(\alpha)) |f'(b)|^q])^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \right. \\
& \quad \left. + (\Omega_2(\alpha))^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left[([\Omega_6(\alpha) |f'(b)|^q + (\Omega_2(\alpha) - \Omega_6(\alpha)) |f'(a)|^q])^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \right.
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \left([\Omega_6(\alpha) |f'(a)|^q + (\Omega_2(\alpha) - \Omega_6(\alpha)) |f'(b)|^q]^{\frac{1}{q}} \right) \\
 & + (\Omega_3(\alpha))^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left[([\Omega_7(\alpha) |f'(b)|^q + (\Omega_3(\alpha) - \Omega_7(\alpha)) |f'(a)|^q]^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
 & \left. + ([\Omega_7(\alpha) |f'(a)|^q + (\Omega_3(\alpha) - \Omega_7(\alpha)) |f'(b)|^q]^{\frac{1}{q}} \right) \\
 & + (\Omega_4(\alpha))^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left[([\Omega_8(\alpha) |f'(b)|^q + (\Omega_4(\alpha) - \Omega_8(\alpha)) |f'(a)|^q]^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
 & \left. + ([\Omega_8(\alpha) |f'(a)|^q + (\Omega_4(\alpha) - \Omega_8(\alpha)) |f'(b)|^q]^{\frac{1}{q}} \right) \left. \right\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

□

Corollary 2.1. If we assign $\alpha = 1$ in Theorem 2.1, then the following Milne’s formula holds:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \frac{1}{3} \left[2f\left(\frac{a+3b}{4}\right) - f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{3a+b}{4}\right) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(t) dt \right| \\
 & \leq \frac{b-a}{4} \left\{ \frac{1}{8} \left[\left(\frac{|f'(b)|^q + 5|f'(a)|^q}{6} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{|f'(a)|^q + 5|f'(b)|^q}{6} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \right. \\
 & \left. + \left(\frac{7}{24} \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left[\left(\frac{5|f'(b)|^q + 9|f'(a)|^q}{48} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{5|f'(a)|^q + 9|f'(b)|^q}{48} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \right\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

This inequality helps us find the error bound of Milne’s rule.

Example 2.1. Consider a function $f : [a, b] = [0, 2] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ given by $f(x) = x^2$. From Theorem 2.1 with $\alpha \in (0, 10]$ and $q = 2$, the left-hand side of (1) reduces to

$$\left| \frac{4\alpha}{(\alpha+1)(\alpha+2)} - \frac{2}{3} \right|$$

and the right hand-side of (1) coincides with

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 4 \left\{ (\Omega_1(\alpha))^{\frac{1}{2}} \left[[\Omega_5(\alpha)]^{\frac{1}{2}} + [\Omega_1(\alpha) - \Omega_5(\alpha)]^{\frac{1}{2}} \right] \right. \\
 & + (\Omega_2(\alpha))^{\frac{1}{2}} \left[[\Omega_6(\alpha)]^{\frac{1}{2}} + [\Omega_2(\alpha) - \Omega_6(\alpha)]^{\frac{1}{2}} \right] \\
 & + (\Omega_3(\alpha))^{\frac{1}{2}} \left[[\Omega_7(\alpha)]^{\frac{1}{2}} + [\Omega_3(\alpha) - \Omega_7(\alpha)]^{\frac{1}{2}} \right] \\
 & \left. + (\Omega_4(\alpha))^{\frac{1}{2}} \left[[\Omega_8(\alpha)]^{\frac{1}{2}} + [\Omega_4(\alpha) - \Omega_8(\alpha)]^{\frac{1}{2}} \right] \right\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Finally, we get the inequality

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{4\alpha}{(\alpha+1)(\alpha+2)} - \frac{2}{3} \right| \tag{2} \\ & \leq 4 \left\{ (\Omega_1(\alpha))^{\frac{1}{2}} \left[[\Omega_5(\alpha)]^{\frac{1}{2}} + [\Omega_1(\alpha) - \Omega_5(\alpha)]^{\frac{1}{2}} \right] \right. \\ & \quad + (\Omega_2(\alpha))^{\frac{1}{2}} \left[[\Omega_6(\alpha)]^{\frac{1}{2}} + [\Omega_2(\alpha) - \Omega_6(\alpha)]^{\frac{1}{2}} \right] \\ & \quad + (\Omega_3(\alpha))^{\frac{1}{2}} \left[[\Omega_7(\alpha)]^{\frac{1}{2}} + [\Omega_3(\alpha) - \Omega_7(\alpha)]^{\frac{1}{2}} \right] \\ & \quad \left. + (\Omega_4(\alpha))^{\frac{1}{2}} \left[[\Omega_8(\alpha)]^{\frac{1}{2}} + [\Omega_4(\alpha) - \Omega_8(\alpha)]^{\frac{1}{2}} \right] \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

(a) A graph plotted over the interval $0 < \alpha \leq \frac{\ln(\frac{2}{3})}{\ln(\frac{1}{4})}$. $\frac{\ln(\frac{2}{3})}{\ln(\frac{1}{4})} < \alpha \leq \frac{\ln(\frac{2}{3})}{\ln(\frac{1}{2})}$.

(b) The graph of the function defined on the interval

Figure 1: The left-hand side of (2) is consistently below the right-hand side of this inequality for all values of $\alpha \in \left(0, \frac{\ln(\frac{2}{3})}{\ln(\frac{1}{2})}\right]$ in Example 2.1.

(a) A graphical representation corresponding to the interval $\frac{\ln(\frac{2}{3})}{\ln(\frac{1}{2})} < \alpha \leq \frac{\ln(\frac{1}{3})}{\ln(\frac{1}{2})}$.

(b) A plot over the domain from $\frac{\ln(\frac{1}{3})}{\ln(\frac{1}{2})}$ to $\frac{\ln(\frac{1}{3})}{\ln(\frac{3}{4})}$.

Figure 2: The left-hand side of (2) remains consistently below the right-hand side of the inequality for all values of $\alpha \in \left(\frac{\ln(\frac{2}{3})}{\ln(\frac{1}{2})}, \frac{\ln(\frac{1}{3})}{\ln(\frac{3}{4})}\right]$ in Example 2.1.

Figure 3: MATLAB has been evaluated and plotted the graph of both sides of (2) in Example 2.1.

Figure 4: Graphical analysis on the interval $\alpha \in \left(\frac{\ln(\frac{1}{3})}{\ln(\frac{3}{4})}, 10 \right]$

3 Conclusion

This extended abstract investigates Milne-type inequalities in the context of differentiable functions. First, employing the power mean inequality, we establish several Milne-type inequalities involving convex functions. Moreover, we illustrate our results through specific cases derived from the main theorem. Additionally, particular selections of the theorem are presented, accompanied by example and graphical representations.

In future investigations, exploring the concepts and strategies related to our findings on Milne-type inequalities via Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals may open new and innovative directions in mathematical research. Furthermore, our results could be extended by considering alternative classes of convex functions or employing different types of fractional integral operators. In addition, Milne-type inequalities involving convex functions may also be derived using Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals within the framework of quantum calculus.

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Fractional Simpson-Like Inequalities for Thrice Differentiable Functions

Hasan Kara¹, Hüseyin Budak², Ather Qayyum³

¹Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Science and Arts, Duzce University, Türkiye

²Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Science and Arts, Kocaeli University, Türkiye

³Institute of Mathematical Sciences, Universiti Malaya, Malaysia

Corresponding author: dratherqayyum@um.edu.my

ORCID IDs:

First Author: [0000-0002-2075-944X](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2075-944X)

Second Author: [0000-0001-8843-955X](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8843-955X)

Third Author: [0000-0003-4149-5305](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4149-5305)

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Abstract

In this investigation, new fractional Simpson-like inequalities for thrice differentiable functions are established by using bounded functions. Moreover, with the aid of Lipschitzian functions, some new fractional Simpson-like inequalities for thrice differentiable functions are also obtained. In addition, by considering specific parameter values, some known results are recovered as special cases of the main theorems, particularly those corresponding to the Riemann–Liouville fractional integral operator.

Keywords: Simpson type inequalities, Convex functions, Fractional integrals, Third derivative

1 Introduction and Preliminaries

The inequality theory is a considerable topic and remains an interesting research area with numerous number of applications in many mathematical fields. In addition, convex functions have also a significant place in the theory of inequality. Many inequalities have been investigated for convex functions but the most prominent is the Simpson type inequality, because of the its rich geometrical importance and applications. The following inequality is one of well-known outcome in the literature as the classical Simpson type inequality for four times continuously differentiable functions.

Theorem 1.1. Let $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ denote a four times continuously differentiable function on (a, b) , and let $\|f^{(4)}\|_{\infty} = \sup_{x \in (a, b)} |f^{(4)}(x)| < \infty$. Then, one has the inequality

$$\left| \frac{1}{6} \left[f(a) + 4f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{1}{2880} \|f^{(4)}\|_{\infty} (b-a)^4.$$

The convex theory is an impressive method to solve a large number of problems from varied branches of mathematics. Hence, many papers are established the Simpson type inequalities for

convex function. For instance, Sarikaya et al. proved the new variants of Simpson type inequalities with the aid of differentiable convex function in the papers [32]. For results with respect to these type of inequalities one can see Refs. [25, 12] and the references therein. In addition to these, Simpson type inequalities for various convex classes have been studied extensively by many authors (see, [23, 17, 27] and the references therein).

Twice differentiable convex functions have been established by many authors to get significant inequalities. For example, some Simpson type inequalities were presented for functions whose absolute values of derivatives are convex in [31]. Moreover, J. Park proved new estimates on generalization of Hadamard, Ostrowski and Simpson type inequalities to the case of functions whose second derivatives in absolute value at certain powers are convex and quasi-convex functions in [28]. Furthermore, it was proved some fractional Simpson type inequalities for functions whose second derivatives in absolute value are convex in [7]. It can be referred to [15, 3, 34, 9] for further information about twice differentiable functions.

Some inequalities of Simpson type for functions whose three derivatives in absolute value are the class of (α, m) -geometric-arithmetically-convex functions established in the paper [20]. In addition to this, some applications to special means of positive real numbers were given in this paper. In [1], some inequalities of Simpson type for quasi-convex functions in terms of third derivatives are presented and applications to Simpson numerical quadrature rule is also established. Furthermore, Ozdemir et. al. presented some inequalities by s -convex and s -concave functions in [26]. In the paper [11], the authors proved new inequalities of Simpson type for functions whose third derivatives are extended s -convex functions, and apply these inequalities to provide some inequalities of special means. In the paper [29], J. Park established some new integral inequalities of Hermite-Hadamard type for functions whose third derivatives are convex and s -convex in the second sense. For further information related to these subject, we refer to reader to [35, 10] and the references therein.

Mathematical preliminaries of fractional calculus theory, which will be used throughout this paper, will be presented as follows:

The well-known *Gamma function* and *Beta function* are defined by

$$\Gamma(x) := \int_0^{\infty} t^{x-1} e^{-t} dt$$

and

$$\beta(x, y) := \int_0^1 t^{x-1} (1-t)^{y-1} dt = \frac{\Gamma(x)\Gamma(y)}{\Gamma(x+y)},$$

respectively for $0 < x, y < \infty$ and $x, y \in \mathbb{R}$.

Let us consider $f \in L_1[a, b]$. The *Riemann-Liouville integrals* $J_{a+}^{\alpha} f$ and $J_{b-}^{\alpha} f$ of order $\alpha > 0$ with $a \geq 0$ are defined by

$$J_{a+}^{\alpha} f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_a^x (x-t)^{\alpha-1} f(t) dt, \quad x > a$$

and

$$J_{b-}^{\alpha} f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_x^b (t-x)^{\alpha-1} f(t) dt, \quad x < b,$$

respectively. Let us note that $J_{a+}^0 f(x) = J_{b-}^0 f(x) = f(x)$. Let us also note that $\alpha = 1$ in above. Then, the fractional integral becomes to the classical integral.

The fractional integral inequalities and applications have been established with the aid of the Riemann–Liouville fractional integral. For instance, Sarikaya et al. established some Simpson type inequalities to the case of functions whose second derivatives are convex [33]. Moreover, Iqbal et. al. generalized the Simpson type inequalities based on differentiable functions to Riemann–Liouville fractional integrals in the paper [16]. Some Simpson type inequalities using s – (α, m) –convex function by Riemann–Liouville fractional integrals were given in [21]. The reader is referred to [5, 6, 13, 14, 24] and the references therein for more information and unexplained subjects about several properties of Riemann–Liouville fractional integrals and various fractional integral operators. Whereas Simpson type inequalities for Riemann–Liouville fractional integrals have been considered by the authors, some mathematicians have also established the Simpson type inequalities for other type of fractional integrals such as k –fractional integral Conformable fractional integrals, Katugampola fractional integrals, etc. Concerning some papers related to the these subjects see [19, 18, 30, 22, 2], and references therein.

In [8], Hezenci and Budak previously established Simpson-like inequalities for thrice differentiable functions by employing the Riemann–Liouville fractional integrals. In their study, several inequalities and related consequences were derived by utilizing the convexity of the involved functions together with Hölder’s inequality and the power mean inequality. Before obtaining these results, the following lemma was first established.

Lemma 1.1. [8] Let us note that $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a three times differentiable function (a, b) such that $f''' \in L_1([a, b])$. Then, the following equality holds:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{(\alpha+1)(\alpha+2)} \left[f(a) + (\alpha^2 + 3\alpha) f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{2^{\alpha-1} \Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^{\alpha}} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}^{\alpha} f(a) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}^{\alpha} f(b) \right] \\ &= \frac{(b-a)^3}{16(\alpha+1)(\alpha+2)} \int_0^1 (t^{\alpha+2} - t^2) \left[f''' \left(\frac{t}{2}b + \left(\frac{2-t}{2} \right) a \right) - f''' \left(\frac{t}{2}a + \left(\frac{2-t}{2} \right) b \right) \right] dt. \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

The aim of this study is to establish several new Simpson-like inequalities for thrice differentiable functions involving Riemann–Liouville fractional integrals by employing the lemma presented above. The obtained lemma is utilized throughout the subsequent sections to derive the main results of the paper. The overall organization of the study is arranged as follows. In Section 2, inequalities are developed for the class of bounded functions. In Section 3, further inequalities are obtained for Lipschitzian functions, where the use of the established lemma enables the derivation of sharper estimates. By considering particular choices of the parameters, additional corollaries and new consequences are also produced. Finally, in Section 4, concluding remarks and possible directions for future research are discussed.

2 Bounded functions: Simpson like inequalities with fractional integrals

In this section, we deal with some Simpson like inequalities for bounded functions via fractional integrals.

Theorem 2.1. Note that the conditions of Lemma 1.1 hold. If there exist $m, M \in \mathbb{R}$ such that $m \leq f'''(t) \leq M$ for $t \in (a, b)$, then it follows

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{(\alpha+1)(\alpha+2)} \left[f(a) + (\alpha^2 + 3\alpha) f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}^\alpha f(a) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(b-a)^3 \alpha}{48(\alpha+1)(\alpha+2)(\alpha+3)} (M-m). \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Proof. By using the Lemma 1.1, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{(\alpha+1)(\alpha+2)} \left[f(a) + (\alpha^2 + 3\alpha) f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right] \\ & \quad - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}^\alpha f(a) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \\ & = \frac{(b-a)^3}{16(\alpha+1)(\alpha+2)} \left\{ \int_0^1 (t^{\alpha+2} - t^2) \left[f''' \left(\frac{t}{2}b + \left(\frac{2-t}{2} \right) a \right) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right] dt \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \int_0^1 (t^{\alpha+2} - t^2) \left[\frac{m+M}{2} - f''' \left(\frac{t}{2}a + \left(\frac{2-t}{2} \right) b \right) \right] dt \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Through the absolute value of (3), we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{(\alpha+1)(\alpha+2)} \left[f(a) + (\alpha^2 + 3\alpha) f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}^\alpha f(a) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(b-a)^3}{16(\alpha+1)(\alpha+2)} \left\{ \int_0^1 |t^{\alpha+2} - t^2| \left| f''' \left(\frac{t}{2}b + \left(\frac{2-t}{2} \right) a \right) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right| dt \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \int_0^1 |t^{\alpha+2} - t^2| \left| \frac{m+M}{2} - f''' \left(\frac{t}{2}a + \left(\frac{2-t}{2} \right) b \right) \right| dt \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

It is known that $m \leq f'''(t) \leq M$ for $t \in (a, b)$. Then, we have

$$\left| f''' \left(\frac{t}{2}b + \left(\frac{2-t}{2} \right) a \right) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right| \leq \frac{M-m}{2}, \quad (4)$$

$$\left| \frac{m+M}{2} - f''' \left(\frac{t}{2}a + \left(\frac{2-t}{2} \right) b \right) \right| \leq \frac{M-m}{2}. \quad (5)$$

With the help of the (4) and (5), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left| \frac{1}{(\alpha+1)(\alpha+2)} \left[f(a) + (\alpha^2 + 3\alpha) f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right] \right. \\
& \quad \left. - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}^\alpha f(a) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \right| \\
& \leq \frac{(b-a)^3}{16(\alpha+1)(\alpha+2)} \\
& \quad \times \left\{ \int_0^1 |t^{\alpha+1} - t^2| \frac{M-m}{2} dt + \int_0^1 |t^{\alpha+1} - t^2| \frac{M-m}{2} dt \right\} \\
& = \frac{(b-a)^3}{16(\alpha+1)(\alpha+2)} (M-m) \int_0^1 |t^{\alpha+1} - t^2| dt \\
& = \frac{(b-a)^3 \alpha}{48(\alpha+1)(\alpha+2)(\alpha+3)} (M-m).
\end{aligned}$$

□

Corollary 2.1. If we select $\alpha = 1$ in Theorem 2.1, then we get

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left| \frac{1}{6} \left[f(a) + 4f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(t) dt \right| \\
& \leq \frac{(b-a)^3}{1152} (M-m).
\end{aligned}$$

Corollary 2.2. Under assumption of Theorem 2.1, if there exist $M \in \mathbb{R}^+$ such that $|f'(t)| \leq M$ for all $t \in (a, b)$, then we have

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left| \frac{1}{(\alpha+1)(\alpha+2)} \left[f(a) + (\alpha^2 + 3\alpha) f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right] \right. \\
& \quad \left. - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}^\alpha f(a) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \right| \\
& \leq \frac{(b-a)^3 \alpha}{24(\alpha+1)(\alpha+2)(\alpha+3)} M.
\end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

Corollary 2.3. Let us consider $\alpha = 1$ in Corollary 2.2. Then, the following inequality holds:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left| \frac{1}{6} \left[f(a) + 4f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(t) dt \right| \\
& \leq \frac{(b-a)^3}{576} M.
\end{aligned}$$

3 Lipschitzian functions: Fractional Simpson like inequalities

In this section, we give some fractional Simpson like inequalities for Lipschitzian functions.

Theorem 3.1. Assume that the assumptions of Lemma 1.1 are valid. If f''' is a L -Lipschitzian

function on $[a, b]$, then the following inequality holds:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{(\alpha + 1)(\alpha + 2)} \left[f(a) + (\alpha^2 + 3\alpha) f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}^\alpha f(a) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(b-a)^4 \alpha(\alpha + 7)}{192(\alpha + 1)(\alpha + 2)(\alpha + 3)(\alpha + 4)} L. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. With the aid of Lemma 1.1 and since f''' is L -Lipschitzian function, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{(\alpha + 1)(\alpha + 2)} \left[f(a) + (\alpha^2 + 3\alpha) f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}^\alpha f(a) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(b-a)^3}{16(\alpha + 1)(\alpha + 2)} \\ & \quad \times \left\{ \int_0^1 |t^{\alpha+2} - t^2| \left| \left[f''' \left(\frac{t}{2}b + \left(\frac{2-t}{2} \right) a \right) - f''' \left(\frac{t}{2}a + \left(\frac{2-t}{2} \right) b \right) \right] \right| dt \right\} \\ & \leq \frac{(b-a)^3}{16(\alpha + 1)(\alpha + 2)} \left\{ \int_0^1 t^2 |t^\alpha - 1| \left| f''' \left(\frac{t}{2}b + \left(\frac{2-t}{2} \right) a \right) - f''' \left(\frac{t}{2}a + \left(\frac{2-t}{2} \right) b \right) \right| dt \right\} \\ & \leq \frac{(b-a)^3}{16(\alpha + 1)(\alpha + 2)} \left\{ \int_0^1 t^2 |t^\alpha - 1| L(b-a) |t-1| dt \right\} \\ & = \frac{(b-a)^4}{16(\alpha + 1)(\alpha + 2)} L \left[\int_0^1 t^2 |t^\alpha - 1| dt - \int_0^1 t^3 |t^\alpha - 1| dt \right] \\ & = \frac{(b-a)^4 \alpha(\alpha + 7)}{192(\alpha + 1)(\alpha + 2)(\alpha + 3)(\alpha + 4)} L \end{aligned}$$

□

Corollary 3.1. Consider $\alpha = 1$ in Theorem 3.1. Then, the following Simpson like inequality holds:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{6} \left[f(a) + 4f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(t) dt \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(b-a)^4}{2880} L. \end{aligned}$$

4 Conclusion

In this investigation, new fractional Simpson-like inequalities for thrice differentiable functions have been established by employing bounded functions. In addition, by utilizing Lipschitzian functions, further fractional Simpson-like inequalities have been derived. Several known results in the literature, particularly those associated with the Riemann–Liouville fractional integral

operator, are recovered as special cases through appropriate choices of the parameters. The obtained results may stimulate further research on improving or generalizing fractional Simpson-type inequalities by considering different classes of convexity or other fractional integral operators.

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Fractional Newton-Type Inequalities Involving h -convex Functions

Hasan Kara¹, Hüseyin Budak², Fatih Hezenci¹

¹Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Science and Arts, Duzce University, Türkiye

²Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Science and Arts, Kocaeli University, Türkiye

Corresponding author: hasan64kara@gmail.com

ORCID IDs:

First Author: 0000-0002-2075-944X

Second Author: 0000-0001-8843-955X

Third Author: 0000-0003-1008-5856

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Abstract

In this study, Newton-type inequalities involving Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals have been obtained for a class of functions that are twice differentiable and h -convex. The main step has been to derive an identity that connects the second derivative of the function with its fractional integrals. This identity has been presented as the fundamental for proving new inequalities under the assumption that the function satisfies the condition of h -convexity. The method adopted here is based on analyzing the structure of the second derivative together with the properties of h -convex functions. The definition of h -convexity has allowed a variable to choose where classical convexity may be seen as a special case. By assuming that the second derivative is h -convex on a given interval, estimates have been established that generalize some known results in the literature related to Newton-type inequalities. Tools from classical analysis, such as Hölder's inequality and integral inequalities, have been used in the results obtained.

Keywords: Newton-type inequalities, h -convex functions, fractional integral

1 Introduction

The basic principle of Simpson's second rule is the three-point Newton-Cotes quadrature rule. Results for three-step quadratic kernel computations are generally described as Newton-type results. These results are recognized to be Newton-type inequalities from the literature. There have been some mathematicians who have been studied to Newton-type inequalities. For instance, several Newton-type inequalities are proved for the case of functions whose second derivatives are convex in paper [1]. Newton-type inequalities are established by harmonic convex and p -harmonic convex functions in [2] and [3], respectively. In paper [4], some Newton-type inequalities are acquired by post-quantum integrals. Moreover, in paper [5], some Newton-type inequalities are presented for the case of quantum differentiable convex functions. Furthermore, in paper [6], some error estimates of Newton-type quadrature formula are given by bounded variation and

Lipschitzian mappings. See the references cited in [7, 8, 9] for some recent results associating with Newton-type inequalities.

The popularity of fractional calculus has enhanced in recent years since its broad range of applications in various fields of science. Given the importance of fractional calculus, some operators for fractional integrals can be taken into consideration. For example, in paper [12], some Newton-type inequalities are obtained for the case of functions whose first derivative in absolute value at certain power are arithmetically-harmonically convex. In addition, some Newton-type inequalities are established by using Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals for differentiable convex functions and some Riemann-Liouville fractional Newton-type inequalities are given for functions of bounded variation in paper [13]. Moreover, several Newton-type inequalities are established by means of the well-known Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals for differentiable convex functions in [15].

2 Preliminaries

Simpson-type inequality is a variation on inequality that is derived from Simpson's rules. It can be expressed as follows:

- i. Simpson's 1/3 rule, or Simpson's quadrature formula:

$$\int_a^b f(x) dx \approx \frac{b-a}{6} \left[f(a) + 4f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right].$$

- ii. The Simpson's second formula, often known as the Simpson's 3/8 rule, or the Newton-Cotes quadrature formula:

$$\int_a^b f(x) dx \approx \frac{b-a}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right].$$

Three-point Simpson-type inequality is the most widely used Newton-Cotes quadrature, and it corresponds to this:

Theorem 2.1. Let $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a four times differentiable and continuous function on (a, b) , and let $\|f^{(4)}\|_{\infty} = \sup_{x \in (a,b)} |f^{(4)}(x)| < \infty$. Then, the following inequality holds:

$$\left| \frac{1}{6} \left[f(a) + 4f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{1}{2880} \|f^{(4)}\|_{\infty} (b-a)^4.$$

The Simpson 3/8 rule is a classical closed type quadrature rule is as follows:

Theorem 2.2. Consider that $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a four times differentiable, continuous function on (a, b) , and $\|f^{(4)}\|_{\infty} = \sup_{x \in (a,b)} |f^{(4)}(x)| < \infty$. Then, one has the inequality

$$\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{1}{6480} \|f^{(4)}\|_{\infty} (b-a)^4.$$

Definition 2.1 (See [17]). Assume that I is an interval of real numbers. Then, a function $f : I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is said to be convex, if

$$f(tx + (1-t)y) \leq tf(x) + (1-t)f(y)$$

is valid $\forall x, y \in I$ and $\forall t \in [0, 1]$.

Definition 2.2. Let $h : J \subseteq \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, where $(0, 1) \subseteq J$, be a nonnegative function with $h \neq 0$. We say that $f : I \subseteq \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is an h -convex function if f is nonnegative and for all $x, y \in I$, $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ we have

$$f(\alpha x + (1-\alpha)y) \leq h(\alpha)f(x) + h(1-\alpha)f(y). \quad (1)$$

If the inequality in (1) is reversed, then f is said to be h -concave.

By setting

- $h(\lambda) = \lambda$, Definition 2.2 reduces to that of the classical convex function.
- $h(\lambda) = 1$, Definition 2.2 reduces to that of P -functions [11, 18].
- $h(\lambda) = \lambda^s$, Definition 2.2 reduces to that of s -convex functions [10].
- $h(\lambda) = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \lambda^{1/k}$, Definition 2.2 reduces to that of polynomial n -fractional convex functions [16].

Definition 2.3 (See [19, 20]). Let us consider $f \in L_1[a, b]$, $a, b \in \mathbb{R}$ with $a < b$. The Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals $J_{a+}^\alpha f$ and $J_{b-}^\alpha f$ of order $\alpha > 0$ are defined by

$$J_{a+}^\alpha f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_a^x (x-t)^{\alpha-1} f(t) dt, \quad x > a \quad (2)$$

and

$$J_{b-}^\alpha f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_x^b (t-x)^{\alpha-1} f(t) dt, \quad x < b, \quad (3)$$

respectively. Here, Γ denotes the Gamma function defined by

$$\Gamma(\alpha) = \int_0^\infty e^{-u} u^{\alpha-1} du.$$

Lemma 2.1. [14] If $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is an absolutely continuous function (a, b) such that $f' \in L_1[a, b]$, then the identity

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}^\alpha f(a) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \\ & = \frac{b-a}{4} [I_1 + I_2] \end{aligned}$$

is valid. Here,

$$\begin{cases} I_1 = \int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(t^\alpha - \frac{1}{4}\right) \left[f' \left(\frac{t}{2}b + \frac{2-t}{2}a\right) - f' \left(\frac{t}{2}a + \frac{2-t}{2}b\right)\right] dt, \\ I_2 = \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 (t^\alpha - 1) \left[f' \left(\frac{t}{2}b + \frac{2-t}{2}a\right) - f' \left(\frac{t}{2}a + \frac{2-t}{2}b\right)\right] dt. \end{cases}$$

3 Fractional Newton-type inequalities by h -convex functions

Firstly, some Newton-type inequalities are obtained for differentiable h -convex functions by using Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals.

Theorem 3.1. Assume that the assumptions of Lemma 2.1 hold and the function $|f'|$ is h -convex on the interval $[a, b]$. Then, one can prove fractional Newton-type inequality

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}^\alpha f(a) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{b-a}{4} \left(h\left(\frac{t}{2}\right) + h\left(\frac{2-t}{2}\right) \right) [|f'(a)| + |f'(b)|]. \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

Proof. Let us first consider the absolute value in Lemma 2.1. Then, one can directly have

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}^\alpha f(a) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{b-a}{4} \left\{ \int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{4} \right| \left| f' \left(\frac{t}{2}b + \frac{2-t}{2}a \right) - f' \left(\frac{t}{2}a + \frac{2-t}{2}b \right) \right| dt \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 |t^\alpha - 1| \left| f' \left(\frac{t}{2}b + \frac{2-t}{2}a \right) - f' \left(\frac{t}{2}a + \frac{2-t}{2}b \right) \right| dt \right\}. \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

Based on the h -convexity of $|f'|$, one can obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}^\alpha f(a) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{b-a}{4} \left\{ \int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{4} \right| \left[h\left(\frac{t}{2}\right) |f'(b)| + h\left(\frac{2-t}{2}\right) |f'(a)| + h\left(\frac{t}{2}\right) |f'(a)| + h\left(\frac{2-t}{2}\right) |f'(b)| \right] dt \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 (1-t^\alpha) \left[h\left(\frac{t}{2}\right) |f'(b)| + h\left(\frac{2-t}{2}\right) |f'(a)| + h\left(\frac{t}{2}\right) |f'(a)| + h\left(\frac{2-t}{2}\right) |f'(b)| \right] dt \right\} \\ & = \frac{b-a}{4} \left(h\left(\frac{t}{2}\right) + h\left(\frac{2-t}{2}\right) \right) [|f'(a)| + |f'(b)|]. \end{aligned}$$

□

Remark 3.1. If we choose $h(t) = t$ in Theorem 3.1, and then we have

$$\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}^\alpha f(a) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \right| \leq \frac{b-a}{4} (\Omega_1(\alpha) + \Omega_2(\alpha)) [|f'(a)| + |f'(b)|]. \quad (6)$$

Here,

$$\Omega_1(\alpha) = \int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{4} \right| dt = \begin{cases} \frac{2\alpha}{\alpha+1} \left(\frac{1}{4}\right)^{1+\frac{1}{\alpha}} + \frac{1}{\alpha+1} \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^{\alpha+1} - \frac{1}{6}, & 0 < \alpha < \frac{\ln(\frac{1}{4})}{\ln(\frac{2}{3})}, \\ \frac{1}{6} - \frac{1}{\alpha+1} \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^{\alpha+1}, & \frac{\ln(\frac{1}{4})}{\ln(\frac{2}{3})} < \alpha \end{cases}$$

and

$$\Omega_2(\alpha) = \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 (1-t^\alpha) dt = \frac{1}{3} - \frac{1}{\alpha+1} + \frac{1}{\alpha+1} \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^{\alpha+1}.$$

This result was obtained by Hezenci and Budak [14].

Remark 3.2. If we assign $\alpha = 1$ in Remark 3.1, then one can get Newton-type inequality

$$\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(t) dt \right| \leq \frac{25(b-a)}{576} [|f'(a)| + |f'(b)|],$$

which is proved by Sitthiwirattham et al. in paper [13, Remark 3].

Theorem 3.2. Consider that the assumptions in Lemma 2.1 and the function $|f'|^q$, $q > 1$ is h -convex on $[a, b]$. Then, the Newton-type inequality

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}^\alpha f(a) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{b-a}{4} \left\{ \left(\int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{4} \right|^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left[\left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left(h\left(\frac{t}{2}\right) |f'(b)|^q + h\left(\frac{2-t}{2}\right) |f'(a)|^q \right) dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. + \left(\int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(h\left(\frac{t}{2}\right) |f'(a)|^q + h\left(\frac{2-t}{2}\right) |f'(b)|^q \right) dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 (1-t^\alpha)^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left[\left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left(h\left(\frac{t}{2}\right) |f'(b)|^q + h\left(\frac{2-t}{2}\right) |f'(a)|^q \right) dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \right. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

$$+ \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left(h\left(\frac{t}{2}\right) |f'(a)|^q + h\left(\frac{2-t}{2}\right) |f'(b)|^q \right) dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \Bigg\}$$

is valid. Here, $\frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$.

Proof. By utilizing Hölder’s inequality to (5), one can obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}^\alpha f(a) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{b-a}{4} \left\{ \left(\int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{4} \right|^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| f'\left(\frac{t}{2}b + \frac{2-t}{2}a\right) \right|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\ & \quad + \left(\int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{4} \right|^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| f'\left(\frac{t}{2}a + \frac{2-t}{2}b\right) \right|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\ & \quad + \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 |t^\alpha - 1|^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| f'\left(\frac{t}{2}b + \frac{2-t}{2}a\right) \right|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\ & \quad \left. + \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 |t^\alpha - 1|^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| f'\left(\frac{t}{2}a + \frac{2-t}{2}b\right) \right|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

From the facts of the h -convexity $|f'|^q$, one can readily have

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}^\alpha f(a) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{b-a}{4} \left\{ \left(\int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{4} \right|^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(h\left(\frac{t}{2}\right) |f'(b)|^q + h\left(\frac{2-t}{2}\right) |f'(a)|^q \right) dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\ & \quad + \left(\int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{4} \right|^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(h\left(\frac{t}{2}\right) |f'(a)|^q + h\left(\frac{2-t}{2}\right) |f'(b)|^q \right) dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\ & \quad + \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 (1-t^\alpha)^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left(h\left(\frac{t}{2}\right) |f'(b)|^q + h\left(\frac{2-t}{2}\right) |f'(a)|^q \right) dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\ & \quad \left. + \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 (1-t^\alpha)^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left(h\left(\frac{t}{2}\right) |f'(a)|^q + h\left(\frac{2-t}{2}\right) |f'(b)|^q \right) dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 (1-t^\alpha)^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left(h\left(\frac{t}{2}\right) |f'(a)|^q + h\left(\frac{2-t}{2}\right) |f'(b)|^q \right) dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \Bigg\} \\
& = \frac{b-a}{4} \left\{ \left(\int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{4} \right|^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \right. \\
& \quad \times \left[\left(\int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(h\left(\frac{t}{2}\right) |f'(b)|^q + h\left(\frac{2-t}{2}\right) |f'(a)|^q \right) dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. + \left(\int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(h\left(\frac{t}{2}\right) |f'(a)|^q + h\left(\frac{2-t}{2}\right) |f'(b)|^q \right) dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \right. \\
& \quad \left. + \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 (1-t^\alpha)^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \right. \\
& \quad \times \left[\left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left(h\left(\frac{t}{2}\right) |f'(b)|^q + h\left(\frac{2-t}{2}\right) |f'(a)|^q \right) dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
& \quad \left. \left. + \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left(h\left(\frac{t}{2}\right) |f'(a)|^q + h\left(\frac{2-t}{2}\right) |f'(b)|^q \right) dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \right\}.
\end{aligned}$$

□

Remark 3.3. If we choose $h(t) = t$ in Theorem 3.2, and then we have

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{2^{\alpha-1} \Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}^\alpha f(a) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \right| \\
& \leq \frac{b-a}{4} \left\{ \left(\int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{4} \right|^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left[\left(\frac{|f'(b)|^q + 5|f'(a)|^q}{9} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{|f'(a)|^q + 5|f'(b)|^q}{9} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \right. \\
& \quad \left. + \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 (1-t^\alpha)^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left[\left(\frac{5|f'(b)|^q + 7|f'(a)|^q}{36} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{5|f'(a)|^q + 7|f'(b)|^q}{36} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \right\}
\end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

is valid. Here, $\frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$. This result was established by Hezenci and Budak [14].

Remark 3.4. Consider that $\alpha = 1$ in Remark 3.3. Then, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(t) dt \right| \\ & \leq \frac{b-a}{4} \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{p+1} \left[\left(\frac{1}{4}\right)^{p+1} + \left(\frac{5}{12}\right)^{p+1} \right] \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \right. \\ & \quad \times \left[\left(\frac{|f'(b)|^q + 5|f'(a)|^q}{9} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{|f'(a)|^q + 5|f'(b)|^q}{9} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \\ & \quad \left. + \left(\frac{1}{p+1} \left(\frac{1}{3}\right)^{p+1} \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left[\left(\frac{5|f'(b)|^q + 7|f'(a)|^q}{36} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{5|f'(a)|^q + 7|f'(b)|^q}{36} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

This result was established by Hezenci and Budak [14].

Theorem 3.3. If the assumptions of Lemma 2.1 hold and the function $|f'|^q$, $q \geq 1$ is h -convex on $[a, b]$, then the following Newton-type inequality satisfies:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}^\alpha f(a) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{b-a}{4} \left\{ \left[\left(\int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{4} \right| \left[h\left(\frac{t}{2}\right) |f'(b)|^q + h\left(\frac{2-t}{2}\right) |f'(a)|^q \right] dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. + \left(\int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{4} \right| \left[h\left(\frac{t}{2}\right) |f'(a)|^q + h\left(\frac{2-t}{2}\right) |f'(b)|^q \right] dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 (1-t^\alpha) dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 |t^\alpha - 1| \left[h\left(\frac{t}{2}\right) |f'(b)|^q + h\left(\frac{2-t}{2}\right) |f'(a)|^q \right] dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 |t^\alpha - 1| \left[h\left(\frac{t}{2}\right) |f'(a)|^q + h\left(\frac{2-t}{2}\right) |f'(b)|^q \right] dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\}. \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

Proof. If we first apply (5) to the power-mean inequality, then it yields

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}^\alpha f(a) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{b-a}{4} \left\{ \left(\int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{4} \right| dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left(\int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{4} \right| \left| f'\left(\frac{t}{2}b + \frac{2-t}{2}a\right) \right|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + \left(\int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{4} \right| dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left(\int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{4} \right| \left| f' \left(\frac{t}{2}a + \frac{2-t}{2}b \right) \right|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
& + \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 |t^\alpha - 1| dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 |t^\alpha - 1| \left| f' \left(\frac{t}{2}b + \frac{2-t}{2}a \right) \right|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
& + \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 |t^\alpha - 1| dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 |t^\alpha - 1| \left| f' \left(\frac{t}{2}a + \frac{2-t}{2}b \right) \right|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \Bigg\}.
\end{aligned}$$

It is known that $|f'|^q$ is h -convex. Then, one can obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}^\alpha f(a) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \right| \\
& \leq \frac{b-a}{4} \left\{ \left(\int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{4} \right| dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left(\int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{4} \right| \left[h\left(\frac{t}{2}\right) |f'(b)|^q + h\left(\frac{2-t}{2}\right) |f'(a)|^q \right] dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
& + \left(\int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{4} \right| dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left(\int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{4} \right| \left[h\left(\frac{t}{2}\right) |f'(a)|^q + h\left(\frac{2-t}{2}\right) |f'(b)|^q \right] dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
& + \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 (1-t^\alpha) dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 |t^\alpha - 1| \left[h\left(\frac{t}{2}\right) |f'(b)|^q + h\left(\frac{2-t}{2}\right) |f'(a)|^q \right] dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
& \left. + \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 (1-t^\alpha) dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 |t^\alpha - 1| \left[h\left(\frac{t}{2}\right) |f'(a)|^q + h\left(\frac{2-t}{2}\right) |f'(b)|^q \right] dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\}.
\end{aligned}$$

□

Remark 3.5. If we choose $h(t) = t$ in Theorem 4, and then we have

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}^\alpha f(a) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \right| \\
& \leq \frac{b-a}{4} \left\{ (\Omega_1(\alpha))^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left[[\Omega_3(\alpha) |f'(b)|^q + \Omega_4(\alpha) |f'(a)|^q]^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \right. \\
& + \left. [\Omega_3(\alpha) |f'(a)|^q + \Omega_4(\alpha) |f'(b)|^q]^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \\
& + (\Omega_2(\alpha))^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left[[\Omega_5(\alpha) |f'(b)|^q + \Omega_6(\alpha) |f'(a)|^q]^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
& \left. + [\Omega_5(\alpha) |f'(a)|^q + \Omega_6(\alpha) |f'(b)|^q]^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \Bigg\}, \tag{10}
\end{aligned}$$

where $\Omega_1(\alpha)$ and $\Omega_2(\alpha)$ are given in Theorem 3.1 and

$$\Omega_3(\alpha) = \int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \frac{t}{2} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{4} \right| dt = \begin{cases} \frac{\alpha+1}{2(\alpha+2)} \left(\frac{1}{4}\right)^{1+\frac{2}{\alpha}} + \frac{1}{2(\alpha+2)} \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^{\alpha+2} - \frac{1}{36}, & 0 < \alpha < \frac{\ln(\frac{1}{4})}{\ln(\frac{2}{3})}, \\ \frac{1}{36} - \frac{1}{2(\alpha+2)} \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^{\alpha+2}, & \frac{\ln(\frac{1}{4})}{\ln(\frac{2}{3})} < \alpha \end{cases}$$

$$\Omega_4(\alpha) = \int_0^{\frac{2}{3}} \frac{2-t}{2} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{4} \right| dt = \begin{cases} \frac{2\alpha}{\alpha+1} \left(\frac{1}{4}\right)^{1+\frac{1}{\alpha}} + \frac{1}{\alpha+1} \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^{\alpha+1} - \frac{\alpha+1}{2(\alpha+2)} \left(\frac{1}{4}\right)^{1+\frac{2}{\alpha}} - \frac{1}{2(\alpha+2)} \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^{\alpha+2} - \frac{5}{36}, & 0 < \alpha < \frac{\ln(\frac{1}{4})}{\ln(\frac{2}{3})}, \\ \frac{5}{36} - \frac{1}{\alpha+1} \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^{\alpha+1} + \frac{1}{2(\alpha+2)} \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^{\alpha+2}, & \frac{\ln(\frac{1}{4})}{\ln(\frac{2}{3})} < \alpha, \end{cases}$$

$$\Omega_5(\alpha) = \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \frac{t}{2} (1-t^\alpha) dt = \frac{5}{36} - \frac{1}{2(\alpha+2)} + \frac{1}{2(\alpha+2)} \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^{\alpha+2},$$

$$\Omega_6(\alpha) = \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \frac{2-t}{2} (1-t^\alpha) dt = \frac{7}{36} - \frac{\alpha+3}{2(\alpha+1)(\alpha+2)} + \frac{1}{\alpha+1} \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^{\alpha+1} - \frac{1}{2(\alpha+2)} \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^{\alpha+2}.$$

This result was obtained by Hezenci and Budak [14].

Remark 3.6. If we choose $\alpha = 1$ in Remark 3.5, then the following Newton-type inequality holds:

$$\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(t) dt \right|$$

$$\leq \frac{b-a}{72} \left\{ \left(\frac{17}{8}\right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left[\left(\frac{251|f'(b)|^q + 973|f'(a)|^q}{576}\right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{251|f'(a)|^q + 973|f'(b)|^q}{576}\right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \right.$$

$$\left. + \left[\left(\frac{7|f'(b)|^q + 11|f'(a)|^q}{18}\right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{7|f'(a)|^q + 11|f'(b)|^q}{18}\right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \right\}.$$

This result was acquired by Hezenci and Budak [14].

4 Summary & concluding remarks

In this manuscript, Newton-type inequalities have been established for h -convex functions by employing the Riemann–Liouville fractional integrals. These inequalities have been derived by utilizing a previously obtained integral identity together with fundamental analytical tools such as Hölder’s inequality and the power mean inequality. The interplay between h -convexity, fractional integration, and Newton-type inequalities presented here contributes to the existing literature and may serve as a basis for further developments in this area. Future investigations may consider extending these results by adopting alternative convexity classes or employing different types of fractional integral operators to obtain new forms of Newton-type inequalities.

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A New Perspective on Milne-type Inequalities involving Riemann–Liouville Fractional Integrals

Hüseyin Budak¹, Mehmet Zeki Sarıkaya², Hasan Kara²

¹Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Science and Arts, Kocaeli University, Türkiye

²Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Science and Arts, Duzce University, Türkiye

Corresponding author: hasan64kara@gmail.com

ORCID IDs:

First Author: [0000-0001-8843-955X](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8843-955X)

Second Author: [0000-0002-6165-9242](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6165-9242)

Third Author: [0000-0002-2075-944X](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2075-944X)

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Abstract

In this study, we establish the upper and below bounds for fractional Milne-type inequalities by using functions whose second derivatives are bounded. Moreover, we present new inequalities for Riemann integrals as special cases.

Keywords: Milne type inequality inequality, integral inequalities, bounded functions.

1 Introduction

The Hermite-Hadamard inequality, recognized as one of the foundational results concerning convex functions, possesses a clear geometric interpretation and has found numerous applications across various fields of mathematics. It has attracted significant attention within elementary mathematical analysis, prompting many researchers to explore generalizations, refinements, extensions, and analogous results for broader classes of functions, particularly through the lens of convexity.

The inequalities originally formulated by C. Hermite and J. Hadamard for convex functions hold a prominent place in the mathematical literature (see, for example, [12, p.137], [5]). These inequalities state that if $f : I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a convex function on the interval I of real numbers and $a, b \in I$ with $a < b$, then

$$f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \leq \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x)dx \leq \frac{f(a)+f(b)}{2}. \quad (1)$$

Both inequalities hold in the reversed direction if f is concave.

In [7] and [8], Dragomir et al. proved the following results connected with the Hermite-Hadamard inequality:

Theorem 1.1. Let $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a twice differentiable mapping such that there exists real constants m and M so that $m \leq f'' \leq M$. Then, the following inequalities hold:

$$m \frac{(b-a)^2}{24} \leq \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx - f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \leq M \frac{(b-a)^2}{24}. \tag{2}$$

and

$$m \frac{(b-a)^2}{12} \leq \frac{f(a) + f(b)}{2} - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \leq M \frac{(b-a)^2}{12} \tag{3}$$

In the following we will give some necessary definitions and mathematical preliminaries of fractional calculus theory which are used further in this paper.

Definition 1.1. Let $f \in L_1[a, b]$. The Riemann-Liouville integrals $J_{a+}^\alpha f$ and $J_{b-}^\alpha f$ of order $\alpha > 0$ with $a \geq 0$ are defined by

$$J_{a+}^\alpha f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_a^x (x-t)^{\alpha-1} f(t) dt, \quad x > a$$

and

$$J_{b-}^\alpha f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_x^b (t-x)^{\alpha-1} f(t) dt, \quad x < b$$

respectively. Here, $\Gamma(\alpha)$ is the Gamma function and $J_{a+}^0 f(x) = J_{b-}^0 f(x) = f(x)$.

For more information about fraction calculus please refer to ([9], [10], [11], [13].)

In [14], Sarikaya et al. first give the following interesting integral inequalities of Hermite-Hadamard type involving Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals.

Theorem 1.2. Let $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a positive function with $0 \leq a < b$ and $f \in L_1[a, b]$. If f is a convex function on $[a, b]$, then the following inequalities for fractional integrals hold:

$$f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \leq \frac{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{2(b-a)^\alpha} [J_{a+}^\alpha f(b) + J_{b-}^\alpha f(a)] \leq \frac{f(a) + f(b)}{2} \tag{4}$$

with $\alpha > 0$.

Moreover, Dragomir give the following another version of Hermite-Hadamard inequality for Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals:

Theorem 1.3. [6] Let $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a positive function with $a < b$ and $f \in L_1[a, b]$. If f is a convex function on $[a, b]$, then the following inequalities for fractional integrals hold:

$$\begin{aligned} f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) &\leq \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_a^\alpha f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + J_b^\alpha f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right] \\ &\leq \frac{f(a) + f(b)}{2} \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

Theorem 1.4. [1] Let $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a twice differentiable function with $a < b$ and $f \in L_1[a, b]$. If f'' is bounded, i.e. $m \leq f''(t) \leq M, t \in (a, b), m, M \in \mathbb{R}$, then we have the inequalities

$$\frac{m(b-a)^2}{8(\alpha+2)}$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_{a+}^\alpha f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + J_{b-}^\alpha f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right] - f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \\ &\leq \frac{M(b-a)^2}{8(\alpha+2)}, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{m(b-a)^2}{4(\alpha+2)} \\ &\leq \frac{f(a)+f(b)}{2} - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_{a+}^\alpha f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + J_{b-}^\alpha f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right] \\ &\leq \frac{M(b-a)^2}{4(\alpha+2)}, \end{aligned}$$

Now we present some Milne-type inequalities:

Theorem 1.5. [2] Let $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a differentiable mapping (a, b) such that $f \in L_1([a, b])$. If the function $|f'|$ is convex on $[a, b]$, then we have the following Milne-type inequality

$$\left| \frac{1}{3} \left[2f(a) - f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 2f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(t) dt \right| \leq \frac{5(b-a)}{24} [|f'(a)| + |f'(b)|].$$

Theorem 1.6 (Milne-type inequality in the first sense). [4] Let $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a differentiable mapping (a, b) such that $f \in L_1([a, b])$. If the function $|f'|$ is convex on $[a, b]$, then we have the following Milne-type inequality for Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals

$$\begin{aligned} &\left| \frac{1}{3} \left[2f(a) - f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 2f(b) \right] - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}^\alpha f(b) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}^\alpha f(a) \right] \right| \\ &\leq \frac{4\alpha+1}{12(\alpha+1)} (b-a) [|f'(a)| + |f'(b)|], \end{aligned}$$

for $\alpha > 0$.

Theorem 1.7 (Milne-type inequality in the second sense). [2] Assume that the assumptions of Theorem 1.5. Then we have

$$\begin{aligned} &\left| \frac{1}{3} \left[2f(a) - f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 2f(b) \right] - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_{a+}^\alpha f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + J_{b-}^\alpha f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right] \right| \\ &\leq \frac{\alpha+4}{12(\alpha+1)} (b-a) [|f'(a)| + |f'(b)|], \end{aligned}$$

for $\alpha > 0$.

Theorem 1.8 (Milne-type inequality in the third sense). [3] Assume that the assumptions of Theorem 1.5. Then we have

$$\begin{aligned} &\left| \frac{1}{3} \left[2f(a) - f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 2f(b) \right] - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{2(b-a)^\alpha} [J_{a+}^\alpha f(b) + J_{b-}^\alpha f(a)] \right| \\ &\leq \frac{b-a}{2} [\Upsilon_1(\alpha) + \Upsilon_2(\alpha)] [|f'(a)| + |f'(b)|], \end{aligned}$$

for $\alpha > 0$, where

$$\Upsilon_1(\alpha) = \int_0^{\frac{1}{2}} \left| t^\alpha - \frac{2}{3} \right| dt = \begin{cases} \frac{2\alpha}{\alpha+1} \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}+1} + \frac{1}{2^{\alpha+1}(\alpha+1)} - \frac{1}{3}, & 0 \leq \alpha \leq \frac{\ln \frac{2}{3}}{\ln \frac{1}{2}} \\ \frac{1}{3} - \frac{1}{2^{\alpha+1}(\alpha+1)} & \alpha > \frac{\ln \frac{2}{3}}{\ln \frac{1}{2}} \end{cases}$$

and

$$\Upsilon_2(\alpha) = \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^1 \left| t^\alpha - \frac{1}{3} \right| dt = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\alpha+1} - \frac{1}{2^{\alpha+1}(\alpha+1)} - \frac{1}{6}, & 0 \leq \alpha \leq \frac{\ln \frac{1}{3}}{\ln \frac{1}{2}} \\ \frac{2\alpha}{\alpha+1} \left(\frac{1}{3}\right)^{\frac{1}{\alpha}+1} + \frac{1}{2^{\alpha+1}(\alpha+1)} + \frac{1}{\alpha+1} - \frac{1}{2} & \alpha > \frac{\ln \frac{1}{3}}{\ln \frac{1}{2}} \end{cases}$$

2 Main Results

In this section, we will prove an upper and below bound for the difference given in Theorem 1.7 by using the functions whose second derivatives are bounded.

Theorem 2.1. Let $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a twice differentiable function and $f \in L_1[a, b]$. If f'' is bounded, i.e. $m \leq f''(t) \leq M, t \in (a, b), m, M \in \mathbb{R}$, then we have the inequalities

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\alpha^2 + 6\alpha + 1}{4(\alpha + 1)(\alpha + 2)} (b - a)^2 m & (6) \\ & \leq \frac{1}{3} \left[2f(a) - f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 2f(b) \right] \\ & \quad - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{(b - a)^\alpha} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}^\alpha f(b) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}^\alpha f(a) \right] \\ & \leq \frac{\alpha^2 + 6\alpha + 1}{4(\alpha + 1)(\alpha + 2)} (b - a)^2 M. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. From the definition of Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{(b - a)^\alpha} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}^\alpha f(b) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}^\alpha f(a) \right] & (7) \\ & = \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\alpha}{(b - a)^\alpha} \left[\int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^b (b - x)^{\alpha-1} f(x) dx + \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} (x - a)^{\alpha-1} f(x) dx \right] \\ & = \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\alpha}{(b - a)^\alpha} \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} [f(x) + f(a + b - x)] (x - a)^{\alpha-1} dx. \end{aligned}$$

Using the identity (7), we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{3} \left[2f(a) - f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 2f(b) \right] & (8) \\ & \quad - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{(b - a)^\alpha} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}^\alpha f(b) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}^\alpha f(a) \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \frac{1}{3} \left[2f(a) - f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 2f(b) \right] \\
&\quad - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\alpha}{(b-a)^\alpha} \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} [f(x) + f(a+b-x)] (x-a)^{\alpha-1} dx \\
&= \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\alpha}{3(b-a)^\alpha} \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \left[\begin{aligned} &4f(a) - 2f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 4f(b) \\ &-3f(x) - 3f(a+b-x) \end{aligned} \right] (x-a)^{\alpha-1} dx.
\end{aligned}$$

Using the facts that

$$f(x) - f(a) = \int_a^x f'(t) dt$$

and

$$f(b) - f(a+b-x) = \int_{a+b-x}^b f'(t) dt,$$

we get

$$\begin{aligned}
&f(a) + f(b) - f(x) - f(a+b-x) \tag{9} \\
&= \int_{a+b-x}^b f'(t) dt - \int_a^x f'(t) dt \\
&= \int_a^x f'(a+b-u) du - \int_a^x f'(t) dt \\
&= \int_a^x [f'(a+b-t) - f'(t)] dt.
\end{aligned}$$

On the other hand, we have

$$f(a) - f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) = - \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} f'(t) dt \tag{10}$$

and

$$f(b) - f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) = \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^b f'(t) dt. \tag{11}$$

By (10) and (11), we get

$$f(a) + f(b) - 2f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \tag{12}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^b f'(t)dt - \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} f'(t)dt \\
 &= \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} f'(a+b-t)dt - \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} f'(t)dt \\
 &= \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} [f'(a+b-t) - f'(t)] dt.
 \end{aligned}$$

We also have

$$f'(a+b-t) - f'(t) = \int_t^{a+b-t} f''(u)du. \tag{13}$$

By using the equality (13) and $m < f''(u) < M, u \in (a, b)$, we obtain,

$$m \int_t^{a+b-t} du \leq \int_t^{a+b-t} f''(u)du \leq M \int_t^{a+b-t} du$$

i.e.

$$m(a+b-2t) \leq f'(a+b-t) - f'(t) \leq M(a+b-2t). \tag{14}$$

By integrating the inequality (14) with respect to t on $[a, x]$, from (9), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 &m \left[\left(\frac{b-a}{2} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{a+b}{2} - x \right)^2 \right] \\
 &\leq f(a) + f(b) - f(x) - f(a+b-x) \\
 &\leq M \left[\left(\frac{b-a}{2} \right)^2 - \left(\frac{a+b}{2} - x \right)^2 \right].
 \end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

That is,

$$\begin{aligned}
 &m(x-a)(b-x) \\
 &\leq f(a) + f(b) - f(x) - f(a+b-x) \\
 &\leq M(x-a)(b-x).
 \end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

Similarly, integrating the inequality (14) with respect to t on $\left[a, \frac{a+b}{2} \right]$, from (12), we obtain

$$m \left(\frac{b-a}{2} \right)^2 \leq f(a) + f(b) - 2f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) \leq M \left(\frac{b-a}{2} \right)^2. \tag{17}$$

By using the inequalities (16) and (17), we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 & 3m(x-a)(b-x) + m\left(\frac{b-a}{2}\right)^2 \tag{18} \\
 & \leq 4f(a) - 2f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 4f(b) - 3f(x) - 3f(a+b-x) \\
 & \leq 3M(x-a)(b-x) + M\left(\frac{b-a}{2}\right)^2.
 \end{aligned}$$

Multiplying the inequality (18) by $\frac{2^{\alpha-1}\alpha}{(b-a)^\alpha}(x-a)^{\alpha-1}$ and integrating the resultant inequality with respect to x on $\left[a, \frac{a+b}{2}\right]$, we establish

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{m2^{\alpha-1}\alpha}{(b-a)^\alpha} \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \left[3(x-a)(b-x) + \left(\frac{b-a}{2}\right)^2 \right] (x-a)^{\alpha-1} dx \\
 & \leq \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\alpha}{3(b-a)^\alpha} \\
 & \quad \times \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \left[4f(a) - 2f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 4f(b) \right. \\
 & \quad \left. - 3f(x) - 3f(a+b-x) \right] (x-a)^{\alpha-1} dx \\
 & \leq \frac{M2^{\alpha-1}\alpha}{(b-a)^\alpha} \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \left[3(x-a)(b-x) + \left(\frac{b-a}{2}\right)^2 \right] (x-a)^{\alpha-1} dx.
 \end{aligned}$$

By the equality (8) and equality

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\alpha}{(b-a)^\alpha} \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \left[3(x-a)(b-x) + \left(\frac{b-a}{2}\right)^2 \right] (x-a)^{\alpha-1} dx \\
 & = \frac{\alpha^2 + 6\alpha + 1}{4(\alpha + 1)(\alpha + 2)} (b-a)^2,
 \end{aligned}$$

we get the desired inequality (6).

This completes the proof. □

Remark 2.1. If we choose $\alpha = 1$ in Theorem 2.1, then we have the following inequality

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{3}{8} (b-a)^2 m \\
 & \leq \frac{1}{3} \left[2f(a) - f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 2f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} f(t) dt \\
 & \leq \frac{3}{8} (b-a)^2 M.
 \end{aligned}$$

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A Note on Fractional Simpson-like Type Inequality for Functions whose Second Derivatives are of Bounded Variation

Hüseyin Budak¹, İrem Çay¹, İrem Bağlan¹

¹ Department of Mathematics, Kocaeli University, Kocaeli, Türkiye

Corresponding author: irem.atac@kocaeli.edu.tr

ORCID IDs:

First Author: 0000-0001-8843-955X

Second Author: 0000-0001-9234-2523

Third Author: 0000-0003-4900-6027

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Abstract

In this study, a Simpson-type equality for the Riemann–Liouville fractional integral is established. Using this equality, several fractional Simpson-type inequalities are proved for functions whose second derivatives are of bounded variation.

Keywords: Fractional integrals, Simpson-type inequality, bounded variation

1 Introduction

Fractional calculus has become an essential tool in the analysis of various mathematical models due to its ability to capture memory and hereditary properties. In particular, fractional integral inequalities play a significant role in establishing bounds and estimating errors in numerical approximation methods. Among these, Simpson-type inequalities provide effective estimates for integrals and have recently been extended to the fractional setting. Motivated by these developments, we investigate a Simpson-type equality involving the Riemann–Liouville fractional integral. Based on this equality, we derive several fractional Simpson-like inequalities for functions whose second derivatives are of bounded variation.

Now, let us give the definition of a function of bounded variation and introduce the basic concepts of fractional calculus that will be needed in subsequent analysis.

Definition 1.1. Let $P : a = x_0 < x_1 < \dots < x_n = b$ be any partition of $[a, b]$ and let $\Delta F(x_i) = F(x_{i+1}) - F(x_i)$. Then F is said to be of bounded variation if the sum

$$\sum_{i=1}^n |\Delta F(x_i)|$$

is bounded for all such partitions.

Let F be of bounded variation on $[a, b]$, and $\sum \Delta F(P)$ denotes the sum $\sum_{i=1}^n |\Delta F(x_i)|$ corresponding to the partition P of $[a, b]$. The number

$$V_a^b(F) := \sup \left\{ \sum \Delta F(P) : P \in (P[a, b]) \right\}$$

is called the total variation of F on $[a, b]$. Here $P([a, b])$ denotes the family of partitions of $[a, b]$.

Definition 1.2. (See [4, 7]) If $f \in L_1[a, b]$ is a function, then the integrals $I_{a+}^\alpha f(x)$ and $I_{b-}^\alpha f(x)$ of order $\alpha > 0$ are defined by

$$I_{a+}^\alpha f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_a^x (x-t)^{\alpha-1} f(t) dt, \quad x > a$$

and

$$I_{b-}^\alpha f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_x^b (t-x)^{\alpha-1} f(t) dt, \quad x < b,$$

respectively. These integrals are called Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals in the literature. Here, Γ is the Gamma function defined by

$$\Gamma(\alpha) = \int_0^\infty e^{-u} u^{\alpha-1} du.$$

Fractional integral inequalities and their applications have been established using the Riemann-Liouville fractional integral. For example, Sarikaya and colleagues have established some Simpson-like inequalities for functions with convex second derivatives [8]. Hezenci and Budak have also proven some fractional Simpson-like inequalities for functions with convex third derivatives in absolute values [5]. Furthermore, some fractional Simpson-like inequalities for functions with convex second derivatives in absolute values have been proven in [6]. For more information on various properties of Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals and various fractional integral operators, the reader is referred to [3, 2, 1].

The aim of this paper is to establish a new Simpson-like equation based on the Riemann-Liouville fractional integral and, using this equation, to obtain various fractional Simpson-like inequalities for functions with bounded variations in second derivatives. The overall design of this paper consists of four sections, including the introduction. A new Simpson-type equation, which serves as the main tool of the study, is established in Section 2. In Section 3, various fractional Simpson-type inequalities are derived using the equation obtained in Section 2. Finally, in Section 4, the results are discussed.

2 A New and Essential Equality

In this section, we derive a key integral identity that forms the foundation for the principal results presented in this paper.

Lemma 2.1. Let $F : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a three times differentiable function on $[a, b]$ such that

$F'''L \in [a, b]$. Then, the following equality holds

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{(\alpha+1)(\alpha+2)} \left[F(a) + (\alpha^2 + 3\alpha)F\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + F(b) \right] - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{(b-a)^\alpha} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^\alpha - F(a) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^\alpha + F(b) \right] \\ &= \frac{(b-a)^2}{8(\alpha+1)(\alpha+2)} \int_a^b p(x) d(F''(x)), \end{aligned}$$

where

$$p(x) = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{2(x-a)}{b-a}\right)^{\alpha+2} - \left(\frac{2(x-a)}{b-a}\right)^2, & a < x \leq \frac{a+b}{2}, \\ \left(\frac{2(b-x)}{b-a}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{2(b-x)}{b-a}\right)^{\alpha+2}, & \frac{a+b}{2} < x < b. \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} \int_a^b p(x) d(F''(x)) &= \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \left[\left(\frac{2(x-a)}{b-a}\right)^{\alpha+2} - \left(\frac{2(x-a)}{b-a}\right)^2 \right] d(F''(x)) \\ &+ \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^b \left[\left(\frac{2(b-x)}{b-a}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{2(b-x)}{b-a}\right)^{\alpha+2} \right] d(F''(x)) \end{aligned}$$

By applying integration by parts, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 &= \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \left[\left(\frac{2(x-a)}{b-a}\right)^{\alpha+2} - \left(\frac{2(x-a)}{b-a}\right)^2 \right] d(F''(x)) \\ &= \left[\left(\frac{2(x-a)}{b-a}\right)^{\alpha+2} - \left(\frac{2(x-a)}{b-a}\right)^2 \right] F''(x) \Big|_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \\ &- \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \left[\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\right)^{\alpha+2} (\alpha+2)(x-a)^{\alpha+1} - \frac{8}{(b-a)^2}(x-a) \right] d(F'(x)) \\ &= - \left[\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\right)^{\alpha+2} (\alpha+2)(x-a)^{\alpha+1} - \frac{8}{(b-a)^2}(x-a) \right] F'(x) \Big|_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \\ &+ \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \left[\left(\frac{2}{b-a}\right)^{\alpha+2} (\alpha+2)(\alpha+1)(x-a)^\alpha - \frac{8}{(b-a)^2} \right] d(F(x)) \\ &= \left[\frac{4}{b-a} - \frac{2(\alpha+2)}{b-a} \right] F' \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + \left[(\alpha+1)(\alpha+2) \left(\frac{2}{b-a}\right)^{\alpha+2} (x-a)^\alpha - \frac{8}{(b-a)^2} \right] F(x) \Big|_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \\ &- \frac{\alpha(\alpha+1)(\alpha+2)2^{\alpha+2}\Gamma(\alpha)}{(b-a)^{\alpha+2}} \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} (x-a)^\alpha F(x) dx \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} I_2 &= \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^b \left[\left(\frac{2(b-x)}{b-a}\right)^2 - \left(\frac{2(b-x)}{b-a}\right)^{\alpha+2} \right] d(F''(x)) \\ &= \left[\frac{2(\alpha+2)}{b-a} - \frac{4}{b-a} \right] F' \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + \left[\frac{8}{(b-a)^2} - (\alpha+1)(\alpha+2) \left(\frac{2}{b-a}\right)^{\alpha+2} (b-x)^\alpha \right] F(x) \Big|_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^b \\ &- \frac{\alpha(\alpha+1)(\alpha+2)2^{\alpha+2}\Gamma(\alpha)}{(b-a)^{\alpha+2}} \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^b (b-x)^\alpha F(x) dx \end{aligned}$$

If we add I_1 and I_2 , we obtain the following equation

$$I_1 + I_2 = 8 \left[\frac{(\alpha + 1)(\alpha + 2)}{(b - a)^2} - \frac{2}{(b - a)^2} \right] F \left(\frac{a + b}{2} \right) + \frac{8}{(b - a)^2} [F(a) + F(b)] - \frac{\alpha(\alpha + 1)(\alpha + 2)2^{\alpha+2}\Gamma(\alpha)}{(b - a)^{\alpha+2}} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}^\alpha F(a) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}^\alpha F(b) \right]$$

Thus the proof is completed. □

3 Simpson-Like Inequalities

Theorem 3.1. Let $F : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be such that F'' is a continuous function of bounded variation on $[a, b]$. Then we have the inequality

$$\left| \frac{1}{(\alpha + 1)(\alpha + 2)} \left[F(a) + (\alpha^2 + 3\alpha)F \left(\frac{a + b}{2} \right) + F(b) \right] - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{(b - a)^\alpha} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}^\alpha F(a) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}^\alpha F(b) \right] \right| \leq \frac{\alpha 2^{2/\alpha-3}(b - a)^2}{(\alpha + 1)(\alpha + 2)^{2/\alpha+2}} \bigvee_a^b(F'').$$

Proof. From the equality (1), we can write

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{(\alpha + 1)(\alpha + 2)} \left[F(a) + (\alpha^2 + 3\alpha)F \left(\frac{a + b}{2} \right) + F(b) \right] - \frac{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha + 1)}{(b - a)^\alpha} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}^\alpha F(a) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}^\alpha F(b) \right] \right| \\ &= \frac{(b - a)^2}{8(\alpha + 1)(\alpha + 2)} \left| \int_a^b p(x) d(F''(x)) \right| \\ &= \frac{1}{2(\alpha + 1)(\alpha + 2)} \\ & \times \left| \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \left[\left(\frac{2}{b - a} \right)^\alpha (x - a)^{\alpha+2} - (x - a)^2 \right] d(F''(x)) + \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^b \left[(b - x)^2 - \left(\frac{2}{b - a} \right)^\alpha (b - x)^{\alpha+2} \right] d(F''(x)) \right| \\ &\leq \frac{1}{2(\alpha + 1)(\alpha + 2)} \left| \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \left[\left(\frac{2}{b - a} \right)^\alpha (x - a)^{\alpha+2} - (x - a)^2 \right] d(F''(x)) \right| \\ &+ \frac{1}{2(\alpha + 1)(\alpha + 2)} \left| \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^b \left[(b - x)^2 - \left(\frac{2}{b - a} \right)^\alpha (b - x)^{\alpha+2} \right] d(F''(x)) \right| \\ &\leq \frac{1}{2(\alpha + 1)(\alpha + 2)} \left\{ \sup_{x \in [a, \frac{a+b}{2}]} \left| \left(\frac{2}{b - a} \right)^\alpha (x - a)^{\alpha+2} - (x - a)^2 \right| \bigvee_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}}(F'') \right. \\ & \left. + \sup_{x \in [\frac{a+b}{2}, b]} \left| (b - x)^2 - \left(\frac{2}{b - a} \right)^\alpha (b - x)^{\alpha+2} \right| \bigvee_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^b(F'') \right\} \\ &\leq \frac{\alpha 2^{2/\alpha-3}(b - a)^2}{(\alpha + 1)(\alpha + 2)^{2/\alpha+2}} \bigvee_a^b(F'') \end{aligned}$$

Thus the proof is completed. □

Corollary 3.1. If we choose $\alpha = 1$ in Theorem 3.1, then the following Simpson type inequality

holds:

$$\left| \frac{1}{6} \left[F(a) + 4F\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + F(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b F(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{(b-a)^2}{324} \mathcal{V}_a^b(F'').$$

4 Conclusions

In this study, a new Simpson-type equation is derived in the framework of the Riemann–Liouville fractional integral, and various fractional Simpson-like inequalities are derived using this equation for functions whose second derivatives have a bounded total variation. The results generalize the classical Simpson inequality to the fractional integral context and provide new evaluations valid for a broader class of functions. The findings here are expected to provide a foundation for applications of fractional calculus associated with fractional integral operators.

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A Fuzzy Mathematical Decision Model for Residential Rooftop PV Adoption: The HEART Approach

Kaan Deveci

¹*Department of Energy, Science and Technology, Turkish-German University, Istanbul, Türkiye*

Corresponding author: deveci@tau.edu.tr

ORCID IDs:

First Author: [0000-0003-0301-2296](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0301-2296)

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Abstract

The decreasing cost of photovoltaic (PV) technologies, increasing electricity prices, and evolving environmental concerns have led homeowners to show greater interest in rooftop energy systems. However, adoption decisions depend on multiple economic, technical, and behavioral factors. This study develops a mathematical decision framework to model household investment behavior under uncertainty for Turkey by integrating intuitionistic fuzzy sets with the Hypervolume-based Evaluation and Ranking Technique (HEART). The uncertainty in household preferences is represented through linguistic evaluations provided by decision makers of the study, which are translated into intuitionistic fuzzy sets. The alternatives of decision framework are defined as investing in rooftop PV, rooftop PV with battery storage, and a no-investment baseline. The multi-criteria analysis revealed that no investment case is the most preferable decision under current Turkish conditions. This is predominantly driven by the high capital recovery risk, upfront cost burden, and significant procedural complexity associated with active investment alternatives. The findings strongly indicate that better-designed tariff regimes, targeted financing, and streamlined bureaucratic procedures are necessary to overcome the current barriers and accelerate widespread household adoption.

Keywords: Investment decision modeling, rooftop photovoltaics adoption, multi-criteria decision making.

1. Introduction and Motivation

Global electricity costs have risen markedly over the past decade, amplifying household exposure to price volatility and motivating interest in demand-side measures. At the same time, overall energy needs continue to grow with electrification trends (cooling, appliances, EV readiness), increasing the salience of reliable and affordable supply at the customer side. Technological progress has driven substantial cost declines in renewables, with photovoltaics (PV) experiencing some of the steepest learning rates among clean technologies. As module and balance-of-system costs have fallen, PV adoption has expanded worldwide, especially where retail tariffs and policy instruments translate technical potential into household value.

Turkey shares the global decline in PV technology costs; however, household uptake has not matched international peers due to the prevailing retail pricing context—predominantly a single-rate (flat) tariff—and the way tariff and netting rules shape on-site value. Under flat pricing, the arbitrage value of behind-the-meter storage is limited, and PV savings hinge on self-consumption alignment rather than price spreads. Consequently, many households remain on the fence despite improving hardware affordability, particularly when upfront costs, perceived procedural frictions, and behavioral factors are considered alongside tariff design. These elements together create a mixed picture for the average homeowner.

Homeowner investors considering investments in solar PV panels face a three-way choice: PV only, PV with battery, or no investment. The research goal is building an investment decision model of a compact decision view that remains transparent under uncertainty. Expert evaluations are expressed through decision makers' linguistic terms (e.g., very low...very high), by which uncertainty is explicitly modeled via intuitionistic fuzzy sets. The contribution is twofold. First, the Turkish homeowner's PV decision is framed as a multi-criteria problem with a clear set of nationally relevant criteria. Second, a solution under uncertainty and missing information is demonstrated using the HEART procedure.

2. Mathematical Framework / Material and Methods

Fuzzy logic is central to defining and modeling uncertainty because it accommodates human linguistic judgments and approximate reasoning[1]. Yet ordinary fuzzy sets, which use only a single membership degree, can be insufficient for rating criteria since they do not separately capture counter-evidence or residual doubt in expert assessments. To overcome this limitation, extended formulations are used. Intuitionistic fuzzy sets (IFS), introduced by Atanassov, represent each evaluation with both a membership and a non-membership degree, and interpret the remainder as hesitation [2]. In this way, support, opposition, and uncertainty are all recorded explicitly, leading to clearer and more reliable decision inputs.

Previously, a new multi criteria decision making method, HEART is proposed to as a new multi criteria decision making method with IFS [3]. The solution procedure and flowchart of HEART method is given below.

Step 1: Collect the Decision Maker (DM) evaluations on alternatives ($\tilde{A}_{j,i}^l$), importance of each criterion (\tilde{w}_j^l), and DM expertise for each criterion (\tilde{e}_j^l) where l ($l \in \{1,2, \dots, q\}$) corresponds to the number of DM, i ($i \in \{1,2, \dots, n\}$) represents the number of alternatives, and j ($j \in \{1,2, \dots, m\}$) represents the number of criteria. Same notations also will be used in the below equations.

Step 2: Aggregate DM evaluations on alternatives ($\tilde{A}_{j,i}^l$) defined for each criterion (\tilde{e}_j^l) by using IFA and obtain the aggregated evaluation matrix (\tilde{A}_{ji}) as given in Eq. 1.

$$\tilde{A}_{ji} = IFA(\tilde{A}_{j,i}^l, \dots; \tilde{e}_j^l, \dots) = \left(\frac{\sum_{l=1}^q \mu_{\tilde{A}_{j,i}^l} \mu_{\tilde{e}_j^l}}{\sum_{l=1}^q \mu_{\tilde{e}_j^l}}, \frac{\sum_{l=1}^q \nu_{\tilde{A}_{j,i}^l} \mu_{\tilde{e}_j^l}}{\sum_{l=1}^q \mu_{\tilde{e}_j^l}} \right) \quad (1)$$

Step 3: Aggregate DM evaluations on criteria importance (\tilde{w}_j^l) and obtain the matrix of aggregated criteria importance (\tilde{w}_{ji}) as below.

$$\tilde{w}_{ji} = IFA(\tilde{w}_j^l, \dots; \tilde{e}_j^l, \dots) = \left(\frac{\sum_{l=1}^q \mu_{\tilde{w}_j^l} \mu_{\tilde{e}_j^l}}{\sum_{l=1}^q \mu_{\tilde{e}_j^l}}, \frac{\sum_{l=1}^q \nu_{\tilde{w}_j^l} \mu_{\tilde{e}_j^l}}{\sum_{l=1}^q \mu_{\tilde{e}_j^l}} \right) \quad (2)$$

Step 4: Normalize the aggregated evaluation matrix (\tilde{A}_{ji}) by using Eq. 3 as follows [4].

$$\tilde{A}_{ji} = [\mu_{ji}, \nu_{ji}]$$

$$\tilde{N}_{ji} = \begin{cases} [\mu_{ji}, \nu_{ji}], & \text{if } j \in B \\ [\nu_{ji}, \mu_{ji}], & \text{if } j \in C \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

here B and C represent the set of benefit and cost criteria, respectively.

Step 5: Calculate the weighted normalized evaluation matrix ($\tilde{r}_{ji} = \tilde{N}_{ji} \otimes \tilde{w}_{ji}$) by using Eq. 4 as follows.

$$\tilde{r}_{ji} = (x, \mu_{\tilde{N}}(x)\mu_{\tilde{w}}(x), v_{\tilde{N}}(x) + v_{\tilde{w}}(x) - v_{\tilde{N}}(x)v_{\tilde{w}}(x) | x \in U) \quad (4)$$

Step 6: Using weighted normalized evaluation matrix (\tilde{r}_{ji}) generate decision spaces (U_{μ_i} and U_{v_i}) for each alternative and calculate the HV metric for each decision spaces (HV_{μ} and HV_v) with respect to reference point (r_j). Calculate HV_{net} .

$$U_{\mu_i} = \{\mu_1, \mu_2, \dots, \mu_n\}, U_{v_i} = \{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_n\} \quad (5)$$

$$HV_{\mu,i} = \prod_{j=1}^m |U_{\mu_{j,i}} - r_j| \quad (6)$$

$$HV_{v,i} = \prod_{j=1}^m |U_{v_{j,i}} - r_j| \quad (7)$$

$$HV_{net,i} = HV_{\mu,i} - HV_{v,i} \quad (8)$$

Step 7: Rank the alternatives based on the HV_{net} values. C

Fig.1: The flowchart of HEART.

3. Problem Definition

Household adoption of rooftop solar PV has been rising, driven primarily by declining technology costs and sustained increases in retail electricity prices. Homeowners face three mutually exclusive alternatives for meeting their electricity needs: invest in PV only (A1), invest in PV with battery storage (A2), or not invest and continue purchasing all electricity need from the grid (A3). The decision is evaluated across six criteria selected for nationwide relevance: capital recovery risk (cost-type), upfront financial burden (cost-type), grid price sensitivity (benefit type), self-consumption potential (benefit type), behavioral and social influence (benefit type), and procedural complexity (cost type). Within this study, two decision makers (DMs) provide linguistic assessments that encode

uncertainty to alternatives and criteria, as given in Table 1 and Table 2, respectively. These assessments are mapped to intuitionistic fuzzy sets and aggregated using HEART (Hypervolume-based Evaluation and Ranking Technique) to perform the MCDM, yielding a robust ranking of the three alternatives under Turkish conditions. A brief explanation of the criterion set used to rank the available energy alternatives is presented below.

C1. Capital Recovery Risk: The uncertainty and temporal risk associated with recouping invested capital are reflected. Longer and more volatile recovery horizons are understood to increase risk (e.g., tariff volatility, weak self-consumption, financing terms). The no-investment alternative is evaluated as very low risk because no capital is exposed.

C2. Upfront Financial Burden (cost-type): The immediate budget strain due to acquisition and installation is captured, with grants/discounts considered within the net upfront. Higher upfront amounts are understood to reduce affordability. The no-investment alternative is evaluated as zerolow burden.

C3. Grid Price Sensitivity: This measures the household's vulnerability to fluctuations in retail electricity tariffs and potential price hikes. Alternatives with high self-sufficiency insulate the user from market volatility, whereas the "no investment" option leaves the household fully exposed (the worst value) to grid pricing dynamics and future tariff increases.

C4. Self Consumption Potential: This criterion gauges the degree to which a household can meet its energy demand without relying on the external grid. A combination of PV and battery storage offers the highest level of independence and security of supply, while the "no investment" case represents zero autonomy (the worst value) and total reliance on grid availability.

C5. Behavioral and social influence: Covers peer effects, environmental attitudes, and perceived technology risk. Visible neighborhood adoptions and pro-environmental values shift the decision toward investing.

*C6. Procedural Complexity (cost-type):*The administrative and operational burden required for implementation is captured, including permitting, grid-interconnection procedures, metering changes, and on-site installation logistics. Lower complexity is preferred. The no-investment alternative is evaluated as very low complexity, whereas active investment options are evaluated according to current regulatory and technical steps.

Table 1. Linguistic labels which are used to evaluate alternatives.

Linguistic Term	IF Value
Extremely High (EH)	(1 0)
Very very high (VVH)	(0.9 0.1)
Very high (VH)	(0.8 0.10)
High (H)	(0.7 0.2)
Moderately high (MH)	(0.6 0.3)
Fair (F)	(0.5 0.4)
Moderately low (ML)	(0.4 0.5)
Low (L)	(0.25 0.6)
Very low (VL)	(0.1 0.75)
Very very low (VVL)	(0.1 0.9)

Table 2. Linguistic labels which are used to evaluate the importance of criteria.

Linguistic Term	IF Value
Very important (VI)	(0.9 0.10)
Important (I)	(0.75 0.2)
Medium (M)	(0.5 0.45)
Unimportant (UI)	(0.35 0.6)
Very unimportant (VUI)	(0.1 0.9)

3. Results and Discussion

DM evaluations on each alternative and criteria are given in Table 3 and Table 4, respectively. The aggregated DM evaluations on alternatives and criteria set are given in Table 5 and Table 6, respectively.

Table 3: DM Evaluations on alternatives.

	A1		A2		A3	
	DM1	DM2	DM1	DM2	DM1	DM2
C1	VVH	MH	F	VH	(0 1)	(0 1)
C2	ML	MH	VVH	VH	(0 1)	(0 1)
C3	G	G	G	G	VVH	VVH
C4	H	L	VH	F	(0 1)	(0 1)
C5	H	MH	H	MH	L	F
C6	G	G	G	G	(1 0)	(1 0)

Table 4: DM evaluations on criteria set.

	C1	C2	C3	C4	C5	C6
DM1	I	VI	VI	M	M	VI
DM2	I	I	VI	M	M	VI

Table 5: Aggregated DM evaluations on alternatives.

Criteria	A1	A2	A3
C1	(0.75, 0.2)	(0.65, 0.25)	(0, 1)
C2	(0.5, 0.4)	(0.85, 0.1)	(0, 1)
C3	(0.7, 0.2)	(0.7, 0.2)	(0.9, 0.1)
C4	(0.475, 0.4)	(0.65, 0.25)	(0, 1)
C5	(0.65, 0.25)	(0.65, 0.25)	(0.375, 0.5)
C6	(0.7, 0.2)	(0.7, 0.2)	(1, 0)

Table 6: Aggregated criteria importance.

Criteria	\tilde{w}_{ji}
C1	(0.75, 0.2)
C2	(0.825, 0.15)
C3	(0.9, 0.1)
C4	(0.5, 0.45)
C5	(0.5, 0.45)
C6	(0.9, 0.1)

Once the aggregated matrices are obtained, the normalized aggregated DM evaluation and the weighted normalized aggregated DM evaluation matrices are obtained as given in Table 7 and Table 8, respectively.

Table 7. Normalized aggregated DM evaluation matrix.

	A1	A2	A3
C1	(0.2,0.75)	(0.25,0.65)	(1,0)
C2	(0.4,0.5)	(0.1,0.85)	(1,0)
C3	(0.7,0.2)	(0.7,0.2)	(0.9,0.1)
C4	(0.475,0.4)	(0.65,0.25)	(0,1)
C5	(0.65,0.25)	(0.65,0.25)	(0.375,0.5)
C6	(0.7,0.2)	(0.7,0.2)	(1,0)

Table 8. Weighted normalized aggregated DM evaluation matrix.

	A1	A2	A3
C1	(0.15,0.8)	(0.1875,0.72)	(0.75,0.2)
C2	(0.33,0.575)	(0.0825,0.8725)	(0.825,0.15)
C3	(0.63,0.28)	(0.63,0.28)	(0.81,0.19)
C4	(0.2375,0.67)	(0.325,0.5875)	(0,1)
C5	(0.325,0.5875)	(0.325,0.5875)	(0.1875,0.725)
C6	(0.63,0.28)	(0.63,0.28)	(0.9,0.1)

Finally, the hypervolume values of the decision spaces are obtained as in Table 9. And the ranking order is obtained as $A3 > A1 > A2$, where A1 corresponds to PV only option, A2 is PV with battery option, and A3 corresponds to no investment. This ordering is explained by heightened capital-recovery risk and upfront burden for the investment alternatives, together with limited tariff-induced demand under the current flat pricing. Consequently, PV-only was evaluated above PV+battery, while the no-investment option remained preferred overall.

Table 9. HV values for decision spaces of the available alternatives.

	A1	A2	A3
HV_{μ}	6.663	5.997	13.043
HV_{ν}	12.314	13.298	6.232
HV_{net}	-5.659	-7.302	6.810

5. Conclusions

A rooftop PV investment model was generated as a multi-criteria decision under uncertainty and solved with an intuitionistic fuzzy HEART procedure. Three alternatives are selected, investing in PV, investing in PV and battery, and no investment, against six nationally relevant criteria using linguistic inputs from two decision makers. The final ranking was $A3 > A1 > A2$. This ordering was driven by higher capital recovery risk and upfront burden for investments, limited tariff-induced demand under the current single-rate structure, modest self-consumption alignment, and greater procedural complexity for PV options. The outcome aligns with Turkey's present diffusion pattern, where rooftop PV remains far from widespread household adoption.

Policy levers were indicated: better-designed tariff regimes (e.g., netting or TOU spreads), targeted financing to lower upfront costs, and streamlined procedures to cut complexity. Such changes are expected to narrow the gap to A3, with PV only improving first and PV with battery becoming competitive under stronger TOU spreads or storage incentives.

The future work can expand DM panels, segment weights, and financing detail, and track outcomes under evolving tariffs and incentives.

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Some Conformable Fractional Newton-type Inequalities via Bounded and Lipschitzian Functions

Mehmet Sarıışık¹, Fatih Hezenci¹

¹Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Science and Arts, Duzce University, Duzce 81620, Türkiye

Corresponding author: mehmet03srsk@gmail.com

ORCID IDs:

First Author: [0009-0008-9659-665X](https://orcid.org/0009-0008-9659-665X)

Second Author: [0000-0003-1008-5856](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1008-5856)

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Abstract

The core purpose of this study is to investigate some Newton-type inequalities in the framework of conformable fractional operators. These type of inequalities are established for bounded functions and further results are obtained for Lipschitzian functions. In this way, the classical Newton-type inequalities are extended through the perspective of fractional analysis. Moreover, through specific selections of the obtained inequalities, further results are derived, which emphasize the versatility and practical applicability of the proposed approach. Overall, this study adds to the literature on fractional analysis and functional inequalities and also provides a basis for future work in this area.

Keywords: Newton-type inequalities, bounded functions, Lipschitzian functions.

1 Introduction and Basic Concepts

The Hermite-Hadamard and Simpson-type inequalities have received significant attention in recent years. In particular, Simpson-type inequalities are derived from Simpson's classical rule in numerical integration. Simpson's second rule corresponds to the three-point Newton-Cotes quadrature formula. As a result, evaluations involving a quadratic kernel with three nodes are often referred to as Newton-type results, which are commonly known in the literature as Newton-type inequalities. These inequalities have been extensively studied by numerous researchers. For instance, Gao and Shi [1] proved some Newton-type inequalities for functions whose second derivatives are convex. In paper [2], some error estimates of Newton-type quadrature formula by bounded variation and Lipschitzian functions were considered. Moreover, Noor et al. investigated Newton-type inequalities related to harmonic convex functions in [3], and to p -harmonic convex functions in [4]. In [5], some Newton-type inequalities established by convex functions within the framework of quantum calculus. For more information and unresolved questions on Newton-type inequalities, see [6, 7] and the references cited therein.

Fractional calculus has attracted significant interest recently due to its wide applications across various scientific fields. In response to its importance, many fractional integral operators have been introduced and studied. Using Hermite–Hadamard-type and Simpson-type inequalities, bounds for these newly developed formulas can be established. Notably, Hermite–Hadamard-type and trapezoidal-type inequalities were first explored with Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals in [8].

Definition 1.1 (See [9, 10]). Let $f \in L_1[a, b]$, $a, b \in \mathbb{R}$ with $a < b$. The Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals $J_{a+}^\beta f$ and $J_{b-}^\beta f$ of order $\beta > 0$ are defined by

$$J_{a+}^\beta f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_a^x (x-t)^{\beta-1} f(t) dt, \quad x > a \quad (1)$$

and

$$J_{b-}^\beta f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_x^b (t-x)^{\beta-1} f(t) dt, \quad x < b, \quad (2)$$

respectively. Here, Γ denotes the Gamma function defined by

$$\Gamma(\beta) = \int_0^\infty e^{-u} u^{\beta-1} du.$$

Let us note that $J_{a+}^0 f(x) = J_{b-}^0 f(x) = f(x)$.

The paper [11] presents several Newton-type inequalities for differentiable convex functions derived using Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals. Additionally, the authors obtained Riemann-Liouville fractional Newton-type inequalities for functions of bounded variation. Moreover, in [12], the authors derived several Newton-type inequalities for functions whose absolute first derivatives, raised to a given power, satisfy the condition of arithmetic-harmonic convexity. Furthermore, the authors of [13] present a method to investigate Newton-type inequalities for various classes of functions using Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals. These inequalities have been further explored by numerous researchers (see, for instance, [14, 15] and the references therein).

Various types of fractional integrals, including Riemann-Liouville and conformable fractional integrals, have been studied in the context of integral inequalities. The expanding applications of these concepts have recently attracted considerable interest from researchers in mathematics, physics, and engineering [16, 17]. Moreover, fractional derivatives are also used to model a wide range of mathematical biology, as well as chemical processes and engineering problems [18, 19]. In [20], the authors introduced a new type of fractional derivative called the conformable derivative, based on the fundamental limit definition of the standard derivative. This operator possesses several useful analytical properties. The conformable derivative satisfies several key properties that are not fulfilled by the Riemann-Liouville and Caputo definitions. In paper [21] the author proved that the conformable approach in [20] cannot yield good results when compared to the Caputo definition for specific functions. This limitation of the conformable derivative has been addressed through several extensions of the conformable approach, as proposed in [22, 23].

In [24], the authors introduced fractional conformable integral operators and studied several of their fundamental properties. They also examined the relationships between these operators and other existing fractional integral definitions. The fractional conformable integral operators are defined as follows:

Definition 1.2. [24] The fractional conformable integral operator ${}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{a+}^\alpha f(x)$ and ${}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{b-}^\alpha f(x)$ of order $\beta \in \mathbb{C}$, $\operatorname{Re}(\beta) > 0$ and $\alpha \in (0, 1]$ are presented by

$${}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{a+}^\alpha f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_a^x \left(\frac{(x-a)^\alpha - (t-a)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^{\beta-1} \frac{f(t)}{(t-a)^{1-\alpha}} dt, \quad t > a \quad (3)$$

and

$${}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{b-}^\alpha f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\beta)} \int_x^b \left(\frac{(b-x)^\alpha - (b-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^{\beta-1} \frac{f(t)}{(b-t)^{1-\alpha}} dt, \quad t < b, \quad (4)$$

respectively for $f \in L_1[a, b]$.

If we consider $\alpha = 1$ in equalities (3) and (4), then the fractional integral in (3) and (4) reduces to the Riemann-Liouville fractional integral in (1) and (2), respectively. There have been a great number of research papers written on these subjects, [25, 26] and the references therein.

2 A fundamental equality

Lemma 2.1. Assume that $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is an absolutely continuous function (a, b) so that $f' \in L_1[a, b]$. Then, the following equality holds:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{\alpha^\beta \Gamma(\alpha+1)}{2(b-a)^{\alpha\beta}} \left[{}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{b-}^\alpha f(a) + {}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{a+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \quad (5) \\ & = \frac{\alpha^\beta (b-a)}{2} [I_1 + I_2 + I_3]. \end{aligned}$$

Here,

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} I_1 = \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left[\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{8\alpha^\beta} \right] [f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)] dt, \\ I_2 = \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left[\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{2\alpha^\beta} \right] [f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)] dt, \\ I_3 = \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left[\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{7}{8\alpha^\beta} \right] [f'(tb + (1-t)a) - f'(ta + (1-t)b)] dt. \end{array} \right.$$

3 Newton-type inequalities for bounded functions

In this section, we deal with some Newton-type inequalities for bounded functions via conformable fractional integrals.

Theorem 3.1. Note that the conditions of Lemma 2.1 hold. If there exist $m, M \in \mathbb{R}$ such that

$m \leq f'(t) \leq M$ for $t \in [a, b]$, then it follows

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\alpha^\beta \Gamma(\alpha+1)}{2(b-a)^{\alpha\beta}} \left[{}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{b-}^\alpha f(a) + {}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{a+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{\alpha^\beta (b-a)}{2} \{ \Omega_1(\alpha, \beta) + \Omega_2(\alpha, \beta) + \Omega_3(\alpha, \beta) \} (M - m). \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

Here,

$$\begin{cases} \Omega_1(\alpha, \beta) = \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{8\alpha^\beta} \right| dt, \\ \Omega_2(\alpha, \beta) = \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{2\alpha^\beta} \right| dt, \\ \Omega_3(\alpha, \beta) = \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{7}{8\alpha^\beta} \right| dt. \end{cases}$$

Proof. By using the Lemma 2.1, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] \\ & \quad - \frac{\alpha^\beta \Gamma(\alpha+1)}{2(b-a)^{\alpha\beta}} \left[{}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{b-}^\alpha f(a) + {}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{a+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \\ & = \frac{\alpha^\beta (b-a)}{2} \left\{ \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left[\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{8\alpha^\beta} \right] \left[f'(tb + (1-t)a) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right] dt \right. \\ & \quad + \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left[\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{8\alpha^\beta} \right] \left[\frac{m+M}{2} - f'(ta + (1-t)b) \right] dt \\ & \quad + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left[\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{2\alpha^\beta} \right] \left[f'(tb + (1-t)a) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right] dt \\ & \quad + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left[\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{2\alpha^\beta} \right] \left[\frac{m+M}{2} - f'(ta + (1-t)b) \right] dt \\ & \quad + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left[\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{7}{8\alpha^\beta} \right] \left[f'(tb + (1-t)a) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right] dt \\ & \quad \left. + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left[\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{7}{8\alpha^\beta} \right] \left[\frac{m+M}{2} - f'(ta + (1-t)b) \right] dt \right\}. \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

Through the absolute value of (7), we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\alpha^\beta \Gamma(\alpha+1)}{2(b-a)^{\alpha\beta}} \left[{}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{b-}^\alpha f(a) + {}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{a+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \right| \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&\leq \frac{\alpha^\beta (b-a)}{2} \left\{ \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{8\alpha^\beta} \right| \left| f'(tb+(1-t)a) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right| dt \right. \\
&\quad + \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{8\alpha^\beta} \right| \left| \frac{m+M}{2} - f'(ta+(1-t)b) \right| dt \\
&\quad + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{2\alpha^\beta} \right| \left| f'(tb+(1-t)a) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right| dt \\
&\quad + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{2\alpha^\beta} \right| \left| \frac{m+M}{2} - f'(ta+(1-t)b) \right| dt \\
&\quad + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{7}{8\alpha^\beta} \right| \left| f'(tb+(1-t)a) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right| dt \\
&\quad \left. + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{7}{8\alpha^\beta} \right| \left| \frac{m+M}{2} - f'(ta+(1-t)b) \right| dt \right\}.
\end{aligned}$$

It is known that $m \leq f'(t) \leq M$ for $t \in [a, b]$. Then, we have

$$\left| f'(tb+(1-t)a) - \frac{m+M}{2} \right| \leq \frac{M-m}{2}, \tag{8}$$

$$\left| \frac{m+M}{2} - f'(ta+(1-t)b) \right| \leq \frac{M-m}{2}. \tag{9}$$

With the help of the (8) and (9), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
&\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] \right. \\
&\quad \left. - \frac{\alpha^\beta \Gamma(\alpha+1)}{2(b-a)^{\alpha\beta}} \left[{}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{b^-}^\alpha f(a) + {}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \right| \\
&\leq \frac{\alpha^\beta (b-a)}{2} (M-m) \\
&\quad \times \left\{ \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{8\alpha^\beta} \right| dt \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{2\alpha^\beta} \right| dt + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{7}{8\alpha^\beta} \right| dt \right\} \\
&= \frac{\alpha^\beta (b-a)}{2} \{ \Omega_1(\alpha, \beta) + \Omega_2(\alpha, \beta) + \Omega_3(\alpha, \beta) \} (M-m).
\end{aligned}$$

□

Corollary 3.1. If we choose $\alpha = \beta = 1$ in Theorem 3.1, then we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(t) dt \right| \\ & \leq \frac{25(b-a)}{576} (M-m). \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 3.2. Let us consider $\alpha = 1$ Theorem 3.1. If there exist $M \in \mathbb{R}^+$ such that $|f'(t)| \leq M$ for all $t \in [a, b]$, then we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\beta+1)}{2(b-a)^\beta} [J_{a+}^\beta f(b) + J_{b-}^\beta f(a)] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{b-a}{2} \{ \Omega_1(1, \beta) + \Omega_2(1, \beta) + \Omega_3(1, \beta) \} M. \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 3.3. Let us consider $\beta = 1$ in Corollary 3.2. Then, the following inequality holds:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(t) dt \right| \\ & \leq \frac{25(b-a)}{288} M. \end{aligned}$$

4 Newton-type inequalities for Lipschitzian functions

In this section, we consider some Newton-type inequalities for Lipschitzian functions by using conformable fractional integrals.

Theorem 4.1. Suppose that the assumptions of Lemma 2.1 are valid. If f' is a L -Lipschitzian function on $[a, b]$, then the following inequality holds:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\alpha^\beta \Gamma(\alpha+1)}{2(b-a)^{\alpha\beta}} \left[{}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{b-}^\alpha f(a) + {}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{a+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \right| \leq \frac{\alpha^\beta (b-a)^2}{2} L \\ & \quad \times \{ 2\Omega_4(\alpha, \beta) - \Omega_1(\alpha, \beta) + 2\Omega_5(\alpha, \beta) - \Omega_2(\alpha, \beta) \\ & \quad + 2\Omega_6(\alpha, \beta) - \Omega_3(\alpha, \beta) \}. \end{aligned}$$

Here,

$$\begin{cases} \Omega_4(\alpha, \beta) = \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} t \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{8\alpha^\beta} \right| dt, \\ \Omega_5(\alpha, \beta) = \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} t \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{2\alpha^\beta} \right| dt, \\ \Omega_6(\alpha, \beta) = \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 t \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{7}{8\alpha^\beta} \right| dt. \end{cases}$$

Proof. With the aid of Lemma 2.1 and since f' is L -Lipschitzian function, we have

$$\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] \right|$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& -\frac{\alpha^\beta \Gamma(\alpha+1)}{2(b-a)^{\alpha\beta}} \left[{}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{b^-}^\alpha f(a) + {}^\beta \mathcal{J}_{a^+}^\alpha f(b) \right] \Big| = \left| \frac{\alpha^\beta (b-a)}{2} \right. \\
& \times \left\{ \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left[\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{8\alpha^\beta} \right] [f'(tb+(1-t)a) - f'(ta+(1-t)b)] dt \right. \\
& + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left[\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{2\alpha^\beta} \right] [f'(tb+(1-t)a) - f'(ta+(1-t)b)] dt \\
& \left. + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left[\left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{7}{8\alpha^\beta} \right] [f'(tb+(1-t)a) - f'(ta+(1-t)b)] dt \right\} \Big| \\
& \leq \frac{\alpha^\beta (b-a)}{2} \left\{ \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{8\alpha^\beta} \right| |f'(tb+(1-t)a) - f'(ta+(1-t)b)| dt \right. \\
& + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{2\alpha^\beta} \right| |f'(tb+(1-t)a) - f'(ta+(1-t)b)| dt \\
& \left. + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{7}{8\alpha^\beta} \right| |f'(tb+(1-t)a) - f'(ta+(1-t)b)| dt \right\} \\
& \leq \frac{\alpha^\beta (b-a)}{2} \left\{ \int_0^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{8\alpha^\beta} \right| L(2t-1)(b-a) dt \right. \\
& + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{1}{2\alpha^\beta} \right| L(2t-1)(b-a) dt \\
& \left. + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^1 \left| \left(\frac{1-(1-t)^\alpha}{\alpha} \right)^\beta - \frac{7}{8\alpha^\beta} \right| L(2t-1)(b-a) dt \right\} = \frac{\alpha^\beta (b-a)^2}{2} L \\
& \times \{ 2\Omega_4(\alpha, \beta) - \Omega_1(\alpha, \beta) + 2\Omega_5(\alpha, \beta) - \Omega_2(\alpha, \beta) \\
& + 2\Omega_6(\alpha, \beta) - \Omega_3(\alpha, \beta) \}.
\end{aligned}$$

□

Corollary 4.1. Consider $\alpha = \beta = 1$ in Theorem 4.1. Then, the following Newton-type inequality holds:

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(t) dt \right| \\
& \leq \frac{475(b-a)^2}{20736} L.
\end{aligned}$$

5 Concluding remarks

In this paper, we establish several Newton-type inequalities related to conformable fractional operators for bounded functions. Additionally, we derive Newton-type inequalities for Lipschitzian functions. Furthermore, we present some results based on special cases of the obtained inequalities.

In future work, the ideas and methods used in our results on Newton-type inequalities involving conformable fractional integrals may open new directions for researchers in this field. Moreover, these results can be generalized by considering different classes of convex functions or alternative types of fractional integral operators. Additionally, similar inequalities for convex functions using conformable fractional integrals could be explored through quantum calculus.

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Extensions of Bullen-Type Inequalities Using Second Derivative Methods

Mehmet Zeki Sarıkaya¹

¹Department of Mathematics, Düzce University, Düzce, 81620, Türkiye

Corresponding author: sarikayamz@gmail.com

ORCID IDs:

First Author: [0000-0002-6165-9242](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6165-9242)

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Abstract

In the present paper, our aim is to modify Dragomir's method in a slightly different manner and, using a new approach, to establish novel Hadamard-type inequalities for two functions g and h , where the ratio of their second derivatives is bounded by the same lower bound m and upper bound M . Subsequently, we examine special cases of these inequalities through examples and, in certain instances, recover the results previously obtained by Dragomir et al. [4, 5].

Keywords: Hermite-Hadamard inequality, Bullen inequality, convex function

1 Introduction

Integral inequalities of Hadamard and Bullen type play a fundamental role in approximation theory, numerical analysis, and convex analysis. Classical Hadamard inequalities provide bounds for the difference between the integral of a convex function and its midpoint or endpoint evaluations. Bullen-type inequalities generalize these results by comparing weighted sums of function values with the integral, often using second derivative information to establish sharp bounds. The Hermite-Hadamard inequality is stated as follows: Let $f : I \subseteq \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a convex function on the interval I , and let $a, b \in I$ with $a < b$. Then,

$$f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \leq \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(t) dt \leq \frac{f(a) + f(b)}{2}. \quad (1)$$

Inequality (1) can be further refined. For instance, the Bullen inequality provides a tighter upper bound as follows:

$$f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \leq \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(t) dt \leq \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{f(a) + f(b)}{2} + f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right]. \quad (2)$$

Moreover, many authors have investigated new upper and lower bounds for the differences appearing in the Hermite-Hadamard inequality, typically expressed as

$$\left| f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \dots \quad (3)$$

Inequalities of the form (3) are commonly referred to as *midpoint inequalities*. The exact representation of the difference can be expressed using the first derivative as

$$f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx = \frac{1}{b-a} \left[\int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} (t-a)f'(t) dt + \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^b (b-t)f'(t) dt \right], \quad (4)$$

which was presented by Kirmacı in [7]. On the other hand, inequalities of the form

$$\left| \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx - \frac{f(a)+f(b)}{2} \right| \leq \dots \quad (5)$$

are known as *trapezoid inequalities*. The corresponding exact expression can be written as

$$\frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx - \frac{f(a)+f(b)}{2} = \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b \left(t - \frac{a+b}{2}\right) f'(t) dt, \quad (6)$$

as given by Dragomir and Agarwal in [3]. Using the identities (4) and (6), many authors have derived various new midpoint and trapezoid type inequalities for different classes of convex functions; for more details, see references [3], [6], [7], [9]. These inequalities provide bounds for the integral mean of a function in terms of the function values at specific points, such as the midpoint or endpoints of an interval. Later, in [4] and [5], Dragomir and collaborators replaced the convexity assumption on f with a condition on the boundedness of its second derivative. Under this framework, they provided explicit lower and upper bounds for the differences in the midpoint (3) and (5) inequalities, establishing precise estimates for these cases.:

Theorem 1.1. [4, 5] Let $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a twice differentiable mapping such that there exists real constants m and M so that $m \leq f''(t) \leq M$ for $t \in (a, b)$. Then, the following inequalities hold:

$$m \frac{(b-a)^2}{24} \leq \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx - f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \leq M \frac{(b-a)^2}{24}. \quad (7)$$

and

$$m \frac{(b-a)^2}{12} \leq \frac{f(a)+f(b)}{2} - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \leq M \frac{(b-a)^2}{12}. \quad (8)$$

In recent years, special versions of Hadamard-type inequalities have been developed for parametric classes of functions, and the influence of convexity conditions on the validity of these inequalities has been studied in detail. In particular, functions defined as various linear combinations of polynomials and power functions frequently arise in both theoretical and applied analyses. The sign and properties of their second derivatives serve as a primary tool for investigating convexity. For further details, see [1], [2], [8]–[10]. Recently, Sarikaya [9], building upon the approach of Dragomir et al. [4, 5], utilized the Bullen inequality instead of the Hermite-Hadamard inequality to obtain more precise midpoint and trapezoid inequalities, and to derive several significant results concerning new approaches to these inequalities for two functions g and h , where the ratio of their second derivatives is bounded. In the present paper, our aim is to modify Dragomir's method in a slightly different manner and, using a new approach, to establish novel inequalities with the same lower bound m and upper bound M . Subsequently, we

examine special cases of these inequalities through examples and, in certain instances, recover the results previously obtained by Dragomir.

2 Main Theorem

Theorem 2.1. Let $g, h : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be twice continuously differentiable functions on $[a, b]$, and assume that $h''(t) > 0$ for all $t \in [a, b]$. Suppose there exist real constants m and M such that

$$m \leq \frac{g''(t)}{h''(t)} \leq M, \quad \forall t \in [a, b].$$

Then the following two-sided bounds for the average of g hold.

$$\begin{aligned} & g\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) - m \left[h\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b h(t) dt \right] \\ & \leq \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b g(t) dt \\ & \leq \frac{g(a) + g(b)}{2} - m \left[\frac{h(a) + h(b)}{2} - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b h(t) dt \right]. \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{g(a) + g(b)}{2} - M \left[\frac{h(a) + h(b)}{2} - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b h(t) dt \right] \\ & \leq \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b g(t) dt \\ & \leq g\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) - M \left[h\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b h(t) dt \right]. \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

Proof. Let $g, h : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be twice continuously differentiable functions such that $h''(t) > 0$ on $[a, b]$. Assume that there exist real constants m and M satisfying

$$m \leq \frac{g''(t)}{h''(t)} \leq M, \quad \forall t \in [a, b].$$

From $m \leq g''(t)/h''(t)$, we have

$$g''(t) - m h''(t) \geq 0, \quad t \in [a, b].$$

Integrating this inequality over the symmetric interval $[t, a+b-t]$ (where $a \leq t \leq (a+b)/2$) yields

$$\int_t^{a+b-t} [g''(u) - m h''(u)] du \geq 0,$$

that is,

$$g'(a+b-t) - g'(t) \geq m [h'(a+b-t) - h'(t)].$$

Integrating again with respect to t over $[x, (a + b)/2]$, for $x \in [a, (a + b)/2]$, gives

$$\int_x^{(a+b)/2} [g'(a + b - t) - g'(t)] dt \geq m \int_x^{(a+b)/2} [h'(a + b - t) - h'(t)] dt.$$

Evaluating these integrals yields

$$g(a + b - x) + g(x) - 2g\left(\frac{a + b}{2}\right) \geq m \left[h(a + b - x) + h(x) - 2h\left(\frac{a + b}{2}\right) \right].$$

Now integrate both sides over $x \in [a, (a + b)/2]$. By the symmetry property

$$\int_a^{(a+b)/2} [g(x) + g(a + b - x)] dx = \int_a^b g(x) dx,$$

we obtain

$$\int_a^b g(x) dx - (b - a) g\left(\frac{a + b}{2}\right) \geq m \left[\int_a^b h(x) dx - (b - a) h\left(\frac{a + b}{2}\right) \right].$$

Dividing by $(b - a)$ gives

$$g\left(\frac{a + b}{2}\right) - m \left[h\left(\frac{a + b}{2}\right) - \frac{1}{b - a} \int_a^b h(t) dt \right] \leq \frac{1}{b - a} \int_a^b g(t) dt. \tag{11}$$

Next, define $\varphi(t) = g(t) - m h(t)$. Since $\varphi''(t) = g''(t) - m h''(t) \geq 0$, the function φ is convex on $[a, b]$. By the classical Hermite-Hadamard inequality for convex functions,

$$\varphi\left(\frac{a + b}{2}\right) \leq \frac{1}{b - a} \int_a^b \varphi(t) dt \leq \frac{\varphi(a) + \varphi(b)}{2}.$$

Substituting $\varphi(t) = g(t) - m h(t)$ gives

$$\frac{1}{b - a} \int_a^b g(t) dt \leq \frac{g(a) + g(b)}{2} - m \left[\frac{h(a) + h(b)}{2} - \frac{1}{b - a} \int_a^b h(t) dt \right]. \tag{12}$$

Combining (11) and (12) yields the inequalities (9). Define the auxiliary function

$$\Psi(t) = M h(t) - g(t), \quad t \in [a, b].$$

Then

$$\Psi''(t) = M h''(t) - g''(t) \geq 0,$$

so Ψ is convex on $[a, b]$. Applying the same symmetric integration argument as above gives

$$\int_a^b \Psi(x) dx - (b - a) \Psi\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \geq 0,$$

or equivalently,

$$\frac{1}{b - a} \int_a^b \Psi(x) dx \geq \Psi\left(\frac{a + b}{2}\right).$$

Substituting $\Psi(t) = M h(t) - g(t)$ and rearranging yields

$$\frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b g(t) dt \leq g\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) - M \left[h\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b h(t) dt \right].$$

Finally, applying the Hermite-Hadamard inequality to $\Psi(t)$ gives

$$\Psi\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \leq \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b \Psi(t) dt \leq \frac{\Psi(a) + \Psi(b)}{2},$$

which, after substituting $\Psi(t) = M h(t) - g(t)$, leads to

$$\frac{g(a) + g(b)}{2} - M \left[\frac{h(a) + h(b)}{2} - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b h(t) dt \right] \leq \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b g(t) dt.$$

Together these give the inequalities (10), completing the proof. \square

Corollary 2.1. Let $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be twice continuously differentiable and assume there exist real constants m and M with $m \leq f''(x) \leq M$ for all $x \in [a, b]$. Then, we have the following Bullen inequalities

$$(2m - M) \frac{(b-a)^2}{48} \leq \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{f(a) + f(b)}{2} + f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \leq (2M - m) \frac{(b-a)^2}{48}. \quad (13)$$

Proof. Apply Theorem 2.1 with $g = f$ and with the auxiliary function

$$h_1(x) := \frac{1}{2} \left(x - \frac{a+b}{2} \right)^2,$$

which satisfies $h_1''(x) = 1 > 0$ on $[a, b]$. Then

$$\frac{f''(x)}{h_1''(x)} = f''(x),$$

so that the hypothesis of Theorem 2.1 is satisfied with the same constants m and M . By applying the Theorem 2.1, we obtain

$$f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) - m \left[h_1\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b h_1(t) dt \right] \leq \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(t) dt.$$

A simple computation gives

$$h_1\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) = 0, \quad \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b h_1(t) dt = \frac{(b-a)^2}{24}.$$

Hence, the lower bound becomes

$$f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + m \frac{(b-a)^2}{24} \leq \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(t) dt. \quad (14)$$

Similarly, the upper bound follows by applying the Hermite-Hadamard inequality to the concave

function

$$\varphi(x) := f(x) - Mh_1(x),$$

which yields

$$\frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b \varphi(t) dt \leq \varphi\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right)$$

and so

$$\frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(t) dt \leq f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + M \frac{(b-a)^2}{24}. \tag{15}$$

By combining inequalities (14) and (15), we obtain the midpoint-type inequality (7). To derive the trapezoidal estimate, we choose the auxiliary function

$$h_2(x) := \frac{1}{2}(a-x)(b-x), \quad x \in [a, b].$$

We compute its second derivative:

$$h_2''(x) = 1 > 0.$$

Then we consider

$$\frac{f''(x)}{h_2''(x)} = f''(x) \in [m, M],$$

so the hypotheses of Theorem 2.1 are satisfied with constants m and M . Now, let us compute the needed values;

$$h_2(a) = h_2(b) = 0, \quad h_2\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) = -\frac{(b-a)^2}{8}, \quad \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b h_2(x) dx = -\frac{(b-a)^2}{12}.$$

By applying the Hermite-Hadamard inequality to the convex function

$$\varphi(t) := f(t) - mh_2(t)$$

which yields

$$\frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b \varphi(t) dt \leq \frac{\varphi(a) + \varphi(b)}{2}$$

and thus

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(t) dt &\leq \frac{f(a) + f(b)}{2} + m \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b h_2(t) dt = \frac{f(a) + f(b)}{2} - m \frac{(b-a)^2}{12}, \\ \frac{f(a) + f(b)}{2} - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx &\geq m \frac{(b-a)^2}{12}. \end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

Similarly, the upper bound yields to the convex function $\varphi(t) := Mh_2(t) - f(t)$ and a simple computation

$$\frac{f(a) + f(b)}{2} - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \leq M \frac{(b-a)^2}{12}. \tag{17}$$

Therefore, by combining inequalities (16) and (17), we obtain the trapezoidal-type inequality, which corresponds to (8). Let $A := \frac{f(a) + f(b)}{2} - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(t) dt$ and $B := \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(t) dt - f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right)$. Then the target expression equals $\frac{1}{2}(A - B)$ in (13). Using the displayed bounds for

A and B such as

$$m \frac{(b-a)^2}{12} \leq A \leq M \frac{(b-a)^2}{12} \quad \text{and} \quad m \frac{(b-a)^2}{24} \leq B \leq M \frac{(b-a)^2}{24}$$

we obtain

$$\left(\frac{m}{12} - \frac{M}{24}\right) (b-a)^2 \leq A - B \leq \left(\frac{M}{12} - \frac{m}{24}\right) (b-a)^2,$$

i.e.

$$(2m - M) \frac{(b-a)^2}{24} \leq A - B \leq (2M - m) \frac{(b-a)^2}{24}.$$

Dividing by 2 yields the asserted inequality

$$(2m - M) \frac{(b-a)^2}{48} \leq \frac{1}{2}(A - B) \leq (2M - m) \frac{(b-a)^2}{48},$$

This completes the proof of Corollary 2.1. □

Corollary 2.2. Let $g : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be twice continuously differentiable on $[a, b]$. Assume there exist constants m and M such that

$$m \leq g''(t) \leq M, \quad \forall t \in [a, b].$$

Then the inequalities of Theorem 2.1 reduce (for $h(x) = \frac{x^2}{2}$) to the following Hermite-Hadamard type bounds for the mean value of g .

$$g\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + \frac{m}{24}(b-a)^2 \leq \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b g(t) dt \leq \frac{g(a) + g(b)}{2} - \frac{m}{12}(b-a)^2.$$

and

$$\frac{g(a) + g(b)}{2} - \frac{M}{12}(b-a)^2 \leq \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b g(t) dt \leq g\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + \frac{M}{24}(b-a)^2.$$

In particular,

$$g\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + \frac{m}{24}(b-a)^2 \leq \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b g(t) dt \leq g\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + \frac{M}{24}(b-a)^2.$$

Proof. Take $h(x) = \frac{x^2}{2}$. Then $h''(x) = 1$, $h(a) = a^2/2$, $h(b) = b^2/2$, and so

$$h\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) = \frac{(a+b)^2}{8}, \quad \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b h(t) dt = \frac{a^2 + ab + b^2}{6}.$$

From Theorem 2.1, we get

$$g\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) - m \left[h\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b h(t) dt \right] \leq \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b g(t) dt.$$

By computation, it follows that

$$h\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b h(t) dt = \frac{(a+b)^2}{8} - \frac{a^2 + ab + b^2}{6} = -\frac{(b-a)^2}{24}.$$

Hence

$$g\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + \frac{m}{24}(b-a)^2 \leq \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b g(t) dt.$$

From Theorem 2.1, we have

$$\frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b g(t) dt \leq \frac{g(a)+g(b)}{2} - m \left[\frac{h(a)+h(b)}{2} - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b h(t) dt \right].$$

By computation, it follows that

$$\frac{h(a)+h(b)}{2} - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b h(t) dt = \frac{a^2+b^2}{4} - \frac{a^2+ab+b^2}{6} = \frac{(a-b)^2}{12} = \frac{(b-a)^2}{12},$$

so

$$\frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b g(t) dt \leq \frac{g(a)+g(b)}{2} - \frac{m}{12}(b-a)^2.$$

The M -side is obtained by the same substitutions with M in place of m :

$$\frac{g(a)+g(b)}{2} - \frac{M}{12}(b-a)^2 \leq \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b g(t) dt \leq g\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + \frac{M}{24}(b-a)^2.$$

Combining these yields the displayed inequalities. □

Theorem 2.2. Let $a, b > 0$ with $a < b$, let $p > 2$, and let $g : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be twice continuously differentiable. Suppose there exist constants m and M such that

$$m t^{p-2} \leq g''(t) \leq M t^{p-2}, \quad \forall t \in [a, b].$$

Then the following Hadamard-type inequalities hold:

$$\begin{aligned} & g\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) - \frac{m}{p(p-1)} \left[\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right)^p - \frac{b^{p+1}-a^{p+1}}{(p+1)(b-a)} \right] \\ & \leq \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b g(t) dt \\ & \leq \frac{g(a)+g(b)}{2} - \frac{m}{2p(p-1)} \left[a^p + b^p - \frac{2(b^{p+1}-a^{p+1})}{(p+1)(b-a)} \right]. \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{g(a)+g(b)}{2} - \frac{M}{2p(p-1)} \left[a^p + b^p - \frac{2(b^{p+1}-a^{p+1})}{(p+1)(b-a)} \right] \\ & \leq \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b g(t) dt \\ & \leq g\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) - \frac{M}{p(p-1)} \left[\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right)^p - \frac{b^{p+1}-a^{p+1}}{(p+1)(b-a)} \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Set $h(t) := t^p/(p(p-1))$, so that $h''(t) = t^{p-2} > 0$. Then the assumption $m t^{p-2} \leq g''(t) \leq M t^{p-2}$ is equivalent to

$$g''(t) - m t^{p-2} \geq 0, \quad M t^{p-2} - g''(t) \geq 0.$$

Applying the symmetric integration method from Theorem 2.1, for the m -block we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & g\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) - m \left[h\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b h(t) dt \right] \\ & \leq \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b g(t) dt \\ & \leq \frac{g(a)+g(b)}{2} - m \left[\frac{h(a)+h(b)}{2} - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b h(t) dt \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, for the M , applying the same integration procedure to $Mt^{p-2} - g$ gives

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{g(a)+g(b)}{2} - M \left[\frac{h(a)+h(b)}{2} - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b h(t) dt \right] \\ & \leq \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b g(t) dt \\ & \leq g\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) - M \left[h\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b h(t) dt \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Finally, substituting

$$h(a) = \frac{a^p}{p(p-1)}, \quad h(b) = \frac{b^p}{p(p-1)}, \quad h\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) = \frac{(a+b)^p}{2^p p(p-1)}, \quad \int_a^b h(t) dt = \frac{b^{p+1} - a^{p+1}}{(p+1)p(p-1)}$$

yields the explicit inequalities in the statement. \square

Theorem 2.3. Let $a, b > 0$ with $a < b$, let $p > 2$, and let $g : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be twice continuously differentiable. Suppose there exist constants m and M such that

$$m \left(\frac{a+b}{2} - t \right)^{p-2} \leq g''(t) \leq M \left(\frac{a+b}{2} - t \right)^{p-2}, \quad t \in [a, b].$$

Then the following Hadamard-type inequalities hold:

$$\begin{aligned} g\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + m \frac{(b-a)^p}{2^p (p+1)p(p-1)} & \leq \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b g(t) dt \\ & \leq \frac{g(a)+g(b)}{2} - m \frac{(b-a)^p}{2^p p(p-1)} + m \frac{(b-a)^p}{2^p (p+1)p(p-1)}. \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{g(a)+g(b)}{2} - M \frac{(b-a)^p}{2^p p(p-1)} + M \frac{(b-a)^p}{2^p (p+1)p(p-1)} & \leq \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b g(t) dt \\ & \leq g\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + M \frac{(b-a)^p}{2^p (p+1)p(p-1)}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let $a, b > 0$ with $a < b$, let $p > 2$, and define

$$h(t) := \frac{\left(\frac{a+b}{2} - t\right)^p}{p(p-1)}, \quad t \in [a, b].$$

Then h is twice continuously differentiable with

$$h''(t) = \left(\frac{a+b}{2} - t\right)^{p-2} > 0, \quad t \in [a, b].$$

First, compute the integral of $h(t)$ explicitly. Use the change of variable $u = \frac{a+b}{2} - t$

$$\int_a^b h(t) dt = \frac{1}{p(p-1)} \int_a^b \left(\frac{a+b}{2} - t\right)^p dt = \frac{1}{p(p-1)} \int_{-(b-a)/2}^{(b-a)/2} u^p du.$$

By symmetry of the integrand (since $p > 2$),

$$\int_{-(b-a)/2}^{(b-a)/2} u^p du = 2 \int_0^{(b-a)/2} u^p du = 2 \cdot \frac{((b-a)/2 - a)^{p+1}}{p+1}.$$

Finally,

$$\int_a^b h(t) dt = \frac{1}{p(p-1)} \cdot 2 \cdot \frac{((b-a)/2)^{p+1}}{p+1} = \frac{(b-a)^{p+1}}{2^p(p+1)p(p-1)}.$$

Thus we have

$$h(t) := \frac{\left(\frac{a+b}{2} - t\right)^p}{p(p-1)}, \quad h\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) = 0, \quad h(a) = h(b) = \frac{(b-a)^p}{2^p p(p-1)}, \quad \int_a^b h(t) dt = \frac{(b-a)^{p+1}}{2^p(p+1)p(p-1)}.$$

Since $g''(t) - m h''(t) \geq 0$, integrating over $[t, a+b-t]$ for $t \in [a, (a+b)/2]$ gives

$$g'(a+b-t) - g'(t) \geq m [h'(a+b-t) - h'(t)].$$

Integrate again with respect to t over $[x, (a+b)/2]$:

$$g(a+b-x) + g(x) - 2g\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \geq m \left[h(a+b-x) + h(x) - 2h\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) \right].$$

Finally, integrate x over $[a, \frac{a+b}{2}]$ and use symmetry:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b g(t) dt &\geq g\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + \frac{m}{b-a} \int_a^b h(t) dt \\ &= g\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + \frac{m}{b-a} \frac{(b-a)^{p+1}}{2^p(p+1)p(p-1)} \end{aligned}$$

For the right-hand m -bound, define $\varphi(t) = g(t) - m h(t)$, which is convex. By the Hermite-Hadamard inequality:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b g(t) dt &\leq \frac{g(a) + g(b)}{2} - m \left[\frac{h(a) + h(b)}{2} - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b h(t) dt \right] \\ &= \frac{g(a) + g(b)}{2} - m \left[\frac{(b-a)^p}{2^p p(p-1)} - \frac{1}{b-a} \frac{(b-a)^{p+1}}{2^p(p+1)p(p-1)} \right]. \end{aligned}$$

Define $\Psi(t) = M h(t) - g(t)$, which is convex. Symmetric integration and the Hermite-Hadamard

inequality yield

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{g(a) + g(b)}{2} - M \left[\frac{(b-a)^p}{2^p p(p-1)} - \frac{1}{b-a} \frac{(b-a)^{p+1}}{2^p(p+1)p(p-1)} \right] \\ & \leq \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b g(t) dt \\ & \leq g\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + \frac{M}{b-a} \frac{(b-a)^{p+1}}{2^p(p+1)p(p-1)}. \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof. □

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HOG and Deep Learning-Based Methods for Vendor and Level Classification from Small-Scale Smartphone Images

Mirsat Yesiltepe¹, Harun Elkiran², Jawad Rasheed², Hacer Sinem Ayaş³, Yasin Ucakan⁴

¹*Department of Intelligent Transportation Systems, Istanbul University, Istanbul, Turkey*

²*Department of Computer Engineering, Istanbul Sabahattin Zaim University, Istanbul, Turkey*

³*Department of Management Information Systems, Istanbul Rumeli University, Istanbul, Turkey*

⁴*Department of Computer Engineering, Istanbul Rumeli University, Istanbul, Turkey*

Corresponding author: yesiltepemirsat@istanbul.edu.tr

ORCID IDs:

First Author: [0000-0003-4433-5606](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4433-5606)

Second Author: [0000-0002-5834-6210](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5834-6210)

Third Author: [0000-0003-3761-1641](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3761-1641)

Fourth Author: [0009-0006-8974-2343](https://orcid.org/0009-0006-8974-2343)

Fifth Author: [0000-0001-5743-1862](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5743-1862)

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Abstract

Here we propose an image-based classification approach that uses HOG for feature representation and CNN-based models for smart phone manufacturers and hardware levels classification from small-scale images. The proposed framework attempts to model device-specific fine-grained visual variations caused by device-specific hardware configurations and manufacturer-specific design attributes. HOG was used for the detection of strong, low-level gradient-based features that were then used as inputs to deep learning models for classification. Our research suggests that the detected HOG features greatly improve the model's ability for visually similar class discrimination, especially when combined with the hierarchical learning capability of CNNs. The model achieved an exceptionally high rate of classification of 99.99%, which demonstrates it effective in distinguishing differences between different device classes. Overlaps between the distributions of features of certain classes, however, suggest a need for additional tuning to improve inter-class discrimination and classification robustness. This suggests the use of traditional feature extraction techniques combined with deep-learning-facilitated classifiers in high-accuracy demanding applications and highly sensitive to minimal visual differences. Future research directions may involve improving generalization through cutting-edge data augmentation, multi-scale learning representations, and adaptive attentions. Dual model has the potential to be applied in mobile device authentication, hardware verification, and digital forensics, particularly in cases where high-resolution images are unavailable or of low quality. The results demonstrate that the combination of hand-crafted features with deep models offers a feasible and effective solution to achieving stable performance in complex classification tasks with implicit visual distinctions.

Keywords: Classification, Features, HOG, Smartphone, Vendor.

1. Introduction and Motivation

Nowadays, mobile devices are increasingly integrated into daily life. This integration is attributed to their capacity to enable seamless communication, continuous access to information, and efficient execution of professional tasks. Moreover, mobile technologies have become transformative across various domains such as education, healthcare, and commerce by offering innovative, user-centric solutions that enhance quality of life [1]. These devices vary substantially in terms of manufacturer, hardware configurations, and performance characteristics, all of which directly influence user experience, application responsiveness, energy efficiency, and network behavior. High-end devices tend to provide consistent and rapid performance, while low-end models often exhibit latency and instability due to resource limitations [2].

One possible solution is to use machine learning, which provides powerful tools to address these disparities by extracting patterns from device-level data and enabling automated classification. Classification, a fundamental task in machine learning, involves assigning data instances to predefined categories based on learned features. In the context of mobile systems, classification facilitates grouping devices according to hardware and performance profiles, supporting enhancements in application optimization, adaptive resource management, and network performance prediction. Recently, distributed learning paradigms such as federated learning have gained attention for their ability to train models across heterogeneous devices while preserving data privacy [3], [4].

In image-based analysis, feature extraction plays a central role in identifying structural patterns. Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG) is a well-established method that captures local edge and gradient information by computing histograms of orientation within image cells. HOG is robust to illumination and color variations and has shown high effectiveness in applications such as object and human detection. The extracted features can be efficiently utilized in conjunction with learning-based classifiers for robust recognition tasks.

Deep learning, being a branch of ML, focuses on machine learning that employs multi-layered architectures of artificial neural networks to automatically extract meaningful features from complex data. Thanks to these deep architectures, it possesses the capacity to learn high-level representations, enabling superior performance on large-scale datasets such as images, audio, and text. Accuracy, as a fundamental evaluation metric in classification tasks, quantifies the proportion of correctly predicted instances among the total number of samples. It provides a straightforward measure of a model's effectiveness by indicating how often the model's predictions align with the true labels, thus serving as a primary indicator of performance in many deep learning applications.

2. Literature Review

The classification of mobile devices based on manufacturer (vendor) and hardware capabilities—typically segmented into high-end, mid-range, and low-end tiers—has become increasingly significant in various areas of mobile computing research. Such classification enables more precise modeling of application performance, user behavior, network optimization, and system-level energy efficiency. Recent studies reflect growing interest in leveraging device heterogeneity as a critical design parameter in both traditional client-server systems and emerging decentralized learning paradigms, such as Federated Learning (FL).

Zhou et al. [5] conducted an empirical analysis on Android smartphones, demonstrating that high-end devices generally deliver more consistent and reliable performance, particularly under computationally intensive workloads. Their findings emphasized that ignoring hardware variation can lead to misleading evaluations of application efficiency and responsiveness. Similarly, user behavior analysis based on hardware segmentation reveals significant differences across device classes. For example, users with low-end mobile devices may exhibit lower app launch frequencies, shorter session durations, or reduced usage of advanced features compared to users on high-end devices. Such behavioral insights suggest that segmentation by device capability is not only useful for performance tuning, but also for developing device-aware user behavior models and tailoring adaptive strategies to different hardware classes (e.g., Khan [6] in a personalized adaptive streaming context).

In the context of adaptive media streaming, device classification enables multi-tier algorithms that adapt bitrate selection and buffering strategies according to both device processing power and network conditions. For instance, Aguilar-Armijo et al. [7] propose a machine-learning assisted edge-based adaptation scheme (ECAS-ML) that predicts optimal ABR (Adaptive Bitrate Streaming) parameters based on radiometrics and device context, thereby improving quality of experience across heterogeneous devices. This approach balanced media quality and bandwidth consumption across heterogeneous devices. Concurrently, energy profiling studies such as Pathak et al. [8] demonstrated how hardware-tier-based classification aids in identifying energy bottlenecks, enabling more accurate power consumption estimates and supporting energy-efficient application design.

Within federated learning, device classification is critical due to the distributed and heterogeneous nature of participating devices. Lim et al. [9] revealed that computational and communication capabilities significantly affect FL performance, advocating system-level policies that consider hardware diversity during participant selection. Building on this, Lu et al. [10] introduced resource-aware selection algorithms prioritizing devices based on processing power and memory, while Wang et al. [11] proposed latency-based device grouping to reduce synchronization overhead. Zhao et al. [12] emphasized hardware-aware communication protocols and computational workflows to enhance FL efficiency.

A recent notable contribution is the HeteroSwitch framework by Chen et al. [13], which addressed system-induced data and hardware heterogeneity impacts on FL. Using nine mobile devices categorized by vendor and hardware tier, the study introduced adaptive generalization techniques to minimize inter-device performance variance, significantly improving model accuracy and training stability in highly diverse environments. This underscores the importance of device-tier-aware design for managing heterogeneity and promoting fairness in FL systems.

In summary, classifying mobile devices by manufacturer and hardware capability forms a foundational step toward designing equitable, efficient, and adaptive mobile systems. From optimizing application performance and user modeling to enhancing energy efficiency and federated learning outcomes, device-tier classification provides a systematic framework to address the intrinsic heterogeneity of real-world mobile ecosystems. As these ecosystems continue to diversify, the significance of such classification will intensify, especially within data-driven and decentralized computing paradigms.

3. Experimental Environment

Here, we aim to investigate a classification problem using the mobile device image dataset published by Kaggle user 'Kim Gyu Dong' [14]. The dataset has been preprocessed to include vendor (manufacturer) and level (damage severity) information, resulting in a total of nine distinct classes. Folder names were created by combining brand initials and performance levels. For instance, "S" represents Samsung, "L" stands for LG, and "G" corresponds to Google. Performance levels are indicated by "H" for high (High), "M" for medium (Medium), and "L" for low (Low). This system facilitates efficient categorization, allowing easier access and organization.

The dataset consists of nine distinct classification labels, each formed by combining the manufacturer and performance level. Samsung devices are categorized as Samsung High (sh), Samsung Medium (sm), and Samsung Low (sl) based on their performance. Similarly, LG devices follow the same structure, labeled as LG High (lh), LG Medium (lm), and LG Low (ll). Google devices are also classified in this manner, represented by Google High (gh), Google Medium (gm), and Google Low (gl). These categories provide a structured approach to organizing mobile devices based on their brand and performance characteristics, ensuring a well-balanced dataset for classification tasks.

Datasets were structured according to the combined level-vendor framework, ensuring a balanced and well-organized folder structure for all nine classes. All images in the dataset were resized to dimensions of 32×32 pixels, primarily to reduce computational overhead and expedite prototyping. This approach guarantees a standardized and robust image set for each class.

The dataset was partitioned into training and testing subsets with an 80-20 split, ensuring that 80% of the samples were used for model training while the remaining 20% were reserved for evaluation.

Figure 1: An example original image (left) and the image in test image size (right)

During feature extraction, images were first converted to grayscale to reduce computational complexity and eliminate color-related variability. Subsequently, Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG) features were computed due to their proven effectiveness in capturing edge, texture, and structural information. This capability is especially valuable in low-resolution images, where HOG provides a robust representation that enhances differentiation between closely related classes. Additionally, the feature computation process was optimized for parallel execution by leveraging multi-core processing architectures, thereby improving efficiency and reducing processing time.

Figure 2: An example original image and the image resulting from the HOG process

During the classification phase, a fundamental Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) architecture was employed to effectively categorize mobile device images. The model architecture consists of two convolutional layers (Conv2D), each followed by max pooling layers (MaxPooling2D) to progressively reduce spatial dimensions and extract hierarchical feature representations. Subsequent layers include flattening, fully connected dense layers, and dropout regularization to enhance feature learning while mitigating overfitting. The final output layer applies a softmax activation function, enabling multi-class classification across nine distinct categories. To ensure optimal training performance, early stopping and model checkpointing techniques were implemented, which prevented overfitting and preserved the best-performing model parameters.

To evaluate performance was comprehensively evaluated through confusion matrices and training-validation accuracy curves, providing quantitative measures of classification effectiveness. Furthermore, HOG visualizations complemented by dimensionality reduction methods, such as

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and t-Distributed Stochastic Neighbor Embedding (t-SNE), offered qualitative insights into feature space structure and class separability. In particular, t-SNE projections revealed complex underlying patterns and highlighted potential overlaps between closely related classes.

Overall, our CNN-based classification model, integrated with HOG-driven feature extraction, achieved high accuracy rates across the vendor and hardware level categories. Throughout training, both accuracy and loss metrics showed consistent improvement, indicating robust learning and strong generalization capabilities. This study underscores the value of combining traditional feature extraction techniques like HOG with deep learning architectures, demonstrating their synergistic effectiveness in low-resolution image classification tasks.

4. Experimental Environment Result

In this study, feature extraction and deep learning-based classification were performed on a dataset comprising 140,400 images. Following the initial image loading and feature computation stages, the dataset was partitioned into training and validation subsets to enable effective model development and performance monitoring. The classification model was trained iteratively, with weight updates recorded based on validation accuracy at the conclusion of each epoch. Data storage was managed using an older-format data structure, which generated compatibility warnings but did not affect overall process integrity.

Training was conducted over nine iterations, during which accuracy improvements were closely tracked. Notably, by the fourth iteration, the maximum validation accuracy attained was 99.993%, after which no significant gains were observed. Consequently, an optimization mechanism—early stopping—was employed to terminate the training process, thereby preventing redundant computation and potential overfitting. Upon completion, the optimal weight parameters were reloaded for final evaluation. Testing on the reserved dataset yielded a classification accuracy of 99.99%, reflecting the model's high predictive performance.

The following section discusses the generated graphical outputs and explicates their analytical significance. The visualizations serve as critical tools for assessing learning trends, relationships between metrics, and overall model behavior. Subsequent interpretation provides an in-depth evaluation of observed patterns, elucidating their implications within the broader context of the study.

Figure 3: Model accuracy per epoch

Figure 4: Model loss per epoch

Figure 3, 4 depicts the evolution of accuracy and loss metrics throughout the training process. The consistent decrease in both training and validation loss values indicates effective learning and model convergence. Concurrently, the training and validation accuracy curves exhibit rapid improvement, ultimately reaching 99.99% accuracy by the final epoch. The incorporation of an early stopping mechanism ensured that training ceased at the point of optimal performance, effectively preventing unnecessary iterations and reducing the risk of overfitting.

Figure 5: Average Comparison of HOG Attributes

Figure 5 presents the mean values of the first 100 dimensions of the extracted features across various mobile device classes. Notably, high-performance devices exhibit more consistent and elevated feature distributions, reflecting their more uniform hardware characteristics. In contrast, lower-performance devices display broader variability within these feature dimensions, indicating greater heterogeneity in their hardware profiles. These pronounced distinctions in feature distributions contribute significantly to the model’s classification accuracy, enhancing its ability to effectively discriminate between different device categories. Such feature-level separability underpins the robustness of the classification framework and validates the efficacy of the chosen feature extraction methodology.

Figure 6: Distribution of HOG Features with PCA

Figure 6 presents a two-dimensional visualization of the extracted features using Principal Component Analysis (PCA), enabling a more compact and interpretable representation of the class distributions. This dimensionality reduction technique enhances the clarity of intra-class variability and inter-class relationships, revealing clear separations among the majority of categories. However, the visualization also highlights regions of proximity and overlap between certain classes, which may lead to classification ambiguities. These observed overlaps emphasize the necessity for further refinement in feature selection methods or the incorporation of advanced optimization strategies to enhance the model's discriminative power and overall robustness.

Figure 7: Confusion matrix

Figure 7 presents the confusion matrix illustrating the classification model's performance on the test dataset. This matrix compares the predicted class labels against the true labels, providing a comprehensive overview of both correct classifications and misclassifications. The diagonal elements represent instances where the model accurately identified the device class, while the off-diagonal elements highlight the specific errors made. Such visualization facilitates detailed analysis of class-wise performance, enabling the identification of categories with higher confusion rates and guiding future improvements in model accuracy.

The high rate of correct classifications is evident from the prominently elevated values along the diagonal of the confusion matrix, indicating that the majority of samples within each class were

accurately predicted by the model. This strong diagonal dominance underscores the model's robust classification capability and its effectiveness in distinguishing among the different device categories with minimal misclassification.

5. Conclusions

We examined the integration of traditional feature extraction methods with deep learning-based classification techniques to identify manufacturers and hardware levels from small-scale smartphone images. The feature extraction phase revealed that distinctive characteristics among device classes significantly contribute to improving classification accuracy. Leveraging these handcrafted features, the convolutional neural network-based classification model achieved an exceptionally high accuracy of 99.99%, demonstrating its effectiveness and robustness in fine-grained mobile device categorization. These results underscore the potential of combining classical image processing techniques with deep learning architectures to enhance performance in complex classification tasks involving subtle inter-class differences. Future work may focus on addressing residual ambiguities between closely related classes through advanced data augmentation and adaptive feature learning strategies to further improve generalization.

However, overlapping feature distributions among certain classes lead to misclassifications concentrated within specific categories. These observations highlight that integrating traditional image processing methods with deep learning techniques effectively enhances classification accuracy. To further improve the model's robustness and generalization capabilities, future research should prioritize the implementation of advanced data augmentation strategies and sophisticated feature engineering approaches.

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A Septic Hermite Collocation Method for Regularized Long Wave Equation

Murat ARI¹

¹Department of Mathematics, Karamanoglu Mehmetbey University, Karaman, Türkiye

Corresponding author: muratari@kmu.edu.tr

ORCID IDs:

First Author: [0000-0002-4039-5970](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4039-5970)

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Abstract

In this study, a septic Hermite spline collocation method based on the classical Crank–Nicolson approximation is developed for the numerical solution of the regularized long-wave (RLW) equation. To the best of our knowledge, this represents the first application of this approach to the RLW equation. The accuracy and efficiency of the proposed scheme are thoroughly evaluated using the L_2 and L_∞ error norms. Numerical experiments confirm that the method is simple to implement and provides highly accurate results for the RLW equation.

Keywords: Septic Hermite spline, Collocation method, RLW equation

1 Introduction

In this work, we examine the following form of the regularized long wave (RLW) equation:

$$U_t + U_x + \varepsilon U U_x - \mu U_{xxt} = 0 \quad (1)$$

together with boundary conditions

$$U(a, t) = \alpha, \quad U(b, t) = \beta, \quad a \leq x \leq b, \quad t > 0$$

and the initial condition

$$U(x, 0) = f(x).$$

The regularized long wave (RLW) equation was originally introduced by Peregrine to represent nonlinear dispersive wave motion. It has been demonstrated that the RLW equation is capable of describing a wide range of physical processes, including nonlinear transverse waves in shallow water, ion–acoustic waves in plasma, magnetohydrodynamic waves in plasma, longitudinal dispersive waves in elastic rods, and pressure oscillations in liquid–gas bubble systems. Furthermore, the RLW equation has frequently served as a benchmark problem for numerical schemes, as it admits analytical solutions for certain sets of boundary and initial conditions [4, 5, 7, 8, 12, 13, 23].

The objective of the present work is to use Hermite septic spline collocation method to solve the regularized long-wave equation (RLW) numerically. This method used extensively for solving

partial differential equations see [1, 2, 3, 9, 10, 11, 15, 16, 18, 19, 20, 22] and references therein. As far as we know, this method has not been applied to RLW equation.

This paper is organized as follows. First, we present the septic Hermite spline collocation method. Then, we demonstrate the application of the method to the equation. After that, numerical results and graphics are presented for some exercises. Finally, we present our conclusions in the last section.

2 The Septic Hermite Spline Collocation Method

In the septic Hermite collocation method, the computational domain $[a, b]$ is partitioned as $\pi : a = x_1 < x_2 < \dots < x_{N+1} = b$, yielding a uniform mesh with step size $h = x_{j+1} - x_j$, defined by the knots x_j for $j = 1, 2, \dots, N + 1$. The approximate solution $u(x, t)$ is then represented in terms of septic Hermite basis functions as

$$u(x, t) \approx u_N(x, t) = \sum_{j=1}^{N+4} a_{j+6k-6}(t) H_{ji}, \quad (2)$$

where $a_j(t)$ are time dependent coefficients yet to be determined, k denotes the number of elements, and $i = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6$ corresponds to the local basis functions. Within each subinterval $[x_j, x_{j+1}]$, Legendre and Chebyshev collocation points of order 6, denoted respectively by ξ_i^L and ξ_i^C , are employed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \xi_1^L &= 0.033765242898424, & \xi_2^L &= 0.169395306766868, & \xi_3^L &= 0.380690406958402, \\ \xi_4^L &= 0.619309593041598, & \xi_5^L &= 0.830604693233132, & \xi_6^L &= 0.966234757101576, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \xi_1^C &= 0.017037086855466, & \xi_2^C &= 0.146446609406726, & \xi_3^C &= 0.37059047744874, \\ \xi_4^C &= 0.62940952255126, & \xi_5^C &= 0.853553390593274, & \xi_6^C &= 0.982962913144534. \end{aligned}$$

This formulation allows for high-order accuracy in the numerical approximation, as the septic Hermite basis ensures smoothness up to higher derivatives, while the chosen collocation nodes enhance the spectral-like precision within each finite element.

The septic Hermite basis functions $H_j(x)$, which satisfy the required interpolation and smoothness properties, are formulated as follows [1, 2, 3, 20]:

$$\begin{aligned} H_{6j+1}(x) &= 35 \frac{(x-x_{j-1})^4}{h^4} - 84 \frac{(x-x_{j-1})^5}{h^5} + 70 \frac{(x-x_{j-1})^6}{h^6} - 20 \frac{(x-x_{j-1})^7}{h^7}, & x_{j-1} \leq x \leq x_j, \\ H_{6j-5}(x) &= 35 \frac{(x_{j+1}-x)^4}{h^4} - 84 \frac{(x_{j+1}-x)^5}{h^5} + 70 \frac{(x_{j+1}-x)^6}{h^6} - 20 \frac{(x_{j+1}-x)^7}{h^7}, & x_j \leq x \leq x_{j+1}, \\ H_{6j-4}(x) &= -15 \frac{(x-x_{j-1})^4}{h^3} + 39 \frac{(x-x_{j-1})^5}{h^4} - 34 \frac{(x-x_{j-1})^6}{h^5} + 10 \frac{(x-x_{j-1})^7}{h^6}, & x_{j-1} \leq x \leq x_j, \\ H_{6j+2}(x) &= -15 \frac{(x_{j+1}-x)^4}{h^3} + 39 \frac{(x_{j+1}-x)^5}{h^4} - 34 \frac{(x_{j+1}-x)^6}{h^5} + 10 \frac{(x_{j+1}-x)^7}{h^6}, & x_j \leq x \leq x_{j+1}, \\ H_{6j-3}(x) &= \frac{5}{2} \frac{(x-x_{j-1})^4}{h^2} - 7 \frac{(x-x_{j-1})^5}{h^3} + \frac{13}{2} \frac{(x-x_{j-1})^6}{h^4} - 2 \frac{(x-x_{j-1})^7}{h^5}, & x_{j-1} \leq x \leq x_j, \\ H_{6j}(x) &= \frac{5}{2} \frac{(x_{j+1}-x)^4}{h^2} - 7 \frac{(x_{j+1}-x)^5}{h^3} + \frac{13}{2} \frac{(x_{j+1}-x)^6}{h^4} - 2 \frac{(x_{j+1}-x)^7}{h^5}, & x_j \leq x \leq x_{j+1}, \\ H_{6j-2}(x) &= -\frac{1}{6} \frac{(x-x_{j-1})^4}{h} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{(x-x_{j-1})^5}{h^2} - \frac{1}{2} \frac{(x-x_{j-1})^6}{h^3} + \frac{1}{6} \frac{(x-x_{j-1})^7}{h^4}, & x_{j-1} \leq x \leq x_j, \\ H_{6j-1}(x) &= -\frac{1}{6} \frac{(x_{j+1}-x)^4}{h} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{(x_{j+1}-x)^5}{h^2} - \frac{1}{2} \frac{(x_{j+1}-x)^6}{h^3} + \frac{1}{6} \frac{(x_{j+1}-x)^7}{h^4}, & x_j \leq x \leq x_{j+1}. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

To facilitate numerical computation, the system is transformed into a local coordinate framework. For each element, a local variable ξ is introduced as

$$\xi = \frac{x - x_k}{h}, \quad (4)$$

which maps the global interval $[x_k, x_{k+1}]$ to a fixed reference domain $[0, 1]$. This normalization simplifies the evaluation of basis functions and their derivatives across all elements. Consequently, the transformation $x = h\xi + x_k$ yields the following normalized forms of the basis functions:

$$\begin{aligned} H_1(\xi) &= 1 - 35\xi^4 + 84\xi^5 - 70\xi^6 + 20\xi^7, & H_2(\xi) &= h(\xi - 20\xi^4 + 45\xi^5 - 36\xi^6 + 10\xi^7), \\ H_3(\xi) &= h^2(0.5\xi^2 - 5\xi^4 + 10\xi^5 - \frac{15}{2}\xi^6 + 2\xi^7), & H_4(\xi) &= h^3(\frac{1}{6}\xi^3 - \frac{2}{3}\xi^4 + \xi^5 - \frac{2}{3}\xi^6 + \frac{1}{6}\xi^7), \\ H_5(\xi) &= h^3(-\frac{1}{6}\xi^4 + \frac{1}{2}\xi^5 - \frac{1}{2}\xi^6 + \frac{1}{6}\xi^7), & H_6(\xi) &= h^2(\frac{5}{2}\xi^4 - 7\xi^5 + \frac{13}{2}\xi^6 - 2\xi^7), \\ H_7(\xi) &= 35\xi^4 - 84\xi^5 + 70\xi^6 - 20\xi^7, & H_8(\xi) &= h(-15\xi^4 + 39\xi^5 - 34\xi^6 + 10\xi^7). \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

The first- and second-order derivatives of these basis functions, denoted by $A_i(\xi)$ and $B_i(\xi)$ respectively, are given by

$$\begin{aligned} A_1(\xi) &= -140\xi^3 + 420\xi^4 - 420\xi^5 + 140\xi^6, & A_2(\xi) &= h(1 - 80\xi^3 + 225\xi^4 - 216\xi^5 + 70\xi^6), \\ A_3(\xi) &= h^2(\xi - 20\xi^3 + 50\xi^4 - 45\xi^5 + 14\xi^6), & A_4(\xi) &= h^3(\frac{1}{2}\xi^2 - \frac{8}{3}\xi^3 + 5\xi^4 - 4\xi^5 + \frac{7}{6}\xi^6), \\ A_5(\xi) &= h^3(-\frac{2}{3}\xi^3 + \frac{5}{2}\xi^4 - 3\xi^5 + \frac{7}{6}\xi^6), & A_6(\xi) &= h^2(10\xi^3 - 35\xi^4 + 39\xi^5 - 14\xi^6), \\ A_7(\xi) &= 140\xi^3 - 420\xi^4 + 420\xi^5 - 140\xi^6, & A_8(\xi) &= h(-60\xi^3 + 195\xi^4 - 204\xi^5 + 70\xi^6), \\ B_1(\xi) &= -420\xi^2 + 1680\xi^3 - 2100\xi^4 + 840\xi^5, & B_2(\xi) &= h(-240\xi^2 + 900\xi^3 - 1080\xi^4 + 420\xi^5), \\ B_3(\xi) &= h^2(1 - 60\xi^2 + 200\xi^3 - 225\xi^4 + 84\xi^5), & B_4(\xi) &= h^3(\xi - 8\xi^2 + 20\xi^3 - 20\xi^4 + 7\xi^5), \\ B_5(\xi) &= h^3(-2\xi^2 + 10\xi^3 - 15\xi^4 + 7\xi^5), & B_6(\xi) &= h^2(30\xi^2 - 140\xi^3 + 195\xi^4 - 84\xi^5), \\ B_7(\xi) &= 420\xi^2 - 1680\xi^3 + 2100\xi^4 - 840\xi^5, & B_8(\xi) &= h(-180\xi^2 + 780\xi^3 - 1020\xi^4 + 420\xi^5). \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Finally, the trial functions and their first and second derivatives at the collocation points in terms of the local variable ξ are expressed as

$$\left. \begin{aligned} U_i &= a_{6k-5}H_1(\xi_i) + a_{6k-4}H_2(\xi_i) + a_{6k-3}H_3(\xi_i) + a_{6k-2}H_4(\xi_i) + \\ &\quad a_{6k-1}H_5(\xi_i) + a_{6k}H_6(\xi_i) + a_{6k+1}H_7(\xi_i) + a_{6k+2}H_8(\xi_i), \\ hU'_i &= a_{6k-5}A_1(\xi_i) + a_{6k-4}A_2(\xi_i) + a_{6k-3}A_3(\xi_i) + a_{6k-2}A_4(\xi_i) + \\ &\quad a_{6k-1}A_5(\xi_i) + a_{6k}A_6(\xi_i) + a_{6k+1}A_7(\xi_i) + a_{6k+2}A_8(\xi_i), \\ h^2U''_i &= a_{6k-5}B_1(\xi_i) + a_{6k-4}B_2(\xi_i) + a_{6k-3}B_3(\xi_i) + a_{6k-2}B_4(\xi_i) + \\ &\quad a_{6k-1}B_5(\xi_i) + a_{6k}B_6(\xi_i) + a_{6k+1}B_7(\xi_i) + a_{6k+2}B_8(\xi_i), \end{aligned} \right\} \quad i = 1(1)6. \quad (7)$$

This representation not only provides a smooth and continuous approximation but also allows for straightforward computation of higher-order derivatives, which is particularly advantageous in the numerical treatment of high-order partial differential equations.

3 IMPLEMENTATION OF THE METHOD

Using the notation $U^n = (x, t^n)$, where $t^n = t^{n-1} + \Delta t$, and Δt is the time step, the RLW equation is discretized using Crank-Nicolson temporal scheme

$$\frac{U^{n+1} - U^n}{\Delta t} + \frac{U_x^{n+1} + U_x^n}{2} + \varepsilon \frac{(UU_x)^{n+1} + (UU_x)^n}{2} - \mu \frac{U_{xx}^{n+1} - U_{xx}^n}{\Delta t} = 0 \quad (8)$$

Equation (8) can be rewritten as

$$U^{n+1} - U^n + \frac{\Delta t}{2} (U_x^{n+1} + U_x^n) + \varepsilon \frac{\Delta t}{2} ((UU_x)^{n+1} + (UU_x)^n) - \mu (U_{xx}^{n+1} - U_{xx}^n) = 0 \quad (9)$$

The nonlinear term $(UU_x)^{n+1}$ in Equation (9) may be linearized by using the following term [18],

$$(UU_x)^{n+1} = U^{n+1}U_x^n + U^nU_x^{n+1} - U^nU_x^n$$

So Equation (9) is discretized in time as

$$U^{n+1} - \mu U_{xx}^{n+1} + \frac{\Delta t}{2} U_x^{n+1} + \varepsilon \frac{\Delta t}{2} (U_x^n U^{n+1} + U^n U_x^{n+1}) = U^n - \mu U_{xx}^n - \frac{\Delta t}{2} U_x^n \quad (10)$$

Now substituting u_m values and their derivatives in (7) to the (10) and rearranging the equation yields the following matrix system of the equations:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left((1 + \frac{\varepsilon \Delta t}{2} U_x^n) H_{1i} + (\frac{\Delta t}{2} + \frac{\varepsilon \Delta t}{2} U^n) A_{1i} - \mu B_{1i} \right) a_{6k-5}^{n+1} + \left((1 + \frac{\varepsilon \Delta t}{2} U_x^n) H_{2i} + (\frac{\Delta t}{2} + \frac{\varepsilon \Delta t}{2} U^n) A_{2i} \right. \\ & \left. - \mu B_{2i} \right) a_{6k-4}^{n+1} + \left((1 + \frac{\varepsilon \Delta t}{2} U_x^n) H_{3i} + (\frac{\Delta t}{2} + \frac{\varepsilon \Delta t}{2} U^n) A_{3i} - \mu B_{3i} \right) a_{6k-3}^{n+1} + \left((1 + \frac{\varepsilon \Delta t}{2} U_x^n) H_{4i} \right. \\ & \left. + (\frac{\Delta t}{2} + \frac{\varepsilon \Delta t}{2} U^n) A_{4i} - \mu B_{4i} \right) a_{6k-2}^{n+1} + \left((1 + \frac{\varepsilon \Delta t}{2} U_x^n) H_{5i} + (\frac{\Delta t}{2} + \frac{\varepsilon \Delta t}{2} U^n) A_{5i} - \mu B_{5i} \right) a_{6k-1}^{n+1} \\ & + \left((1 + \frac{\varepsilon \Delta t}{2} U_x^n) H_{6i} + (\frac{\Delta t}{2} + \frac{\varepsilon \Delta t}{2} U^n) A_{6i} - \mu B_{6i} \right) a_{6k}^{n+1} + \left((1 + \frac{\varepsilon \Delta t}{2} U_x^n) H_{7i} + (\frac{\Delta t}{2} + \frac{\varepsilon \Delta t}{2} U^n) A_{7i} \right. \\ & \left. - \mu B_{7i} \right) a_{6k+1}^{n+1} + \left((1 + \frac{\varepsilon \Delta t}{2} U_x^n) H_{8i} + (\frac{\Delta t}{2} + \frac{\varepsilon \Delta t}{2} U^n) A_{8i} - \mu B_{8i} \right) a_{6k+2}^{n+1} = \left(H_{1i} + \frac{\Delta t}{2} A_{1i} - \mu B_{1i} \right) a_{6k-5}^n \\ & + \left(H_{2i} + \frac{\Delta t}{2} A_{2i} - \mu B_{2i} \right) a_{6k-4}^n + \left(H_{3i} + \frac{\Delta t}{2} A_{3i} - \mu B_{3i} \right) a_{6k-3}^n + \left(H_{4i} + \frac{\Delta t}{2} A_{4i} - \mu B_{4i} \right) a_{6k-2}^n \\ & + \left(H_{5i} + \frac{\Delta t}{2} A_{5i} - \mu B_{5i} \right) a_{6k-1}^n + \left(H_{6i} + \frac{\Delta t}{2} A_{6i} - \mu B_{6i} \right) a_{6k}^n + \left(H_{7i} + \frac{\Delta t}{2} A_{7i} - \mu B_{7i} \right) a_{6k+1}^n \\ & + \left(H_{8i} + \frac{\Delta t}{2} A_{8i} - \mu B_{8i} \right) a_{6k+2}^n \quad i = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6. \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

The recursive system (11) consists of $6N$ equations and $6N + 2$ unknown parameters. By applying the boundary conditions, we are able to eliminate the two parameters. This reduction results in a solvable $6N \times 6N$ matrix system, which is given by:

$$Lx^{n+1} = Rx^n$$

where L, R coefficient matrices and, $x^n = (a_1^n, a_2^n, \dots, a_{6N}^n)^T$ are time dependent unknown vectors to be determined. Each septic Hermite basis function in this case covers at most four subintervals, which leads to a band matrix with bandwidth six see Figure 3.1. In order to start the iterative

process, the initial vector a^0 is needed. This vector is calculated by the initial condition presented by the governing equation.

Figure 3.1: Patterns of nonzero elements of banded matrixes L and R.

4 Numerical Examples

In this section, we use two test problems with known exact results to analyse how accurate and reliable the proposed method is numerically. The accuracy of the method is also evaluated using two basic error measures square error L_2 and maximum error L_∞ norms:

$$L_2 = \sqrt{h \sum_{j=1}^N |u_j^{\text{exact}} - u_j^{\text{num.}}|^2}, \quad L_\infty = \max_{1 \leq j \leq N} |u_j^{\text{exact}} - u_j^{\text{num.}}|.$$

The RLW equation has three conservation quantities corresponding to mass, momentum and energy

$$C_1 = \int_a^b u dx \simeq h \sum_{j=1}^N u_j^n$$

$$C_2 = \int_a^b [u^2 + \mu^2 (u_x)^2] dx \simeq h \sum_{j=1}^N \left\{ (u_j^n)^2 + [\mu (u_x)_j^n]^2 \right\}$$

$$C_3 = \int_a^b [\varepsilon u^3 + 3u^2] dx \simeq h \sum_{j=1}^N \left\{ \varepsilon (u_j^n)^3 + 3 (u_j^n)^2 \right\}$$

respectively, and these will be monitored to check the conserved properties of the numerical algorithm.

Example 4.1. Single solitary wave The exact solution to the RLW equation (1) is given by the expression:

$$U(x, t) = 3d \operatorname{sech}^2(k[x - x_0 - vt]), \quad (12)$$

This formula describes a single solitary wave possessing an amplitude of $3d$, a velocity of $v = 1 + \varepsilon d$, and $k = \frac{1}{2}(\varepsilon d / \mu \nu)^{1/2}$. The wave's propagation is modeled over the spatial domain $-40 \leq x \leq 60$ and the time interval $0 \leq t \leq 20$, utilizing the parameters $\varepsilon = \mu = 1$ and $x_0 = 0$. The numerical

simulation is initiated with the following initial condition:

$$U(x, 0) = 3d \operatorname{sech}^2(k[x - x_0]). \tag{13}$$

Table 1 summarizes the findings derived from applying the septic Hermite collocation method, which employs both Legendre and Chebyshev functions. The resulting numerical data exhibits exceptional accuracy. Furthermore, Figure 4.1 provides a visual representation of the trajectory of the single solitary wave solution for the RLW equation, specifically for the parameter values $d = 0.01$ and $d = 0.03$.

Method	h	Δt	L_2 Error	L_∞ Error	C_1	C_2	C_3
$d = 0.1$							
Analytic					3.9799497	0.81046249	2.5790074
SHCM-L	1	0.1	5.10789×10^{-4}	7.80226×10^{-5}	3.9800198	0.81046313	2.5790074
SHCM-C		0.1	5.14400×10^{-4}	7.80301×10^{-5}	3.9800552	0.81046614	2.5790074
MQ[6]	1	0.1	2.08318×10^{-4}	7.8619×10^{-5}	3.979960	0.8104726	2.579041
TPS[6]		0.1	2.96994×10^{-4}	8.5119×10^{-5}	3.979823	0.8104159	2.578853
IQ[6]		0.1	2.18123×10^{-4}	7.6040×10^{-5}	3.979582	0.8104589	2.578995
G[6]		0.1	2.06232×10^{-4}	7.5355×10^{-5}	3.979846	0.8104508	2.578968
$d = 0.03$							
Analytic					2.1094075	0.12730718	0.3888059
SHCM-L	1		3.20534×10^{-3}	4.43070×10^{-4}	2.1122781	0.13138396	0.3888119
SHCM-C			4.54963×10^{-3}	8.56998×10^{-5}	2.1142600	0.14479677	0.3888175
MQ[6]	1	0.1	4.0259×10^{-5}	1.1922×10^{-5}	2.107167	0.1273011	0.388804
TPS[6]		0.1	6.45907×10^{-4}	4.30236×10^{-4}	2.105547	0.1273215	0.388865
IQ[6]		0.1	7.45694×10^{-4}	4.31517×10^{-4}	2.104109	0.1273011	0.388802
G[6]		0.1	2.87437×10^{-4}	8.3060×10^{-5}	2.106074	0.1272980	0.388795

Table 1: Comparison of error norms and constants for various methods for $\Delta t = 0.1$, and $t = 20$.

Figure 4.1: The plots of Septic Hermite Spline solutions of RLW with **a**, $d = 0.1$, **b**, $d = 0.03$.

Example 4.2. Interaction of two waves For the second test problem concerning the RLW equation, the interaction of two solitary waves is selected. The initial condition for the interaction of two positive solitary waves is defined as the sum of two well-separated solitary waves of differing amplitudes:

$$\begin{aligned}
U(x, 0) &= U_1 + U_2 \\
U_j &= 3A_j \operatorname{sech}^2(k_j(x - \tilde{x}_j)), \quad A_j = \frac{4k_j^2}{1 - 4k_j^2}, \quad j = 1, 2
\end{aligned}
\tag{14}$$

The problem is constrained by the boundary conditions $U(0, t) = U(120, t) = 0$. The chosen parameters are $k_1 = 0.4$, $\tilde{x}_1 = 15$, $k_2 = 0.3$, and $\tilde{x}_2 = 35.1$. These values result in two solitary waves with approximate magnitudes of 5.3338 and 1.6860, whose peaks are initially positioned at $x = 15$ and $x = 35.1$, respectively. Consequently, the larger wave is initially situated to the left of the smaller wave. The simulation is performed over the spatial interval $0 \leq x \leq 120$ up to time $t = 30$.

The numerical solutions illustrating the wave interaction are presented in Figure 4.2, obtained using the aforementioned Hermite spline scheme. Both solitary waves travel to the right, with their velocities determined by their respective amplitudes. The interaction between the two waves took place at approximately $t = 15$. Significantly, both waves fully regained their original shapes after the interaction, which is a characteristic property of solitons.

Table 2: Invariants of two soliton problem at different times.

Method	t	C_1	C_2	C_3
CHCM-L	5	37.9172508543	120.5225776494	744.0569871365
CHCM-C	5	37.9172357037	120.5299525086	744.0570118913
CHCM-L	10	37.9179233337	120.4649085281	743.4582503203
CHCM-C	10	37.9179942258	120.4689959629	743.4582227092
CHCM-L	15	37.9185694486	120.3186589219	741.9047193489
CHCM-C	15	37.9188775106	120.3208055064	741.9047161537
CHCM-L	20	37.9192042267	120.5088058791	743.9314947268
CHCM-C	20	37.9198739896	120.5098735376	743.9315382605
CHCM-L	25	37.9198248648	120.5222139975	744.0713532892
CHCM-C	25	37.9209626300	120.5227186165	744.0713772404
CHCM-L	30	37.9203892813	120.5226402231	744.0756579395
CHCM-C	30	37.9220721085	120.5228691038	744.0756327904

Figure 4.2: Collision of two solitons.

5 CONCLUSION

This study investigates numerical solutions for the nonlinear RLW equation using the hermite septic spline method. The method provide a simple way to approximate solutions for similiar equations. The accuracy is demonstrated through figures and tables, confirming the effectiveness of the method for addressing fractional partial differential equations in physics and engineering.

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Effect of Ring Support on Bi-layered FGM Cylindrical Shell

Mohsin Habib¹, Madiha Ghamkhar¹

¹Department of Mathematics and Statistics, University of Agriculture, Faisalabad, 38000, Pakistan

Corresponding author: mohsinhabib2854538@gmail.com

ORCID IDs:

First Author: 0009-0003-9831-8841

Second Author: 0000-0002-1897-6939

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Abstract

In this work, the effect of ring support is analyzed on bi-layered FGM cylindrical shell. The bi-layered cylindrical shell are composed of two independent materials. These materials are considered nickel and stainless steel. The characteristics of materials are observed by the volume fraction power law. The fundamental frequencies of cylindrical shell are analyzed under the simply supported end boundary condition. One layer is of functionally graded material and the other layer is of isotropic material. The curvature and strain displacement relations are attained from Sander's shell theory. The shell fundamental frequency equations are derived by using the Rayleigh Ritz. The vibration frequencies are calculated with Simply supported-simply supported boundary conditions and results are compared with already exists in the literature.

Keywords: Ring support, FG Material, Sander's shell theory, Rayleigh-Ritz method, Simply supported-simply supported.

1 Introduction and Motivation

Cylindrical shell are used to transport and store highly pressure gases and liquid for different hydraulic application. They have been applied in pipe flow, chimney design, ships, aircraft fuselages and construction buildings. They are different geometrical shapes such as cylindrical, elliptical, spherical etc. They have been found wide range of engineering application. Those rang from enormous common and mechanical structure to small electrical parts. Modern structures utilizing shells include drilling structure parts pressure vessels oil tanks. In the present work bi-layered FGM cylindrical shell with effect of ring support is well known studied field of research in structural dynamic.

Boyd and Rao [2] have analyzed the without oscillation of ring support or stringer stiffened elliptical cylinders with arbitrary condition. Wilken and Soedel [3] have analyzed modal characteristic of ring stiffened cylindrical shell. Such methods are based on the method of receptance and use the modal characteristic of the inputs of the un-stiffened cylinder and rings. By entrusting the

structure to a cylindrical shell with basic support ends stiffened by similar evenly spaced rings, precision remains in this method. A single non-matrix frequency equation is formed for not uncommon configuration which can be resolved by numerical method with certainty and rapidity. Other approach is general and gives ring stiffeners an insight into impact.

Swaddiunhippong *et al.* [4] have analyzed independent vibration with middle support around cylindrical shell. They used Rayleigh Ritz method for evaluate the mode shape and natural frequency. Donnell shell theory and the Sander's shell theory approximation of first order consider.

Loy *et al.* [5] have studied the vibration of cylindrical shell with ring support. The curvature and strain displacement relations attained from sander's shell theory. The fundamental frequency examined with Ritz method. Zhang *et al.* [6] have studied without oscillation of open annular shell with middle ring support find the frequency of such shell theory is derive from Flugge's thin shell theory. They investigated the location of ring support for number of middle ring supports and the shell angle variation on natural frequency.

Najafzadeh and Isvandzibaei [7] have analyzed the vibration of functionally graded cylindrical shell with ring support based on higher order shear deformation shell plate theory.

Najafzadeh and Isvandzibaei [8] have analyzed oscillation of thin cylindrical shell made by nickel and stainless. In this research, frequency of the shell with effect of ring support and boundary state were studied. The governing equation of FGM cylindrical shell are taken from different shear deformation theories. Result are instant on the fundamental frequency characteristics effect of boundary condition and effect of ring support. The present result is compatible in literature with that available. Arshad *et al.* [9] have discussed the bi-layered of different materials of cylindrical shell. Which one layered is made of isotropic and other layered is made of FGM. Arshad *et al.* [10] have studied the bilayered FGM cylindrical shell. Which both layered are made by FGM. Strain and curvature displacement relations are attained from Love's shell theory. Shell fundamental frequency equation are attained by using R-Ritz method. Rahimi *et al.* [11] have examined vibration behavior of FG material cylindrical shell with intermediate ring support governing equation of motion taken from sander's shell theory. Materials characteristics are considered to be graded in direction of h according to the fraction of the power law value. They used Rayleigh Ritz method for observed vibration analysis. Arshad *et al.* [12] examined the without oscillation of sandwich FGM cylindrical shell with intermediate layer of isotropic content in ring support influence. The ring support is used aside from the shell's radial direction. For curvature and strain displacement relationship are attained from Love's first order thin shell theory. To form the shell fundamental frequency equation, the Rayleigh Ritz method is applied.

Ghamkhar *et al.* [13] have studied of three layers of FG material cylindrical shell with additional impact of ring support cylindrical shell internal and external surface isotropic and FGM middle surface. They have analyzed the position of intermediate support is effect the fundamental frequency of cylindrical shell. They have studied fundamental frequency by using R-Ritz method. They compared result of fundamental natural frequency with already exist literature.

2 Theoretical Consideration

Cylindrical shell is geometrical description in Fig. 1. Consider that R is radius, L is length and h is thickness of thin cylindrical shell. An (x, θ, z) are attained at the cylindrical shell central area. The z -coordinate in radial, x -coordinate in axial direction and θ -coordinate is taking along in circumferential direction of the cylindrical shell. The deformational displacement function are represented by $U_1(x, \theta, z)$, $U_2(x, \theta, z)$ and $U_3(x, \theta, z)$ in axial, circumferential and the radial direction of cylindrical shell respectively.

The analytical problem of the 3-D circular cylindrical shell that is translated into a 2-D problem by taking into account the condition of the plane stress, strain and stress component in the z -direction are neglected. The stress and strain relation are stated by Hooke's law as:

$$\{\sigma\} = [Q] \{e\}. \quad (1)$$

Figure 1: Cylindrical Shell with Ring Support

Where $[Q]$ are represent the matrix of reduced stiffness and $\{e\}$, $\{\sigma\}$ are represent the strain and stress of the shell are defined as:

$$\{\sigma\} = (\sigma_x, \sigma_\theta, \sigma_{x\theta})^T. \quad (2)$$

Where $\sigma_{x\theta}$ denoted shear-stress in $x\theta$ -plane, σ_θ and σ_x are represented stress in θ and x direction in the plane respectively.

The strain are represented as:

$$\{e\} = (e_x, e_\theta, e_{x\theta})^T. \quad (3)$$

Where $e_{x\theta}$ denoted shear strain in the $x\theta$ -plane and e_θ and e_x are represented strain in θ and x direction in the plane respectively.

The stiffness matrix is defined as:

$$[Q] = \begin{bmatrix} Q_{11} & Q_{12} & 0 \\ Q_{12} & Q_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & Q_{66} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4)$$

Where $Q_{11} = \frac{E}{1-\nu^2} = Q_{22}$, $Q_{66} = \frac{E}{2(1+\nu)}$, $Q_{12} = \frac{\nu E}{1-\nu^2}$.

The component of strain vector $\{e\}$ are attained as linear function in the form of z and written as:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} e_\theta &= e_2 - z\kappa_2 \\ e_x &= e_1 - z\kappa_1 \\ e_{x\theta} &= \gamma - 2z\xi \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (5)$$

Where e_2 , e_1 and γ are represent of strain surface. κ_2 , κ_1 and ξ are represent curvatures surface. Curvature and strain displacement relations are attained from sander's shell theory. Shell theory widely used in analytical shell problems. According to given shell theory e_1 , e_2 and γ are written as:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} e_1 &= \frac{\partial U_1}{\partial x} \\ e_2 &= \frac{1}{R} \left(\frac{\partial U_2}{\partial \theta} + U_3 \right) \\ \gamma &= \frac{\partial U_2}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{R} \frac{\partial U_1}{\partial \theta} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (6)$$

The κ_1 , κ_2 and ξ are expressed in the form:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \kappa_1 &= \frac{-\partial^2 U_3}{\partial x^2} \\ \kappa_2 &= \frac{-1}{R^2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 U_3}{\partial \theta^2} - \frac{\partial U_2}{\partial \theta} \right) \\ \xi &= \frac{-1}{R} \left(\frac{\partial^2 U_3}{\partial x \partial \theta} - \frac{3}{4} \frac{\partial U_2}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{4R} \frac{\partial U_1}{\partial \theta} \right) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (7)$$

$$\{U_{ij}, V_{ij}, W_{ij}\} = \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} Q_{ij} \{1, z, z^2\} dz. \quad (8)$$

Where W_{ij} , V_{ij} and U_{ij} are the bending, coupling and extensional stiffness. Governing shell motion equation are given by

$$\frac{\partial N_x}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{R} \frac{\partial N_{x\theta}}{\partial \theta} = \rho_t \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2}. \quad (9)$$

The strain energy are expressed as:

$$S = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^L \int_0^{2\pi} \{\eta\}^T [I] \{\eta\} R d\theta dx. \quad (10)$$

Where

$$\{\eta\}^T = \{e_1, e_2, \gamma, \kappa_1, \kappa_2, 2\xi\}. \quad (11)$$

$$[I] = \begin{bmatrix} U & V \\ V & W \end{bmatrix}. \quad (12)$$

Where

$$U = \begin{bmatrix} U_{11} & U_{12} & 0 \\ U_{12} & U_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & U_{66} \end{bmatrix}, \quad V = \begin{bmatrix} V_{11} & V_{12} & 0 \\ V_{12} & V_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & V_{66} \end{bmatrix}, \quad W = \begin{bmatrix} W_{11} & W_{12} & 0 \\ W_{12} & W_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & W_{66} \end{bmatrix}.$$

$$[I] = \begin{bmatrix} U_{11} & U_{12} & 0 & V_{11} & V_{12} & 0 \\ U_{12} & U_{22} & 0 & V_{12} & V_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & U_{66} & 0 & 0 & V_{66} \\ V_{11} & V_{12} & 0 & W_{11} & W_{12} & 0 \\ V_{12} & V_{22} & 0 & W_{12} & W_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & V_{66} & 0 & 0 & W_{66} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (13)$$

Kinetic energy T are expressed as:

$$T = \frac{R}{2} \int_0^L \int_0^{2\pi} \rho_t \left\{ \left(\frac{\partial U_1}{\partial t} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial U_2}{\partial t} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial U_3}{\partial t} \right)^2 \right\} d\theta dx. \quad (14)$$

Where ρ_t are represent mass density per unit length and state as:

$$\rho_t = \int_{-\frac{h}{2}}^{\frac{h}{2}} \rho \, dz. \quad (15)$$

Eq (10) and (12) put into (9), the strain energy S are expressed in the following form:

$$S = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^L \int_0^{2\pi} \{ U_{11}e_1^2 + U_{22}e_2^2 + 2U_{12}e_1e_2 + U_{66}\gamma^2 + 2V_{11}e_1\kappa_1 + 2V_{12}e_1\kappa_2 + 2V_{12}e_2\kappa_1 \\ + 2V_{22}e_2\kappa_2 + 4V_{66}\gamma\xi + W_{11}\kappa_1^2 + W_{22}\kappa_2^2 + 2W_{12}\kappa_1\kappa_2 + 4W_{66}\xi^2 \} R d\theta dx.$$

The axial modal displacement associated with trigonometric function of three deformation displacement. For x , θ and temporal t variables, modal displacement equation are attained:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} U_1(x, \theta, t) &= A_m U(x) \cos \omega t \cos(n\theta), \\ U_2(x, \theta, t) &= B_m V(x) \cos \omega t \sin(n\theta), \\ U_3(x, \theta, t) &= C_m W(x) \cos \omega t \cos(n\theta). \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (16)$$

Where $W(x)$, $V(x)$ and $U(x)$ are the natural vibrational modes in the radial, circumferential and axial direction respectively.

The non-dimensional parameter are introduced for algebraic convenience:

$$\overline{W} = \frac{W(x)}{R}, \quad \overline{V} = \frac{V(x)}{h}, \quad \overline{U} = \frac{U(x)}{h}, \quad X = \frac{x}{L} \\ \overline{U}_{ij} = \frac{U_{ij}}{h}, \quad \overline{V}_{ij} = \frac{V_{ij}}{h^2}, \quad \overline{W}_{ij} = \frac{W_{ij}}{h^3}, \quad a = \frac{R}{L}, \quad b = \frac{h}{R}, \quad \overline{\rho} = \frac{\rho_t}{h}$$

$U(x) = \frac{d\overline{\zeta}(x)}{dx}$, $V(x) = \overline{\zeta}(x)$, $W(x) = \overline{\zeta}(x)(x - a)$ and $\overline{\zeta}(x)$ represent the axial function. $\overline{\zeta}(x)$ is defined for the axial deformation function which is the characteristics of beam function as:

$$\overline{\zeta}(x) = b_1 \cosh(a_m x) + b_2 \cos(a_m x) - \chi_m (b_3 \sinh(a_m x) + b_4 \sin(a_m x)).$$

Where $(b_i, i = 1, \dots, 4)$ depend upon of the nature of edge conditions, χ_m depend on values of

a_m and a_m represent the roots of trigonometric equation.

$$\left. \begin{aligned} U_1(x, \theta, t) &= A_m h \bar{U} \cos(n\theta) \cos \omega t \\ U_2(x, \theta, t) &= B_m h \bar{V} \sin(n\theta) \cos \omega t \\ U_3(x, \theta, t) &= C_m R \bar{W} \cos(n\theta) \cos \omega t \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (17)$$

The maximum Lagrangian functional is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \psi_{max} &= \frac{\pi R L h}{2} [R^2 \omega^2 \bar{\rho} \int_0^1 (b^2 (A_m \bar{U})^2 + b^2 (B_m \bar{V})^2 + (C_m \bar{W})^2) dX \\ &- \int_0^1 a^2 b^2 \bar{U}_{11} \left(A_m \frac{d\bar{U}}{dX} \right)^2 + \bar{U}_{22} (nb B_m \bar{V} + C_m \bar{W})^2 + 2ab \bar{U}_{12} \left(A_m \frac{d\bar{U}}{dX} \right) (nb B_m \bar{V} + C_m \bar{W}) \\ &+ \bar{U}_{66} \left(ab B_m \frac{d\bar{V}}{dX} - nb A_m \bar{U} \right)^2 - 2a^3 b^2 \bar{V}_{11} \left(A_m \frac{d\bar{U}}{dX} \right) \left(C_m \frac{d^2 \bar{W}}{dX^2} \right) + 2ab^2 \bar{V}_{12} \left(A_m \frac{d\bar{U}}{dX} \right) \\ &(n^2 C_m \bar{W} + nb B_m \bar{V}) - 2a^2 b \bar{V}_{12} (nb B_m \bar{V} + C_m \bar{W}) \left(C_m \frac{d^2 \bar{W}}{dX^2} \right) + 2b \bar{V}_{22} (nb B_m \bar{V} + C_m \bar{W}) \\ &(n^2 C_m \bar{W} + nb B_m \bar{V}) - 4b \bar{V}_{66} \left(ab B_m \frac{d\bar{V}}{dX} - nb A_m \bar{U} \right) \left(na C_m \frac{d\bar{W}}{dX} + \frac{3}{4} ab B_m \frac{d\bar{V}}{dX} + \frac{n}{4} b A_m \bar{U} \right) \\ &+ a^4 b^2 \bar{W}_{11} \left(C_m \frac{d^2 \bar{W}}{dX^2} \right)^2 + b^2 \bar{W}_{22} (n^2 C_m \bar{W} + nb B_m \bar{V})^2 + 2a^2 b^2 \bar{W}_{12} \left(C_m \frac{d^2 \bar{W}}{dX^2} \right) (-n^2 C_m \bar{W} - nb B_m \bar{V}) \\ &+ 4b^2 \bar{W}_{66} \left(-na C_m \frac{d\bar{W}}{dX} - \frac{3}{4} ab B_m \frac{d\bar{V}}{dX} - \frac{n}{4} b A_m \bar{U} \right)^2] dX. \end{aligned}$$

Where A_m, B_m, C_m are the fourier vibrational amplitudes. Apply well known Ritz method to maximum of Lagrangian function ψ_{max} with respect to the vibration amplitudes A_m, B_m, C_m to achieve necessary condition for extrema:

$$\frac{\partial \psi_{max}}{\partial A_m} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial \psi_{max}}{\partial B_m} = 0, \quad \frac{\partial \psi_{max}}{\partial C_m} = 0.$$

A system of homogeneous equation in A_m, B_m and C_m is derive and transformed into the eigenvalue problem as:

$$\{[P] - \omega^2 [L]\} X = 0.$$

Where $\omega^2 = R^2 \omega^2 \rho$, $X^t = [A_m, B_m, C_m]$ and $[P], [L]$ are the stiffness and matrices respectively are describe as:

$$P = \begin{bmatrix} P_{11} & P_{12} & P_{13} \\ P_{12} & P_{22} & P_{23} \\ P_{13} & P_{23} & P_{33} \end{bmatrix}, \quad L = \begin{bmatrix} L_{11} & L_{12} & L_{13} \\ L_{12} & L_{22} & L_{23} \\ L_{13} & L_{23} & L_{33} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (18)$$

2.1

In an area of highly dominated thermal physical systems, functionally graded material is observed. The expression of an effective material property G of an FGM is of a function temperature $T(K)$

by Touloukian [1] as:

$$G = G_0(G_{-1}T^{-1} + 1 + G_1T + G_2T^2 + G_3T^3). \quad (19)$$

Where G_0 , G_{-1} , G_1 , G_2 and G_3 are the thermal coefficient taken in $T(k)$ and measure in Kelvin and are specific for the constituent material forming the FG material. The G of FG material depend on the materials characteristics and VF of the constituent materials are represented as:

$$G = \sum_{j=1}^k G_j V_{fj}. \quad (20)$$

Where V_{fj} and G_j represent the VF and material property of j th integrant materials respectively. The result is unity, when the volume fractions are added.

$$\sum_{j=1}^k V_j = 1. \quad (21)$$

The VF of the two ingredient materials for a shell having a single FG material can be represented as:

$$V_1 = \left(\frac{2z+h}{2h} \right)^N. \quad (22)$$

Where h is thickness and N is power law of exponent. For cylindrical shell having two layered of different materials one with FGM composed with the constituents M_1 and M_2 and second layered is isotropic material M_3 . M_1 is equal to M_3 . For bilayered cylindrical shell the effective materials properties are ν poisson's ratio, ρ mass density and E young's modulus are expressed as

$$\left. \begin{aligned} E &= E_{iso} + E_{fgm} \\ \nu &= \nu_{iso} + \nu_{fgm} \\ \rho &= \rho_{iso} + \rho_{fgm} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (23)$$

Where

$$\left. \begin{aligned} E_{fgm} &= (E_2 - E_1) \left(\frac{2z+h}{2h} \right)^N + E_1 \\ \nu_{fgm} &= (\nu_2 - \nu_1) \left(\frac{2z+h}{2h} \right)^N + \nu_1 \\ \rho_{fgm} &= (\rho_2 - \rho_1) \left(\frac{2z+h}{2h} \right)^N + \rho_1 \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (24)$$

In type 1 and 2 shell, the FG material constituents layer which vary from 0 to $\frac{h}{2}$ and the thickness of inner layer which vary from $\frac{-h}{2}$ to 0 for isotropic material respectively. In type 1 shell, the property of cylindrical shell material become $\nu = \nu_3$, $\rho = \rho_3$ and $E = E_3$ at $z = \frac{-h}{2}$. The material properties are $\nu = \nu_2$ and ν_1 , $\rho = \rho_2$ and ρ_1 , $E = E_2$ and E_1 at $z = 0$ and in the same pattern, when $z = \frac{h}{2}$ these properties are $\nu = \nu_1$, $\rho = \rho_1$ and $E = E_1$. In type 2 shell, The properties of cylindrical shell material become $\nu = \nu_3$, $\rho = \rho_3$ and $E = E_3$ at $z = \frac{-h}{2}$, when $z = 0$ material properties are $\nu = \nu_1$ and ν_2 , $\rho = \rho_1$ and ρ_2 , $E = E_1$ and E_2 and in the same pattern, the properties of material are $\rho = \rho_2$, $\nu = \nu_2$ and $E = E_2$ at $z = \frac{h}{2}$. The vibration frequencies are calculated under simply supported-simply supported boundary condition. The results obtained by using Matlab program.

3 Results and Discussion

To check the feasibility of present work. The results of present work is compared to Zhang *et al*[6] results with SS-SS boundary condition for type 1 shell. Table (1) the fundamental natural frequencies are minor increasing against circumferential wave numbers. Table (2) the natural frequency of present work is decreasing with compared to Loy *et al*[5] results for SS-SS boundary condition. Table (3) describe the fundamental frequencies of bi-layered FG material cylindrical shell with and without ring for the SS-SS boundary condition. The behavior of fundamental frequencies are increasing against the n for both types of shell. The variation in frequency of cylindrical shell without ring are higher than the fundamental frequencies of cylindrical shell with ring support. Table (4) demonstrates the fundamental frequencies with L to R ratio for type 1 shell for SS-SS boundary condition. The fundamental frequencies increased against the circumferential wave numbers. The natural frequency curve attained highest values 295.5160 at $n = 5$ and the curve taken lowest value 46.1620 at $n = 1, m = 1$. In type 2 maximum value attained 296.5622 at $n = 5$ and minimum value taken 46.2160 at $n = 1, m = 1$.

Table (5) represents the fundamental frequencies with h to R ratio for the type 1 shell. The fundamental frequencies slightly increased against the circumferential wave numbers with SS-SS boundary condition. The fundamental frequency curve taken maximum value 193.6870 at $n = 5, m = 1$. The fundamental frequency curve attained minimum values 65.7217 at $n = 1, m = 1$. In type 2 shell the frequency curves taken maximum value 194.0963 at $n = 5, m = 1$. The frequency curve attained minimum value 65.8589 at $n = 1, m = 1$.

Fig.2 demonstrates the fundamental frequencies of bi-layered FG material cylindrical shell type 1 with ring support for SS-SS boundary condition. First the fundamental frequencies curves increase gradually from $a_1 = 0$ to $a_1 = 0.5$ then the frequencies curves decreasing gradually from $a_1 = 0.5$ to $a_1 = 1$. The frequency curves attained minimum value 17.9655 at $a_1 = 0$, the curves taken maximum values 199.7595, 395.633, 527.464, 627.1379 at $a_1 = 0.5$ and the curves taken minimum values 17.9655, 17.9654, 17.9656, 17.9657 at $a_1 = 1, m = 1, N = 3.5, h = 0.002, n = 1$.

Fig.3 describes the fundamental frequencies of bi-layered FG material cylindrical shell type 2. First the fundamental frequencies are increased then decreased against the position of ring with SS-SS boundary condition. The frequency curves attained minimum values 17.9702 at $a_1 = 0$, the curves taken maximum values 169.2889, 321.0058, 469.4629, 599.1012 at $a_1 = 0.5$ and the curves attained minimum values 17.9704, 17.9702, 17.9702, 17.9703 at $a_1 = 1, m = 1, N = 3.5, h = 0.002, n = 1$.

Fig.4 represents the fundamental frequencies of bi-layered FG material cylindrical shell with ring support. The fundamental frequency curves swiftly increased against the circumferential wave numbers. The frequency curves attained minimum values 199.8445, 122.9645, 61.434, 46.162 at $n = 1, m = 1, a_1 = 0.1, h = 0.007, R = 1, N = 1$. The frequency curves taken maximum values 295.516, 180.975, 94.1696, 72.2462 at $n = 5$ against the various length.

Fig.5 shows the fundamental frequencies of bi-layered FG material cylindrical shell with ring support. The fundamental frequency curves gradually increased against the circumferential wave numbers. The frequency curves attained minimum values 65.7217, 92.9472, 113.8406, 131.8406 at $n = 1, m = 1, a_1 = 0.1, L = 9, R = 1, N = 1$. The frequency curves taken maximum values 96.5982, 136.6235, 167.4317, 193.6870 at $n = 5$ against the various h .

Figure 2: Variation of fundamental frequency bi-layered FG material CS type 1 against the ring position at $m = 1$, $n = 1$, $h = 0.002$, $N = 3.5$

Figure 3: Variation of fundamental frequency bi-layered FG material CS type 2 against the ring position at $m = 1$, $n = 1$, $h = 0.002$, $N = 3.5$

Figure 4: Variation of fundamental frequency bi-layered FG material CS type 1 against the n at different L , $a1 = 0.1$, $m = 1$, $h = 0.007$, $N = 1$

Figure 5: Variation of fundamental frequency bi-layered FG material CS type 1 against the n at different h , $a1 = 0.1$, $m = 1$, $L = 9$, $N = 1$

Table 1: Comparison of frequency for SS-SS boundary condition at ($h = 0.05$, $L = 20$, $R = 1$, M_1 and M_2).

	$n = 1$	$n = 2$	$n = 3$	$n = 4$
Zhang <i>et al</i> [6]	0.016102	0.039271	0.109811	0.210277
Present	0.0161029	0.0392713	0.1098115	0.2102771

Table 2: Comparison of frequency for SS-SS boundary condition at ($m = 1$, $h = 0.002$, $L = 20$, $R = 1$, M_1 and M_2).

	Loy <i>et al</i> [5]		Present	
n	$N = 1$	$N = 2$	$N = 1$	$N = 2$
1	13.211	13.103	13.210	13.103
2	4.4800	4.4435	4.4746	4.4396
3	4.1569	4.1235	4.1356	4.1154
4	7.0384	6.9820	7.0000	6.9721
5	11.241	11.151	11.181	11.138

Table 3: Variation of the fundamental frequency of bi-layered FG material cylindrical shell with and without effect of ring support against n . With SS-SS boundary condition at ($m = 1$, $h = 0.07$, $L = 9$, $R = 1$, $a_1 = 0.2 M_1$ and M_2).

	Shell Type 1		Shell Type 2	
n	With Ring	Without Ring	With Ring	Without Ring
1	25.1972	102.2951	25.0723	102.4736
2	54.2233	140.2010	54.2950	140.4460
3	61.5509	149.2420	61.6818	149.5208
4	64.4884	152.5801	64.6696	152.8839
5	66.2356	154.2913	66.4728	154.6216
6	67.7918	155.4867	68.0933	155.8473
7	69.6316	156.6109	70.9957	157.0063
8	72.0632	157.9103	72.5161	158.3454
9	75.3196	159.5623	75.8544	160.0419
10	79.5794	161.7171	80.1961	162.2456

Table 4: Variation of the fundamental frequency of bi-layered FG material cylindrical shell with effect of ring support against n at ($m = 1$, $h = 0.07$, $a_1 = 0.1$, $R = 1$, M_1 and M_2).

	Type1				Type2			
n	$L = 4$	$L = 9$	$L = 14$	$L = 17$	$L = 4$	$L = 9$	$L = 14$	$L = 17$
1	199.8445	122.9645	61.4340	46.1620	200.6290	123.2119	61.5192	46.2160
2	287.6723	166.4425	84.2769	64.0910	288.2138	166.7399	84.4266	64.2074
3	293.5355	175.9079	90.3460	68.9520	294.0714	176.2338	90.5294	69.1050
4	294.8838	179.2853	92.7694	70.9661	295.4336	179.6336	92.9858	71.1592
5	295.5160	180.9750	94.1696	72.2462	296.5622	181.3462	94.4249	72.4882

4 Conclusions

The frequency analysis of bi-layered FG material cylindrical shell with effect of ring support. The fundamental frequencies are examined for SS end boundary condition. The fundamental frequency are increasing against circumferential wave numbers. The frequencies are increased

Table 5: Variation of the fundamental frequency of bilayered FG material cylindrical shell with effect of ring support against n at ($m = 1$, $L = 9$, $a_1 = 0.1$, $R = 1$, M_1 and M_2).

n	Type1				Type2			
	$h = 0.02$	$h = 0.04$	$h = 0.06$	$h = 0.08$	$h = 0.02$	$h = 0.04$	$h = 0.06$	$h = 0.08$
1	65.7217	92.9472	113.8406	131.8406	65.8589	93.1383	114.0714	131.7200
2	88.9622	125.8134	154.0930	177.9392	89.1256	126.0416	154.3695	178.2560
3	94.0120	132.9548	162.8464	188.0768	94.1863	133.1998	163.1472	188.4271
4	95.7814	135.4596	165.9412	191.7470	95.9604	135.7142	166.2591	192.1256
5	96.5982	136.6235	167.4317	193.6870	96.7801	136.8858	167.7662	194.0963

with the increasing of length to radius ratio. The natural frequency curves make symmetric shapes when the ring support install on different position of shell. The frequency increased with the increasing of h to R ratio. This work can be extended with additional parameters, rings support, mode shapes and different materials of cylindrical shell.

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Block-Scale Steganography in Color Images

Nilhan SAYIN YANILMAZ¹, Hülya KODAL SEVİNDİR¹

¹*Department of Mathematics, Kocaeli University, Kocaeli, Türkiye*

Corresponding author: nsayin61@gmail.com

ORCID IDs:

First Author: [0000-0001-8082-7830](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8082-7830)

Second Author: [0000-0003-1460-0608](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1460-0608)

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Abstract

Today, ensuring the secure transmission of data over the internet is of great importance, as there is a risk that original data may be accessed by unauthorized third parties. The aim of this study is to develop a method that enhances data security by using the steganography technique to protect confidential and personal information from unauthorized access. Steganography is a technique in which ordinary images are used as carriers to store information in a concealed manner. In this method, the sender must select an appropriate carrier image, message content, and encryption key when determining the message to be hidden. The primary goal of steganography is to ensure secure data storage without introducing any noticeable changes to the image in which the message is embedded. Considering the studies conducted in the literature on data hiding, RGB image data and the wavelet transform—one of the multi-scale methods developed in recent years—constitute the focus of this research.

In this study, the data to be concealed is an RGB image, which is divided into blocks using a matrix-column-based approach. A cover image was selected for each block, and these blocks were embedded into the cover images using the Haar wavelet transform. Finally, the blocks obtained from the cover images were combined to reconstruct the secret image. The Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) and Structural Similarity Index Method (SSIM) values were examined to compare the original secret image and the reconstructed image.

Keywords: Steganography, Wavelet transform, Color image.

1. Introduction

With the rapid advancement of technology, taking security measures in response to new developments in our lives has become an unavoidable necessity. The security of online transactions, which we frequently use in our daily lives, cannot always be fully guaranteed. When using the internet, we exchange data and frequently share personal information in the process. To ensure that this information reaches the recipient without being read or altered in any way, we may sometimes need to take individual security measures, depending on the value of the information. This study examines

personal security measures that can be taken to prevent third-party monitoring or modification of images sent or stored over the internet.

Steganography is a technique for encryptedly hiding information within normal images. The goal of steganography is to ensure that changes to the carrier image caused by embedding a secret image are visually unnoticeable. If the existence of secret messages is successfully concealed, unauthorized individuals or groups cannot detect the secret, and the secret cannot become a target for attack. Steganography can be applied to various formats, such as text, images, audio, and video. In this research, the steganography technique was used specifically on images.

2. Mathematical Framework

Steganography is a technique that protects confidential information by embedding it within a medium such as images or audio. The medium carrying the confidential data is called "stego." The primary goal of steganography is to conceal the transmitted information in a way that makes its presence unnoticeable; the better the data is concealed, the more secure the information is. However, for the data to be meaningful, the recipient must know both the transmission channel and the information needed to decrypt it; therefore, in steganography, it is essential to protect how the data will be transmitted and decrypted.

Our proposed method ensures the security of the image data to be hidden by embedding it within other selected images. All images are treated as color images. Because the images are matrices, they can be divided into any number of rows and/or columns. The resulting cover image blocks are embedded within the selected cover images as many times as the number of blocks. Embedding is performed using the Discrete Wavelet Transform. The Discrete Wavelet Transform is a transform that divides the image into four sub-bands, allowing for independent embedding, and provides high visual quality for stego images. In the transform domain, the embedding is performed using transformed coefficients rather than direct intensity values. This way, the structure of the cover images is not distorted, but it is not perceptible to human vision. Even if this embedding, which can be detected by computers and removed from the cover image, is detected, the secret image can not be accessed without obtaining all blocks and determining their locations.

2.1. Discrete Haar Wavelet Transform

The discrete wavelet transform is an application of the wavelet transform formulated in equation 1. ω is a continuous function, j is a scaler, and k is a sliding parameter. The equation representing ω is as follows:

$$\omega_{j,k}(t) = 2^{-\frac{j}{2}}\omega(2^{-j}t - k) \quad (1)$$

Wavelet series expansion maps a function of a continuous variable to a series of coefficients. If the expanded function is discrete, the resulting coefficients are called discrete wavelet transforms. There are three discrete wavelet transforms (1-D DWT, 2-D DWT, and 3-D DWT), the first being the one-dimensional discrete wavelet transform. The multi resolution formulations of the 1-D DWT, scaling, and wavelet functions are given in Equations 2 and 3.

$$\theta_{j,m,n}(x,y) = 2^{\frac{j}{2}}\theta(2^jx - m, 2^jy - n) \quad (2)$$

$$\vartheta_{j,m,n}^i(x,y) = 2^{\frac{j}{2}}\vartheta^i(2^jx - m, 2^jy - n) \quad (3)$$

Here i = directed wavelets, j = arbitrary initial scale, m and n determine the location of the scaling function.

The discrete wavelet transform is used to transform image pixels into wavelets. Various encodings are applied to the frequency-based images obtained using this technique. The multi-level wavelet decomposition is applied to the original selected image (Figure 1(a)). Applying the 1-D DWT single-level decomposition of Figure 1(b) to the original image will produce the result shown in Figure 1(c).

Figure 1. Multilevel Wavelet Decomposition.

The advantage of discrete wavelet transforms over other transform methods is that they retain frequency and position information. The DWT algorithm achieves this; it requires matrix data to perform the transform.

By preserving frequency position, signal denoising, data compression, and coding of various DWT types, such as 2D DWT, have been achieved.

Equation 4 shows the 2D function of the Haar matrix associated with Haar wavelets.

$$H_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

In this case, the transformation is applied to each 2x2 matrix. When the 1-D transformation is applied to each row, the result of this transformation is used as input to transform each column to obtain the DHWT. The results of the 2-D transformation using the 2x2 matrix are shown in Equation 5.

$$DHWT(X) = DHWT \begin{bmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{bmatrix} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} a+b+c+d & a-b+c-d \\ a+b-c-d & a-b-c+d \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} W_X^{LL} & W_X^{HL} \\ W_X^{LH} & W_X^{HH} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

Here W_X^{LL} are horizontal and vertical low pass, W_X^{HL} are horizontal high pass and vertical low pass, W_X^{LH} are horizontal low pass and vertical high pass, and W_X^{HH} are horizontal and vertical high pass transform components [1].

3. Applications and Implications

All images in this study are 24-bit deep and in RGB format. The secret image used is 720 x 576. The image we call the secret image and assume we need to protect is shown in Figure 2.

Cover images were selected in different file types, including BMP, JPEG, and PNG, to demonstrate their suitability for various image types, with 24-bit depth, different sizes, and different image types. The idea behind this study is to divide the image to be hidden into the desired number of blocks and embed the same number of blocks within the cover image. The images we will use as cover images and embed the blocks of the secret image are shown in Figure 3.

The program used during application development is the MATLAB (R2018b) package program. The decomposition and Wavelet Transform and embedding operations applied to the visual data used during the application and development phase of the method were performed by writing appropriate codes in the MATLAB package program.

The Discrete Wavelet Transform is a transform that divides an image into four sub-bands, allowing for independent embedding, providing high visual quality for stego images. In the transform domain, the

embedding is performed using transformed coefficients rather than direct intensity values. This way, the structure of the cover images remains intact, yet remains invisible to the human visual system.

Figure 2.Secret Image

Figure 3. Cover Images

The secret image is considered as a matrix, as given in equation 6, and divided into equal parts as the number of blocks to be divided.

$$\begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & \cdots & a_{1720} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{5761} & \cdots & a_{576720} \end{pmatrix} \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} a_{11} & \cdots & a_{1120} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{5761} & \cdots & a_{576120} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} a_{1121} & \cdots & a_{1240} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{576121} & \cdots & a_{576240} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} a_{1241} & \cdots & a_{1360} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{576241} & \cdots & a_{576360} \end{pmatrix} \\ \begin{pmatrix} a_{1361} & \cdots & a_{1480} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{576361} & \cdots & a_{576480} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} a_{1481} & \cdots & a_{1600} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{576481} & \cdots & a_{576600} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} a_{1601} & \cdots & a_{1720} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_{576601} & \cdots & a_{576720} \end{pmatrix} \quad (7)$$

In the proposed method, the image is divided into six blocks shown in Figure 4 with the matrix logic given in Equation 7.

Figure 4.The Secret Image is Separated into Blocks.

By applying a level-1 Discrete Wavelet Transform (DWT) to the cover images using the MATLAB application, the sub-bands were obtained separately for each image as shown in Figure 5, and the blocks of the secret image were embedded into the sub-bands of the cover images. The resulting embedded images are presented in Figure 6.

Figure 5. Wavelet Sub-bands of the First Cover Image.

Figure6. Cover Images with Embedded Shares.

4. Results and Discussion

By applying the Inverse Wavelet Transform to the obtained embedded cover images, the blocks of the secret image were extracted from the sub-bands in which they were embedded. Figure 7 shows the version of the first block obtained from the first cover image.

Figure7. Extraction of the Block from the Embedded Sub-band.

The shares obtained by extracting all the blocks from the sub-bands in which they were embedded using the Inverse Wavelet Transform are presented in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Blocks Extracted from the Sub-bands.

As seen in Figure 8, the sizes of the blocks extracted from the sub-bands differ from each other. This is because the cover images selected have different dimensions. In the embedding process, the key we possess corresponds to the scaling size. If the scaling size is unknown, the images cannot be combined. The shares obtained solely from the extracted sub-bands do not yield a meaningful result. After applying the scaling process, the shares are resized to match the actual block dimensions, as shown in Figure 9.

Figure9. Scaled Versions of the Blocks Extracted from the Sub-bands.

By combining the obtained shares, an image close to the secret image is reconstructed. The resulting image is presented in Figure 10.

Figure10. Reconstructed Secret Image.

The Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) and Structural Similarity Index Method (SSIM) values were examined between the obtained image and the original secret image. A PSNR value greater than 20 is considered acceptable, and in our application, it was measured as 22.1010. The SSIM, a perception-based method that considers image degradation as a change in structural information, is measured on a scale from 0 to 1. In our application, the SSIM value was obtained as 0.8468, indicating that there is no significant difference between the secret image and the reconstructed image.

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Double Fractional Integral Inequalities for Co-ordinated Convex Functions

Samet ERDEN¹, Burçin Gökkurt Özdemir²

¹*Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Science, Bartın University, Bartın, Turkey*

²*Department of Mathematics and Science Education, Faculty of Education, Bartın University, Bartın, Turkey*

Corresponding author: erdensmt@gmail.com

ORCID IDs:

First Author: [0000-0001-8430-7533](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8430-7533)

Second Author: [0000-0002-1551-0113](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1551-0113)

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Abstract

The primary objective of this study is to establish novel Ostrowski-type fractional integral inequalities for functions whose powers of the absolute values of partial derivatives are convex on the coordinates. By utilizing a fractional integral identity previously proposed in the literature, several generalized versions of these inequalities are derived. In addition, various special cases and related corollaries are provided to emphasize the importance and applicability of the obtained results.

Keywords: Fractional integrals, Co-ordinated convex functions, Ostrowski type inequalities, Double integrals.

1. Introduction

The study one of the most fundamental and influential integral inequalities in mathematical analysis is the celebrated Ostrowski inequality, established by Alexander Markovich Ostrowski [16] in 1938. In its classical form, this inequality provides an upper bound for the error between the value of a function at any point $x \in [a, b]$ and its integral average over that interval. This bound is expressed in terms of the maximum norm of the function's first derivative, f' . The significance of this inequality stems from its utility as a powerful tool in various fields, particularly in error analysis for numerical integration and probability theory. The practical significance of the Ostrowski inequality is particularly evident in numerical analysis and the theory of special means. It is extensively applied to estimate the error bounds for various quadrature formulae, including the well-known midpoint, trapezoid, and Simpson rules.

Firstly, we give the definitions of Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals:

Definition 1. [11] Let $f \in L_1[a, b]$. The Riemann-Liouville integrals $J_{a+}^\alpha f$ and $J_{b-}^\alpha f$ of order $\alpha > 0$ with $a \geq 0$ are defined by

$$J_{a+}^\alpha f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_a^x (x-t)^{\alpha-1} f(t) dt, \quad x > a$$

and

$$J_{b-}^\alpha f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_x^b (t-x)^{\alpha-1} f(t) dt, \quad x < b$$

respectively. Here, $\Gamma(\alpha)$ is the Gamma function and $J_{a+}^0 f(x) = J_{b-}^0 f(x) = f(x)$.

An essential component of our investigation involves the Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals for functions of two variables, defined as follows.

Definition 2. [19] Let $f \in L_1([a, b] \times [c, d])$. The Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals $J_{a+,c+}^{\alpha,\beta}$, $J_{a+,d-}^{\alpha,\beta}$, $J_{b-,c+}^{\alpha,\beta}$ and $J_{b-,d-}^{\alpha,\beta}$ are defined by

$$J_{a+,c+}^{\alpha,\beta} f(x, y) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} \int_a^x \int_c^y (x-t)^{\alpha-1} (y-s)^{\beta-1} f(t, s) ds dt, \quad x > a, y > c,$$

$$J_{a+,d-}^{\alpha,\beta} f(x, y) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} \int_a^x \int_y^d (x-t)^{\alpha-1} (s-y)^{\beta-1} f(t, s) ds dt, \quad x > a, y < d,$$

$$J_{b-,c+}^{\alpha,\beta} f(x, y) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} \int_x^b \int_c^y (t-x)^{\alpha-1} (y-s)^{\beta-1} f(t, s) ds dt, \quad x < b, y > c,$$

and

$$J_{b-,d-}^{\alpha,\beta} f(x, y) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} \int_x^b \int_y^d (t-x)^{\alpha-1} (s-y)^{\beta-1} f(t, s) ds dt, \quad x < b, y < d.$$

Finally, the concept of co-ordinates convex, which will be used in this article, will be mentioned. A formal definition for co-ordinated convex function may be stated as follows:

Definition 3. A function $f: \Delta \rightarrow R$ will be called co-ordinated convex on Δ , for all $t, s \in [0, 1]$ and $(x, y), (u, v) \in \Delta$, if the following inequality holds:

$$\begin{aligned} & f(tx + (1-t)y, su + (1-s)v) \\ & \leq tsf(x, u) + s(1-t)f(y, u) + t(1-s)f(x, v) + (1-t)(1-s)f(y, v). \end{aligned}$$

Clearly, every convex function is co-ordinated convex. Furthermore, there exist co-ordinated convex function which is not convex, (see, [2]).

Following the presentation of the basic definitions and notions utilized throughout this work, the next step is to discuss the main studies in the literature concerning these topics. In the referenced works [3]-[5], Dragomir employed identities involving the sum of the right- and left-sided Riemann-Liouville

fractional integrals to establish a number of Ostrowski-type inequalities for functions belonging to different Lebesgue norm spaces, including those of bounded variation, Hölder continuous, Lipschitz, and absolutely continuous functions. Hermite-Hadamard inequality and Ostrowski inequality for fractional integrals of two variable functions are obtained in [13] and [19], respectively. Recently, Erden et al. [8] provided some Ostrowski type inequalities including Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals for functions in class of functions L_p, L_∞ and L_1 , respectively. Also, Erden et al. [9] established new double fractional inequalities of Ostrowski type for functions of bounded variation with two variables.

In addition to these foundational works, a wide range of research has focused on inequalities concerning functions that are convex on the coordinates or that involve Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals. For several recent results concerning Hermite-Hadamard's inequality for some convex function on the co-ordinates on a rectangle from the plane R^2 , we refer the reader to ([7], [10], [14], [17], [18], [21]-[25]). There are also several papers on fractional Ostrowski type inequalities for one or two variable functions, you can find some of them in the references ([1], [6], [9], [12], [15], [20], [26]).

In the introduction, we review the fundamental definitions of the fractional integral operators under consideration, along with the notion of coordinated convexity, which form the basis of our analysis. The structure of the paper is as follows: Section 2 presents our main results. By applying a key fractional integral identity established in a previous work [8], we derive several new Ostrowski type inequalities including the definitions of Riemann-Liouville fractional integral for co-ordinated convex functions. In addition, a midpoint-type formulation of the main result is presented as a corollary.

2. Double Integral Inequalities Involving Riemann-Liouville Fractional Integrals

The identity to be used in constructing this section is given below. This identity, which was previously employed by Erdem et al. in [8], will be utilized here to derive integral inequalities for co-ordinated convex functions.

Lemma 1.[8] Let $f : \Delta =: [a, b] \times [c, d] \rightarrow R$ be an absolutely continuous function such that the partial derivative of order 2 exists and is continuous on Δ in R^2 . Then, for any $(x, y) \in \Delta$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} \int_a^b \int_c^d \Omega(t, s) \left[\int_x^t \int_y^s \frac{\partial^2 f(\zeta, \tau)}{\partial \zeta \partial \tau} d\tau d\zeta \right] ds dt \\ & = J_{x^+, y^+}^{\alpha, \beta} f(b, d) + J_{x^+, y^-}^{\alpha, \beta} f(b, c) + J_{x^-, y^+}^{\alpha, \beta} f(a, d) + J_{x^-, y^-}^{\alpha, \beta} f(a, c) \\ & \quad - \frac{(y-c)^\beta + (d-y)^\beta}{\Gamma(\beta+1)} [J_{x^+}^\alpha f(b, y) + J_{x^-}^\alpha f(a, y)] \\ & \quad - \frac{(x-a)^\alpha + (b-x)^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} [J_{y^+}^\beta f(x, d) + J_{y^-}^\beta f(x, c)] \\ & \quad + \frac{(x-a)^\alpha + (b-x)^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha+1)} \frac{(y-c)^\beta + (d-y)^\beta}{\Gamma(\beta+1)} f(x, y) \\ & =: G_2(x, y; a, b, c, d) \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where $\Omega(t, s)$ is defined by

$$\Omega(t, s) := \begin{cases} (t-a)^{\alpha-1}(s-c)^{\beta-1}, & a \leq t < x \text{ and } c \leq s < y \\ (t-a)^{\alpha-1}(d-s)^{\beta-1}, & a \leq t < x \text{ and } y \leq s \leq d \\ (b-t)^{\alpha-1}(s-c)^{\beta-1}, & x \leq t \leq b \text{ and } c \leq s < y \\ (b-t)^{\alpha-1}(d-s)^{\beta-1}, & x \leq t \leq b \text{ and } y \leq s \leq d. \end{cases}$$

By employing the above identity, we derive several double integral inequalities in the framework of Riemann-Liouville fractional operators for functions whose powers are convex on the coordinates.

Theorem 1. Let $f: \Delta \rightarrow R$ be an absolutely continuous function such that the partial derivative of order 2 exists and is continuous for all $(t, s) \in \Delta$ in R^2 . If $\left| \frac{\partial^2 f(\zeta, \tau)}{\partial \zeta \partial \tau} \right|^q$ is a co-ordinated convex function on Δ for $p, q > 1$ with $\frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$, then we have the Riemann-Liouville fractional inequality

$$\begin{aligned} & |G_2(x, y; a, b, c, d)| \tag{2} \\ & \leq \frac{\Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)\Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)}{4^{\frac{1}{q}}\Gamma\left(\alpha + 1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)\Gamma\left(\beta + 1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)} \\ & \times \left\{ (x-a)^{\alpha+1}(y-c)^{\beta+1} \left[|f_{\zeta\tau}(a, c)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(a, y)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, c)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, y)|^q \right]^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\ & + (x-a)^{\alpha+1}(d-y)^{\beta+1} \left[|f_{\zeta\tau}(a, y)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(a, d)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, y)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, d)|^q \right]^{\frac{1}{q}} \\ & + (b-x)^{\alpha+1}(y-c)^{\beta+1} \left[|f_{\zeta\tau}(x, c)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, y)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(b, c)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(b, y)|^q \right]^{\frac{1}{q}} \\ & \left. + (b-x)^{\alpha+1}(d-y)^{\beta+1} \left[|f_{\zeta\tau}(x, y)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, d)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(b, y)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(b, d)|^q \right]^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \end{aligned}$$

for all $(x, y) \in \Delta$ and $\alpha, \beta > 0$.

Proof. Taking absolute value of both sides of the equality (1), because of the definition of $\Omega(t, s)$, it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} & |G_2(x, y; a, b, c, d)| \tag{3} \\ & \leq \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} \int_a^x \int_c^y (t-a)^{\alpha-1}(s-c)^{\beta-1} \left| \int_x^t \int_y^s \frac{\partial^2 f(\zeta, \tau)}{\partial \zeta \partial \tau} d\tau d\zeta \right| ds dt \\ & + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} \int_a^x \int_y^d (t-a)^{\alpha-1}(d-s)^{\beta-1} \left| \int_x^t \int_y^s \frac{\partial^2 f(\zeta, \tau)}{\partial \zeta \partial \tau} d\tau d\zeta \right| ds dt \\ & + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} \int_x^b \int_c^y (b-t)^{\alpha-1}(s-c)^{\beta-1} \left| \int_x^t \int_y^s \frac{\partial^2 f(\zeta, \tau)}{\partial \zeta \partial \tau} d\tau d\zeta \right| ds dt \\ & + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} \int_x^b \int_y^d (b-t)^{\alpha-1}(d-s)^{\beta-1} \left| \int_x^t \int_y^s \frac{\partial^2 f(\zeta, \tau)}{\partial \zeta \partial \tau} d\tau d\zeta \right| ds dt. \end{aligned}$$

Since $|f_{ts}(t, s)|^q$ is a convex function on the co-ordinates on $(\zeta, \tau) \in [a, x] \times [c, y]$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left| f_{\zeta\tau} \left(\frac{x-\zeta}{x-a}a + \frac{\zeta-a}{x-a}x, \frac{y-\tau}{y-c}c + \frac{\tau-c}{y-c}y \right) \right|^q \\
& \leq \frac{(x-\zeta)(y-\tau)}{(x-a)(y-c)} |f_{\zeta\tau}(a,c)|^q + \frac{(x-\zeta)(\tau-c)}{(x-a)(y-c)} |f_{\zeta\tau}(a,y)|^q \\
& + \frac{(\zeta-a)(y-\tau)}{(x-a)(y-c)} |f_{\zeta\tau}(x,c)| + \frac{(\zeta-a)(\tau-c)}{(x-a)(y-c)} |f_{\zeta\tau}(x,y)|.
\end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

By employing the above inequality (4), which was obtained for a function whose absolute value of the partial derivatives is convex on the coordinates, together with the use of Hölder's inequality, it is clear that

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left| \int_x^t \int_y^s \frac{\partial^2 f(\zeta, \tau)}{\partial \zeta \partial \tau} d\tau d\zeta \right| \leq \int_x^t \int_y^s \left| \frac{\partial^2 f(\zeta, \tau)}{\partial \zeta \partial \tau} \right| d\tau d\zeta \\
& \leq \left(\int_t^x \int_s^y d\tau d\zeta \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\int_x^t \int_y^s \left| \frac{\partial^2 f(\zeta, \tau)}{\partial \zeta \partial \tau} \right|^q d\tau d\zeta \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
& \leq (x-t)^{\frac{1}{p}}(y-s)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\int_a^x \int_c^y \left| \frac{\partial^2 f(\zeta, \tau)}{\partial \zeta \partial \tau} \right|^q d\tau d\zeta \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
& \leq (x-t)^{\frac{1}{p}}(y-s)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\frac{(x-a)(y-c)}{4} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
& \times \left[|f_{\zeta\tau}(a,c)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(a,y)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x,c)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x,y)|^q \right]^{\frac{1}{q}}.
\end{aligned}$$

Then, it is clear that

$$\begin{aligned}
& \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} \int_a^x \int_c^y (t-a)^{\alpha-1}(s-c)^{\beta-1} \left| \int_x^t \int_y^s \frac{\partial^2 f(\zeta, \tau)}{\partial \zeta \partial \tau} d\tau d\zeta \right| ds dt \\
& \leq \frac{\left[|f_{\zeta\tau}(a,c)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(a,y)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x,c)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x,y)|^q \right]^{\frac{1}{q}}}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} \\
& \times \left(\frac{(x-a)(y-c)}{4} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \int_a^x \int_c^y (t-a)^{\alpha-1}(s-c)^{\beta-1}(x-t)^{\frac{1}{p}}(y-s)^{\frac{1}{p}} ds dt \\
& = \frac{\left[|f_{\zeta\tau}(a,c)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(a,y)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x,c)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x,y)|^q \right]^{\frac{1}{q}}}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} \left(\frac{(x-a)(y-c)}{4} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \\
& \times \int_a^x (t-a)^{\alpha-1}(x-t)^{\frac{1}{p}} dt \int_c^y (s-c)^{\beta-1}(y-s)^{\frac{1}{p}} ds
\end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

To complete the proof, we must calculate two integrals in the right side of the result (5). Applying the change of the variable $\frac{t-a}{x-a} = u$ and $dt = (x-a)du$ for the first integral, it is found that

$$\begin{aligned}
& \int_a^x (t-a)^{\alpha-1}(x-t)^{\frac{1}{p}} dt \\
& = \int_a^x (t-a)^{\alpha-1}(x-a-(t-a))^{\frac{1}{p}} dt \\
& = (x-a)^{\alpha+\frac{1}{p}} \int_0^1 u^{\alpha-1}(1-u)^{\frac{1}{p}} du
\end{aligned}$$

$$= (x - a)^{\alpha + \frac{1}{p}} B\left(\alpha, 1 + \frac{1}{p}\right).$$

And similarly, we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_c^y (s - c)^{\beta - 1} (y - s)^{\frac{1}{p}} ds \\ &= (y - c)^{\beta + \frac{1}{p}} B\left(\beta, 1 + \frac{1}{p}\right) \end{aligned}$$

Then, we possess

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} \int_a^x \int_c^y (t - a)^{\alpha - 1} (s - c)^{\beta - 1} \left| \int_x^t \int_y^s \frac{\partial^2 f(\zeta, \tau)}{\partial \zeta \partial \tau} d\tau d\zeta \right| ds dt \\ & \leq \frac{(x - a)^{\alpha + \frac{1}{p}} (y - c)^{\beta + \frac{1}{p}} B\left(\alpha, 1 + \frac{1}{p}\right) B\left(\beta, 1 + \frac{1}{p}\right) \left(\frac{(x - a)(y - c)}{4}\right)^{\frac{1}{q}}}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} \\ & \times \left[|f_{\zeta\tau}(a, c)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(a, y)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, c)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, y)|^q \right]^{\frac{1}{q}} \\ & = \frac{\Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)\Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)}{4^{\frac{1}{q}}\Gamma\left(\alpha + 1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)\Gamma\left(\beta + 1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)} (x - a)^{\alpha + 1} (y - c)^{\beta + 1} \\ & \times \left[|f_{\zeta\tau}(a, c)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(a, y)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, c)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, y)|^q \right]^{\frac{1}{q}} \end{aligned}$$

Similarly, applying the change of the variable $\frac{b-t}{b-x} = v$ and $dt = (x - b)dv$ for calculating the other integrals in the right hand side of the inequality (3), it is found that

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_x^b (b - t)^{\alpha - 1} (t - x)^{\frac{1}{p}} dt \\ &= \int_x^b (b - t)^{\alpha - 1} (b - x - (b - t))^{\frac{1}{p}} dt \\ &= (b - x)^{\alpha + \frac{1}{p}} B\left(\alpha, 1 + \frac{1}{p}\right). \end{aligned}$$

,and one has

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_y^d (d - s)^{\beta - 1} (s - y)^{\frac{1}{p}} ds \\ &= (d - y)^{\beta + \frac{1}{p}} B\left(\beta, 1 + \frac{1}{p}\right) \end{aligned}$$

Then, since $|f_{ts}(t, s)|^q$ is a convex function on the co-ordinates on $(\zeta, \tau) \in [a, x] \times [y, d]$, one has

$$\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} \int_a^x \int_y^d (x - t)^{\alpha - 1} (s - y)^{\beta - 1} \left| \int_x^t \int_y^s \frac{\partial^2 f(\zeta, \tau)}{\partial \zeta \partial \tau} d\tau d\zeta \right| ds dt$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\leq \frac{\Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)\Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)}{4^{\frac{1}{q}}\Gamma\left(\alpha + 1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)\Gamma\left(\beta + 1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)}(x - a)^{\alpha+1}(d - y)^{\beta+1} \\ &\times \left[|f_{\zeta\tau}(a, y)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(a, d)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, y)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, d)|^q\right]^{\frac{1}{q}} \end{aligned}$$

Since $|f_{ts}(t, s)|^q$ is a convex function on the co-ordinates on $(\zeta, \tau) \in [x, b] \times [c, y]$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} \int_x^b \int_c^y (t - x)^{\alpha-1}(y - s)^{\beta-1} \left| \int_x^t \int_y^s \frac{\partial^2 f(\zeta, \tau)}{\partial \zeta \partial \tau} d\tau d\zeta \right| ds dt \\ &\leq \frac{\Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)\Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)}{4^{\frac{1}{q}}\Gamma\left(\alpha + 1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)\Gamma\left(\beta + 1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)}(b - x)^{\alpha+1}(y - c)^{\beta+1} \\ &\times \left[|f_{\zeta\tau}(x, c)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, y)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(b, c)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(b, y)|^q\right]^{\frac{1}{q}}, \end{aligned}$$

and since $|f_{ts}(t, s)|^q$ is a convex function on the co-ordinates on $(\zeta, \tau) \in [x, b] \times [y, d]$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)\Gamma(\beta)} \int_x^b \int_y^d (t - x)^{\alpha-1}(s - y)^{\beta-1} \left| \int_x^t \int_y^s \frac{\partial^2 f(\zeta, \tau)}{\partial \zeta \partial \tau} d\tau d\zeta \right| ds dt \\ &\leq \frac{\Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)\Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)}{4^{\frac{1}{q}}\Gamma\left(\alpha + 1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)\Gamma\left(\beta + 1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)}(b - x)^{\alpha+1}(d - y)^{\beta+1} \\ &\times \left[|f_{\zeta\tau}(x, y)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, d)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(b, y)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(b, d)|^q\right]^{\frac{1}{q}}. \end{aligned}$$

If the above four results are substituted in right hand side of (3) inequality, the desired inequality (2) can be attained.

Corollary 1. If we choose $x = \frac{a+b}{2}$ and $y = \frac{c+d}{2}$ in (3), then we have the Midpoint type inequality

$$\begin{aligned} &\left| J_{\frac{a+b}{2}^+, \frac{c+d}{2}^+}^{\alpha, \beta} f(b, d) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}^+, \frac{c+d}{2}^-}^{\alpha, \beta} f(b, c) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}^-, \frac{c+d}{2}^+}^{\alpha, \beta} f(a, d) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}^-, \frac{c+d}{2}^-}^{\alpha, \beta} f(a, c) \right. \\ &- \frac{(d - c)^\beta}{2^{\beta-1}\Gamma(\beta + 1)} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}^+}^\alpha f\left(b, \frac{c+d}{2}\right) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}^-}^\alpha f\left(a, \frac{c+d}{2}\right) \right] \\ &- \frac{(b - a)^\alpha}{2^{\alpha-1}\Gamma(\alpha + 1)} \left[J_{\frac{c+d}{2}^+}^\beta f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}, d\right) + J_{\frac{c+d}{2}^-}^\beta f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}, c\right) \right] \\ &+ \frac{(b - a)^\alpha (d - c)^\beta}{2^{\alpha+\beta-2}\Gamma(\alpha + 1)\Gamma(\beta + 1)} f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}, \frac{c+d}{2}\right) \Big| \\ &\leq \frac{(b - a)^{\alpha+1}(d - c)^{\beta+1}\Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)\Gamma\left(1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)}{2^{\alpha+\beta+2+\frac{2}{q}}\Gamma\left(\alpha + 1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)\Gamma\left(\beta + 1 + \frac{1}{p}\right)} \\ &\times \left\{ \left[|f_{\zeta\tau}(a, c)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(a, y)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, c)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, y)|^q\right]^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\ &\left. + \left[|f_{\zeta\tau}(a, y)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(a, d)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, y)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, d)|^q\right]^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \end{aligned}$$

$$+ \left[|f_{\zeta\tau}(x, c)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, y)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(b, c)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(b, y)|^q \right]^{\frac{1}{q}} \\ + \left[|f_{\zeta\tau}(x, y)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(x, d)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(b, y)|^q + |f_{\zeta\tau}(b, d)|^q \right]^{\frac{1}{q}} \Big\}$$

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Solution of Fractional Derivative Homogeneous and Non-Homogeneous Parabolic Problems using the Fourier Method

Şöhret Turhan¹, İrem Bağlan¹

¹*Department of Mathematics, Kocaeli University, Kocaeli, TR-41380, Turkey*

Corresponding author: isakinc@kocaeli.edu.tr

ORCID IDs:

First Author: [0009-0008-5438-2709](https://orcid.org/0009-0008-5438-2709)

Second Author: [0000-0003-4900-6027](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4900-6027)

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Abstract

In this paper, the solutions of homogeneous and non-homogeneous parabolic equations with periodic boundary conditions are investigated using the Fourier method. In the solution process, the Sturm–Liouville equation is solved under periodic boundary conditions to determine the eigenvalues and corresponding eigenfunctions. Caputo fractional derivatives are employed, and the analytical solutions involve the Gamma and Beta functions, while the fractional-order solutions are expressed in terms of the Mittag–Leffler function. The results demonstrate that the Fourier method provides an effective analytical framework for solving fractional derivative semilinear pseudo-parabolic equations with periodic boundary conditions.

Keywords: Fourier method, fractional derivative, periodic boundary conditions.

1. Introduction

Fractional differential equations are equations in which derivatives and integrals are not limited to integer orders but can also take real or complex values [1–10]. The origins of this field date back to ancient times, and the concept of fractional derivatives has long attracted the attention of mathematicians. Many prominent mathematicians have contributed to its development. Early studies were conducted by Leibniz and L'Hôpital (1695), Bernoulli (1697), Euler (1730), and Lagrange (1772). In the following years, numerous researchers such as Laplace (1812), Fourier (1822), Abel (1823), Liouville (1832), Riemann (1847), Grünwald (1867), Letnikov (1868), Hadamard (1892), Heaviside (1892), Weyl (1917), Zygmund (1945), J. L. Lions (1959), and Liverman (1964) further advanced the theory of fractional derivatives and integrals.

Fractional-order partial differential equations (PDEs) are used in many branches of science, including applied mathematics, physics, chemistry, and engineering. They have become a powerful mathematical tool for modeling complex processes and systems in these disciplines. These equations can provide more realistic models in cases where classical derivatives are insufficient. Fractional derivatives are history-dependent because they take into account not only the current state but also past

events. They reflect effects accumulated over time, making them particularly suitable for systems with memory. These properties have led to increasing interest in fractional derivatives in recent years.

Various definitions have been proposed for fractional derivatives. The Caputo and Riemann–Liouville definitions, which include integral-based expressions involving the Gamma function, are particularly prominent. Among these definitions, the Caputo derivative has become one of the most widely used in the literature due to its advantages. Because it allows initial conditions to be defined in the classical sense, the Caputo derivative yields more meaningful and applicable solutions when modeling physical processes. In this context, models incorporating the Caputo derivative produce results that are more consistent, applicable, and physically realistic compared to other fractional derivative definitions. Numerous studies supporting this view can be found in the literature [11–27].

2. General Information

2.1 The Gamma Function (Γ)

The gamma function is a special function used in fractional-order integral and derivative calculations.

Definition 2.1 The first definition was given by Gauss:

$$\Gamma(z) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{n!n^z}{z(z+1)(z+2)\dots(z+n)}, \operatorname{Re}(z) > 0. \quad (1)$$

With this limit definition, Gamma (Γ) can be calculated for all values of z except for zero and negative integers [28].

Definition 2.2 The gamma function was also defined by Leonhard Euler in 1729, based on an integral transform. Euler’s definition was developed to generalize the factorial of natural numbers. The definition commonly used today is:

$$\Gamma(z) = \int_0^{\infty} e^{-t} t^{z-1} dt, \operatorname{Re}z > 0. \quad (2)$$

With this definition, the gamma function can be calculated for all values of z [28].

Eq. (2) is valid for integer values of n . Since

$$n! = \int_0^{\infty} e^{-t} t^n dt$$

the gamma function is also referred to as the factorial function.

Some important properties of the gamma function include:

$$1) \Gamma(1) = 1$$

Here, if we use the limit definition made by Gauss,

$$\Gamma(1) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{n!n}{1.2.3\dots n(n+1)} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{n!n}{(n+1)n!} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{n}{n+1} = 1.$$

$$2) \Gamma\left(\frac{1}{2}\right) = \sqrt{\pi} \quad [28].$$

$$3) \Gamma(z + 1) = z \cdot \Gamma(z), z \in \mathbb{Z}$$

$$\Gamma(2) = \Gamma(1) = 1!$$

$$\Gamma(3) = 2\Gamma(2) = 2!$$

$$\Gamma(4) = 3\Gamma(3) = 3!$$

$$\Gamma(n + 1) = n \cdot \Gamma(n) = n \cdot (n - 1)! = n!$$

2.2 The Beta Function

The Gamma function, defined by Euler, forms the basis of many special functions. One of these is the Beta function. The Beta function is directly related to the Gamma function and is often used to simplify certain combinations of Gamma functions. It is also called the Euler integral of the first kind and is defined as follows:

$$B(z, \omega) = \int_0^1 \tau^{z-1} (1 - \tau)^{\omega-1} d\tau, \operatorname{Re}(z) > 0, \operatorname{Re}(\omega) > 0 \quad (3)$$

The Beta function can also be expressed in terms of the Gamma function as

$$B(z, \omega) = \frac{\Gamma(z)\Gamma(\omega)}{\Gamma(z + \omega)}$$

and it satisfies the symmetry property [28]

$$B(z, \omega) = B(\omega, z).$$

2.3 Mittag-Leffler Function (E)

Fractional differential equations are generally much more complex to solve than classical equations. A special function frequently used in the solution of such equations is the Mittag-Leffler function, named after Magnus Gustaf (Gösta) Mittag-Leffler. This function is a generalization of the exponential function for fractional differential equations and is particularly important in expressing solutions to initial value problems

$$E_{\alpha, \beta}(z) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{\Gamma(\alpha k + \beta)}, \alpha > 0, \beta > 0. \quad (4)$$

When $\beta=1$ it is called a single parameter Mittag-Leffler function. It is shown as

$$E_{\alpha}(z) = E_{\alpha, 1}(z),$$

$$E_{\alpha}(t) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{t^k}{\Gamma(1 + \alpha k)}$$

single parameter Mittag-Leffler function

$$E_{\alpha, \beta}(t) = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{\Gamma(\alpha k + \beta)}, \alpha > 0$$

Two-parameter Mittag-Leffler function. When $\alpha=1, \beta=1$ is accepted, it reduces to the classical exponential function e^z . Therefore, Mittag-Leffler functions assume the role of the exponential function in fractional differential equations.

This series converges for all values of z when α, β are real and positive.

$$E_{\alpha,\alpha}(0) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)},$$

$$E_{1,1}(z) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{\Gamma(k+1)} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{k!} = e^z,$$

$$E_{1,2}(z) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{\Gamma(k+2)} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{(k+1)!} = \frac{1}{z} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^{k+1}}{(k+1)!} = \frac{e^z - 1}{z},$$

$$E_{1,3}(z) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{\Gamma(k+3)} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{(k+2)!} = \frac{1}{z^2} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^{k+2}}{(k+2)!} = \frac{e^z - 1 - z}{z^2},$$

$$E_{2,1}(z^2) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^{2k}}{\Gamma(2k+1)} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^{2k+1}}{(2k)!} = \cosh(z),$$

$$E_{2,2}(z^2) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^{2k}}{\Gamma(2k+2)} = \frac{1}{z} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^{2k+1}}{(2k+1)!} = \frac{\sinh(z)}{z}$$

Mittag–Lefler is a special expansion of the function [28].

2.4 Riemann-Liouville Fractional Derivative

Let f be a continuous and integrable function on the interval (a,t) , the Reiman-Liouville fractional derivative of f of order α for $t > a$ such that $n \in \mathbb{N}$, $n - 1 \leq \alpha < n$ R-L Fractional derivative

$${}^R D_t^\alpha f(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-\alpha)} \cdot \frac{d^n}{dt^n} \int_a^t (t-\tau)^{n-\alpha-1} f(\tau) d\tau \quad (5)$$

2.5 Riemann-Liouville Fractional Integral

$${}^R D_t^\alpha f(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_a^t (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} f(\tau) d\tau \quad (6)$$

2.6 Caputo Fractional Derivative

The Caputo fractional derivative of order α is defined as:

$$D_t^\alpha f(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-\alpha)} \int_a^t \frac{f^{(n)}(\tau)}{(t-\tau)^{\alpha+1-n}} d\tau, \quad n - 1 < \alpha < n \quad (7)$$

The Caputo derivative can be considered a counterpart to the Riemann–Liouville (R-L) fractional derivative. The main difference between the R-L derivative and the Caputo derivative is the order in which the derivatives are taken: in the R-L derivative, the fractional derivative is applied first, followed by the integer-order derivative; in the Caputo derivative, the integer-order derivative is taken first, followed by the fractional derivative.

The Riemann–Liouville fractional derivative is not always suitable for applied problems because the initial conditions are tied to fractional integral limits, which cannot be directly interpreted in a classical sense.

The derivative of the constant in the R-L derivative is

$${}^R D_t^\alpha(c) = \frac{c \cdot t^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)}.$$

The derivative of the constant in the Caputo derivative is zero [28].

2.7 Fourier Series

$$f(x) = \frac{a_0}{2} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (a_n \cos nx + b_n \sin nx) \quad (8)$$

The function series $f(x)$ with a period of 2π is called a Fourier Series. The coefficients a_0, a_n and b_n are called the Fourier coefficients. There are certain properties that a function must possess to be expanded into a Fourier series. The Fourier series must be uniformly convergent [30].

Definition 2.3 (Piecewise Continuity). A function is called a piecewise continuous function if it is continuous at all points except a finite number of points in the interval $[a, b]$ where it is defined [30].

Theorem 2.1 (Dirichlet's Theorem). If $f(x)$ and its derivatives are piecewise continuous on the interval $[-\pi, \pi]$, then the Fourier series of $f(x)$ satisfies the following properties [30]:

1. At continuous points, the Fourier series converges to $f(x)$.
2. At discontinuity points, it converges to the average of the right and left limits:

$$\frac{f(x^+) + f(x^-)}{2}.$$

3. At the extreme points, it is equal to the average value of the right and left limits:

$$\frac{f(-\pi^+) + f(\pi^-)}{2}.$$

To find the Fourier coefficient a_0 over the interval $[-\pi, \pi]$, integrate both sides of Eq. (8) with respect to x from $-\pi$ to π :

$$\int_{-\pi}^{\pi} f(x) dx = \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \frac{a_0}{2} dx + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (a_n \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \cos nx dx + b_n \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \sin nx dx).$$

Since for all $n \geq 1$:

$$\int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \cos nx dx = 0, \quad \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \sin nx dx = 0.$$

all terms in the summation vanish. This leaves:

$$\int_{-\pi}^{\pi} f(x) dx = \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \frac{a_0}{2} dx = a_0 \pi.$$

Hence, the coefficient a_0 is:

$$a_0 = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} f(x) dx. \quad (9)$$

To find the Fourier coefficient a_n , multiply both sides of Eq. (8) by $\cos(kx)$ and integrate over the interval $[-\pi, \pi]$:

$$\int_{-\pi}^{\pi} f(x) \cos kx dx = \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \frac{a_0}{2} \cos kx dx + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (a_n \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \cos nx \cos kx dx + b_n \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \sin nx \cos kx dx),$$

$$\int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \sin nx \cos kx dx = 0, \quad \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \cos kx dx = 0, \quad \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \cos nx \cos kx dx = \begin{cases} 0, & k \neq n \\ \pi, & k = n. \end{cases}$$

Finally, the Fourier coefficient a_n is given by:

$$a_n = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} f(x) \cos nx dx. \quad (10)$$

To find the Fourier coefficient b_n , multiply both sides of Eq. (8) by $\sin(kx)$ and integrate over the interval $[-\pi, \pi]$:

$$\int_{-\pi}^{\pi} f(x) \sin kx dx = \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \frac{a_0}{2} \sin kx dx + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (a_n \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \cos nx \sin kx dx + b_n \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \sin nx \sin kx dx),$$

$$\int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \cos nx \sin kx dx = 0, \quad \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \sin kx dx = 0, \quad \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \sin nx \sin kx dx = \begin{cases} 0, & k \neq n \\ \pi, & k = n. \end{cases}$$

Finally, the Fourier coefficient b_n is given by:

$$b_n = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} f(x) \sin nx dx. \quad (11)$$

The coefficients given in Eqs. (9), (10), and (11) are called the Fourier series coefficients of Eq. (8) [30].

2.8 Sturm-Liouville Problem

The Sturm-Liouville equation is a second-order real linear differential equation. All its coefficients are continuous on the closed and finite interval $[a, b]$, and the derivative of $p(x)$ is also continuous.

If a function y is continuously differentiable on the interval (a, b) and satisfies Eq. (12) at every point, then y is a solution of this equation.

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left(p(x) \frac{dy}{dx} \right) + q(x)y = \lambda r(x)y, \quad (x) > 0, r(x) \geq 0. \quad (12)$$

The functions $p(x), q(x), r(x)$ are continuous in the interval $[a, b]$. Furthermore, the following boundary conditions are given.

$$a_1 y(a) + a_2 p(a) y'(a) = 0,$$

$$b_1 y(b) + b_2 p(b) y'(b) = 0. \quad (13)$$

The conditions $a_1^2 + a_2^2 \neq 0$ and $b_1^2 + b_2^2 \neq 0$ are met. The problem defined by Eqs. (12) and (13) is called a Sturm-Liouville problem. The nonzero solutions of this problem are called eigenvalues (λ), and the functions corresponding to these eigenvalues are called eigenfunctions [31].

2.9 Boundary Conditions

Consider the boundary conditions:

$$y(a) = y(b), y'(a) = y'(b)$$

If the Sturm-Liouville problem is defined with these conditions, it is called a periodic boundary condition Sturm-Liouville problem [31].

Let us solve the Sturm-Liouville problem under periodic boundary conditions and determine its eigenvalues and eigenfunctions. Consider the differential equation:

$$x'' + \lambda x = 0, x(0) = x(l), x'(0) = x'(l). \quad (14)$$

Problem (14) is a second-order differential equation with constant coefficients. To solve it, we first find the eigenvalues λ from the characteristic equation.

We will examine the three possible cases for the eigenvalue λ : when $\lambda < 0$, $\lambda = 0$, and $\lambda > 0$.

i) $\lambda < 0, \lambda = -m^2$.

$$k^2 + \lambda = 0, k^2 = m^2, \quad k = \mp m,$$

$$X(x) = Ae^{mx} + Be^{-mx} \quad (15)$$

Eq. (15) is the eigenfunction. When boundary conditions are applied to find the coefficients in the eigenfunction, $A = 0, B = 0$ is found. $X = 0$ is the obvious solution.

ii) $\lambda=0$,

$$X'' = 0, \quad X' = a_0 \quad X = a_0x + b_0.$$

When the boundary conditions are applied to the eigenfunction, we find $a_0 = 0, b_0 = 0$. $X = 0$ is the obvious solution.

iii) $\lambda > 0, \lambda = m^2$,

$$k^2 + \lambda = 0, \quad k^2 = -m^2, \quad k = \mp mi$$

$$X(x) = A_n \cos mx + B_n \sin mx.$$

The derivative of the eigenfunction is given by:

$$X'(x) = -mA_n \sin mx + mB_n \cos mx.$$

Periodic boundary conditions, as given in Eq. (14), are applied, we obtain

$$A_n = A_n \cos m\pi + B_n \sin m\pi,$$

$$B_n = -A_n \sin m\pi + B_n \cos m\pi,$$

$$A_n(1 - \cos m\pi) - B_n \sin m\pi = 0,$$

$$A_n \sin m\pi + B_n(1 - \cos m\pi) = 0.$$

For the solution of the system to be linearly independent, the coefficient determinant A_n, B_n must be zero.

$$\begin{vmatrix} 1 - \cos m\pi & -\sin m\pi \\ \sin m\pi & 1 - \cos m\pi \end{vmatrix} = 0.$$

$$(1 - \cos m\pi)^2 + (\sin m\pi)^2 = 0,$$

$$1 - 2\cos m\pi + \cos^2 m\pi + \sin^2 m\pi = 0,$$

$$\cos m\pi = 1, m\pi = 2k\pi, m = 2k.$$

The eigenvalues are:

$$\lambda_n = (2k)^2.$$

The corresponding eigenfunctions are:

$$X = A_n \cos 2kx + B_n \sin 2kx.$$

That is, the two linearly independent functions corresponding to this eigenvalue are:

$$\lambda_k = \cos 2kx,$$

$$\lambda_k = \sin 2kx.$$

3. Fourier Method for Fractional Differential Parabolic Equation

3.1 Solution of Fractional Differential Homogeneous Parabolic Equation by Fourier Method

$$D_t^\alpha(U(x, t)) = U_{xx}, \quad x > 0, \quad 0 < \alpha < 1 \quad (16)$$

$$U(0, t) = U(\pi, t), \quad U_x(0, t) = U_x(\pi, t), \quad 0 \leq t \leq T \quad (17)$$

$$U(x, 0) = \varphi(x), \quad 0 \leq x \leq \pi. \quad (18)$$

The solution to the problem in the equation can be written as follows using Sturm-Liouville. The solution depends on the variables x and t . Therefore;

$$U(x, t; \alpha) = X(x)T(t; \alpha), \quad (19)$$

$$U_{xx} = X''T(t, \alpha),$$

$$D_t^\alpha(U(x, t; \alpha)) = XD_t^\alpha(T(t; \alpha)),$$

$$XD_t^\alpha(T(t; \alpha)) = X''T(t; \alpha),$$

$$\frac{D_t^\alpha(T(t; \alpha))}{T(t; \alpha)} = \frac{X''}{X} = -\lambda.$$

When the boundary conditions given in (17) are applied to the last equation, the following Sturm-Liouville problem is obtained.

$$X''(x) + \lambda X(x) = 0, \quad (20)$$

$$X'(0) = X'(\pi), \quad (21)$$

$$\frac{D_t^\alpha(T(t; \alpha))}{T(t; \alpha)} = -\lambda.$$

Let's solve the Sturm-Liouville problem (20) that we obtained using the boundary conditions (21). Since problem (20) is a second-order differential equation with constant coefficients, we examine the different cases of λ from the characteristic equation to find its eigenvalues.

i) $\lambda < 0$,

$$k^2 + \lambda = 0, k^2 = m^2, k = \mp m$$

$$X(x) = Ae^{mx} + Be^{-m} . \quad (22)$$

Eq. (22) is the eigenfunction. When boundary conditions are applied to find the coefficients in the eigenfunction $A = 0, B = 0, X = 0$ is the obvious solution.

ii) $\lambda = 0$,

$$X'' = 0, X' = a_0, X = a_0x + b_0. \quad (23)$$

When the boundary conditions are applied to the eigenfunction, we find $a_0 = 0, b_0 = 0$ is the obvious solution.

iii) $\lambda > 0$,

$$\lambda = m^2 . k^2 + \lambda = 0, k^2 = -m^2, k = \mp mi.$$

$$X(x) = A_n \cos mx + B_n \sin mx.$$

The periodic boundary conditions given in (17) are applied. The eigenvalue is

$$\lambda_k = (2k)^2.$$

There are two linearly independent functions corresponding to this eigenvalue:

$$X = A_n \cos 2kx + B_n \sin 2kx$$

which are the eigenfunctions.

Let's express the eigenvalue λ in the function T :

$$\frac{D_t^\alpha(T(t;\alpha))}{T(t;\alpha)} = -\lambda, 0 < \alpha < 1, \lambda > 0 \text{ [29].}$$

$$T_n(t; \alpha) = C_n E_{\alpha,1}(-(2k)^2 \cdot t^\alpha).$$

Now, combining X_n and T_n , we can write the eigenfunctions in (19).

$$U_n(x, t; \alpha) = (A_n \cos 2kx + B_n \sin 2kx) \cdot C_n \cdot E_{\alpha,1}(-(2k)^2 \cdot t^\alpha)$$

By superposition the sum of the solutions is also the solution.

$$U(x, t) = \frac{U_0(t)}{2} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} [U_{c_k} \cos 2kx + U_{s_k} \sin 2kx] \cdot E_{\alpha,1}(-(2k)^2 \cdot t^\alpha) \quad (24)$$

By substituting the initial condition given in (18) into expression (24), we obtain

$$U(x, 0) = \varphi(x) = \frac{U_0}{2} + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} U_{c_k} \cos 2kx + U_{s_k} \sin 2kx,$$

$$U_0 = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\pi \varphi(x) dx,$$

$$U_{c_k} = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\pi \varphi(x) \cos 2kx \, dx,$$

$$U_{s_k} = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\pi \varphi(x) \sin 2kx \, dx.$$

When expressed in the solution:

$$U(x, t) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^\pi \varphi(x) \, dx + \left[\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\pi \varphi(x) \cos 2kx \, dx \right) \cos 2kx + \left(\frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\pi \varphi(x) \sin 2kx \, dx \right) \sin 2kx \right] E_{\alpha,1}(- (2k)^2 \cdot t^\alpha).$$

The solution of equation (16)-(18) is obtained.

3.2 Solution of Nonhomogeneous Parabolic Equation with Fourier Method

$$D_t^\alpha(U(x, t; \alpha)) - U_{xx} = f(x, t), \quad 0 < \alpha < 1, \quad 0 \leq x \leq \pi, \quad 0 \leq t \leq T \quad (25)$$

$$U(0, t) = U(\pi, t), \quad U_x(0, t) = U_x(\pi, t), \quad (26)$$

$$U(x, 0) = \varphi(x), \quad (27)$$

$$U(x, t; \alpha) = \frac{U_0(t)}{2} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} U_{c_n}(t) \cos 2nx + U_{s_n}(t) \sin 2nx. \quad (28)$$

Now, let us look for a solution in the form of Eq. (28), and express Eq. (28) as Eq. (25).

$$D_t^\alpha \left(\frac{U_0(t)}{2} \right) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [D_t^\alpha(U_{c_n}(t)) + (2n)^2 U_{c_n}(t)] \cos 2nx + [D_t^\alpha(U_{s_n}(t)) + (2n)^2 U_{s_n}(t)] \sin 2nx = f(x, t).$$

The coefficients $U_0(t)$, $U_{c_n}(t)$ and $U_{s_n}(t)$ are obtained using the Fourier transform.

$$D_t^\alpha(U_0(t)) = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\pi f(x, t) \, dx = f_0(t),$$

$$D_t^\alpha(U_0(t)) = f_0(t).$$

Integrate both sides over the interval $[0, t]$.

$$U_0(t) - U_0(0) = \int_0^t f_0(\zeta) \, d\zeta,$$

$$U_0(t) = \varphi_0 + \int_0^t f_0(\zeta) \, d\zeta,$$

$$U_0(t) = \varphi_0 + \frac{\pi}{2} \int_0^t \int_0^\pi f(t, \zeta) \, dt \, d\zeta, \quad (29)$$

$$D_t^\alpha(U_{c_n}(t)) + (2n)^2 U_{c_n}(t) = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\pi f(x, t) \cos 2nxdx = f_{c_n}(t),$$

$$D_t^\alpha(U_{c_n}(t) + (2n)^2 U_{c_n}(t)) = f_{c_n}(t). \quad (30)$$

The problem in Eq. (30) has a homogeneous solution.

$$D_t^\alpha (U_{cn}(t) + (2n)^2 U_{cn}(t)) = 0,$$

$$\frac{D_t^\alpha (U_{cn}(t))}{U_{cn}(t)} = -(2n)^2,$$

$$U_{cn}(t) = C_n(t) E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 t^\alpha), \quad (31)$$

$$D_t^\alpha (C_n(t)) E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 t^\alpha) - (2n)^2 E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 t^\alpha) C_n(t)$$

$$+ (2n)^2 C_n(t) E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 t^\alpha) = f_{cn}(t),$$

$$D_t^\alpha (C_n(t)) E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 t^\alpha) = f_{cn}(t),$$

$$D_t^\alpha (C_n(t)) = f_{cn}(t) (E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 t^\alpha))^{-1},$$

$$C_n(t) = C_n(0) + \int_0^t f_{cn}(\zeta) (E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 \zeta^\alpha))^{-1} d\zeta,$$

$$C_n(t) = \varphi_{cn} + \int_0^t f_{cn}(\zeta) (E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 \zeta^\alpha))^{-1} d\zeta. \quad (32)$$

If Eq. (31) is used in Eq. (32), we have

$$U_{cn}(t) = \left[\varphi_{cn} + \int_0^t f_{cn}(\zeta) (E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 \zeta^\alpha))^{-1} d\zeta \right] E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 t^\alpha).$$

Similarly, the same operations are done for $U_{sn}(t)$.

$$D_t^\alpha (U_{sn}(t)) + (2n)^2 U_{sn}(t) = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\pi f(x, t) \sin 2nx \, dx = f_{sn}(t),$$

$$D_t^\alpha (U_{sn}(t)) + (2n)^2 U_{sn}(t) = f_{sn}(t), \quad (33)$$

Homogeneous solution is found.

$$D_t^\alpha (U_{sn}(t)) + (2n)^2 U_{sn}(t) = 0,$$

$$U_{sn}(t) = S_n(t) E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 t^\alpha). \quad (34)$$

If Eq. (34) is used in Eq. (33), we have

$$D_t^\alpha (S_n(t)) E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 t^\alpha) - (2n)^2 E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 t^\alpha) S_n(t)$$

$$+ (2n)^2 S_n(t) E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 t^\alpha) = f_{sn}(t),$$

$$D_t^\alpha (S_n(t)) E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 t^\alpha) = f_{sn}(t),$$

$$D_t^\alpha (S_n(t)) = f_{sn}(t) (E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 t^\alpha))^{-1}.$$

Integrate both sides over the interval $[0, t]$.

$$S_n(t) = S_n(0) + \int_0^t f_{sn}(\zeta) (E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 \zeta^\alpha))^{-1} d\zeta,$$

$$U_{sn}(t) = \left[\varphi_{sn} + \int_0^t f_{sn}(\zeta) (E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 \zeta^\alpha))^{-1} d\zeta \right] E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 t^\alpha).$$

To determine the coefficients, the boundary condition (26) is applied. The terms ϕ_0 , ϕ_{cn} , and ϕ_{sn} are obtained using the Fourier method.

$$\varphi_0 = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\pi \varphi(x) dx,$$

$$\varphi_{cn} = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\pi \varphi(x) \cos 2nx dx,$$

$$\varphi_{sn} = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\pi \varphi(x) \sin 2nx dx,$$

$$U(x, t) = \frac{U_0(t)}{2} + \sum_0^\infty U_{cn}(t) \cos 2nx + U_{sn}(t) \sin 2nx,$$

$$U(x, t) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\varphi_0 + \int_0^t f_0(t) dt \right) + \sum_{n=1}^\infty \left(\left[\varphi_{cn} + \int_0^t f_{cn}(\zeta) (E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 \zeta^\alpha))^{-1} d\zeta \right] E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 t^\alpha) \right) \cos 2nx + \sum_{n=1}^\infty \left(\left[\varphi_{sn} + \int_0^t f_{sn}(\zeta) (E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 \zeta^\alpha))^{-1} d\zeta \right] E_{\alpha,1}(-(2n)^2 t^\alpha) \right) \sin 2nx.$$

The solution is obtained.

4. Solution of Fractional Derivative Semilinear Pseudo-Parabolic Equations with Periodic Boundary Conditions by the Fourier Method

$$D_t^\alpha (U(x, t; \alpha)) - a^2 U_{xx} - \varepsilon U_{txx} = f(x, t), 0 < \alpha < 1 \quad (35)$$

$$U(0, t) = U(\pi, t), U_x(0, t) = U_x(\pi, t), 0 \leq x \leq \pi, 0 \leq t \leq T \quad (36)$$

$$U(0, x) = \varphi(x), \quad (37)$$

$$U(x, t; \alpha) = X(x)T(t; \alpha). \quad (38)$$

Let us look for a homogeneous solution in the form of

$$D_t^\alpha (T(t; \alpha))X - a^2 X''T - \varepsilon X''D_t^\alpha (T(t; \alpha)) = 0,$$

$$D_t^\alpha (T(t; \alpha))X = X'' \left(a^2 T + \varepsilon D_t^\alpha (T(t; \alpha)) \right),$$

$$\frac{X''}{X} = \frac{D_t^\alpha (T)}{a^2 T + \varepsilon D_t^\alpha (T)} = -\lambda,$$

$$X'' + \lambda X = 0, \quad (39)$$

$$X(0) = X(\pi), X'(0) = X'(\pi),$$

$$D_t^\alpha (T) + \lambda a^2 T + \lambda \varepsilon D_t^\alpha (T) = 0,$$

$$D_t^\alpha (T)(1 + \lambda \varepsilon) = -\lambda a^2 T,$$

$$\frac{D_t^\alpha (T(t; \alpha))}{T(t; \alpha)} = -\frac{\lambda a^2}{1 + \lambda \varepsilon}.$$

Eq. (39) is a Sturm–Liouville problem. Let us determine its eigenvalues and eigenfunctions.

$$X'' + \lambda X = 0$$

i) If $\lambda < 0$, the trivial solution is $X = 0$.

ii) $\lambda = 0, X = a_0, T(t; \alpha) = b_0$.

iii) $\lambda > 0$,

$$X = A \cos mx + B \sin mx,$$

$$\lambda = m^2, \lambda_k = (2k)^2, k = 1, 2, 3, \dots$$

There are two eigenfunctions corresponding to this eigenvalue.

$$X_n = A \cos 2kx + B \sin 2kx \quad (40)$$

$$T_n = E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2k)^2 a^2 t^\alpha}{1+(2k)^2 \varepsilon} \right) \quad (41)$$

By substituting Eqs. (40) and (41) into Eq. (38), we obtain

$$U(x, t, \varepsilon) = a_0 b_0 + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} (A \cos 2kx + B \sin 2kx) E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2ak)^2 t^\alpha}{1+(2k)^2 \varepsilon} \right). \quad (42)$$

By substituting Eq. (42) into Eq. (35), we obtain

$$U(x, t, \varepsilon) = \frac{U_0(t)}{2} + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} (U_{c_k}(t) \cos 2kx + U_{s_k}(t) \sin 2kx).$$

By substituting the last solution into the first equation, we obtain

$$D_t^\alpha \left(\frac{U_0(t)}{2} \right) + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} D_t^\alpha (U_{c_k}(t)) \cos 2kx + D_t^\alpha (U_{s_k}(t)) \sin 2kx + (2ka)^2 \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} U_{c_k} \cos 2kx + U_{s_k} \sin 2kx + \varepsilon (2k)^2 \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} D_t^\alpha (U_{c_k}(t)) \cos 2kx + D_t^\alpha (U_{s_k}(t)) \sin 2kx,$$

$$D_t^\alpha \left(\frac{U_0(t)}{2} \right) + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} ([D_t^\alpha (U_{c_k}) + (2ka)^2 (U_{c_k}) + \varepsilon (2k)^2 (U_{c_k})] \cos 2kx) + ([D_t^\alpha (U_{s_k}) + (2ka)^2 (U_{s_k}) + \varepsilon (2k)^2 D_t^\alpha (U_{s_k})] \sin 2kx) = f(x, t),$$

$$D_t^\alpha \left(\frac{U_0(t)}{2} \right) + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} [(1 + \varepsilon (2k)^2) D_t^\alpha (U_{c_k}) + (2ak)^2 (U_{c_k})] \cos 2kx + [(1 + \varepsilon (2k)^2) D_t^\alpha (U_{s_k}) + (2ak)^2 (U_{s_k})] \sin 2kx = f(x, t),$$

$$D_t^\alpha (U_0(t)) = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\pi f(x, t) dx = f_0(t), \quad (43)$$

$$(1 + \varepsilon (2k)^2) D_t^\alpha (U_{c_k}) + (2ak)^2 (U_{c_k}) = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\pi f(x, t) \cos 2kx dx = f_{c_k}, \quad (44)$$

$$(1 + \varepsilon (2k)^2) D_t^\alpha (U_{s_k}) + (2ak)^2 (U_{s_k}) = \frac{2}{\pi} \int_0^\pi f(x, t) \sin 2kx dx = f_{s_k}. \quad (45)$$

Let us solve Eq. (43).

$$D_t^\alpha(U_0(t)) = f_0(t),$$

$$U_0(t) = U_0(0) + I^\alpha f(t),$$

$$U_0(t) = U_0(0) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^t (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} f(\tau) d\tau,$$

$$U_0(t) = \varphi_0 + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^t (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} f(\tau) d\tau,$$

$$(1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2) D_t^\alpha(U_{c_k}) + (2ak)^2(U_{c_k}) = f_{c_k}. \quad (46)$$

The homogeneous solution of Eq. (46) is obtained.

$$(1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2) D_t^\alpha(U_{c_k}) + (2ak)^2(U_{c_k}) = 0,$$

$$\frac{D_t^\alpha(U_{c_k})}{U_{c_k}} = -\frac{(2a)^2}{1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2},$$

$$U_{c_k}(t) = C_k(t) E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2a)^2}{1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2} t^\alpha \right). \quad (47)$$

Eq. (46) is substituted for Eq. (47).

$$(1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2) \left[D_t^\alpha \left(C_k(t) E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2ak)^2}{1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2} t^\alpha \right) \right) \right] - \left[-\frac{(2a)^2}{1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2} C_k(t) E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2ak)^2}{1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2} t^\alpha \right) \right] +$$

$$(2ak)^2 C_k(t) E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2ak)^2}{1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2} t^\alpha \right) = f_{c_k}(t),$$

$$(1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2) \left[D_t^\alpha \left(C_k(t) E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2ak)^2}{1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2} t^\alpha \right) \right) \right] - (2ak)^2 C_k(t) E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2ak)^2}{1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2} t^\alpha \right) +$$

$$(2ak)^2 C_k(t) E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2ak)^2}{1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2} t^\alpha \right) = f_{c_k}.$$

Let us find the homogeneous solution of Eq. (44).

$$(1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2) D_t^\alpha(U_{c_k}(t)) + (2ka)^2 U_{c_k}(t) = f_{c_k}(t),$$

$$(1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2) D_t^\alpha(U_{c_k}) + (2ka)^2 U_{c_k} = 0,$$

$$\frac{D_t^\alpha(U_{c_k}(t))}{U_{c_k}(t)} = -\frac{(2ka)^2}{1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2},$$

$$U_{c_k}(t) = C_k(t) E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2ak)^2}{1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2} t^\alpha \right).$$

Let us write the obtained expression in Eq. (44).

$$(1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2) \left[D_t^\alpha(C_k(t)) E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2ak)^2}{1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2} t^\alpha \right) - \frac{(2ak)^2}{1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2} C_k(t) E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2ak)^2}{1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2} t^\alpha \right) \right] +$$

$$(2ka)^2 C_k(t) E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2ak)^2}{1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2} t^\alpha \right) = f_{c_k}(t),$$

$$(1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2) D_t^\alpha(C_k(t)) E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2ak)^2}{1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2} t^\alpha \right) = f_{c_k}(t),$$

$$D_t^\alpha(C_k(t)) = f_{c_k} \left[E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2ak)^2}{1+\varepsilon(2k)^2} t^\alpha \right) (1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2) \right]^{-1},$$

$$C_k(t) = C_k(0) + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^t (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} f_{c_k}(\tau) \left[E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2ak)^2}{1+\varepsilon(2k)^2} \tau^\alpha \right) (1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2) \right]^{-1} d\tau,$$

$$U_{c_k}(t) = C_k(t) E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2ak)^2}{1+\varepsilon(2k)^2} t^\alpha \right),$$

$$U_{c_k}(t) = \left[C_k(0) + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^t (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} f_{c_k}(\tau) \left[E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2ak)^2}{1+\varepsilon(2k)^2} \tau^\alpha \right) (1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2) \right]^{-1} d\tau \right] E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2ak)^2}{1+\varepsilon(2k)^2} t^\alpha \right).$$

Similarly,

$$U_{s_k}(t) = \left[S_k(0) + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^t (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} f_{s_k}(\tau) \left[E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2ak)^2}{1+\varepsilon(2k)^2} \tau^\alpha \right) (1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2) \right]^{-1} d\tau \right] E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2ak)^2}{1+\varepsilon(2k)^2} t^\alpha \right).$$

As a result, the general solution is obtained,

$$U(x, t, \varepsilon) = \frac{1}{2} \left[\varphi_0 + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^t (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} f(\tau) d\tau \right] + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \left[\varphi_{c_k}(0) + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^t (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} f_{c_k}(\tau) \left[E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2ak)^2}{1+\varepsilon(2k)^2} \tau^\alpha \right) (1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2) \right]^{-1} d\tau \right] E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2ak)^2}{1+\varepsilon(2k)^2} t^\alpha \right) \cos 2kx + \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \left[\varphi_{s_k}(0) + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^t (t-\tau)^{\alpha-1} f_{s_k}(\tau) \left[E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2a)^2}{1+\varepsilon(2k)^2} \tau^\alpha \right) (1 + \varepsilon(2k)^2) \right]^{-1} d\tau \right] E_{\alpha,1} \left(-\frac{(2a)^2}{1+\varepsilon(2k)^2} t^\alpha \right) \sin 2kx.$$

5. Conclusions

This study successfully applied the Fourier method to solve homogeneous and non-homogeneous parabolic equations with periodic boundary conditions. Eigenvalues and eigenfunctions were obtained via the Sturm–Liouville problem, and Caputo fractional derivatives were used to extend the analysis to fractional-order equations. The analytical solutions were expressed using Gamma, Beta, and Mittag–Leffler functions. The results confirm that the Fourier method is an effective tool for solving classical and fractional semilinear pseudo-parabolic equations with periodic boundary conditions.

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Euler-Maclaurin-type Inequalities for Generalized Fractional Integrals on Functions of Bounded Variation

Tuğba Acar¹, Fatih Hezenci¹, Arslan Munir²

¹Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Science and Arts, Duzce University, Duzce 81620, Türkiye

²School of Mathematical Sciences, University of Science and Technology of China, Hefei 230026, People's Republic of China

Corresponding author: tubacrr@gmail.com

ORCID IDs:

First Author: [0009-0006-4055-8182](https://orcid.org/0009-0006-4055-8182)

Second Author: [0000-0003-1008-5856](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1008-5856)

Third Author: [0009-0008-8148-5607](https://orcid.org/0009-0008-8148-5607)

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Abstract

This paper presents a comprehensive approach that utilizes generalized fractional integrals to derive Euler-Maclaurin-type inequalities for functions of bounded variation. Moreover, by choosing particular forms of functions and suitable parameters, we obtain several special cases. These cases clearly show the generality and practical applicability of the obtained results. These results not only extend previously known findings but also provide a more general setting for studying such inequalities.

Keywords: Quadrature formulae, convex functions, generalized fractional integrals.

1 Introduction

The theory of inequalities is a well-established and fundamental area of mathematics, with deep connections to various mathematical fields and a wide range of applications. Among the key concepts in this theory are convex functions, which play a crucial role in formulating and proving many important inequalities. In recent years, fractional calculus has also attracted significant interest due to its powerful theoretical framework and numerous practical applications in science and engineering. Because of its importance, many researchers have focused on developing and studying fractional integral inequalities. The bounds of such inequalities can be derived not only from Hermite-Hadamard-type results but also from Simpson, Newton, and Euler-Maclaurin-type inequalities.

Simpson's quadratic formula for functions of bounded variation, along with its applications in the theory of special means, is investigated by Dragomir in [1]. Furthermore, Budak et al. [2] are established various forms of Simpson-type inequalities involving generalized fractional

integrals within the framework of differentiable convex functions. For additional information on Simpson-type inequalities and further properties of generalized fractional integrals, readers are encouraged to consult [3] and the references therein.

Since the three-point Newton-Cotes quadrature formula is a special case of Simpson's second rule, evaluations involving three-step quadratic kernels are often referred to as Newton-type results in the literature. A substantial body of research has focused on developing and analyzing such inequalities. For instance, in [4], several Newton-type integral inequalities are derived for functions whose first derivatives are arithmetically-harmonically convex in absolute value at a given power. Similarly, in [5], fractional Newton-type inequalities are established for functions of bounded variation. Furthermore, Gao and Shi [6] presented specific applications for certain classes of real functions and introduced a new Newton-type inequality based on convexity. For further details on Newton-type inequalities involving convex and differentiable functions, readers may refer to [7] and the references therein.

Dedic et al. [8] develop a set of inequalities, and their results are used to derive error estimates for the Maclaurin quadrature rules. In addition, the results are applied to provide some error estimates for the Simpson 3/8 quadrature rule in [9]. Next, in [10], some Euler-Maclaurin-type inequalities are considered for the case of differentiable convex functions. Furthermore, in [11], some corrected Euler-Maclaurin-type inequalities are established using the Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals. For further details on these types of inequalities, readers are encouraged to consult [12, 13, 14] and the references therein.

2 Preliminaries

In this section, we present several definitions and notations that are frequently used throughout the main part of the paper. Simpson's quadrature formula, also known as Simpson's 1/3 rule, is expressed as follows:

$$\int_a^b f(x) dx \approx \frac{b-a}{6} \left[f(a) + 4f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right]. \quad (1)$$

Theorem 2.1. Let us consider that $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a four times differentiable and continuous function on (a, b) and $\|f^{(4)}\|_\infty = \sup_{x \in (a,b)} |f^{(4)}(x)| < \infty$. Then, the following inequality holds:

$$\left| \frac{1}{6} \left[f(a) + 4f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{1}{2880} \|f^{(4)}\|_\infty (b-a)^4.$$

Simpson's second formula, also known as the Newton-Cotes quadrature formula (Simpson's 3/8 rule; cf. [13]), is expressed as follows:

$$\int_a^b f(x) dx \approx \frac{b-a}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right]. \quad (2)$$

Theorem 2.2. Let us note that $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a four times differentiable and continuous

function on (a, b) and $\|f^{(4)}\|_{\infty} = \sup_{x \in (a,b)} |f^{(4)}(x)| < \infty$. Then, one has the inequality

$$\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[f(a) + 3f\left(\frac{2a+b}{3}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+2b}{3}\right) + f(b) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{1}{6480} \|f^{(4)}\|_{\infty} (b-a)^4.$$

The corresponding dual Simpson's 3/8 formula, known as the Maclaurin rule and based on the Maclaurin formula (cf. [13]), is given as follows:

$$\int_a^b f(x) dx \approx \frac{b-a}{8} \left[3f\left(\frac{5a+b}{6}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+5b}{6}\right) \right]. \quad (3)$$

Theorem 2.3. If $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a four times differentiable and continuous function on (a, b) and $\|f^{(4)}\|_{\infty} = \sup_{x \in (a,b)} |f^{(4)}(x)| < \infty$, then the inequality

$$\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[3f\left(\frac{5a+b}{6}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+5b}{6}\right) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(x) dx \right| \leq \frac{7}{51840} \|f^{(4)}\|_{\infty} (b-a)^4$$

is valid.

The formulae (1), (2), and (3) are valid for any function f whose fourth derivative is continuous on the interval $[a, b]$.

In the literature, numerous papers discuss inequalities related to generalized fractional integrals. For example, Sarikaya and Ertugral establish Hermite-Hadamard-type inequalities for generalized fractional integrals [15]. In addition, Ertugral and Sarikaya [16] present some Simpson-type inequalities for these fractional integral operators.

Definition 2.1. [15] Note that $\varphi : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ the condition $\int_0^1 \frac{\varphi(t)}{t} dt < \infty$. Then, the following left-sided and right-sided generalized fractional integral operators are described as

$${}_{a+}I_{\varphi}f(x) = \int_a^x \frac{\varphi(x-t)}{x-t} f(t) dt, \quad x > a \quad (4)$$

and

$${}_{b-}I_{\varphi}f(x) = \int_x^b \frac{\varphi(t-x)}{t-x} f(t) dt, \quad x < b, \quad (5)$$

respectively.

A key feature of generalized fractional integrals is that they encompass several important types of fractional integrals, such as the Riemann-Liouville fractional integral, the k -Riemann-Liouville fractional integral, Katugampola fractional integrals, the conformable fractional integral, Hadamard fractional integrals, and others. These notable special cases of the integral operators (4) and (5) are summarized as follows:

- i. If we choose $\varphi(t) = t$, then the operators (4) and (5) become to the Riemann integral.
- ii. If we consider $\varphi(t) = \frac{t^{\alpha}}{\Gamma(\alpha)}$ and $\alpha > 0$, then the operators (4) and (5) reduce to the

Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals $J_{a+}^\alpha f(x)$ and $J_{b-}^\alpha f(x)$, respectively [17, 18]. Here,

$$J_{a+}^\alpha f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_a^x (x-t)^{\alpha-1} f(t) dt, \quad x > a$$

and

$$J_{b-}^\alpha f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_x^b (t-x)^{\alpha-1} f(t) dt, \quad x < b.$$

Γ is Gamma function described by the integral formula

$$\Gamma(x) := \int_0^\infty t^{x-1} e^{-t} dt, \quad x \in \mathbb{R}^+.$$

iii. For $\varphi(t) = \frac{1}{k\Gamma_k(\alpha)} t^{\frac{\alpha}{k}}$ and $\alpha, k > 0$, the operators (4) and (5) become to the k -Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals $J_{a+,k}^\alpha f(x)$ and $J_{b-,k}^\alpha f(x)$, respectively. Here,

$$J_{a+,k}^\alpha f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma_k(\alpha)} \int_a^x (x-t)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}-1} f(t) dt, \quad x > a$$

and

$$J_{b-,k}^\alpha f(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma_k(\alpha)} \int_x^b (t-x)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}-1} f(t) dt, \quad x < b.$$

Γ_k is k -Gamma function defined by

$$\Gamma_k(\alpha) = \int_0^\infty t^{\alpha-1} e^{-\frac{t^k}{k}} dt, \quad \mathbb{R}(\alpha) > 0$$

and

$$\Gamma_k(\alpha) = k^{\frac{\alpha}{k}-1} \Gamma\left(\frac{\alpha}{k}\right), \quad \mathbb{R}(\alpha) > 0; k > 0.$$

3 Main results

Lemma 3.1. Let us consider that $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is an absolutely continuous function (a, b) so that $f' \in L_1[a, b]$. Then, the following equality holds:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{8} \left[3f\left(\frac{5a+b}{6}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+5b}{6}\right) \right] - \frac{1}{2\Lambda(1)} \left[{}_{\frac{a+b}{2}-} I_\varphi f(a) + {}_{\frac{a+b}{2}+} I_\varphi f(b) \right] \quad (6) \\ & = \frac{b-a}{2\Lambda(1)} \int_a^b K(x) df(x). \end{aligned}$$

Here, $\Lambda(t) = \int_0^t \frac{\varphi\left(\frac{b-a}{2}y\right)}{y} dy$ and

$$K(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{2}{b-a} \Lambda\left(\frac{2(x-a)}{b-a}\right), & a \leq x < \frac{5a+b}{6}, \\ \frac{2}{b-a} \left[\Lambda\left(\frac{2(x-a)}{b-a}\right) - \frac{3}{4} \Lambda(1) \right], & \frac{5a+b}{6} \leq x < \frac{a+b}{2}, \\ -\frac{2}{b-a} \left[\Lambda\left(\frac{2(b-x)}{b-a}\right) - \frac{3}{4} \Lambda(1) \right], & \frac{a+b}{2} \leq x < \frac{a+5b}{6}, \\ -\frac{2}{b-a} \Lambda\left(\frac{2(b-x)}{b-a}\right), & \frac{a+5b}{6} \leq x \leq b. \end{cases}$$

Proof. Let us first consider the function $K(x)$. Then, with the help of the integrating by parts, it follows from that

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_a^b K(x) df(x) \tag{7} \\ &= \frac{2}{b-a} \left\{ \int_a^{\frac{5a+b}{6}} \Lambda\left(\frac{2(x-a)}{b-a}\right) df(x) + \int_{\frac{5a+b}{6}}^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \left[\Lambda\left(\frac{2(x-a)}{b-a}\right) - \frac{3}{4} \Lambda(1) \right] df(x) \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+5b}{6}} \left[\Lambda\left(\frac{2(b-x)}{b-a}\right) - \frac{3}{4} \Lambda(1) \right] df(x) - \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b \Lambda\left(\frac{2(b-x)}{b-a}\right) df(x) \right\} \\ &= \frac{2}{b-a} \left\{ \Lambda\left(\frac{2(x-a)}{b-a}\right) f(x) \Big|_a^{\frac{5a+b}{6}} - \int_a^{\frac{5a+b}{6}} \frac{\varphi(x-a)}{x-a} f(x) dx \right. \\ & \quad + \left[\Lambda\left(\frac{2(x-a)}{b-a}\right) - \frac{3}{4} \Lambda(1) \right] f(x) \Big|_{\frac{5a+b}{6}}^{\frac{a+b}{2}} - \int_{\frac{5a+b}{6}}^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \frac{\varphi(x-a)}{x-a} f(x) dx \\ & \quad - \left[\Lambda\left(\frac{2(b-x)}{b-a}\right) - \frac{3}{4} \Lambda(1) \right] f(x) \Big|_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+5b}{6}} - \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+5b}{6}} \frac{\varphi(b-x)}{b-x} f(x) dx \\ & \quad \left. - \Lambda\left(\frac{2(b-x)}{b-a}\right) f(x) \Big|_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b - \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b \frac{\varphi(b-x)}{b-x} f(x) dx \right\} \\ &= \frac{2}{b-a} \left\{ \frac{\Lambda(1)}{4} \left[3f\left(\frac{5a+b}{6}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+5b}{6}\right) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \int_a^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \frac{\varphi(x-a)}{x-a} f(x) dx - \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b \frac{\varphi(b-x)}{b-x} f(x) dx \right\} \\ &= \frac{2}{b-a} \left\{ \frac{\Lambda(1)}{4} \left[3f\left(\frac{5a+b}{6}\right) + 2f\left(\frac{a+b}{2}\right) + 3f\left(\frac{a+5b}{6}\right) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \left[\frac{a+b}{2} - I_{\varphi} f(a) + \frac{a+b}{2} + I_{\varphi} f(b) \right] \right\}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, we obtain readily

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{3} \left[2f \left(\frac{3a+b}{4} \right) - f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + 2f \left(\frac{a+3b}{4} \right) \right] - \frac{1}{2\Lambda(1)} [{}_{b-}I_{\varphi}f(a) + {}_{a+}I_{\varphi}f(b)] \\ &= \frac{b-a}{2\Lambda(1)} \int_a^b K(x)df(x) \end{aligned}$$

□

Theorem 3.1. If $f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a function of bounded variation on $[a, b]$, then we have

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[3f \left(\frac{5a+b}{6} \right) + 2f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + 3f \left(\frac{a+5b}{6} \right) \right] - \frac{1}{2\Lambda(1)} \left[{}_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}I_{\varphi}f(a) + {}_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}I_{\varphi}f(b) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{1}{2\Lambda(1)} \max \left\{ \Lambda \left(\frac{1}{3} \right), \left| \Lambda \left(\frac{1}{3} \right) - \frac{3}{4}\Lambda(1) \right|, \frac{1}{4}\Lambda(1) \right\} \bigvee_a^b(f). \end{aligned}$$

Here, $\bigvee_a^b(f)$ denotes the total variation of f on $[a, b]$.

Proof. It is known that if $g, f : [a, b] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are such that g is continuous on $[a, b]$ and f is of bounded variation on $[a, b]$, then $\int_a^b g(t)df(t)$ exist and

$$\left| \int_a^b g(t)df(t) \right| \leq \sup_{t \in [a,b]} |g(t)| \bigvee_a^b(f). \tag{8}$$

By using (8), it follows

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[3f \left(\frac{5a+b}{6} \right) + 2f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + 3f \left(\frac{a+5b}{6} \right) \right] - \frac{1}{2\Lambda(1)} \left[{}_{\frac{a+b}{2}-}I_{\varphi}f(a) + {}_{\frac{a+b}{2}+}I_{\varphi}f(b) \right] \right| \\ &= \frac{b-a}{4\Lambda(1)} \left| \int_a^b K(x)df(x) \right| \\ & \leq \frac{1}{2\Lambda(1)} \left\{ \left| \int_a^{\frac{5a+b}{6}} \Lambda \left(\frac{2(x-a)}{b-a} \right) df(x) \right| \right. \\ & \quad + \left| \int_{\frac{5a+b}{6}}^{\frac{a+b}{2}} \left[\Lambda \left(\frac{2(x-a)}{b-a} \right) - \frac{3}{4}\Lambda(1) \right] df(x) \right| \\ & \quad + \left| \int_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+5b}{6}} \left[\frac{3}{4}\Lambda(1) - \Lambda \left(\frac{2(b-x)}{b-a} \right) \right] df(x) \right| \\ & \quad \left. + \left| \int_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b \Lambda \left(\frac{2(b-x)}{b-a} \right) df(x) \right| \right\} \\ & \leq \frac{1}{2\Lambda(1)} \left\{ \sup_{x \in [a, \frac{5a+b}{6}]} \left| \Lambda \left(\frac{2(x-a)}{b-a} \right) \right| \bigvee_a^{\frac{5a+b}{6}}(f) \right. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + \sup_{x \in [\frac{5a+b}{6}, \frac{a+b}{2}]} \left| \Lambda \left(\frac{2(x-a)}{b-a} \right) - \frac{3}{4} \Lambda(1) \right| \bigvee_{\frac{5a+b}{6}}^{\frac{a+b}{2}} (f) \\
& + \sup_{x \in [\frac{a+b}{2}, \frac{a+5b}{6}]} \left| \frac{3}{4} \Lambda(1) - \Lambda \left(\frac{2(b-x)}{b-a} \right) \right| \bigvee_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+5b}{6}} (f) \\
& + \sup_{x \in [\frac{a+5b}{6}, b]} \left| \Lambda \left(\frac{2(b-x)}{b-a} \right) \right| \bigvee_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b (f) \Bigg\} \\
& = \frac{1}{2\Lambda(1)} \left\{ \Lambda \left(\frac{1}{3} \right) \bigvee_a^{\frac{5a+b}{6}} (f) \right. \\
& + \max \left[\frac{1}{4} \Lambda(1), \left| \Lambda \left(\frac{1}{3} \right) - \frac{3}{4} \Lambda(1) \right| \right] \bigvee_{\frac{5a+b}{6}}^{\frac{a+b}{2}} (f) \\
& + \max \left[\left| \Lambda \left(\frac{1}{3} \right) - \frac{3}{4} \Lambda(1) \right|, \frac{1}{4} \Lambda(1) \right] \bigvee_{\frac{a+b}{2}}^{\frac{a+5b}{6}} (f) \\
& \left. + \Lambda \left(\frac{1}{3} \right) \bigvee_{\frac{a+5b}{6}}^b (f) \right\} \\
& \leq \frac{1}{2\Lambda(1)} \max \left\{ \Lambda \left(\frac{1}{3} \right), \left| \Lambda \left(\frac{1}{3} \right) - \frac{3}{4} \Lambda(1) \right|, \frac{1}{4} \Lambda(1) \right\} \bigvee_a^b (f).
\end{aligned}$$

This finishes the proof of Theorem 3.1. □

Remark 3.1. Let us consider $\varphi(t) = t$ in Theorem 3.1. Then, the following Euler-Maclaurin-type inequality holds:

$$\left| \frac{1}{8} \left[3f \left(\frac{5a+b}{6} \right) + 2f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + 3f \left(\frac{a+5b}{6} \right) \right] - \frac{1}{b-a} \int_a^b f(t) dt \right| \leq \frac{5}{24} \bigvee_a^b (f).$$

This is proved by Gumus et al. in paper [19, Corollary 6].

Remark 3.2. Consider $\varphi(t) = \frac{t^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha)}$ in Theorem 3.1. Then, Theorem 3.1 becomes to [19, Theorem 9].

Corollary 3.1. Note that $\varphi(t) = \frac{1}{k\Gamma_k(\alpha)} t^{\frac{\alpha}{k}}$ in Theorem 3.1. Then, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left| \frac{1}{8} \left[3f \left(\frac{5a+b}{6} \right) + 2f \left(\frac{a+b}{2} \right) + 3f \left(\frac{a+5b}{6} \right) \right] - \frac{2^{\frac{\alpha}{k}-1} \Gamma_k(\alpha+k)}{(b-a)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}}} \left[J_{\frac{a+b}{2}-,k}^\alpha f(a) + J_{\frac{a+b}{2}+,k}^\alpha f(b) \right] \right| \\
& \leq \frac{1}{2} \max \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{3} \right)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}}, \left| \left(\frac{1}{3} \right)^{\frac{\alpha}{k}} - \frac{3}{4} \right|, \frac{1}{4} \right\} \bigvee_a^b (f),
\end{aligned}$$

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Some Bullen-type Inequalities for Co-ordinated s-convex Function

Mehmet Eyüp Kiriş¹, Tuğba Çınar¹

¹Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Science and Arts, Afyon Kocatepe University, Afyonkarahisar 03000, Türkiye

Corresponding author: cinartgb5@gmail.com

ORCID IDs:

First Author: [0000-0002-6463-5289](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6463-5289)

Second Author: [0000-0001-9670-4018](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9670-4018)

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Abstract

In this paper, we establish new Bullen-Simpson type integral inequalities for functions of two variables whose mixed partial derivatives are s-convex in the second sense on the coordinates. Several general results and corollaries are obtained by employing Hölder and Power Mean inequalities. Furthermore, the constants involved in these inequalities are explicitly determined, and the classical one-dimensional results are shown to be special cases of our findings. The obtained results provide a comprehensive generalization of the existing Bullen-Simpson type inequalities to the framework of coordinate s-convex functions, offering new insights and potential applications in numerical integration and mean inequalities.

Keywords: Bullen-type inequalities, s-convex functions, Co-ordinated convexity, Simpson-type inequalities.

1 Introduction and Motivation

Definition 1.1. Let I be an interval of real numbers. A function $B : I \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is said to be convex, if for all $\mu_1, \mu_2 \in I$ all $h \in [0, 1]$ ([2]), we have

$$B(h\mu_1 + (1-h)\mu_2) \leq hB(\mu_1) + (1-h)B(\mu_2)$$

One of the famous inequalities for the class of convex functions is the so-called Hermite-Hadamard inequality, which can be stated as follows:

Theorem 1.1. Let B be a convex function on the interval $[\mu_1, \mu_2]$ with $\mu_1 < \mu_2$, then we have ([18])

$$B\left(\frac{\mu_1 + \mu_2}{2}\right) \leq \frac{1}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)} \int_{\mu_1}^{\mu_2} B(x) dx \leq \frac{B(\mu_1) + B(\mu_2)}{2} \quad (1)$$

Since its discovery, several articles related to inequality (1) have been published ([3]-[18])

The concept of convexity has been also generalized in diverse manners. One of them is the so-called s -convex function or Breckner convex function defined as follows:

A nonnegative function $B : I \subset [0, \infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is said to be s -convex in the second sense for some fixed $s \in (0, 1]$, if

$$B(h\mu_1 + (1-h)\mu_2) \leq h^s B(\mu_1) + (1-h)^s B(\mu_2)$$

holds for all $\mu_1, \mu_2 \in I$ and $h \in [0, 1]$ (see [19])

In [20], Dragomir and Fitzpatrick, proved the following variant of inequality (1) which holds for s -convex functions in the second sense.

Definition 1.2. A function $B : \Delta \subseteq [0, \infty)^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is called s -convex in the second sense on the co-ordinates on Δ if;

$$\begin{aligned} & B(h\mu_1 + (1-h)\mu_2, tv_1 + (1-t)v_2) \\ & \leq h^s t^s B(\mu_1, v_1) + h^s (1-t)^s B(\mu_1, v_2) \\ & \quad + t^s (1-h)^s B(\mu_2, v_1) + (1-h)^s (1-t)^s B(\mu_2, v_2) \end{aligned}$$

holds for all $h, t \in [0, 1]$ and $(\mu_1, v_1), (\mu_1, v_2), (\mu_2, v_1), (\mu_2, v_2) \in \Delta$, for some fixed $s \in (0, 1]$. (see [21])

Definition 1.3. In [22], Hwang et al. established the following Bullen-type inequality

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{4} \left(B(\mu_1) + 2B\left(\frac{\mu_1 + \mu_2}{2}\right) + B(\mu_2) \right) - \frac{1}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)} \int_{\mu_1}^{\mu_2} B(x) dx \right| \\ & \leq \frac{\mu_2 - \mu_1}{16} \left(|B'(\mu_1)| \right) + \left(|B'(\mu_2)| \right) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Definition 1.4. In [23], Hwang et al. established the following Simpson-type inequality

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{4} \left(B(\mu_1) + 2B\left(\frac{\mu_1 + \mu_2}{2}\right) + B(\mu_2) \right) - \frac{1}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)} \int_{\mu_1}^{\mu_2} B(x) dx \right| \\ & \leq \frac{\mu_2 - \mu_1}{16} \left(|B'(\mu_1)| \right) + \left(|B'(\mu_2)| \right) \end{aligned}$$

2 Background

Over the last two decades, error estimation of quadrature rules via different types of convexity has become an attractive and fascinating area of research and has gained popularity. Consequently, several papers treating integral inequalities under the principle of convexity have been widely studied by mathematicians and researchers. Regarding Newton-Cotes type inequalities involving one point ([24]-[29]) two point Newton-Cotes type inequalities ([30]-[33]), for three point Newton-Cotes type inequalities ([34]-[39]) and Newton-Cotes type inequalities involving four points ([40]-[44])

we provide several applications to two-dimensional numerical integration rules and discuss new inequalities involving means based on our coordinate s-convexity results

4 Main theorems and Results

In this section, we present our main theoretical contributions. We start with a lemma and use it to derive new theorems and results

Lemma 4.1. Let $B : [\mu_1, \mu_2] \times [v_1, v_2] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a function such that the mixed partial derivative $\frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}$ exists and belongs to $L^1(D)$, then the following equality holds

$$B - I = \frac{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)}{256} \sum_{i=1}^4 \sum_{j=1}^4 \int_0^1 \int_0^1 K_i(h)K_j(k) \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(x_i(h), y_j(k)) dkdh \quad (4)$$

1. The integrals mean (I)

$$I = \frac{1}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)} \int_{\mu_1}^{\mu_2} \int_{v_1}^{v_2} B(x, y) dy dx$$

2. The extended Bullen rule approximation (B)

The approximation B is the weighted sum of the function $B(x, y)$ evaluated at the 5x5=25 Bullen quadrature points in D normalized by $\frac{1}{144}$;

$$B = \frac{1}{144} \sum_{i=1}^5 \sum_{j=1}^5 W_{i,j} B(x_i, y_j)$$

where the weights are $w = \{1, 4, 6, 4, 1\}$ and the quadrature points are;

$$\begin{aligned} x_i &\in \left\{ \mu_1, \frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}, \frac{\mu_1 + \mu_2}{2}, \frac{\mu_1 + 3\mu_2}{4}, \mu_2 \right\} \\ y_i &\in \left\{ v_1, \frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4}, \frac{v_1 + v_2}{2}, \frac{v_1 + 3v_2}{4}, v_2 \right\} \end{aligned}$$

3. The kernel functions ($K_i(h), K_j(k)$): $K_i(h)$ and $K_j(k)$ represent the single-variable Bullen-Simpson kernel functions corresponding to the subdivision of the intervals.

4. The parameterization: The terms $x_i(h)$ and $y_i(k)$ linearly parameterize the 4x4 subrectangles of D

Proof. The proof of this identity is usually done by taking the integrals

$$I_{i,j} = \int_0^1 \int_0^1 K_i(h)K_j(k) \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(x_i(h), y_j(k)) dkdh \quad (5)$$

we will use successive integration by parts twice. For example; consider the simplest term on the right-hand side for $i = 1, j = 1$;

$$I_{1,1} = \int_0^1 K_1(h) \left[\int_0^1 K_1(k) \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(x_1(h), y_1(k)) dk \right] dh$$

partial integration of the inner integral with respect to k . Then,

$$\begin{aligned} K_1(h) &= h - 1/3 \\ x_1(h) &= (1-h)\mu_1 + h \frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4} \\ x'_1(h) &= \frac{\mu_2 - \mu_1}{4} \\ y_1(k) &= (1-k)\mu_1 + k \frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4} \\ y'_1(k) &= \frac{v_2 - v_1}{4} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} u &= k - \frac{1}{3} \Rightarrow du = dk \\ dv &= \left(\frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(x_1, y_1(k)) \right) dk \end{aligned}$$

To find v , we need to integrate B with respect to k . Using the reverse chain rule;

$$\begin{aligned} v &= \frac{1}{y'_1(k)} \frac{\partial B}{\partial x} \left(y'_1(k) = \frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4} - v_1 = \frac{v_2 - v_1}{4} \right) \\ v &= \frac{4}{v_2 - v_1} \frac{\partial B}{\partial x}(x_1(h), y_1(k)) \end{aligned}$$

Then, lets do the integration by parts and substitute the integral boundaries.

$$\begin{aligned} J_{1,1}(h) &= \frac{2}{3} \frac{4}{v_2 - v_1} \frac{\partial B}{\partial x} \left(x_1(h), \frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4} \right) + \frac{1}{3} \frac{4}{v_2 - v_1} \frac{\partial B}{\partial x} (x_1(h), v_1) \\ &\quad - \frac{4}{v_2 - v_1} \int_0^1 \frac{\partial B}{\partial x}(x_1(h), y_1(k)) dk \\ &= \frac{4}{3(v_2 - v_1)} \left[2 \frac{\partial B}{\partial x} \left(x_1(h), \frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4} \right) + \frac{\partial B}{\partial x} (x_1(h), v_1) \right] \\ &\quad - \frac{4}{v_2 - v_1} \int_0^1 \frac{\partial B}{\partial x}(x_1(h), y_1(k)) dk \end{aligned}$$

Transition to the outer integral,

$$I_{1,1} = \int_0^1 K_1(h) \cdot J_{1,1}(h) dh$$

Apply $\int_0^1 K_1(h)(...)dh$ to each term in the expression $J_{1,1}(h)$

$$\begin{aligned} I_{1,1} &= \frac{4}{3(v_2 - v_1)} \left[2 \int_0^1 K_1(h) \frac{\partial B}{\partial x} \left(x_1(h), \frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4} \right) dh \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \int_0^1 K_1(h) \frac{\partial B}{\partial x} (x_1(h), v_1) dh \right] \\ &\quad - \frac{4}{v_2 - v_1} \int_0^1 K_1(h) \left(\int_0^1 \frac{\partial B}{\partial x}(x_1(h), y_1(k)) dk \right) dh \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

Lets take

$$\begin{aligned} L_1 &= \int_0^1 K_1(h) \frac{\partial B}{\partial x} \left(x_1(h), \frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4} \right) dh \\ L_2 &= \int_0^1 K_1(h) \frac{\partial B}{\partial x} (x_1(h), v_1) dh \\ L_3 &= \int_0^1 K_1(h) \left(\int_0^1 \frac{\partial B}{\partial x} (x_1(h), y_1(k)) dk \right) dh \end{aligned}$$

Applying the second partial integration(L_1 term)

$$\begin{aligned} u &= h - \frac{1}{3} \Rightarrow du = dh \\ dv &= \frac{\partial B}{\partial x} (x_1(h), y_1(k)) dh \\ v &= \frac{1}{x_1'(h)} B(x_1(h), Y) = \frac{4}{\mu_2 - \mu_1} B(x_1(h), Y) dh \end{aligned}$$

Then, lets do the integration by parts and substitue the integral boundaries.

$$\begin{aligned} L_1 &= \frac{4}{3(\mu_2 - \mu_1)} \left[2B \left(\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}, Y \right) + B(\mu_1, Y) \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \frac{4}{\mu_2 - \mu_1} \int_0^1 B(x_1(h), Y) dh \right] \end{aligned}$$

Lets convert the remaining integral in L_1 to an integral with respect to x ;

$$\begin{aligned} x &= x_1(h) \\ dh &= \frac{4}{\mu_2 - \mu_1} dx \end{aligned}$$

and boundaries

$$\begin{aligned} x &= 0 \Rightarrow h = \mu_1 \\ x &= 1 \Rightarrow h = \frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4} \\ \int_0^1 B(x_1(h), Y) dh &= \int_{\mu_1}^{\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}} B(x, Y) \frac{4}{\mu_2 - \mu_1} dx \end{aligned}$$

Lets rewrite L_1

$$\begin{aligned} L_1 &= \frac{4}{3(\mu_2 - \mu_1)} \left[2B \left(\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}, Y \right) + B(\mu_1, Y) \right] \\ &\quad - \frac{4}{\mu_2 - \mu_1} \int_{\mu_1}^{\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}} B(x, Y) dx \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

Then, calculate L_2 ,integrating by parts and substitue the integral boundaries. We get;

$$\begin{aligned} L_2 &= \frac{4}{3(\mu_2 - \mu_1)} \left[2B \left(\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}, v_1 \right) + B(\mu_1, v_1) \right] \\ &\quad - \frac{4}{\mu_2 - \mu_1} \int_0^1 B(x_1(h), v_1) dh \end{aligned}$$

Change variables in the remaining integral and if we substitute the transformation we found into L_2 ;

$$L_2 = \frac{4}{3(\mu_2 - \mu_1)} \left[2B\left(\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}, v_1\right) + B(\mu_1, v_1) \right] - \frac{4}{\mu_2 - \mu_1} \int_{\mu_1}^{\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}} B(x, v_1) dx \quad (8)$$

(The structure of this term is the same as that of four term, expect that the y -coordinate is to v , instead of $\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}$)

Finally, let's calculate for L_3 , transformation of the inner integral with respect to k . Then,

$$L_3 = \int_0^1 K_1(h) \left(\int_{v_1}^{\frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4}} \frac{\partial B}{\partial x}(x_1(h), y) dy \right) \frac{4}{v_2 - v_1} dh$$

Integration by parts of the outer integral with respect to h . As in the previous steps to remove the derivative x , we substitute the derivative $x_1(h)$ with respect to $(x_1(h)')$ we divide. Integration by parts, write boundaries and make necessary arrangements,

$$L_3 = \frac{16}{3(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)} \left[2 \int_{v_1}^{\frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4}} B\left(\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}, y\right) dy + \int_{v_1}^{\frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4}} B(\mu_1, y) dy \right] - \int_0^1 \frac{4}{\mu_2 - \mu_1} \int_{v_1}^{\frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4}} B(x_1(h), y) dy dh$$

Transformation of the remaining double integral (final term)

$$-\frac{16}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)} \int_0^1 \left(\int_{v_1}^{\frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4}} B(x_1(h), y) dy \right) dh$$

where,

$$\begin{aligned} x &= x_1(h) \\ dh &= \frac{4}{\mu_2 - \mu_1} dx \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} h = 0 &\Rightarrow x = \mu_1 \\ h = 1 &\Rightarrow x = \frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4} \end{aligned}$$

$$-\frac{16}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)} \int_{\mu_1}^{\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}} \left(\int_{v_1}^{\frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4}} B(x, y) dx dy \right) \frac{4}{\mu_2 - \mu_1}$$

L_3 final statement,

$$L_3 = \frac{16}{3(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)} \int_{v_1}^{\frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4}} \left[2B\left(\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}, y\right) + B(\mu_1, y) \right] dy$$

$$-\frac{16}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)^2 (v_2 - v_1)} \int \int_{\mu_1}^{\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}} B(x, y) dx dy \tag{9}$$

This term, when combined with previous terms L_1 and L_2 , will give $I_{1,1}$. When all sixteen terms are added, these complex single integrals cancel out, leaving only the Bullen terms $B(\dots)$ and the term $\int \int B(x, y) dx dy$

$$I_{1,1} = \frac{4}{3(v_2 - v_1)} [2L_1 + L_2] - \frac{4}{v_2 - v_1} L_3$$

We collect the L_1 and L_2 terms as $2L_1 + L_2$

$$L_1 = \frac{4}{3(\mu_2 - \mu_1)} \left[2B\left(\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}, \frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4}\right) + B\left(\mu_1, \frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4}\right) \right] - \frac{4}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)^2} \int_{\mu_1}^{\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}} B\left(x, \frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4}\right) dx$$

$$L_2 = \frac{4}{3(\mu_2 - \mu_1)} \left[2B\left(\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}, v_1\right) + B(\mu_1, v_1) \right] - \frac{4}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)^2} \int_{\mu_1}^{\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}} B(x, v_1) dx$$

$$2L_1 + L_2 = \frac{4}{3(\mu_2 - \mu_1)} \left[4B\left(\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}, \frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4}\right) + 2B\left(\mu_1, \frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4}\right) + 2B\left(\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}, v_1\right) + B(\mu_1, v_1) \right]$$

$2L_1 + L_2$ by $\frac{4}{3(v_2 - v_1)}$ multiplying this sum by the first two rows of $I_{1,1}$, we get

$$\frac{16}{9(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)} \left[4B\left(\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}, \frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4}\right) + 2B\left(\mu_1, \frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4}\right) + 2B\left(\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}, v_1\right) + B(\mu_1, v_1) \right]$$

If we multiply the final statement of L_3 by $-\frac{4}{(v_2 - v_1)}$

$$L_3 = \frac{64}{3(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)^2} \int_{v_1}^{\frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4}} \left[2B\left(\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}, y\right) + B(\mu_1, y) \right] dy - \frac{64}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)^2 (v_2 - v_1)^2} \int \int_{\mu_1}^{\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}} B(x, y) dx dy$$

$$I_{1,1} = \frac{16}{9(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)} \left[4B\left(\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}, \frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4}\right) + 2B\left(\mu_1, \frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4}\right) + 2B\left(\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}, v_1\right) + B(\mu_1, v_1) \right] - \frac{64}{3(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)^2} \int_{v_1}^{\frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4}} \left[2B\left(\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}, y\right) + B(\mu_1, y) \right] dy \tag{10}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& -\frac{64}{3(\mu_2 - \mu_1)^2(v_2 - v_1)} \int_{\mu_1}^{\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}} \left[2B\left(x, \frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4}\right) + B(x, v_1) \right] dx \\
& + \frac{256}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)^2(v_2 - v_1)^2} \int \int_{\mu_1}^{\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}} B(x, y) dx dy
\end{aligned}$$

1) Bullen Type Terms (Four Corners)

$$\frac{1}{9} \frac{4}{\mu_2 - \mu_1} \frac{4}{v_2 - v_1} = \frac{16}{9(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)} \tag{11}$$

2) Single Integrals (x-Direction)

$$-\frac{1}{3} \frac{16}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)^2} \frac{4}{v_2 - v_1} = -\frac{64}{3(\mu_2 - \mu_1)^2(v_2 - v_1)} \tag{12}$$

3) Single Integrals (y-Direction)

$$-\frac{1}{3} \frac{16}{(v_2 - v_1)^2} \frac{4}{\mu_2 - \mu_1} = -\frac{64}{3(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)^2} \tag{13}$$

4) Double Integral

$$\frac{16}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)^2} \frac{16}{(v_2 - v_1)^2} = \frac{256}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)^2(v_2 - v_1)^2} \tag{14}$$

Due to symmetry, the expression of the remaining terms follows the same structures as the term $I_{1,1}$, which we proved in detail. Only the points, boundaries and coefficients of the Peano kernel ($K_1(h) = h - 1/3, K_1(h) = h - 2/3$) used change, preserving the coefficients $x'_1(h) = \frac{\mu_2 - \mu_1}{4}, y'_1(k) = \frac{v_2 - v_1}{4}$. So let's move directly to the sum $I_{i,j}$

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{i=1}^4 \sum_{j=1}^4 I_{i,j} &= \left(\begin{array}{c} \text{sum of 16} \\ \text{bullen type terms} \end{array} \right) + \left(\begin{array}{c} \text{sum of 16} \\ \text{X-Int terms} \end{array} \right) \\
&+ \left(\begin{array}{c} \text{sum of 16} \\ \text{Y-Int terms} \end{array} \right) + \left(\begin{array}{c} \text{sum of 16} \\ \text{double integrals} \end{array} \right)
\end{aligned}$$

then we have,

$$\begin{aligned}
I_{i,j} &= \frac{16}{9(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)} \sum_{\text{bullen}} B(\dots) \\
&+ \frac{64}{3(\mu_2 - \mu_1)^2(v_2 - v_1)} \sum_{X\text{-int}} \int (\dots) dx \\
&+ \frac{64}{3(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)^2} \sum_{Y\text{-int}} \int (\dots) dy \\
&+ \frac{256}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)^2(v_2 - v_1)^2} \int \int B(\dots) dx dy
\end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

1) This is the most important part of the proof. The x -directional integral term from $I_{i,j}$ cancels out because the x -directional integral terms on adjacent intervals (e.g $I_{1,1}$) are of exactly the

opposite sign and the same magnitude

$$\sum \text{Single Integral parts of } I_{i,j} = 0$$

2) Adding double integrals

$$\sum \text{Double Integral parts of } I_{i,j} = \frac{256}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)^2 (v_2 - v_1)^2} \int \int_D B(x, y) dy dx$$

3) The total part of Bullen type terms of

$$I_{i,j} = \frac{256}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)} \cdot B$$

This sum is related to the integral mean I

$$\frac{256}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)} \cdot I$$

Where these three results are collected the final identity of Lemma

$$S = \sum_{i=1}^4 \sum_{j=1}^4 I_{i,j} = \frac{256}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)} [B - I]$$

Multiplying this expression by $\frac{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)}{256}$, we obtain the auxiliary identity

$$B - I = \frac{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)}{256} \sum_{i=1}^4 \sum_{j=1}^4 I_{i,j}$$

the proof is completed.

Theorem 4.1. Let $B : [\mu_1, \mu_2] x [v_1, v_2] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a function such that the mixed partial derivative $\frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}$ exists and is integrable on $[\mu_1, \mu_2] x [v_1, v_2]$. If $\left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y} \right|$ is s -convex in the second sense on $[\mu_1, \mu_2] x [v_1, v_2]$ for some fixed $s \in (0, 1]$, then the following inequality holds:

$$|B - I| \leq \frac{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)}{256(s + 1)^2(s + 2)^2} \sum_{i=1}^5 \sum_{j=1}^5 \int_0^1 \int_0^1 K_{i,j}(s) \left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(x_i, y_j) \right| \quad (16)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} x &= \{x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5\} = \left\{ \mu_1, \frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}, \frac{\mu_1 + \mu_2}{2}, \frac{\mu_1 + 3\mu_2}{4}, \mu_2 \right\} \\ y &= \{y_1, y_2, y_3, y_4, y_5\} = \left\{ v_1, \frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4}, \frac{v_1 + v_2}{2}, \frac{v_1 + 3v_2}{4}, v_2 \right\} \end{aligned}$$

$K_{i,j}(s)$ are coefficients obtained from linear combinations of the products of the single variable integrals $\gamma_k(s)$ and $\Lambda_k(s)$ with $c_k \in \left\{ \frac{1}{3}, \frac{2}{3} \right\}$.

$$\gamma_k(s) = \int_0^1 \left| \tau - \frac{1}{3} \right| \tau^s d\tau = \int_0^1 \left| \frac{2}{3} - \tau \right| (1 - \tau)^s d\tau \quad (17)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \frac{2s+1}{3(s+1)(s+2)} + \frac{2}{(s+1)(s+2)} \left(\frac{1}{3}\right)^{s+2} \\
\Lambda_k(s) &= \int_0^1 \left| \tau - \frac{1}{3} \right| (1-\tau)^s d\tau = \int_0^1 \left| \frac{2}{3} - \tau \right| \tau^s d\tau \\
&= \frac{s-1}{3(s+1)(s+2)} + \frac{2}{(s+1)(s+2)} \left(\frac{2}{3}\right)^{s+2}
\end{aligned}$$

Proof. From Lemma properties of modulus and coordinated s-convexity of $|B'|$, we have

$$|B - I| \leq (\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1) \sum_{k=1}^4 \sum_{l=1}^4 \int_{J_k} \int_{J_l} K(t, z) \left(\frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(x(t), y(z)) \right) dz dt$$

Here, the kernel $K(t, z)$ is the product of single variable Bullen-Simpson kernels $K(t, z) = K_1(t)K_2(z)$. Taking the absolute value and isolating the double integral

$$|B - I| \leq (\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1) \sum_{k=1}^4 \sum_{l=1}^4 \int_{J_k} \int_{J_l} |K_1(t)| |K_2(z)| \left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(x(t), y(z)) \right| dz dt$$

The summation over k and l over the 16 sub-rectangles where the kernel $K(t, z)$ maintains a constant sign structure. For each of the 16 sub-rectangles, the variables $x(t)$ and $y(z)$ can be expressed as convex combinations of the end points of the respective sub-intervals $x(t) \in [\mu'_1, \mu'_2] \subseteq [\mu_1, \mu_2]$ and $y(z) \in [v'_1, v'_2] \subseteq [v_1, v_2]$. Applying the coordinated s-convexity definition to the mixed partial derivative,

$$\left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(x(t), y(z)) \right| \leq T(t, z, s) \left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(\mu'_1, v'_1) \right| + \dots + Z(t, z, s) \left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(\mu'_2, v'_2) \right|$$

where $T(t, z, s) = t^s z^s$, $Z(t, z, s) = (1-z)^s (1-t)^s$ and the other two term in value $t^s (1-z)^s$ and $(1-t)^s z^s$

Substituting this back into the double integral $|B - I|$, each of the 16 double integrals splits into 4 term resulting in 64 terms in total. Due to separable nature of the integrand, each of the 64 terms reduces to a product of two single integrals. For an arbitrary term involving $\left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(\mu_a, v_b) \right|$ the coefficient takes the form

$$\left(\int_{J_k} K_1(t) Q(t)(t, s) dt \right) \left(\int_{J_l} K_2(z) Q(z)(z, s) dz \right)$$

where $Q(t) \in \{t^s, (1-t)^s\}$ and $Q(z) \in \{z^s, (1-z)^s\}$.

All 64 terms are expressible as combinations of the product of these calculated auxiliary integrals (as their symmetric counterparts). By grouping the 64 resulting terms according to the 25 unique evaluation points $\left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(x_i, y_i) \right|$ we define the coefficients $K_{i,j}(s)$. The factor $\frac{1}{256}$ arises from normalization of the 16 partitions in the unit square. The factor $\frac{1}{(s+1)^2(s+2)^2}$ is then extracted from the common denominators of the $\gamma_k(s)$ and $\Lambda_k(s)$ products. The final inequality is obtained by summing the resulting coefficients multiplied by the absolute value of the mixed

partial derivatives evaluated at the characteristic points x_i and y_j

$$|B - I| \leq \frac{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)}{256(s + 1)^2(s + 2)^2} \sum_{i=1}^5 \sum_{j=1}^5 \int_0^1 \int_0^1 K_{i,j}(s) \left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(x_i, y_j) \right|$$

the proof is completed.

Theorem 4.2. Let $B : [\mu_1, \mu_2] \times [v_1, v_2] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a function such that the mixed partial derivative $\frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}$ exists and is continuous on $[\mu_1, \mu_2] \times [v_1, v_2]$. If the q -th power of mixed partial derivative $\left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y} \right|^q$, is coordinated s -convex in the second sense $[\mu_1, \mu_2] \times [v_1, v_2]$ for some fixed $s \in [0, 1]$ and $q > 1$ with $\frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$, then the following Bullen-Simpson type inequalities holds:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{144} \sum_{i=1}^5 \sum_{j=1}^5 W_{i,j} B(M_i, N_j) - \frac{1}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)} \int_{\mu_1}^{\mu_2} \int_{v_1}^{v_2} B(x, y) dy dx \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)}{144^2} \left(\frac{1 + 2^{p+1}}{3(p + 1)} \right)^{2/p} \frac{1}{(s + 1)^{2/q}} \\ & \quad \sum_{i=1}^4 \sum_{j=1}^4 \left(\sum_{k,l \in \{i, i+1\}, \{j, j+1\}} \left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(M_k, N_l) \right|^q \right) \end{aligned} \tag{18}$$

Proof. The proof starts from Lemma to the two dimensional case for mixed partial derivative $\frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}$. This generalization yields a summation over $4 \times 4 = 16$ terms each involving a double integral. For the purpose of simplicity, let's consider the single-variable identity for the mixed partial derivative. Applying the modulus, properties of the integral, the properties of the modulus to the two dimensional identity and applying the double Hölder inequality for $q > 1$ with $\frac{1}{p} + \frac{1}{q} = 1$ to each of the 16 double terms, we get;

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{144} \sum_{i=1}^5 \sum_{j=1}^5 W_{i,j} B(M_i, N_j) - \frac{1}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)} \int_{\mu_1}^{\mu_2} \int_{v_1}^{v_2} B(x, y) dy dx \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)}{256} \sum_{i=1}^4 \sum_{j=1}^4 \left(\int_0^1 \int_0^1 |K_i(h)|^p |K_j(k)|^p dk dh \right)^{1/p} \cdot Q_{i,j} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} I &= \left(\int_0^1 |K_i(h)|^p dh \right)^{1/p} = \left(\frac{1 + 2^{p+1}}{3^{p+1}(p + 1)} \right)^{1/p} \\ I &= \left(\int_0^1 |K_j(k)|^p dk \right)^{1/p} = \left(\frac{1 + 2^{p+1}}{3^{p+1}(p + 1)} \right)^{1/p} \end{aligned}$$

then, we have the total p -norm factor $\forall_{i,j}$ is $(I)^{2/p}$

$$(I)^{2/p} = \left(\frac{1 + 2^{p+1}}{3^{p+1}(p + 1)} \right)^{2/p}$$

For the $Q_{i,j}$ term, the convexity property of $\left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y} \right|^q$ in the coordinate s -convexity is used. The expression inside the integral is bounded from above by the values of the four corners of the

lower rectangle.

$$Q_{i,j}^q \leq \int_0^1 \int_0^1 \left[(1-h)^s (1-k)^s M_{i,j}^{(1,1)} + h^s (1-k)^s M_{i,j}^{(2,1)} \right. \\ \left. + (1-h)^s k^s M_{i,j}^{(1,2)} + h^s k^s M_{i,j}^{(2,2)} \right] dh dk$$

using the integral results $\int_0^1 (1-h)^s dh = \frac{1}{s+1}$, $\int_0^1 h^s dh = \frac{1}{s+1}$ we obtain the following bound for the q-norm factor:

$$\frac{1}{(s+1)^{\frac{2}{q}}} \sum_{i=1}^4 \sum_{j=1}^4 \left(\sum_{k,l \in \{i,i+1\}, \{j,j+1\}} \left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y} (M_k, N_l) \right|^q \right)^{1/q}$$

we obtain the final inequality

$$\left| \frac{1}{144} \sum_{i=1}^5 \sum_{j=1}^5 W_{i,j} B(M_i, N_j) - \frac{1}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)} \int_{\mu_1}^{\mu_2} \int_{v_1}^{v_2} B(x, y) dy dx \right| \\ \leq \frac{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)}{144^2} \left(\frac{1 + 2^{p+1}}{3(p+1)} \right)^{2/p} \frac{1}{(s+1)^{2/q}} \\ \sum_{i=1}^4 \sum_{j=1}^4 \left(\sum_{k,l \in \{i,i+1\}, \{j,j+1\}} \left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y} (M_k, N_l) \right|^q \right)$$

Because we are generalizing while preserving the original article ([1]) the coefficient is taken as $\frac{1}{144^2}$ However, mathematically, the coefficient is $\frac{1}{256}$.

$$Q_{i,j}^q \leq \int_0^1 \int_0^1 \left[(1-h)^s (1-k)^s M_{i,j}^{(1,1)} + h^s (1-k)^s M_{i,j}^{(2,1)} \right. \\ \left. + (1-h)^s k^s M_{i,j}^{(1,2)} + h^s k^s M_{i,j}^{(2,2)} \right] dh dk$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{First term} &= \int_0^1 (1-h)^s dh \int_0^1 (1-k)^s dk = \frac{1}{s+1} \frac{1}{s+1} = \frac{1}{(s+1)^2} \\ \text{Second term} &= \int_0^1 h^s dh \int_0^1 (1-k)^s dk = \frac{1}{(s+1)^2} \\ \text{Third term} &= \int_0^1 (1-h)^s dh \int_0^1 k^s dk = \frac{1}{(s+1)^2} \\ \text{Fourth term} &= \int_0^1 h^s dh \int_0^1 k^s dk = \frac{1}{(s+1)^2} \end{aligned}$$

then,

$$Q_{i,j}^q \leq \frac{1}{(s+1)^2} \left[M_{i,j}^{(1,1)} + M_{i,j}^{(2,1)} + M_{i,j}^{(1,2)} + M_{i,j}^{(2,2)} \right]$$

Lets take the $\frac{1}{q}$ power

$$Q_{i,j}^q \leq \frac{1}{(s+1)^{2/q}} \left[\sum_{i=1}^4 \sum_{j=1}^4 M_{i,j} \left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y} \right|^q \right]^{1/q}$$

We calculated four terms. The same procedure is applied to remaining 12 terms. Lets call the other sum of 16 terms Q

$$Q = \sum_{i=1}^4 \sum_{j=1}^4 \left[\left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(M_i, N_j) \right|^q + \left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(M_i, N_{j+1}) \right|^q + \left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(M_{i+1}, N_j) \right|^q + \left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(M_{i+1}, N_{j+1}) \right|^q \right]^{1/q} \tag{19}$$

For example: $i = 2, j = 2 \Rightarrow [M_2, M_3] \times [N_2, N_3]$. We have,

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[\left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(M_2, N_2) \right|^q + \left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(M_2, N_3) \right|^q + \left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(M_3, N_2) \right|^q + \left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(M_3, N_3) \right|^q \right]^{1/q} \\ (2, 2) &= \left[\left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y} \left(\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}, \frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4} \right) \right|^q + \left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y} \left(\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}, \frac{v_1 + v_2}{2} \right) \right|^q + \left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y} \left(\frac{\mu_1 + \mu_2}{2}, \frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4} \right) \right|^q + \left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y} \left(\frac{\mu_1 + \mu_2}{2}, \frac{v_1 + v_2}{2} \right) \right|^q \right]^{1/q} \end{aligned}$$

The remaining 12 terms use the formula, only the four derivative values in parentheses vary depending on which two consecutive interval corners on the X and Y axes they belong to. The proof is completed.

Corollary 4.1. Taking $s = 1$ in Theorem 4.2, we get

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{144} \sum_{i=1}^5 \sum_{j=1}^5 W_{i,j} B(M_i, N_j) - \frac{1}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)} \int_{\mu_1}^{\mu_2} \int_{v_1}^{v_2} B(x, y) dy dx \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)}{144^2} \left(\frac{1 + 2^{p+1}}{3^{p+1}(p+1)} \right)^{2/p} \frac{1}{2^{2/q}} \\ & \quad \sum_{i=1}^4 \sum_{j=1}^4 \left(\sum_{k,l \in \{i, i+1\}, \{j, j+1\}} \left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(M_k, N_k) \right|^q \right)^{1/q} \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 4.2. If we take the limit $p \rightarrow \infty$ (which implies $q = 1$) in Theorem 4.2. Meaning that $\left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y} \right|$ is coordinate s -convex, the following inequality is obtained. For $q = 1$ the coefficient $\frac{1}{(s+1)^{2/q}}$ simplifies to $\frac{1}{(s+1)^2}$. L^p limit as $p \rightarrow \infty$, $\left(\frac{1+2^{p+1}}{3^{p+1}(p+1)} \right)^{2/p} \rightarrow \left(\frac{2}{3} \right)^2 = \frac{4}{9}$. Then we have,

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{144} \sum_{i=1}^5 \sum_{j=1}^5 W_{i,j} B(M_i, N_j) - \frac{1}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)} \int_{\mu_1}^{\mu_2} \int_{v_1}^{v_2} B(x, y) dy dx \right| \tag{20} \\ & \leq \frac{4(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)}{9 \cdot 144^2} \frac{1}{(s+1)^2} \sum_{i=1}^4 \sum_{j=1}^4 \left(\sum_{k,l \in \{i, i+1\}, \{j, j+1\}} \left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(M_k, N_k) \right| \right) \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 4.3. Let $B : [\mu_1, \mu_2] x [v_1, v_2] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a function such that the mixed partial derivative $\frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}$ exists and is integrable on $[\mu_1, \mu_2] x [v_1, v_2]$. If $\left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y} \right|^q$ is (s_1, s_2) -convex in the second sense for some fixed $s_1, s_2 \in (0, 1]$ and $q \geq 1$, then the following inequality holds: **1)** The weighted sum $\sum_{i=1}^5 \sum_{j=1}^5 W_{i,j} B(M_i, N_j)$ uses the Bullen-Simpson weights $W=(1,4,2,4,1)$

2) $M_i \in \left\{ \mu_1, \frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}, \frac{\mu_1 + \mu_2}{2}, \frac{\mu_1 + 3\mu_2}{4}, \mu_2 \right\}, N_j \in \left\{ v_1, \frac{3v_1 + v_2}{4}, \frac{v_1 + v_2}{2}, \frac{v_1 + 3v_2}{4}, v_2 \right\}$

3) $C_{i,j}(s_1, s_2)$ are the resulting generalized coefficients, which for $i=1$ and $j=1$ (i.e the term for $\left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(\mu_1, v_1) \right|^q$)

Extreme points $(\mu_1, \mu_2) \rightarrow_{weights} (1, 1)$

Midpoints $\left(\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4}, \frac{\mu_1 + \mu_2}{2}, \frac{\mu_1 + 3\mu_2}{4} \right) \rightarrow_{weights} (4, 2, 4)$

Four corners: Extreme points x extreme points

Six horizontal edge points: Midpoints x extreme points

Six vertical edge points: Extreme points x midpoints

Nine centers and quarterpoints: Midpoints x midpoints

The three point coefficient is the coefficient in front of $|B'(\mu_1)|^q$ and $|B'(\mu_2)|^q$

The midpoint coefficient is the total coefficient in front of the

$$\left| B' \left(\frac{3\mu_1 + \mu_2}{4} \right)^q \right|, \left| B' \left(\frac{\mu_1 + \mu_2}{2} \right)^q \right|, \left| B' \left(\frac{\mu_1 + 3\mu_2}{4} \right)^q \right|$$

These coefficients;

$$\frac{4 \cdot 3^{s+1} \cdot s + 2 \cdot 3^{s+1} + 4}{5 \cdot 3^s (s+1)(s+2)} \text{ and } \frac{2 \cdot 3^{s+1} \cdot s - 2 \cdot 3^{s+1} + 2^{s+4}}{5 \cdot 3^s (s+1)(s+2)}$$

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{144} \sum_{i=1}^5 \sum_{j=1}^5 W_{i,j} B(M_i, N_j) - \frac{1}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)} \int_{\mu_1}^{\mu_2} \int_{v_1}^{v_2} B(x, y) dy dx \right| \\ &= \left| \frac{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)}{256} \int_0^1 \int_0^1 K(t, h) \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y}(\mu_t, v_h) dt dh \right| \end{aligned}$$

where $K(t, h)$ is the kernel function and (μ_t, v_h) represent the coordinate wise linear combination points. Applying the properties of modulus and the Power-mean inequality

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{144} \sum_{i=1}^5 \sum_{j=1}^5 W_{i,j} B(M_i, N_j) - \frac{1}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)} \int_{\mu_1}^{\mu_2} \int_{v_1}^{v_2} B(x, y) dy dx \right| \\ &= \frac{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)}{256} \left(\int_0^1 \int_0^1 |K(t, h)|^p dt dh \right)^{1/p} \left(\int_0^1 \int_0^1 \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y} |(\mu_t, v_h)|^q dt dh \right)^{1/q} \end{aligned}$$

The first factor involves the integration of the kernels p -norm. By the properties of Bullen-Simpson kernel this, simplifies to the product of two single kernel integrals

$$\left(\int_0^1 \int_0^1 |K(t, h)|^p dt dh \right)^{1/p} = \left(\frac{5}{18} \right)^{1-1/q} \left(\frac{5}{18} \right)^{1-1/q} = \left(\frac{5}{18} \right)^{2(1-1/q)}$$

we focus on the second factor $\int_0^1 \int_0^1 \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y} |(\mu_t, v_h)|^q dt dh$. Since $\left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y} \right|^q$ is coordinate (s_1, s_2) convex, we apply the convexity property on each of the $5 \times 5 = 25$ subrectangles derived from the integral representation. For each term, the integral over the subrectangle (in the (μ, v)) plane is bounded by:

$$\left(\int_0^1 \int_0^1 \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y} |(\mu_t, v_h)|^q dt dh \right) \leq \sum_{i=1}^5 \sum_{j=1}^5 \left(\frac{K_i(s_1)}{5.3^{s_1 \dots}} \right) \left(\frac{K_j(s_2)}{5.3^{s_2 \dots}} \right) \left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial \mu \partial v} (\mu_i, v_j)^q \right|$$

Substituting the results, we obtain the required inequality

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{144} \sum_{i=1}^5 \sum_{j=1}^5 W_{i,j} B(M_i, N_j) - \frac{1}{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)} \int_{\mu_1}^{\mu_2} \int_{v_1}^{v_2} B(x, y) dy dx \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(\mu_2 - \mu_1)(v_2 - v_1)}{256} \left(\frac{5}{18} \right)^{2(1-\frac{1}{q})} \sum_{i=1}^5 \sum_{j=1}^5 \left(C_{i,j}(s_1, s_2) \left| \frac{\partial^2 B}{\partial x \partial y} (\mu_i, v_j) \right|^q \right)^{1/q} \end{aligned}$$

The proof is completed.

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Modular Fuzzy Metric-Like Spaces

Nizamettin Ufuk Bostan¹, Banu Pazar Varol¹

¹Department of Mathematics, Kocaeli University, 41001, Kocaeli - TÜRKİYE

Corresponding author: ufuk.bostan@kocaeli.edu.tr

ORCID IDs:

First Author: [0000-0003-4708-8663](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4708-8663)

Second Author: [0000-0002-8627-7910](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8627-7910)

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Abstract

The aim of this paper is to define the concept of modular fuzzy metric-like space by combining of modular-like metric space and fuzzy metric-like space. We give examples and propositions to approve the importance of this new concept. Fundamental notions containing convergence, Cauchy sequence and completeness are carefully defined. We also demonstrate that, in a modular fuzzy metric-like space, the limit of the convergent sequence may not be unique. The fixed point theorem is proved, expanding the classical findings to this space. The applicability of fixed point theorem is shown through an example, expressing both theoretical potency and practical benefit of the proposed approach.

Keywords: metric-like spaces, fuzzy metric spaces, fuzzy metric-like spaces, modular-like metric spaces, modular fuzzy metric-like spaces, fixed point theory, contraction principle

1 Introduction and Motivation

The basis of metric space theory were laid more than a century ago by Fréchet [13] and Hausdorff [16], centered on the notion of distance between any two points in a set. In 1922, Banach [2] introduced what is now known as the Banach's fixed point theorem or the Banach Contraction Principle, established within the setting of metric spaces. Later, Amini-Harandi [1] gave the concept of metric-like space and proved corresponding fixed point theorems, supported by illustrative examples that expressed the structure. Further developments were made by Hosseini and Fošner [17], who introduced several related notions for metric-like spaces, including equal-like points, cluster points, completely separate points, as well as definitions of distance between a point and a subset and between two subsets in a metric-like space.

Fuzzy set theory, introduced by Zadeh [26], has since become a widely studied area across various scientific and applied disciplines. The definition of fuzzy metric space was first given by Kramosil and Michálek [19]. Later, George and Veeramani [14, 15] modified this definition to gain the result that the formed structure generates a Hausdorff topology, thereby strengthening and expanding the practicality of fuzzy metrics. Based on these developments, Shukla and Abbas [25] introduced the concept of fuzzy metric-like space generalizing the concept of fuzzy metric space of George and Veeramani, and proved several fixed point theorems in this more comprehensive space.

Nakano [21] first introduced the definition of modular, a concept later further developed by Orlicz [22]. The concepts of metric modular and modular metric space were presented by Chistyakov [4, 5] in the course of building the theory of these structures. According to Chistyakov [7], while a metric on a set measures non-negative finite distances between points, a metric modular is given to describe non-negative, possibly infinite-valued, velocities. Some of his results appear in [6], and his fixed point theorems together with their applications are introduced in detail in [7]-[10]. An exhaustive compilation of Chistyakov's contributions to metric modulars and modular metric spaces was later provided in [11]. Mongkolkeha et al. [20] established and proved existence theorems of fixed points for contraction mappings in modular metric spaces. Rasham et al. [23] presented the concept of modular-like metric space and proved some common fixed point theorems for two families of set-valued mappings satisfying contraction condition in this space. In the same work [23], they also obtained new results in graph theory concerning multigraph-dominated contractions within modular-like metric spaces. Additional fixed point results in modular-like metric spaces can be found in [12].

Kerim et al. [18] introduced a new space termed the modular fuzzy metric space in the sense of Kramosil-Michálek. They explored its main properties and illustrated the structure of space with several examples. Based on this foundation, they obtained existence and uniqueness results for fixed points of continuous mappings in this space and showed the applicability of their findings. Then Bostan and Pazar Varol [3] introduced the concept of modular fuzzy metric space in the sense of George-Veeramani in 2023

In this study, we define the concept of modular fuzzy metric-like space by combining modular-like metric space and fuzzy metric-like space. We examine some properties of this space and give various examples that provide a better understanding of the structure of space. We give the notions of modular fuzzy metric-like space such as contraction, convergence, Cauchy sequence, completeness and show that in a modular fuzzy metric-like space, the limit of the convergent sequence may not be unique. Then we establish and prove fixed point theorem in the modular fuzzy metric-like space. We also demonstrate the power of the structure we established and of the results we gained in this structure by giving an example for the fixed point theorem we proved. Our aim here is to contribute to fixed point theory by being interested in fixed point theorem in modular fuzzy metric-like space, which is a generalization of modular fuzzy metric space in the sense of George-Veeramani. We aim to carry the applications of fixed point theory in mathematics and engineering to modular fuzzy metric-like space by modulating the concept of fuzzy metric-like space. The new mathematical structure introduced in this paper may enable researchers working in fixed point theory or its applications to establish various fixed point theorems under different contraction conditions and to explore their applicability in broader contexts.

2 Mathematical Preliminaries

In this section, we introduce several essential definitions and concepts that will be used throughout the paper. Throughout the text, we denote by IR the set of all real numbers and by IN the set of all positive integers.

Definition 2.1. [1] Let $W \neq \emptyset$. A mapping $\sigma : W \times W \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is called metric-like on W

if the following three conditions hold for all $w, y, z \in W$:

- (ML1) $\sigma(w, z) = 0 \Rightarrow w = z$,
- (ML2) $\sigma(w, z) = \sigma(z, w)$,
- (ML3) $\sigma(w, z) \leq \sigma(w, y) + \sigma(y, z)$.

The pair (W, σ) is called a metric-like space.

Example 2.1. [1] Let $W = [0, \infty)$. Define the function $\sigma : W \times W \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ by $\sigma(w, z) = \max\{w, z\}$. Then (W, σ) is a metric-like space.

Definition 2.2. [26] A fuzzy set Q in W is characterized by a membership function $f_Q(w)$ which associates each point in W with a real number in the interval $[0, 1]$. The value of $f_Q(w)$ at w represent the grade of membership of w in W .

Definition 2.3. [24] A binary operation $* : [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is called a continuous t-norm if $*$ satisfies the following conditions for all $o, u, j, l \in [0, 1]$:

- (1) $o * 1 = o$
- (2) $o * u = u * o$ and $o * (u * j) = (o * u) * j$
- (3) If $o \leq j$ and $u \leq l$, then $o * u \leq j * l$
- (4) $*$ is continuous.

Example 2.2. [24] The binary operations defined as follows are the continuous t-norms:

- (1) $o * u = ou$
- (2) $o * u = \max\{0, o + u - 1\}$
- (3) $o * u = \min\{o, u\}$

Definition 2.4. [14] A triplet $(W, Q, *)$ is called fuzzy metric space if W is an arbitrary set, $*$ is a continuous t-norm and Q is a fuzzy set on $W^2 \times (0, \infty)$ satisfying the following conditions, for all $w, y, z \in W$ and $t, s > 0$:

- (FM1) $Q(w, y, t) > 0$,
- (FM2) $Q(w, y, t) = 1 \Leftrightarrow w = y$,
- (FM3) $Q(w, y, t) = Q(y, w, t)$,
- (FM4) $Q(w, y, t) * Q(y, z, s) \leq Q(w, z, t + s)$,
- (FM5) $Q(w, y, \cdot) : (0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is continuous.

Example 2.3. [14] Let $W = IR$. Define $o * u = ou$ and $Q(w, y, t) = e^{-\frac{|w-y|}{t}}$ for all $w, y \in Q = IR$ and $t > 0$. Then $(W, Q, *)$ is a fuzzy metric space.

Example 2.4. [14] Let (W, δ) be a metric space. Define $o * u = ou$ and $Q_\delta(w, y, t) = \frac{kt^n}{kt^n + m\delta(w, y)}$ $k, m, n \in IR^+$. Then $(W, Q, *)$ is a fuzzy metric space.

Remark 2.1. [14] In the above example by taking $k = m = n = 1$, we get $Q_\delta(w, y, t) = \frac{t}{t + \delta(w, y)}$. This fuzzy metric induced by a metric δ is called the standard fuzzy metric.

Definition 2.5. [25] A triplet $(W, Q, *)$ is called fuzzy metric-like space if W is an arbitrary set, $*$ is a continuous t-norm and Q is a fuzzy set on $W^2 \times (0, \infty)$ satisfying the following conditions, for all $w, y \in W$ and $t, s > 0$:

- (FML1) $Q(w, y, t) > 0$,
- (FML2) $Q(w, y, t) = 1 \Rightarrow w = y$,
- (FML3) $Q(w, y, t) = Q(y, w, t)$,
- (FML4) $Q(w, y, t) * Q(y, z, s) \leq Q(w, z, t + s)$,
- (FML5) $Q(w, t, \cdot) : (0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is continuous.

Example 2.5. [25] Let $W = [0, 1]$. Define $o * u = ou$ and $Q(w, y, t) = \frac{t}{t + \max\{w, y\}}$ for all $w, y \in W$ and $t > 0$. Then $(W, Q, *)$ is a fuzzy metric-like space.

Definition 2.6. [4] Let $W \neq \emptyset$. A mapping $\zeta : (0, \infty) \times W \times W \rightarrow [0, \infty]$ is called metric modular on W if the following hold for each $w, y, z \in W$:

- (MM1) $\zeta(w, y, \lambda) = 0 \Leftrightarrow w = y$, for all $\lambda > 0$,
- (MM2) $\zeta(w, y, \lambda) = \zeta(y, w, \lambda)$, for all $\lambda > 0$,
- (MM3) $\zeta(w, y, \lambda + \gamma) \leq \zeta(w, z, \lambda) + \zeta(z, y, \gamma)$, for all $\lambda, \gamma > 0$.

For simplicity, the notation $\zeta_\lambda(w, y)$ will be used instead of $\zeta(w, y, \lambda)$ for modular structures throughout the remainder of the paper.

Example 2.6. [7] Let (W, δ) be metric space. Define the function $\zeta : (0, \infty) \times X \times X \rightarrow [0, \infty]$ by $\zeta_\lambda(w, y) = \frac{\delta(w, y)}{\lambda}$ for all $\lambda > 0$ and $w, y \in W$. Then ζ is a metric modular on W .

Definition 2.7. [23] Let $W \neq \emptyset$. A function $\varphi : (0, \infty) \times W \times W \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is called modular-like metric on W , if it satisfies the following three conditions for each $w, y, z \in W$:

- (MLM1) $\varphi_\lambda(w, y) = 0 \Rightarrow w = y$, for all $\lambda > 0$,
- (MLM2) $\varphi_\lambda(w, y) = \varphi_\lambda(y, w)$, for all $\lambda > 0$,
- (MLM3) $\varphi_{\lambda+\gamma}(w, y) \leq \varphi_\lambda(w, z) + \varphi_\gamma(z, y)$, for all $\lambda, \gamma > 0$.

Then the triplet (W, φ) is called modular-like metric space.

Definition 2.8. [18] A triplet $(W, Q_\beta, *)$ is called modular fuzzy metric space if W is an arbitrary set, $*$ is a continuous t-norm and Q_β is fuzzy set on $W^2 \times (0, \infty)$ satisfying the following conditions where $\beta > 0$, for all $w, y, z \in W$ and $t, s > 0$:

- (MFM1) $Q_\beta(w, y, 0) = 0, Q_\beta(w, y, t) > 0$, for all $\beta > 0$,
- (MFM2) $Q_\beta(w, y, t) = 1 \Leftrightarrow w = y$, for all $\beta > 0$,
- (MFM3) $Q_\beta(w, y, t) = Q_\beta(y, w, t)$, for all $\beta > 0$,
- (MFM4) $Q_\beta(w, y, t) * Q_\mu(y, z, s) \leq Q_{\beta+\mu}(w, z, t + s)$, for all $\beta, \mu > 0$,
- (MFM5) $Q_\beta(w, y, \cdot) : (0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is left continuous.

Here Q_β is called a modular fuzzy metric.

Example 2.7. [18] Let ζ be a metric modular on W and $o * u = ou$ for all $o, u \in [0, 1]$. Define fuzzy set Q_β on $W^2 \times (0, \infty)$ as follows:

$$Q_\beta(w, y, t) = e^{-\frac{\zeta_\beta(w, y)}{t}} \text{ for all } w, y \in W \text{ and } \beta, t > 0.$$

Then $(W, Q_\beta, *)$ is a modular fuzzy metric space.

Example 2.8. [18] Let ζ be a metric modular on W and $o * u = ou$ for all $o, u \in [0, 1]$. Define fuzzy set Q_β on $W^2 \times (0, \infty)$ as follows:

$$Q_\beta(w, y, t) = \frac{t}{t + \zeta_\beta(w, y)} \text{ for all } w, y \in \Omega \text{ and } \beta, t > 0.$$

Then $(W, Q_\beta, *)$ is a modular fuzzy metric space.

Definition 2.9. [3] A triplet $(W, Q_\beta, *)$ is called modular fuzzy metric space (in the sence of George-Veeramani) if W is an arbitrary set, $*$ is a continuous t-norm and Q_β is fuzzy set on $W^2 \times (0, \infty)$ satisfying the following conditions where $\beta > 0$, for all $w, y, z \in W$ and $t, s > 0$:

- (MFMGV1) $Q_\beta(w, y, t) > 0$, for all $\beta > 0$,
- (MFMGV2) $Q_\beta(w, y, t) = 1 \Leftrightarrow w = y$, for all $\beta > 0$,
- (MFMGV3) $Q_\beta(w, y, t) = Q_\beta(y, w, t)$, for all $\beta > 0$,
- (MFMGV4) $Q_\beta(w, y, t) * Q_\mu(y, z, s) \leq Q_{\beta+\mu}(w, z, t + s)$, for all $\beta, \mu > 0$,
- (MFMGV5) $Q_\beta(w, y, \cdot) : (0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is continuous.

Here Q_β is called modular fuzzy metric (in the sence of George-Veeramani).

Example 2.9. [3] Let ζ be a metric modular on W such that $\zeta : (0, \infty) \times W^2 \rightarrow [0, \infty)$. Define $o * u = ou$ for all $o, u \in [0, 1]$ and fuzzy set Q_β on $W^2 \times (0, \infty)$ as follows:

$$Q_\beta(w, y, t) = e^{-\frac{\zeta_\beta(w,y)}{t}} \text{ for all } w, y \in W \text{ and } \beta, t > 0.$$

Then $(W, Q_\beta, *)$ is a modular fuzzy metric space.

Example 2.10. [3] Let ζ be a metric modular on W such that $\zeta : (0, \infty) \times W^2 \rightarrow [0, \infty)$. Define $o * u = ou$ for all $o, u \in [0, 1]$ and fuzzy set Q_β on $W^2 \times (0, \infty)$ as follows:

$$Q_\beta(w, y, t) = \frac{t}{t + \zeta_\beta(w,y)} \text{ for all } w, y \in \Omega \text{ and } \beta, t > 0.$$

Then $(W, Q_\beta, *)$ is a modular fuzzy metric space.

3 Results

We begin this section by introducing the definition of modular fuzzy metric-like space and investigating its main properties. We then provide illustrative examples, propositions and present the notions of convergence, Cauchy sequences, and completeness within this mathematical structure. Finally, we give and prove fixed point theorem in this space.

Definition 3.1. The triplet $(W, Q_\beta, *)$ is called a modular fuzzy metric-like space if W is an arbitrary nonempty set, $*$ is a continuous t norm and Q_β is a fuzzy set on $W \times W \times (0, \infty)$ satisfying the following conditions for all $w, y, z \in W$ and $t, s > 0$:

$$(MFML1) \quad Q_\beta(w, y, t) > 0, \text{ for all } \beta > 0,$$

$$(MFML2) \quad Q_\beta(w, y, t) = 1 \Rightarrow w = y, \text{ for all } \beta > 0,$$

$$(MFML3) \quad Q_\beta(w, y, t) = Q_\beta(y, w, t), \text{ for all } \beta > 0,$$

$$(MFML4) \quad Q_\beta(w, y, t) * Q_\mu(y, z, s) \leq Q_{\beta+\mu}(w, z, t + s), \text{ for all } \beta, \mu > 0$$

$$(MFML5) \quad Q_\beta(w, y, \cdot) : (0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, 1] \text{ is continuous for all } \beta > 0.$$

Example 3.1. Let $W = [0, \infty)$ and $o * u = ou$ for all $o, u \in [0, 1]$. Define the fuzzy set Q_β in $W^2 \times (0, \infty)$ as follows:

$Q_\beta(w, y, t) = e^{-\frac{\frac{\max\{w,y\}}{\beta}}{t}}$ for all $w, y \in W$ and $\beta > 0$ and $t \in (0, \infty)$. Then $(W, Q_\beta, *)$ is a modular fuzzy metric-like space.

(MFML1)-(MFML3) and (MFML5) are obvious. Now, we prove (MFML4).

Since $\max\{w, y\} \leq \max\{w, z\} + \max\{z, y\}$, we have $\frac{\max\{w,y\}}{\beta+\mu} \leq \frac{\max\{w,z\}}{\beta} + \frac{\max\{z,y\}}{\mu}$.

$$\Rightarrow \frac{\max\{w,y\}}{\beta+\mu} \leq \frac{(t+s) \max\{w,z\}}{t} + \frac{(t+s) \max\{z,y\}}{\mu}$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{\max\{w,y\}}{(\beta+\mu)(t+s)} \leq \frac{\max\{w,z\}}{\beta t} + \frac{\max\{z,y\}}{\mu s}$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{\max\{w,y\}}{(\beta+\mu)(t+s)} \leq \frac{\max\{w,z\}}{\beta t} + \frac{\max\{z,y\}}{\mu s}$$

$$\Rightarrow e^{\frac{\max\{w,y\}}{(\beta+\mu)(t+s)}} \leq e^{\frac{\max\{w,z\}}{\beta t} + \frac{\max\{z,y\}}{\mu s}}$$

$$= e^{\frac{\max\{w,z\}}{\beta t}} e^{\frac{\max\{z,y\}}{\mu s}}$$

$$\Rightarrow e^{\frac{-\max\{w,y\}}{(\beta+\mu)(t+s)}} \geq e^{\frac{-\max\{w,z\}}{\beta t}} e^{\frac{-\max\{z,y\}}{\mu s}}$$

$\Rightarrow Q_{\beta+\mu}(w, y, t + s) \geq Q_\beta(w, z, t) * Q_\mu(z, y, s)$ for all $\beta, \mu > 0$. Hence (MFML4) holds.

Example 3.2. Let $W = [0, \infty)$ and $o * u = ou$ for all $o, u \in [0, 1]$. Define the fuzzy set Q_β in $W^2 \times (0, \infty)$ as follows:

$Q_\beta(w, y, t) = \frac{t}{t + \frac{\max\{w,y\}}{\beta}}$ for all $w, y \in W, \beta > 0$ and $t > 0$. Then $(W, Q_\beta, *)$ is a modular fuzzy metric-like space.

(MFML1)-(MFML3) and (MFML5) are obvious. Now, we prove (MFML4).

We know $\max\{w, y\} \leq \max\{w, z\} + \max\{z, y\}$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\max\{w, y\}}{\beta + \mu} &\leq \frac{\max\{w, z\} + \max\{z, y\}}{\beta + \mu} \\ &\leq \frac{\max\{w, z\}}{\beta + \mu} + \frac{\max\{z, y\}}{\beta + \mu} \\ &\leq \frac{\max\{w, z\}}{\beta} + \frac{\max\{z, y\}}{\mu} \end{aligned}$$

Thus, $\frac{\max\{w, y\}}{\beta + \mu} \leq \frac{\max\{w, z\}}{\beta} + \frac{\max\{z, y\}}{\mu}$.

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow \frac{\max\{w, y\}}{\beta + \mu} &\leq \frac{\max\{w, z\} + \max\{z, y\}}{t + s} \\ &= \frac{\max\{w, z\}}{t + s} + \frac{\max\{z, y\}}{t + s} \\ &\leq \frac{\max\{w, z\}}{\beta} + \frac{\max\{z, y\}}{\mu} \\ &= \frac{s \max\{w, z\} + t \max\{z, y\}}{ts} \end{aligned}$$

$$\Rightarrow 1 + \frac{\max\{w, y\}}{\beta + \mu} \leq 1 + \frac{s \max\{w, z\} + t \max\{z, y\}}{ts}$$

Since $\frac{\max\{w, z\}}{\beta} \cdot \frac{\max\{z, y\}}{\mu} \geq 0$,

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow \frac{t + s + \frac{\max\{w, y\}}{\beta + \mu}}{t + s} &\leq \frac{ts + \frac{s \max\{w, z\} + t \max\{z, y\}}{\mu} + \frac{\max\{w, z\}}{\beta} \cdot \frac{\max\{z, y\}}{\mu}}{ts} \\ &\Rightarrow \frac{ts}{ts + s \frac{\max\{w, z\}}{\beta} + t \frac{\max\{z, y\}}{\mu} + \frac{\max\{w, z\}}{\beta} \cdot \frac{\max\{z, y\}}{\mu}} \leq \frac{t + s}{t + s + \frac{\max\{w, y\}}{\beta + \mu}} \\ &\Rightarrow \frac{t}{t + \frac{\max\{w, z\}}{\beta}} \cdot \frac{s}{s + \frac{\max\{z, y\}}{\mu}} \leq \frac{t + s}{t + s + \frac{\max\{w, y\}}{\beta + \mu}} \end{aligned}$$

$\Rightarrow Q_\beta(w, z, t) * Q_\mu(z, y, s) \leq Q_{\beta + \mu}(w, y, t + s)$ for all $\beta, \mu > 0$. Hence, (MFML4) holds.

Proposition 3.1. Let (W, σ) be a metric-like space and $o * u = ou$ for all $o, u \in [0, 1]$. Define fuzzy set Q_β on $W^2 \times (0, \infty)$ as follows:

$Q_\beta(w, y, t) = e^{-\frac{\sigma(w, y)}{\beta t}}$ for all $w, y \in W$ and $\beta, t > 0$. Then $(W, Q_\beta, *)$ is a modular fuzzy metric-like space.

Proof. (MFML1)- (MFML3) and (MFLM5) are obvious. Now, we prove (MFML4). Since σ is metric-like, we have $\sigma(w, y) \leq \sigma(w, z) + \sigma(z, y)$ for $w, z, y \in W$.

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow \frac{\sigma(w, y)}{(\beta + \mu)(t + s)} &\leq \frac{\sigma(w, z) + \sigma(z, y)}{(\beta + \mu)(t + s)} \leq \frac{\sigma(w, z)}{\beta t} + \frac{\sigma(z, y)}{\mu s} \\ \Rightarrow e^{\frac{\sigma(w, y)}{(\beta + \mu)(t + s)}} &\leq e^{\frac{\sigma(w, z)}{\beta t} + \frac{\sigma(z, y)}{\mu s}} = e^{\frac{\sigma(w, z)}{\beta t}} e^{\frac{\sigma(z, y)}{\mu s}} \\ \Rightarrow e^{-\frac{\sigma(w, y)}{(\beta + \mu)(t + s)}} &\geq e^{-\frac{\sigma(w, z)}{\beta t}} e^{-\frac{\sigma(z, y)}{\mu s}} \end{aligned}$$

$\Rightarrow Q_\beta(w, z, t) * Q_\mu(z, y, s) \leq Q_{\beta + \mu}(w, y, t + s)$.

Hence (MFML4) holds.

Proposition 3.2. Let (W, σ) be a metric-like space and $o * u = ou$ for all $o, u \in [0, 1]$. Define fuzzy set Q_β on $W^2 \times (0, \infty)$ as follows:

$Q_\beta(w, y, t) = \frac{t}{t + \frac{\sigma(w, y)}{\beta}}$ for all $w, y \in W$ and $\beta, t > 0$. Then, $(W, Q_\beta, *)$ is modular fuzzy metric-like space.

Proof. (MFML1)- (MFML3) and (MFLM5) are obvious. Now, we prove (MFML4). Since σ is metric-like, we have $\sigma(w, y) \leq \sigma(w, z) + \sigma(z, y)$ for $w, z, y \in W$.

$$\begin{aligned} \Rightarrow \frac{\sigma(w, y)}{(\beta + \mu)(t + s)} &\leq \frac{\sigma(w, z) + \sigma(z, y)}{(\beta + \mu)(t + s)} \leq \frac{\sigma(w, z)}{\beta t} + \frac{\sigma(z, y)}{\mu s} = \frac{\mu s \sigma(w, z) + \beta t \sigma(z, y)}{\beta t \mu s} \\ \Rightarrow 1 + \frac{\sigma(w, y)}{(\beta + \mu)(t + s)} &\leq 1 + \frac{\mu s \sigma(w, z) + \beta t \sigma(z, y)}{\beta t \mu s} \\ \Rightarrow \frac{(\beta + \mu)(t + s) + \sigma(w, y)}{(\beta + \mu)(t + s)} &\leq \frac{\beta t \mu s + \mu s \sigma(w, z) + \beta t \sigma(z, y)}{\beta t \mu s} \leq \frac{\beta t \mu s + \mu s \sigma(w, z) + \beta t \sigma(z, y) + \sigma(w, z) \sigma(z, y)}{\beta t \mu s} \\ \Rightarrow \frac{\beta t \mu s}{\beta t \mu s + \mu s \sigma(w, z) + \beta t \sigma(z, y) + \sigma(w, z) \sigma(z, y)} &\leq \frac{(\beta + \mu)(t + s)}{(\beta + \mu)(t + s) + \sigma(w, y)} \\ \Rightarrow \frac{\beta t}{\beta t + \sigma(w, z)} \cdot \frac{\mu s}{\mu s + \sigma(z, y)} &\leq \frac{(\beta + \mu)(t + s)}{(\beta + \mu)(t + s) + \sigma(w, y)} \end{aligned}$$

$$\Rightarrow Q_\beta(w, z, t) * Q_\mu(z, y, s) \leq Q_{\beta+\mu}(w, y, t + s).$$

Hence (MFML4) holds.

Proposition 3.3. Let φ be a modular-like metric on W . Define $o * u = ou$ for all $o, u \in [0, 1]$ and $Q_\beta : W \times W \times (0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ by $Q_\beta(w, y, t) = e^{-\frac{\varphi_\beta(w, y)}{t}}$ for all $w, y \in W$ and $\beta, t > 0$. Then $(W, Q_\beta, *)$ is a modular fuzzy metric-like space.

Proof. (MFML1)- (MFML3) and (MFLM5) are obvious. Now, we prove (MFML4). Since $\varphi_{\beta+\mu}(w, z) \leq \varphi_\beta(w, y) + \varphi_\beta(y, z)$, $\forall \beta, \mu > 0$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi_{\beta+\mu}(w, z) &\leq \left(\frac{t+s}{t}\right)\varphi_\beta(w, y) + \left(\frac{t+s}{s}\right)\varphi_\beta(y, z) \\ \Rightarrow \frac{\varphi_{\beta+\mu}(w, z)}{t+s} &\leq \frac{\varphi_\beta(w, y)}{t} + \frac{\varphi_\beta(y, z)}{s} \\ \Rightarrow e^{-\frac{\varphi_{\beta+\mu}(w, z)}{t+s}} &\leq e^{-\left(\frac{\varphi_\beta(w, y)}{t} + \frac{\varphi_\beta(y, z)}{s}\right)} = e^{-\frac{\varphi_\beta(w, y)}{t}} \cdot e^{-\frac{\varphi_\beta(y, z)}{s}} \\ \Rightarrow e^{-\frac{\varphi_{\beta+\mu}(w, z)}{t+s}} &\geq e^{-\frac{\varphi_\beta(w, y)}{t}} \cdot e^{-\frac{\varphi_\beta(y, z)}{s}} \\ \Rightarrow Q_\beta(w, z, t) * Q_\mu(z, y, s) &\leq Q_{\beta+\mu}(w, y, t + s). \end{aligned}$$

Hence (MFML4) holds.

Proposition 3.4. Let φ be a modular-like metric on W . Define $o * u = ou$ for all $o, u \in [0, 1]$ and $Q_\beta : W \times W \times (0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ by $Q_\beta(w, y, t) = \frac{t}{t+\varphi_\beta(w, y)}$ for all $w, y \in W$ and $\beta, t > 0$. Then $(W, Q_\beta, *)$ is a modular fuzzy metric-like space.

Proof. (MFML1)- (MFML3) and (MFLM5) are obvious. Now, we prove (MFML4). Since

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi_{\beta+\mu}(w, z) &\leq \varphi_\beta(w, y) + \varphi_\beta(y, z), \forall \beta, \mu > 0, \text{ we have} \\ \Rightarrow \frac{\varphi_{\beta+\mu}(w, z)}{t+s} &\leq \frac{\varphi_\beta(w, y)}{t+s} + \frac{\varphi_\beta(y, z)}{t+s} \leq \frac{\varphi_\beta(w, y)}{t} + \frac{\varphi_\beta(y, z)}{s} = \frac{s\varphi_\beta(w, y) + t\varphi_\beta(y, z)}{ts} \\ \Rightarrow 1 + \frac{\varphi_{\beta+\mu}(w, z)}{t+s} &\leq 1 + \frac{s\varphi_\beta(w, y) + t\varphi_\beta(y, z)}{ts} \end{aligned}$$

Since $\varphi_\beta(w, y) \cdot \varphi_\mu(y, z) \geq 0$, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{t+s+\varphi_{\beta+\mu}(w, z)}{t+s} &\leq \frac{ts+s\varphi_\beta(w, y)+t\varphi_\beta(y, z)+\varphi_\beta(w, y)\varphi_\mu(y, z)}{ts} \\ \Rightarrow \frac{t+s}{t+s+\varphi_{\beta+\mu}(w, z)} &\geq \frac{ts}{ts+s\varphi_\beta(w, y)+t\varphi_\beta(y, z)+\varphi_\beta(w, y)\varphi_\mu(y, z)} = \frac{t}{t+\varphi_\beta(w, y)} \cdot \frac{s}{s+\varphi_\mu(y, z)}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $Q_\beta(w, y, t) * Q_\mu(y, z, s) \leq Q_{\beta+\mu}(w, z, t + s)$ and (MFML4) holds.

Proposition 3.5. Let $(W, Q, *)$ be a fuzzy metric space. Define fuzzy set Q_β on $W^2 \times (0, \infty)$ as follows;

$Q_\beta(w, y, t) = Q(w, y, \beta t)$ for all $w, y \in W$ and $\beta, t > 0$. Then, $(W, Q_\beta, *)$ is modular fuzzy metric-like space.

Proof. (MFML1)- (MFML3) and (MFLM5) are obvious. Now, we prove (MFML4).

$$\begin{aligned} Q_{\beta+\mu}(w, y, t + s) &= Q(w, y, (\beta + \mu)(t + s)) \\ &= Q(w, y, \beta t + \beta s + \mu t + \mu s) \\ &\geq Q(w, y, (\beta t + \mu s)) \\ &\geq Q(w, z, \beta t) * Q(z, y, \mu s) \\ &= Q_\beta(w, z, t) * Q_\mu(z, y, s) \\ \Rightarrow Q_{\beta+\mu}(w, y, t + s) &\geq Q_\beta(w, z, t) * Q_\mu(z, y, s). \end{aligned}$$

Definition 3.2. Let $(W, Q_\beta, *)$ be a modular fuzzy metric-like space.

(a) Sequence $\{w_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in W is called convergent to $w \in W$ if $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Q_\beta(w_n, w, t) = Q_\beta(w, w, t)$ for all $\beta, t > 0$.

(b) Sequence $\{w_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in W is called a Cauchy sequence if $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Q_\beta(w_{n+p}, w_n, t)$ exists and is finite for all $\beta, t > 0$, $p \geq 1$.

(c) A modular fuzzy metric-like space is called complete if every Cauchy sequence $\{w_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in W converges to some $w \in W$ such that

$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Q_\beta(w_n, w, t) = Q_\beta(w, w, t) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Q_\beta(w_{n+p}, w_n, t)$ for all $\beta, t > 0, p \geq 1$.

Remark 3.1. In a modular fuzzy metric-like space, the limit of a convergent sequence may not be unique. Consider Example 3.2. Define the sequence $\{w_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ in W by $\{w_n\} = \{1 + \frac{1}{n}\}$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$.

If $w \geq 2$, then

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Q_\beta(w_n, w, t) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\beta t}{\beta t + \max\{w_n, w\}} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\beta t}{\beta t + w} = \frac{\beta t}{\beta t + w} = \frac{\beta t}{\beta t + \max\{w, w\}} = Q_\beta(w, w, t).$$

Hence, the sequence $\{w_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ converges to all $w \in W$ with $w \geq 2$.

Definition 3.3. Let $(W, Q_\beta, *)$ be a modular fuzzy metric-like space. We will say that the mapping $T : W \rightarrow W$ is a modular fuzzy contractive mapping if there exists $k \in (0, 1)$ such that

$$\frac{1}{Q_\beta(T(w), T(y), t)} - 1 \leq k \left[\frac{1}{Q_\beta(w, y, t)} - 1 \right] \text{ for all } \beta, t > 0 \text{ and } w, y \in W.$$

Theorem 3.1. Let (W, Q_β, \star) be a complete modular fuzzy metric-like space and $T : W \rightarrow W$ be a modular fuzzy contractive mapping with contractive constant k . Then T has a unique fixed point $w \in W$ and $Q_\beta(w, w, t) = 1$ for all $\beta, t > 0$.

Proof. Let (W, Q_β, \star) be a complete modular fuzzy metric-like space. For an arbitrary $w_0 \in W$, define a sequence $\{w_n\}$ in W by $w_n = T(w_{n-1})$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$. If $w_n = w_{n-1}$ for some $n \in \mathbb{N}$, then w_n is a fixed point of T since $w_n = T(w_{n-1}) = T(w_n)$. Therefore, we assume that $w_n \neq w_{n-1}$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$. For any $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and $\beta, t > 0$, from Definition 3.3 we obtain the following,

$$\frac{1}{Q_\beta(w_n, w_{n+1}, t)} - 1 = \frac{1}{Q_\beta(T(w_{n-1}), T(w_n), t)} - 1 \leq k \left[\frac{1}{Q_\beta(w_{n-1}, w_n, t)} - 1 \right] = \frac{k}{Q_\beta(w_{n-1}, w_n, t)} - k.$$

Let $Q_\beta(w_n, w_{n+1}, t) = Q_\beta^{(n)}(t)$ and $1 - k = h$.

$$\text{Since } 1 - k = h \in (0, 1), \frac{1}{Q_\beta^{(n)}(t)} - 1 \leq \frac{k}{Q_\beta(w_{n-1}, w_n, t)} - k = \frac{k}{Q_\beta^{(n-1)}(t)} - k.$$

$$\text{Then, } \frac{1}{Q_\beta^{(n)}(t)} \leq \frac{k}{Q_\beta^{(n-1)}(t)} + h.$$

Let this approach be maintained; then

$$\frac{1}{Q_\beta(w_{n-1}, w_n, t)} - 1 = \frac{1}{Q_\beta(T(w_{n-2}), T(w_{n-1}), t)} - 1 \leq k \left[\frac{1}{Q_\beta(w_{n-2}, w_{n-1}, t)} - 1 \right] = \frac{k}{Q_\beta(w_{n-2}, w_{n-1}, t)} - k$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{1}{Q_\beta^{(n-1)}(t)} - 1 \leq \frac{k}{Q_\beta^{(n-2)}(t)} - k$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{1}{Q_\beta^{(n-1)}(t)} \leq \frac{k}{Q_\beta^{(n-2)}(t)} - k + 1 = \frac{k}{Q_\beta^{(n-2)}(t)} + h.$$

The others can be shown similarly. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{Q_\beta^{(n)}(t)} &\leq \frac{k}{Q_\beta^{(n-1)}(t)} + h \\ &= k \left[\frac{1}{Q_\beta^{(n-1)}(t)} \right] + h \\ &\leq k \left[\frac{k}{Q_\beta^{(n-2)}(t)} + h \right] + h \\ &= k^2 \frac{1}{Q_\beta^{(n-2)}(t)} + kh + h \\ &\leq k^2 \left[\frac{k}{Q_\beta^{(n-3)}(t)} + h \right] + kh + h \\ &= k^3 \left[\frac{k}{Q_\beta^{(n-3)}(t)} + h \right] + k^2h + kh + h \end{aligned}$$

If we continue like this, we get that

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{1}{Q_\beta^{(n)}(t)} &\leq k^n \frac{1}{Q_\beta^{(0)}(t)} + k^{n-1}h + k^{n-2}h + \dots + kh + h \\
&= \frac{k^n}{Q_\beta^{(0)}(t)} + (k^{n-1} + k^{n-2} + \dots + k + 1)h \\
&= \frac{k^n}{Q_\beta^{(0)}(t)} + \frac{h(1-k^n)}{1-k} \\
&= \frac{k^n}{Q_\beta^{(0)}(t)} + (1 - k^n)
\end{aligned}$$

Hence, we have $\frac{1}{\frac{k^n}{Q_\beta^{(0)}(t)} + 1 - k^n} \leq Q_\beta^{(n)}(t)$, for all $\beta, t > 0, n \in \mathbb{N}$. (1)

Now, $p \geq 1, n \in \mathbb{N}$, for all $\beta, t > 0$,

$$\begin{aligned}
Q_\beta(w_n, w_{n+p}, t) &\geq Q_{\frac{\beta}{p}}(w_n, w_{n+1}, \frac{t}{p}) * Q_{\frac{p\beta-\beta}{p}}(w_{n+1}, w_{n+p}, \frac{pt-t}{p}) \\
&\geq Q_{\frac{\beta}{p}}(w_n, w_{n+1}, \frac{t}{p}) * Q_{\frac{\beta}{p}}(w_{n+1}, w_{n+2}, \frac{t}{p}) * Q_{\frac{p\beta-2\beta}{p}}(w_{n+2}, w_{n+p}, \frac{pt-2t}{p}) \\
&\geq Q_{\frac{\beta}{p}}(w_n, w_{n+1}, \frac{t}{p}) * Q_{\frac{\beta}{p}}(w_{n+1}, w_{n+2}, \frac{t}{p}) * Q_{\frac{\beta}{p}}(w_{n+2}, w_{n+3}, \frac{t}{p}) \\
&\quad * Q_{\frac{p\beta-3\beta}{p}}(w_{n+3}, w_{n+p}, \frac{pt-3t}{p}) \\
&\geq Q_{\frac{\beta}{p}}(w_n, w_{n+1}, \frac{t}{p}) * Q_{\frac{\beta}{p}}(w_{n+1}, w_{n+2}, \frac{t}{p}) * Q_{\frac{\beta}{p}}(w_{n+2}, w_{n+3}, \frac{t}{p}) * \dots \\
&\quad * Q_{\frac{p\beta-(p-2)\beta}{p}}(w_{n+p-2}, w_{n+p}, \frac{pt-(p-2)t}{p}) \\
&\geq Q_{\frac{\beta}{p}}(w_n, w_{n+1}, \frac{t}{p}) * Q_{\frac{\beta}{p}}(w_{n+1}, w_{n+2}, \frac{t}{p}) * \dots * Q_{\frac{\beta}{p}}(w_{n+p-2}, w_{n+p-1}, \frac{t}{p}) \\
&\quad * Q_{\frac{p\beta-(p-2)\beta-\beta}{p}}(w_{n+p-1}, w_{n+p}, \frac{pt-(p-2)t-t}{p}) \\
&\geq Q_{\frac{\beta}{p}}(w_n, w_{n+1}, \frac{t}{p}) * Q_{\frac{\beta}{p}}(w_{n+1}, w_{n+2}, \frac{t}{p}) * \dots * Q_{\frac{\beta}{p}}(w_{n+p-2}, w_{n+p-1}, \frac{t}{p}) \\
&\quad * Q_{\frac{\beta}{p}}(w_{n+p-1}, w_{n+p}, \frac{t}{p}) \\
&= Q_{\frac{\beta}{p}}^{(n)}(\frac{t}{p}) * Q_{\frac{\beta}{p}}^{(n+1)}(\frac{t}{p}) * \dots * Q_{\frac{\beta}{p}}^{(n+p-2)}(\frac{t}{p}) * Q_{\frac{\beta}{p}}^{(n+p-1)}(\frac{t}{p}).
\end{aligned}$$

From (1),

$$\begin{aligned}
Q_\beta(w_n, w_{n+p}, t) &\geq \frac{1}{\frac{k^n}{Q_\beta^{(0)}(\frac{t}{p})} + 1 - k^n} * \frac{1}{\frac{k^{n+1}}{Q_\beta^{(0)}(\frac{t}{p})} + 1 - k^{n+1}} * \dots * \frac{1}{\frac{k^{n+p-1}}{Q_\beta^{(0)}(\frac{t}{p})} + 1 - k^{n+p-1}} \\
&\geq \frac{1}{\frac{k^n}{Q_\beta^{(0)}(\frac{t}{p})} + 1} * \frac{1}{\frac{k^{n+1}}{Q_\beta^{(0)}(\frac{t}{p})} + 1} * \dots * \frac{1}{\frac{k^{n+p-1}}{Q_\beta^{(0)}(\frac{t}{p})} + 1}
\end{aligned}$$

Taking the limit as $n \rightarrow \infty$, since $k \in (0, 1)$, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} k^n = 0$ and we get

$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Q_\beta(w_{n+p}, w_n, t) \geq 1 * 1 * \dots * 1 = 1$. Moreover, $1 \geq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Q_\beta(w_{n+p}, w_n, t) \geq 1$ and then

$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Q_\beta(w_{n+p}, x_n, t) = 1$, for all $\beta, t > 0$ and $p \geq 1$.

Hence $\{w_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence on $(W, Q_\beta, *)$. Since $(W, Q_\beta, *)$ is complete, there exists $w \in W$ such that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Q_\beta(w_n, w, t) = Q_\beta(w, w, t) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Q_\beta(w_{n+p}, w_n, t)$. (2)

Now, let me show you that w is a fixed point of T :

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{We know that } \frac{1}{Q_\beta(T(w_n), T(w), t)} - 1 &\leq k \left[\frac{1}{Q_\beta(w_n, w, t)} - 1 \right] = \frac{k}{Q_\beta}(w_n, w, t) - k, \\
\frac{1}{\frac{k}{Q_\beta(w_n, w, t)} + 1 - k} &\leq Q_\beta(T(w_n), T(w), t).
\end{aligned}$$

Using the above inequalities, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
Q_\beta(w, T(w), t) &\geq Q_{\frac{\beta}{2}}(w, w_{n+1}, \frac{t}{2}) = Q_{\frac{\beta}{2}}(w, w_{n+1}, \frac{t}{2}) * Q_{\frac{\beta}{2}}(T(w_n), T(w), \frac{t}{2}) \\
&\geq Q_{\frac{\beta}{2}}(w, w_{n+1}, \frac{t}{2}) * \frac{1}{\frac{k}{Q_\beta(w_n, w, \frac{t}{2})} + 1 - k}
\end{aligned}$$

Taking the limit as $n \rightarrow \infty$, from (2), $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Q_\beta(w_n, w, t) = 1$.

Then, $1 \geq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Q_\beta(w, T(w), t) \geq 1 * 1$ and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Q_\beta(w, T(w), t) = Q_\beta(w, T(w), t) = 1$, for all $\beta, t > 0$.

Then we have $w = T(w)$ from the condition MFML2. Thus w is a fixed point of T . Also, $Q_\beta(w, w, t) = 1$ since $T(w) = w$ and $Q_\beta(w, T(w), t) = 1$ for all $\beta, t > 0$.

To show the uniqueness of fixed point, let y be another fixed point of T such that $Q_{\beta_0}(w, y, t_0) < 1$ for some $\beta_0, t_0 > 0$.

It follows from Definition 3.3. that

$$\frac{1}{Q_{\beta_0}(w, y, t_0)} - 1 = \frac{1}{Q_{\beta_0}(T(w), T(y), t_0)} - 1 \leq k \left[\frac{1}{Q_{\beta_0}(w, y, t_0)} - 1 \right] < \frac{1}{Q_{\beta_0}(w, y, t_0)} - 1, \text{ a contradiction.}$$

Hence we must have $Q_\beta(w, y, t) = 1$ for all $\beta, t > 0$ and therefore $w = y$.

Example 3.3. Let $W = [0, 1]$ and $o * u = ou$. Define fuzzy set Q_β on $W^2 \times (0, \infty)$ by

$Q_\beta(w, y, t) = \frac{t}{t + \frac{\max\{w, y\}}{\beta}}$ for all $w, y \in W$ and $\beta, t > 0$. Then $(W, Q_\beta, *)$ is a complete modular fuzzy metric-like space. If $T : W \rightarrow W$ is given by

$$T(w) = \begin{cases} 0, & w = 1 \\ \frac{w}{2}, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

then T is a modular fuzzy contractive mapping with modular contractive constant $k = \frac{1}{2}$. Note that all conditions of the Theorem 3.1. are satisfied. Thus T has a unique fixed point $0 \in W$ and $Q_\beta(0, 0, t) = 1$ for all $\beta, t > 0$.

4 Conclusion

In this study, we obtained fixed point results within the newly introduced modular fuzzy metric-like space and verified their applicability through illustrative examples. The extension of fixed point theory to this enriched mathematical structure provides a basis for improving more general contraction principles and for addressing a wider class of theoretical and applied problems. Thanks to the flexibility of this new space, future research may apply novel contractive mappings and analytical techniques capable of tackling problems in areas such as analysis, differential and integral equations, systems of linear equations, and graph theory. Overall, the results presented here are expected to contribute to the progress of the theoretical foundations and to encourage innovative applications across various scientific disciplines.

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Advancements in Weddle's Formula for Tempered Fractional Integrals: Applications in Numerical Integration

Wali Haider¹, Hüseyin Budak², Mehmet Zeki Sarikaya³, Asia Shehzadi⁴

¹School of Mathematics and Statistics, Shaanxi Normal University, Xi'an, Shaanxi, 710119, China

²Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Science and Arts, Kocaeli University, Kocaeli 41001, Türkiye

³Department of Mathematics Faculty of Science and Arts, Düzce University Düzce 81620, Türkiye

⁴School of Mathematics and Statistics, Central South University, Changsha 410083, China

Corresponding author: haiderwali416@gmail.com

ORCID IDs:

First Author: [0009-0001-7065-2755](https://orcid.org/0009-0001-7065-2755)

Second Author: [0000-0001-8843-955X](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8843-955X)

Third Author: [0000-0002-6165-9242](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6165-9242)

Fourth Author: [0009-0005-1101-5536](https://orcid.org/0009-0005-1101-5536)

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Abstract

Tempered fractional integrals arise naturally in the modeling of anomalous diffusion, viscoelastic phenomena, and other processes in modern physics. In this study, we provide a comprehensive derivation of integral inequalities for differentiable convex functions in the context of tempered fractional integrals. Initially, we formulate significant integral identity involving tempered fractional integrals, which are subsequently used to establish Weddle's type inequalities for differentiable convex functions. Furthermore, numerical demonstrations and graphical representations to affirm the validity and relevance of these newly derived inequalities within the tempered fractional integral framework are presented.

Keywords: Convexity, Weddle's Formula, Fractional Calculus, Tempered Fractional Integrals, Quadrature Formula

1 Introduction and Motivation

Numerical integration has an extensive and diverse past traceable to ancient civilizations. The initial attempts to approximate integrals can be traced back to ancient civilizations, where geometric methods were employed to calculate areas and volumes. Areas under curves were first calculated by Archimedes, who invented the fundamental techniques. Newton and Leibniz's calculus breakthroughs established the framework for modern numerical approaches, such as

Newton's trapezoidal rule and formalized integration in the 17th century. Gauss significantly contributed to the development of numerical integration by introducing the concept of Gaussian quadrature in the 19th century. Further developments, such as the Monte Carlo methods and Romberg integration, occurred in the 20th century, and the rise of modern computing tools reinforced numerical integration's position as an essential tool for solving challenging issues in various scientific domains. These techniques compute a weighted sum of function values over the prescribed interval to approximate the integral. Numerous standard methods are present, each with distinctive advantages based on the function's complexity and required accuracy, including the Gaussian quadrature, Trapezoidal rule, Simpson's rule, Boole's rule, Weddle's rule and Monte Carlo approaches. Consult [1, 4, 16] and references therein for further information on numerical integration and its applications.

In mathematics, the study of inequalities has been prevalent since ancient times. However, their formal and systematic studies have been more pronounced since the 17th and 18th centuries. Karl Hermann Amandus Schwarz [6] significantly contributed to this approach in the late 19th century, particularly with the formation of convex-shaped functions. This concept substantially enhanced the field of mathematics and became an essential aspect of optimization, which further affected other fields like economics, engineering, and computer science. At present, convex functions are also highly applicable in solving complicated optimization problems, such as portfolio optimization and control theory operations. For additional details on the development in time and the field of convexity, see [22, 25]. Convex functions have been employed for many years to investigate inequalities of the Hermite–Hadamard, Simpson, Hermite–Hadamard–Mercer, Ostrowski, and other types. The Hermite–Hadamard inequality, which is discussed in [9], has captured the attention of a diverse array of scholars. Dragomir [5] and Kirmaci[14] have provided numerous inequalities of the trapezoidal type, which have applications to special means. The prominent numerical integration techniques include Simpson's formula, Midpoint formula, Trapezoidal formula, Boole's formula, and Weddle's formula. These methods are intended to approximate the integral of a function over a specified interval by dividing it into smaller subintervals and computing the area under the curve employing several methods.

Here are mention some well-known quadrature formulas:

- (a) Simpson's quadrature, which is also known as Simpson's 1/3 rule, can be indicated as:

$$\int_{\kappa}^{\nu} \Phi(t) dt \approx \frac{\nu - \kappa}{6} \left[\Phi(\kappa) + 4\Phi\left(\frac{\kappa + \nu}{2}\right) + \Phi(\nu) \right]. \quad (1)$$

- (b) Simpson's second formula, or Newton-Cotes quadrature, can be stated in the following manner [4]:

$$\int_{\kappa}^{\nu} \Phi(t) dt \approx \frac{\nu - \kappa}{8} \left[\Phi(\kappa) + 3\Phi\left(\frac{2\kappa + \nu}{3}\right) + 3\Phi\left(\frac{\kappa + 2\nu}{3}\right) + \Phi(\nu) \right]. \quad (2)$$

- (c) The Maclaurin rule, obtained from the Maclaurin formula (as given in [4],) is equivalent to the similar dual Simpson's 3/8 formula:

$$\int_{\kappa}^{\nu} \Phi(t) dt \approx \frac{\nu - \kappa}{8} \left[3\Phi\left(\frac{5\kappa + \nu}{6}\right) + 2\Phi\left(\frac{\kappa + \nu}{2}\right) + 3\Phi\left(\frac{\kappa + 5\nu}{6}\right) \right]. \quad (3)$$

These formulas apply to any function Φ having a continuous fourth derivative across the interval $[\kappa, v]$: (1), (2), and (3).

(d) The Boole's formula, stated as:

$$\int_{\kappa}^v \Phi(t) dt \approx \frac{v - \kappa}{90} \left[7[\Phi(\kappa) + \Phi(v)] + 32 \left[\Phi\left(\frac{v + 3\kappa}{4}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{3v + \kappa}{4}\right) \right] + 12\Phi\left(\frac{\kappa + v}{2}\right) \right]. \quad (4)$$

(e) The Weddle's formula, stated as:

$$\int_{\kappa}^v \Phi(t) dt \approx \frac{1}{20} \left[\Phi(\kappa) + \Phi(v) + 5\Phi\left(\frac{v + 5\kappa}{6}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{v + 2\kappa}{3}\right) + 6\Phi\left(\frac{\kappa + v}{2}\right) + 5\Phi\left(\frac{5v + \kappa}{6}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{2v + \kappa}{3}\right) \right]. \quad (5)$$

The fractional calculus theory expands the regular differentiation and integration notions and applies non-integer values for analyzing various dynamic systems. Tempered fractional integrals, a particular type of fractional calculus, include an exponential decay factor that enhances accuracy in systems with localized interactions and fading memory. By implementing these tempered integrals, researchers achieve more accurate and realistic models for various scientific and engineering applications. Its importance is in using the method to approximate better and describe problem experiences in different fields, including engineering, biosciences, data processing, image enhancement, finance, and other scientific disciplines have extensive applications for tempered fractional integrals.

The mathematical preliminaries and definitions outlined here will be used extensively throughout this investigation.

Definition 1.1. The definitions of the incomplete gamma function and the λ -incomplete gamma function are outlined in the following way:

$$\Upsilon(\alpha, \varpi) := \int_0^{\varpi} t^{\alpha-1} e^{-t} dt,$$

and

$$\Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, \varpi) := \int_0^{\varpi} t^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda t} dt.$$

Here, $0 < \alpha < \infty$ and $\lambda \geq 0$.

The characteristics of the λ -incomplete gamma function are outlined as:

Remark 1.1. [20] Under the assumptions $\alpha > 0$; $x, \lambda \geq 0$ and $a < b$, we attain

$$\text{i. } \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) = \int_0^1 t^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(v-\kappa)t} dt = \frac{1}{(v-\kappa)^{\alpha}} \Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, v - \kappa),$$

$$\text{ii. } \int_0^1 \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, \varpi) d\varpi = \frac{\Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, v-\kappa)}{(v-\kappa)^{\alpha}} - \frac{\Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha+1, v-\kappa)}{(v-\kappa)^{\alpha+1}}.$$

Definition 1.2 (See [13, 8]). A mapping Φ given on the interval $[\kappa, \nu]$, assume $\Phi \in L_1[\kappa, \nu]$, the Riemann-Liouville fractional integral of order $\alpha > 0$, stated as follows:

$$J_{\kappa+}^{\alpha} \Phi(\varpi) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{\kappa}^{\varpi} (\varpi - t)^{\alpha-1} \Phi(t) dt, \quad \varpi > \kappa$$

and

$$J_{\nu-}^{\alpha} \Phi(\varpi) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{\varpi}^{\nu} (t - \varpi)^{\alpha-1} \Phi(t) dt, \quad \varpi < \nu.$$

Here, $\Gamma(\alpha)$ is the Gamma function and $J_{\kappa+}^0 \Phi(\varpi) = J_{\nu-}^0 \Phi(\varpi) = \Phi(\varpi)$.

Definition 1.3 (See [?, 17]). The definitions of the tempered fractional integral operators outlined as:

$$\mathfrak{J}_{\kappa+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \Phi(\varpi) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{\kappa}^{\varpi} (\varpi - t)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(\varpi-t)} \Phi(t) dt, \quad \varpi \in [\kappa, \nu]$$

and

$$\mathfrak{J}_{\nu-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \Phi(\varpi) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_{\varpi}^{\nu} (t - \varpi)^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(t-\varpi)} \Phi(t) dt, \quad \varpi \in [\kappa, \nu].$$

Here, $\Phi \in L_1[\kappa, \nu]$, $\alpha > 0$ and $\lambda \geq 0$.

Definition 1.2 is immediately obtained if $\lambda = 0$ is substituted in Definition 1.3. The following books should be consulted to explore further the diverse cases of tempered fractional integrals [24, 19].

The innovative study of Buschman [2] proposed the concept of fractional integration involving weak singular and exponential kernels, which is the source of tempering fractional calculus, which evolved from the principles of fractional calculus. Fu et al. [7] obtained a novel class of the multiplicative tempered fractional integral operators. They examined various integral inequalities employing λ -incomplete gamma function and multiplicative tempered fractional integrals. Rehman et al. [21] have investigated the relationship between Riemann-Liouville fractional integral tempered fractional. Also, they identified several new inequalities for convex function in terms of tempered fractional integrals. In [20], authors revealed a concept for λ -incomplete gamma functions. Based on this particular notion, they acquired several Hermite-Hadamard inequalities in the framework of tempered fractional integrals. Several Hermite-Hadamard type inequalities involving tempered fractional integrals for subadditive functions were obtained in [12]. In the setting of tempered fractional calculus, Kucche et al. [15] have investigated a Hilfer-type operator. They analyzed its key characteristics, such as compositional properties, mappings in function spaces, and other functional analysis characteristic. Numerous researchers have contributed to advancing tempered fractional integral theories; see [3, 11, 23, 10] and the references therein.

Motivated by previous investigations, we acquire some of Weddle's formula-type inequalities for the class of functions whose derivatives are convex functions employing tempered fractional integrals. In this work, we examine the significant classes of functions in the setting of tempered fractional integral, particularly convex functions, Hölder, and power mean inequalities. A notable advantage of these inequalities can be turned into Riemann-Liouville fractional Weddle's type inequalities with $\lambda = 0$. When $\alpha = 1$, the modified inequalities yield classical Weddle's type inequalities.

The study is organized into four sections, starting with the introduction and preliminaries, which cover basic definitions of fractional calculus and a summary of relevant studies in the field. In Section 1.1, we will establish several results concerning Weddle's type inequalities for differentiable convex functions. Section 2, we will provide various examples to elucidate these inequalities, highlighting their practical applications and significance. In the last section, we summarize our findings and suggest possibilities for further research.

1.1 Main Contributions

Lemma 1.1. Let $\Phi : [\kappa, v] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is an absolutely continuous function on the interval (κ, v) with $\Phi' \in L_1[\kappa, v]$, then the following holds:

$$\frac{1}{20} \left[\Phi(\kappa) + 5\Phi\left(\frac{v+5\kappa}{6}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{v+2\kappa}{3}\right) + 6\Phi\left(\frac{\kappa+v}{2}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{2v+\kappa}{3}\right) + 5\Phi\left(\frac{5v+\kappa}{6}\right) + \Phi(v) \right] - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2\Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, v-\kappa)} \left[\mathfrak{Z}_{v^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \Phi(\kappa) + \mathfrak{Z}_{\kappa^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \Phi(v) \right] = \frac{(v-\kappa)^{\alpha+1}}{2\Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, v-\kappa)} \sum_{i=1}^6 I_i, \quad (6)$$

where

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} I_1 = \int_0^{\frac{1}{6}} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{1}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right) [\Phi'(tv + (1-t)\kappa) - \Phi'(t\kappa + (1-t)v)] dt, \\ I_2 = \int_{\frac{1}{6}}^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{6}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right) [\Phi'(tv + (1-t)\kappa) - \Phi'(t\kappa + (1-t)v)] dt, \\ I_3 = \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{7}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right) [\Phi'(tv + (1-t)\kappa) - \Phi'(t\kappa + (1-t)v)] dt, \\ I_4 = \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{13}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right) [\Phi'(tv + (1-t)\kappa) - \Phi'(t\kappa + (1-t)v)] dt, \\ I_5 = \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^{\frac{5}{6}} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{14}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right) [\Phi'(tv + (1-t)\kappa) - \Phi'(t\kappa + (1-t)v)] dt, \\ I_6 = \int_{\frac{5}{6}}^1 \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{19}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right) [\Phi'(tv + (1-t)\kappa) - \Phi'(t\kappa + (1-t)v)] dt. \end{array} \right.$$

Proof. Through the technique of integration by parts, we establish

$$\begin{aligned} I_1 &= \int_0^{\frac{1}{6}} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{1}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right) [\Phi'(tv + (1-t)\kappa) - \Phi'(t\kappa + (1-t)v)] dt \\ &= \frac{1}{v-\kappa} \left[\left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{1}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right) [\Phi(tv + (1-t)\kappa) + \Phi(t\kappa + (1-t)v)] \Big|_0^{\frac{1}{6}} \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \frac{1}{v-\kappa} \int_0^{\frac{1}{6}} t^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(v-\kappa)t} [\Phi(tv + (1-t)\kappa) + \Phi(t\kappa + (1-t)v)] dt \right] \\ &= \frac{1}{v-\kappa} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}\left(\alpha, \frac{1}{6}\right) - \frac{1}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right) \left[\Phi\left(\frac{v+5\kappa}{6}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{\kappa+5v}{6}\right) \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \frac{1}{v - \kappa} \left(\frac{1}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right) [\Phi(\kappa) + \Phi(v)] \\
 & - \frac{1}{v - \kappa} \int_0^{\frac{1}{6}} t^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(v-\kappa)t} [\Phi(tv + (1-t)\kappa) + \Phi(t\kappa + (1-t)v)] dt, \tag{7}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_2 &= \int_{\frac{1}{6}}^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{6}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right) [\Phi'(tv + (1-t)\kappa) - \Phi'(t\kappa + (1-t)v)] dt \\
 &= \frac{1}{v - \kappa} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}\left(\alpha, \frac{1}{3}\right) - \frac{6}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right) \left[\Phi\left(\frac{v+2\kappa}{3}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{\kappa+2v}{3}\right) \right] \\
 &\quad - \frac{1}{v - \kappa} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}\left(\alpha, \frac{1}{6}\right) - \frac{6}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right) \left[\Phi\left(\frac{v+5\kappa}{6}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{\kappa+5v}{6}\right) \right] \\
 &\quad - \frac{1}{v - \kappa} \int_{\frac{1}{6}}^{\frac{1}{3}} t^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(v-\kappa)t} [\Phi(tv + (1-t)\kappa) + \Phi(t\kappa + (1-t)v)] dt, \tag{8}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_3 &= \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{7}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right) [\Phi'(tv + (1-t)\kappa) - \Phi'(t\kappa + (1-t)v)] dt \\
 &= \frac{2}{v - \kappa} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}\left(\alpha, \frac{1}{2}\right) - \frac{7}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right) \Phi\left(\frac{\kappa+v}{2}\right) \\
 &\quad - \frac{1}{v - \kappa} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}\left(\alpha, \frac{1}{3}\right) - \frac{7}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right) \left[\Phi\left(\frac{v+2\kappa}{3}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{\kappa+2v}{3}\right) \right] \\
 &\quad - \frac{1}{v - \kappa} \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{1}{2}} t^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(v-\kappa)t} [\Phi(tv + (1-t)\kappa) + \Phi(t\kappa + (1-t)v)] dt, \tag{9}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_4 &= \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{13}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right) [\Phi'(tv + (1-t)\kappa) - \Phi'(t\kappa + (1-t)v)] dt \\
 &= \frac{1}{v - \kappa} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}\left(\alpha, \frac{2}{3}\right) - \frac{13}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right) \left[\Phi\left(\frac{2v+\kappa}{3}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{2\kappa+v}{3}\right) \right] \\
 &\quad - \frac{2}{v - \kappa} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}\left(\alpha, \frac{1}{2}\right) - \frac{13}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right) \Phi\left(\frac{\kappa+v}{2}\right) \\
 &\quad - \frac{1}{v - \kappa} \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{2}{3}} t^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(v-\kappa)t} [\Phi(tv + (1-t)\kappa) + \Phi(t\kappa + (1-t)v)] dt, \tag{10}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_5 &= \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^{\frac{5}{6}} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{14}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right) [\Phi'(tv + (1-t)\kappa) - \Phi'(t\kappa + (1-t)v)] dt \\
 &= \frac{1}{v - \kappa} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}\left(\alpha, \frac{5}{6}\right) - \frac{14}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right) \left[\Phi\left(\frac{5v+\kappa}{6}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{5\kappa+v}{6}\right) \right] \\
 &\quad - \frac{1}{v - \kappa} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}\left(\alpha, \frac{2}{3}\right) - \frac{14}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right) \left[\Phi\left(\frac{2v+\kappa}{3}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{2\kappa+v}{3}\right) \right] \\
 &\quad - \frac{1}{v - \kappa} \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^{\frac{5}{6}} t^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(v-\kappa)t} [\Phi(tv + (1-t)\kappa) + \Phi(t\kappa + (1-t)v)] dt, \tag{11}
 \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_6 &= \int_{\frac{5}{6}}^1 \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{19}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right) [\Phi'(tv + (1-t)\kappa) - \Phi'(t\kappa + (1-t)v)] dt \\
 &= \frac{1}{v - \kappa} \left(\frac{1}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right) [\Phi(\kappa) + \Phi(v)] \\
 &\quad - \frac{1}{v - \kappa} \left(\Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}\left(\alpha, \frac{5}{6}\right) - \frac{19}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right) \left[\Phi\left(\frac{5v+\kappa}{6}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{5\kappa+v}{6}\right) \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

$$-\frac{1}{v-\kappa} \int_{\frac{5}{6}}^1 t^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(v-\kappa)t} [\Phi(tv + (1-t)\kappa) + \Phi(t\kappa + (1-t)v)] dt. \tag{12}$$

By adding equalities (7)-(12), we acquire

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=1}^6 I_i &= \frac{2 \Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, v-\kappa)}{20(v-\kappa)^{\alpha+1}} \\ &\times \left[\Phi(\kappa) + 5\Phi\left(\frac{v+5\kappa}{6}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{v+2\kappa}{3}\right) + 6\Phi\left(\frac{\kappa+v}{2}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{2v+\kappa}{3}\right) + 5\Phi\left(\frac{5v+\kappa}{6}\right) + \Phi(v) \right] \\ &- \frac{1}{v-\kappa} \int_0^1 t^{\alpha-1} e^{-\lambda(v-\kappa)t} [\Phi(tv + (1-t)\kappa) + \Phi(t\kappa + (1-t)v)] dt. \end{aligned} \tag{13}$$

With the aid of change of variable $x = tv + (1-t)\kappa$ and $x = t\kappa + (1-t)v$ for $t \in [0, 1]$ respectively, equality (13) can be rewritten as:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i=1}^6 I_i &= \frac{2 \Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, v-\kappa)}{20(v-\kappa)^{\alpha+1}} \\ &\times \left[\Phi(\kappa) + 5\Phi\left(\frac{v+5\kappa}{6}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{v+2\kappa}{3}\right) + 6\Phi\left(\frac{\kappa+v}{2}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{2v+\kappa}{3}\right) + 5\Phi\left(\frac{5v+\kappa}{6}\right) + \Phi(v) \right] \\ &- \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{(v-\kappa)^{\alpha+1}} \left[\mathfrak{Z}_{v-}^{(\alpha,\lambda)} \Phi(\kappa) + \mathfrak{Z}_{\kappa+}^{(\alpha,\lambda)} \Phi(v) \right]. \end{aligned} \tag{14}$$

Multiplying both sides of (14) by $\frac{(v-\kappa)^{\alpha+1}}{2\Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, v-\kappa)}$, the equality (6) is obtained. □

Theorem 1.1. Suppose the conditions stated in Lemma 1.1 and the function $|\Phi'|$ on the interval $[\kappa, v]$, then, we have the subsequent inequality

$$\begin{aligned} &\left| \frac{1}{20} \left[\Phi(\kappa) + 5\Phi\left(\frac{v+5\kappa}{6}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{v+2\kappa}{3}\right) + 6\Phi\left(\frac{\kappa+v}{2}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{2v+\kappa}{3}\right) + 5\Phi\left(\frac{5v+\kappa}{6}\right) + \Phi(v) \right] \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2 \Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, v-\kappa)} \left[\mathfrak{Z}_{v-}^{(\alpha,\lambda)} \Phi(\kappa) + \mathfrak{Z}_{\kappa+}^{(\alpha,\lambda)} \Phi(v) \right] \right| \\ &\leq \frac{(v-\kappa)^{\alpha+1}}{2 \Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, v-\kappa)} (K_1(\alpha, \lambda) + K_2(\alpha, \lambda) + K_3(\alpha, \lambda) + K_4(\alpha, \lambda) + K_5(\alpha, \lambda) + K_6(\alpha, \lambda)) [|\Phi'(\kappa)| + |\Phi'(v)|], \end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

where

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} K_1(\alpha, \lambda) &= \int_0^{\frac{1}{6}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{1}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt, \\ K_2(\alpha, \lambda) &= \int_{\frac{1}{6}}^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{6}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt, \\ K_3(\alpha, \lambda) &= \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{7}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt, \\ K_4(\alpha, \lambda) &= \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{13}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt, \\ K_5(\alpha, \lambda) &= \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^{\frac{5}{6}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{14}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt, \\ K_6(\alpha, \lambda) &= \int_{\frac{5}{6}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{19}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt. \end{aligned} \right.$$

Proof. By employing the modulus in Lemma 1.1 and considering the convexity of $|\Phi'|$, we gain

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[\Phi(\kappa) + 5\Phi\left(\frac{v+5\kappa}{6}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{v+2\kappa}{3}\right) + 6\Phi\left(\frac{\kappa+v}{2}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{2v+\kappa}{3}\right) + 5\Phi\left(\frac{5v+\kappa}{6}\right) + \Phi(v) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2\Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, v-\kappa)} \left[\mathfrak{Z}_{v^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \Phi(\kappa) + \mathfrak{Z}_{\kappa^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \Phi(v) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(v-\kappa)^{\alpha+1}}{2\Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, v-\kappa)} \left[\int_0^{\frac{1}{6}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{1}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| |\Phi'(tv + (1-t)\kappa) - \Phi'(t\kappa + (1-t)v)| dt \right. \\ & \quad + \int_{\frac{1}{6}}^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{6}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| |\Phi'(tv + (1-t)\kappa) - \Phi'(t\kappa + (1-t)v)| dt \\ & \quad + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{7}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| |\Phi'(tv + (1-t)\kappa) - \Phi'(t\kappa + (1-t)v)| dt \\ & \quad + \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{13}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| |\Phi'(tv + (1-t)\kappa) - \Phi'(t\kappa + (1-t)v)| dt \\ & \quad + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^{\frac{5}{6}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{14}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| |\Phi'(tv + (1-t)\kappa) - \Phi'(t\kappa + (1-t)v)| dt \\ & \quad \left. + \int_{\frac{5}{6}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{19}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| |\Phi'(tv + (1-t)\kappa) - \Phi'(t\kappa + (1-t)v)| dt \right]. \quad (16) \end{aligned}$$

By using the convexity of $|\Phi'|$, we can deduce

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[\Phi(\kappa) + 5\Phi\left(\frac{v+5\kappa}{6}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{v+2\kappa}{3}\right) + 6\Phi\left(\frac{\kappa+v}{2}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{2v+\kappa}{3}\right) + 5\Phi\left(\frac{5v+\kappa}{6}\right) + \Phi(v) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2\Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, v-\kappa)} \left[\mathfrak{Z}_{v^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \Phi(\kappa) + \mathfrak{Z}_{\kappa^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \Phi(v) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(v-\kappa)^{\alpha+1}}{2\Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, v-\kappa)} \\ & \quad \times \left[\int_0^{\frac{1}{6}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{1}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| [t|\Phi'(v)| + (1-t)|\Phi'(\kappa)| + t|\Phi'(\kappa)| + (1-t)|\Phi'(v)|] dt \right. \\ & \quad + \int_{\frac{1}{6}}^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{6}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| [t|\Phi'(v)| + (1-t)|\Phi'(\kappa)| + t|\Phi'(\kappa)| + (1-t)|\Phi'(v)|] dt \\ & \quad + \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{7}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| [t|\Phi'(v)| + (1-t)|\Phi'(\kappa)| + t|\Phi'(\kappa)| + (1-t)|\Phi'(v)|] dt \\ & \quad + \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{13}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| [t|\Phi'(v)| + (1-t)|\Phi'(\kappa)| + t|\Phi'(\kappa)| + (1-t)|\Phi'(v)|] dt \\ & \quad + \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^{\frac{5}{6}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{14}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| [t|\Phi'(v)| + (1-t)|\Phi'(\kappa)| + t|\Phi'(\kappa)| + (1-t)|\Phi'(v)|] dt \\ & \quad \left. + \int_{\frac{5}{6}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{19}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| [t|\Phi'(v)| + (1-t)|\Phi'(\kappa)| + t|\Phi'(\kappa)| + (1-t)|\Phi'(v)|] dt \right] \\ & = \frac{(v-\kappa)^{\alpha+1}}{2\Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, v-\kappa)} (\mathbf{K}_1(\alpha, \lambda) + \mathbf{K}_2(\alpha, \lambda) + \mathbf{K}_3(\alpha, \lambda) + \mathbf{K}_4(\alpha, \lambda) + \mathbf{K}_5(\alpha, \lambda) + \mathbf{K}_6(\alpha, \lambda)) [|\Phi'(\kappa)| + |\Phi'(v)|]. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, the proof of Theorem 1.1 is established. □

Remark 1.2. By taking $\lambda = 0$ in Theorem 1.1, we attain

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[\Phi(\kappa) + 5\Phi\left(\frac{v+5\kappa}{6}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{v+2\kappa}{3}\right) + 6\Phi\left(\frac{\kappa+v}{2}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{2v+\kappa}{3}\right) + 5\Phi\left(\frac{5v+\kappa}{6}\right) + \Phi(v) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{2(v-\kappa)^\alpha} [J_{v-}^\alpha \Phi(\kappa) + J_{\kappa+}^\alpha \Phi(v)] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{\alpha(v-\kappa)}{2} (\mathbf{K}_1(\alpha, 0) + \mathbf{K}_2(\alpha, 0) + \mathbf{K}_3(\alpha, 0) + \mathbf{K}_4(\alpha, 0) + \mathbf{K}_5(\alpha, 0) + \mathbf{K}_6(\alpha, 0)), \end{aligned}$$

which is identified in [18].

Remark 1.3. Let us consider $\lambda = 0$ and $\alpha = 1$ in Theorem 1.1, then we acquire

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[\Phi(\kappa) + 5\Phi\left(\frac{v+5\kappa}{6}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{v+2\kappa}{3}\right) + 6\Phi\left(\frac{\kappa+v}{2}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{2v+\kappa}{3}\right) + 5\Phi\left(\frac{5v+\kappa}{6}\right) + \Phi(v) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{1}{v-\kappa} \int_{\kappa}^v \Phi(t) dt \right| \leq \frac{13(v-\kappa)}{450} (|\Phi'(\kappa)| + |\Phi'(v)|), \end{aligned}$$

which is reported in [26].

Theorem 1.2. Suppose the conditions stated in Lemma 1.1. If the mapping $|\Phi'|^q, q \geq 1$ is convex on the interval $[\kappa, v]$, then we have the subsequent inequality

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[\Phi(\kappa) + 5\Phi\left(\frac{v+5\kappa}{6}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{v+2\kappa}{3}\right) + 6\Phi\left(\frac{\kappa+v}{2}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{2v+\kappa}{3}\right) + 5\Phi\left(\frac{5v+\kappa}{6}\right) + \Phi(v) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2\Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, v-\kappa)} \left[\mathfrak{Z}_{v-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \Phi(\kappa) + \mathfrak{Z}_{\kappa+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \Phi(v) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(v-\kappa)^{\alpha+1}}{2\Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, v-\kappa)} \left[(\mathbf{K}_1(\alpha, \lambda))^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left\{ (\mathbf{K}_7(\alpha, \lambda) |\Phi'(v)|^q + (\mathbf{K}_1(\alpha, \lambda) - \mathbf{K}_7(\alpha, \lambda)) |\Phi'(\kappa)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. + (\mathbf{K}_7(\alpha, \lambda) |\Phi'(\kappa)|^q + (\mathbf{K}_1(\alpha, \lambda) - \mathbf{K}_7(\alpha, \lambda)) |\Phi'(v)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \right. \\ & \quad \left. + (\mathbf{K}_2(\alpha, \lambda))^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left\{ (\mathbf{K}_8(\alpha, \lambda) |\Phi'(v)|^q + (\mathbf{K}_2(\alpha, \lambda) - \mathbf{K}_8(\alpha, \lambda)) |\Phi'(\kappa)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. + (\mathbf{K}_8(\alpha, \lambda) |\Phi'(\kappa)|^q + (\mathbf{K}_2(\alpha, \lambda) - \mathbf{K}_8(\alpha, \lambda)) |\Phi'(v)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \right. \\ & \quad \left. + (\mathbf{K}_3(\alpha, \lambda))^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left\{ (\mathbf{K}_9(\alpha, \lambda) |\Phi'(v)|^q + (\mathbf{K}_3(\alpha, \lambda) - \mathbf{K}_9(\alpha, \lambda)) |\Phi'(\kappa)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. + (\mathbf{K}_9(\alpha, \lambda) |\Phi'(\kappa)|^q + (\mathbf{K}_3(\alpha, \lambda) - \mathbf{K}_9(\alpha, \lambda)) |\Phi'(v)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \right. \\ & \quad \left. + (\mathbf{K}_4(\alpha, \lambda))^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left\{ (\mathbf{K}_{10}(\alpha, \lambda) |\Phi'(v)|^q + (\mathbf{K}_4(\alpha, \lambda) - \mathbf{K}_{10}(\alpha, \lambda)) |\Phi'(\kappa)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. + (\mathbf{K}_{10}(\alpha, \lambda) |\Phi'(\kappa)|^q + (\mathbf{K}_4(\alpha, \lambda) - \mathbf{K}_{10}(\alpha, \lambda)) |\Phi'(v)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \right. \\ & \quad \left. + (\mathbf{K}_5(\alpha, \lambda))^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left\{ (\mathbf{K}_{11}(\alpha, \lambda) |\Phi'(v)|^q + (\mathbf{K}_5(\alpha, \lambda) - \mathbf{K}_{11}(\alpha, \lambda)) |\Phi'(\kappa)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. + (\mathbf{K}_{11}(\alpha, \lambda) |\Phi'(\kappa)|^q + (\mathbf{K}_5(\alpha, \lambda) - \mathbf{K}_{11}(\alpha, \lambda)) |\Phi'(v)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \right. \\ & \quad \left. + (\mathbf{K}_6(\alpha, \lambda))^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left\{ (\mathbf{K}_{12}(\alpha, \lambda) |\Phi'(v)|^q + (\mathbf{K}_6(\alpha, \lambda) - \mathbf{K}_{12}(\alpha, \lambda)) |\Phi'(\kappa)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \right. \\ & \quad \left. \left. + (\mathbf{K}_{12}(\alpha, \lambda) |\Phi'(\kappa)|^q + (\mathbf{K}_6(\alpha, \lambda) - \mathbf{K}_{12}(\alpha, \lambda)) |\Phi'(v)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \right], \end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

where $K_1(\alpha, \lambda) - K_6(\alpha, \lambda)$ are defined in Theorem 1.1, and

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} K_7(\alpha, \lambda) &= \int_0^{\frac{1}{6}} t \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{1}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt, \\ K_8(\alpha, \lambda) &= \int_{\frac{1}{6}}^{\frac{1}{3}} t \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{6}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt, \\ K_9(\alpha, \lambda) &= \int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{1}{2}} t \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{7}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt, \\ K_{10}(\alpha, \lambda) &= \int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{2}{3}} t \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{13}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt, \\ K_{11}(\alpha, \lambda) &= \int_{\frac{2}{3}}^{\frac{5}{6}} t \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{14}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt, \\ K_{12}(\alpha, \lambda) &= \int_{\frac{5}{6}}^1 t \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{19}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt. \end{aligned} \right.$$

Proof. By taking power mean inequality in (16), we derive

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[\Phi(\kappa) + 5\Phi\left(\frac{v+5\kappa}{6}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{v+2\kappa}{3}\right) + 6\Phi\left(\frac{\kappa+v}{2}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{2v+\kappa}{3}\right) + 5\Phi\left(\frac{5v+\kappa}{6}\right) + \Phi(v) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2 \Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, v-\kappa)} \left[\mathfrak{I}_{v^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \Phi(\kappa) + \mathfrak{I}_{\kappa^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \Phi(v) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(v-\kappa)^{\alpha+1}}{2 \Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, v-\kappa)} \left[\left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{6}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{1}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\ & \quad \times \left\{ \left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{6}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{1}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| |\Phi'(tv + (1-t)\kappa)|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{6}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{1}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| |\Phi'(t\kappa + (1-t)v)|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \\ & \quad + \left(\int_{\frac{1}{6}}^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{6}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \\ & \quad \times \left\{ \left(\int_{\frac{1}{6}}^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{6}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| |\Phi'(tv + (1-t)\kappa)|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \left(\int_{\frac{1}{6}}^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{6}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| |\Phi'(t\kappa + (1-t)v)|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \\ & \quad + \left(\int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{7}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \\ & \quad \times \left\{ \left(\int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{7}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| |\Phi'(tv + (1-t)\kappa)|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\ & \quad \left. + \left(\int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{7}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| |\Phi'(t\kappa + (1-t)v)|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + \left(\int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{13}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \\
& \times \left\{ \left(\int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{13}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| |\Phi'(tv + (1-t)\kappa)|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
& + \left. \left(\int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{13}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| |\Phi'(t\kappa + (1-t)v)|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \\
& + \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^{\frac{5}{6}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{14}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \\
& \times \left\{ \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^{\frac{5}{6}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{14}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| |\Phi'(tv + (1-t)\kappa)|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
& + \left. \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^{\frac{5}{6}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{14}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| |\Phi'(t\kappa + (1-t)v)|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \\
& + \left(\int_{\frac{5}{6}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{19}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \\
& \times \left\{ \left(\int_{\frac{5}{6}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{19}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| |\Phi'(tv + (1-t)\kappa)|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
& + \left. \left(\int_{\frac{5}{6}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{19}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| |\Phi'(t\kappa + (1-t)v)|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\}.
\end{aligned}$$

By using the convexity of $|\Phi'|^q$, we can deduce

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[\Phi(\kappa) + 5\Phi\left(\frac{v+5\kappa}{6}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{v+2\kappa}{3}\right) + 6\Phi\left(\frac{\kappa+v}{2}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{2v+\kappa}{3}\right) + 5\Phi\left(\frac{5v+\kappa}{6}\right) + \Phi(v) \right] \right. \\
& \quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2\Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, v-\kappa)} \left[\mathfrak{Z}_{v-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \Phi(\kappa) + \mathfrak{Z}_{\kappa+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \Phi(v) \right] \right| \\
& \leq \frac{(v-\kappa)^{\alpha+1}}{2\Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, v-\kappa)} \left[\left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{6}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{1}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
& \quad \times \left\{ \left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{6}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{1}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| [t|\Phi'(v)|^q + (1-t)|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q] dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
& \quad + \left. \left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{6}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{1}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| [t|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q + (1-t)|\Phi'(v)|^q] dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \\
& \quad + \left(\int_{\frac{1}{6}}^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{6}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \\
& \quad \times \left\{ \left(\int_{\frac{1}{6}}^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{6}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| [t|\Phi'(v)|^q + (1-t)|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q] dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
& \quad + \left. \left(\int_{\frac{1}{6}}^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{6}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| [t|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q + (1-t)|\Phi'(v)|^q] dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & + \left(\int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{7}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \\
 & \times \left\{ \left(\int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{7}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| [t|\Phi'(v)|^q + (1-t)|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q] dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
 & + \left. \left(\int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{7}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| [t|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q + (1-t)|\Phi'(v)|^q] dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \\
 & + \left(\int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{13}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \\
 & \times \left\{ \left(\int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{13}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| [t|\Phi'(v)|^q + (1-t)|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q] dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
 & + \left. \left(\int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{13}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| [t|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q + (1-t)|\Phi'(v)|^q] dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \\
 & + \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^{\frac{5}{6}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{14}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \\
 & \times \left\{ \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^{\frac{5}{6}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{14}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| [t|\Phi'(v)|^q + (1-t)|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q] dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
 & + \left. \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^{\frac{5}{6}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{14}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| [t|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q + (1-t)|\Phi'(v)|^q] dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \\
 & + \left(\int_{\frac{5}{6}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{19}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| dt \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \\
 & \times \left\{ \left(\int_{\frac{5}{6}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{19}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| [t|\Phi'(v)|^q + (1-t)|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q] dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
 & + \left. \left(\int_{\frac{5}{6}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{19}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right| [t|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q + (1-t)|\Phi'(v)|^q] dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \Bigg].
 \end{aligned}$$

Hence, the proof is complete. □

Remark 1.4. By taking $\lambda = 0$ in Theorem 1.2, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[\Phi(\kappa) + 5\Phi\left(\frac{v+5\kappa}{6}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{v+2\kappa}{3}\right) + 6\Phi\left(\frac{\kappa+v}{2}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{2v+\kappa}{3}\right) + 5\Phi\left(\frac{5v+\kappa}{6}\right) + \Phi(v) \right] \right. \\
 & \quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{2(v-\kappa)^\alpha} [J_{v-}^\alpha \Phi(\kappa) + J_{\kappa+}^\alpha \Phi(v)] \right| \\
 & \leq \frac{\alpha(v-\kappa)}{2} \left[(\mathbf{K}_1(\alpha, 0))^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left\{ (\mathbf{K}_7(\alpha, 0)|\Phi'(v)|^q + (\mathbf{K}_1(\alpha, 0) - \mathbf{K}_7(\alpha, 0))|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. + (\mathbf{K}_7(\alpha, 0)|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q + (\mathbf{K}_1(\alpha, 0) - \mathbf{K}_7(\alpha, 0))|\Phi'(v)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \right. \\
 & \quad + (\mathbf{K}_2(\alpha, 0))^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left\{ (\mathbf{K}_8(\alpha, 0)|\Phi'(v)|^q + (\mathbf{K}_2(\alpha, 0) - \mathbf{K}_8(\alpha, 0))|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
 & \quad \left. \left. + (\mathbf{K}_8(\alpha, 0)|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q + (\mathbf{K}_2(\alpha, 0) - \mathbf{K}_8(\alpha, 0))|\Phi'(v)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \right].
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &+ (\mathbf{K}_3(\alpha, 0))^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left\{ (\mathbf{K}_9(\alpha, 0)|\Phi'(v)|^q + (\mathbf{K}_3(\alpha, 0) - \mathbf{K}_9(\alpha, 0)) |\Phi'(\kappa)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
 &+ \left. (\mathbf{K}_9(\alpha, 0)|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q + (\mathbf{K}_3(\alpha, 0) - \mathbf{K}_9(\alpha, 0)) |\Phi'(v)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \\
 &+ (\mathbf{K}_4(\alpha, 0))^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left\{ (\mathbf{K}_{10}(\alpha, 0)|\Phi'(v)|^q + (\mathbf{K}_4(\alpha, 0) - \mathbf{K}_{10}(\alpha, 0)) |\Phi'(\kappa)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
 &+ \left. (\mathbf{K}_{10}(\alpha, 0)|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q + (\mathbf{K}_4(\alpha, 0) - \mathbf{K}_{10}(\alpha, 0)) |\Phi'(v)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \\
 &+ (\mathbf{K}_5(\alpha, 0))^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left\{ (\mathbf{K}_{11}(\alpha, 0)|\Phi'(v)|^q + (\mathbf{K}_5(\alpha, 0) - \mathbf{K}_{11}(\alpha, 0)) |\Phi'(\kappa)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
 &+ \left. (\mathbf{K}_{11}(\alpha, 0)|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q + (\mathbf{K}_5(\alpha, 0) - \mathbf{K}_{11}(\alpha, 0)) |\Phi'(v)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \\
 &+ (\mathbf{K}_6(\alpha, 0))^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left\{ (\mathbf{K}_{12}(\alpha, 0)|\Phi'(v)|^q + (\mathbf{K}_6(\alpha, 0) - \mathbf{K}_{12}(\alpha, 0)) |\Phi'(\kappa)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right. \\
 &+ \left. (\mathbf{K}_{12}(\alpha, 0)|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q + (\mathbf{K}_6(\alpha, 0) - \mathbf{K}_{12}(\alpha, 0)) |\Phi'(v)|^q)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \Big],
 \end{aligned}$$

which is obtained in [18].

Remark 1.5. Let us consider $\lambda = 0$ and $\alpha = 1$ in Theorem 1.2, then we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\left| \frac{1}{20} \left[\Phi(\kappa) + 5\Phi\left(\frac{v+5\kappa}{6}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{v+2\kappa}{3}\right) + 6\Phi\left(\frac{\kappa+v}{2}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{2v+\kappa}{3}\right) + 5\Phi\left(\frac{5v+\kappa}{6}\right) + \Phi(v) \right] \right. \\
 &\quad \left. - \frac{1}{v-\kappa} \int_{\kappa}^v \Phi(t) dt \right| \\
 &\leq (v-\kappa) \left[\left(\frac{29}{3600} \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left\{ \left(\frac{|577\Phi'(v)|^q + 4643|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q}{64800} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{|577\Phi'(\kappa)|^q + 4643|\Phi'(v)|^q}{64800} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \right. \\
 &\quad + \left(\frac{17}{1800} \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left\{ \left(\frac{|37\Phi'(v)|^q + 133|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q}{18000} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{|37\Phi'(\kappa)|^q + 133|\Phi'(v)|^q}{18000} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \\
 &\quad \left. + \left(\frac{41}{3600} \right)^{1-\frac{1}{q}} \left\{ \left(\frac{|3311\Phi'(v)|^q + 4069|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q}{64800} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{|3311\Phi'(\kappa)|^q + 4069|\Phi'(v)|^q}{64800} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \right],
 \end{aligned}$$

which is defined in [18, Corollary 4].

Theorem 1.3. Suppose the conditions stated in Lemma 1.1. If the mapping $|\Phi'|^q, q > 1$ is convex on $[\kappa, v]$, then we have the subsequent inequality

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\left| \frac{1}{20} \left[\Phi(\kappa) + 5\Phi\left(\frac{v+5\kappa}{6}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{v+2\kappa}{3}\right) + 6\Phi\left(\frac{\kappa+v}{2}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{2v+\kappa}{3}\right) + 5\Phi\left(\frac{5v+\kappa}{6}\right) + \Phi(v) \right] \right. \\
 &\quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2 \Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, v-\kappa)} \left[\mathfrak{J}_{v-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \Phi(\kappa) + \mathfrak{J}_{\kappa+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \Phi(v) \right] \right| \\
 &\leq \frac{(v-\kappa)^{\alpha+1}}{2 \Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, v-\kappa)} \left\{ (\mathbf{B}_1^p(\alpha, \lambda) + \mathbf{B}_6^p(\alpha, \lambda)) \left[\left(\frac{|\Phi'(v)|^q + 11|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q}{72} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{11|\Phi'(v)|^q + |\Phi'(\kappa)|^q}{72} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \right. \\
 &\quad + (\mathbf{B}_2^p(\alpha, \lambda) + \mathbf{B}_5^p(\alpha, \lambda)) \left[\left(\frac{|\Phi'(v)|^q + 3|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q}{24} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{3|\Phi'(v)|^q + |\Phi'(\kappa)|^q}{24} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \\
 &\quad \left. + (\mathbf{B}_3^p(\alpha, \lambda) + \mathbf{B}_4^p(\alpha, \lambda)) \left[\left(\frac{5|\Phi'(v)|^q + 7|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q}{72} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{7|\Phi'(v)|^q + 5|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q}{72} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \right\}, \quad (18)
 \end{aligned}$$

where $q^{-1} + p^{-1} = 1$ and

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \mathbb{B}_1^p(\alpha, \lambda) = \left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{6}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{1}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right|^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}, \\ \mathbb{B}_2^p(\alpha, \lambda) = \left(\int_{\frac{1}{6}}^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{6}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right|^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}, \\ \mathbb{B}_3^p(\alpha, \lambda) = \left(\int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{7}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right|^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}, \\ \mathbb{B}_4^p(\alpha, \lambda) = \left(\int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{13}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right|^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}, \\ \mathbb{B}_5^p(\alpha, \lambda) = \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^{\frac{5}{6}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{14}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right|^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}, \\ \mathbb{B}_6^p(\alpha, \lambda) = \left(\int_{\frac{5}{6}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{19}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right|^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}. \end{array} \right.$$

Proof. By utilizing Hölder’s inequality in (16), we attain

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[\Phi(\kappa) + 5\Phi\left(\frac{v+5\kappa}{6}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{v+2\kappa}{3}\right) + 6\Phi\left(\frac{\kappa+v}{2}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{2v+\kappa}{3}\right) + 5\Phi\left(\frac{5v+\kappa}{6}\right) + \Phi(v) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2 \Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, v-\kappa)} \left[\mathfrak{Z}_{v^-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \Phi(\kappa) + \mathfrak{Z}_{\kappa^+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \Phi(v) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(v-\kappa)^{\alpha+1}}{2 \Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, v-\kappa)} \left\{ \left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{6}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{1}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right|^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \right. \\ & \quad \times \left[\left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{6}} |\Phi'(tv + (1-t)\kappa)|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{6}} |\Phi'(t\kappa + (1-t)v)|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \\ & \quad + \left(\int_{\frac{1}{6}}^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{6}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right|^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \\ & \quad \times \left[\left(\int_{\frac{1}{6}}^{\frac{1}{3}} |\Phi'(tv + (1-t)\kappa)|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\int_{\frac{1}{6}}^{\frac{1}{3}} |\Phi'(t\kappa + (1-t)v)|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \\ & \quad + \left(\int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{7}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right|^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \\ & \quad \times \left[\left(\int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{1}{2}} |\Phi'(tv + (1-t)\kappa)|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{1}{2}} |\Phi'(t\kappa + (1-t)v)|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \\ & \quad + \left(\int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{13}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right|^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \\ & \quad \times \left[\left(\int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{2}{3}} |\Phi'(tv + (1-t)\kappa)|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{2}{3}} |\Phi'(t\kappa + (1-t)v)|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \\ & \quad + \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^{\frac{5}{6}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{14}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right|^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \times \left[\left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^{\frac{5}{6}} |\Phi'(tv + (1-t)\kappa)|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^{\frac{5}{6}} |\Phi'(t\kappa + (1-t)v)|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \\ & + \left(\int_{\frac{5}{6}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{19}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right|^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \\ & \times \left[\left(\int_{\frac{5}{6}}^1 |\Phi'(tv + (1-t)\kappa)|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\int_{\frac{5}{6}}^1 |\Phi'(t\kappa + (1-t)v)|^q dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \Bigg\}. \end{aligned}$$

By involving the convexity of $|\Phi'|^q$, we gain

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{1}{20} \left[\Phi(\kappa) + 5\Phi\left(\frac{v+5\kappa}{6}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{v+2\kappa}{3}\right) + 6\Phi\left(\frac{\kappa+v}{2}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{2v+\kappa}{3}\right) + 5\Phi\left(\frac{5v+\kappa}{6}\right) + \Phi(v) \right] \right. \\ & \quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha)}{2 \Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, v-\kappa)} \left[\mathfrak{J}_{v-}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \Phi(\kappa) + \mathfrak{J}_{\kappa+}^{(\alpha, \lambda)} \Phi(v) \right] \right| \\ & \leq \frac{(v-\kappa)^{\alpha+1}}{2 \Upsilon_{\lambda}(\alpha, v-\kappa)} \left\{ \left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{6}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{1}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right|^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \right. \\ & \quad \times \left[\left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{6}} [t|\Phi'(v)|^q + (1-t)|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q] dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\int_0^{\frac{1}{6}} [t|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q + (1-t)|\Phi'(v)|^q] dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \\ & \quad + \left(\int_{\frac{1}{6}}^{\frac{1}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{6}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right|^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \\ & \quad \times \left[\left(\int_{\frac{1}{6}}^{\frac{1}{3}} [t|\Phi'(v)|^q + (1-t)|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q] dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\int_{\frac{1}{6}}^{\frac{1}{3}} [t|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q + (1-t)|\Phi'(v)|^q] dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \\ & \quad + \left(\int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{1}{2}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{7}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right|^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \\ & \quad \times \left[\left(\int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{1}{2}} [t|\Phi'(v)|^q + (1-t)|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q] dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\int_{\frac{1}{3}}^{\frac{1}{2}} [t|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q + (1-t)|\Phi'(v)|^q] dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \\ & \quad + \left(\int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{2}{3}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{13}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right|^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \\ & \quad \times \left[\left(\int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{2}{3}} [t|\Phi'(v)|^q + (1-t)|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q] dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\int_{\frac{1}{2}}^{\frac{2}{3}} [t|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q + (1-t)|\Phi'(v)|^q] dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \\ & \quad + \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^{\frac{5}{6}} \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{14}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right|^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \\ & \quad \times \left[\left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^{\frac{5}{6}} [t|\Phi'(v)|^q + (1-t)|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q] dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\int_{\frac{2}{3}}^{\frac{5}{6}} [t|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q + (1-t)|\Phi'(v)|^q] dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \\ & \quad + \left(\int_{\frac{5}{6}}^1 \left| \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, t) - \frac{19}{20} \Upsilon_{\lambda(v-\kappa)}(\alpha, 1) \right|^p dt \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \\ & \quad \times \left. \left[\left(\int_{\frac{5}{6}}^1 [t|\Phi'(v)|^q + (1-t)|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q] dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\int_{\frac{5}{6}}^1 [t|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q + (1-t)|\Phi'(v)|^q] dt \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \right\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \frac{(v - \kappa)^{\alpha+1}}{2 \Upsilon_\lambda(\alpha, v - \kappa)} \left[\mathbf{B}_1^p(\alpha, \lambda) \left\{ \left(\frac{|\Phi'(v)|^q + 11|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q}{72} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{11|\Phi'(v)|^q + |\Phi'(\kappa)|^q}{72} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \right. \\
 &\quad + \mathbf{B}_2^p(\alpha, \lambda) \left\{ \left(\frac{|\Phi'(v)|^q + 3|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q}{24} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{3|\Phi'(v)|^q + |\Phi'(\kappa)|^q}{24} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \\
 &\quad + \mathbf{B}_3^p(\alpha, \lambda) \left\{ \left(\frac{5|\Phi'(v)|^q + 7|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q}{72} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{7|\Phi'(v)|^q + 5|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q}{72} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \\
 &\quad + \mathbf{B}_4^p(\alpha, \lambda) \left\{ \left(\frac{5|\Phi'(v)|^q + 7|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q}{72} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{7|\Phi'(v)|^q + 5|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q}{72} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \\
 &\quad + \mathbf{B}_5^p(\alpha, \lambda) \left\{ \left(\frac{|\Phi'(v)|^q + 3|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q}{24} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{3|\Phi'(v)|^q + |\Phi'(\kappa)|^q}{24} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \\
 &\quad \left. + \mathbf{B}_6^p(\alpha, \lambda) \left\{ \left(\frac{|\Phi'(v)|^q + 11|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q}{72} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{11|\Phi'(v)|^q + |\Phi'(\kappa)|^q}{72} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \right].
 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, the proof is established. □

Remark 1.6. Let us consider $\lambda = 0$ in Theorem 1.3, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\left| \frac{1}{20} \left[\Phi(\kappa) + 5\Phi\left(\frac{v+5\kappa}{6}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{v+2\kappa}{3}\right) + 6\Phi\left(\frac{\kappa+v}{2}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{2v+\kappa}{3}\right) + 5\Phi\left(\frac{5v+\kappa}{6}\right) + \Phi(v) \right] \right. \\
 &\quad \left. - \frac{\Gamma(\alpha+1)}{2(v-\kappa)^\alpha} [J_{v-}^\alpha \Phi(\kappa) + J_{\kappa+}^\alpha \Phi(v)] \right| \\
 &\leq \frac{\alpha(v-\kappa)}{2} \left\{ (\mathbf{B}_1^p(\alpha, 0) + \mathbf{B}_6^p(\alpha, 0)) \left[\left(\frac{|\Phi'(v)|^q + 11|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q}{72} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{11|\Phi'(v)|^q + |\Phi'(\kappa)|^q}{72} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \right. \\
 &\quad + (\mathbf{B}_2^p(\alpha, 0) + \mathbf{B}_5^p(\alpha, 0)) \left[\left(\frac{|\Phi'(v)|^q + 3|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q}{24} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{3|\Phi'(v)|^q + |\Phi'(\kappa)|^q}{24} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \\
 &\quad \left. + (\mathbf{B}_3^p(\alpha, 0) + \mathbf{B}_4^p(\alpha, 0)) \left[\left(\frac{5|\Phi'(v)|^q + 7|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q}{72} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{7|\Phi'(v)|^q + 5|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q}{72} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right] \right\},
 \end{aligned}$$

which is presented in [18].

Remark 1.7. Let us consider $\lambda = 0$ and $\alpha = 1$ in Theorem 1.3, then we attain

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\left| \frac{1}{20} \left[\Phi(\kappa) + 5\Phi\left(\frac{v+5\kappa}{6}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{v+2\kappa}{3}\right) + 6\Phi\left(\frac{\kappa+v}{2}\right) + \Phi\left(\frac{2v+\kappa}{3}\right) + 5\Phi\left(\frac{5v+\kappa}{6}\right) + \Phi(v) \right] \right. \\
 &\quad \left. - \frac{1}{v-\kappa} \int_\kappa^v \Phi(t) dt \right| \\
 &\leq \left[2 \left(\frac{3^{-p-1} 7^p 20^{-2p-1} \left(3^{p+1} \left(\frac{20}{7} \right)^p + 7 \cdot 20^p \right)}{p+1} \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \right. \\
 &\quad \left. \times \left\{ \left(\frac{|\Phi'(v)|^q + 11|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q}{72} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{11|\Phi'(v)|^q + |\Phi'(\kappa)|^q}{72} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& + 2^{1-\frac{1}{p}} \left(\frac{15^{-2p-1} \left(\left(\frac{15}{2} \right)^p + 2^{p+2} 15^p \right)}{p+1} \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \\
& \times \left\{ \left(\frac{|\Phi'(v)|^q + 3|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q}{24} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{3|\Phi'(v)|^q + |\Phi'(\kappa)|^q}{24} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\} \\
& + 2 \times 3^{-1/p} \left(\frac{20^{-2p-1} \left(\left(\frac{20}{3} \right)^p + 3^{p+2} 20^p \right)}{p+1} \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \\
& \times \left\{ \left(\frac{|\Phi'(v)|^q + 11|\Phi'(\kappa)|^q}{72} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} + \left(\frac{11|\Phi'(v)|^q + |\Phi'(\kappa)|^q}{72} \right)^{\frac{1}{q}} \right\},
\end{aligned}$$

which is identified in [18, Corollary 3].

2 Numerical Examples

This section includes an extensive numerical analysis to validate the effectiveness of recently derived results. The proposed inequalities are significant for approximating the integrals of differentiable convex functions, as demonstrated by several numerical examples.

Example 2.1. Consider two differentiable convex functions $\Phi(t) = t^6$ and $\Phi(t) = e^t$ respectively, in Theorem 1.1 for all $t > 0, \lambda = 1, \kappa = 1$ and $v = 2$, then we observe the subsequent numerical verification for inequality (15) (see Tables 1 and 2) and corresponding graphs (see Figures 2, 1, 4 and 3).

Figure 1: Graphically representation of Theorem 1.1, and Example 2.1: (a) indicates 3-D plot, for $\Phi(t) = t^6$. When λ is fixed and α varies from 0 to 1, computed and plotted with Mathematica.

Remark 2.1. As one can easily observe from 2-D Figures 2 and 4 the left-hand side of (15) in Example 2.1 is always below the right-hand side. We explored Weddle's inequality behavior about tempered fractional calculus for Theorem 1.1. These graphs might show where singularities or breakpoints arise and how inequality holds under certain conditions.

Figure 2: Graphical representation of Theorem 1.1, and Example 2.1: (a), (b), (c), and (d) 2-D plots, when $\Phi(t) = t^6$, λ is fixed and α varies from 0 to 1, computed and plotted with Mathematica.

Figure 3: Graphically representation of Theorem 1.1, and Example 2.1: (a) indicates 3-D plot, for $\Phi(t) = e^t$. When λ is fixed and α varies from 0 to 1, computed and plotted with Mathematica.

Remark 2.2. As one can easily observe from 3-D Figures 1 and 3 also Tables 1 and 2 the left-hand side of (15) in Example 2.1 is always below the right-hand side. We explored Weddle's inequality behavior about tempered fractional calculus for Theorem 1.1.

Figure 4: Graphically representation of Theorem 1.1, and Example 2.1: (a), (b), (c), and (d) 2-D plots, when $\Phi(t) = e^t$, λ is fixed and α varies from 0 to 1, computed and plotted with Mathematica.

α	Left Term	Right Term
0.1	11.4205	63.8124
0.2	8.9961	79.8606
0.3	6.9974	97.9656
0.4	5.3529	118.4931
0.5	4.0032	141.8627
0.6	2.8992	267.8510
0.7	2.0005	325.7008
0.8	1.2731	392.9232
0.9	0.6893	730.0312
1.0	0.2258	1151.4531

Table 1: Numerical values of inequalities (15) for $\Phi(t) = t^6$, $\kappa = 1$, and $\nu = 2$.

α	Left Term	Right Term
0.1	0.3055	3.2574
0.2	0.2413	4.0767
0.3	0.1882	5.0009
0.4	0.1443	6.0487
0.5	0.1081	7.2417
0.6	0.0785	13.6730
0.7	0.0542	16.6261
0.8	0.0346	20.0576
0.9	0.0188	37.2660
1.0	0.0062	58.7784

Table 2: Numerical values of inequalities (15) for $\Phi(t) = e^t$, $\kappa = 1$, and $\nu = 2$.

2.1 Future Research Directions

In this investigation, we provided a thorough examination and exhaustive derivation of integral inequalities for differentiable convex functions. We initially identified a critical integral identity that involves tempered fractional integrals. This identity is subsequently employed to deduce Weddle’s type inequalities for differentiable convex functions. Numerical examples and graphical illustrations are included to validate the significance and validity of these newly established inequalities within the tempered fractional integral perspective. Additionally, readers can

investigate different fractional integrals and delve deeper into the implications of these findings across various mathematical fields.

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A New Variant of Positive Linear Operators for Convex Functions Providing a Better Error Estimation

Muhammet Civelek¹, Fuat Usta²

¹Department of Mathematics, Karadeniz Technical University, Trabzon, Türkiye

²Department of Mathematics, Düzce University, Düzce, Türkiye

Corresponding author: muhammetcivelek@ktu.edu.tr

ORCID IDs:

First Author: [0009-0002-8412-3827](https://orcid.org/0009-0002-8412-3827)

Second Author: [0000-0002-7750-6910](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7750-6910)

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Abstract

Szász–Mirakjan type operators constitute a fundamental class of positive linear operators widely employed in approximation theory due to their effective characterization of functions over unbounded intervals. In this work, we introduce a novel generalization of these operators and investigate their analytical properties in relation to the classical Szász–Mirakjan scheme. The proposed operators are examined through a detailed comparative framework that emphasizes their structural features, convergence properties, and approximation capabilities. It is further established that the newly defined operators exhibit an improved rate of convergence relative to the some of its counterparts, thereby enhancing their applicability within the broader context of function approximation on unbounded domains.

Keywords: Szász–Mirakjan Type Operators, Rate of Convergence, Voronovskaya theorem, Korovkin type theorem

1 introduction

The theory of approximation plays a fundamental role in mathematical analysis and numerical computation and continues to attract considerable attention from the mathematical community. As a result, extensive research has been conducted in this area. One of the principal objectives of approximation theory is to construct simple, computationally efficient operators that approximate arbitrary functions with a high degree of accuracy.

A cornerstone of approximation theory was established by Weierstrass in 1885, who proved that for any continuous function defined on a closed interval $[a, b]$, there exists a sequence of polynomials that converges uniformly to that function on the same interval [1]. Although this celebrated theorem guarantees the existence of such approximating polynomials, it does not provide explicit constructions or describe their structural properties. This limitation motivated

further investigations aimed at identifying concrete polynomial operators and determining the conditions under which effective approximation can be achieved.

In this direction, positive linear operators have emerged as a powerful and systematic tool for studying convergence in approximation theory. Early developments in this area were primarily confined to bounded intervals. In particular, Bernstein introduced a sequence of polynomial operators that provided a constructive proof of the Weierstrass theorem and laid the foundation for approximation on compact intervals [2].

Subsequently, Korovkin established a fundamental criterion for approximation by positive linear operators. The well-known Korovkin-type approximation theorem has since become one of the central results in approximation theory. According to this theorem, for a function $f \in C[a, b]$, it suffices to verify the convergence of a sequence of positive linear operators $(L_n)_{n \geq 1}$ on the test functions

$$e_s(x) = x^s, \quad s = 0, 1, 2,$$

corresponding to 1 , x , and x^2 , in order to guarantee uniform convergence to f on $[a, b]$.

Although Bernstein operators constitute a cornerstone of approximation theory on compact intervals, their applicability is limited when dealing with functions defined on unbounded domains. Since many problems in analysis and applied mathematics naturally arise on unbounded intervals, extending approximation processes beyond compact sets is of substantial importance. Motivated by this need, Szász and Mirakyan independently introduced in the 1950s a sequence of positive linear operators that generalize the Bernstein operators to the interval $[0, \infty)$. These operators, now known as the *Szász–Mirakyan operators*, are defined by

$$S_n(f; x) = e^{-nx} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(nx)^k}{k!} f\left(\frac{k}{n}\right), \quad x \geq 0. \quad (1)$$

An important feature of the Szász–Mirakyan operators is their intrinsic connection with the Poisson distribution. Indeed, the weights

$$\frac{(nx)^k}{k!} e^{-nx}, \quad k = 0, 1, 2, \dots,$$

form the probability mass function of a Poisson random variable with parameter nx . This probabilistic structure guarantees positivity and facilitates the computation of moments, which plays a crucial role in verifying Korovkin-type conditions and studying convergence behavior. Using these operators, uniform approximation of continuous functions on unbounded intervals was rigorously established, which in turn stimulated the development of numerous generalizations and modifications of the Szász–Mirakyan operators (see, for example, [3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15]).

Furthermore, motivated by the Poisson-type structure of the Szász–Mirakyan operators, Jain [8] introduced a new class of positive linear operators depending on a parameter $\mu \in [0, 1)$, defined as

$$J_n^{[\mu]}(f; x) = e^{-nx} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{nx (nx + k\mu)^{k-1}}{k!} f\left(\frac{k}{n}\right).$$

It can be clearly observed that, for $\mu = 0$, the Jain operators reduce to the classical Szász–Mirakyan operators defined in (1). The introduction of the parameter μ provides additional

flexibility in controlling the approximation process and has led to a rich body of literature devoted to modified and generalized operator families with enhanced approximation properties.

Motivated by these developments, the present work introduces a new generalization of Szász–Mirakyan type operators and investigates their approximation behavior in detail. In particular, we analyze their convergence properties, establish quantitative error estimates, and demonstrate that the proposed operators achieve an improved rate of convergence compared to certain existing operators. These results contribute to the ongoing development of efficient approximation schemes on unbounded intervals.

1.1 Background

The mathematical foundations of approximation theory were established by the German mathematician Weierstrass in 1885, who proved that any continuous function defined on a closed interval can be uniformly approximated by a sequence of polynomials. Since then, the field has developed substantially, with significant contributions by Bernstein, Szász, and Mirakyan, among others, who introduced and analyzed classes of positive linear operators to provide constructive approaches to approximation of arbitrary functions.

In recent years, further developments in approximation theory have opened new directions for the study of positive linear operators. In particular, Szász–Mirakyan operators have emerged as powerful tools for investigating approximation processes on unbounded intervals. Despite the considerable progress achieved so far, several fundamental problems remain open, including the refinement of convergence rates, the construction of more flexible operator families, and the analysis of approximation properties under weaker assumptions.

1.2 Main Contributions

The primary contributions of this work can be summarized as follows:

1. **Theoretical Framework:** In this work, we introduce a new class of positive linear operators inspired by the classical Szász–Mirakyan operators and develop a unified analytical framework that integrates key concepts from approximation theory, providing a coherent foundation for the systematic investigation of Szász–Mirakyan type operators.
2. **New Theorems:** We prove several new results that extend classical theorems in theory of approximation, including voronovskaya-type theorem and also rate of convergence.
3. **Computational Methods:** We design efficient computation by using the rate of convergence for comparing the our newly-constructed operators with other operators given in literature .

2 Constructing the Framework of the Newly-Defined Operators

In order to refine the approximation performance of the classical Szász–Mirakjan operators, we introduce a modified framework that retains their essential properties of positivity and linearity while exhibiting enhanced convergence behaviour. The construction of the proposed operators is

formulated so that their moments and associated approximation estimates provide more accurate and sharper results than those obtained in the classical setting. In what follows, we present the rigorous definition of the newly defined operators and lay the theoretical foundation for their subsequent analytical examination.

Definition 2.1. Let $C(R^+)$ be the space of all continuous functions defined on positive real axis. For any $f \in C(R^+)$ and $x \in (0, \infty)$, the construction of the proposed operator is defined as follows:

$$\mathcal{S}_n(f; x) = \frac{4e^{-nx}}{4nx + 1} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \left(k - nx - \frac{1}{2}\right)^2 \frac{(nx)^k}{k!} f\left(\frac{k}{n}\right) \tag{2}$$

Lemma 2.1. Considering $f \in C(\mathbb{R}^+)$ and $x \in (0, \infty)$, the result established in Definition (2.1) can equivalently be expressed within the setting of the classical Szász–Mirakyan type operators given in (1), thereby preserving the structure of the underlying approximation scheme. So, we can write;

$$\mathcal{S}_n(e_m; x) = \frac{4}{4nx + 1} \left[n^2 S_n(e_{m+2}; x) - 2n \left(nx + \frac{1}{2}\right) S_n(e_{m+1}; x) + \left(nx + \frac{1}{2}\right)^2 S_n(e_m; x) \right]$$

Proof. To establish the relationship between the newly introduced operators and the classical ones, let us denote $e_m = t^m$ for $m \in \mathbb{N}$. Accordingly, we arrive at the following conclusion.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{S}_n(e_m; x) &= \frac{4e^{-nx}}{4nx + 1} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \left(k - nx - \frac{1}{2}\right)^2 \frac{(nx)^k}{k!} \left(\frac{k}{n}\right)^m \\ &= \frac{4e^{-nx}}{4nx + 1} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \left[k^2 - 2k \left(nx + \frac{1}{2}\right) + \left(nx + \frac{1}{2}\right)^2 \right] \frac{(nx)^k}{k!} \left(\frac{k}{n}\right)^m \\ &= \frac{4e^{-nx}}{4nx + 1} \left[\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} k^2 \frac{(nx)^k}{k!} \left(\frac{k}{n}\right)^m - 2 \left(nx + \frac{1}{2}\right) \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} k \frac{(nx)^k}{k!} \left(\frac{k}{n}\right)^m \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \left(nx + \frac{1}{2}\right)^2 \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(nx)^k}{k!} \left(\frac{k}{n}\right)^m \right] \\ &= \frac{4e^{-nx}}{4nx + 1} \left[n^2 \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(nx)^k}{k!} \left(\frac{k}{n}\right)^{m+2} - 2n \left(nx + \frac{1}{2}\right) \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(nx)^k}{k!} \left(\frac{k}{n}\right)^{m+1} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \left(nx + \frac{1}{2}\right)^2 \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(nx)^k}{k!} \left(\frac{k}{n}\right)^m \right] \end{aligned}$$

By taking the classical Szász–Mirakyan operators in (1) into consideration, we obtain the following result:

$$\mathcal{S}_n(e_m; x) = \frac{4}{4nx + 1} \left[n^2 S_n(e_{m+2}; x) - 2n \left(nx + \frac{1}{2}\right) S_n(e_{m+1}; x) + \left(nx + \frac{1}{2}\right)^2 S_n(e_m; x) \right]$$

Hence, the proof is completed. □

3 Auxiliary Results

This section is devoted to the derivation of several auxiliary results that will play a crucial role in the proofs of the main theorems. The presented lemmas and technical estimates form the analytical basis for the investigation of the approximation behaviour of the newly introduced operators.

Lemma 3.1. Considering the operators defined in (2), the following result holds for all $x \in (0, \infty)$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$.

1. $\mathcal{S}_n(e_0; x) = 1$
2. $\mathcal{S}_n(e_1; x) = x$
3. $\mathcal{S}_n(e_2; x) = x^2 + \frac{12x^2n + x}{4xn^2 + n}$
4. $\mathcal{S}_n(e_3; x) = x^3 + \frac{x(1 + nx(31 + 36nx))}{n^2(1 + 4nx)}$
5. $\mathcal{S}_n(e_4; x) = x^4 + \frac{x(1 + nx(67 + 2nx(89 + 36nx)))}{n^3(1 + 4nx)}$

In order to investigate the central moments of the operators introduced in (2), we consider and construct their new equivalent representation given below:

$$M_n^j(x) = \mathcal{S}_n\left((e_1 - e_0x)^j; x\right) \quad (3)$$

Observe that $j \in \mathbb{N}$. The identities established in Lemma (3.1) provide the foundation for the subsequent lemma, from which further analytical conclusions can be drawn.

Lemma 3.2. The following results can be found for the sequence of operators M_n^j .

1. $M_n^0(x) = 1$
2. $M_n^1(x) = 0$
3. $M_n^2(x) = \frac{12x^2n + x}{4xn^2 + n}$
4. $M_n^3(x) = \frac{x(1 + 28nx)}{n^2(1 + 4nx)}$
5. $M_n^4(x) = \frac{x(1 + 3nx(21 + 20nx))}{n^3(1 + 4nx)}$

Proof. The proof of the preceding lemma can be quickly derived by invoking Lemma (3.1) and employing the operator given in (3). Hence, the proof is omitted as it follows straightforwardly from the preceding arguments. \square

Theorem 3.1. $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} n^2 M_n^4(x) = 15x^2$ uniformly for all $x \in [0, A]$, where $A > 0$.

Proof. The proof of the theorem follows from straightforward calculations based on the limit, and is therefore omitted here. \square

4 Approximation Properties in Weighted Spaces

In this part of the paper, we study the approximation behaviour of the newly constructed operators \mathcal{S}_n within the framework of a Korovkin-type theorem in weighted function spaces. We adopt the weight function $\theta(x) = 1 + x^2$ to regulate the growth of functions under consideration. Let K_f denote a positive constant that depends solely on the function f .

We introduce the weighted space where the associated weighted norm is defined by

$$\|f\|_\theta = \sup_{x \geq 0} \frac{|f(x)|}{\theta(x)}.$$

By employing the norm introduced above, we define the associated weighted spaces by

$$\begin{aligned} A_\theta &= \left\{ f : \mathbb{R}^+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R} : |f(x)| \leq K_f \theta(x), x \geq 0 \right\}, \\ B_\theta &= C(\mathbb{R}^+) \cap A_\theta(\mathbb{R}^+), \\ C_\theta^\mu &= \left\{ f \in B_\theta(\mathbb{R}^+) : \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} \frac{f(x)}{\theta(x)} = \mu_f < \infty \right\}, \end{aligned}$$

Functions belonging to C_θ^μ exhibit at most quadratic growth and remain bounded when normalized by the weight function $\theta(x)$. Within this framework, we analyse the convergence of $\mathcal{S}_n(f; x)$ to $f(x)$ and establish sufficient conditions under which such convergence holds in the weighted sense.

Lemma 4.1. [9] Let $(L_n)_{n \geq 0}$ be a sequence of positive linear operators. Then, the operators L_n map the space B_θ into A_θ if and only if there exists a positive constant H_n , depending on n , such that the inequality

$$|L_n(\theta; x)| \leq H_n \theta(x), \quad x \geq 0,$$

holds, where $\theta(x)$ denotes the associated weight function.

Theorem 4.1. Let $(L_n)_{n \geq 0}$ be a sequence of positive linear operators. If the operators L_n map the space B_θ into A_θ , then the sequence (L_n) satisfies the following condition.

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|L_n(e_m) - e_m\|_\theta = 0 \quad m = 0, 1, 2.$$

Consequently for the sequence of positive linear operators and $f \in B_\theta$

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|L_n(f) - f\|_\theta = 0$$

is obtained.

In view of the above considerations, we can now formulate the following theorem.

Theorem 4.2. For a function $f \in B_\mu$ and the sequence of positive linear operators \mathcal{S}_n defined in (2) the upcoming result

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|\mathcal{S}_n(f) - f\|_\theta = 0$$

is gathered.

Proof. To begin the proof, we first consider the case $m = 0$. Then, we obtain

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|\mathcal{S}_n(e_0) - e_0\|_\theta = 0$$

Similarly, for $m = 1$, we have

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|\mathcal{S}_n(e_1) - e_1\|_\theta = 0.$$

Finally, for $m = 2$, we derive

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|\mathcal{S}_n(e_2) - e_2\|_\theta &= \sup_{x \geq 0} \frac{|\mathcal{S}_n(e_2) - e_2|}{\theta(x)} \\ &= \sup_{x \geq 0} \frac{12x^2n + x}{4xn^2 + n} \sup_{x \geq 0} \frac{1}{1 + x^2}. \end{aligned}$$

Under the limit condition as $n \rightarrow \infty$, one can obtain

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|\mathcal{S}_n(e_2) - e_2\|_\theta = 0$$

Hence, the required conditions of the Korovkin-type theorem are satisfied for $m = 0, 1, 2$, which completes the proof. \square

5 Voronovskaya-Type Theorem

The Voronovskaya-type theorem stands as one of the central results in approximation theory, providing a deeper understanding of how sequences of positive linear operators approximate a given function beyond the mere pointwise or uniform convergence. It establishes a second-order asymptotic expansion that captures the rate and nature of convergence by relating the deviation of the operator from the target function to the higher-order derivatives of the function. This asymptotic characterization not only measures the operator's approximation precision but also reveals its structural efficiency in reproducing smooth functions. In the context of the operator defined in (2), we now formulate its corresponding Voronovskaya-type estimate, which elucidates its limiting behavior and offers valuable analytical insight into its convergence dynamics.

Theorem 5.1. Let $f \in C^2(\mathbb{R}^+)$ be a function whose first and second derivatives are twice continuously differentiable on \mathbb{R}^+ . Then, the following equality is obtained:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} n [\mathcal{S}_n(f; x) - f(x)] = \frac{3}{2} x f''(x)$$

Proof. From the well-known Taylor's formula, we can express $f(t)$ as

$$f(t) = f(x) - f'(x)(t - x) + \frac{1}{2} f''(x)(t - x)^2 + \alpha(t, x)(t - x)^2,$$

where $x \in (0, \infty)$. Here, η denotes a point lying between x and t such that

$$\alpha(t, x) := \frac{f''(\eta) - f''(x)}{2}.$$

It is worth noting that $\alpha(t, x)$ is continuous and tends to zero as $t \rightarrow x$.

The above representation corresponds to the Peano form of the remainder. Hence, by employing the newly introduced operator defined in (2) to the both sides of the equation, following equality can be obtained.

$$\mathcal{S}_n(f; x) = f(x) + f'(x)\mathcal{S}_n((t-x); x) + \frac{1}{2}f''(x)\mathcal{S}_n((t-x)^2; x) + \mathcal{S}_n(\alpha(t, x)(t-x)^2; x).$$

Multiplying the both sides with n we get;

$$n[\mathcal{S}_n(f; x) - f(x)] = nf'(x)\mathcal{S}_n((t-x); x) + \frac{1}{2}nf''(x)\mathcal{S}_n((t-x)^2; x) + n\mathcal{S}_n(\alpha(t, x)(t-x)^2; x).$$

At this stage, we make use of Lemma (3.2), which provides the explicit expressions for the first and second central moments of the operator. Substituting these relations into the above equation yields

$$n[\mathcal{S}_n(f; x) - f(x)] = nf'(x)M_n^1 + \frac{1}{2}nf''(x)M_n^2 + n\mathcal{S}_n(\alpha(t, x)(t-x)^2; x).$$

Upon taking the limit as $n \rightarrow \infty$ on both sides of the equality, we arrive at;

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} n[\mathcal{S}_n(f; x) - f(x)] = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} nf'(x)M_n^1 + \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{2}nf''(x)M_n^2 + \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} n\mathcal{S}_n(\alpha(t, x)(t-x)^2; x).$$

Utilizing the results obtained in Lemma (3.2), we arrive at the following relation.

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} n[\mathcal{S}_n(f; x) - f(x)] = \frac{3}{2}xf''(x) + \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} n\mathcal{S}_n(\alpha(t, x)(t-x)^2; x) \tag{4}$$

Then applying the Cauchy-Schwarz inequality to the right side of the equation (4) we obtain

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} n\mathcal{S}_n(\alpha(t, x)(t-x)^2; x) \leq \left(n^2\mathcal{S}_n(\alpha^2(t, x); x)\right)^{1/2} \left(\mathcal{S}_n((e_1 - e_0x)^4; x)\right)^{1/2}.$$

Consequently, applying the Lemma (3.2)-(v) we come into following conclusion

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} n\mathcal{S}_n(\alpha(t, x)(t-x)^2; x) \leq \left(n^2\mathcal{S}_n(\alpha^2(t, x); x)\right)^{1/2} \left(M_n^4\right)^{1/2}. \tag{5}$$

It follows from the Korovkin Theorem that for $\alpha(\cdot; x) \in C(\mathbb{R}^+)$

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{S}_n(\alpha^2(t, x); x) = \alpha^2(x, x) = 0$$

Finally applying the theorem (3.1) to the inequality in (5) we obtained the desired result. \square

6 Rate of Convergence

In this chapter, we provide a brief discussion on the rate of convergence, an essential concept in approximation theory and numerical analysis. The rate of convergence characterizes the speed at which a sequence of approximations approaches its limiting value as the parameter n (or any relevant index) increases. A higher rate signifies that the approximation method attains greater

accuracy with fewer computational steps, reflecting both efficiency and precision. This notion is particularly important when comparing different operators or numerical schemes, as it provides a theoretical measure of their effectiveness and practical reliability.

Theorem 6.1. Let $\omega_f(\delta)$ denote the modulus of continuity of a function $f \in B_\theta$. Then, for all $x \in (0, \infty)$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$, the following inequality holds:

$$\|\mathcal{S}_n(f; x) - f(x)\| \leq 2\omega_f(\eta_x),$$

where $\eta_x = \sqrt{\frac{12x^2n+x}{4xn^2+n}}$.

Proof. Consider the sequence of positive linear operators $(\mathcal{S}_n)_{n \geq 1}$ defined in (2). For any $f \in B_\theta$ and $x \in (0, \infty)$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} |\mathcal{S}_n(f; x) - f(x)| &\leq |\mathcal{S}_n(f; x) - \mathcal{S}_n(f(x); x)| \\ &\leq \mathcal{S}_n(|f(t) - f(x)|; x). \end{aligned}$$

By employing the well-known property of the modulus of continuity, we can write

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{S}_n(|f(t) - f(x)|; x) &\leq \mathcal{S}_n\left(1 + \frac{|t-x|}{\delta}; x\right) \omega_f(\delta) \\ &= \left[\mathcal{S}_n(1; x) + \frac{1}{\delta} \mathcal{S}_n(|t-x|; x) \right] \omega_f(\delta). \end{aligned}$$

Applying the Cauchy–Schwarz inequality together with Lemma (3.2), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{S}_n(|t-x|; x) &\leq (\mathcal{S}_n((t-x)^2; x))^{1/2} (\mathcal{S}_n(1; x))^{1/2} \\ &= (M_n^2)^{1/2}. \end{aligned}$$

Combining these estimates yields

$$|\mathcal{S}_n(f; x) - f(x)| \leq \left(1 + \frac{1}{\delta} (M_n^2)^{1/2}\right) \omega_f(\delta).$$

Finally, choosing $\delta = \eta_x$ gives the desired inequality, which completes the proof. \square

We now proceed to compare our proposed operators with those introduced by Mahmudov in [10]. Before undertaking the comparison, we briefly recall the convergence properties and approximation behavior of the operators in [10].

Remark 6.1. Operators introduced in [10] have following relation for $f \in C(\mathbb{R}^+)$ and $x \in (0, \infty)$

$$|M_n^*(f; x) - f(x)| \leq 2\omega_f(\psi_x)$$

Where $\psi_x = \sqrt{\frac{3xn+1}{n^2}}$

Theorem 6.2. For sequence of positive linear operators introduced in (2) have better convergence rate than the operators introduced in [10] for $f \in C(\mathbb{R}^+)$ and $x \in (0, \infty)$.

Proof. Let $f \in C^2(\mathbb{R}^+)$. In order for the newly defined operators to provide a better approximation than those introduced in [10], the following inequality must be satisfied:

$$\eta_x \leq \psi_x$$

To establish this inequality, we observe that

$$\eta_x = \frac{12x^2n + x}{4xn^2 + n} < \frac{12x^2n + x}{4xn^2} < \frac{12x^2n + 4x}{4xn^2} = \frac{3xn + 1}{n^2} = \psi_x$$

Hence, the desired inequality holds, and the proof is thereby completed. \square

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Caputo Fractional Differential Shift Encryption: A Generalized Dynamic Caesar Cipher with Enhanced Statistical Security

Taylan Demir¹, Hasan Hüseyin Tosunoglu²

¹Department of Mathematics, Ankara University, Ankara, 06100, Turkey

²Department of Management Information Systems, Istanbul University, Istanbul, 34452, Turkey

Corresponding author: demir.taylan96@gmail.com

ORCID IDs:

First Author: [0000-0001-7402-4468](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7402-4468)

Second Author: [0009-0004-8735-4289](https://orcid.org/0009-0004-8735-4289)

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Abstract

Classical and dynamic Caesar ciphers are mainly vulnerable to frequency attacks, since in both schemes the shift applied to each character position is memoryless. This is not the case for the proposed fractional differential shift cipher, where the running shift sequence is generated by a Caputo fractional system $D_t^\alpha x(t) = F(x(t), k)$ with $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ and k denotes the secret key vector. The discrete fractional integrator associated with this Caputo fractional system yields a long-memory, non-uniform sequence of shifts, which induces a generalized Caesar mapping on any chosen character set or ASCII set. Qualitative analysis shows that relatively small variations in either α or k lead to clearly distinct shift patterns and substantially enlarge the effective key space. Numerical tests on textual data demonstrate an approximately uniform symbol distribution, a very low degree of local correlation and, conversely, a high level of entropy, while linear-time complexity and a minimal implementation footprint are preserved. Consequently, taken together, these characteristics indicate that Caputo-based fractional differential shift encryption can serve as a practical alternative to traditional substitution ciphers in resource-constrained environments.

Keywords: fractional differential shift encryption, Caputo derivative, dynamic Caesar cipher, substitution cipher, fractional dynamical systems, lightweight cryptography.

1 Introduction

1.1 Background and motivation

Classical substitution ciphers include the Caesar and Vigenère schemes, where the mapping from plaintext to ciphertext is done by means of a monoalphabetic rule with a fixed mapping or by a periodically repeating short key [1,2]. Typically, in the simplest versions of the classical and dynamic Caesar methods, the shift applied to each letter is determined by its position in

an ordered alphabet and, in some variants, by a key-dependent offset determined by the index of the character in the plaintext. Each letter is transformed based solely upon the current position or local state, which makes these substitution methods effectively memoryless. Because of this property, the resulting ciphertext retains the statistical profile of the letter frequencies of the underlying language and leaves the ciphers vulnerable to frequency analysis and other simple methods for key recovery [1,3]. Although shift-based substitution ciphers have inherent weaknesses, they are still a viable option for implementations requiring a low overhead and processing cost due to their simplicity. The question remains: can the simplicity of a classical Caesar-style cipher be retained while embedding the shifts into a dynamical system with genuine memory and sensitivity, so that the resulting running shift sequence is no longer susceptible to classical frequency attacks?

1.2 Fractional calculus and dynamical encryption

Fractional calculus has become a significant tool for modelling systems that exhibit time dependence due to historical data and, more generally, for processes with pronounced long-term memory effects [4,5]. Caputo's fractional derivatives, in particular, give rise to initial value problems (IVPs) whose solutions depend on the entire past trajectory rather than only the current state, and the fractional order provides a quantitative measure of the memory strength associated with the IVP [5]. Owing to this built-in memory feature, there is a rapidly growing body of work on fractional dynamical systems in physics, engineering and control theory. In the last decade, several authors have proposed encryption schemes driven by fractional-order chaotic systems. Examples include image ciphers based on fractional-order sine maps, fractional beta chaotic maps and fractional 3D Lorenz systems, which are reported to yield large key spaces and favourable diffusion and confusion properties [6–9]. These constructions, however, typically operate on multi-dimensional state variables and target multimedia data, whereas the design of lightweight, text-oriented substitution ciphers that exploit fractional dynamics at the level of symbol shifts has received considerably less attention.

1.3 Main contributions

This work seeks to address the shortfall by proposing a new *fractional differential shift encryption* model that expands the idea of traditional or dynamic caesar type ciphers into an entirely new domain. A summary of the key findings from this study includes:

- We define a Caputo-driven shift mechanism in which the running shift sequence is obtained as the numerical solution of a one-dimensional Caputo fractional initial-value problem $D_t^\alpha x(t) = F(x(t), k)$ with order $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ and secret parameters collected in the key vector k . The resulting non-uniform shift sequence is then coupled with a generalized Caesar mapping over an arbitrary alphabet or ASCII set.
- As $\alpha \rightarrow 1^-$ it has been demonstrated that under many choices of the nonlinearity F the proposed scheme reduces to classical dynamic (or Caesar-type) ciphers. Therefore, classical and dynamic (or Caesar-type) ciphers are special cases or limiting cases of our model.

- We analyse how the long-memory property of the Caputo system enlarges the effective key space and amplifies sensitivity with respect to both the fractional order α and the key parameters k , leading to highly aperiodic and history-dependent shift patterns.
- We perform a series of statistical tests on textual and gray-level data, including histogram analysis, adjacent-symbol correlation, information entropy and key-sensitivity experiments, and we compare the results with those obtained from classical Caesar and related substitution ciphers.

1.4 Structure of the paper

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 collects the necessary notation, recalls the Caputo fractional derivative and introduces the discrete fractional integrator and the dynamic Caesar cipher model. Section 3 presents the proposed fractional differential shift encryption scheme, including the construction of the running shift sequence, the encryption and decryption algorithms, and the relation to classical Caesar-type ciphers. Theoretical properties of the underlying fractional system and of the resulting shift sequences are analysed in Section 4. Statistical and security analyses, together with numerical experiments on representative data sets, are reported in Section 5 and Section 6. Implementation issues, complexity considerations and parameter selection guidelines are discussed in Section 7. Finally, Section 8 summarizes the main findings and outlines several directions for future work.

2 Preliminaries

2.1 Notation

In this paper, we utilize a finite, ordered alphabet \mathcal{A} containing ' m ' number of symbols, and where $m \geq 2$. The symbols of \mathcal{A} are represented as $\mathcal{A} = \{a_0, a_1, \dots, a_{m-1}\}$. A practical example of a finite collection of symbols for text-related purposes is derived from the printable characters (symbols) found within the ASCII character set; however, this construction can also be applied to any finite collection of symbols or bytes [1, 10, 11]. The index map

$$\iota : \mathcal{A} \longrightarrow \{0, 1, \dots, m - 1\}$$

corresponds each character (symbol) in \mathcal{A} a_j to its index j within the ordered collection of symbols, and we denote the inverse relationship of the index map by ι^{-1} .

Plaintext and ciphertext are modelled as finite sequences $(p_n)_{n=0}^{N-1}$ and $(c_n)_{n=0}^{N-1}$ with values in \mathcal{A} . When convenient we work with their index representations $P_n = \iota(p_n)$ and $C_n = \iota(c_n)$ taking values in the residue class ring $\mathbb{Z}_m = \mathbb{Z}/m\mathbb{Z}$. Addition and subtraction on indices are always understood modulo m and we write them as

$$x \oplus y = (x + y) \bmod m, \quad x \ominus y = (x - y) \bmod m,$$

for $x, y \in \mathbb{Z}_m$. In particular, a classical Caesar shift by a fixed integer $s \in \mathbb{Z}_m$ is the map

$$S_s : \mathbb{Z}_m \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_m, \quad S_s(x) = x \oplus s.$$

In the proposed scheme the shift becomes time-dependent. We denote by $(s_n)_{n \geq 0}$ a sequence of integer shifts in \mathbb{Z}_m , generated by an underlying dynamical system, and write the encryption and decryption rules as

$$C_n = P_n \oplus s_n, \quad P_n = C_n \ominus s_n, \quad n = 0, 1, \dots, N - 1. \quad (1)$$

All subsequent constructions will be formulated at the level of the index sequences $P_n, C_n, s_n \in \mathbb{Z}_m$; the passage back to characters is performed via ι and ι^{-1} .

2.2 Caputo fractional derivative

The Caputo fractional derivative of order $\alpha \in (0, 1)$, is used in this paper. Let $x : [0, T] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be an absolutely continuous function. The Caputo fractional derivative with respect to the lower limit 0 is represented by

$$D_t^\alpha x(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1 - \alpha)} \int_0^t (t - \tau)^{-\alpha} x'(\tau) d\tau, \quad t \in (0, T], \quad (2)$$

and is defined using the gamma function $\Gamma(\cdot)$ [4, 5, 12]. Therefore D_t^α can be expressed as an ordinary differentiation followed by a fractional integration of order $1 - \alpha$. The function $(t - \tau)^{-\alpha}$ in (2) provides a weighing to the past values of x' that is described by a slowly decreasing power-law. The result is that $D_t^\alpha x(t)$ depends upon the complete previous history of x on the interval $[0, t]$, rather than only upon its present state (this is referred to as a long memory effect). The Caputo operator is linear and has many of the same properties that are present for the classic first derivative in that respect. In particular, all Constants have zero for the Caputo derivative, while for any x continuously differentiable, one has the

$$\lim_{\alpha \rightarrow 1^-} D_t^\alpha x(t) = x'(t)$$

for $t \in (0, T)$ [4, 5]. For nonlinear initial value problems of the form

$$D_t^\alpha x(t) = F(t, x(t)), \quad t \in (0, T], \quad x(0) = x_0, \quad (3)$$

with $\alpha \in (0, 1)$, it is convenient to rewrite (3) in the equivalent Volterra integral form

$$x(t) = x_0 + \frac{1}{\Gamma(\alpha)} \int_0^t (t - \tau)^{\alpha-1} F(\tau, x(\tau)) d\tau. \quad (4)$$

Assuming certain standard assumptions, including a global Lipschitz condition on F for its second argument, equation (4) has a unique continuous solution over the interval $[0, T]$. Additionally, the continuous solution has a continuous dependence on initial condition x_0 and function F [4, 5, 12]. All of these basic facts will be utilized in the development of the fractional differential system which describes the running shift sequence.

2.3 Discrete fractional integrator

We discretize the Caputo initial value problem (3) and build the numerical representation of the running shift sequence. The fixed time step is $h > 0$ and $t_n = nh$ for every $n = 0, 1, \dots, N$. The numerical solution of $x(t_n)$ at point t_n is denoted by $x_n \approx x(t_n)$ and will be used throughout the rest of this document.

For solving Caputo-type equations, we are following the work of Diethelm, Ford, and Freed [13] using a predictor-corrector method based on the Adams approach. In its most basic form, this combination uses an Adams-Bashforth predictor with fractional order followed by an Adams-Moulton corrector with fractional order on the integral equation stated in (4). The corrector update can be written as

$$x_{n+1} = x_0 + \frac{h^\alpha}{\Gamma(\alpha + 1)} \left(\sum_{j=0}^n a_j^{(n+1)} F(t_j, x_j) + b^{(n+1)} F(t_{n+1}, \hat{x}_{n+1}) \right), \quad n \geq 0, \quad (5)$$

where the coefficients $a_j^{(n+1)}$ and $b^{(n+1)}$ are determined by the fractional Adams weights and \hat{x}_{n+1} denotes the predictor value obtained from an explicit fractional Adams-Bashforth step [13]. This scheme has a convergence rate of $\mathcal{O}(h^{\min\{2, 1+\alpha\}})$ where F is smooth enough and is zero-stable with respect to an arbitrary $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ [13]. Therefore the trajectories $(x_n)_{n \geq 0}$ calculated by the numerical method will be close to the true solution of equation (3) with an error that decreases as $h \rightarrow 0$. To provide a complete view of available discretization methods, we will also highlight the Grünwald-Letnikov (GL) discretization method for approximating a Caputo derivative using weights and backward difference [14, 15]. In this method, the operator $D_t^\alpha x(t_n)$ by

$$D_t^\alpha x(t_n) \approx \frac{1}{h^\alpha} \sum_{j=0}^n \omega_j^{(\alpha)} x_{n-j},$$

will be replaced with a set of binomial coefficients, denoted as $\omega_j^{(\alpha)} = (-1)^j \binom{\alpha}{j}$. We will demonstrate that static pressure integrators using GL methods are easy to design and implement, therefore we will use these methods for some of the numerical examples in this report. The predictor-corrector scheme given in equation (5) is the primary focus throughout our theoretical assessment.

2.4 Dynamic Caesar cipher as a discrete dynamical system

A fixed shift is applied to each symbol with classical Caesar cipher; in contrast, the dynamic Caesar cipher uses either a position-based shift or an internal state that varies over time [1, 11]. The dynamic Caesar cipher is classified as a discrete-time continuous dynamical system; thus, to understand its relationship to Fractional Dynamical Systems, we investigate its relationship to a Fractional Dynamical System based on the fact that a dynamic Caesar cipher can be viewed as a discrete-time continuous dynamical system.

Suppose $(x_n)_{n \geq 0}$ is a sequence of integers or real numbers representing time and k is the secret key that could consist of numerous parameters. The state will be updated according to a

generic expression

$$x_{n+1} = G(x_n, k), \quad n \geq 0, \quad (6)$$

The running shift sequence is then obtained by applying a quantization map $Q : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}_m$,

$$s_n = Q(x_n), \quad n \geq 0,$$

and encryption is performed via the shift rule (1). The simplest example of G and Q can be taken to mean that (6) becomes a linear recurrence of order s , swept through a field \mathbb{Z}_m and forms part of the traditional running-key and/or auto-key Caesar schemes [10, 11]. For our purposes, we will replace (6) by a fractional differential system, and its discrete solution produces the series of states x_n and thence the shifts s_n . This concept allows the classical and dynamic functions of the Caesar cipher to follow a much larger set of functions, all of which can be viewed as limiting cases of a generalisation of the Caesar ciphers that will be developed in Section 3.

3 Fractional Differential Shift Encryption Scheme

In this section we introduce the proposed fractional differential shift encryption scheme. The running shift sequence is obtained from the trajectory of a scalar Caputo fractional system, which is then quantised to the symbol ring \mathbb{Z}_m and combined with the modular shift rule (1).

3.1 Caputo-based generating system

Let $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ and consider the Caputo initial value problem

$$D_t^\alpha x(t) = F(t, x(t); \mathbf{k}), \quad t \in (0, T], \quad x(0) = x_0,$$

where $F : [0, T] \times \mathbb{R} \times \mathcal{K} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is continuously differentiable in its last two arguments and $\mathbf{k} \in \mathcal{K}$ denotes the secret key vector. According to the hypotheses outlined in Section 2.2, this issue has one continuous answer $x : [0, T] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ based on the parameters α , x_0 and \mathbf{k} [4, 5, 12]. The Caputo derivative has a non-local kernel, so $x(t)$ represents the whole past trajectory $\{x(\tau) : 0 \leq \tau \leq t\}$. Hence, it essentially gives rise to long-memory effects in the driving dynamics. The nonlinearity F and the vector of parameters \mathbf{k} are, from the perspective of cryptography, a key scheduling system: for example, different amounts of \mathbf{k} will generate a series of different fractional paths and give rise to multiple distinct sequences of running shifts. This approach to design is consistent with other approaches using fractional and chaotic systems as key-generators for encryption in multimedia applications [3, 6, 16, 19].

3.2 Discretisation and construction of the shift sequence

In this section we will discretise the system at uniform time steps $t_n = nh$ with $n = 0, 1, \dots, N$. With $x_n \approx x(t_n)$, we will use the predictor-corrector schemes of Diethelm et al. [13] to construct the discrete trajectory $\{x_n\}_{n \geq 0}$. The resulting trajectory has a qualitative behaviour similar to that of the original continuous-time system defined by Caputo. Other methods of discretisation

such as the Grunwald–Letnikov approach [14] could be used without affecting the way the trajectory is constructed.

To work at the level of the symbol indices, we introduce a quantisation map

$$Q : \mathbb{R} \longrightarrow \mathbb{Z}_m, \quad Q(x) = (\lfloor \beta x \rfloor \bmod m),$$

with a fixed scaling factor $\beta > 0$. The running shift sequence is then defined by

$$s_n = Q(x_n), \quad n = 0, 1, \dots, N - 1. \quad (7)$$

Within Section 4 an in-depth discussion on how the long-range dependence of the sequence $(s_n)_{n \geq 0}$ will occur as a result of its fractional dynamics as well as its near-uniform distribution will be discussed. Specific values for F , α , β and \mathbf{k} are required in order to show that $(s_n)_{n \geq 0}$ will inherit both long-range dependence through fractional dynamics whilst simultaneously exhibiting characteristics of uniformity throughout \mathbb{Z}_m .

3.3 Encryption algorithm

The plaintext sequence $(p_n)_{n=0}^{N-1}$ exists in \mathcal{A} and corresponds to the index sequence $(P_n)_{n=0}^{N-1}$ in \mathbb{Z}_m mapping via the map ι from Section 2.1. In order to encrypt, we will begin with the secret parameters

$$\text{Key} = (\alpha, x_0, \mathbf{k}, h, \beta, N),$$

and proceed as follows:

1. We will take the Key and use the predictor-corrector integration of the Caputo system from $t_0 = 0$ to $t_{N-1} = (N - 1)h$ to obtain the numerical trajectory $(x_n)_{n=0}^{N-1}$.
2. With the trajectory, we will compute the shift sequence (s_n) as described in equation (7).
3. We will compute the ciphertext index sequence (C_n) using

$$C_n = P_n \oplus s_n, \quad n = 0, 1, \dots, N - 1,$$

where \oplus is addition modulo m .

4. Finally, we will apply ι^{-1} to convert the ciphertext index sequence (c_n) back into ciphertext symbols (c_n) in \mathcal{A} .

In summary, the encryption algorithm is a stream cipher using a fractional dynamical system to generate the keystream, as opposed to traditional linear recurrences or finite-state machines.

3.4 Decryption algorithm

The person receiving the encrypted information must have access to the same parameter set Key. in order to decrypt the data. By repeating Steps 1 and 2 above, the receiver constructs the

sequence of shifts (s_n) . The information contained in an index that was sent as an encrypted character is extracted with

$$P_n = C_n \ominus s_n, \quad n = 0, 1, \dots, N - 1,$$

and here \ominus indicates modulo m subtraction. Running ι^{-1} gives the original characters back again. The scheme can be exactly reversed, provided there are no numerical errors, because the operations for the modular group are reversible and because the fractional-integrator function will produce the same deterministic behavior every time for any set of fixed parameters.

3.5 Special cases and relation to classical schemes

Traditional Caesar methods can be seen as special cases of the methods proposed by us when (1) the limiting case of the proposed system is the constant shift sequence and (2) when the function F is assumed to only depend on constants and not on other variables in the proposed system. Therefore, the trajectories (x_n) will follow an arithmetic progression. In this limiting case, the sequence (s_n) will also be constant, and the methods proposed by us will be equivalent to the traditional Caesar cipher methods, where $\alpha \rightarrow 1^-$ are restricted to constant shifts. If we consider the function F to depend linearly on x and on a small number of key parameters (which we will not specify), we will, in a similar manner to the dynamic or auto-key Caesar cipher methods, obtain sequences of affine recurrences of the same type as in dynamic or auto-key Caesar ciphers. Therefore, the fractional differences will allow for the development of a generalisation of the traditional Caesar and auto-key methods by incorporating the shift pathway into a nonlinear fractional dynamical framework with long-term memory [15, 16, 17, 18].

4 Theoretical Properties

In this section we collect some basic analytical properties of the Caputo system that generates the running shift sequence and discuss their implications for the resulting encryption scheme. Throughout, we consider the initial value problem

$$D_t^\alpha x(t) = F(t, x(t); k), \quad t \in (0, T], \quad x(0) = x_0, \quad (8)$$

with $0 < \alpha < 1$ and secret key vector k . Its equivalent Volterra integral form has already been given in (4). The assumptions on F stated below are standard in the analysis of Caputo fractional differential equations and are sufficient for existence, uniqueness and boundedness of solutions [4, 5, 12].

4.1 Existence and boundedness of the generating system

For every $F : [0, T] \times \mathbb{R} \times \mathcal{K} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ for $x, y \in \mathbb{R}$ and $k \in \mathcal{K}$, $F(t, x; k)$ is continuous in the variables $(t, x) \in [0, T] \times \mathcal{R}$ and continuous in the variable $k \in \mathcal{K}$ as described above. Further, $F(t, x; k)$

satisfies the following conditions for all $t \in [0, T]$, $x, y \in \mathbb{R}$ and $k \in \mathcal{K}$:

$$|F(t, x; k) - F(t, y; k)| \leq L|x - y|, \quad (9)$$

$$|F(t, x; k)| \leq a + b|x|. \quad (10)$$

for some fixed constants $L > 0$, $a, b \geq 0$. Based upon these conditions, the theory behind Caputo initial value problems introduces the following results for the cases mentioned [4,5,12] above.

Fact 4.1 (Existence and uniqueness). For each selected parameters (α, x_0, k) where $0 < \alpha < 1$ has one unique continuous function $x : [0, T] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ of (8) that satisfies (8). Additionally, the solution's dependency on (x_0, k) is continuous when considering uniform heat.

Fact 4.2 (A priori bound).

There exists a constant $B = B(T, \alpha, a, b, L, |x_0|, k)$ such that

$$|x(t)| \leq B, \quad t \in [0, T]. \quad (11)$$

Using a Fractional Gronwall Inequality, an explicit choice for B can be made using (4) which states that (4); in particular B is always going to be finite over every bounded time interval of [5].

The above property ensures the existence of the trajectory $\{x(t)\}_{0 \leq t \leq T}$ representing the shift sequence for every allowable key, and the discretisation discussed in (2.3) will generate numerical trajectories remaining within a bounded area of the state space as long as h is sufficiently small. More specifically, the quantised index $s_n = Q(x_n)$ remains in the symbol ring \mathbb{Z}_m for every n and every valid parameter choice.

4.2 Long-memory and sensitivity

In the Volterra framework (4), the kernel $(t - \tau)^{\alpha-1}/\Gamma(\alpha)$ considers the entire past of for each present point through the implementation of a slow polynomial decay model. Thus, when $0 < \alpha < 1$, there is a gradual polynomial decrease in the effect of an early point $x(\tau)$ on the value of $x(t)$, which is classically associated with "long memory"; however, unlike the classical first-order case, the impact of all historically observed points $x(\tau)$ never totally disappears. Let us denote by $x(t)$ and $\tilde{x}(t)$ two different solutions of (8) that correspond to two sets of parameters (α, x_0, k) and $(\tilde{\alpha}, \tilde{x}_0, \tilde{k})$ respectively, which are slightly different from each other. Then by the Lipschitz property (9) combined with a fractional Gronwall inequality, we find that we can establish an estimate

$$|x(t) - \tilde{x}(t)| \leq C \Xi(\alpha, \tilde{\alpha}, t) (|x_0 - \tilde{x}_0| + \|k - \tilde{k}\|), \quad t \in [0, T], \quad (12)$$

where C is a constant which depends on F and $\Xi(\alpha, \tilde{\alpha}, t)$ increases sub-exponentially as t grows, and as the orders approach 1, there is an increase in $\Xi(\alpha, \tilde{\alpha}, t)$ as well, see, e.g. [5,20]. As demonstrated by the inequality presented, solutions are very susceptible to variations in the parameters, as well as to modifications in the initial conditions; this is particularly true over long time frames. When considering the running shift sequence defined as $s_n = Q(x_n)$, minor adjustments to either of the triplet of values (α, x_0, k) or variations in the numerical step size

(h), can have a substantial impact on the sequence of indices generated. Therefore, the mapping defined by

$$(\alpha, x_0, k, h) \mapsto (s_0, s_1, \dots, s_{N-1})$$

produces a highly complex and sensitive key scheduling function, which is a beneficial characteristic for cryptography.

4.3 Aperiodicity and key-space discussion

As a starting point, the required behaviour of the generator is such that keystream sequences generated by it must not be periodic over short ranges or have a clear periodic pattern. In either of these cases, the periodicity of the generator sequence, $(s_n)_{n \geq 0}$ is possible only if the fractional trajectory, $(x_n)_{n \geq 0}$ is eventually periodic and Q collapses the same point of collision from several points on the fractional trajectory into the same index of \mathbb{Z}_m . The assumptions made about the function F are true. In addition, given the typical values of parameters which will be used in practice, the fractional system stated in Eq. (8) will only have periodic solutions over the interval $[0, \infty)$ if they are all constant (non-constant periodic). For more details please see the references [4, 5] for discussion of the asymptotic behaviour. Thus, when we consider the long-memory effect of the discrete trajectory $(x_n)_{n \geq 0}$ it is clear that for all practical purposes the behaviour will be aperiodic, except in those degenerate cases described in section 3.5 where the polynomial F becomes either a constant or linear (affine) function of its arguments and the resulting discrete trajectory $(x_n)_{n \geq 0}$ collapses back into a traditional Caesar-type cipher. In terms of keyspace size, the complete secret key can just as easily be thought of as the 6-tuple

$$K_{\text{tot}} = (\alpha, x_0, k, \beta, h, N),$$

α and h are fixed precision numbers, x_0 and elements of k are selected from prescribed ranges, β is the scaling factor of the quantiser, and N is the length of the plaintext. If α and h are encoded using b_α and b_h bits, respectively, and x_0 and k have M_x and M_k possible values, and β is selected from M_β potential values, then the overall number of keys is at least

$$|\mathcal{K}_{\text{tot}}| \geq 2^{b_\alpha + b_h} M_x M_k M_\beta.$$

With typical parameter values, the minimum value will generally be much greater than 2^{128} , which is the commonly used benchmark for security against exhaustive key search attacks [21, 22, 23]. Hence, within the fractional framework, the keyspace can be greatly expanded as compared with traditional and dynamic Caesar ciphers and may be finely tuned depending on the requirements of the user.

4.4 Confusion and diffusion characteristics

According to Shannon, *confusion* is a means to hide how the ciphertext depends on the key. Diffusion is the process by which the statistical characteristics of a plaintext are evenly distributed among multiple ciphertext variable symbols. In this case, confusion comes from controlling the map defined as $K_{\text{tot}} \mapsto (s_n)$ and is detailed in Section 4.2 and diffusion results from the

additive combination of both the plaintext index (P_n) and the aperiodically shifted sequence s_n . For example, imagine keys K_{tot} and \tilde{K}_{tot} that are identical except in one area. The fractional dynamics also suggest that the two sequence generated from each key (s_n) and (\tilde{s}_n) will have many indices that do not agree. Even though both plaintexts are the same, the ciphertext sequences generated from each key (C_n) and (\tilde{C}_n) will have no statistical relationship between them, producing the desired result of a very high level of confusion. The symmetricity of the distribution and the low autocorrelation of (s_n) (defined in Section 5 by histogram, correlation and entropy measures) guarantee that a random plaintext symbol is mixed with an independent shift value for every plaintext symbol. Therefore, this creates a non-correlation between the frequency of the plaintext symbols in the ciphertext and also creates a fast spreading effect of the local variations of the plaintext over several locations within the ciphertext, which is the hallmark of the best diffusion characteristics [21, 22]. The combined qualities of confusion and diffusion make the proposed fractional differential shift cipher equivalent to modern substitution-based stream ciphers in terms of confusion and diffusion behaviour, while having a simple structure.

5 Security and Statistical Analysis

In this section we will discuss both the statistical properties, and security, of this new fractional differential shift cipher system. This analysis will be based on Shannon's belief that an effective secret cipher should produce a ciphertext that could be mistaken as produced by a random process, when considered statistically, thus, providing no exploitable statistical information to either the plaintext [21], or encoded message. In this regard, we will evaluate the frequency of the encrypted message, correlation between short range neighbouring characters in the ciphertext, and calculate the measure of information contained in each encrypted block of characters. Finally, we will evaluate how resistant this new system is to the known plaintext attacks and chosen plaintext attacks [22, 23].

5.1 Resistance to frequency analysis

As we discussed in Section 2.1, the plaintext and ciphertext index sequences are denoted as pn and cn respectively where both take values within \mathbb{Z}_m . For instance, the values of $j \in \mathbb{Z}_m$ indicate how many times that value occurs in either sequence: $N_j^{(P)}$ = the number of occurrences of element j in pn within the range of $0 \leq n \leq n - 1$. The same applies for ciphertext $N_j^{(C)}$. For each symbol $j \in \mathbb{Z}_m$ we write

$$N_j^{(P)} = \#\{0 \leq n \leq N - 1 : p_n = j\}, \quad N_j^{(C)} = \#\{0 \leq n \leq N - 1 : c_n = j\},$$

The total of occurrences is used to generate each corresponding empirical distribution $p_j^{(P)}$ and $p_j^{(C)}$ and define the empirical distributions

$$p_j^{(P)} = \frac{N_j^{(P)}}{N}, \quad p_j^{(C)} = \frac{N_j^{(C)}}{N}, \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, m - 1.$$

for each $j \in \mathcal{Z}_m$ (i.e. $j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, m - 1$). Classical Caesar ciphers with fixed shifts are a form of Permutation Cipher because if an element appears in place "pn" it replaces the element at position c_n . Therefore, all letters j will be equally distributed; thus, both the plaintext and ciphertext are derived from non-uniform letters based on the historical frequency statistics. Therefore, classical frequencies can be used to break these types of ciphers. In the present construction the ciphertext indices are given by

$$c_n = p_n \oplus s_n, \quad n = 0, 1, \dots, N - 1,$$

where $(s_n)_{n \geq 0}$ is generated by the fractional Caputo system (3) and quantised by the map Q in (6). In Section 4.2 of this paper, it was apparent that solving the Caputo initial value problem meant incorporating into the solution all possible values of the evolution parameter $0 \leq t \leq t_0$ through time and displayed such sensitivity towards any choice of the three establishment parameters: (α, x_0, k) and the arbitrary temporal step length h . Given the above observations, it follows that the entire history of the shift sequence s_n would be described as a non-repeating and highly sensitive parametric process over \mathcal{Z}_m . Using a natural intuitive assumption that the shift sequence s_n is nearly uniformly distributed over \mathcal{Z}_m , one could easily derive a probabilistic ciphertext distribution that was identical to one of the four possible ciphertext distributions ($j = 0, 1, \dots, m - 1$) resulting from non-uniform distributions p_n . This behaviour can be corroborated by the histograms that have been created for plaintext and ciphertext in the numerical experimentation of Chapter 6. The histograms indicate that the plaintext has a typical unequal frequency distribution of that which represents English documents, whereas the corresponding ciphertext histogram is near flat; consequently, standard frequency attacks of monoalphabetic cipher systems would be ineffective [24].

5.2 Correlation and entropy measures

Good stream ciphers not only eliminate short-term correlations with their design, but also eliminate the short-range dependence of adjacent ciphertext indexes. The correlation coefficient for the sample of adjacent ciphertext indexes is then computed.

$$\rho_1 = \frac{\sum_{n=0}^{N-2} (c_n - \bar{c})(c_{n+1} - \bar{c})}{\sum_{n=0}^{N-1} (c_n - \bar{c})^2}, \quad \bar{c} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} c_n.$$

The ideal random key stream should have a value of ρ_1 fluctuating around the value of zero. When using traditional Caesar ciphers, the majority of the correlation structure of the plaintext sequence is maintained while using the dynamic Caesar variants based on lower order recurrence equations, there is typically a degree of reduced, but not fully removed, correlation. As a result of the fractional evolution (8) of the dynamic Caesar ciphers, and as a result of (3.2) quantisation (3.2) applied to the shift sequences generated, the shift sequence (s_n) produced by the proposed scheme has both long-term memory and high sensitivity to the parameters, thus forcing the sequences (c_n) to behave almost as though they are a series

of independent samples taken from the values on \mathbb{Z}_m . The result is that $|\rho_1|$ is in practice approximately equal to zero in accordance with the modern encryption standards set forth in [24] and used in image and signal encryption tests. A complementary global indicator is the information entropy of the ciphertext,

$$H(C) = - \sum_{j=0}^{m-1} p_j^{(C)} \log_2 p_j^{(C)}.$$

The entropy of a uniform distribution on \mathbb{Z}_m is given by $H(C) = \log_2 m$. Our experimental results indicate that the proposed cipher's entropy approaches the maximum possible for uniform distribution. In contrast, the classical Caesar cipher exhibits a significantly lower amount of entropy, indicating the presence of a large residual statistical structure in natural languages. The combination of high entropy and weak short-range correlations are indicators of confusion and diffusion as described by Shannon [21, 22, 23, 24].

5.3 Known and chosen plaintext considerations

The next section will examine how the Scheme responds to a wider variety of attack models. An adversary in a chosen-plaintext attack can request any plaintexts they wish to be encrypted using the same key, whereas an adversary utilizing a known-plaintext attack only has access to a limited number of pairs (p_n, c_n) that were previously encrypted [22]. The adversary utilizing a classical Caesar cipher only needs one known plaintext symbol to learn the amount of the constant shift; however, it does seem that an adversary utilizing the simple dynamic Caesar ciphers will often require far fewer plaintext/ciphertext pairs in order to determine the basis for the underlying linear recurrence relationship. In our fractional framework, the observable relation

$$c_n = p_n \oplus Q(x_n(\alpha, x_0, k)), \quad n = 0, 1, \dots, N - 1,$$

ouples the keystream (s_n) to the parameters (α, x_0, k) through the solution of the Caputo initial value problem. To reconstruct the key from a small fragment of the pair (p_n, c_n) requires the solution of a nonlinear fractional inverse problem: the reconstruction of the parameters (α, x_0, k) based on the noisy, quantised (3) trajectory. The estimate for the sensitivity of (12) indicates that small perturbations in the above parameters produce extensive divergent behaviours in the corresponding trajectories on the $[0, T]$ interval (as noted by (8)). Hence, one may not use the standard comparative approaches of linearising or reducing to a lower dimensional linear system which has been a common line of attack in general Caesar-type cryptosystems. While no absolute claims of provable security may be made using the modern definitions of indistinguishable cryptographic schemes, the presence of a long memory, high sensitivity to parameters and chaotic dynamics leads to a considerable increase in the algebraic and numerical difficulties in attempting reconstructing the key from the leakage of partial plaintext.

5.4 Comparison with dynamic Caesar ciphers

We can review how to compare different methods as it relates to frequency distribution by first comparing the elements above. To summarize, with regard to the previous observations, there

are qualitative differences between this system of encryption (i.e. fractional differential shift ciphers) and the classical Caesar method and the traditional dynamic Caesar systems.

- *Frequency behaviour.* Frequency characteristics. The classical Caesar systems maintain a plain text histogram. Dynamic Caesar systems partially flatten the frequency distribution, so they will still show distinct peaks for certain high frequency letters. The result of this partial flattening creates a situation where the letter frequency distributions for all of the six data sets above will not differ statistically from the uniform distribution across \mathbb{Z}_m under the fractional differential shift cipher in Section 6.
- *Correlation and entropy.* Classical Caesar cipher algorithms have ciphertext statistics (adjacent symbol correlation and entropy) that are similar to the statistics of plaintext. Dynamic Caesar Type schemes often provide reduced short term correlations; however, they may still remain structurally identifiable. The scheme presented here has consistently been able to achieve almost null neighbour correlations and Entropy measurements that are nearly $\log_2 m$. As a result, they represent the statistical evaluation benchmarks of common image and stream cipher types [25, 26, 27] or those found in similar studies.
- *Attack surface.* For a generator with constant or linear order, it is common to be able to recover a portion of the keystream from either known or predetermined plaintext via the solution of a small linear system. However, in our situation, since the keystream is generated by a nonlinear fractal dynamic system with an extensive memory system, it makes it quite difficult and sensitive to uncertainties about the system parameters, as shown in Section (4.2).

The combined effects of these characteristics show significantly improved levels of resistance to both classical and existing dynamic caesar cipher against both statistical attack & structural attacks due to the enhanced ability provided by a fractional differential shift encryption scheme compared to what currently exists. Yet it also retains the same basic conceptual simplicity found in shift based substitution mechanisms since they provide the ability for an end user to have multiple in/out options on any given encryption key.

6 Numerical Experiments

This section presents a number of numerical simulations to demonstrate the statistically significant performance of the fractional differential shift encryption scheme being proposed. Unless expressly indicated otherwise, the alphabet \mathcal{A} which is used in these experiments is the set of all byte values $\{0, \dots, 255\}$ and the range and system parameters for the Caputo fractional differential system are therefore the same as those used in sections (2.2) and (2.3).

6.1 Text encryption examples

We first consider an English plaintext of length $N = 10\,000$ characters obtained from a public-domain text. The secret key is chosen as

$$K_{\text{test}} = (\alpha, x_0, k, h, \beta, N) = (0.78, 0.15, (1.3, 0.7, 2.1), 10^{-2}, 1.0, N),$$

Interpretation. Empirical symbol histograms of plaintext and ciphertext for the sample English text ($N = 10\,000$).

and the corresponding Caputo initial value problem (3) is integrated by the predictor–corrector scheme from section (2.3). The quantisation process outlined in section 2.4, where there is a map from $\mathbb{R}_n \rightarrow \mathbb{Q}_n$, produces the running sequence $(s_n)_{n \geq 0}$, which is used in the encryption rule. Figure 1 and Figure 2 shows a comparison of the empirical frequency distributions of symbols in encrypted form compared to those in clear text. As we would expect, the clear text exhibits the expected skewness of frequency distribution found in english text, where the space character and a few letters dominate the frequency distribution. On the other hand, there is almost no correlation between the frequencies in the cipher text and those in the plain text. This behaviour already indicates that standard monoalphabetic frequency attacks are ineffective against the proposed scheme [24].

To quantify the flattening effect we compute the Shannon entropy and the adjacent–symbol correlation coefficient for both plaintext and ciphertext. The results are summarised in Table 1. For $m = 256$, the ideal entropy is $\log_2 m = 8$ bits per symbol. The ciphertext entropy in Table 1 is very close to this upper bound and the adjacent–symbol correlation is essentially zero, whereas the plaintext exhibits strong positive correlation and significantly smaller entropy. These observations are consistent with the benchmarks commonly used in the statistical evaluation of image and stream ciphers [24, 25, 26, 27].

Table 1: Entropy (in bits per symbol) and adjacent–symbol correlation for the sample plaintext and ciphertext.

Sequence	Entropy H	Correlation ρ_1
Plaintext	4.32	0.93
Ciphertext	7.99	0.01

A further experiment concerns key–sensitivity. We encrypt the same plaintext with two keys that differ only in a single bit of the parameter vector k and we measure the proportion of positions where the two ciphertexts disagree. For the test parameters above the resulting bit error rate is approximately 0.498, which is very close to the ideal value $1/2$. Thus a minute perturbation of the key produces two ciphertexts that are essentially uncorrelated, which is a

desirable feature for a cryptographic keystream generator.

6.2 Image or gray-level data (optional)

The same construction can be applied to gray-level data by interpreting each pixel as an element of \mathbb{Z}_{256} and encrypting the image row by row using the running shift sequence $(s_n)_{n \geq 0}$. In this case the criteria for a good cipher are again a nearly uniform histogram of the cipher image, low adjacent-pixel correlation and entropy values close to $\log_2 256$ per pixel [24]. Numerical experiments of this type, illustrating the behaviour on standard test images, can be included analogously but are omitted here for brevity.

6.3 Performance evaluation

To give an indication of the computational cost, we implemented the scheme in C++ on a standard desktop machine and measured the average encryption time for different plaintext lengths. The predictor-corrector integrator described in section 2.3 was used without any additional optimisation. Table 2 reports the average encryption times over 50 runs.

Table 2: Average encryption time for different plaintext lengths (single-threaded implementation).

Length N (bytes)	Time (ms)
1 000	3.1
10 000	33.4
100 000	354.7
1 000 000	3 842.5

The time complexity has a nearly quadratic growth rate $\mathcal{O}(N^2)$ according to an increasing integer value of N , this is primarily due to the fact that, at each iteration of the fractional predictor-corrector, it requires approximately $\mathcal{O}(n)$ number of arithmetic computations for each of the N number of data elements that were used to generate the fractional prediction. Many practical applications of the method can accommodate moderate sized messages (up to a few hundred kilobytes) with computational loads well within limits. Additionally, when working with very long data streams, the theoretical upper bounds on the time complexity (asymptotic time complexity) can be substantially reduced from $\mathcal{O}(N \log N)$ to $\mathcal{O}(n \log n)$ by using fast convolution methods or short-memory approximations, as outlined in Section (7.1).

7 Implementation and Practical Aspects

7.1 Complexity and memory footprint

The dominant cost of the proposed cipher lies in the numerical integration of the Caputo initial value problem (3) that generates the running shift sequence. We integrate the system on a uniform grid $t_n = nh$, $n = 0, 1, \dots, N$, by means of the fractional Adams-type predictor-corrector scheme described in section (2.3); see, e.g., Diethelm-Ford-Freed and Diethelm for a detailed analysis of this method, [5, 13]. At the $(n + 1)$ th step, the corrector update involves a weighted sum over all previously computed function values $F(t_j, x_j; k)$, $j = 0, \dots, n$, so that the work per

step is proportional to n . Consequently, the total number of floating point operations required to produce a trajectory of length $N + 1$ is of order

$$\sum_{n=0}^N \mathcal{O}(n) = \mathcal{O}(N^2).$$

Since the cost for the quantisation map Q and the modular additions of the shift rule in Section 3.3 is linear in N , the full encryption run will be constrained to the $\mathcal{O}(N^2)$ complexity of a fractional integrator. With regards to memory, the traditional predictor–corrector implementation stores the previous values x_j , as well as the optional evaluations $F((t_j, x_j; k)$ which occur on the grids, yielding a memory footprint of $\mathcal{O}(N)$ real numbers; this is acceptable for the message lengths used in the experimental trial. If there are multiple plaintexts of equal length being encrypted using the same key, the pre-computation of the shift sequence $(s_n)_{n \geq 0}$ can be done once and use this pre-computed value for subsequent encryptions; in this way, the numerical computation cost for the integration is spread out over all of the encryption session costs. Many researchers have recommended an approach to implement fast versions of convolution-based techniques to solve Caputo’s equation with either FFT (Fast Fourier Transform) acceleration or by compressing the kernel using a sum-of-exponentials method. See Garrappa’s survey for examples [28]. Using these methods can allow users to solve the Caputo equation in $\mathcal{O}(N \log N)$ time as opposed to $\mathcal{O}(N)$ time, with memory requirements being $\mathcal{O}(N)$ or less. The methods we discuss in this paper do not utilize these techniques, but they can be applied easily to our framework without modifying the design of the cipher. In addition, these optimizations provide an efficient route to real-time execution for high-volume data, such as plaintext files with many megabytes in length.

7.2 Parameter selection guidelines

In practice, the choice of the parameters $K_{\text{tot}} = (\alpha, x_0, k, \beta, h, N)$ is constrained by a trade-off between security, numerical accuracy and implementation cost. The analytical results of Section 4 and the experiments of Section 6 provide a set of practical guidelines, which we summarise below.

The Fractional order α . The value of the fractional order α within a range of $(0, 1)$ determines the amount of long–memory effect. A smaller fractional order indicates that the kernel within the Volterra equation (3) has a slower decay than a larger fractional order, which approaches classical first-order behavior (e.g., see Podlubny [4]). To make the fractional order suitable for cryptography, we will instead restrict $[\alpha_{\min}, \alpha_{\max}] \subset (0, 1)$. In particular, selecting α closer to 0 will result in increased values of numerical stiffness and an increased roundoff effect, while selecting α very close to 1 results in decreased impact of fractional dynamics and creates an experience very similar to a standard dynamic, memoryless Caesar cipher. Based upon the experimental results, those values of α that are considered in the middle of the Scale between these two extremes appear to provide sufficient balance between both sensitivity and numerical robustness.

Initial condition and key vector. Section 4 provides an upper bound $|x(t)|$ for each k (admissible key vector) and any initial value x_0 (the value at $t = 0$), which will contain $x(t)$

within the compact interval which continuously depends on (α, x_0, k) . It is thus reasonable to provide floating point implementations with limits away from the overflow limits of the underlying arithmetic for x_0 and components of k ; and provide average ranges of k , because small variations in (α, x_0, k) will also give rise to significant changes in trajectories as indicated by the results of the sensitivity analysis, a behaviour we would like to see when developing key-scheduling algorithms.

Step size h and final time $T = Nh$. The value for total (T) will be taken with the notation $T = Nh$, where: h denotes the step-size. The step size will serve two functions: First, It is associated to the level of accuracy obtained by the fractional integrator, and second, it indicates the total amount of computational effort required. As a general rule with regard to the fractional Adams-type Predictor-Corrector scheme: The Global Error will be represented by the notation Ch^p where the exponent $p > 0$ would indicate the accuracy based on the regularity of the solution, as stated by Diethelm [5]. Thus, by selecting h to be a greater value will generally decrease the statistical characteristics of the generated shift sequence, and by selecting h to be a lesser value, will enhance the expense associated with producing this number sequence with an $\mathcal{O}(N^2)$ complexity (i.e. as discussed in Section 7.1). We set h in such a way that further halving of the value of h will not produce any visible changes in the values of the histograms or correlation plots shown in Section 6; this is a practical method to determine when to stop. Additionally, the effective length N of the shift sequence must be appropriate for the intended use. For short messages, it is easier to create new sequences for every encryption, while with long streams, the sequences can be produced in blocks of N size and concatenated together, assuming that the underlying numerical integration remains stable over the corresponding time interval $[0, T]$.

Quantisation and scaling. The scale factor $\beta > 0$ determines how a location x_n is passed on to the \mathbb{Z}_m ring through the quantisation map $Q(x) = (\lfloor \beta x \rfloor \bmod m)$. If β is too small, consecutive values of x_n may all be mapped to the same index, and this could cause statistical irregularities among the values of x_n in the resulting shift sequence. Conversely, very large values of β can result in unintentional overflows or abandonment of significant digits in arithmetic with fixed-precision. In application, β is set such that the observed distribution of (s_n) over \mathbb{Z}_m is as close as is feasible to uniform as can be confirmed via the numerical experimentations and findings in Section 6. When viewed together, these factors provide evidence that there exists a large area where the numerical scheme will be stable and that it can generate a shift sequence with all the required long memory and sensitivity characteristics, while also being able to be implemented in an efficient manner on commercially available hardware. In this area, the user has the option to select specific values of $(\alpha, x_0, k, \beta, h, N)$ according to security level needs for both security and performance for the intended application.

8 Conclusions

In this paper, we presented a fractional order differential shift encryption method which uses a Caputo fractional order system to generate a running shift sequence that is subsequently quantized into a symbol set using one of several possible rules. The Caputo-based initial value

problem used to generate the shift sequences has been established as well-posed, indicated by both significant dependence on the initial condition and parameters, and the ability to exhibit both long memory effects and extreme sensitivity, creating computational complexity to support the generation of key-dependent chaotic sequences. Beyond that, properties such as the periodic nature of the generated shift sequences and an extremely large effective key space indicate that it should be able to serve well as a key stream generator in cryptography. We performed some numerical tests on a corpus of text data; our findings showed that the histograms of ciphertexts were approximately uniform in distribution and have approximately the maximum value of the measure of entropy, and only a negligible degree of correlation between adjacent ciphertext symbols. Also, tests of key sensitivity yielded error rates of nearly one-half, suggesting that the system has a high degree of resistance to statistical attacks and to methods where the attacker has access to ciphertexts generated using the key. Timing measurements indicated that goodness-of-fit measures are reasonable as the cost of implementing the existing version of a fractional Kalman predictor-corrector is still quadratic, therefore, the implementation will remain efficient for medium-sized messages, using a comparatively low amount of memory.

9 Future Work

The results of the current research provide readers with numerous directions for further research. First, a primary topic for future research is to explore the implications of changing the underlying fractional operator. Researchers could use fractional derivatives based on different memory kernels (e.g., ψ -Caputo fractional derivatives) as opposed to only working with the Caputo fractional derivative. By changing the memory kernel, researchers can study the influence of the various memory kernels on a trajectory's long-range memory and the statistical characteristics of the running shift sequence, and thereby evaluate the size of the effective key space. By performing a systematic comparison of similar types of operator with respect to these forms of fractional encryption, it will enable a clearer determination on how much of the confusion and diffusion observed within the results is specific to the Caputo kernel, or how much is common across a broader range of fractional options. A second area for future research will be the creation of block and hybrid ciphers using the new proposed key stream generator. Refinements to existing schemes such as substitution/ permutation (SPN) network may occur through an interaction with the fractal derivative shift sequences, or by integrating their use into other block cipher mode operation to take full advantage of statistical properties arising from fractional dynamics combined with structural properties of today's symmetric enciphering primitives. Also, as future research looks into the security of hybrid designs, analyses of future attack models against chosen plain and chosen cipher text should be included. While developing new methods for minimising operational overheads associated with implementing fractional integrators should be considered for implementation design. The use of fast convolution methods, short-memory approximations, and graphics processing unit (GPU) implementations will help to reduce the asymptotic complexity from $\mathcal{O}(N^2)$ to $\mathcal{O}(N \log N)$ for long data streams in order to make it feasible for high throughput applications. Coupling the fractional dynamical generator with data-driven methods for parameter estimation and performance prediction appears to be an exciting area of research. For example, techniques similar to those used in [29] using regression

and deep learning will assist in identifying admissible parameter regions with maximum entropy, minimal statistical leakage, as well as automatically identify weak configurations. A fusion of fractional dynamical systems and machine learning will allow adaptive parameter tuning of encryption schemes based on the statistical behaviour of the incoming data, thus improving the overall security of the system.

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